

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS	Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 1 / 550

Technical Research Report

REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS

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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 2 / 550	

ADDITIONAL REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS

1	Introduction.....	14
1.1	Technical Report Structure	14
1.2	Acronyms and Abbreviations.....	15
2	Systematic Literature Review Process Overview.....	16
2.1	Step A: Definition of Keywords for Searches	16
2.2	Step B: Definition of Search Engines.....	19
2.3	Step C: SLR Search Language Results with Duplicate Removal.....	20
2.4	Step D: TAK Filter	20
2.5	Step E: Questionnaire for Full Text Review	21
2.6	Step F: Full Text Semantic Review	21
3	Remarks on SpringerLink Search Engine Applicability	23
4	Instantiation of the SLR Search Language on Search Engines	29
4.1	ACM	29
4.2	Engineering Village	30
4.3	Scopus.....	31
4.4	Web of Science	32
4.5	Wiley.....	33
5	SLR TAK Filter Results	34
6	Overview of the State of the Art of Categories C1, C2, C4, and C5.....	55
6.1	Category C1: AI Employed on Off-Line Safety Assurance.....	55
6.2	Category C2: AI Employed on Safety-Critical Functions	58
6.3	Category C4: Contextualization of AI on Industry 4.0 Applications	61
6.4	Category C5: AI Employed in Security-Critical Functions with Potential Impact on Safety	62
7	Additional Bibliometrics of Category C3 References	63
7.1	Relevance of the Safety Assurance of AI-Based Systems.....	63
7.2	Q-Index Overall Analysis.....	64
7.3	Cross-Analysis of Q-Index and Authors.....	66
7.4	Cross-Analysis of Q-Index and Periodic Publications	71
7.5	Cross-Analysis of Q-Index and Research Events / Proceedings.....	74
8	Category C3 References Full Text SLR Results Reports	78
8.1	Compilation of Data from Question Q1 Answers.....	78
8.2	Compilation of Data from Question Q2 Answers.....	85

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 3 / 550	

8.3	Reference [36]	94
8.4	Reference [46]	95
8.5	Reference [53]	97
8.6	Reference [54]	98
8.7	Reference [55]	99
8.8	Reference [56]	100
8.9	Reference [57]	101
8.10	Reference [58]	102
8.11	Reference [67]	104
8.12	Reference [70]	104
8.13	Reference [71]	106
8.14	Reference [73]	108
8.15	Reference [80]	109
8.16	Reference [81]	109
8.17	Reference [89]	111
8.18	Reference [92]	113
8.19	Reference [95]	114
8.20	Reference [98]	114
8.21	Reference [100]	115
8.22	Reference [101]	116
8.23	Reference [104]	117
8.24	Reference [107]	118
8.25	Reference [115]	118
8.26	Reference [116]	120
8.27	Reference [117]	120
8.28	Reference [119]	122
8.29	Reference [121]	123
8.30	Reference [131]	124
8.31	Reference [133]	126
8.32	Reference [134]	127
8.33	Reference [139]	129
8.34	Reference [143]	131
8.35	Reference [151]	131
8.36	Reference [154]	133
8.37	Reference [156]	135
8.38	Reference [160]	136

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 4 / 550	

8.39	Reference [161]	136
8.40	Reference [163]	138
8.41	Reference [165]	139
8.42	Reference [166]	140
8.43	Reference [167]	141
8.44	Reference [170]	142
8.45	Reference [175]	143
8.46	Reference [180]	145
8.47	Reference [181]	146
8.48	Reference [182]	146
8.49	Reference [185]	147
8.50	Reference [193]	149
8.51	Reference [195]	150
8.52	Reference [200]	152
8.53	Reference [201]	153
8.54	Reference [202]	154
8.55	Reference [207]	155
8.56	Reference [208]	156
8.57	Reference [209]	157
8.58	Reference [210]	158
8.59	Reference [212]	160
8.60	Reference [213]	161
8.61	Reference [214]	163
8.62	Reference [215]	163
8.63	Reference [218]	164
8.64	Reference [219]	166
8.65	Reference [222]	167
8.66	Reference [223]	169
8.67	Reference [227]	170
8.68	Reference [228]	171
8.69	Reference [231]	171
8.70	Reference [232]	172
8.71	Reference [233]	173
8.72	Reference [237]	174
8.73	Reference [239]	175
8.74	Reference [240]	176

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 5 / 550	

8.75	Reference [241]	177
8.76	Reference [242]	179
8.77	Reference [245]	180
8.78	Reference [247]	181
8.79	Reference [251]	182
8.80	Reference [252]	182
8.81	Reference [253]	183
8.82	Reference [254]	184
8.83	Reference [255]	185
8.84	Reference [256]	185
8.85	Reference [259]	186
8.86	Reference [262]	187
8.87	Reference [266]	188
8.88	Reference [267]	188
8.89	Reference [269]	189
8.90	Reference [275]	190
8.91	Reference [276]	191
8.92	Reference [283]	191
8.93	Reference [287]	192
8.94	Reference [289]	193
8.95	Reference [295]	194
8.96	Reference [297]	195
8.97	Reference [302]	197
8.98	Reference [306]	197
8.99	Reference [307]	198
8.100	Reference [318]	198
8.101	Reference [332]	199
8.102	Reference [340]	200
8.103	Reference [347]	202
8.104	Reference [354]	202
8.105	Reference [358]	203
8.106	Reference [373]	205
8.107	Reference [390]	206
8.108	Reference [394]	206
8.109	Reference [396]	207
8.110	Reference [398]	208

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 6 / 550	

8.111	Reference [399]	209
8.112	Reference [404]	210
8.113	Reference [419]	210
8.114	Reference [420]	212
8.115	Reference [433]	213
8.116	Reference [443]	213
8.117	Reference [445]	214
8.118	Reference [447]	217
8.119	Reference [453]	220
8.120	Reference [454]	221
8.121	Reference [455]	223
8.122	Reference [456]	224
8.123	Reference [465]	225
8.124	Reference [495]	225
8.125	Reference [496]	226
8.126	Reference [522]	226
8.127	Reference [526]	227
8.128	Reference [528]	228
8.129	Reference [532]	230
8.130	Reference [533]	230
8.131	Reference [534]	231
8.132	Reference [535]	231
8.133	Reference [537]	233
8.134	Reference [542]	233
8.135	Reference [544]	234
8.136	Reference [546]	235
8.137	Reference [547]	236
8.138	Reference [548]	237
8.139	Reference [549]	239
8.140	Reference [551]	240
8.141	Reference [553]	242
8.142	Reference [557]	243
8.143	Reference [563]	244
8.144	Reference [565]	246
8.145	Reference [566]	247
8.146	Reference [569]	248

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 7 / 550	

8.147	Reference [570]	249
8.148	Reference [574]	251
8.149	Reference [576]	252
8.150	Reference [577]	253
8.151	Reference [578]	254
8.152	Reference [579]	256
8.153	Reference [582]	256
8.154	Reference [586]	258
8.155	Reference [587]	259
8.156	Reference [588]	261
8.157	Reference [596]	263
8.158	Reference [600]	264
8.159	Reference [601]	267
8.160	Reference [602]	270
8.161	Reference [603]	271
8.162	Reference [604]	272
8.163	Reference [605]	273
8.164	Reference [610]	275
8.165	Reference [613]	276
8.166	Reference [614]	277
8.167	Reference [616]	277
8.168	Reference [617]	279
8.169	Reference [618]	279
8.170	Reference [619]	281
8.171	Reference [620]	282
8.172	Reference [621]	283
8.173	Reference [630]	284
8.174	Reference [632]	284
8.175	Reference [634]	284
8.176	Reference [637]	285
8.177	Reference [640]	286
8.178	Reference [642]	286
8.179	Reference [644]	287
8.180	Reference [650]	288
8.181	Reference [662]	289
8.182	Reference [663]	290

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 8 / 550	

8.183	Reference [664]	291
8.184	Reference [666]	292
8.185	Reference [667]	292
8.186	Reference [668]	293
8.187	Reference [669]	294
8.188	Reference [670]	294
8.189	Reference [671]	295
8.190	Reference [672]	296
8.191	Reference [673]	296
8.192	Reference [675]	297
8.193	Reference [676]	298
8.194	Reference [682]	300
8.195	Reference [684]	300
8.196	Reference [686]	301
8.197	Reference [687]	303
8.198	Reference [688]	304
8.199	Reference [689]	304
8.200	Reference [690]	305
8.201	Reference [691]	306
8.202	Reference [692]	307
8.203	Reference [693]	308
8.204	Reference [694]	310
8.205	Reference [695]	311
8.206	Reference [696]	312
8.207	Reference [697]	313
8.208	Reference [705]	313
8.209	Reference [706]	315
8.210	Reference [709]	316
8.211	Reference [712]	318
8.212	Reference [713]	318
8.213	Reference [714]	319
8.214	Reference [715]	319
8.215	Reference [716]	320
8.216	Reference [717]	320
8.217	Reference [718]	321
8.218	Reference [719]	322

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 9 / 550	

8.219	Reference [728]	324
8.220	Reference [739]	325
8.221	Reference [740]	325
8.222	Reference [741]	326
8.223	Reference [743]	327
8.224	Reference [744]	328
8.225	Reference [745]	330
8.226	Reference [748]	330
8.227	Reference [749]	331
8.228	Reference [750]	332
8.229	Reference [751]	333
8.230	Reference [752]	334
8.231	Reference [755]	335
8.232	Reference [757]	335
8.233	Reference [760]	336
8.234	Reference [761]	337
8.235	Reference [762]	338
8.236	Reference [763]	339
8.237	Reference [765]	340
8.238	Reference [766]	341
8.239	Reference [768]	342
8.240	Reference [769]	343
8.241	Reference [770]	344
8.242	Reference [771]	345
8.243	Reference [773]	346
8.244	Reference [777]	347
8.245	Reference [778]	347
8.246	Reference [779]	348
8.247	Reference [780]	349
8.248	Reference [781]	350
8.249	Reference [782]	351
8.250	Reference [783]	352
8.251	Reference [785]	352
8.252	Reference [786]	354
8.253	Reference [787]	356
8.254	Reference [788]	357

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 10 / 550	

8.255	Reference [789]	358
8.256	Reference [791]	359
8.257	Reference [796]	360
8.258	Reference [797]	362
8.259	Reference [798]	363
8.260	Reference [799]	364
8.261	Reference [802]	365
8.262	Reference [805]	366
8.263	Reference [806]	367
8.264	Reference [807]	367
8.265	Reference [813]	368
8.266	Reference [814]	369
8.267	Reference [819]	371
8.268	Reference [820]	371
8.269	Reference [823]	373
8.270	Reference [829]	374
8.271	Reference [830]	376
8.272	Reference [831]	377
8.273	Reference [832]	378
8.274	Reference [838]	379
8.275	Reference [839]	380
8.276	Reference [843]	381
8.277	Reference [844]	384
8.278	Reference [845]	385
8.279	Reference [846]	386
8.280	Reference [847]	387
8.281	Reference [849]	388
8.282	Reference [850]	389
8.283	Reference [859]	390
8.284	Reference [868]	391
8.285	Reference [870]	392
8.286	Reference [872]	393
8.287	Reference [873]	394
8.288	Reference [874]	395
8.289	Reference [875]	397
8.290	Reference [879]	398

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 11 / 550	

8.291	Reference [883]	399
8.292	Reference [884]	400
8.293	Reference [886]	401
8.294	Reference [887]	401
8.295	Reference [889]	402
8.296	Reference [895]	402
8.297	Reference [896]	404
8.298	Reference [898]	405
8.299	Reference [900]	406
8.300	Reference [905]	407
8.301	Reference [906]	409
8.302	Reference [920]	410
8.303	Reference [921]	411
8.304	Reference [922]	412
8.305	Reference [923]	413
8.306	Reference [925]	414
8.307	Reference [934]	415
8.308	Reference [935]	416
8.309	Reference [936]	418
8.310	Reference [937]	418
8.311	Reference [938]	419
8.312	Reference [939]	420
8.313	Reference [941]	421
8.314	Reference [942]	421
8.315	Reference [943]	422
8.316	Reference [944]	422
8.317	Reference [947]	423
8.318	Reference [949]	425
8.319	Reference [954]	426
8.320	Reference [955]	428
8.321	Reference [960]	429
8.322	Reference [962]	431
8.323	Reference [963]	433
8.324	Reference [968]	434
8.325	Reference [971]	435
8.326	Reference [972]	436

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 12 / 550	

8.327	Reference [973]	437
8.328	Reference [974]	438
8.329	Reference [976]	439
8.330	Reference [978]	440
8.331	Reference [980]	441
9	Bibliography	444

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 13 / 550	

VERSION CONTROL

Revision	Date	Description
1	August 27 th , 2021	First official release.
2	September 28 th , 2021	Section 7.4: Minor correction on the reference to ‘IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems’.
3	February 2 nd , 2022	Full update in order to include SLR results based on references collected on January 18 th , 2022.
4	May 10 th , 2022	Inclusion of Table 2 in section 5; inclusion of section 6.inclusion of sections 8.1 and 8.2.
5	October 10 th , 2022	Full update in order to include SLR results based on references collected on August 26 th , 2022.
6	November 24 th , 2022	Update of section 2.1 to include additional justification on how the SLR Search Language has been crafted. This text has been moved from the original manuscript of the paper ‘ <i>Safety Assurance of Artificial Intelligence-Based Systems: A Systematic Literature Review on the State of the Art and Guidelines for Future Work</i> ’ to this technical research report considering suggestions provided by the reviewers.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 14 / 550	

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this technical research report is to detail non-essential yet relevant results and analyses related to the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) which bases the DSc. Thesis '*Safety ArtISt: Um Método para a Garantia de Segurança Crítica de Sistemas com Inteligência Artificial*'. Details related to the SLR carried out up to August 26th, 2022 were also covered and/or discussed within the research paper '*Safety Assurance of Artificial Intelligence-Based Systems: A Systematic Literature Review on the State of the Art and Guidelines for Future Work*'.

These results, albeit not fundamental to justify the novelty and the main results reported within the research paper '*Safety Assurance of Artificial Intelligence-Based Systems: A Systematic Literature Review on the State of the Art and Guidelines for Future Work*', are worth coverage and analysis so as to provide a full insight of the SLR operationalization and its underlying results.

1.1 TECHNICAL REPORT STRUCTURE

The remainder of this technical research report has been structured in the following way:

- Section 2 provides an overview of the SLR process, reinforcing information already covered in the research paper '*Safety Assurance of Artificial Intelligence-Based Systems: A Systematic Literature Review on the State of the Art and Guidelines for Future Work*' for contextualization purposes;
- Section 3 expands on the technical justification which bases the decision on disregarding SpringerLink from the search engines considered within the SLR according to tests and analyses carried out on January 13th, 2021;
- Section 4 covers the instantiation of the SLR Search Language syntax on each of the search engines considered within the SLR;
- Section 5 provides the full list of papers obtained at the SLR Title-Abstract-Keywords (TAK) filter, as well as their resulting categorization, as per searches carried out up to August 26th, 2022;
- Section 6 presents an overview of the state of the art of research which, albeit relating artificial intelligence (AI) to safety, does not directly address the safety assurance of AI-based systems. These correspond to publications within categories C1, C2, C4, and C5;
- Section 7 covers additional bibliometrics analyses regarding the full text review of category

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 15 / 550

C3 texts, as per searches carried out on August 26th, 2022;

- Section 8 presents the SLR Results Report of the category C3 texts after their full review, as per searches carried out on August 26th, 2022;
- Finally, section 9 presents the full bibliographic references quoted within this technical report.

1.2 ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

The acronyms and abbreviations used in this technical research report are as follows.

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
C0	Category 0
C1	Category 1
C2	Category 2
C3	Category 3
C4	Category 4
C5	Category 5
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DL	Deep Learning
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRNN	Deep Recurrent Neural Network
DT	Decision Tree
EOF	End of File
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
ML	Machine Learning
OG	Objective Group
RF	Random Forest
RIS	Research Information Systems
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SL	Supervised Learning
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TAK	Title-Abstract-Keyword
UL	Unsupervised Learning

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 16 / 550	

2 SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW PROCESS OVERVIEW

We carried out a six-step SLR in order to collect information regarding the state of the art and gaps for future work on the safety assessment of AI-based safety-critical systems. The SLR steps are presented in the following sections and have been carried out in the same sequence herein reported.

2.1 STEP A: DEFINITION OF KEYWORDS FOR SEARCHES

The first step aims to provide the set of keywords that will be used in the SLR search engines to retrieve references which are potentially related to the safety assessment of AI-based safety-critical systems.

For this purpose, we have iteratively conceived a formal SLR Search Language written in Wirth's notation to define expressions that shall be satisfied by the references' TAKs, so that only references fully satisfying these conditions are effectively retrieved and considered in the next SLR steps. The expressions which are part of the SLR Search Language include not only terms which shall exist within the TAK information, but also terms whose existence on TAK information automatically exclude the related reference from the retrieved results.

The final version of the SLR Search Language considered in this version of the SLR is presented as follows. . Words in **bold** are terminal terms.

expression = area_of_interest and application not other_areas.

and = "**AND**".

not = "**NOT**".

area_of_interest = safety_area and means.

safety_area = safety_area_noun | safety_area_verb

safety_area_noun = ("**safety analys***" | "**safety assessment***" | "**safety verification***" | "**safety validation***" | "**safety evaluation***" | "**safety assurance***" | "**safety case***" | "**safety**" and ("**assessment case***" | "**assessment pattern***" | "**risk analys***" | "**risk assessment***" | "**risk evaluation***" | "**hazard analys***" | "**hazard assessment***" | "**hazard evaluation***")

analy* safety" | "**assess* safety**" | "**verif* safety**" | "**validat* safety**" | "**evaluat* safety**" | "**assur* safety**")

means = ("**method***" | "**methodolog***" | "**technique***" | "**approach**" | "**framework***").

application = intelligence | learning | expert | data_analysis | aut_adapt |

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 17 / 550	

"4.0".

intelligence = ("artificial" | "machine") and ("intelligence") | "AI" | "cognitive computing" | "computer cognition" | "intelligent computing".

learning = (("machine" | "transfer" | "deep" | "supervised" | "reinforcement" | "semi-supervised" | "unsupervised") and "learning") | "neural network*".

expert = ("expert" | "knowledge-based") and ("system*").

classification data_analysis = "data" and ("classification" | "mining" | "science" | "analytics" | "clustering" | "grouping").

aut_adapt = ("autonomy" | "autonomous system*" | "autonomous computing" | "automatic system*" | "automatic computing" | "adaptive system*" | "adaptive computing" | "adaptation" | "adaptiveness").

other_areas = ("credit*" | "asset*" | "insurance*" | "portfolio*" | "investment*" | "stock*" | "pregnan*" | "drug*" | "flood*" | "earthquake*" | "mine*" | "coal" | "ergonom*" | "construction site*" | "dam*" | "oil").

The SLR Search Language comprises expressions which satisfy three criteria: the presence of terms related to the safety assurance domain (represented by the identifier 'area_of_interest' and its derived low-level identifiers), the presence of terms related to AI (represented by the identifier 'application' and its derived low-level identifiers), and the absence of terms related to applications which are not related to the technical safety domain (represented by the negation of the identifier 'other_areas' and its derived low-level identifiers). All identifiers were iteratively crafted in preliminary phases of the SLR based on two aspects: (i.) the relevance of expressions for the scope of the research, and (ii.) the retrieval of a quantity of publications feasible for the objectives of this SLR whilst maximizing as much as possible relevant papers on the safety assurance of AI-based systems. Details on these identifiers are hereafter presented to justify the SLR Search Language.

The safety-related identifier 'area_of_interest' comprises two alternate lower level identifiers – namely, 'safety_area_noun' and 'safety_area_verb' – which shall be satisfied along with a third identifier named 'means'

The identifier 'safety_area_noun' includes a list of non-verbal expressions, on singular and plural forms whenever applicable, with relevant activities and/or products of the safety assurance process. The activities included within 'safety_area_noun' are 'safety analysis', 'safety assessment', 'safety assurance', 'safety verification', 'safety validation', 'safety evaluation', and its plural variants.

In addition to these expressions, 'risk analysis', 'risk assessment', 'risk evaluation', 'hazard analysis',

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 18 / 550	

‘hazard assessment’, ‘hazard evaluation’, and its plurals have also been considered. Two remarks related to risk and hazard- related expressions, stemming from the iterative development of the SLR Search Language, are worth highlighting:

- a) All of them explicitly require the word ‘safety’ to also exist on the searched texts. This precondition has been added because, when without it, a significant number of the retrieved results related to hazard and risk lacked proper contextualization to the safety assurance area. Most references dealt with exploring specific hazards and/or risks for application domains and were primarily related to environment and health concerns, which are outside the scope of this SLR;
- b) No expressions relating ‘hazard’ and ‘risk’ to the ‘assurance’, ‘verification’, and ‘validation’ activities were included in the final version of the SLR Search Language. During the development of the SLR Search Language, these expressions were thoroughly exercised on search engines and retrieved none to very few (< 5) results from any of them.

‘safety_area_noun’ also includes expressions related to the final products of a safety assurance process – namely, safety case and assurance case –, along with its respective plurals. Moreover, assurance patterns have also been included, given the increasing efforts of building reusable *de facto patterns* for assuring the safety of similar AI-based systems.

The identifier ‘safety_area_verb’, in turn, includes expressions similar in meaning to those of ‘safety_area_noun’, but instead based on verbal constructions. One point that is worth of highlight for ‘safety_area_verb’ is that all expressions considered within this SLR are of the form ‘verb (in any tense) + safety’, hence not including expressions in which other words are in between them (e.g., the expression ‘assuring the safety of’ is not herein considered). This decision was taken because considering more general verb-related expressions with words between the corresponding verbs and ‘safety’ would represent at least a fourfold increase on the quantity of publications to be reviewed (>20k). In addition to the significant efforts in reviewing such a big quantity of publications, the analysis of a sample of some of these additional publications, classified as ‘most relevant’ as per the search engines, allowed identifying no clear potential of increasing the awareness on the safety assurance of AI-based systems, thus leading to their exclusion.

Finally, the identifier ‘means’ presents a list of expressions that are related to systematizing a systems safety lifecycle. It includes the words method, methodology, technique, approach, framework, and their corresponding plurals.

The identifier ‘application’ is composed of five lower level identifiers – namely,

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 19 / 550	

‘intelligence’, ‘learning’, ‘expert’, ‘data_analysis’, and ‘aut_adapt’. It also includes the terminal term ‘4.0’, aimed to retrieve results referring to Industry 4.0 as a whole.

Each of the identifiers that are part of ‘application’ covers a specific set of expressions related to AI. The identifier ‘intelligence’ includes expressions employed to make generic reference to AI. The identifier ‘learning’ includes expressions specifically related to machine learning (ML) and its variants. Furthermore, given the significant emphasis on neural networks – which consist on one type of ML model –, specific terms related to them have also been added to ‘learning’.

The identifier ‘expert’ comprises singular and plural expressions related to knowledge-based systems, also formerly known as expert systems. The identifier ‘data_analysis’ reunites expressions related to data science métier, which has a close relationship to AI. Finally, the identifier ‘aut_adapt’ includes a series of expressions related to autonomy, automatism, and adaptiveness, which have been significantly leveraged by the popularization of AI.

The objective of the identifier ‘other_areas’ is to automate the exclusion of texts which, despite satisfying the search criteria of the identifiers ‘area_of_interest’ and ‘application’, have been manually identified as unrelated to the safety assurance of AI-based systems at the initial stages of the SLR. The expressions that were included within ‘other_areas’ comprise themes such as pharmaceutical research, stock market analyses, and environment, health and safety (EHS).

The identifier ‘other_areas’ has been iteratively built throughout this SLR as a non-exhaustive set of expressions which represent the main themes and keywords of the aforementioned references unrelated to the safety assurance of AI-based systems. If these expressions were not deemed for exclusion, >10k potentially unrelated texts would still be retrieved for manual appreciation, making this SLR unfeasible in due time for a negligible impact on characterizing the area of interest. The terms which were included within the ‘other_areas’ identifier allowed a sharp reduction of falsely relevant texts whilst retaining results that are important for the research.

2.2 STEP B: DEFINITION OF SEARCH ENGINES

The search engines considered for this SLR are the same ones employed in [1] with the exception of SpringerLink, which was excluded based on the analysis presented in section 3, and ScienceDirect, which fully overlaps Scopus for TAK information as per [2]. This means that this SLR has been carried out considering ACM, Engineering Village, Scopus, Web of Science, and Wiley as sources for potential publications.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 20 / 550	

2.3 STEP C: SLR SEARCH LANGUAGE RESULTS WITH DUPLICATE REMOVAL

The SLR Search Language presented in Step A (section 2.1) has been instantiated on each search engine defined in Step B (section 2.2) so as to extract potentially relevant references for the purpose of this SLR. Afterwards, the results have been filtered so that duplicate entries of a same reference can be ruled out and, hence, accounted for just once at the end on this step.

The instantiation of the SLR Search Language within each search engine has been performed in accordance to the built-in search syntax of the respective search engine. The details regarding the specificities of the SLR Search Language instantiation for each search engine are covered in section 4.

The retrieval of results from each search engine has been performed by exporting the obtained results (including their TAK information) in BibTeX format and loading them onto Mendeley and JabRef softwares for duplicate processing and reference management throughout the research lifecycle. The BibTeX format has only been replaced by the Research Information Systems (RIS) format for Scopus results after Scopus-exported BibTeX files led to improper parsing due to unexpected End of File (EOF) within the string data.

The duplicate removal process has been carried out in a semiautomatic way by using duplicate removal tools within Mendeley and JabRef softwares and manually confirming or negating the merging of each group of potential duplicates.

2.4 STEP D: TAK FILTER

The TAK filter comprises a manual semantic analysis of the TAK information of all results obtained at the end of Step C (section 2.3) in order to evaluate the potential of each reference in contributing with the results within the scope of the SLR. This evaluation has been performed by classifying each of the evaluated references in six categories (C0 to C5), which were defined based on the SLR scope and attributed to each reference according to their TAK information. The categories C0 to C5 are as follows:

- **C0:** Not relevant to the research;
- **C1:** Research on AI applied in off-line safety assurance;
- **C2:** Research on AI applied in safety-critical functions, but without evidence of safety assessment per se;
- **C3:** Research on the safety assurance of AI-based safety-critical functions;

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 21 / 550	

- **C4:** Contextualization of AI on Industry 4.0 applications;
- **C5:** Research on AI employed in security-critical functions with potential impact on safety.

Since the categories C1-C5 are not mutually exclusive, any reference can be attributed to more than one of these categories based on the TAK information. Moreover, if the TAK information is not sufficiently precise so as to rule out any of the categories C1-C5, a reference may be conservatively inserted within any of these categories at the TAK filter step, so as to allow further analyses on the next SLR steps. The latter condition is most notably applicable to C3, which is directly related to the objective of this research.

2.5 STEP E: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR FULL TEXT REVIEW

In order to guide the extraction of relevant information when assessing the full text of the references considered relevant at the TAK filter step, a questionnaire comprising six questions related to the scope of this SLR has been created. The questions are as follows:

- **Q1:** What is the objective of the research?
- **Q2:** Which AI techniques were considered in the research?
- **Q3:** How has the safety assurance of AI been considered within the study?
- **Q4:** Which results were obtained on the research (including potential shortcomings)?
- **Q5:** Which future research topics were identified by the authors?
- **Q6:** What other strengths and weaknesses were identified in the study during its review?

Questions Q1-Q4 were created so as to extract information related to the state of the art of the AI-based systems safety assessment, whereas questions Q5 and Q6 allow obtaining information regarding current research gaps and opportunities for future work. It is worth highlighting that question Q6 includes our own critical review of all references, thus allowing us to cross-fertilize our assessment with information obtained not only from other reviewed references, but also with our own experience.

2.6 STEP F: FULL TEXT SEMANTIC REVIEW

The full text semantic review aims to evaluate the relevant references extracted on the TAK filter (section 2.4) based on answers to the questionnaire defined in Step E (section 2.5). In addition to these answers, a quality index herein called Q-Index has also been defined with the objective of assessing

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 22 / 550	

how applicable each reference is to the purpose of this SLR. At the end, a full text report including the answers to questions Q1-Q6 and the Q-Index is generated for each reference so as to allow the extraction of the SLR overall conclusions.

The Q-Index is defined as an integer number within the interval [0; 6] and defined as follows:

- **Q = 0:** Reference practically not relevant to the SLR purpose;
- **Q = 1:** Reference weakly relevant to the SLR purpose;
- **Q = 2:** Reference fairly relevant to the SLR purpose;
- **Q = 3:** Reference sufficiently relevant to the SLR purpose;
- **Q = 4:** Reference with above average relevance to the SLR purpose;
- **Q = 5:** Reference with very good relevance to the SLR purpose;
- **Q = 6:** Reference with strong relevance to the SLR purpose.

In addition to the previous classification, a fuzzy criterion has also been conceived for the Q-Index in order to improve the interpretation of final results. The fuzzy categories for the Q-Index were defined as follows:

- **Low Quality References:** Q = 0 and Q = 1;
- **Average Quality References:** Q = 2 and Q = 3;
- **High Quality References:** Q = 4, Q = 5 and Q = 6.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 23 / 550	

3 REMARKS ON SPRINGERLINK SEARCH ENGINE APPLICABILITY

The objective of this section is to present a technical analysis which justifies that the non-applicability of SpringerLink to the SLR has at most marginal impact over its coverage completeness. Two main arguments are presented: (i.) the references retrieved by SpringerLink are covered by other search engines (notably Engineering Village, Scopus, and Web of Science), and (ii.) the SpringerLink search engine has issues in dealing with the SLR Search Language which would ultimately lead to a significant number of potentially irrelevant results, hence compromising the time-effectiveness of the SLR.

Both arguments are based on evidence collected on January 13th, 2021 that the SpringerLink search works unreliably with the SLR Search Language. The following reasoning has been applied to collect and analyze the SpringerLink search engine inefficacy:

Step 1: Two searches were performed with the SLR Search Language: one of them considering the final and most restrictive version of the ‘other_areas’ identifier, and another one with the more permissive version of the ‘other_areas’ identifier, referred to as the ‘Deprecated Version’ at the final part of 2.1. After performing both searches, it has been noticed that the most restrictive one retrieved a higher number of results than the most permissive variant – thus, contrary to what would be expected.

These results are depicted in Figure 1 (‘Deprecated Version’ of more permissive ‘other_areas’ identifier – 606 retrieved results) and Figure 2 (final and most restrictive ‘other_areas’ identifier – 1141 results), respectively.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 24 / 550	

SpringerLink

Sign up / Log in English Academic edition

Search: ("safety analysis" OR "safety assessment" OR "safety verification" OR "safety validation" OR "safety evaluation" OR "safety assurance" OR "risk analysis")

Home • Books A - Z • Journals A - Z • Videos • Librarians

606 Result(s) for ("safety analysis" OR "safety assessment" OR "safety verification" OR "safety validation" OR "safety evaluation" OR "safety assurance" OR "risk analysis")

Page 1 of 31

Sort By: Relevance, Newest First, Oldest First, Date Published

Include Preview-Only content

Refine Your Search

Content Type

Article	343
Chapler	247
Conference Paper	20
Reference Work Entry	16

Discipline see all

Medicine & Public Health	256
Engineering	93
Computer Science	89
Physics	26
Business and Management	23

Subdiscipline see all

Imaging / Radiology	92
Internal Medicine	71
Artificial Intelligence	62
Intensive / Critical Care Medicine	45
Ultrasound	42

Language

English	597
German	9

Article **ECR 2019: Book of Abstracts** [Open Access](#)
Insights into Imaging (2019)
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Article **ECR 2018 - BOOK OF ABSTRACTS** [Open Access](#)
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Article **Annual Congress of the European Association of Nuclear Medicine**
 October 12 – 16, 2019 Barcelona, Spain
European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging (2019)
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SPRINGER NATURE

Figure 1: SpringerLink Results with the SLR Search Language including the Deprecated and Permissive Version of 'other_areas' Identifier

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 25 / 550	

SpringerLink search results for the query: ("safety analysis" OR "safety assessment" OR "safety verification" OR "safety validation" OR "safety evaluation" OR "safety assurance" OR ("safety" AND "other_areas")).

1,141 Result(s) for '("safety analysis" OR "safety assessment" OR "safety verification" OR "safety validation" OR "safety evaluation" OR "safety assurance" OR ("safety" AND "other_areas"))'

Refine Your Search

Content Type

Chapter	629
Article	484
Conference Paper	123
Reference Work Entry	28

Discipline

Computer Science	287
Medicine & Public Health	284
Engineering	263
Business and Management	73
Physics	33

Subdiscipline

Artificial Intelligence	229
Imaging / Radiology	100
Computer Communication Networks	89
Computational Intelligence	86
Information Systems Applications (incl. Internet)	78

Language

English	1,130
German	11

Sort By: Relevance, Newest First, Oldest First, Date Published

Article
ECR 2019: Book of Abstracts
Insights into Imaging (2019)
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Insights into Imaging (2018)
[Download PDF](#) (11726 KB) [Open Access](#)

Article
Annual Congress of the European Association of Nuclear Medicine
 October 12 – 16, 2019 Barcelona, Spain
European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging (2019)

Figure 2: SpringerLink Results with the SLR Search Language including the Final and Restrictive Version of 'other_areas' Identifier

In both cases, after clicking any option on the screen (e.g. move to next page, filter by category or area), an error message is presented showing that there are issues with the HTTPS request header (see further details on Step 2 as follows). This message is shown in Figure 3.

Bad Message 431

reason: Request Header Fields Too Large

Figure 3: Error Message with Overly Long Search Expressions

Step 2: One of the possible causes for the Figure 3 HTTPS error message stems from the fact that the search expressions used in both search attempts is too big to fit an HTTPS GET request (used at SpringerLink searches), exceeding the 2048 character capacity for this standard. As a result, smaller

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 26 / 550	

expressions derived from applying distributive and DeMorgan properties to the SLR Search Language could be an alternative for searches on SpringerLink.

An attempt has been tried with the following expression, which includes (i.) a subset of the SLR Search Language expressions derived from the ‘area_of_interest’ identifier, (ii.) a single expression of the SLR Search Language of the ‘application’ identifier and (iii.) the equivalent DeMorgan expression of the final, restrictive ‘other_areas’ identifier.

```
"safety analysis" AND ("method" OR "methodology" OR "technique" OR
"approach" OR "framework") AND "artificial intelligence" AND NOT "credit"
AND NOT "asset" AND NOT "insurance" AND NOT "portfolio" AND NOT
"investment" AND NOT "stock" AND NOT "disease" AND NOT "disorder" AND NOT
"medical" AND NOT "syndrome" AND NOT "care" AND NOT "health" AND NOT
"pregnant" AND NOT "drug" AND NOT "cardiac" AND NOT "flood" AND NOT
"earthquake"
```

The resulting HTTPS GET command link, reproduced as follows, has 849 characters according to Microsoft Word 2010 character count – hence, less than its 2048 limit. Issues after clicking any option on the screen (e.g. move to next page, filter by category or area) no longer exist – thus supporting the justification that the Figure 3 error message results from overflow of the HTTPS GET command related to the search.

HTTPS GET command link:

```
https://link.springer.com/search?query=%E2%80%9Csafety+analysis%E2%80%9D+AND+%28%E2%80%9Cmethod%E2%80%9D+OR+%E2%80%9Cmethodology%E2%80%9D+OR+%E2%80%9Ctechnique%E2%80%9D+OR+%E2%80%9Capproach%E2%80%9D+OR+%E2%80%9Cframework%E2%80%9D%29+AND+%E2%80%9Cartificial+intelligence%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%22credit%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Casset%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cinsurance%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cportfolio%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cinvestment%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cstock%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cdisease%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cdisorder%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cmedical%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Csyndrome%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Ccare%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Chealth%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cpregnant%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cdrug%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Ccardiac%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cflood%E2%80%9D+AND+NOT+%E2%80%9Cearthquake%E2%80%9D
```

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 27 / 550	

Nevertheless, the retrieved results (38529) according to Figure 4 screen print) are still misleading and potentially incorrect. The justification for this is related to the fact that the search expression used in Figure 4 test is even more restrictive than the one employed in Step 1's Figure 2 test, since the test related to Figure 4 disregards all safety-related keywords from the SLR Search Language 'area_of_interest' identifier OR-combined with "safety analysis" and all AI-related keywords from the SLR Search Language 'application' identifier OR-combined with "artificial intelligence" without reducing the scope of the 'other_areas' identifier, which was just rewritten applying the DeMorgan property "*NOT (X1 OR ... OR Xk)*" as "*NOT X1 AND NOT ... AND NOT Xk*". Based on this analysis, it would be expected that the search depicted in Figure 4 should have retrieved less results than those of Step 1's Figure 2 test. The actual result, however, opposes to this premise, since a significantly higher number of references (38529 versus 1141) has been obtained as per Figure 4.

The screenshot displays the SpringerLink search interface. At the top, the search bar contains the query: "safety analysis" AND ("method" OR "methodology" OR "technique" OR "approach" OR "framework") AND "artificial intelligence" AND NOT. Below the search bar, the results section shows 38,529 results. The left sidebar provides filters for Content Type, Discipline, Subdiscipline, and Language. The main content area lists several articles, including "ECR 2019: Book of Abstracts", "ECR 2018 - BOOK OF ABSTRACTS", "Annual Congress of the European Association of Nuclear Medicine", and "Abstracts from the 2020 Annual Meeting of the Society of General Internal Medicine". A "nature careers" banner is visible on the right side of the page.

Figure 4: SpringerLink Results with Overly Restrictive Subset of the SLR Search Language

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 28 / 550	

Conclusion: Based on the previous evidence, the SpringerLink search engine has been deemed unreliable for this SLR. Moreover, further analyses of the results retrieved in some sample searches allowed identifying that the same results could be obtained by means of three referential search engines already considered within this SLR – namely, Engineering Village, Scopus and Web of Science – for both periodic (e.g. journals) and non-periodic (e.g. conference proceedings and book chapters) sources.

From a conservative point of view, the former results led us to consider that the omission of SpringerLink from the final list of the SLR search engines would at most have a marginal effect on its coverage, most likely with older (earlier than 1990) and non-periodic references which may lack DOI indexation on the referential search engines Engineering Village, Scopus and Web of Science. This marginal impact can be considered of low risk for the completeness and the soundness of our research based on its emergence especially during the 2010s (see further details on sections 7 and 8) and comes at the profit of a more time-effective effort on the SLR, since we can still work with SpringerLink-sourced references (retrieved from Engineering Village, Scopus and Web of Science) without the overhead of excessive potentially irrelevant research stemming from the unreliable search engine of SpringerLink.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 29 / 550	

4 INSTANTIATION OF THE SLR SEARCH LANGUAGE ON SEARCH ENGINES

Given that each search engine has its own syntax and search options, the objective of this section is to present how the SLR Search Language has been instantiated into each of the search engines and detail occasional search engine options which were also set to ensure that searches have been performed taking into account full TAK information within their respective full database.

4.1 ACM

Source: <https://dl.acm.org/search/advanced>

Search Expression: ("safety analys*" OR "safety assessment*" OR "safety verification*" OR "safety validation*" OR "safety evaluation*" OR "safety assurance*" OR "safety case*" OR ("safety" AND ("assurance case*" OR "assurance pattern*" OR "risk analys*" OR "risk assessment*" "risk evaluation*" OR "hazard analys*" OR "hazard assessment*" "hazard evaluation*"))) OR ("analy* safety" OR "assess* safety" OR "verif* safety" OR "validat* safety" OR "evaluat* safety" OR "assur* safety")) AND ("method*" OR "methodolog*" OR "technique*" OR "approach" OR "approaches" OR "framework*") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "machine intelligence" OR "AI" OR "cognitive computing" OR "computer cognition" OR "intelligent computing" OR "neural network*" OR "machine learning" OR "transfer learning" OR "deep learning" OR "supervised learning" OR "reinforcement learning" OR "unsupervised learning" OR "semi-supervised learning" OR "expert system*" OR "knowledge-based system*" OR "data classification" OR "data mining" OR "data science" OR "data analytics" OR "data clustering" OR "data grouping" OR "autonomy" OR "autonomous system*" OR "autonomous computing" OR "automatic system*" OR "automatic computing" OR "adaptive system*" OR "adaptive computing" OR "adaptation" OR "adaptiveness" OR "4.0") AND NOT "credit*" AND NOT "asset*" AND NOT "insurance*" AND NOT "portfolio*" AND NOT "investment*" AND NOT "stock*" AND NOT "pregnan*" AND NOT "drug*" AND NOT "flood*" AND NOT "earthquake*" AND NOT "coal" AND NOT "ergonom*" AND NOT "construction site*" AND NOT "dam*" AND NOT "oil"

Additional Remarks: Three searches were separately performed for each of the fields "Title", "Abstract", and "Author Keyword" within the "ACM Guide to Computing Literature". The three fields were considered in separate searches since the ACM search engine would automatically

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 30 / 550	

consider an “AND” relationship for all three aforementioned fields instead of the desired “OR” relationship. Moreover, the DeMorgan law has been applied to the “other_areas” search words because the ACM search engine had issues to process them in their original structure.

When performing the ‘advanced search’ on ACM, it is highly advised to press the ‘Clear’ button before a new query in order to ensure that the ACM search engine is fully reset.

4.2 ENGINEERING VILLAGE

Source: <https://www.engineeringvillage.com/search/quick.url>

Search Expression: (“safety analys*” OR “safety assessment*” OR “safety verification*” OR “safety validation*” OR “safety evaluation*” OR “safety assurance*” OR “safety case*” OR (“safety” AND (“assurance case*” OR “assurance pattern*” OR “risk analys*” OR “risk assessment*” “risk evaluation*” OR “hazard analys*” OR “hazard assessment*” “hazard evaluation*”))) OR (“analy* safety” OR “assess* safety” OR “verif* safety” OR “validat* safety” OR “evaluat* safety” OR “assur* safety”)) AND (“method*” OR “methodolog*” OR “technique*” OR “approach” OR “approaches” OR “framework*”) AND (“artificial intelligence” OR “machine intelligence” OR “AI” OR “cognitive computing” OR “computer cognition” OR “intelligent computing” OR “neural network*” OR “machine learning” OR “transfer learning” OR “deep learning” OR “supervised learning” OR “reinforcement learning” OR “unsupervised learning” OR “semi-supervised learning” OR “expert system*” OR “knowledge-based system*” OR “data classification” OR “data mining” OR “data science” OR “data analytics” OR “data clustering” OR “data grouping” OR “autonomy” OR “autonomous system*” OR “autonomous computing” OR “automatic system*” OR “automatic computing” OR “adaptive system*” OR “adaptive computing” OR “adaptation” OR “adaptiveness” OR “4.0”) NOT “credit*” NOT “asset*” NOT “insurance*” NOT “portfolio*” NOT “investment*” NOT “stock*” NOT “pregnan*” NOT “drug*” NOT “flood*” NOT “earthquake*” NOT “coal” NOT “ergonom*” NOT “construction site*” NOT “dam*” NOT “oil”

Additional Remarks: Search performed comprising an “OR” relationship of each of the fields “Title”, “Abstract”, and “Keyword” by using the standard search object “Subject / Title / Abstract”. Moreover, the DeMorgan law has been applied to the “other_areas” search words because the Engineering Village negation operator ‘NOT’ is directly translated into “AND NOT”.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 31 / 550	

4.3 SCOPUS

Source: <https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri?display=advanced>

Search Expression: TITLE-ABS-KEY(((("safety analys*" OR "safety assessment*" OR "safety verification*" OR "safety validation*" OR "safety evaluation*" OR "safety assurance*" OR "safety case*" OR ("safety" AND ("assurance case*" OR "assurance pattern*" OR "risk analys*" OR "risk assessment*" "risk evaluation*" OR "hazard analys*" OR "hazard assessment*" "hazard evaluation*")))) OR ("analy* safety" OR "assess* safety" OR "verif* safety" OR "validat* safety" OR "evaluat* safety" OR "assur* safety")) AND ("method*" OR "methodolog*" OR "technique*" OR "approach" OR "approaches" OR "framework*") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "machine intelligence" OR "AI" OR "cognitive computing" OR "computer cognition" OR "intelligent computing" OR "neural network*" OR "machine learning" OR "transfer learning" OR "deep learning" OR "supervised learning" OR "reinforcement learning" OR "unsupervised learning" OR "semi-supervised learning" OR "expert system*" OR "knowledge-based system*" OR "data classification" OR "data mining" OR "data science" OR "data analytics" OR "data clustering" OR "data grouping" OR "autonomy" OR "autonomous system*" OR "autonomous computing" OR "automatic system*" OR "automatic computing" OR "adaptive system*" OR "adaptive computing" OR "adaptation" OR "adaptiveness" OR "4.0") AND NOT "credit*" AND NOT "asset*" AND NOT "insurance*" AND NOT "portfolio*" AND NOT "investment*" AND NOT "stock*" AND NOT "pregnan*" AND NOT "drug*" AND NOT "flood*" AND NOT "earthquake*" AND NOT "coal" AND NOT "ergonom*" AND NOT "construction site*" AND NOT "dam*" AND NOT "oil")

Additional Remarks: Search performed comprising an “OR” relationship of each of the fields “Title”, “Abstract”, and “Keyword” by using the “TITLE-ABS-KEY” function provided at the Scopus Advanced Search Engine. Moreover, the DeMorgan law has been applied to the “other_areas” search words.

As already mentioned on section 2.3, the results were exported in RIS format for Scopus results after Scopus-exported BibTeX files led to improper parsing due to unexpected End of File (EOF) within the string data, as signaled by the JabRef and Mendeley parsers.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 32 / 550	

4.4 WEB OF SCIENCE

Source:

https://apps.webofknowledge.com/UA_GeneralSearch_input.do?product=UA&SID=8B5vSxsdDhCP AOPFMUw&search_mode=GeneralSearch

Search Expression: (("safety analys*" OR "safety assessment*" OR "safety verification*" OR "safety validation*" OR "safety evaluation*" OR "safety assurance*" OR "safety case*" OR ("safety" AND ("assurance case*" OR "assurance pattern*" OR "risk analys*" OR "risk assessment*" "risk evaluation*" OR "hazard analys*" OR "hazard assessment*" "hazard evaluation*"))) OR ("analy* safety" OR "assess* safety" OR "verif* safety" OR "validat* safety" OR "evaluat* safety" OR "assur* safety")) AND ("method*" OR "methodolog*" OR "technique*" OR "approach" OR "approaches" OR "framework*") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "machine intelligence" OR "AI" OR "cognitive computing" OR "computer cognition" OR "intelligent computing" OR "neural network*" OR "machine learning" OR "transfer learning" OR "deep learning" OR "supervised learning" OR "reinforcement learning" OR "unsupervised learning" OR "semi-supervised learning" OR "expert system*" OR "knowledge-based system*" OR "data classification" OR "data mining" OR "data science" OR "data analytics" OR "data clustering" OR "data grouping" OR "autonomy" OR "autonomous system*" OR "autonomous computing" OR "automatic system*" OR "automatic computing" OR "adaptive system*" OR "adaptive computing" OR "adaptation" OR "adaptiveness" OR "4.0") NOT "credit*" NOT "asset*" NOT "insurance*" NOT "portfolio*" NOT "investment*" NOT "stock*" NOT "pregnan*" NOT "drug*" NOT "flood*" NOT "earthquake*" NOT "coal" NOT "ergonom*" NOT "construction site*" NOT "dam*" NOT "oil"

Additional Remarks: Search performed at the entire Web of Science database (option “*Todas as Bases de Dados*”) within the field “*Tópico*”, which includes Title, Abstract and Keywords according to the Web of Science search engine: “*Pesquisa o título, resumo, as palavras-chave do autor e muito mais.*”. Moreover, the DeMorgan law has been applied to the “*other_areas*” search words because the Web of Science search engine negation operator ‘NOT’ is automatically interpreted as “AND NOT”.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 33 / 550	

4.5 WILEY

Source: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/search/advanced>

Search Expression: (("safety analys*" OR "safety assessment*" OR "safety verification*" OR "safety validation*" OR "safety evaluation*" OR "safety assurance*" OR "safety case*" OR ("safety" AND ("assurance case*" OR "assurance pattern*" OR "risk analys*" OR "risk assessment*" "risk evaluation*" OR "hazard analys*" OR "hazard assessment*" "hazard evaluation*")))) OR ("analy* safety" OR "assess* safety" OR "verif* safety" OR "validat* safety" OR "evaluat* safety" OR "assur* safety")) AND ("method*" OR "methodolog*" OR "technique*" OR "approach" OR "approaches" OR "framework*") AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "machine intelligence" OR "AI" OR "cognitive computing" OR "computer cognition" OR "intelligent computing" OR "neural network*" OR "machine learning" OR "transfer learning" OR "deep learning" OR "supervised learning" OR "reinforcement learning" OR "unsupervised learning" OR "semi-supervised learning" OR "expert system*" OR "knowledge-based system*" OR "data classification" OR "data mining" OR "data science" OR "data analytics" OR "data clustering" OR "data grouping" OR "autonomy" OR "autonomous system*" OR "autonomous computing" OR "automatic system*" OR "automatic computing" OR "adaptive system*" OR "adaptive computing" OR "adaptation" OR "adaptiveness" OR "4.0") AND NOT "credit*" AND NOT "asset*" AND NOT "insurance*" AND NOT "portfolio*" AND NOT "investment*" AND NOT "stock*" AND NOT "pregnan*" AND NOT "drug*" AND NOT "flood*" AND NOT "earthquake*" AND NOT "coal" AND NOT "ergonom*" AND NOT "construction site*" AND NOT "dam*" AND NOT "oil"

Additional Remarks: Search performed separately for each of the fields "Title", "Abstract", and "Author Keyword". The three fields were considered in separate searches since the Wiley search engine would automatically consider an "AND" relationship for all three aforementioned fields instead of the desired "OR" relationship. Moreover, the DeMorgan law has been applied to the "other_areas" search words.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 34 / 550	

5 SLR TAK FILTER RESULTS

The SLR TAK filter allowed identifying that, among the 5090 results retrieved from search engines up to August 26th, 2022, 4112 of them (80.8%) were classified within C0 due to their lack of relevance to the purpose of this research. The remaining 978 references (19.2%) were attributed to at least one of the C1-C5 categories as per Table 1 based on the semantic analysis of their TAK information. The results presented in Table 1 allow concluding that there are 414 references on C1, 487 references on C2, 329 references on C3, 32 references on C4 and 29 references on C5.

Table 1: List of C1-C5 References Obtained with the TAK Filter with Search Engine Results from August 26th, 2022

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[3]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[4]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[5]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[6]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[7]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[8]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[9]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[10]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[11]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[12]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[13]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[14]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[15]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[16]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[17]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[18]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[19]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[20]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[21]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[22]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[23]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[24]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[25]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[26]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[27]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[28]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[29]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[30]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[31]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[32]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[33]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[34]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[35]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[36]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[37]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 35 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[38]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[39]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[40]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[41]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[42]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[43]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[44]	YES	NO	NO	NO	YES
[45]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[46]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[47]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[48]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[49]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[50]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[51]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[52]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[53]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[54]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[55]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[56]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[57]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[58]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[59]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[60]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[61]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[62]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[63]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[64]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[65]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[66]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[67]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[68]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[69]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[70]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[71]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[72]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[73]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[74]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[75]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[76]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[77]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[78]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[79]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[80]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[81]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[82]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[83]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[84]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[85]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[86]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[87]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 36 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[88]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[89]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[90]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[91]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[92]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[93]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[94]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[95]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[96]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[97]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[98]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[99]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[100]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[101]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[102]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[103]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[104]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[105]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[106]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[107]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[108]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[109]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[110]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[111]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[112]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[113]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[114]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[115]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[116]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[117]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[118]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[119]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[120]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[121]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[122]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[123]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[124]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[125]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[126]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[127]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[128]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[129]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[130]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[131]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[132]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[133]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[134]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[135]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[136]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[137]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 37 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[138]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[139]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[140]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[141]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[142]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[143]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[144]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[145]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[146]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[147]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[148]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[149]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[150]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[151]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[152]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[153]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[154]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[155]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[156]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[157]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[158]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[159]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[160]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[161]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[162]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[163]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[164]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[165]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[166]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[167]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[168]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[169]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[170]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[171]	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES
[172]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[173]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[174]	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO
[175]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[176]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[177]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[178]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[179]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[180]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[181]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[182]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[183]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[184]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[185]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[186]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[187]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 38 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[188]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[189]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[190]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[191]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[192]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[193]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[194]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[195]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[196]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[197]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[198]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[199]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[200]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[201]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[202]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[203]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[204]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[205]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[206]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[207]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[208]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[209]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[210]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[211]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[212]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[213]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[214]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[215]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[216]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[217]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[218]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[219]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[220]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[221]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[222]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[223]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[224]	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES
[225]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[226]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[227]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[228]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[229]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[230]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[231]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[232]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[233]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[234]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[235]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[236]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[237]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 39 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[238]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[239]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[240]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[241]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[242]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[243]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[244]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[245]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[246]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[247]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[248]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[249]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[250]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[251]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[252]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[253]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[254]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[255]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[256]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[257]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[258]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[259]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[260]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[261]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[262]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[263]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[264]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[265]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[266]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[267]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[268]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[269]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[270]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[271]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[272]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[273]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[274]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[275]	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO
[276]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[277]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[278]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[279]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[280]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[281]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[282]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[283]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[284]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[285]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[286]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[287]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 40 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[288]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[289]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[290]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[291]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[292]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[293]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[294]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[295]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[296]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[297]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[298]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[299]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[300]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[301]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[302]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[303]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[304]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[305]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[306]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[307]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[308]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[309]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[310]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[311]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[312]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[313]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[314]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[315]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[316]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[317]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[318]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[319]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[320]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[321]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[322]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[323]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[324]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[325]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[326]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[327]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[328]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[329]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[330]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[331]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[332]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[333]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[334]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[335]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[336]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[337]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 41 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[338]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[339]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[340]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[341]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[342]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[343]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[344]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[345]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[346]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[347]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[348]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[349]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[350]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[351]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[352]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[353]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[354]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[355]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[356]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[357]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[358]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[359]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[360]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[361]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[362]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[363]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[364]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[365]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[366]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[367]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[368]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[369]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[370]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[371]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[372]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[373]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[374]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[375]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[376]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[377]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[378]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[379]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[380]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[381]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[382]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[383]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[384]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[385]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[386]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[387]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 42 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[388]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[389]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[390]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[391]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[392]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[393]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[394]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[395]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[396]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[397]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[398]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[399]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[400]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[401]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[402]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[403]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
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[405]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[406]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[407]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[408]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[409]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[410]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[411]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[412]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[413]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[414]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[415]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[416]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[417]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[418]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[419]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[420]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[421]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[422]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[423]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[424]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[425]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[426]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[427]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[428]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[429]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[430]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[431]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[432]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[433]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[434]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[435]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[436]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[437]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 43 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[438]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[439]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[440]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[441]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[442]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[443]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[444]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[445]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[446]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[447]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[448]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[449]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[450]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[451]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[452]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[453]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[454]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[455]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[456]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[457]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[458]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[459]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[460]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[461]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[462]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[463]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[464]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[465]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[466]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[467]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[468]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[469]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[470]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[471]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[472]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[473]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[474]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[475]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[476]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[477]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[478]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[479]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[480]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[481]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[482]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[483]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[484]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[485]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[486]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[487]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 44 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[488]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[489]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[490]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[491]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[492]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[493]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[494]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[495]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[496]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[497]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[498]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[499]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[500]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[501]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[502]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[503]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
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[505]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[506]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[507]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[508]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[509]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[510]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[511]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[512]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[513]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[514]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[515]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[516]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[517]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[518]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[519]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[520]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[521]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[522]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[523]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[524]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[525]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[526]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[527]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[528]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[529]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[530]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[531]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[532]	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO
[533]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[534]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[535]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[536]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[537]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 45 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[538]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[539]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[540]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[541]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[542]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[543]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[544]	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
[545]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[546]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[547]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[548]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[549]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[550]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[551]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[552]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[553]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[554]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
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[556]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
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[560]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[561]	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES
[562]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[563]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[564]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[565]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[566]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[567]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[568]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[569]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[570]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[571]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[572]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[573]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[574]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[575]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[576]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[577]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[578]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[579]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[580]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[581]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[582]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[583]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[584]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[585]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[586]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[587]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 46 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[588]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[589]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[590]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[591]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[592]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[593]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[594]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[595]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[596]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[597]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[598]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[599]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[600]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[601]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[602]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
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[614]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[615]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[616]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[617]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[618]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[619]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[620]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[621]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[622]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[623]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[624]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[625]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[626]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[627]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[628]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[629]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[630]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[631]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[632]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[633]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[634]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[635]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[636]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[637]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 47 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[638]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[639]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[640]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[641]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[642]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[643]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[644]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
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[646]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[647]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
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[651]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
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[655]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
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[661]	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO
[662]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[663]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[664]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[665]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[666]	NO	NO	YES	YES	NO
[667]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[668]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[669]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[670]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
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[672]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[673]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
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[675]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
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[679]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[680]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[681]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[682]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[683]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[684]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[685]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[686]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[687]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 48 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[688]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[689]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[690]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[691]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[692]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[693]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[694]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[695]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[696]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[697]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[698]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[699]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[700]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[701]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[702]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[703]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
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[710]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[711]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[712]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[713]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[714]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[715]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[716]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[717]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[718]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[719]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[720]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[721]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[722]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[723]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[724]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[725]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[726]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[727]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[728]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[729]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[730]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[731]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[732]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[733]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[734]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[735]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[736]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[737]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 49 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[738]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[739]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[740]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[741]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[742]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[743]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[744]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[745]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[746]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[747]	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES
[748]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[749]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[750]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[751]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[752]	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES
[753]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[754]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[755]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[756]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
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[759]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[760]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[761]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[762]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
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[767]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[768]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[769]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[770]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[771]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[772]	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO
[773]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[774]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[775]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[776]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[777]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[778]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[779]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[780]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[781]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[782]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[783]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[784]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[785]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[786]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[787]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 50 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[788]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[789]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[790]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[791]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[792]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[793]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[794]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[795]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[796]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[797]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[798]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[799]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[800]	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
[801]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[802]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[803]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[804]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[805]	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
[806]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[807]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[808]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
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[810]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[811]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[812]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[813]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[814]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[815]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[816]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[817]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[818]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[819]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[820]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[821]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[822]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[823]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[824]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[825]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[826]	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES
[827]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[828]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[829]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[830]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[831]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[832]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[833]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[834]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[835]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[836]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[837]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 51 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
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[839]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[840]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[841]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[842]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[843]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[844]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[845]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[846]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[847]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[848]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[849]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[850]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[851]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
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[855]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[856]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[857]	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO
[858]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[859]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[860]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[861]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[862]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[863]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[864]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[865]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[866]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[867]	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES
[868]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[869]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[870]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[871]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[872]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
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[874]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
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[876]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[877]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[878]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[879]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[880]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[881]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[882]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[883]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[884]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[885]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[886]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[887]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 52 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[888]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[889]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[890]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[891]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[892]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[893]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[894]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[895]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[896]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[897]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[898]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[899]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[900]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[901]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[902]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[903]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[904]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[905]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[906]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[907]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[908]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
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[910]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[911]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[912]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[913]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[914]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[915]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[916]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[917]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[918]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[919]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
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[921]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[922]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[923]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[924]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
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[926]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[927]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[928]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[929]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[930]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[931]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[932]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[933]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[934]	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO
[935]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[936]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[937]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 53 / 550

#Reference	Category C1?	Category C2?	Category C3?	Category C4?	Category C5?
[938]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[939]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[940]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[941]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[942]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[943]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[944]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[945]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[946]	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
[947]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[948]	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO
[949]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
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[962]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
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[967]	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
[968]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[969]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[970]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[971]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[972]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[973]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[974]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[975]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[976]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
[977]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[978]	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO
[979]	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO
[980]	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO

The quantity of publications of each category per year is, in turn, presented in Table 2.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 54 / 550

Table 2: Number of Publications of Each Category Per Year

Year	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
1986	1	1	0	0	0
1987	3	1	0	0	0
1988	3	2	0	0	0
1989	2	1	0	0	0
1990	0	0	0	0	0
1991	0	0	0	0	0
1992	2	0	0	0	0
1993	2	0	0	0	0
1994	3	1	2	0	0
1995	2	0	0	0	0
1996	2	0	0	0	0
1997	5	0	0	0	0
1998	4	0	0	0	0
1999	4	0	0	0	0
2000	2	1	0	0	0
2001	3	1	0	0	0
2002	5	0	0	0	0
2003	3	1	0	0	0
2004	3	2	2	0	0
2005	7	5	1	0	0
2006	5	0	3	0	0
2007	7	7	3	0	0
2008	4	3	2	0	0
2009	14	8	2	0	0
2010	15	6	4	0	0
2011	14	10	3	0	0
2012	12	6	1	0	0
2013	12	9	3	0	3
2014	10	7	3	0	0
2015	12	11	1	1	0
2016	18	15	7	0	0
2017	21	27	16	1	0
2018	17	35	33	2	4
2019	41	71	45	8	6
2020	76	94	67	8	6
2021	59	99	84	11	6
2022	21	63	47	1	4

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 55 / 550	

6 OVERVIEW OF THE STATE OF THE ART OF CATEGORIES C1, C2, C4, AND C5

This section presents a summary on research which relates AI to safety in a way which is marginally relevant for the purpose of the research on the safety assurance of AI-based systems. Despite the marginal relevance, advancements in these studies are still worth consideration for the safety assurance of AI-based systems for two main reasons:

- a) It is possible to identify potential applications which can benefit from the safety assurance of AI-based systems;
- b) Advancements and open challenges on areas which are prerequisites for the safety assurance of AI-based systems, such as security, can also provide insight for potential future work on the safety assurance of AI-based systems.

Taking into account the categories defined in the SLR method (see section 2.4), C1, C2, C4, and C5 are within the scope of the forthcoming sections.

6.1 CATEGORY C1: AI EMPLOYED ON OFF-LINE SAFETY ASSURANCE

The references which were classified in C1 cover using AI techniques to support off-line safety analyses. Hence, AI is not within the analyzed systems themselves; instead, they are solely employed to aid human safety experts on their safety assurance tasks by increasing automation and awareness, as well as reducing the effort for these tasks. The very first effort identified within this context is the research published by Mancini [512], which targets the safety analysis of nuclear reactors based on data collected as they operate. Since then, every year so far comprises at least one publication which is part of C1. The only exception to this behavior happened in 1990, when no C1 references were identified.

Throughout the timespan of all C1 publications, two main approaches in using AI to support safety analysis methods have been identified. The first one is based on employing AI to support human decision on operation-related safety analyses and predictive maintenance, and are represented by, e.g., the research by Kang and Kang [300], Moradi et al. [59], and Li et al. [700].

The second one, in turn, involves automating safety analysis methods in general. Hence, it covers automating not only well-known general-purpose safety analysis methods, such as Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP), Failure Modes, Effects and Criticality Analysis (FMECA) and FTA, but also safety analysis methods crafted for specific applications, such as metro and rail domains. A

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 56 / 550	

reference list on some research papers of this group is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Examples of C1 Research Papers with AI Applied to Support Safety Analysis Methods

Safety Analysis Methods with AI	Examples of Research Papers
HAZOP	Srinivasan and Venkatasubramanian [485], [486] Wu et al. [334] Bartlett and Andrews [472] Linard et al. [52] Möhrle et al. [281], [317] Purba et al. [406]
FTA	Shi et al. [402] Song et al. [417] Xie et al. [500] Zeller and Hoefig [282] Q. Zhang et al. [595] Ahmed and Gu [37] Cichocki and Górski [467]
FMECA	Rauschenbach and Nuffer [50] Stanojević and Ćirović [42] Yang, Bonsall and Wang [434] Zaman et al. [338]
Application-specific methods	Hadj-Mabrouk [30], [132], [135], [136], [191], [264], [291], [589]

The most remarkable AI models used in C1 are knowledge-based systems (formerly known as ‘expert systems’) (e.g., Ahmed and Gu [37], Brooker [395]) and machine learning (ML) techniques, with emphasis to neural networks (e.g., Ranyal and Jain [592]), reinforcement learning algorithms (Q-learning and other variants; e.g., Bernhard et al. [148], Moradi et al. [59], Radaideh et al. [607]) and Bayesian networks to model data uncertainty (e.g., Linard et al. [52], Rauschenbach and Nuffer [50]). Target applications, in turn, include developing and applying AI-based safety analysis methods to power plants, transportation systems (notably semiautonomous and fully autonomous ones) and process-based industries. Some examples of research papers for each of these applications are listed in Table 4.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 57 / 550	

Table 4: Main Application Domains of C1 and Examples of Research Papers

C1 Application Domains	Examples of Research Papers
Power plants	<p>Nuclear plants</p> <p>Cho [511] Huang et al. [316] Kim et al. [103], [590] Chongchong Liu et al. [591] Mandelli et al. [350] Mazrou [424] Purba et al. [401] Radaideh et al. [607] Yang, Jeong e Park [497] Zio et al. [430]</p> <p>Hydroelectric plants</p> <p>Onoda et al. [413], [438]</p> <p>Thermal plants</p> <p>Gu et al. [369] Liang et al. [367]</p> <p>Power distribution</p> <p>Li et al. [531] Wen et al. [142]</p>
Transportation systems	<p>Maritime transportation</p> <p>Chen et al. [284] Huang et al. [169] Kim [159] Lei at al. [274] Talavera Ortiz et al. [344] M. Zhang et al. [31] Bosse et al. [345] Carson et al. [172] Lee et al. [66] Luxhøj [323]</p> <p>Air transportation</p> <p>Ma et al. [146] Oztekin [328] Pedroni and Zio [322] Wang and Cao [403] Zhang et al. [331] Bati and Withington [120] Bearfield and Marsh [457]</p> <p>Rail-based transportation</p> <p>Guo et al. [229] Hadj-Mabrouk [30], [132], [135], [191], [263], [264] Kaeeni et al. [244]</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 58 / 550	

C1 Application Domains		Examples of Research Papers
	Road-based transportation	Lv et al. [234] Parkinson et al. [299] Ranyal and Jain [592] Singhal et al. [77] Zhu et al. [177] Chen et al. [85] Tian et al. [118] Wu et al. [88] Xie et al. [190]
Process industries	Chemical and petrochemical industries Other process industries	Arunthavanathan et al. [558] Ban [258] Guzman-Urbina and Aoyama [238] Shi et al. [402] Song et al. [417] Srinivasan and Venkatasubramanian [485], [486] Adedigba et al. [278] Dobaj et al. [199] Garvin and Kimbleton [622] Khakzad et al. [356] Tan et al. [364]

6.2 CATEGORY C2: AI EMPLOYED ON SAFETY-CRITICAL FUNCTIONS

The references which were classified in C2 cover the usage of AI within safety-critical systems, so that systems now rely on AI to automatically perform at least one of their safety-critical functions. Even though C2 introduces the concept of ‘safety-critical AI’, the main drawback shared by publications within C2 is the lack of evidence that these AI-based functions design and implementation have been indeed assessed and assured as sufficiently safe.

The first C2 publication is the one by Washio et al. [513], in which an expert system is employed to automatically monitor operational data of nuclear power plant equipment and advise human operators on the need of action to mitigate a potentially hazardous situation. The following years up to 2006 had occasional C2 research papers, followed by a regular stream of yearly publications starting on 2007.

Time progression also shows an evolving trend on both the AI techniques and the applications covered in C2 publications. With regard to AI techniques, the initial prevalence of knowledge-based systems throughout the 1980s and 1990s (e.g., Erdmann and Sun [510], Uhrig [509], and Washio et al.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 59 / 550

[513]) has been replaced by ML-based solutions starting on the 2000s. A non-exhaustive summary of the prominent ML techniques used in C2 research is presented on Table 5 along with supporting examples of recent reference papers.

Table 5: Main AI Techniques of C2 and Examples of Research Papers

AI Technique	Examples of Research Papers	
Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs)	Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)	R. Chen et al. [572] Yu et al. [27]
	Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) and Hybrid Neural Networks (HNNs)	Bao et al. [124] Hu et al.[64] Jia et al. [626]
	Deep Recurrent Neural Networks (DRNNs) in Long Short-Term Memories (LSTMs)	Hanifa and Akbar [198] Hong et al. [138] Y. Lin et al. [580]
Logistic Regression		Cai et al. [26] Wang et al. [129] Xing et al. [62]
k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN)		Orsini et al. [625] T. Chen et al. [28] Farid et al. [127] Hu et al. [64]
Decision Trees (DTs) and Random Forests (RFs)		Li et al. [250] Stohl and Stibor [617] Xing et al. [62] You et al. [265]
Boosting		Farid et al. [127] Geramifard et al. [376] Li et al. [250] Orsini et al. [625]
Support Vector Machines (SVMs)		Xing et al. [62] You et al. [265] Yu and Abdel-Aty [346] Baheri et al. [573] El-Shamouty et al. [615]
Reinforcement Learning (with Deep Learning)		Hodge et al. [93] Reyad et al. [708] Wang et al. [43]

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 60 / 550	

The main C2 target application is related to automating ground vehicles, initially with driving-assisting functions [476] and then followed by research towards their unmanned operation. The automation of other transportation means, including air transportation, railway transportation and maritime transportation, have also been covered within C2 research. Furthermore, C2 also encompasses using AI for safety-critical functions on medical systems (e.g., cardiac monitoring and patient homecare) and power generation and distribution, as well as general-purpose research on safety-critical AI applied to electrical, electronic and programmable electronic (E/E/PE) devices. Some examples of research papers for each of these applications are listed in Table 6.

Table 6: Main Application Domains of C2 and Examples of Research Papers

C2 Application Domains	Examples of Research Papers
Transportation systems	Road-based transportation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Baheri et al. [573] Bajcsy et al. [179] Cai et al. [26] Chakraborty et al. [158] Chen et al. [28], [220] Chen et al. [572] Dávid et al. [188] Farid et al. [127] Garoui [288] Gull and Mogali [418] Hossain et al. [125] Katrakazas et al. [126] Li et al. [110] Li et al. [298] Md Muzahid et al. [562] Muril et al. [609] Nine et al. [606] Peng et al. [211] Raksincharoensak et al. [414] Rong et al. [429] Wei [476] Xiao et al. [33] Xu et al. [111] Yin et al. [581] Yu et al. [585] Zeng et al. [568] Air transportation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cui et al. [349]

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 61 / 550	

C2 Application Domains	Examples of Research Papers
	Gan and Li [333] Geramifard et al. [376] Hanifa and Akbar [198] Herbert et al. [178] Hodge et al. [93] Kikumoto et al. [599] Lin et al. [580] Xu et al. [216] Yel and Bezzo [150]
Rail-based transportation	Yong et al. [320] Chen et al. [97] Gao and Shi [96] Grinyak and Devyatisilny [330] Gucma and Marcjan [361] Lisowski [325]
Maritime transportation	D. Liu et al. [87] Phung et al. [204] Szlapczynski and Niksa-Rynkiewicz [230] Zhao and Fu [543] Zhao et al. [305] Zhen et al. [273]
Medical systems	Aljaaf et al. [311] Namba and Yamada [221]
Power generation and distribution	Alfonsi et al. [329], [351] Liang et al. [106]
Generalities on E/E/PE Systems	Dilokthanakul and Shanahan [226] Kugele et al. [271] Puch et al. [225]

6.3 CATEGORY C4: CONTEXTUALIZATION OF AI ON INDUSTRY 4.0 APPLICATIONS

The references which were classified in C4 provide examples of safety-critical problems and applications within the context of Industry 4.0. It is deemed that texts within this category can shed some light on applications which can most benefit from a general-purpose and structured safety assurance method for AI-based systems.

The texts which belong to C4 have been published since 2015. Papers within this category emphasize

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 62 / 550	

supply chain and manufacturing automation (e.g., Etz et al. [575], Sobb et al. [561]), human behavior modeling [186] and main safety challenges on automated transportation, nuclear and hydraulic systems (e.g., Alessandrini et al. [327], Cokorilo [25], Hamer et al. [24], Kim et al. [174]).

6.4 CATEGORY C5: AI EMPLOYED IN SECURITY-CRITICAL FUNCTIONS WITH POTENTIAL IMPACT ON SAFETY

The references which were classified in C5 bear some relationship between security and AI from which the safety assurance area can somehow benefit. The two main approaches of research classified in C5 include the usage of AI for security assurance (e.g., Demidov et al. [205], Wang et al. [140]) and the security analysis of AI-based systems (e.g., Chu et al. [74], Lichte and Wolf [44], Link et al. [194], Piètre-Cambacédès and Bouissou [357]).

AI-based techniques explored in C5, such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [981] and means to increase robustness to information falsifying attacks [982], can be reused in other contexts to aid the safety assurance of AI-based systems (e.g., GANs generating corner scenarios to challenge safety-critical AI).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 63 / 550	

7 ADDITIONAL BIBLIOMETRICS OF CATEGORY C3 REFERENCES

The objective of this section is to expand on the category C3 bibliometrics covered in the research paper ‘*Safety Assurance of Artificial Intelligence-Based Systems: A Systematic Literature Review on the State of the Art and Guidelines for Future Work*’. The results herein presented extend further than the timespan of the aforementioned paper, going up to August 26th, 2022, and comprise more in-depth analyses on the relevance of the safety assurance of AI-based systems and the most prominent authors, events and periodics which cover such a theme.

These analyses are detailed in the forthcoming sections.

7.1 RELEVANCE OF THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS

We justify that the safety assurance of AI-based systems is an increasingly relevant research theme by means of Figure 1, which is a graph with yearly advancements on the safety assurance of AI-based since 1994 (green line) and a 3-year moving average (brown line).

Figure 1: Number of C3 References per Year (Green) and 3-Year Moving Average (Brown)

Figure 1 data shows a sharp increase of C3-classified publications especially starting in 2015, indicating that the safety assessment of AI-based systems has been increasingly explored by

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 64 / 550	

researchers over the last years. The reduction in 2022 is not further discussed because the assessed data goes up to August 26th, 2022.

This corroborates the justification of this research as important for the safety assessment of AI-based systems. The herein documented SLR is the first step towards future contribution on the area, since it allows identifying current scientific advancements and gaps so that future research efforts are directed in filling at least some of the identified gaps.

7.2 Q-INDEX OVERALL ANALYSIS

We also in Figure 2 and Figure 3 the yearly absolute and relative contributions, respectively, of Low, Medium and High quality references (as per the fuzzy Q-Index classification presented in section 2.6). In these graphs, the period ranging from 1995 to 2003 has been deliberately omitted because no C3 references have been identified by means of the TAK filter within this range.

Figure 2: Absolute Number of C3 References per Year from 1994 onwards for each Q-Index Fuzzy Group

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 65 / 550	

Figure 3: Relative Contribution of Yearly C3 References from 1994 onwards for each Q-Index Fuzzy Group

Figure 2 confirms the overall increase of C3 publications with time especially starting on 2015, as stated in section 7.1. In addition to this, it is possible to notice that high quality references had steep increases especially in 2017 and 2020, which contributes even more to the section 7.1 justification that the safety assurance of AI-based systems has become increasingly more important over the last years. Moreover, Figure 2 and Figure 3 show that high quality references have also become the most frequent among all C3 references starting in 2019. Even though a similar behavior has been observed during the 2004-2007 period, this is not deemed consistent and sufficient relevant for generalization because most of the high quality research of this timespan has been carried out by two researchers only (T. Kelly and Z. Kurd) [444], [446], [455] and [464], thus not as widespread throughout the research community as of 2019 onwards.

The overall increase of the Q-index with time is also depicted in a yearly representation on Figure 4, which provides the average Q-index reached by all C3 publication in every year within the range 1994-2022 except for the 1995-2003 because the latter does not sport any C3 reference.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 66 / 550	

Figure 4: Yearly Evolution of the Publications Average Q-Index

Figure 4 shows that the Q-index has increased with time especially from 2017 onwards, peaking at more than 3 from 2020 onwards. Two spurious peaks are worth highlighting: the first one, related to 2004-2007, is justified by the standing out of the aforementioned publications by T. Kelly and Z. Kurd on a very constrained set of no more than three publications per year, whereas the second one, in 2012, is justified by the existence of a single C3 reference [373], which was rated as high quality (Q-Index = 5).

7.3 CROSS-ANALYSIS OF Q-INDEX AND AUTHORS

A cross-analysis involving the Q-Index of C3 references and their authors has been performed in order to identify the most prominent authors of C3 categories taking into account three author-related metrics.

- a) **Number of C3 Publications:** This corresponds to a count of all author's publications within C3. It is not deemed fully suitable for quality analysis because a high number of publications does not necessarily translate into high quality. ;
- b) **Number of High Quality C3 Publications:** This corresponds to a count of the author's publications which have been rated with a high Q-Index (i.e. $Q \geq 4$ as per criteria defined in section 2.6);
- c) **Average C3 Q-Index:** This metric corresponds to the arithmetic average Q-Index of all

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 67 / 550	

publications of an author. No weighted averages related to the timeliness of the research papers (e.g. higher weight for recent publications and lower weight for older publications) have been attributed in this step.

The graph presented in Figure 5 summarizes the most relevant findings related to the three aforementioned metrics. The information presented in the graph was ranked in descending order of “average C3 Q-Index” and only comprises authors (i.) with at least 3 C3 publications, OR (ii.) with at least one C3 high quality ($Q \geq 4$) publication, OR (iii.) whose average Q-Index is higher than 3. Whenever at least two authors shared the exact same three metrics, they were grouped into equivalence classes labeled from “Group A” to “Group S” in Figure 5. Please refer to Table 7 to Table 9 for the full list of authors which are part of each of these groups. The list of all metrics obtained by each author/group depicted in Figure 5 is detailed in Table 10.

The authors on the lower tiers in Figure 5 (notably from G. Li up to M. Trapp) did not score high quality papers with regard to the scope of this SLR and are especially related to publications which were conservatively classified as part of C3 during the TAK Filter because TAK information was not sufficient to rule out this classification. Their research mainly covers adaptive systems without taking into account AI aspects (notably P. Liggesmeyer, D. Schneider and M. Trapp) or the exploration of safety-related AI systems without an in-depth consideration of safety assessment per se.

Figure 5: Cross-Analysis of Authorship and Q-Index

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 68 / 550

Table 7: List of Groups A, C, D, E, F, G, I, and J Authors

Group A	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G	Group I	Group J
S. A. Smolka	J. Austin	R. Salay	E. Tang	M. Fazlyab	D. H. Tran	C. Huang	J. Liu
S. D. Stoller	J. Zhang	X. Li	Q. Zhao	M. Morari	F. Flammini	I. Ruchkin	J. Sun
	Y. Ji		R. Ivanov		M. Sha	M. Cleaveland	K. Leung
			T. Lawton		M. Wagner	O. Sokolsky	
			Y. Wang		P. Koopman		
					Q. Chen		
					Q. Wang		
					Q. Zhu		
					R. Alur		
					Y. Hu		
					Z. Porter		

Table 8: List of Groups K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, and S Authors

Group K	Group L	Group M	Group N	Group P	Group Q	Group R	Group S
C. Picardi	D. M. Lopez	R. Hawkins	A. Carron	C. Hartsell	D. Genin	H. Zhao	D. Meltz
N. Jansen	W. Lin	S. Wang	I. Lamrani	Z. Wang	S. Zhang	R. Alexander	F. Ishikawa
		X. Zhang	L. Ma				H. Guterman
			X. Xie				S. Kabir
			Y. Liu				Z. Liu
			C. Thomas				
			H. Zheng				
			J. Chen				
			N. Hamilton				
			R. Grosu				
			R. Lee				
			S. Bak				
			W. Li				

Table 9: List of Groups B, H and O Authors

Group B		Group H			Group O	
A. Frorath	L. Zhang	A. Abate	H. Xi	P. Lu	A. Easwaran	M. Balchanos
A. Irfan	M. Adedjouma	A. Aldo Faisal	H. Zhang	P. S. Thomas	A. Groza	M. Borg
A. Knoll	M. Frey	A. B. Hocking	H. Zhou	P. Sarathy	A. K. Akametalu	M. Brito
A. Maleki	M. H. Osman	A. Baldovin	H. Zhu	P. Vlantis	A. Murugesan	M. Caporuscio
A. Pereira	M. Khalili	A. C. Gordon	J. A. Vincent	Q. Hao	A. Rawson	M. D'Angelo
A. Rohatschek	M. Koren	A. Claviere	J. Adelt	R. Adler	A. Subbaswamy	M. G. Madden
A. Rupalla	M. Mock	A. Grushin	J. Athavale	R. Chen	A. Tacchella	M. Gibson
A. Tarrisse	M. Neuhaeusser	A. H. A. Anderegg	J. Brulé	R. Rosales	B. Cukic	M. Hussain
A. Viehl	M. R. Zofka	A. Maheshwari	J. C. Rowanhill	R. Samanta	B. Lee	M. Kahn
B. J. Taylor	M. Sarvi	A. Peruffo	J. F. Boulineau	R. Yan	B. Tearle	M. Machin
B. Yang	M. T. Amin	A. Sahu	J. Fan	S. Avin	B. Xue	M.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS				Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022		Revision 6	
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO			Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA			Page: 69 / 550	

Group B		Group H			Group O		
						Mladenovski	
C. Paterson	N. Paoletti	A. Tyagi	J. Fischer	S. Baruah	C. Brogle	M. Pavone	
C. Schyr	N. Rajabli	B. B. Sethy	J. Girard-Satabin	S. Chen	C. Lazarus	M. Roy	
C. Smith	N. Wiechowski	B. Jin	J. Gluck	S. Cook	C. Wu	M. Unterreiner	
C. Yan	P. Morgan	B. Knie	J. H. Gillula	S. H. Chung	D. Flynn	M. Wu	
D. Grimm	P. Munk	C. E. Tuncali	J. H. Husen	S. Hsu	D. Gregory	M. Zhang	
D. Schmidt	P. Robinette	C. Garion	J. Hernández-Orallo	S. Jagannathan	D. Zhao	N. Ali	
D. T. Phan	P. Sun	C. Pagetti	J. Kapinski	S. Jana	E. Fuller	P. Becker	
E. Denney	P. Sweatman	C. Stiller	J. L. C. Guo	S. Kokaly	F. U. Muram	P. Schleiss	
F. Blank	R. J. Moss	D. Ahmed	J. Nanda	S. M. Jordan	G. A. Muntean	Q. Li	
F. Hantschel	R. Nardone	D. Kamran	J. Niu	S. Ó Héigeartaigh	G. Jaeger	R. Adams	
F. Huger	S. Ballingall	D. Li	J. Sifakis	S. Raafatnia	G. Vachtsevanos	R. Nardone	
F. Lüttner	S. Dey	D. Lv	J. V Deshmukh	S. Sun	H. Hansson	S. D. Nicoara	
F. Masse	S. Knoop	D. Miller	J. Weimer	S. Vaidya	H. Kuwajima	S. Gupta	
F. T. S. Chan	S. Qu	D. Stojcsics	J. Whitehouse	S. Vock	H. Lam	S. K. Chandrasekar	
G. Pai	S. Scholz	D. Wolf	J. Whittlestone	S. Voß	H. Ren	S. K. S. Gupta	
G. Pedroza	S. Shafaei	Đ. Žikeli	J. Yang	T. A. Beyene	H. Thane	S. Kaynama	
G. Schulz	S. Sheikhi	E. Acar-Celik	K. Chatterjee	T. Carpenter	H. Yasuoka	S. Marrone	
H. Hu	S. Z. Halim	E. Asselin	K. Jothimurugan	T. Cui	I. Kurzidem	S. Oh	
H. Wen	S.-W. Lee	E. Baskaya	K. Pei	T. Dobberphul	I. Ullah	S. Punnekkat	
I. Bose	T. Schamm	E. Wozniak	K. S. Wasson	T. Engelgeh	J. Bragg	S. Sanjeev	
I. Häring	T. Stauner	F. Cai	K. Wardega	T. Liebreuz	J. E. Hai Koh	S. Saria	
J. Muse	U. Mehmood	F. Fratrick	K.-U. Scholl	T. Samann	J. G. Lopez	S. Stober	
K. Rattan	V. Vittorini	F. Martínez-Plumed	L. Chen	T. Tang	J. Gillula	S. Usanavasin	
K. Ross	X. Qiu	F. R. Ward	M. Angus	T. Watanabe	J. Han	S. Yerramalla	
L. Pullum	Y. Hagiwara	F. Wotawa	M. Bronz	U. D. Ferrell	J. He	S. Zug	
L. Scwharz		G. Charpiat	M. Busch	U. Ferrell	J. Henriksson	T. Braunl	
		G. Hou	M. Douthwaite	V. Rocco	J. J. Choi	T. Drage	
		G. Kou	M. Komorowski	W. Cao	J. Schleiss	T. Graeber	
		G. Pu	M. Lopez Diego	W. Kong	J. Thumm	T. Nakae	
		G. Schwalbe	M. M. Zavlanos	X. Lin	J.-E. Hong	T. Zhou	
		G. Siedel	M. P. Chapman	X. Luo	J.-P. Blanquart	V. Abdelzad	
		G. Tan	M. Pajic	Y. Chandak	K. L. Lim	V. D. Nguyen	
		G. Theocharous	M. Paulitsch	Y. Fukazawa	K. Salako	V. Robu	
		H. Choi	M. Schoenauer	Y. Han	K. Socha	W. Ruan	
		H. Ito	M. Schwager	Y. He	K. Sreenath	X. Zhao	
		H. J. Putzer	M. Watanabe	Y. Peng	L. Pulina	Y. Bai	
		H. Kim	M. White	Y. Sun	L. Strigini	Y. Wu	
		H. Liang	M. Wolf	Y. Xiang	L. Todorean	Z. Huang	
		H. Si	N. C. Oza	Z. Chihani	M. A. Javed		

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 70 / 550	

Group B	Group H			Group O
	H. T. Tun	N. Yoshioka	Z. Jiang	
	H. Takeuchi	O. Bastani	Z. Qin	
	H. Washizaki	P. Festor	Z. Zhao	
	H. Wu	P. Herber		

Table 10: Full Results of Authors' Metrics Depicted in Figure 5

Author	Occurrences on Category 3	High Quality Occurrences on Category 3 (4-6)	Average Category 3 Quality
Group A	2	2	6
Group B	1	1	6
Z. Kurd	5	5	5,6
L. Gauerhof	4	4	5,5
Group C	2	2	5,5
Z. Yang	3	3	5,333333333
S. Burton	4	4	5,25
T. Kelly	7	6	5,142857143
K. Czarnecki	5	5	5
Group D	4	4	5
G. J. Pappas	4	3	5
Group E	3	3	5
Group F	3	2	5
Group G	2	2	5
Group H	1	1	5
I. Lee	4	4	4,75
Y. Jia	4	3	4,75
Group I	3	3	4,666666667
J. Li	3	2	4,666666667
J. McDermid	4	3	4,5
Group J	2	2	4,5
Group K	2	1	4,5
X. Huang	3	3	4,333333333
Group L	3	2	4,333333333
T. T. Johnson	7	5	4,142857143
I. Habli	13	9	4,076923077
P. Musau	5	3	4
X. Chen	4	3	4
M. Kwiatkowska	3	3	4
Group M	3	2	4
Group N	2	2	4
Group O	1	1	4
M. J. Kochenderfer	6	3	3,833333333
Y. Zhang	5	4	3,8
A. Corso	3	1	3,666666667

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 71 / 550	

Author	Occurrences on Category 3	High Quality Occurrences on Category 3 (4-6)	Average Category 3 Quality
W. Xiang	5	3	3,6
A. Schmidt	4	2	3,5
Group P	3	2	3,333333333
C. J. Tomlin	5	3	3,2
M. N. Zeilinger	4	3	3
H.-D. Tran	5	2	3
Group Q	3	1	3
K. P. Wabersich	3	2	2,666666667
I. Sorokos	3	1	2,666666667
J. Woodcock	3	0	2,333333333
J. Reich	4	1	2,25
X. Wang	5	1	2
G. Li	3	0	2
Group R	3	0	1,666666667
Group S	3	0	1,333333333
P. Liggesmeyer	4	0	1
S. Müller	3	0	1
D. Schneider	7	0	0,857142857
M. Trapp	6	0	0,833333333

7.4 CROSS-ANALYSIS OF Q-INDEX AND PERIODIC PUBLICATIONS

An analysis similar to that of section 7.3 has been carried out to allow assessing the relationship between periodic publications (e.g. journals, magazines, etc.) and the respective Q-Index metrics attributed to their C3-categorized papers. Three periodics-related metrics, analogous to those of section 7.3, were also adopted for this purpose:

- a) Number of C3 Publications: This corresponds to a count of all C3-categorized papers on each periodic publication;
- b) Number of High Quality C3 Publications: This corresponds to a count of the periodic publications' papers which have been rated with a high Q-Index (i.e. $Q \geq 4$ as per criteria defined in section 2.6);
- c) Average C3 Q-Index: This metric corresponds to the arithmetic average Q-Index of all C3 papers within a periodic publication. No weighted averages related to the timeliness of the research papers (e.g. higher weight for recent publications and lower weight for older publications) have been attributed in this step.

The graph presented in Figure 6 summarizes the most relevant findings related to the three

aforementioned metrics. Information presented in the graph was ranked in descending order of “average C3 Q-Index” and only comprises periodic publications (i.) with at least 2 C3 publications, OR (ii.) with at least one C3 high quality ($Q \geq 4$) publication, OR (iii.) whose average Q-Index is higher than 3. Whenever at least two periodic publications shared the exact same three metrics, they were grouped into equivalence classes labeled from “Group A” to “Group E” in Figure 6. Please refer to Table 11 and Table 12 for the full list of periodic publications which are part of each of these groups, as well as to Table 13 for the detailed metrics results depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Cross-Analysis of Periodic Publications and Q-Index

Table 11: List of Groups A-C Periodic Publications

Group A	Group B	Group C
Computers and Chemical Engineering	ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems	Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems
Decision Support Systems	Information and Software Technology	Applied Sciences
IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering	Methods and Procedures for the Verification and Validation of Artificial Neural Networks	BMJ Health and Care Informatics
Journal of Machine Learning Research		IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing
Journal of Systems and Software		Industrial Management and Data Systems
Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction		Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers
Neural Computing and Applications		Unmanned System Technologies
SAE International Journal of Advances and Current Practices in Mobility		

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 73 / 550	

Table 12: List of Groups D-E Periodic Publications

Group D	Group E	
IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems	ACM Transactions on Modeling and Computer Simulation	IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems
Journal of Systems Architecture	Annals of Mathematics and Artificial Intelligence	IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems
SAE Technical Papers	Automated Software Engineering	Journal of Intelligent and Robotic Systems: Theory and Applications
	Bulletin of the World Health Organization	Journal of Medical and Biological Engineering
	Future Generation Computer Systems	Software Impacts
	IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters	Transport Reviews
	IEEE Transactions on Computer-aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems	

Table 13: Full Results of Periodic Publications Metrics Depicted in Figure 6

Journal	Occurrences on Category 3	High Quality Occurrences on Category 3 (4-6)	Average Category 3 Quality
Group A	1	1	6
Artificial Intelligence	2	2	5,5
Group B	2	2	5
Group C	1	1	5
Group D	2	2	4,5
IEEE Trans. Automatic Control	3	2	4,333333333
Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research	2	1	4
Group E	1	1	4
IEEE Access	3	1	3,666666667
Formal Aspects of Computing	3	1	3,333333333
Safety Science	3	0	2,666666667
Reliability Engineering and System Safety	4	1	2,5
IEEE Trans. Intelligent Transportation Systems	6	2	2,166666667
IEEE Trans. Intelligent Vehicles	2	0	1,5
Accident Analysis and Prevention	2	0	0,5

The two last journals represented in Figure 6 – namely, IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles and Accident Analysis and Prevention, have reached average Q-Indexes lower than 2 (1.5 and 0.5, respectively). The low Q-Index scored by both journals is mostly justified by the conservative classification of its papers as part of C3 during the TAK Filter because their TAK information was not sufficient to rule out this classification.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 74 / 550

7.5 CROSS-ANALYSIS OF Q-INDEX AND RESEARCH EVENTS / PROCEEDINGS

An analysis similar to that of section 7.4 has also been performed to evaluate the relationship between research events which promoted C3 publications (by means of indexed proceedings) and the respective Q-Index metrics attributed to them during this SLR. Metrics analogous to those of section 7.4 were also adopted for this purpose:

- a) Number of C3 Publications: This corresponds to a count of all C3-categorized papers on each research event (by means of its indexed proceedings);
- b) Number of High Quality C3 Publications: This corresponds to a count of the event's papers (identified by means of its indexed proceedings) which have been rated with a high Q-Index (i.e. $Q \geq 4$ as per criteria defined in section 2.6);
- c) Average C3 Q-Index: This metric corresponds to the arithmetic average Q-Index of all C3 papers within the indexed proceedings of an event. No weighted averages related to the timeliness of the research papers (e.g. higher weight for recent publications and lower weight for older publications) have been attributed in this step.

The graph presented in Figure 7 summarizes the most relevant findings related to the three aforementioned metrics. Information presented in the graph was ranked in descending order of "average C3 Q-Index" and only comprises events whose indexed proceedings include (i.) at least 2 C3 publications, OR (ii.) at least one C3 high quality ($Q \geq 4$) publication, OR (iii.) whose average Q-Index is higher than 3. Whenever at least two events shared the exact same three metrics, they were grouped into equivalence classes labeled from "Group A" to "Group M" in Figure 7. Please refer to Table 14 and Table 15 for the full list of events which are part of each of these groups, and to Table 16 for the detailed metrics depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Cross-Analysis of Periodic Publications and Q-Index

Table 14: List of Groups A-G Events

Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G
ICAA	Design Automation Conference	AIAA Scitech Forum	FM	AISTATS	SASSUR	DECSoS
SEKE	DSN	CAIN	IDEAL	CONCUR	STRIVE	WAISE
	NeurIPS	ETAPS		ETFA		
	PAIS	FMCAD		IJCAI		
		IMECE				
		IROS				
		ISSRE				
		LARS				
		NSV				
		REW				
		SBR				
		TACAS				
		VSTTE				
		WRE				

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 76 / 550

Table 15: List of Groups H-M Events

Group H	Group I	Group J	Group K	Group L	Group M
CAV	ICCAD	DepDevOps	ISSREW	AITest	AIAA Guidance, Navigation, and Control Conference
ESREL	ICSE	IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems	SMC	ICUAS	IEE Colloquium on Knowledge-Based Systems for Safety Critical Applications
	IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium	USDAI			
	SEAMS				

Table 16: Full Results of Research Events/Proceedings Publications Metrics Depicted in Figure 7

Event	Occurrences on Category 3	High Quality Occurrences on Category 3 (4-6)	Average Category 3 Quality
Group A	1	1	6
HSCC	3	3	5
Group B	2	2	5
Group C	1	1	5
DASC	6	6	4,666666667
ICCP	2	1	4,5
ICRA	8	6	4
NFM	3	2	4
Group D	2	1	4
Group E	1	1	4
CEUR Workshop	6	4	3,666666667
SAFECOMP	26	16	3,653846154
DATE	4	2	3,5
SafeAI	2	1	3,5
Group F	6	3	3,333333333
ECAI	3	2	3,333333333
Group G	8	4	3,125
ASSURE	7	3	3
ICCPs	3	2	3
Group H	3	1	3
Group I	2	1	3
CDC	5	1	2,6
Group J	2	1	2,5
Group K	3	1	2,333333333
EDCC	7	2	2,285714286
AAAI Conference on AI	3	0	2
ITSC	10	1	1,8
Group L	2	0	1,5

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 77 / 550	

Event	Occurrences on Category 3	High Quality Occurrences on Category 3 (4-6)	Average Category 3 Quality
Group M	2	0	1
MODELS-C	2	0	0,5

Two results from Figure 7 are worth highlighting. Firstly, the low tier events comprising the AAI Conference on AI, ITSC, Group L events, Group M events and MODELS-C, had average Q-Indexes ranging between 2 and 0.5 and were not able to rank any high quality papers despite having at least two C3-categorized papers. The low Q-Index score attributed to these events is mostly justified by the conservative classification of its papers as part of C3 during the TAK Filter because their TAK information was not sufficient to rule out this classification. Secondly, some events were carried out together with other events which might have different rankings. For instance, PAIS was performed together with ECAI from 2020 onwards, and ASSURE was performed together with SAFECOMP in 2015, 2018 and from 2020 onwards.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 78 / 550	

8 CATEGORY C3 REFERENCES FULL TEXT SLR RESULTS REPORTS

The SLR Results Reports for C3-categorized reference at the TAK filter stage are presented in the following subsections. Each subsection corresponds to the SLR Results Report of a category C3 reference and comprises the Q-Index defined according to section 2.6 and the answers to questions Q1-Q6 specified in section 2.5.

The compilation of data collected by the answers to questions Q1 and Q2 is presented in sections 8.1 and 8.2, respectively.

8.1 COMPILATION OF DATA FROM QUESTION Q1 ANSWERS

All C3 references were classified in one out of the four mutually exclusive objective groups (OGs) defined as follows. The mapping of each C3 paper to their respective OGs is presented in Table 17.

- **OG1:** The research only aims to review and/or spot gaps on AI-based systems verification, validation and safety activities;
- **OG2:** The research aims to propose means to ensure that an AI-based system/function is safe and present supporting results;
- **OG3:** The research aims to apply methods defined in other research to ensure that an AI-based system is safe;
- **OG4:** The research covers other topics which may be either marginally related or unrelated to OG1, OG2 and OG3.

Table 17: Data Compilation of Q1 Answers for Category C3 References

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[36]	6	High	X			
[46]	5	High	X			
[53]	6	High		X		
[54]	2	Not High				X
[55]	5	High		X		
[56]	1	Not High	X			
[57]	6	High		X		
[58]	5	High	X			
[67]	2	Not High			X	
[70]	4	High		X		
[71]	6	High		X		
[73]	4	High		X		
[80]	0	Not High				X
[81]	4	High			X	

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 79 / 550

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[89]	4	High		X		
[92]	2	Not High		X		
[95]	1	Not High		X		
[98]	2	Not High		X		
[100]	1	Not High				X
[101]	1	Not High				X
[104]	1	Not High			X	
[107]	3	Not High		X		
[115]	2	Not High			X	
[116]	3	Not High		X		
[117]	5	High		X		
[119]	4	High		X		
[121]	2	Not High		X		
[131]	5	High		X		
[133]	5	High		X		
[134]	5	High		X		
[139]	6	High		X		
[143]	1	Not High				X
[151]	4	High		X		
[154]	2	Not High				X
[156]	1	Not High		X		
[160]	0	Not High				X
[161]	5	High		X		
[163]	2	Not High		X		
[165]	1	Not High				X
[166]	3	Not High		X		
[167]	6	High		X		
[170]	1	Not High				X
[175]	5	High		X		
[180]	3	Not High		X		
[181]	1	Not High	X			
[182]	2	Not High				X
[185]	2	Not High			X	
[193]	1	Not High				X
[195]	5	High		X		
[200]	5	High		X		
[201]	2	Not High				X
[202]	0	Not High				X
[207]	1	Not High				X
[208]	1	Not High				X
[209]	1	Not High				X
[210]	2	Not High				X
[212]	5	High		X		
[213]	4	High		X		
[214]	2	Not High		X		
[215]	4	High		X		
[218]	4	High		X		
[219]	1	Not High				X
[222]	6	High		X		
[223]	5	High		X		

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 80 / 550

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[227]	1	Not High				X
[228]	0	Not High				X
[231]	1	Not High				X
[232]	0	Not High				X
[233]	5	High		X		
[237]	2	Not High			X	
[239]	1	Not High				X
[240]	1	Not High				X
[241]	5	High		X		
[242]	2	Not High				X
[245]	2	Not High				X
[247]	2	Not High			X	
[251]	1	Not High				X
[252]	2	Not High				X
[253]	0	Not High				X
[254]	1	Not High				X
[255]	1	Not High				X
[256]	1	Not High				X
[259]	1	Not High	X			
[262]	3	Not High		X		
[266]	0	Not High				X
[267]	4	High		X		
[269]	0	Not High				X
[275]	1	Not High				X
[276]	0	Not High				X
[283]	3	Not High		X		
[287]	1	Not High				X
[289]	2	Not High	X			
[295]	2	Not High				X
[297]	6	High		X		
[302]	1	Not High				X
[306]	1	Not High				X
[307]	0	Not High				X
[318]	1	Not High				X
[332]	1	Not High		X		
[340]	1	Not High				X
[347]	1	Not High				X
[354]	1	Not High				X
[358]	3	Not High		X		
[373]	5	High		X		
[390]	1	Not High				X
[394]	0	Not High				X
[396]	2	Not High	X			
[398]	1	Not High				X
[399]	0	Not High				X
[404]	0	Not High				X
[419]	1	Not High			X	
[420]	1	Not High				X
[433]	1	Not High				X
[443]	0	Not High				X

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 81 / 550

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[445]	6	High		X		
[447]	6	High		X		
[453]	4	High		X		
[454]	6	High		X		
[455]	1	Not High		X		
[456]	5	High		X		
[465]	6	High		X		
[495]	1	Not High				X
[496]	1	Not High	X			
[522]	4	High		X		
[526]	4	High		X		
[528]	2	Not High		X		
[532]	0	Not High				X
[533]	0	Not High		X		
[534]	1	Not High				X
[535]	2	Not High		X		
[537]	1	Not High				X
[542]	0	Not High				X
[544]	0	Not High	X			
[546]	4	High		X		
[547]	5	High		X		
[548]	5	High		X		
[549]	5	High		X		
[551]	1	Not High				X
[553]	1	Not High				X
[557]	1	Not High				X
[563]	5	High		X		
[565]	2	Not High	X			
[566]	5	High		X		
[569]	0	Not High				X
[570]	6	High	X			
[574]	4	High		X		
[576]	1	Not High				X
[577]	4	High		X		
[578]	6	High		X		
[579]	4	High		X		
[582]	4	High		X		
[586]	4	High		X		
[587]	5	High		X		
[588]	1	Not High			X	
[596]	2	Not High		X		
[600]	6	High	X			
[601]	5	High		X		
[602]	2	Not High		X		
[603]	3	Not High		X		
[604]	5	High		X		
[605]	5	High		X		
[610]	1	Not High				X
[613]	2	Not High		X		
[614]	0	Not High				X

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 82 / 550

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[616]	2	Not High		X		
[617]	0	Not High				X
[618]	5	High		X		
[619]	0	Not High				X
[620]	3	Not High		X		
[621]	6	High		X		
[630]	1	Not High				X
[632]	3	Not High		X		
[634]	1	Not High			X	
[637]	4	High		X		
[640]	4	High		X		
[642]	3	Not High		X		
[644]	6	High		X		
[650]	5	High		X		
[662]	5	High		X		
[663]	4	High		X		
[664]	1	Not High			X	
[666]	0	Not High				X
[667]	2	Not High			X	
[668]	3	Not High			X	
[669]	2	Not High			X	
[670]	1	Not High				X
[671]	3	Not High			X	
[672]	4	High		X		
[673]	4	High		X		
[675]	4	High		X		
[676]	5	High		X		
[682]	6	High	X			
[684]	1	Not High				X
[686]	5	High		X		
[687]	6	High		X		
[688]	1	Not High			X	
[689]	4	High		X		
[690]	3	Not High		X		
[691]	3	Not High			X	
[692]	1	Not High			X	
[693]	5	High		X		
[694]	2	Not High		X		
[695]	5	High		X		
[696]	5	High		X		
[697]	5	High		X		
[705]	2	Not High		X		
[706]	2	Not High		X		
[709]	3	Not High		X		
[712]	1	Not High		X		
[713]	1	Not High		X		
[714]	1	Not High		X		
[715]	5	High		X		
[716]	1	Not High				X
[717]	4	High		X		

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 83 / 550

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[718]	5	High		X		
[719]	5	High		X		
[728]	1	Not High				X
[739]	1	Not High		X		
[740]	5	High		X		
[741]	6	High		X		
[743]	4	High		X		
[744]	5	High		X		
[745]	5	High		X		
[748]	6	High		X		
[749]	0	Not High		X		
[750]	5	High		X		
[751]	6	High		X		
[752]	1	Not High				X
[755]	0	Not High		X		
[757]	0	Not High		X		
[760]	0	Not High		X		
[761]	1	Not High		X		
[762]	5	High	X			
[763]	5	High		X		
[765]	5	High		X		
[766]	5	High		X		
[768]	1	Not High				X
[769]	4	High		X		
[770]	2	Not High				X
[771]	0	Not High				X
[773]	5	High		X		
[777]	3	Not High		X		
[778]	5	High		X		
[779]	5	High		X		
[780]	2	Not High			X	
[781]	3	Not High		X		
[782]	5	High		X		
[783]	0	Not High				X
[785]	5	High		X		
[786]	4	High		X		
[787]	5	High		X		
[788]	3	Not High				X
[789]	5	High		X		
[791]	5	High		X		
[796]	5	High		X		
[797]	3	Not High		X		
[798]	1	Not High		X		
[799]	5	High		X		
[802]	1	Not High			X	
[805]	1	Not High				X
[806]	1	Not High		X		
[807]	0	Not High				X
[813]	4	High			X	
[814]	5	High		X		

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 84 / 550

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[819]	2	Not High			X	
[820]	4	High		X		
[823]	4	High		X		
[829]	6	High	X			
[830]	5	High	X			
[831]	3	Not High		X		
[832]	5	High	X			
[838]	5	High		X		
[839]	4	High		X		
[843]	6	High		X		
[844]	4	High		X		
[845]	5	High		X		
[846]	0	Not High				X
[847]	6	High	X			
[849]	6	High	X			
[850]	3	Not High		X		
[859]	0	Not High				X
[868]	3	Not High			X	
[870]	3	Not High		X		
[872]	5	High		X		
[873]	2	Not High	X			
[874]	1	Not High				X
[875]	1	Not High			X	
[879]	1	Not High				X
[883]	5	High	X			
[884]	6	High	X			
[886]	1	Not High				X
[887]	5	High		X		
[889]	1	Not High	X			
[895]	2	Not High		X		
[896]	5	High		X		
[898]	2	Not High		X		
[900]	5	High			X	
[905]	6	High		X		
[906]	4	High		X		
[920]	2	Not High		X		
[921]	5	High		X		
[922]	6	High	X			
[923]	3	Not High		X		
[925]	1	Not High			X	
[934]	0	Not High				X
[935]	6	High		X		
[936]	5	High		X		
[937]	3	Not High		X		
[938]	4	High			X	
[939]	5	High		X		
[941]	0	Not High				X
[942]	1	Not High				X
[943]	0	Not High				X
[944]	5	High		X		

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 85 / 550

#Ref	Q-Index	Q-Index (Fuzzy)	OG1	OG2	OG3	OG4
[947]	6	High	X			
[949]	2	Not High		X		
[954]	6	High		X		
[955]	1	Not High				X
[960]	2	Not High		X		
[962]	0	Not High				X
[963]	4	High		X		
[968]	2	Not High				X
[971]	4	High		X		
[972]	1	Not High				X
[973]	3	Not High			X	
[974]	1	Not High			X	
[976]	5	High		X		
[978]	4	High	X			
[980]	5	High		X		

8.2 COMPILATION OF DATA FROM QUESTION Q2 ANSWERS

All C3 references were classified in at least one out of the non-mutually exclusive AI variants, ML categories, and AI and ML techniques listed as follows. The mapping of each C3 paper to them is presented in Table 18.

a) AI Variants:

- i. No explicit mention to AI (No AI);
- ii. AI in general (Gen. AI);
- iii. Machine Learning (ML) in general (Gen. AI);
- iv. ‘Classic AI’ search, game theory and evolutionary algorithms (Cl. AI);
- v. Knowledge-Based Probabilistic Models (KBPMs), such as Bayesian approaches, Kalman and Particle Filters, and Dempster-Shafer Theory);

b) ML categories:

- i. Supervised Learning (SL);
- ii. Unsupervised Learning (UL);
- iii. Reinforcement Learning (RL);
- iv. Deep Learning (DL);

c) Specific AI and ML techniques:

- i. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs);

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS							Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022			Revision 6	
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO				Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA			Page: 86 / 550				

- ii. Decision Trees (DTs) and Random Forests (RFs);
- iii. Support Vector Machines (SVMs).

Table 18: Data Compilation of Q2 Answers for Category C3 References

#Ref	Quality	Quality (Fuzzy)	No AI	Gen. AI	Gen. ML	Cl. AI	DL	RL	SL	UL	ANN	SVM	DT / RF	KBPM
[36]	6	High		X	X									
[46]	5	High		X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
[53]	6	High					X	X			X			
[54]	2	Not High	X											
[55]	5	High			X				X					
[56]	1	Not High	X											
[57]	6	High									X			
[58]	5	High		X	X						X			
[67]	2	Not High					X				X			
[70]	4	High		X	X									
[71]	6	High			X									
[73]	4	High			X									X
[80]	0	Not High			X				X					
[81]	4	High			X									X
[89]	4	High	X											
[92]	2	Not High					X				X			
[95]	1	Not High	X											
[98]	2	Not High									X			
[100]	1	Not High									X			X
[101]	1	Not High	X											
[104]	1	Not High						X						
[107]	3	Not High	X											
[115]	2	Not High					X	X						
[116]	3	Not High					X				X			
[117]	5	High			X									
[119]	4	High			X		X				X			X
[121]	2	Not High									X			
[131]	5	High					X	X			X			
[133]	5	High									X			
[134]	5	High			X						X			X
[139]	6	High		X	X									
[143]	1	Not High												X
[151]	4	High			X		X							X
[154]	2	Not High	X											
[156]	1	Not High			X									
[160]	0	Not High			X		X	X			X			
[161]	5	High			X		X				X			
[163]	2	Not High												X
[165]	1	Not High			X									
[166]	3	Not High		X	X			X						
[167]	6	High							X					
[170]	1	Not High		X										
[175]	5	High			X				X					
[180]	3	Not High									X			

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS								Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022			Revision 6	
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO				Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA				Page: 88 / 550				

#Ref	Quality	Quality (Fuzzy)	No AI	Gen. AI	Gen. ML	Cl. AI	DL	RL	SL	UL	ANN	SVM	DT / RF	KBPM
[297]	6	High									X			
[302]	1	Not High	X											
[306]	1	Not High	X											
[307]	0	Not High										X		
[318]	1	Not High	X											
[332]	1	Not High				X					X			X
[340]	1	Not High	X											
[347]	1	Not High	X											
[354]	1	Not High	X											
[358]	3	Not High				X							X	
[373]	5	High			X									
[390]	1	Not High	X											
[394]	0	Not High	X											
[396]	2	Not High									X			
[398]	1	Not High			X	X								
[399]	0	Not High	X											
[404]	0	Not High				X					X			
[419]	1	Not High	X											
[420]	1	Not High									X			
[433]	1	Not High				X								
[443]	0	Not High	X											
[445]	6	High									X			
[447]	6	High									X			
[453]	4	High									X			
[454]	6	High									X			
[455]	1	Not High	X											
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS								Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022			Revision 6	
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO				Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA				Page: 89 / 550				

#Ref	Quality	Quality (Fuzzy)	No AI	Gen. AI	Gen. ML	Cl. AI	DL	RL	SL	UL	ANN	SVM	DT / RF	KBPM
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS								Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022			Revision 6	
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO					Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA				Page: 91 / 550			

#Ref	Quality	Quality (Fuzzy)	No AI	Gen. AI	Gen. ML	Cl. AI	DL	RL	SL	UL	ANN	SVM	DT / RF	KBPM
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS								Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022			Revision 6	
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO				Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA				Page: 92 / 550				

#Ref	Quality	Quality (Fuzzy)	No AI	Gen. AI	Gen. ML	Cl. AI	DL	RL	SL	UL	ANN	SVM	DT / RF	KBPM
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[935]	6	High						X			X			X
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[971]	4	High			X						X			
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[976]	5	High									X			
[978]	4	High			X		X		X		X	X	X	X
[980]	5	High									X			

The graphs presented from Figure 8 to Figure 11, in turn, show how each of the techniques has been covered with time, spanning from 1994 onwards. The graphs present not only the absolute yearly publications mapped to the corresponding aforementioned AI groups, but also their yearly relative share.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 93 / 550	

Figure 8: Yearly Quantity of C3 Publications from 1994 onwards for each AI Variant, ML Category and AI and ML Technique

Figure 9: Proportion of Yearly C3 Publications 1994 onwards for each AI Variant, ML Category and AI and ML Technique

Figure 10: Yearly Quantity of C3 High Quality Publications 1994 onwards for each AI Variant, ML Category and AI and ML Technique

Figure 11: Proportion of Yearly C3 High Quality Publications 1994 onwards for each AI Variant, ML Category and AI and ML Technique

8.3 REFERENCE [36]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present a review to identify and assess initiatives and research relevant to the safety assurance of adaptive safety-critical systems which use machine learning, and to highlight assurance concepts that could benefit from future research;
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 95 / 550	

Q3 Answer	In order to leverage the developed to automated driving systems, the authors performed a review to identify relevant initiatives and research that could inform the development of safety assurance models for automated driving systems. Research includes several other application domains.
Q4 Answer	The authors presented current normative and technical remarks for the safety assurance of automated driving systems.
Q5 Answer	1) Further research on each of the identified concepts should be progressed. 2) No topics related to current regulatory frameworks and industry approaches to safety assurance have been included by the authors.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) The review is not systematic.

8.4 REFERENCE [46]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To clarify the following questions regarding AI safety: a) What is an AI paradigm and how does it affect the understanding and implications of the safety issue? b) Is AI safety research covering the most representative paradigms and the right combinations of paradigms with safety issues? c) Will current research directions in AI safety be able to anticipate more capable and powerful systems yet to come?
Q2 Answer	Two types of AI paradigms: conceptual artifacts and research techniques. A taxonomy of 10 AI conceptual artifacts and 14 research techniques is defined by the authors based on reference studies. There is no universally accepted definition of AI paradigm. Conceptual Artifact: Related to how a system with AI is conceived. Research Technique: Related to methods, algorithms and technical results and methodologies used when conceiving an AI-based system. Classification of artifacts and techniques allows identifying potential arising individual and interaction-caused safety issues. Criteria for defining AI techniques - see results on paper Table 1 (page 3/8): (0) Method: Detection of frequent keywords from AAAI/IJCAI conference and AI Topics data (1997-2017) to detect how safety research is distributed throughout AI techniques. (1) the techniques are sufficiently general to encompass groups of approaches in AI that have been recognized by other approaches (2) overlapping in the techniques is allowed, as there is a high degree of hybridization and combination in AI (3) subcategories are retained for particularly large categories, such as 'machine learning'. Criteria for defining AI artifacts - see results on paper Table 2 (page 4/8): (0) Method: Review of textbooks and historical accounts of AI to ensure greater conceptual stability than techniques and brainstorm of candidates among authors. (1) artifacts should ideally have minimum overlap, each capturing distinctive functionalities. (2) artifacts should be defined independently of how functionalities are achieved. (3) characterize each artifacts in terms of their integration with the external environment, in three ways: (3a) how it interfaces with the environment (e.g. via sensors and actuators, via digital objectives, or via language); (3b) the dynamics of this integration (whether it is interactive or functional); and (3c) the location of this integration (whether it is centralized, distributed, or coupled). Criteria for quantifying the occurrences of AI paradigms: Review of public domain research and media documents from AI Topics (1970-2017) to detect how safety research is distributed throughout AI techniques.
Q3 Answer	The study is not related to performing the safety analysis of AI, but to identifying potential safety issues of AI and mapping them to AI paradigms (techniques and artifacts). Initial discussion on typical safety analysis of AI: Analysis of specific risk or issue under a particular existing

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 96 / 550	

	<p>paradigm, such as interruptibility for reinforcement learning agents, adversarial attacks on deep learning systems, or fake media produced with GANs. Other risks have been ignored because they are outside of the current paradigm: for instance, attacks which go beyond an “independent” or functional interpretation of a neural network, and instead use the “information from previous frames to generate perturbations on later frames”.</p> <p>Method for identifying safety issues of AI: Identification of key terms in surveys, blogs and events in AI safety and clustering them into groups. 22 categories of safety issues were identified (see Table 3, page 7/8). The mapping among AI paradigms and safety issues is presented in Figure 4 (page 6/8). The proportion of safety issues related to each AI paradigm is extracted from AI Topics (2010-2018).</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Responses to Objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> See answers to Question 2; AI safety research is not sufficiently anticipatory, and is heavily weighted towards certain research paradigms. AI safety shall be more explicit about the artifacts and techniques for which a particular issue may be applicable, in order to identify gaps and cover a broader range of issues. <p>Other important results:</p> <p>Figure 3 - page 5/8:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Most frequent recent AI techniques for safety applications: neural networks, general machine learning (both increasing in proportion with time) and planning & scheduling (decreasing in proportion with time but still relevant). Most frequent recent AI artifacts: estimator, agents, creator (all increasing in proportion with time), extractor (nearly constant with time and relevant) and optimizer (decreasing in proportion with time but still relevant). Data suggests a five-year delay (approximately) between when a technique or artifacts becomes popular within general AI research, and when researchers begin to seriously consider the safety issues associated with it. Safety issues are considered reactively in response to dominant research patterns, and are only considered once a paradigm has been prominent for several years. <p>Figure 4 - page 6/8: Allows extracting the proportion of safety issues related to each AI paradigm is extracted from AI Topics (2010-2018).</p>
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Better exploration of the relationship among AI paradigms and safety issues (e.g. how does a safety issue arise from an AI paradigm?). Improve the analysis of the "Confinement problem" due to it being very recent (e.g. might be related to more AI paradigms than the ones identified by the authors). Improve awareness of the proposed AI taxonomy by AI deployers to ensure that the proper safety issues are addressed. The authors identified undetected safety issues stemming from misclassification of AI by deployers. Generalization of AI might lead to new safety issues - especially for machine-learning and agent paradigms. Better exploration of this is necessary, since most AI solutions are application and context-specific. Frequency quantification used within the study is based on number of publications rather than actual applications.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Good AI taxonomy for guiding the development of a safety analysis method for AI. "Confinement problem" (explainable AI with known and limited response) is deemed a recent topic with room for future research. --> Promising technique for the DSc. Generalization of AI safety also has room for future research --> Promising objective for the DSc. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Only AI Topics publications were considered by the authors. Many of the so-called safety issues are security-related instead of safety-related. This results from the own AI safety definition used by the authors. For them, {security} C {safety}. Improve filter of safety-related AI paradigms considering typical safety-critical applications (e.g. automatic transportation systems, healthcare systems, energy provision systems). This is to cover the limitation of Question 5 item "5".

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 97 / 550	

8.5 REFERENCE [53]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present the Neural Simplex Architecture (NSA), an approach to runtime assurance that provides safety guarantees for neural controllers (obtained e.g. using reinforcement learning) of autonomous and other complex systems without unduly sacrificing performance. NSA not only provides safety assurances in the presence of a possibly unsafe neural controller, but can also improve the safety of such a controller in an on line setting via retraining, without overly degrading its performance
Q2 Answer	Deep neural networks combined with reinforcement learning are employed to perform Safe Reinforcement Learning (SRL) within the NSA. SRL Algorithm: DDPG - Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients. DDPG is attractive as it works with deterministic policies, and allows uncorrelated samples to be added to the pool of samples for training or retraining. The latter property is important because it allows to collect disconnected samples of what the NC would do while the plant is under the BC's control, and to use these samples for online retraining of the NC. Supervised learning of the NC with the BC action is not used because the NC would tend to mimic the BC, hence reducing performance.
Q3 Answer	See article's Figure 1 for details on the architecture for safety assurance of an NSA-based system. Basically, a precertified decision module (DM) monitors the output of two controllers - a DNN-based neural controller (NC) and a non AI-based, less efficient and precertified baseline controller (BC). If the decision module detects that the AC generates improper control inputs for it, it switches to the BC until the AC is recovered Its recovery is based on retraining, performed by an uncertified Adaptation Module (AM) while the BC operates. This is performed in such a way that the AM collects online operational data and retrains the NC to the current context - hence avoiding the need for significant initial coverage of the NC in complex scenarios in which this is unfeasible prior to the system operation in a real scenario. When an unsafe situation is detected by the DM, it is informed to the AM so that it trains the NC to avoid this scenario by attaching to it a large negative reward. The recoverable actions by the BC are not used to train the NC while the BC operates --> Safe Reinforcement Learning with Penalized Unrecoverable Continuous Actions (SRL-PUA). The threshold for reverse switching (BC to NC) is more restrictive than the one for forward switching (NC to BC) for two reasons: improve safety and reduce the frequency of switching (NC will be farther from the NC-BC boundary when enabled). Two case studies are considered: a neural controller for a target-seeking rover navigating through an obstacle field and a neural controller for an artificial pancreas.
Q4 Answer	1) It has been observed that retaining the initial training samples of the NC and adding a random exploration noise in all retrainings that were needed during the operation led to better stability and convergence of the updated safe policies. 2) SRL-PUA has been checked as more effective than SRL-BC (when BC recoverable actions are used to retrain the NC while it does not operate) in such a way that an SRL-PUA does not reach an unsafe (unrecoverable) state after some training (i.e., it could be safe on its own under no failure scenario). 3) Both case studies are simulated and reinforce the previous results: a) For the target-seeking rover, online training of the NC following an SRL-PUA approach reduced potential collisions with random obstacles; b) For the artificial pancreas, online training of the NC following an SRL-PUA approach minimized both unsafe scenarios (hyperglycemia caused by not activating the insulin pump when it should and hypoglycemia caused by activating the insulin pump when it should not). Note: in the examples, hypoglycemia has a stricter threshold for being detected as unsafe than hyperglycemia because its effects are worse for the patient than hyperglycemia; moreover, there is no control action to recover from hypoglycemia, since no glucagon pump is considered in the example to circumvent this issue. 4) It is argued that the approach is valid for systems with discrete, continuous and stochastic state spaces. Increasing computational cost may be an issue especially with continuous and stochastic systems.
Q5 Answer	1) Improve the statistic quantification of retraining need for safe operation of the NC. 2) Incorporate behaviors stemming from failures of the controlled system.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) The NSA is an example of a composite fail-safe design in which the safety-critical AI (NC + AM) is

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 98 / 550	

	<p>restrained by deterministic, non-AI-based modules (BC + DM) in order to ensure that the system is safe. Hence, if the non-AI-based modules meet the system safety target on their own, the AI is no longer safety-critical.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Thresholds for DM switching between BC and NC and vice-versa may be difficult to design, since they depend on the application and on other design decisions (e.g. safety-related SW routines periodicity) in order to prevent a late switching to the BC when an unsafe NC pattern starts being recognized by the DM.</p> <p>2) A well-trained NC with SRL-PUA can behave safely on its own in regular operational conditions (i.e., in the absence of failures). No failure analysis has been considered by the authors.</p> <p>3) Case studies are only simulated.</p> <p>4) Increasing computational cost for the NC and AM may be an issue especially with continuous and stochastic systems due to their complexity.</p>
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8.6 REFERENCE [54]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	Presenting and discussing how to address modularity and dynamicity when demonstrating that Adaptive Systems of Systems (SoS) are safe.
Q2 Answer	Even though the paper is not related to AI, its scope comprises adaptive systems. Since adaptiveness can be performed with AI, it is considered that the research can be useful for the safety analysis of AI-based systems. Please refer to Question 2 for how AI is considered in the research.
Q3 Answer	The research starts presenting two Safety Case approaches to address the modularity and the dynamicity of Adaptive SoS: the Modular Safety Case (MSC) and the Dynamic Safety Case (DSC). Their advantages and disadvantages are discussed, as well as which safety-related issues would not be addressed by simply joining both types of Safety Cases.
Q4 Answer	<p>MSC - All system components proven as independent from others are demonstrated as safe in their own safety case. If such a component is changed, only its own safety case has to be updated (i.e., the SoS safety case remains unchanged if the changed component is proven as safe in its own safety case). In order to avoid many components - and, hence, many safety cases - it is wise to choose as modules only components which are foreseen as dynamic during the SoS lifecycle.</p> <p>MSC does not adaptive SoS whose configurations are dynamically designed and configured by the SoS itself (i.e. unconstrained during design). In order to cover this scenario, DSC were conceived.</p> <p>DSC - Safety cases are continuously updated with operational data extracted from a safety management system related to an adaptive SoS in order to ensure that the safety demonstration arguments are continuously evolving. It has three main principles:</p> <p>a) Computing the confidence in and updating the reasoning about safety arguments;</p> <p>b) Formally identifying the dynamic relationships among the components of a system to support automated analyses;</p> <p>c) Allow generalizing from the notion of a standalone argument to a partially evolved argument with open tasks assigned to various stakeholders.</p> <p>The safety management system plays an important role in the safety demonstration, since any lack of confidence on the data it provides (frequency and consistency) can undermine the demonstration that an adaptive SoS is safe with a DSC. However, the DSC lacks the modularization of the MSC.</p> <p>In order to circumvent this, a Dynamic Modular Safety Case (DMSC) is proposed by the authors with the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dynamic Monitoring to identify the changing modules of the system; - Runtime analysis to identify how changes are propagated through the system and the effects of these propagated changes; - Automation of MSC Generation and Updates, in order to dynamically address the safety demonstration of the system modules (including new and changed modules due to the system adaptation). "Contracts" between each

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 99 / 550	

	relating system of a SoS would be identified and, in case any changes occur with a component, the MSC of all components involved in contracts with the changed component would be updated.
Q5 Answer	All DMSC concepts have not been operationalized yet. There is no evidence that they are feasible.
Q6 Answer	Apart from the results presented in Questions 4 and 5, it is emphasized that this paper is not directly related to safety analysis of AI. It was considered as part of the SLR Category 3 because, since adaptiveness can be performed with AI, it is considered that the research can be useful for the safety analysis of AI-based systems.

8.7 REFERENCE [55]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To develop the blocking points that arise for the adoption of AI technologies for functions involving safety and to propose a paradigm shift for the demonstration of safety, in a framework where a formal demonstration is no longer possible, with two methods “proven in use” and not absolute but sufficient.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, but leaning towards Supervised Learning based on the case study contextualization.
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: " (...) <i>AI applications are little used in the railway domain, and are not, up to now, concerned by safety. There are several major obstacles for that: difficulties in safety demonstration, difficulties for elaborate methods associated with these technological developments compatible with the state of the art of the railway, including in particular the railway standards EN 50126, 50128, 50129, difficulties to prove the “GAME” performance.</i>"</p> <p>Main questions answered by the research: " <i>What are the validation means and techniques that would allow systems to be addressed satisfactorily even if there is no guaranteed and reproducible behaviors? Are we able to know, appreciate and identify the limits of the demonstration of safety on such systems? Finally, can we still speak of “safety level” like we do on existing systems, and if so, under what conditions?</i>"</p> <p>Specifically for the AI-related parts of the study, the following claims are presented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>"Machine learning techniques are used precisely in cases where there is no formal specification of the objects to be detected but simply examples of such objects. The validation of these products is not established from a specification (but only through consistency with an expected performance specification";</i> - <i>Failure modes of supervised learning: Incorrect labeling of training samples caused by "(...) forgetfulness, confusion, recording errors, incompleteness, erroneous manual acceptance of an image, sample not sufficiently representative, and on the contrary image surplus (e.g. poorly oriented treatment of related picture elements that were actually unrelated to a signal ..), environment in front of the train which evolves relatively to the environment considered for learning (brighter, darker, snow, rain, a new building etc.), particular lighting, position in the metro line, etc. which do not permit identification of panels, or particular shapes of panels".</i> - <i>List of issues for the safety validation of ML-based algorithms:</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) <i>"At the end of the test phase, the model does not provide any guarantee as to its future detection rate on new or unseen images. Only the actual onsite test can confirm the empirical estimate of such a detection rate."</i> b) <i>"A Machine Learning algorithm or Computer Vision is evaluated only through its empirical performance and general models (or algorithms) are too complex to be inspected and possibly corrected in case of prediction error."</i> c) <i>"This model is trained by minimizing a global error: it can therefore be mistaken on many examples and still display a performance which seems good."</i> d) <i>"Uncertainty would be computable by unusual methods introducing credible intervals in the Bayesian sense. These more rigorous methods are complex in detection applications (Bayesian neural networks), they are extremely computational and often rely on nondeterministic algorithms (Monte Carlo Markov Chain in particular): they have not reached a sufficient level of maturity to be integrated into critical systems."</i> e) <i>"Deep learning has the particularity of being able to establish erroneous correlations without anyone knowing which one."</i> - <i>"The final challenge (or even major incompatibility) with EN 50128 is the separation between the data and the software. Machine learning and computer vision algorithms build their internal parameters using data. Conventional notions associated with generic software, application and specific software (=software with parameters) are no longer applicable."</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 100 / 550	

	<p>Proposed Solutions for ML in Safety Functions:</p> <p>a) Using redundant non-AI-based solutions (e.g. LIDAR for detecting the location of signals);</p> <p>b) Double labeling (by two different operators) and double ML validation. A third person would analyze and correct the discrepancies;</p> <p>c) Training data shall be able to cover all the possible scenarios for the performed, and the model shall be able to detect situations which are not covered by these data (e.g. by learning with data collected during operation);</p> <p>d) Majority voting of multiple input sensors (e.g. temporal redundancy for video);</p> <p>e) Random failures: "<i>Classical RAMS techniques are applicable to address the random failures</i>";</p> <p>f) Reducing SIL thresholds only for requirements apportionment (not changed for systematic failures);</p> <p>g) Considering machine learning development suites and libraries as T3 tools, with the weights of the ML model being the configuration data. Moreover, consider them as 'dual channel' (i.e., using two different sets of tools);</p> <p>h) Demonstration replaced by sufficiency: if given situations are well considered by the ML system, it is possible to justify by the use - for a given learning – a satisfactory capacity to perform a function (<i>proven-in-use</i>).</p> <p>i) To reach a level of confidence about safety, "<i>(...) we must rely on an enough commitment means: definition as exhaustive as possible of the environmental conditions in operation (to establish a learning base), definition what we did not see during the learning (for example: circulation outdoor in the snow) and thus clarify the ODD (Operational Design Domain). With ODD it is possible to add a function which detects if the real conditions are in or out the "Definition Domain (DOD)". "The commitment on result is established on the basis of onsite observations: onsite experimentation with a maximum coverage of external conditions with forecast of a continuous learning process which aims to take into account the errors of the algorithms during the operation to improve them (enrich the learning base), simultaneously enhance learning and apply a reliability growth model."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	The method presented by the authors is discussed for the application of automatic signal recognition by a train. Please refer to Question 3 answers for the most important results.
Q5 Answer	" <i>Onsite experimentation is now necessary to master the safety - reliability compatibility with regard to false negatives and false positives. We must evaluate the relationship between the number of images to be processed to obtain a result with vote and interpretation errors, perception distances, impact of external conditions, response time, effects of consistency tests. All these elements can't be modeled and are not predictable.</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization within the rail domain. 2) Interesting solutions for some of the raised points (e.g. random faults, redundancy). <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of a detailed study showing that the method is sound. The method was created only by means of 'best practices'. 2) Some of the solutions for the raised issues seem simplistic (e.g. reducing SIL thresholds for AI).

8.8 REFERENCE [56]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a Systematic Literature Review on V&V and Safety Assurance of Self-Driving Autonomous Vehicles (at least SAE level 4; SAE level 3 for some specific scenarios).
Q2 Answer	No explicit mention to AI has been identified except for a reference to an AI-related SLR on Autonomous Vehicles (Nascimento et al. (2019)).
Q3 Answer	Despite Self-Driving Autonomous Vehicles may feature AI for safety-related functions, the research does not directly cover AI. V&V and safety assurance have been covered from a qualitative point of view as part of the SLR and both topics are mainly related to testing procedures.
Q4 Answer	An SLR for V&V and Safety Assurance of Self-Driving Autonomous Vehicles has been performed with the identification of bibliometrics results (research centers and result distributions with time), test coverage criteria (scenario, situation or requirements), test coverage maximization techniques (High Throughput Testing - HTT, reinforcement learning, Search-Based Software Testing- SBST and pseudorandom generation) and test setup (simulation and HW).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 101 / 550	

Q5 Answer	1) The terminology for V&V and safety assurance of Self-Driving Autonomous system is not homogeneous; 2) Few techniques for coverage maximization and test setup were identified; 3) Studies feature quality issues.
Q6 Answer	1) The paper has little relevance for the research due to its simplicity and non-meaningful resources; 2) Information regarding the identified V&V and safety assurance techniques can be considered as reference for future research, as identified by the authors themselves, for further refinements of existing techniques and creation of new techniques.

8.9 REFERENCE [57]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	Define and exercise with a case study a process that integrates the development and assurance activities for Machine Learnt Models (MLMs) within safety-related systems. The focus is on the systematic elicitation, traceability and analysis of ML safety requirements throughout the system lifecycle, especially on how these requirements should drive safety assurance within the data management and model learning phases. The case study is for self-driving vehicles to detect pedestrians at crossings.
Q2 Answer	The safety analysis method is deemed applicable to machine learning techniques in general. The case study focuses on two AI techniques: - Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) - SqueezeNet implementation - Region Proposal Networks (RPN).
Q3 Answer	The main idea of the research is that machine learning-based safety critical systems shall feature safety requirements that will govern the machine learning training project (including design and verification activities). The ML lifecycle is split up into five phases: requirements elicitation, data management, model learning, model verification and model deployment. After proper measures are carried out in all these steps, the learnt model shall be acceptably safe when integrated into the system. To ensure that each lifecycle stage provides sufficient evidence for safety arguments, a set of desired properties (desiderata) shall be defined for each stage, in such a way that ML safety requirement are derived from the system requirements based on the chosen ML desiderata of each of the lifecycle five aforementioned stages. Safety requirements shall be defined considering desiderata related to relevance, completeness, accuracy and balance, as derived from a study published by Ashmore, Calinescu and Paterson (2019). - Relevance: specify which safety-related data is important to ensure safety (e.g. data for each situation category that shall be recognized by the system). Aside from the data types themselves, features that influence data (e.g. sensor position and technological characteristics) shall also be included (e.g. sensors influence the data they produce due to distortions introduced by their technological limitations and on where they are positioned within the system). - Completeness: specify which variations on data are needed to ensure proper coverage of all situation categories within the context of operation (e.g. differences in lighting, weather and target shapes and colors, including variations with the distance between sensors and the targets). Requirements related to system operation with wear (e.g. scratched and opaque camera lenses) and faults shall also be taken into account. - Accuracy: specify performance marks that ensure that the quality of the data labeling performed by the AI reach is sufficient (e.g. by comparing how many results of the AI were properly labeled as per data which is known to be within a certain category). Performance and safety shall be balanced. - Balance: Training data shall comprise all plausible classification scenarios as balanced as possible with their actual occurrence within the real world, so as to avoid over and under representation of a category for the system. This would increase errors in detecting that scenario, as well as tolerances within the actual scenario recognition.
Q4 Answer	The safety analysis technique developed by the authors is exercised with a pedestrian crossing detection subsystem, which can be part of a self-driving autonomous vehicle so that the vehicle safely stops when a pedestrian crosses the street. The case study is structured in the following steps: 1) Context of Operation: It defines the boundaries for the system operation, excluding occasional scenarios in which the automated system is forbidden to operate (e.g., snow, night) in order to simplify the input space. They can be defined based on classes of equivalence or formal de facto definitions (ontologies). 2) Components Safety Requirements Definition: System-level safety requirements are refined and mapped into low-level safety requirements up to the system components. These requirements will be the input for the ML requirements elicitation and the forthcoming steps of the ML safety lifecycle (data management, model learning, model verification and model deployment).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 102 / 550	

	<p>3) ML Requirements Elicitation: The case study focused on defining requirements for only two of the ML safety lifecycle steps: data management and model learning.</p> <p>4) ML Requirements Safety Verification: A prototyped object detection system conceived and trained with the JAAD dataset was verified in order to evaluate and justify whether the safety requirements defined in step "3" were fulfilled. This analysis led to the result that most relevance-related requirements and all completeness, accuracy and balance requirements are not fulfilled by the JAAD dataset and that public datasets can be useful for an exploratory analysis in order to refine the requirements.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) Need for future development of the safety analysis method for further steps of safety-critical ML lifecycle (model verification and model deployment).</p> <p>2) Establishing formal contract-based relationships among safety requirements of diverse steps of the system lifecycle to support automated refinement checks.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) This is another study that reinforces that "AI aims to improve system performance while not degrading safety".</p> <p>2) Good contextualization for self-driving autonomous cars current context: "Within the automotive domain, established safety standards such as ISO26262 do not consider MLs. Traditional testing methods and test coverage metrics used for safety-related software, such as Modified Condition Decision Coverage, are not applicable to Neural Networks."</p> <p>3) At least two interesting references for future analysis: - Ashmore et al. (2019) for desiderata (desired properties) at each development step; - Cheng et al. (2018) for safety analysis of Neural Networks.</p> <p>4) Good contextualization within a safety-critical system lifecycle (V cycle).</p> <p>5) Interesting result about public databases for ML design: "public datasets can be useful for an exploratory analysis in order to refine the requirements", but they are not likely to fulfill the safety requirements needed for a safety-critical system unless conceived bearing this in mind.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The paper highlights that some ML safety requirements make it "less likely to produce models which fail to perform appropriately in the real world". As a result, there is still a chance for ML systems to behave inappropriately (i.e. unsafely) even if adequate ML safety requirements are defined and validated. This is not discussed by the authors, but it remains as a valid question for AI-based safety-related developments.</p>

8.10 REFERENCE [58]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present an introductory overview of future evolution of AI and reliability on autonomous safety-critical systems used in ground and air transportation applications.
Q2 Answer	Parts of the research were carried out for general AI, whereas some are applicable to machine learning techniques. Special focus is given to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) due to their more frequent usage in safety-critical systems due to performance features.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors present "<i>a non-comprehensive but representative list</i>" of parameters that influence safety (and reliability) of machine learning-based systems. The parameters are grouped as follows:</p> <p>a) Deployment Context</p> <p>(i.) SAE Level 5 autonomous driving is open context - context cannot be fully determined, and reuse of solutions applicable to the contexts may be troublesome.</p> <p>(ii.) Autonomous driving system mission time</p> <p>(iii.) System misuse (out of context)</p> <p>b) Systematic faults</p> <p>(i.) Mismatch between training data and real context (completeness, generalization and lack of bias)</p> <p>(ii.) Performance requirements and complexity tradeoff. Examples: - ML architecture increases HW complexity which, in turn, increases the system portions that are safety-critical;</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 103 / 550	

	<p>- Power consumption and response time reduce the robustness of the ML algorithm.</p> <p>(iii.) Framework impact over safety. Example: Effects of middleware, operating system, model optimizer and third-party libraries over safety.</p> <p>(iv.) Unclear validation target: System shall be validated by ensuring that the coverage of the implementation meets the system requirements under real deployment context.</p> <p>c) HW faults (hard/permanent and soft/transient faults):</p> <p>(i.) Soft errors triggering safety-critical failures</p> <p>(ii.) Hard errors modifying neural network architecture and/or parameters</p> <p>(iii.) Aging and process disfunction.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>1) Main challenges for AI in safety-critical systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Categorizing information for detecting something; - Strong dependence to data training quality; - Dealing with the "unknown unknowns" (i.e., how to make a ML-based algorithm deal with data that is known to be missing on input data). - Not fully clear how to test and validate AI-based systems. <p>2) Definition of a list of parameters that influence safety of machine learning-based systems.</p> <p>3) According to the authors (no other source provided), soft errors are the most critical when implementing Systems on Chip (SOCs). As a result, safety assurance depends on demonstrating a sufficiently low Soft Errors Rate (SER). SER comprises three rates:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Architectural Vulnerability Factor (AVF): Safety-critical fault probability resulting from microarchitecture and workload; - Timing Vulnerability Factor (TVF): Safety-critical fault probability resulting from workload, clocking and circuit dynamic behavior; - Program Vulnerability Factor (PVF): Safety-critical fault probability resulting from the observable machine learning. <p>4) According to the authors (no other source provided), autonomous vehicles systems tend to have stricter reliability and safety requirements than non-autonomous vehicles systems due to longer mission times which make them more subject to environmental conditions that accelerate wear. COTS usage may also be more restricted due to the stricter safety requirements.</p> <p>5) According to the authors (no other source provided), ML safety is more dependent on input data quality than on ML algorithm implementation.</p> <p>6) Convolutional Neural Networks tend to be more used due to better performance than other ML counterparts. Most of its quality settings are decided during design and training time. Some ways to deal with CNN in safety applications: <i>"plausibility checks that correlate the output of a CNN to additional sensor information from the environment using, for instance, information for a single sensor, several overlapping sensors of the same type or multi-modal sensor input"</i>. Detecting anomalies on safety-critical CNNs can be dealt in the following ways: monitoring environment sensors which can only lead to a detection of environmental conditions that were not well covered during training, monitoring the underlying systems for faults that could influence the CNN and monitoring the behavior of the CNN itself (white box approach) detecting outliers using probabilistic methods.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Improve on the discussion of the main topics of the research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New workloads for SER and functional safety, focusing especially on transient analysis based on AI and deep learning workloads; - Reliability and safety implications due to long mission times, especially when highly dense and smaller electronic devices are used; - Additional architecture considerations for CNNs can help ensuring safety for hardware, learning and newly emerging significant failure classes like "unknown unknowns".
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) This is another study that reinforces that "AI aims to improve system performance while not degrading safety".</p> <p>2) Interesting point of view (parts in bold are fundamental for the statement to be valid - "right" data should meet safety requirements as specified. e.g., in [55]): <i>"AI based systems are capable of living up to the</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 104 / 550	

	<p><i>promise of making more accurate and faster decisions compared to humans, given the right data, thereby resulting in significantly improved safety".</i></p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) According to the authors (no other source provided), ML safety is more dependent on input data quality than on ML algorithm implementation. The importance of input data is clear, but it is debatable to argue that ML algorithms have less impact on safety.</p>
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8.11 REFERENCE [67]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present flight test validation and verification of a neural network longitudinal controller for a fixed-wing unmanned aerial system (UAS) that is trained offline via reinforcement learning using Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients (DDPG) learning algorithm.
Q2 Answer	Deep Neural Networks / Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients.
Q3 Answer	Basics: "A neural network longitudinal controller is developed using a physics-based linear time invariant (LTI) model of an aircraft which is often an imperfect representation of aircraft dynamics. Reinforcement Learning (RL) provides a set of algorithms through which an artificial neural network (ANN) can be trained to behave as a flight controller policy that may provide robust flight performance and more generalization capabilities as compared to traditional standard controllers". "A secondary and conventional LQR (Linear Quadratic Regulator) autopilot system was integrated as a part of the system architecture. A safety-critical monitor continuously checks the ANN control values and the corresponding predicted UAS states, if they are within the envelope protection limits, and switches aircraft control to the conventional and deterministic LQR autopilot system if needed. This safety monitor will allow the ANN to operate as long as it remains inside a predefined safety zone."
Q4 Answer	The authors presented the application of their controller, including the DNN trained by RL the LQR controller and the safety monitor which switches between them, on two situations: hardware-in-the-loop tests and physical tests with a quadcopter. The results were positive, and, from a safety point of view, "it was shown that the switch makes smooth transitions from ANN to LQR in validation & verification flight tests."
Q5 Answer	"We aim to extend successful RL algorithms from the application to rotary-wing aircraft to fixed-wing aircraft."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good contextualization of Reinforcement Learning and Deep Learning as complementary ML methods for a robust solution: "The revival of RL for control and the new excitement for this work comes from the use of deep neural networks as the policy learning agent". Weakness: 1) ML is not safety-critical within the proposed system, since a safety monitors switches the control to a deterministic, non-ML-related controller in case the ML controller violates the safety envelope.

8.12 REFERENCE [70]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present an operational safety verification technique based on hybrid system mining from inputs and output of a deployed AI-based cyber-physical systems. The hybrid system mining is an example of a hybrid automaton model, which is known for allowing formal safety verification of AI-based systems despite the 'no oracle problem' (i.e., lack of reference result for a machine learning problem). The conceived safety verification model is exercised with an artificial pancreas case study.
Q2 Answer	The authors argue that the safety analysis approach is valid for any AI technique; nevertheless, some parts of the paper suggest that machine-learning-related techniques are deemed as the main beneficiaries of the authors' safety analysis approach.
Q3 Answer	The objective of the safety analysis method proposed by the authors is "to ascertain that the safety verification results learned using traces collected from real-world operation of the AI-enabled CPS are consistent with formal or simulated safety verification results" "in a proactive manner" while the system

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 105 / 550	

	<p>operates by applying "reachability analysis over a learned hybrid automaton to verify the safety of the operational AI-enabled CPS"</p> <p>After an AI-based safety-critical system is initially deployed (e.g. for testing purposes), input and output data are collected in such a way to infer whether the system operates as initially specified (e.g. "with regard to the number of modes, flow dynamics, modes transitions, guard conditions, or reset conditions"). This verification is called a conformance test. If inconsistencies are detected (i.e. if the conformance test fails), it is assumed that "there might be a significant change in the initial safety conclusions", meaning that the safety arguments are likely to be undermined.</p> <p>Important Note: The safety analysis method is related to "operational safety", which is defined by the authors as "ensuring that the operation of the AI enabled CPS in the field does not deviate from the safe certified design of the system".</p>
Q4 Answer	The safety analysis method was exercised with a simulated artificial pancreas case study that bases the design of real artificial pancreases and practical input and output data of artificial pancreases provided by MayoClinic. In this case study, the artificial pancreas features an insulin pump whose control shall prevent long-term hyperglycemia and any acute hypoglycemia occurrences.
Q5 Answer	<p>1) "With insufficient I/O traces, the learned hybrid automaton will be an underapproximate representation of the reference specifications model. In this case, the manufacturer should provide complete traces to accomplish the mining process."</p> <p>2) A root cause analysis of Ai issues within the analyzed system by using the learned HA model is indicated by the authors as one of the future research topics.</p> <p>3) "Another direction for improvement is how to decide what is the reasonable period of time to mine again another automaton for periodic safety verification of operational AI-enabled CPS".</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Useful contextualization for the difficulty in ensuring that an AI-based safety-critical system is safe: - "operational components interaction circumstances, inclusion of human-in-the loop, and environmental changes in AI-enabled CPS make formal safety verification a very challenging task". - "formal methods (...) may fall short for AI-Enabled CPS, where complete formal verification models are often unavailable". - This dissonance between "what the system is designed to do", "what the operator thinks the system is doing", and "what the system is actually doing" is an important problem (McDermid, Jia, and Habli 2019).</p> <p>2) Good "no oracle" contextualization with an example of artificial pancreas: the amount of insulin to be released by a pump depends on factors such as the person's mood, meal patterns and physical activities, which are difficult to be predicted when conceiving a machine learning-based system.</p> <p>3) Very interesting conclusion: safety analyses of AI-based systems may need periodic updates to accommodate occasional changes to the learned patterns.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Since the safety analysis method is related to ensuring "operational safety", it seems unlikely (and maybe unfeasible) for their method to be used to evaluate AI failure modes within an AI-based safety-critical systems. It does not seem feasible to exercise many system failures and assess whether the degraded / failed AI operates safely (as specified) by collecting inputs and outputs generated during the system operation for all plausible failure modes.</p> <p>2) The safety analysis method requires that the system under analysis is specified by means of an hybrid automaton. If this is not possible, the authors indicate that it is feasible to perform AI-based transformation of other types of specifications (e.g. SysML-based ones) into hybrid automata. This includes another layer of possible issues during the safety analysis, given that hybrid automata are not widely used, and the specification translator may themselves introduce errors into the system specification employed as part of the safety analysis method.</p> <p>3) The inference of system behavior from its inputs and outputs, performed as part of the safety analysis, also uses AI. Hence, if such an AI is not shown to be sufficiently safe, the results of the safety analysis can also be questioned.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 106 / 550	

8.13 REFERENCE [71]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	<p>To present means to analyze and understand the contribution of the machine learning software elements to safety, and to assure that those contributions have been appropriately managed. This is carried out in the following ways, aiming to automated safety analysis of ML-based cyber and cyber-physical systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introducing the notion of hazard contribution modes (HCMs) to categorize the ways in which the ML elements can contribute to hazardous system states; - Describing how argumentation patterns can capture the reasoning that can be used to assure HCM mitigation.
Q2 Answer	The safety analysis is valid for any machine learning technique regardless of the learning scheme.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "The difficulty of assuring ML safety is due to two differences between an ML algorithm and a traditional software component.</p> <p>(i.) The problems to which ML algorithms are applied are often difficult if not impossible to specify. This condition is often by design—if it were possible to write a specification for a problem, an ML algorithm might not be necessary or useful in the first place.</p> <p>(ii.) ML algorithms and their internal logic are often not interpretable by humans, complicating their oversight. This difficulty of assuring LEC safety presents a gap in the safety assurance practice."</p> <p>Safety Analysis Method: Each ML element has their own Hazard Contribution Modes (HCMs), which are classified according to the result it produces (expected or unexpected) and to its accuracy (accurate or with error). The authors present and justify that there are several similarities between Expected Accurate (EA) and Unexpected Accurate (UA) HCMs, as well as between Expected with Error (EE) and Unexpected with Error (UE) HCMs, meaning that similar countermeasures for safety assurance for each of the two "equivalence classes" are raised.</p> <p>Accuracy: Optimal outputs (e.g. correct classification, near-exact regression, or reward maximizing actions in reinforcement learning). Requires reference data for comparison.</p> <p>Error: Divergence between LEC outputs and the reference values (e.g. ground truth if available for supervised learning, optimal values produced according to the loss, cost, or objective functions of the optimization algorithm for reinforcement learning).</p> <p>Error in supervised learning emerges from a combination of model assumptions (bias), the type and quantity of data used (variance), and noise. In unsupervised learning, error may emerge from an inadequately specified optimization objective (approximation error), model parameter choices that complicate differentiation between distinct inputs (identification error), inadequate data (estimation error), and algorithmic insufficiencies (optimization error) (Liang and Klein 2008).</p> <p>Error thresholds define safety, accuracy and operational acceptability (with regards to functional requirements not safety-related). It is plausible to generate outputs that are (i.) safe, accurate and operationally acceptable, (ii.) safe, inaccurate and operationally acceptable, (iii.) unsafe, accurate and operationally acceptable, (iv.) unsafe, inaccurate and operationally acceptable, and (v.) unsafe, inaccurate and operationally unacceptable.</p> <p>Applying the HCM categories can be viewed as a bottom-up analysis similar to an FMEA. However, HCMs are different than failure modes since not all failure modes are hazardous, whereas all HCMs are by definition. They are also broader than failure modes because they include non-failing outputs that can be hazardous. To the authors, "HCMs would be used alongside, rather than as a replacement, for FMEA".</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>No case studies or practical applications have been presented by the authors; instead, they define the safety analysis method with the Goal Structuring Notation (GSN) and compare and contrast their method with other methods published by other researchers.</p> <p>Given that the main result of the study is the safety analysis method itself, its main guidelines are herein presented:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "Assurance of acceptably mitigating the EA and UA modes can be provided, in part, through evidence of a combination of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – sufficiently reflecting in the training and validation data, all known and identified conditions that are both known hazard precursors and that can be associated to functions allocated to ML components; – penalizing the relevant hazard precursors in the loss, cost, or objective functions of the optimization

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 107 / 550	

	<p>algorithms used, e.g., as parameterized variables of a regularization term added to a loss function. Contextually relevant robustness testing of the ML components can then provide additional evidence assuring that the revised objective functions are suitable to reduce the occurrence of the EA mode;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – comprehensive model testing and verification-based coverage of the identified precursor conditions of the hazards induced by the EA mode." <p>2) "To provide assurance that the EE and UE modes have been acceptably managed, requiring evidence of at least a combination of the following can be useful:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – valid safety thresholds (or bounds) associated with the ML components outputs, derived from system-level safety bounds (or a specification of the safety envelope and associated conditions); – adequately reflecting the ML components specific safety thresholds in the training and validation data; – appropriately reflecting the LEC specific safety thresholds in the loss, cost, or objective functions of the optimization algorithms used. Reflecting appropriateness of the ML algorithms, in turn, relates to demonstrating that they are performant and robust, with the proviso that these assurance properties account for the applicable safety thresholds; – comprehensive model testing and verification that considers error performance in relation to the relevant safety thresholds." <p>3) Items "1)" and "2)" aim to "reduce the opportunities for the EA and EE modes to occur in operation" and to "prevent the runtime occurrence of the UA and UE modes". "To additionally assure that the particular causes of the UA and UE modes have been managed, assurance mechanisms can additionally focus on gathering evidence of a combination of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – comprehensive definition of the operating environment, and the system context, e.g., by leveraging a rich specification of the operating constraints for the system; – sufficiency of the training and validation data, that is assurable through evidence that the data used are relevant, balanced, complete, and accurate. – model validation techniques that are comprehensive and contextually relevant." <p>4) "A layered [architecture] approach is prudent, including architectural mechanisms to reduce or mask the impact of the HCM", e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – runtime monitoring for detection of LEC outputs that violate the applicable safety bounds, – fail-safe/failure tolerance mechanisms that disengage hazardous LEC outputs, or the entire LEC as appropriate, by leveraging assurance measures that provide a quantified notion of confidence in specific LEC assurance properties; – using redundant and sufficiently diverse implementations of the functions that LECs implement, along with runtime monitors for detecting function disagreement."
<p>Q5 Answer</p>	<p>1) Neither the list of HCM presented by the authors nor the mitigation methods are comprehensive, meaning that there might be other HCMs and mitigation measures to be taken into account. For HCMs, the authors suggest, among other references, that Ashmore et al. (2019) is the most promising reference for this so far. For mitigation measures, no reference is indicated.</p> <p>2) The safety analysis arguments presented by the authors with the GSN notation does not take into account potential safety issues stemming from interaction of a ML component with other components (ML-based or not).</p> <p>3) "Safety effects of HCMs cannot be generalized, since details about the specific LEC, its interfaces to the wider system, the system itself, and its operating context are necessary."</p> <p>4) Possible yet unexplored integration with automated safety analysis tools (e.g. AdvocATE).</p> <p>5) Pending refinement of high-level HCMs high-level evidence requirements into lower-level ones that can be linked to objective quality evidence.</p>
<p>Q6 Answer</p>	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) This is another study that reinforces that "AI aims to improve system performance while not degrading safety" with the idea of surrounding AI with a "safety envelope" for its outputs, hence limiting the AI output error which retains the system's safe behavior.</p> <p>2) Sound method for bottom-up analysis during V&V activities which includes the analysis of system faults.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 108 / 550	

	<p>The method allows collecting evidence to build and/or undermine safety arguments.</p> <p>3) Possibility for integration with automated safety analysis tools.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Lacking the analysis of interfaces among system components and with the environment.</p> <p>2) Lacking contextualization with top-down safety analysis in order to map the elicited safety requirements into the evidence built with the proposed bottom-up method.</p> <p>3) No comprehensive list of HCMs and mitigations.</p>
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8.14 REFERENCE [73]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To allow run-time stochastic evaluation of quantitative safety targets, like hazard rate, in self-adaptive event detection systems by using Bayesian Networks and their extensions and show its application in a case study of vehicle detection with multiple sensors for which a real-world data-set is available from a previous study.
Q2 Answer	<p>Two main AI techniques are considered in this research:</p> <p>a) Machine Learning: Usage in self-adaptive systems in the following applications:</p> <p>(i.) to estimate the properties of the system by collecting data at run-time to support adaptation decisions;</p> <p>(ii.) to crosscheck the real-time operational behavior of the system with safety artifacts specified as fault trees;</p> <p>(iii.) to autonomously plan adaptation decisions, especially to cope with (...) distributed sensing and decision making, especially in automotive applications.</p> <p>b) Probabilistic Models (Bayesian Networks, Dempster-Shafer Theory): Usage in self-adaptive systems as part of smart sensing techniques to detect flawed sensors, evaluate the trustworthiness of a sensor network and evaluate risk-related uncertainties.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: AI introduces adaptiveness. As a result, in order to ensure that an adaptive system remains safe with its adaptations, safety is analyzed in runtime with those changes.</p> <p>General concept: "Misdetections and other uncertainties occurring in COTS smart sensors and their operating environments can be monitored at run time in order to dynamically assess system-level requirements like tolerable hazard rate or maximum PFH. To that aim, self-adaptation principles can be employed to enable the system to reconfigure and finally take safe decisions out of possibly unreliable sources."</p> <p>A self-adaptive system is monitored by an additional managing system modeled with the well-established MAPE-K model (Monitor, Analyze, Plan, Execute and Knowledge): "(1) Monitor both the Managed System and the Execution Environment and store data in K, (2) Analyze the data in K to detect anomalies that might prevent the fulfillment of safety requirements, (3) Plan the reconfiguration actions needed to keep the system safe, and (4) Execute the reconfiguration actions at run time." In the proposed model, a keep-alive scheme is implemented at the "Analyze" and "Knowledge" modules during run time and updated on-the-fly to reflect changes in the system itself and in the environment where it operates. During this, is it important that neither system knowledge faults/corruption (including environmental data) nor the analysis leads to a decision that leans towards a potentially unsafe configuration. The MAPE-K-based managing system shall be able to diagnose potential fault sources (i.e., which part of the monitored system generates improper inputs to the managing system), including underlying uncertainties on data. For this purpose, the proposed model employs Bayesian Networks, whose probabilities are set, among other parameters, based on the failure rates / probabilities of the monitored system elements, as well as uncertainties related to the system (including environmental ones) and correlation among elements (e.g. common-cause failures related to environment or overlapping technology drawbacks).</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The proposed model for safe self-adaptation of systems is exercised with a case study of multi-sensor vehicle detection that can be critical for automated level crossing. The results indicate the analysis of the system PFH (probability of failure on demand per hour) for several reconfiguration scenarios.</p> <p>Interesting conclusion: "<i>Given the growing number of smart critical systems like self-driving vehicles, the new versions of safety standards should account for possible self-adaptation to dynamic environments by</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 109 / 550	

	<i>using the so-called explainable artificial intelligence (XAI), possibly favoring xBN models like the ones used in this paper instead of less predictable black-box models (e.g., neural networks), although recent initiatives are addressing those issues in different ways."</i>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) The model assumes that the monitored system voter is sufficiently robust in such a way that it has no meaningful unsafe failure. Only sensor-related failures can affect the monitored system safety.</p> <p>2) Difficulty in assessing and including within the model the correlations stemming from common-cause failures, especially with regard to overlapping technological limitations.</p> <p>3) The tool used to implement the proposed model lacks scalability for systems that dynamically determine their possible configurations. It relies on a configuration file with all possible reconfiguration transitions.</p> <p>4) No tradeoffs for reliability and security have been assessed.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Highlights that certifying safety-critical systems with AI/ML remains controversial.</p> <p>2) Provides good contextualization of AI techniques for self-adaptive systems.</p> <p>3) Interesting conclusion for safety analysis trends favoring unexplainable AI (e.g. neural networks) even with the development of explainable AI (XAI).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The research does not cover potentially unsafe behavior stemming from the managing system itself. How can one ensure that the implemented Bayesian Networks will behave safely throughout the system lifetime?</p>

8.15 REFERENCE [80]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To evaluate which data is needed for assuring that the machine learning for self-driving autonomous cars is sufficiently robust for drivability and to define metrics to determine the drivability of self-driving autonomous cars.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning techniques, notably supervised learning. Reinforcement learning is also mentioned in further discussions by the authors as useable in self-driving autonomous cars.
Q3 Answer	The paper does not deal with the safety analysis of AI; nevertheless, stresses out the importance of training data to ensure that an AI-based system reaches its safety requirements.
Q4 Answer	Since the paper is not related to safety analysis of AI, no in-depth analysis of its additional results are herein presented.
Q5 Answer	Since the paper is not related to safety analysis of AI, no in-depth analysis of its additional results are herein presented.
Q6 Answer	Since the paper is not related to safety analysis of AI, no in-depth analysis of its additional results are herein presented.

8.16 REFERENCE [81]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To build evidence to ensure that autonomous vehicles with artificial intelligence are safe by means of extensive operational tests which ensure high reliability. The authors consider that high reliability is the key for ensuring that a system is safe.
Q2 Answer	The authors consider "machine learning" in a general way as part of the safety-critical systems under analysis. Bayesian Networks are used as a safety analysis tool for ML-based safety-critical systems.
Q3 Answer	Context: The authors deem inevitable that safety standards will have to be revised to include specificities for AI-based systems and consider that safety demonstrations based on simulations and operational testing "seems inevitable" for these systems. In order to ensure the adequacy of the safety demonstration, the following challenges shall be addressed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) ML data shall provide the possibility of confidently demonstrating the probability of rare (unsafe) events; b) Incorporate prior knowledge of conventional systems for safety demonstration; c) Usage of AI-based systems mean that the systems failure rates change with time because of constant

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 110 / 550	

	<p>learning (change of architecture or retraining), and the usage on different environments and traffic conditions.</p> <p>Method:</p> <p>1) For constant failure rate scenarios, a Conservative Bayesian Inference (CBI) method for reliability / safety assessment has been conceived to incorporate both failure-free and “rare failures” evidence. "Being a Bayesian approach, CBI allows for the incorporation of prior knowledge of non-road-testing evidence (e.g., verified aspects of the behavior of an AV's ML algorithms; verification results for the safety subsystems)." Main CBI objective: contrary to conventional Bayesian Networks, the CBI does not require full knowledge of a priori distributions (e.g. failure rate distribution). CBI works with partial a priori distribution constraints based on expert knowledge (e.g. an experienced safety assessor knows, with a certain degree of confidence, that the failure rate of a component is not lower than a limit X nor higher than a limit Y - including for rare events that are likely to have not happened with any system), deduces an a priori distribution which meets all the a priori constraints and reaches the most conservative a posteriori distributions that meets all partial a priori distributions.</p> <p>2) For assessing changes in failure rate, the CBI method is extended to statistical inference using bivariate prior distributions, so that partial prior knowledge on the relationship between the (unknown) failure rates before and after the changes can be used to answer practical questions regarding the deployment of a new version of an AV, or deployment of the same AV in a new environment. As in "1", CBI works with partial a priori distribution constraints based on expert knowledge (e.g. an experienced safety assessor knows, with a certain degree of confidence, that the failure rate of a component is not lower than a limit X nor higher than a limit Y - including for rare events that are likely to have not happened with any system) including for the correlation between contexts (e.g. different environment or SW change), deduces an a priori distribution which meets all the a priori constraints and reaches the most conservative a posteriori distributions that meets all partial a priori distributions.</p>
<p>Q4 Answer</p>	<p>Method #1: The proposed CBI shows how approaches presented by other researchers using the same data and the RAND company inference approach can be either too optimistic or too pessimistic. The method is exercised with three scenarios in which the number of working hours of automatic vehicles system would need (be it simulated, be it in the real world) is estimated based on a safety target and on a priori constraints defined by safety experts.</p> <p>Method #2: Constant rates (Bernoulli process) can be used before and after a system change, but the changing rate with the triggering event shall be identified and dealt with during the safety demonstration, as well as potentially unknown failure rates (e.g. due to the introduction of a new system component within the architecture not yet predicted). The method is exercised with two scenarios in which the number of working hours of automatic vehicles system would need (be it simulated, be it in the real world) is estimated based on a safety target and on a priori constraints defined by safety experts.</p> <p>Additional Results:</p> <p>1) Software Growth Reliability Models (SGRM) are useful for planning, but not for safety assessment of AI-based systems because SGRM extrapolation is not adequate unless one proves that a continuously-evolving AI-based software has a monotonic growth in reliability (and, hence, in safety).</p>
<p>Q5 Answer</p>	<p>Future works:</p> <p>(i) explore practical means for quantitatively stating prior knowledge (e.g. evidence from various system verification methods, applied to the AV system and its subsystems) for input to the CBI method;</p> <p>(ii) adapt CBI extensions to base decisions directly on risk of accidents/fatality-free operation over finite periods, instead of focusing on a specific bound on failure rate. As argued elsewhere [23], this would more directly support sound decisions about the progressive introduction of AVs;</p> <p>(iii) build more detailed safety arguments for architectures using safety subsystems, with appropriate subsystem-level arguments based on the different forms of evidence available about the various subsystems. These arguments would be more easily adapted to evolving ML subsystems;</p> <p>(iv) represent plausible forms of failure correlation (over successive miles driven) within the statistical model in our CBI approach. As outlined, the present CBI model assumes that the fundamental AV failure process is Bernoulli – specifically, that failures over successive miles driven are statistically independent and identically distributed in their occurrence. However, there are a number of analogous assessment scenarios where such independent and identically distributed assumptions may only hold very approximately. In future work, upon explicitly incorporating failure correlation into CBI models, we will quantify the extent to which the independent and identically distributed assumption may undermine</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 111 / 550	

	conservative assessments.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Strong mathematical background for an automated safety assessment model of ML-based systems which incorporates expert knowledge into Bayesian Networks that lead to conservative estimates for operation time which ensures that the system is sufficiently safe.</p> <p>Note: This is strongly tied to the authors' motivation that they deem inevitable that safety standards will have to be revised to include specificities for AI-based systems and consider that safety demonstrations based on simulations and operational testing "seems inevitable" for these systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) A highly reliable system can still be unsafe (e.g. software bug). The argument for SGRM usage in safety demonstrations is also not valid if AI is implemented on hardware (e.g. PLD).</p> <p>2) The authors deem inevitable that safety standards will have to be revised to include specificities for AI-based systems and consider that safety demonstrations based on simulations and operational testing "seems inevitable" for these systems.</p> <p>This is not necessarily true if "explainable AI" is used and if the AI is "contained" (i.e. surrounded by a safety envelope). Nevertheless, one question that still poses in this scenario is if a "traditional safety analysis approach" is feasible based on time for deployment.</p> <p>3) The CBI requires a good safety expert for its operation, otherwise its results can be too conservative or too optimistic if the a priori constraints are not adequate.</p>

8.17 REFERENCE [89]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a dynamic safety assurance scheme for safety-critical systems within Industry 4.0 context, including during the operation of the systems. Industry 4.0 is modular, dynamic and reconfigurable and it also includes the architectural levels of the things, as well as fog and cloud computing.
Q2 Answer	No explicit mention to AI has been identified except for general reference that Industry 4.0 tend to be dynamic with regard to their architecture and configuration.
Q3 Answer	<p>Step 1: Hazard and Operability (HAZOP) and Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) techniques are used for the identification and mitigation/elimination of potential hazards.</p> <p>Step 2: Safety requirements and safety contracts (for interfaces among involved parties) are derived from the hazard analysis results.</p> <p>Step 3: Safety cases are constructed using the OpenCert platform and safety contracts are associated with them to enable necessary changes during runtime. Operational data is employed to support the safety arguments and ensure completeness, consistency and correctness.</p> <p>Safety Contracts: <i>"They help in determining the validity of safety case modules and overall safety case by comparing safety requirement with related operational data when things or infrastructure are altered or substituted in the system, for instance, in response to changes in market, environmental conditions and device failures."</i> They are defined with Assumptions (rules for them to hold) and Guarantees (what happens if the Assumptions hold).</p> <p>Step 4: A simulation-based approach is employed to identify and resolve the deviations between the system understanding reflected in the safety cases and the current system operation in case of changes (e.g. system with adapted architecture or after new learning). <i>"The deviations or mismatches are tracked by comparing the safety contracts with their respective parameters that are gathered from simulations."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The safety assurance method is exercised in a case study of materials transportation and data flow in the Industry 4.0 context, including a situation in which, due to a system change, one of the safety goals is no longer met (leading to a new safety constraint during operation).</p> <p>Although a significant initial effort to derive the safety contracts for uncertainty sources, <i>"it is worthwhile to detect deviations from intended behavior and perform necessary adaptations at the operational phase. In this process, there is a need to handle the short and long-term deviations in different ways. The dynamic risk</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 112 / 550	

	<p><i>management is crucial for short-term deviations, but the safety contracts and safety cases may just be updated for the frequent or long term deviations."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) Evaluate the safety analysis methodology in other case studies (i.e. "other types of machines that have different characteristics and transformation of application domains to the Industry 4.0").</p> <p>2) Improve how to deal with uncertain and missing data: "In the current circumstances when the different configurations are reflected in the safety cases, problems arise, due to unavailability of operational data for all the parts. Accordingly, we plan to support the safety case configurations as part of the dynamic assurance in Industry 4.0."</p> <p>3) Improve flexibility on representing "legacy" Safety Cases not written in GSN nor in the OpenCert platform: "Another limitation is that the identification and resolution of gaps in safety cases is dependent on the GSN and the OpenCert platform. In the future, the safety cases modeled in other formats, such as free text and tabular structures could be supported."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) I4.0 Definition: "The fourth revolution is based on the four integral pillars: interoperability, information transparency, technical assistance and decentralized decisions. Interoperability is the capability to exchange data between machines that enables joint collaboration; Internet-of-Things (IoT) is exploited for interconnecting machines, the ultimate intention is whole automation. A novel enabler of information transparency could be through the concept of digital twins: leverage the virtual equivalents such as simulation models for assessing and improving the real products. Technical assistance provides the means to understand and control events that needs to be supported by systems. In this context, the comprehensive visualizations facilitate human operators to solve the problems in short time frames. The intention of decentralized decisions is to incorporate automatic decision making capabilities in machines so that the human intervention in manufacturing process is not required, which makes the operator rather a supervisor. Its generic architecture consists of three levels: things, fog/edge and cloud. The things and fog/edge represent the local part of the system, whereas the cloud is a remote infrastructure that is typically owned by a third-party service provider. The things interact with the physical environment via different sensing/actuating devices. However, due to their limited storage and processing power, devices from things level rely on the fog or cloud for storage and processing services. The fog acts as a bridge between the things and the cloud. It receives data from the things and perform partial processing, especially for critical functions, or otherwise forward the data to the cloud infrastructure. Likewise, the fog directly instruct to the things, but the cloud forwards commands to the things via fog servers."</p> <p>2) I4.0 safety contextualization: "To perform the safety analysis for Industry 4.0, besides the modular, dynamic and reconfigurable nature, the things, fog/edge and cloud levels need to be considered. Transformation to the Industry 4.0 significantly increases the safety assurance challenges."</p> <p>3) Justification for Dynamic Safety Assessment: "In the context of Industry 4.0, however, the parts of safety cases constructed during system design and development phase may turn out to be incorrect, inapplicable or insufficient during the operation. This can be caused by emergent behaviors and changes performed in consequence of market demands, hazardous conditions or system failures. To exploit the full potential of Industry 4.0, there is a need to support the dynamic safety assurance." "Continued and proactive assessment of autonomous systems to address the mismatches between the 'world as imagined' system and its operational environment we considered and the 'world as observed' analysis based on the operational data". 3rd reference to McDermid et al. (2019)."</p> <p>4) Sound system-level contextualization of the safety assurance process within a V development cycle, including post initial commissioning (operation & maintenance).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No reference to AI-specific hazards and failure modes.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 113 / 550	

8.18 REFERENCE [92]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	<p>To present the Neural Network Verification (NNV) software tool, developed to verify deep neural networks (DNNs) and neural network control systems (NNCSs). The tool features the following resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exact (sound and complete) and over-approximation (sound) safety and robustness verification of feed-forward neural networks (FFNNs); - Exact (sound and complete) and over-approximation (sound) safety and robustness verification of linear plant models; - Over-approximation (sound) safety and robustness verification of non-linear plant models.
Q2 Answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), which include <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i.) Feed-Forward Neural Networks (FFNNs); (ii.) Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). - Learning-Enabled Cyber Physical Systems a.k.a. Neural Network Control Systems (NNCSs).
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "Assuring the safety and robustness of neural network-based systems is challenging because DNNs possess complex nonlinear characteristics. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that their behavior can be unpredictable due to slight perturbations in their inputs (i.e., adversarial perturbations)."</p> <p>Basics: "NNV declares a DNN or a NNCS to be safe if, and only if, their reachable sets do not violate safety properties." (i.e., reachable state set not intersecting with potentially unsafe states). Exact Verification: All states of the DNN/NNCS are identified layer by layer and checked against the list of safe system conditions. If there is at least one state outside the list of safe states, the DNN/NNCS is unsafe; Over-approximation: an approximation of all the DNN/NNCS is identified layer by layer and checked against the list of safe system conditions. If there is at least one state outside the list of safe states, the DNN/NNCS is classified as "uncertain", and a "falsifier" is run to look for potentially unsafe states. If the falsifier can find a counterexample which leads the DNN/NNCS to an unsafe behavior, it is reclassified as "unsafe", otherwise it remains as "uncertain" since it is not sure that it is "safe".</p> <p>Algorithms for over-approximation are typically less computationally demanding than those for exact verification.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"NNV has been successfully applied to safety verification and robustness analysis of several real-world DNNs, primarily feedforward neural networks (FFNNs) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), as well as NNCSs."</p> <p>NNV is assessed using two real-world case studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Safety verification of ACAS Xu networks 2) Safety verification of a deep learning-based adaptive cruise control system.
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Adaptive Cruise Control System Case Study: When a friction term was introduced into the NNCS with simulated training data, all scenarios were classified as unsafe by the NNV. "This problem raises an important issue in training neural network controllers using simulation data, and these schemes may not work in real systems since there is always a mismatch between the plant model in the simulation engine and the real system." 2) General Result: Exact verification algorithms are computationally costly and may be not feasible in some situations.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) NNV has a significantly better performance than other algorithms / frameworks for safety verification of DNN/NNCS. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Over-approximation algorithms have low rate of safe/unsafe classification (no higher than 72% on the examples exercised by the authors). This means that, for at least 28% of the cases, the NNV tool produces inconclusive outputs. 2) NNV seems to be overly conservative in some over-approximation scenarios (e.g. many arguably unsafe results in both case studies).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 114 / 550	

	3) No thorough discussion on either the obtained results or on different verification attempts with various different algorithms for the Adaptive Cruise Control System Case Study.
	4) No analysis of AI failure modes.

8.19 REFERENCE [95]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present an approach for safety analysis of semi-autonomous and autonomous automotive control systems using multi-modal port-Hamiltonian systems by using the Hamiltonian function as a barrier between the energy levels of the safe and unsafe states and employing passivity to prove that trajectories cannot cross this barrier.
Q2 Answer	No reference to AI is performed in this study. Autonomous systems are referred to in a general way due to the analyzed applications within self-autonomous and autonomous automotive control systems.
Q3 Answer	No reference to AI is performed in this study. Autonomous systems are referred to in a general way due to the analyzed applications within self-autonomous and autonomous automotive control systems. The safety analysis is related to the system dynamics model itself regardless of its implementation: dynamic processes are modeled by means of multi-modal port-Hamiltonian systems (MMPHS). MMPHS represent systems based on discrete states and are associated to energy preservation and the Hamiltonian function (total stored energy). Safe states are modeled as low energy states constrained by a maximum energy limit, whereas unsafe states are modeled as high energy states constrained by a minimum energy limit. <i>"Passivity is used to prove that as long as the safe and unsafe energy regions do not overlap, trajectories that begin within a lower energy level (safe states) cannot terminate within a higher energy level (unsafe states)."</i> <i>"Composing controllers designed for interacting subsystems while preserving safety guarantees is a very challenging task."</i>
Q4 Answer	Case Study: Safety analysis of a vehicle dynamics composed with ACC (Adaptive Cruise Control) and LKC (Lane Keeping Control) to ensure that the host vehicle will not collide with a lead vehicle and will not skid off of the road. The control design is implemented and evaluated using a hardware-in-the-loop simulation platform. The experimental results demonstrate the safety analysis approach including the impact of implementation effects such as discretization and quantization.
Q5 Answer	Future work could focus on an alternative discretization process for PHS which minimizes the loss of passivity during discretization.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Mathematical definition of a safe control model for ACC and LKC of self-driving autonomous systems. The model has been conceived in continuous-time domain and exercised as safe within a discrete-time domain typical of computer-based control systems. 2) The MMPHS-based model for safe controllers can be used in several control problems. Weaknesses: 1) The conceived MMPHS-based model for safe controllers is application-specific; hence, new analyses shall be needed for each and every new controller. 2) No fault-related analyses were carried out by the authors. The conceived model is proven as safe from a functional point of view only. 3) No AI-related information is presented throughout the study.

8.20 REFERENCE [98]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present an approach to perform safety verification of Direct Perception Neural Networks (DPNN) based on learning an input property characterizer which extends a DPNN at its close-to-output layers. The objective of this safety verification is to ensure that, under certain input conditions, no undesired outputs occur. The approach is exercised with the safety verification of a DPNN employed to compute, based on camera images, the next waypoint and orientation for autonomous vehicles to follow.
Q2	The research focuses on the safety verification of Direct Perception Neural Networks (DPNNs).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 115 / 550

Answer	
Q3 Answer	<p>Main challenges for the safety verification:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Difficult to formally specify what is the unsafe output that shall never occur. 2) DPNNs usually have many layers totalizing millions of neurons, challenging the scalability of a verification solution. <p>Method description:</p> <p>A close-to-output layer of the DPNN is chosen and bounds to its neurons are conservatively defined by means of static analysis, hence defining a polyhedron with all its possible values as per the static analysis. Afterwards, the same close-to-output layer is analyzed during runtime to check whether it complies with the limits of this polyhedron while processing an output.</p> <p>Main issue: since training is not perfect, there is a non-null probability that the DPNN can generate an undetectably unsafe output. During the safety demonstration, a confidence level can be obtained to prove the hypothesis that the DPNN is safe based on how many samples are used when assessing the DPNN safe behavior.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A case study with a DPNN employed as a hot-standby system for computing the next waypoint of Audi vehicles under R&D has been performed. Based on the DPNN characteristics, a formal verification would be possible; nevertheless, the proposed model for safety verification was used instead. It led to conclusive conditional proving of some safety properties but inconclusive conditional proving of other safety properties (e.g. impossible to ascertain that no straight steering suggestion would be performed when the input road images bend to the right).</p> <p>For some input properties such as traffic participants in adjacent lanes, it was not possible to construct an input property characterizer by taking close-to-output neurons (i.e., the trained classifier acts like 'fair coin flipping').</p> <p>"The initial results demonstrate the potential of using formal methods even on very complex neural networks, while it provides a clear path to engineers to resolve the problem related to how to characterize input conditions for verification (by also applying machine learning techniques)."</p>
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) It led to inconclusive conditional proving of some safety properties (e.g. impossible to ascertain that no straight steering suggestion would be performed when the input road images bend to the right). 2) For some input properties such as traffic participants in adjacent lanes, it was not possible to construct an input property characterizer by taking close-to-output neurons (i.e., the trained classifier acts like 'fair coin flipping'). Still, it should be possible to construct a counter example-based proving either by capturing more data or by using adversarial perturbation techniques. 3) Investigate abstraction which can lead to layer-wise incremental abstraction-refinement techniques.
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The research essentially considers using AI to prove that another AI is safe. How can one ensure that the AI employed as part of the safety verification is also safe? 2) No fault-related analyses were carried out by the authors. The conceived model is proven as safe from a functional point of view only. 3) Safety verification results are associated to a confidence level in real scenarios in which NN training is not deemed perfect. If no significantly high confidence level is reached, the safety verification conclusion may be worth nothing.

8.21 REFERENCE [100]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To describe a process for developing online risk models based on System-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) and Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs).
Q2 Answer	Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs).
Q3 Answer	AI is not analyzed from a safety point of view, but instead used to perform online risk assessment (Category 2 paper). BBN probabilities are defined based on a priori expert information and sensor data during

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 116 / 550	

	operation. The BBN is structured with the top node relating to the unsafe control actions; the latter are related with the high-level risk influencing factors (RIFs) and these, to the leaf low-level RIFs.
Q4 Answer	Novelty: How STPA is used to generate a risk BBN model in a structured manner. Case Study: Autonomous marine systems to follows "fronts" in the water (i.e., transitions from "cold" to "warm" water and vice-versa) to support biological discoveries. The BBN was qualitatively built, but no indication on quantitative figures has been provided. Result: The process is applicable for other types of autonomous system.
Q5 Answer	Developing other case studies.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good contextualization of AI in safety-critical systems: "Supervisory risk control is an emerging research area combining knowledge related to control systems design and risk management. The focus is on creating autonomous systems with enhanced intelligence and automatic high-level decision-making through implementation of risk management capabilities." 2) Good definition of autonomy: "Autonomy can be defined as a system's or subsystem's own ability of integrated sensing, perceiving, analyzing, communicating, planning, decision-making, and acting, to achieve its goals as assigned by its human operator(s) through designed Human-Machine Interface (HMI). This definition is based on the one from NIST (2008), but adjusted to include both manned and unmanned autonomous systems. There are different ways of dividing LoA, for example, into four levels; LoA 1: Automatic operation (remote control); LoA 2: Management by consent; LoA 3: Semi-autonomous or management by exception and LoA 4: Highly autonomous during a mission or operation (...).The four levels here are adapted from NIST (2008) and is relatively general." 3) Good definition of a control system: "A control system can roughly be divided into three main layers (Ludvigsen and Sørensen, 2016; Utne et al., 2017). The "lowest" level is the control execution layer (the reactive control layer), then comes the guidance and optimization layer, and above is the mission or supervisory layer. Supervisory risk control is part of the mission layer and may contribute to improved Artificial Intelligence (AI). Hence, risk control, in terms of an online risk model, is included in the supervisory layer in the control architecture, providing the autonomous system the ability to plan its actions and make decisions." Weaknesses: 1) Marginally related to Category 3, if related at all. 2) No discussion on quantitative figures of the BBN and no discussion on how they can affect safety. 3) No fault-related analyses were carried out by the authors.

8.22 REFERENCE [101]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a risk prediction method based on monitoring data. The author claims that the method is aimed to usage within AI-based systems, but no mention to AI is made throughout the entire paper.
Q2 Answer	The author claims that the method is aimed to usage within AI-based systems, but no mention to AI is made throughout the entire paper.
Q3 Answer	The authors claim that the method is aimed to usage within AI-based systems, but no mention to AI is made throughout the entire paper. The risk analysis method is based on estimating probabilities of failure of system elements based on data periodically collected by monitoring the system.
Q4 Answer	Results are briefly discussed from a qualitative standpoint by the author, who claims to have received prizes from the Russian government with its research because it helped saving over 8 billion rubles in 5 years in oil & gas applications..
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Interesting mathematics for risk assessment based on periodic monitoring data.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 117 / 550	

	Weaknesses: 1) Language issues throughout the text. 2) Lack of analysis of limitations and suggestion of future research topics. 3) Too much self-citing throughout the text (over 20 references are by the same author). 4) No mention to benefits on AI-based systems in comparison with non-AI-based systems.
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8.23 REFERENCE [104]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To improve safe learning control for environment acknowledge by learning agents / robots through warm-up reachability analysis to decrease computation time and create an efficient safe learning framework for robotic systems.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Reinforcement learning is typically unsafe because the system is unconstrained. "<i>Hamilton-Jacobi (HJ) reachability analysis is a technique that determines the safe region within a state space by assuming the system operates under the worst-case conditions. Reachability analysis is robust and computationally intensive, specifying the constraints of the system and ensuring performance and safety guarantees.</i>"</p> <p>Safety Analysis Method: "<i>(...) warm-start reachability analysis is able to produce the same solution as the original method of reachability analysis in less time by updating the safety analysis from the previously computed solution, rather than restarting the analysis from scratch.</i>" "<i>This verification tool is very beneficial because it is robust and can compute strong safety guarantees if the dynamics of the system and the bounds on the disturbance are known.</i>" "<i>The safety analysis is also only valid if the assumptions on the dynamics of the system and bounds on the disturbance hold true. (...) If the system learns that the disturbance is not within the bounds it originally assumed, the system becomes more conservative, staying in a smaller region within the calculated safe set where initial assumptions are still valid. (...) the 95th percent confidence intervals on the resulting GP are set as the new bounds on the disturbance. These new assumptions are then used to recompute the safety analysis to better reflect the true disturbances.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Case study with a simulated quadcopter to demonstrate the improved efficiency of warm-start reachability analysis in response to unexpected disturbances (system and environment). No AI is employed on the Case Study.</p> <p>The paper is not safety-oriented: the authors deem that safety has already been well addressed and they just demonstrate efficiency improvement.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) "Future work aims to demonstrate this improved safe learning framework on real-world systems with the goal of applying this work to more realistic, high-dimensional systems."</p> <p>2) "Additionally, we aim to implement a performance controller that uses reinforcement learning, rather than an LQR controller, to improve the system's ability to travel in and learn about its environment. We also aim to perform reachability analysis online, performing safety analysis and collecting disturbance data in parallel to allow for real-time updates to the safe set."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The Hamilton-Jacobi model can be thought of as an 'envelope' which limits the safety boundaries of a system. Maybe its idea can be extrapolated to other types of systems if equations for its 'dynamics' (including 'logical dynamics' instead of 'physical dynamics') can be determined.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The paper is not safety-oriented: the authors deem that safety has already been well addressed and they just demonstrate efficiency improvement.</p> <p>2) Even though AI is employed within the study motivation and its basics, the case study does not take into account an AI-based controller for the device under study.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 118 / 550	

8.24 REFERENCE [107]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present a framework for developing safe and secure adaptive collaborative systems, with run-time guarantees, focusing on requirement engineering and safety assurance techniques to capture the specific safety and security properties for the collaborative system, and to provide an assurance case guaranteeing that the system is sufficiently safe. For this, an architecture and behavioral models to analyze the requirements at design-time and run-time are proposed together with a real-time-enabled fog/cloud-based deployment to perform the run-time analysis and planning while guaranteeing the real-time constraints.
Q2 Answer	No explicit mention to AI has been identified except for general reference that systems are adaptive with regards to their architecture and implementation.
Q3 Answer	A framework comprising three elements has been conceived by the authors: 1) APAC (Actor-based Platform for Adaptive Collaborative systems): Provides models which address adaptive features of the system, formal analysis, verification techniques and tools to verify that safety and security requirements are valid for a given system configuration. The APAC monitors automatic (re)configuration of systems during adaptation. Its architecture is based on the IBM MAPE-K model (same of [71]). 2) CASSA (Continuous and Adaptive Safety and Security Assurance): Assuring safety and security in a continuous and adaptive manner is a major challenge, not the least due to the increasing number of attack surfaces resulting from the increased connectivity. CASSA provides joint safety and security requirements fed into both analysis models and the time-predictive methods defined in RTCloud. It also extends hazard analysis and risk assessment techniques and proposes methods for (semi-) automatic adaptation of safety and security assurance cases. 3) RTCloud (Real-Time Cloud / Fog Computing): Provides timing guarantees on the execution of real-time applications in the cloud. Current cloud computing usually falls short of time predictability, which is why fog computing has been proposed as a computational model for extending the cloud closer to the objects to be controlled, and providing better timing performance.
Q4 Answer	The paper aims to present the features of the proposed model and define the next steps of the research. There are still no results regarding the implementation of the proposed model.
Q5 Answer	Future development for each element of the proposed safety and security analysis: 1) APAC: Building an architecture for runtime adaptation, building runtime models, developing runtime analysis and formal verification methods, and developing runtime planning and optimization techniques. 2) CASSA: Providing a set of mitigation strategies focusing on a complex adaptive environment, extending the hazard analysis and risk assessment techniques to include safety and security, building a common safety and security assurance approach that will cater for a joint safety and security assurance case, and providing a solution on (semi-) automatic safety and security assurance case adaptation. 3) RTCloud: Defining a model for safety-critical applications to be run in the cloud/fog, developing real-time scheduling techniques for real-time cloud applications, providing end-to-end analysis of real-time cloud applications, proving application placement, providing resource optimization of real-time cloud applications, and prototyping implementation and evaluation. 4) Case Study: Test and apply the proposed model in industrial robotics, transportation and vehicular domain; provide foundation for applicability in other domains including health and smart cities.
Q6 Answer	1) Strength: The ideas are in line with other studies related to the safety and security analysis of adaptive systems; interesting subject for Industry 4.0 context. 2) Weakness: The research is still in initial state, with neither implementation nor results.

8.25 REFERENCE [115]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present how contraction mapping can be used to reach approximate solutions with reinforcement learning in less time than the formal Hamilton-Jacobi reachability analysis and still lead to acceptable quantitative safety analysis as tools to approximate the safe set and optimal safety policy. Validation is carried out by comparing safety results computed through Q-learning to analytic and numerical solutions, and demonstrate its scalability by learning safe sets and control policies for simulated systems of up to 18 state dimensions

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 119 / 550	

	using value learning and policy gradient techniques.
Q2 Answer	<p>Reinforcement learning in general.</p> <p>The case studies refer to four reinforcement learning schemes: tabular Q-learning, deep Q-learning (DQN), REINFORCE, and soft actor-critic.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Proving safety is computationally demanding for complex dynamic systems. "<i>Reinforcement learning functions representing a sum of rewards over time are not well suited to capture the safety objective, since safety is not determined by how much a system fails on average, but by whether it fails at all.</i>"</p> <p>In order to circumvent this, "<i>some approaches have proposed formalizing safety as stability or near constraint satisfaction. Others have built on the Hamilton-Jacobi reachability literature to provide constraint satisfaction guarantees by computing a safety-preserving control policy and overriding the learning controller when it attempts to violate computed safety constraints. Unfortunately, this family of methods inherits the difficult in scaling up computations beyond low-dimensional systems.</i>"</p> <p>Safety Analysis Method: "<i>(...) we propose a similar, tighter discounted formulation of Hamilton-Jacobi safety analysis, obtaining a contraction Bellman operator that lends itself to the use of temporal difference learning techniques. We prove the key properties of this new discounted safety Bellman equation and show that our resulting safety Q-learning algorithm converges to the safety action-value function.</i>"</p> <p>Limitation: "<i>It is important to clarify that our formulation yields a promising new tool for offline safety analysis: it is not in itself a safe learning framework, since it requires experiencing failure states in order to learn safety.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The results of implementing the proposed discounted safety Bellman backup are presented in multiple reinforcement learning schemes - tabular Q-learning, deep Q-learning (DQN), REINFORCE, and soft actor-critic - applied to a total of four different dynamical systems: two dynamical systems commonly used as benchmarks in control theory (2-state double-integrator system and a 4-state cart-pole system), a 6-state lunar lander system and an 18-state half-cheetah system.</p> <p>Pre-condition: Validate the computed safety value function and safe set against analytically and numerically obtained ground-truth references in traditionally tractable systems. This is only carried out for the simpler systems (2-state double-integrator system and a 4-state cart-pole system) because computing the safety value function through dynamic programming is intractable on higher order systems. For these, the model's safety predictions are compared with the observed safety by performing on-policy rollouts in simulation.</p> <p>Results: 1) Adopting function approximation techniques from modern reinforcement learning, allowed showing scalability for higher dimensional systems and find out that the DQN-based approach is accurate compared to analytic solutions and existing numerical methods. 2) It is possible to learn control policies for systems with up 18 state dimensions that preserve safety more proficiently than those optimized for a sum of discounted rewards. However, not all learned control policies were consistently able to preserve safety. Unsafe results are less common on simpler systems (<1E-4 error points) and more frequency on more complex systems (30% error points on the half-cheetah example).</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) Extension for online safety assurance usage: "While our analysis here is presented for deterministic dynamics, robust and stochastic extensions are certainly possible (and have been explored to some extent in the recent work). We expect that such extensions will be important for implementation of our formulation on physical systems, which is of course its ultimate intended application."</p> <p>2) Need for previous simulation before any deployment in the real world: "To reach convergence under model-free learning schemes, the system must repeatedly violate the constraints. Thus model-free algorithms using discounted safety must be used in simulation or an environment where leaving the constraint set does not result in catastrophic failure."</p> <p>3) Not possible to ensure that the system is safe for all tasks: "(...) policies trained with our formulation will seek to maintain safety but not accomplish another task while staying safe."</p> <p>4) Need for formal verification: "It may prove fruitful to investigate combining our work with recent research in neural network verification to provide formal guarantees about learned value functions and</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 120 / 550	

	control policies."
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) No fault-related analyses were carried out by the authors. 2) No contextualization on application domains that differ from robots. 3) Quantitative results, albeit leaning towards safety, are still unacceptable for several safety-critical applications.

8.26 REFERENCE [116]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To propose two software safety cages, which aim to limit the control action of the neural network to a safe operational envelope. The safety cages impose limits on the control action during critical scenarios, which, if breached, change the control action to a more conservative value. Interventions by the safety cages are also used to re-train the network, resulting in a more robust control policy. The case study is related to a deep neural network trained for longitudinal vehicle control, with safety cages designed to prevent forward collisions.
Q2 Answer	Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	In order to circumvent the opaqueness of black-box Deep Neural Networks, the authors propose that safety cages are used to limit the response of the DNNs to a safe envelope. <i>"Safety cages have been proposed for black box systems, where the safety of the system must be ensured without necessarily having full understanding of how the system works. (...) Safety cages eliminate unsafe actions by imposing limits on possible control actions. Utilizing run-time monitoring, the safety cages can change dynamically based on the state of the system and its environment. (...) Safety cages have been used in cyber-physical systems where full offline safety validation is not possible."</i> <i>"Therefore, the safety validation requirements on the neural network can be relaxed, given that the software safety cages can be validated with high assurance"</i>
Q4 Answer	The case study is related to a "(...) deep neural network trained for longitudinal vehicle control, with [two] safety cages designed to prevent forward collisions. Simulated testing in critical scenarios shows the effectiveness of the safety cages in preventing forward collisions whilst under normal highway driving unnecessary interruptions are eliminated, and the deep learning control policy is able to perform unhindered." The safety cages are related to headway time and time to collision. Both were assessed by using two different neural controllers: one of better quality (deep controller), and one deliberately trained to be suboptimal (shallow controller). The simulations results indicated that the safety cages acted especially with the shallow controller, ensuring its safety even in scenarios which could not be generalized by its learned data, and that performance was not reduced by the safety cages.
Q5 Answer	<i>"This work opens multiple potential avenues for future work. The safety cages presented here mitigate forward collisions under highway driving. The presented techniques could be used to further develop safety cages to account for lateral control, urban driving, etc. To improve the safety offered by the safety cages, fault identification and mitigation could be used to identify the effect of faulty measurements on the effectiveness of the safety cages. Furthermore, the interventions by the safety cages could be leveraged to better understand what the network has learned (or has not learned) by identifying the edge cases where the network fails. Further improvements to the re-training framework could also be investigated, for example, by using iterative testing and re-training, or by addressing the imbalance between the scarce interventions of the safety cages relative to the significantly larger original dataset."</i>
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good contextualization of safety cages / envelopes as a means to allow the usage of AI in safety-critical systems. Weakness: 1) ML is not safety-critical within the proposed system, since the safety cages are deterministic and act as a regular controller in case the ML controller violates the safety cage

8.27 REFERENCE [117]

Q-Index	5
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 121 / 550	

Q1 Answer	<p>To present an approach to improve the process of requirements specification in which Machine-Learned Components (MLCs) are developed and operate by explicitly specifying domain-related concepts. The approach extracts an universally accepted benchmark for hard-to-specify concepts and can be used to identify gaps in the associated dataset and the constructed ML model.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>Machine learning in general.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: There are elements which are hard to be thoroughly and unambiguously defined within the project of a MLC, such as a 'pedestrian' (different clothes, shoes, sizes, shapes, colors, carrying objects of different natures).</p> <p>Relation to Safety Analysis of AI: If there are techniques for analyzing and engineering requirement specifications for MLCs, they "will later improve the process of verification and validation of MLCs and assist in understanding the underspecified concepts in both the dataset and machine learning models." Due to this, decomposing high-level requirements into low-level verifiable requirements for the MLCs is a challenging, if feasible, task.</p> <p>Challenges: One of the major barriers is the impotence to systematically reason and specify the semantics of domain-specific concept, and to trace them through various stages of the MLCs life cycle. The following aspects shall be considered:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Dataset Specification [see Kohli et al.): "<i>(...) the specifications should be clearly defined for medical image data, covering all aspects of image management, including image metadata, pixel data, post processing techniques, image cataloging.</i>" 2) Model Specification: "<i>Based on the particular learning algorithms, model specifications normally define how the theoretical properties should hold during the implementation.</i>" 3) MLC Development Process Specification (see Salay and Czarnecki): "<i>(...) training procedure be clearly specified to meet the functional safety standard. For example, n analysis on the adequacy of regularization (one specific technique in machine learning) shall be carried out to mitigate the flaw of over-fitting. Among the process requirements for other phases of the software development, this work delineates a relatively complete set of instructions to realize the safety assurance of software with MLCs for safety critical domains.</i>" 4) Traceability (see Falcini et al. & Banks and Ashmore): "<i>(...) traceable path to demonstrate the compliance of source code with the design specification and coding guidelines. (...) F. Falcini et. al. also called for building the infrastructure to support traceability in automotive software when integrating a "V" model for data development with the standard "V" model for software development, calling the result a "W" model. A. Banks and R. Ashmore have demonstrated the potential of traceability by implementing and maintaining high level software requirements through building confidence in training data. Such confidence includes nine items including data sufficiency, self-consistency and absence of bias. However, the specific steps to achieve this confidence in the training data are yet to be defined.</i>" <p>Specification Process: It comprises five steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Scoping the Domain: Identify what are the important features of the concept by means of web search queries and selecting the most relevant terms. 2) Visualizing the Domain: Create an ontology (de-facto rules) using relevant terms from the previous step and allow its revision by domain experts and stakeholders for completeness and correctness. 3) Interpreting the Domain in the Dataset: Comprehend the concept demonstrated by the data and check inconsistencies between what the dataset represents and the specifications produced in the previous steps to reveal weaknesses on both of them. 4) Interpreting the Domain Learned by ML Model: Some ML models are considered more interpretable (e.g., those created by rule-based techniques) than others (e.g., built by neural network techniques). The comprehensibility of a model depends on the actual contents. Identifying the most relevant and important attributes in a model helps understanding its content. 5) Minding the Gap: "<i>(...) the identified domain concepts in each step can be correlated to identify the gaps among the constructed ontology, dataset representations, and machine learning models.</i>"
Q4 Answer	<p>Case Study: Specifying a 'pedestrian' for a pedestrian detector component from the automotive domain. Steps "1)" to "3)" were exercised within the reported research, whereas steps "4)" was not exercised and step "5)" was partially exercised (ML model gaps were not discussed due to step "4)" skipping).</p>
Q5	<p>1) "<i>(...) to fully implement the proposed approach, specifically, the parts related to interpreting the learned</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 122 / 550

Answer	<p>domain and identifying the gap and validate its effectiveness."</p> <p>2) " (...) to automate the process of ontology creation which so far has been done manually, in order to increase the usability of the approach."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Routing to interesting references that are directly related to the lifecycle of AI-based systems and to techniques for the safety analysis of these systems throughout the entire lifecycle (including systematic fault analyses). Good summary of the most relevant aspects.</p> <p>2) Interesting method for the left side of the V process.</p> <p>3) Interesting introduction for the W process lifecycle, including dataset safety analysis.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The research is still in initial state, with few implementation results.</p> <p>2) Albeit strong when considering systematic failures, no specification regarding random faults is directly considered by the authors.</p>

8.28 REFERENCE [119]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To describe progress with developing automated verification techniques for deep neural networks to ensure safety and robustness of their decisions with respect to input perturbations, featuring algorithms based on feature-guided search, games, global optimization, and Bayesian methods.
Q2 Answer	Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) and Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs).
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "While the accuracy of neural networks has greatly improved, they are susceptible to adversarial examples. an adversarial example is an input which, though initially classified correctly, is misclassified after a minor, perhaps imperceptible, perturbation."</p> <p>Objective: To increase the robustness of Deep Neural Networks. "Robustness (or resilience) of neural networks to adversarial perturbations is an active topic of investigation. (...) Local (also called point-wise) robustness is defined with respect to an input point and its neighborhood as the invariance of the classification over the neighborhood. Global robustness is usually estimated as the expectation of local robustness over the test dataset weighted by the input distribution."</p> <p>Three approaches are presented: heuristic search for adversarial examples, automated verification approaches and probabilistic verification.</p> <p>1) Heuristic Search for Adversarial Examples: These methods are based on optimization problems which aim to change input data and check the resulting behavior of this change on the Deep Neural Network under analysis in order to evaluate if a misclassification occurs.</p> <p>2) Automated Verification: These methods are related to formal guarantees on the robustness of DNNs, at times analyzing the robustness of neural networks by considering the maximal size of the perturbation that will not cause a misclassification (i.e. if there is any perturbation which falls within the corresponding maximal safe radius centered at the point within which no adversarial examples exist). "Since verification for state-of-the-art neural networks is an NP problem, testing methods that ensure high levels of coverage have also been developed."</p> <p>3) Probabilistic Verification: "Since neural networks have a natural probabilistic interpretation, they lend themselves to frameworks for computing probabilistic guarantees on their robustness. Bayesian neural networks (BNNs) are neural networks with distributions over their weights, which can capture the uncertainty within the learning model. The neural network can thus return an uncertainty estimate along with the output, which is important for safety-critical applications." "(...) Probabilistic robustness is considered for BNNs, using a probabilistic generalization of the usual</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 123 / 550	

	statement of (deterministic) robustness to adversarial examples, namely the computation of the probability (...) of the classification being invariant over the neighborhood around a given input point, [by means of] (...). statistical model checking...".
Q4 Answer	The paper is a survey on the state-of-the-art of Deep Neural Networks safety verification; as a result, the survey itself is the result. The conclusion of the survey is that <i>"To achieve "strong" AI, greater emphasis is necessary on rigorous modeling and verification technologies that support reasoning [about interventions, counterfactuals and 'what if' scenarios], as well as development of novel synthesis techniques that guarantee the correctness of machine learning components by construction. Importantly, automated methods that provide probabilistic guarantees which properly take account of the learning process have a role to play and need to be investigated."</i> .
Q5 Answer	Please refer to the Question 4 answer for details.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good contextualization of adversarial attacks. My thought for the research: A random HW failure or a SW systematic failure can introduce an adversarial attack. In this case, other countermeasures can be used as 'redundancy' to avoid the adversarial attack (e.g. complementary sensors for data acquisition, adequate SW production process). Weakness: Short survey with just an overview of the techniques and possible references for further research.

8.29 REFERENCE [121]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present and illustrate the application a novel tool framework for augmenting existing data sets with quality deficits in order to support the validation of image-based safety-critical systems with convolutional neural networks, notably with regard to the quality of their inputs.
Q2 Answer	Convolutional neural networks.
Q3 Answer	Background: <i>"Our experience shows that most datasets are artificially clean, i.e., they omit or at least underrepresent many of the quality deficits that arise in real-world settings (...) A related challenge is that even if representative test data is available, most critical edge cases might be too rare to be included in sufficient numbers in a reasonably sized dataset. Examples are pedestrians on a rural road at night or the combination of a defective headlight and oncoming traffic with high beam."</i> Basics: <i>"(...) there are two ways to deal with these problems: creating artificial images using simulation environments or augmenting existing images with quality deficits. The first approach suffers from the 'reality gap'. Attempts to narrow this gap train specialized GANs and apply them to artificially generated images to make them look more realistic."</i> <i>"Our contribution is a framework and a tool instantiation for augmenting image data with realistic quality issues and corresponding meta-data. The framework provides guidance for the identification of possible quality deficits, the design of a context model for deriving conditional probabilities for the occurrence of possible deficits, and the layering of various kinds of potentially interacting augmentations. Extending existing work, the framework allows (1) enriching datasets with quality deficits reflecting their natural distribution in the target application scope and (2) applying several deficits to the same image without causing artificial overlay issues."</i> <i>"Three kinds of augmentation can be distinguished: (1) those mainly used to increase the number and variety of data points, such as image rotations and shifts; (2) those used to intentionally decrease the quality of the image, making the task harder for the model; and (3) those specifically designed to fool a given data-driven model by generating adversarial examples."</i> The focus of the paper is for the second type of augmentation. Framework: <i>"The overall process consists of two major stages. The first stage (P1-P9) comprises all the steps for building the specific augmentation-tooling instance for a given data-driven component and its target application scope. The second stage (A1-3) comprises all the steps required to apply an augmentation-tooling instance to an image dataset."</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 124 / 550	

	<p>P1 - Understand the Data-Driven Component and Its Target Application Scope.</p> <p>P2 - Identify Quality Deficits (QD) Affecting the Data-Driven Component (including context light, darkness, weather condition – (rain, snow, haze, heat shimmer), shadows, occlusion; for object physical damage – (bent, broken, holes), graffiti and stickers, faded colors, dirty sign, wet sign, snow on sign; and for sensor placement, particles on lens (dirt, snow, rain drops, steam), lens – and sensor limitations (e.g., resolution, noise, glare effects, backlight, motion blur), camera calibration (e.g., defocus, color temperature), camera processing (e.g. compression errors)).</p> <p>P3 - Identify Scope Characteristics Influencing the Occurrence or Intensity of QD.</p> <p>P4 - Define a Causal Model with Dependencies Between Scope Characteristics.</p> <p>P5 - Derive Conditional Probabilities to Quantify Identified Dependencies.</p> <p>P6 - Identify Existing Augmentation Techniques Available for QD.</p> <p>P7 - Define the Order of Applying Augmentations.</p> <p>P8 - Implement the Augmentations for the Quality Deficits.</p> <p>P9 - Derive Conditional Probabilities to Quantify Further Sensor Outputs.</p> <p>A1 - Randomly Sample a Context Vector.</p> <p>A2 - Determine Augmentation(s) to Apply and Their Parameter Values.</p> <p>A3 - Apply Augmentations and Generate Meta-data.</p>
Q4 Answer	The authors only presented their framework for image augmentation to support the validation of image-based safety-critical systems. Practical applications were only quoted as "A preliminary evaluation showed that a tool prototype based on the framework in the context of traffic sign recognition provided visually authentic results on the GTSRB dataset."
Q5 Answer	<p>"At the technical level, the challenge of automatically deriving an object mask that identifies all pixels related to the traffic sign has not been finally solved."</p> <p>"(...) we plan to address UC2 (sample realistic context characteristics in which a given selection of quality deficits may occur) by considering the context model as a Bayesian network and inferring the unobserved scope characteristics with stochastic MCMC simulation."</p> <p>"The parameters of the augmentations still need to be calibrated and validated on empirical data."</p> <p>"We also need to further investigate how well the augmented data represents the intended target application scope. This includes evaluating the coverage of relevant quality deficits and the realism of the generated images, investing the impact of the augmentations on the accuracy of data-driven component outcomes, and finally comparing the impact of the augmented quality deficits with the impact of their natural counterparts."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting insight on the importance of dataset preparation to support the safety assessment of AI-based safety-critical systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Research limited to images only;</p> <p>2) Research in initial state, without actual results to support its feasibility in the way it was conceived by the authors.</p>

8.30 REFERENCE [131]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose a new forward reachability analysis approach to verify safety of cyber-physical systems with reinforcement learning controllers based on two efficient, exact and over-approximate reachability algorithms for neural network control systems using star sets.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning techniques, focusing on Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	Motivation: Deep Neural Networks have been lately used as part of intelligent autonomy as learning-based controllers for autonomous vehicles and air traffic collision avoidance systems. "Recent incidents in autonomous driving (e.g., Tesla and Uber) due to the failures of learning-based components, e.g., misclassifying objects, raises an urgent need for techniques and tools that can formally verify the safety of

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 125 / 550	

	<p>neural network control systems before utilizing them in safety-critical applications."</p> <p>Safety verification of autonomy containing neural network components is difficult because DNNs usually have complex characteristics and behavior that are generally unpredictable. "To explicitly analyze the safety of NNCS, we need to calculate the exact or overapproximate reachable set containing all possible trajectories of the plant that takes the control set from the neural network controller as inputs. To explicitly analyze the safety of NNCS, we need to calculate the exact or overapproximate reachable set containing all possible trajectories of the plant that takes the control set from the neural network controller as inputs. The output set of the plant is feedback to the controller to compute the control set for the next control step. Therefore, if the error in the reachable set computation is large, it quickly becomes larger and larger over time which results in too conservative reachable sets that cannot be used for safety verification."</p> <p>Safety Verification: It shall address the following problems:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Given the initial set of states of the plant, how can we efficiently compute the reachable set of the plant over time steps which depends on the control input produced by the FNN controller with nonlinear activation functions? 2) How can we transform the computed reachable set with a nonlinear transformation function to verify the safety property of the system? 3) How to determine the initial condition of the i-th state $x_i(0)$ that "may" make the system unsafe while keeping the initial conditions of other states unchanged? It is almost impossible to perform backward analysis of CPS with neural network controllers to determine an unsafe initial condition (backward analysis is generally intractable in this case). <p>Basics: A reinforcement learning-based controller determines "the initial conditions for which a safety-critical system with a neural network controller is safe by incrementally searching a critical initial condition where the safety of the system cannot be established."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Results: The approach produces tight over-approximation error and it is computationally efficient for controllers with DNN-based ReLU activation function.</p> <p>Case Study 1: The approach is applied to evaluate the safety of a practical Advanced Emergency Braking System (AEBS) with a reinforcement learning (RL) controller trained using the deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG) method. Two redundant neural networks are used, each one with different architectural settings: one "Actor" NN and one "Critic" NN which monitors if the "Actor" NN is adherent to it. To guarantee safety, it is required that the time-to-collision (TTC) of the car is always larger than a safe threshold defined by the physical characteristics of the vehicle.</p> <p>The results indicate that the approach is less conservative than existing polyhedra-based approaches whilst successfully determining the region of the initial conditions of the AEBS with the RL controller such that the safety of the system is guaranteed.</p> <p>Case Study 2: The approach is also applied to an Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC) system in such a way that two autonomous vehicles equipped with it do not crash with each other, for example, in case the leading vehicle suddenly brakes. Four different NN architectures were exercised in the scenario of sudden braking of the leading vehicle and a 5 x 20 neurons architecture was the only one that lead to safe behaviors within a time range of 5 seconds.</p> <p>Additional Result: To provide an end-to-end design and implementation in a MATLAB toolbox publicly available for evaluation and comparison.</p>
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Reachability analysis approach is limited to feed-forward neural network controllers with ReLU/Saturation activation functions. 2) Extending the proposed methods for nonlinear NNCS with other types of nonlinear activation functions such as Tanh or Sigmoid. 3) Investigating the runtime verification for CPS with learning-enabled components in combination with the neural network reachability analysis methods.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization of the AI safety verification problem for reinforcement learning-based controllers.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 126 / 550	

	<p>2) Good conceptual summary on Neural Networks (section 2.1) and its safety verification problem (section 2.2).</p> <p>3) Strong mathematical basis for the proposed NN safety verification method.</p> <p>4) Interesting approach with two redundant neural networks with different architectures trained with the same data.</p> <p>5) Interesting topics of current discussion for safety assurance of AI-based systems:</p> <p>a) Falsification-Based Safety Assurance of Cyber-Physical Systems with Learning-Enabled Components: In the falsification context, a compositional falsification framework for CPS with machine learning components has been proposed in [10]. In this framework, a temporal logic falsifier cooperates efficiently with a machine learning analyzer to find falsifying executions of the system.</p> <p>b) Safe Reinforcement Learning (SRL): SRL is an essential research topic in safety-critical applications such as medical robotics and self-driving cars. The fundamental challenge in SRL is that the agent not only needs to learn policies that maximize the long-term return based on the reward signal but also ensure the safety constraints in learning or deploying processes.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No fault-related analyses were carried out by the authors.</p> <p>2) No discussion related to common-cause failures related to the same input training data of the two redundant NNs has been performed by the authors.</p> <p>3) Safety verification was carried out for small periods of time within the case studies (e.g. time window of some operation seconds starting on the initial conditions of the scenario to be assessed).</p>
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8.31 REFERENCE [133]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To we present a method for converting a “black box” neural network model into an approximate explainable “white box” model that yields insight into the network’s decision-making criteria.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, with emphasis on Long Short-Term Memory Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: "(...) <i>we present a method where a “black box” neural network model B is converted into a “white box” model W that approximates B’s decisions, but makes them explainable/interpretable. The latter model is created by generating sample points on B’s decision boundary, and then approximating this decision boundary via a set of hyperplanes in the input space. Each decision boundary point is found by perturbing some input via gradient descent until the network changes its decision, where the gradient of the neural network’s output is computed with respect to the input. A local hyperplane is then defined for each decision boundary point, and attempts to separate nearby inputs that lead to one decision from those that lead to another.</i>" --> Idea is to detect state changes on the ANN's response by the descent gradients and define the hyperplanes which approximate the ANN at that point as orthogonal to the gradients.</p> <p>For nonlinear decision boundaries, "<i>Each hyperplane may provide a good approximation of the decision boundary $H(X')$ near the corresponding point X', but this approximation may deteriorate with distance from X'.</i>" .</p> <p>"<i>There are (...) many possible variations on this algorithm. In particular, multiple hyperplanes (rather than just one) can be used for decision-making; this approach can be viewed as a form of ensemble learning.</i>" (e.g. majority voting, averaging or weighted averaging)."</p> <p>"<i>In addition to applying the hyperplanes in order to make decisions, we can also analyze the magnitudes and signs of their coefficients, in order to understand the strength and direction (respectively) of the relationship between the variable value and the network’s output</i>".</p>
Q4 Answer	A case study related to the application of the proposed explainable machine learning procedure to the identification of precursors to degraded aircraft states is presented with three steps. " <i>First, we apply a statistical procedure to detect a degraded state by looking for outliers in the value of a variable, given another variable; specifically, in this study, we look for situations where an approaching aircraft is too far</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 127 / 550	

	<p>away from the airport, given its altitude. Second, we train the recurrent long short-term memory neural network (LSTM) to predict that a degraded state will occur in the future, based on data that was observed in the past and present. (...) Third, we convert the LSTM network into a “white box” model, and analyze this model’s hyperplane coefficients to explain how it makes the predictions; these explanations are then formulated as a precursor.”</p> <p>Important results:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Shortest distance hyperplanes led to a false positive rate which is somewhat higher than it is for LSTM, but not drastically so, while the prediction rate (i.e., degraded state prediction rate) is somewhat higher as well; 2) Hyperplanes had a tendency to predict a degraded state too soon; 3) The averaging and majority voting heuristics gave slightly lower accuracy than the smallest distance heuristic, but slightly higher prediction horizons. The weighted average heuristic demonstrates a reduction in the false positive rate, relative to the single hyperplane approach, suggesting a possible benefit to the use of multiple hyperplanes for decision-making
Q5 Answer	<p>"In the future, it would be of interest to evaluate our explainable machine learning method on other problems, in order to further gauge its strengths and limitations."</p> <p>"Another direction is to apply the approach to other neural network architectures, such as convolutional neural networks and other types of deep neural networks. Here, the network’s decision boundary may be very complex, and a very large number of hyperplanes may be required for an effective approximation; however, our method may still be useful in explaining why a neural network made a given decision for some specific input."</p> <p>"Another challenge is that deep neural networks often have decision boundaries that do not make much sense to a human, and can cause a network to make classification errors that a human would not. However, as strategies are developed for mitigating this problem, neural networks might potentially become more explainable; in turn, approaches for explaining a neural network’s decisions might be used to improve their behavior."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Theoretically sound proposal supported by effective case studies which show the desired improvements of explainable AI. 2) Interesting proposals for future research. 3) The proposed method may be interesting for off-line safety analysis of AI-based systems, but may be prohibitive for on-line safety analysis of more complex AI-based systems with several states or which monitor some continuous variable (state explosion). <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A Java-based implementation of the Long Short-Term Memory Neural Network has been used by the authors. No discussion regarding its safety has been presented. 2) The proposed model may be prohibitive for on-line safety analysis of more complex AI-based systems with several states or which monitor some continuous variable (state explosion).

8.32 REFERENCE [134]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	<p>To detail assurance and behavior bounds for decision making systems from a) algorithmic functional performance; b) scheduling analysis and candidate scheduling paradigms; and c) processor architectures (including multi-core) to support minimized interference in general, mainly with regard to machine learning approaches for control, navigation and guidance applications for unmanned aerial systems (UASs).</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>AI is named in a general way in the paper, but specific techniques are also mentioned:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Machine Learning in general - Multi-Layer Artificial and Deep Neural Networks

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 128 / 550	

	<p>- Statistical / Stochastic Approaches (e.g. Bayesian estimators, Markov chains, Kalman filters).</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: The paper focuses on AI applications related to UAS. The following applications are deemed the most promising and frequent for AI usage within UAS:</p> <p>Perception and modeling</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to extract perception information from large quantity of data Ability to discern patterns and develop model structures <p>Open-ended problem solving</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Reasoning under uncertainty Decision making when conditions are “new” Optimization under very large number of variables with unknown relationships <p>Potential to learn/discover new mechanisms</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to adapt to new situations Ability to generate new approaches" <p>Mission Planning Obstacle Avoidance Navigation and Control Self-Organization and Control</p> <p>Safety-Related Approaches for UAS under Research: Current approaches to certification cannot handle the type of uncertainty and dynamic behavior of these novel applications (e.g., Backward Reachability Sets and Learning Safety, Information theoretic Model Predictive Control).</p> <p>Safety Certification: Repeatability of tests is difficult with AI-based systems, hence becoming certification a challenge. Writing requirements and understanding the importance of input data (for learning-based schemes) and the HW/SW contributions for AI in such a way to ensure safety are also challenges. The paper also mentions other contributing factors for the difficulty of certifying AI-based systems specifically for aerial applications. Since these are not within the scope of the DSc. research, they are not herein listed.</p> <p>The main approach of the paper is that the first path for certifying AI-based safety-critical systems shall rely on well-established 'consensus standards', being the ASTM F3269 (Standard Practice For Methods to Safely Bound Flight Behavior of Unmanned Aircraft Systems Containing Complex Functions" being the most prominent one. The F3269 established a Generic Run-Time Architecture in which a safety-critical complex system (e.g. an AI-based one) is functionally and bounded in time by a pedigreed safety monitor and pedigreed recovery control functions.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Main characteristics of the Bounded Behavior Assurance Methodology presented by the authors:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>"During runtime, decisions are taken to optimize mission-effectiveness while simultaneously monitoring system state to determine if behavior is approaching the boundaries of safety. If this happens, mission-effectiveness ceases to become the primary objective; instead corrective action is taken to ensure that system state remains within the acceptable bounds."</i> <i>"The BBA approach to safety assurance requires that acceptable safe system states be identified and formally specified. Doing so becomes a serious challenge as the functional requirements placed upon autonomous systems repeatedly evolve during the life-time of the system." --> Another reference to "unknown unknowns": "what kinds of assurance requirements could be placed upon system behavior in such unanticipated scenarios".</i> Sometimes formal specification is not feasible for AI-based systems (e.g. what is a pedestrian?). <i>"Hence it appears that assurance cases for AI/ML-based perception systems must be based on extensive testing, and assurance arguments explaining why the training data used to train the system should be considered adequate."</i> Ensuring real-time requirements is even more challenging than in current COTS systems: <i>"Novel scheduling and schedulability-analysis approaches are being explored for enabling the application of the BBA approach for assuring timing correctness in autonomous systems using AI/ML based algorithms."</i>
Q5	<p>Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 129 / 550	

Answer	They just propose that "developers, regulators, policymakers, and researchers evaluate the BBA approaches and use them to the maximum extent to realize the promise of artificial intelligence and machine learning in UAS".
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting contextualization within Industry 4.0: "The convergence of processor architectures and communications networks (5G) coupled with the concepts of cloud and edge intelligence seem to be aligning with the specific needs of AI based applications. For the safety conscious aerospace industry, the AI/ML technologies need to be complimented by a strong assurance framework that can unequivocally establish credibility and confidence(...)."</p> <p>2) Contextualization with regulation: " (...) the underlying regulatory and certification processes lag behind and much work needs to be done in order to find the right balance of regulatory constraint and design freedom to innovate and operate."</p> <p>3) Good AI safety assurance overview: "Safety assurance in autonomous systems cannot realistically be looked upon as a single-step process that is completed after system development and prior to deployment; instead, a lifelong approach is required that must be initiated at the very beginning of the design process and continue through the lifetime of the system".</p> <p>4) Overall good convergence of ideas with other related papers.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No discussion on random failures that affect AI except for the fact that AI-based systems, once contained within the BBA approach, shall be safe regardless of what happens to them.</p> <p>2) Little discussion on shortcomings of the research.</p>

8.33 REFERENCE [139]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	<p>To discuss the challenges of safety assurance of autonomous systems and propose a novel framework for safety assurance that, inter alia, uses machine learning to provide evidence for a system safety case and thus enables the safety case to be updated dynamically as system behavior evolves.</p> <p>Main addressed topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges for using AI and ML in autonomous systems, especially on training and testing; - Challenges for analyzing shared autonomy; - Relationship with known limitations of quantitative risk assessment;
Q2 Answer	AI is named in a general way in the paper, but specific mention to Machine Learning techniques is also made
Q3 Answer	<p>Five main flaws of classic safety assessment:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Unrepeatable, e.g. analysis relies on undocumented assumptions; 2) Invalid, e.g. design models not accurate predictors of operational behavior; 3) Valid but inaccurate, e.g. inadequate treatment of uncertainty such as in object classification; 4) Accurate but challengeable, e.g. insufficient scientific knowledge for parts of the analysis (this is likely to be a particular issue for AS using ML); 5) Ideal (unattainable). <p>Main challenges for reinforcement learning-based AI safety assurance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Avoiding negative side effects – ensuring that the behavior meets safety constraints; 2. Avoiding reward hacking – ensuring that the behavior doesn't get a high reward by 'cheating' and thus avoiding the benefit that was sought; 3. Scalable oversight – this concerns the ability of the human to interact with the system both to monitor it, and to respond to requests for confirmation of decisions prior to actions being taken; 4. Safe exploration – if the system can try out new things (new strategies) how can negative outcomes be avoided if these are circumstances that have not been considered so far;

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 130 / 550	

	<p>5. Robustness to distributional shift – how the system adapts to changes in the operational environment.</p> <p>Proposed Framework Basics: The framework includes continued and proactive assessment in operation, drawing on the ‘world as imagined’ (as we have to consider the system and its environment) and the ‘world as observed’ (or the ‘data world’) reflecting the need to analyze operational data to understand and control the identified dissonances. In this context, the safety case is initially created with the ‘world as imagined’ information and then continuously updated with input collected from the ‘world as observed’.</p> <p>The main challenging gaps between both worlds for safety fall into five main categories: gaps in assumptions on the system or the environment, gaps in scope of what is part of the system environment and what is not, gaps in model fidelity, gaps in training data and gaps in uncertainty (inability to model the real world complexity).</p> <p>In addition to these, five more gap categories are inherent to the ‘world as observed’ in relation to the ‘real world’ (i.e. ground truth): gaps in sensing, gaps in algorithms, gaps in failure conditions, gaps in human performance (including designers and other actors), gaps in resource limitations.</p> <p>ML can also be used as part of the safety analysis: e.g. it is unlikely (undesirable) that good coverage of near-accident data will be achieved using real world data – it is too rare, and too dangerous to collect – thus collection must be augmented by simulation data to get good coverage of the operational design domain (ODD), from a safety perspective. As a result, the following issues shall be addressed as well:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The coverage of the ODD in the data used for training and testing, justifying the ‘skew’ in the data to get coverage of ‘demanding’ situations based on the assessment from the safety analysis; The choice between real-world and simulation data, again based on risk assessment, and dealing with the potential problem of distributional shift between the simulator and AV; The rationale for choosing factors that shape the learning process including selection of training and test data sets, and ‘hyperparameters’ (e.g. derivable by correlation among parameters through Bayesian Networks).
Q4 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Random faults affecting an AI-based system shall be dealt with by means of conventional safety processes. 2) Case study with a health IT system which is meant for medication management has been carried out by applying the proposed framework. It allowed, by usage of ML during the safety analysis itself, to quantify the effects of different causes and controls on each associated hazard, enabling the introduction of hazard controls prioritization.
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) As the ideas are evolving the paper shows a ‘direction of travel’, not a finished product. It is hoped that this will help stimulate debate. 2) No evidence of other systems-based approaches, e.g. STPA/STAMP-based analyses, addressing the identified flaws for the identified safety analysis of AI-based systems. More will need to be done to produce an effective safety analysis process for the ‘world as imagined’, and thus improve the safety analysis of AS. 3) Underwriters Laboratory (UL) standard known as UL 4600 will explicitly address some of the requirements on safety cases for AVs employing AI and ML herein discussed. 4) We see the possibility of developing a new and rich socio-technical ‘theory of safety’ that draws together multiple disciplines, including AI, system safety engineering, law and ethics. A key part of this will be reconciling system safety with AI safety – combining system safety’s view of the harm to humans from AS with the understanding from the AI safety community of what might go wrong in AI and ML.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good definition of autonomous system: "AS are best thought of as systems where decisions that would otherwise have been taken by humans are allocated to machines". 2) First paper addressing, albeit marginally with one single sentence, how to deal with random faults on AI-based systems: they shall be addressed by conventional safety process. 3) The Assuring Autonomy International Programme is working on models to show issues relating to ML in Autonomous Systems. 4) Lots of recurring authors: Ashmore, Calinescu, Paternos, Koopman (see e.g. [55], [69]). 5) Wide and interesting view on a systems-level safety analysis of AI-based systems including the main

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 131 / 550	

issues to be addressed during it.	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The approach of addressing random faults on AI-based systems by conventional safety process seems like an OK approach for implementation features (e.g. parameters), but may be too simplistic if random failures affect the system architecture (e.g. changing a HW-based or an SW-based NN layered architecture). Further research about this is interesting.</p> <p>2) If ML is used to support the safety analysis, how can this ML be ensured as safe prior to / during its use? This is not addressed by the authors.</p>
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8.34 REFERENCE [143]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a new approach where formal verification is employed to validate systems with probabilistic predictions. The methodology to validate perception systems is based on a combination of simulation, formal verification, and statistical analysis. A case study based on the formal verification of a simulated probabilistic perception system for automated risk assessment within autonomous vehicles is performed to evaluate the results of the proposed approach.
Q2 Answer	Bayesian sensing fusion and inference.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Verification through formal model is fairly accurate but it becomes more challenging for autonomous systems in dynamic environments. In the context of intelligent vehicle systems, where states (e.g., estimation of collisions) change and evolve at every time step, exhaustively checking such properties is usually not affordable in many scenarios because of time, complexity and costs constraints.</p> <p>Preconditions: Realistic descriptions of the dynamic physical environment, the perception system under study, and the set of relevant scenarios are needed.</p> <p>Safety Analysis: A probabilistic perception system for automated risk assessment based on gridding the perceived space is analyzed by considering an automaton which describes whether the system is safe. No mention to AI is made on the paper except for the fact that the probabilistic perception system employs Bayesian reasoning to fuse sensing data and decide the next system states for its decision.</p>
Q4 Answer	A case study of a four-way crossroad with one autonomous vehicle crossing it and up to one non-autonomous vehicle concurring has been studied. A deterministic PID control system has been assumed for all vehicles, which travel at a fixed steering angle in such a way that only perpendicular collision is possible. The results indicate that, in at least 15% of the predicted cases (confidence lower than 90%), a collision between both vehicles is plausible, since the probabilistic risk assessment system aboard the autonomous vehicle would fail to detect a near-collision situation.
Q5 Answer	<p>1) Future inclusion of changes to vehicle velocities (variable speeds and changes in direction).</p> <p>2) Consider some more frequent and realistic urban situations, such as stopping behind another vehicle at a stop light or driving for hours.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Low relevance to the research, since only traditional probabilistic autonomy is used.</p> <p>2) No analysis regarding random or systematic failures is presented by the authors.</p>

8.35 REFERENCE [151]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	<p>To propose a general safety framework based on Hamilton–Jacobi reachability methods that can work with an arbitrary learning algorithm by exploiting approximate knowledge of the system dynamics to guarantee constraint satisfaction while minimally interfering with the learning process. Furthermore, a Bayesian mechanism is introduced to refine the safety analysis with new evidence acquired by the system, reducing initial conservativeness while performing real-time validation.</p> <p>A case study based on a quadrotor vehicle in a real world test is performed to support the soundness of the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 132 / 550	

	proposed framework.
Q2 Answer	Learning-based models in general, focusing especially on deep learning methods and stochastic prediction.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Restraining the safe operation of an AI-based system with external systems that limit AI or switching to manual operation is not deemed appropriate by the authors. "It therefore seems imperative to develop principled and provably correct approaches to safety, attuned to the exploration-intensive needs of learning-based algorithms that can be built into the autonomous operation of learning robotic systems."</p> <p>Main features of a safe learning framework: "1) High confidence: The framework should be able to keep the system safe with high probability given the available knowledge about the system and the environment. 2) Modularity: The framework should work in conjunction with an arbitrary learning-based control algorithm, without requiring modifications to said algorithm. 3) Minimal intervention: The framework should not interfere with the learning process unless deemed strictly necessary to ensure safety, and should return control to the learning algorithm as soon as possible."</p> <p>Basics: "A general safety framework that combines model-based control-theoretical analysis with data-driven Bayesian inference to construct and maintain high-probability guarantees around an arbitrary learning-based control algorithm. Drawing on Hamilton–Jacobi robust optimal control techniques, it defines a least-restrictive supervisory control law, which allows the system to freely execute its learning based policy almost everywhere, but imposes a computed action at states where it is deemed critical for safety. The safety analysis is refined through Bayesian inference in light of newly gathered evidence, both avoiding excessive conservativeness and improving reliability by rapidly imposing the computed safe actions if confidence in model-based guarantees decreases due to unexpected observations." It includes "a method for reasoning about the uncertain system dynamics, using Gaussian processes to regularly update the model used for safety analysis, and introduce a Bayesian approach for online validation of model-based guarantees in between updates. We then define an adaptive safety control strategy based on this real-time validation, which leverages the theoretical results from Hamilton–Jacobi analysis to provide stronger guarantees for safe learning under possible model inaccuracies." "The safety problem can be posed as a two-player zero-sum differential game between the system controller and the disturbance. Intuitively, we are requiring the controller to keep the system from violating the constraints for all possible disturbance inputs within a certain family: by conducting a worst-case analysis assuming an optimally adversarial disturbance, we implicitly protect the system against all "suboptimal" disturbances as well."</p> <p>Precondition: Method applicable to "a fully observable system whose underlying dynamics are assumed deterministic, but only partially known", i.e., "systems for which an approximate dynamic model is available but the exact behavior is hard to model a priori".</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>1) "Not only is safety a key requirement for learning in autonomous systems: learning about the real-system's behavior is itself indispensable to provide practical safety guarantees."</p> <p>2) "(...) this is the first work in the area of reachability analysis that reasons online about the validity of computed guarantees and uses a resilient mechanism to continue exploiting them under inaccurate prior assumptions on model error."</p> <p>3) All processing of the safe learning scheme proposed by the authors relies on an arbitrary global confidence threshold for which the safety behavior of the learning controller definitely holds. If this threshold is not observed, a safe controller overrides the learning agent.</p> <p>4) Evaluating the expression which defines the safety global confidence probability is computationally intensive and can limit the practicality of this method for real-time validation of safety guarantees in some applications. an alternative is to replace the global safety analysis with a local criterion that offers faster computation with a weaker (locally valid only) safety guarantee.</p> <p>5) Case Study - Experiment 1: A quadrotor helicopter with a safe learning controller as specified by the authors has been subject to poor initialization in order to check its ability to learn, even in far-from-ideal scenarios, a safe behavior which retains it within the safe envelope and minimizes the action of the safe controller that ensures the safety envelope. After several attempts for the first 30s in trying this with no</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 133 / 550	

	<p>success (an being bounded by the safe controller), the learning agent is finally able to operate safely on its own. "The remarkable result in this experiment is not in the quality of the learned tracking controller after only a few seconds of active exploration (a merit that corresponds to the reinforcement learning method), but the system's ability to achieve competent performance at its task from an extremely poor initial policy while remaining safe at all times."</p> <p>6) Case Study - Experiment 2: The quadrotor helicopter is meant to follow a specific trajectory. In this scenario, the safe controller overrides the learning agent twice, but in over 20s the learning agent takes full control of the quadrotor helicopter with no safety issues (95% confidence).</p> <p>7) Case Study - Experiment 3: The quadrotor is subject to external disturbance (lateral wind). In this scenario, the safe controller overrides the learning agent to avoid crashing with the ground due to the wind.</p>
Q5 Answer	"Scaling up safety certificates as intelligent systems achieve increasing complexity poses an important open-research problem. Our prediction is that, as autonomous systems interact increasingly closely with human beings, the graceful interplay of safety and learning, combining theoretical guarantees with empirical grounding, will become central to their success."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good contextualization of the main challenge for safety analysis of learning-based systems. It is well aligned with McDermid's view on the 'world as imagined', the 'world as observed' and the 'real world': "Current efforts in policy transfer learning propose training an initial control policy in simulation and then carrying it over to the physical system. While progress in this direction is likely to reduce overall training time, it does not eliminate the risk of catastrophic system misbehavior. State-of-the-art neural network policies have been shown to be vulnerable to small changes between training and testing conditions, which inevitably arise between simulated and real systems. Guaranteeing correct behavior of simulation-trained schemes in the real world thus remains an important unsolved problem."</p> <p>2) Good history of safe learning evolution (see section "I-A" for more details). Summary: 1st Generation: Several safe controllers switched by a learning agent which decided the most suitable one with time. 2nd Generation: Minimize the risk of reaching an error state based on heuristic weights on the expected return. 3rd Generation: Ergodicity-based safe exploration policy for Markov processes with uncertain transition measures with the constraint of potentially being able to return to the starting state from any state. 4th Generation: AI is limited by a 'safe envelope'. Good for safety, but may overly constrain performance. 5th Generation: Differential game in which the controller shall keep the system within the safety-related specified constraints despite of actions of an adversarial disturbance. Optimal solution is obtained by the Hamilton-Jacobi reachability algorithm.</p> <p>3) Strong mathematical background.</p> <p>4) Despite claiming that the proposed method does not bound AI, it actually does exactly this by having a safety controller which overrides the system learning agent.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) Due to the strong mathematical background, some parts are difficult to be understood. 2) No analysis regarding random or systematic failures is presented by the authors.</p>

8.36 REFERENCE [154]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present a verification methodology based on the statistical testing of autonomous vehicles safety-related functionality in simulated scenarios. A test-case implementation of the methodology on a full-scale autonomous unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) focusing on verifying the functionality of safe autonomous off-road navigation is also presented.
Q2 Answer	No specific mention to AI techniques or AI in general is made throughout the paper.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 134 / 550	

Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: To what extent can [design experience heuristic/statistics-based algorithms can be trusted with regard to safety and collision avoidance in autonomous vehicles?</p> <p>Basics: "The methodology is based on Statistical Scenarios Testing using the Monte Carlo method in a Simulated Environment. The use of simulation reduces the logistical complexity; implementation of Monte Carlo sampling allows avoiding statistical bias as result of human presumption. Finally, concentration on scenarios instead of mileage is more efficient and avoids the potential statistical bias as a result of vast millage on open roads with no safety-related circumstances." It also "suggests and demonstrates solutions for (...) how long a single scenario shall last, and what shall be done to validate that the simulations sufficiently represent reality."</p> <p>The methodology has five steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) System Requirements Specification: Aims to "unambiguously define the Algorithm Under Test (AUT) requirements regarding safety; this is done in terms of the Scenario Domains (SD) that represent the UGV work environment and Performance Assessment Functions (PAF) that represent safety critical events, prevention of which needs to be proven." The duration of the scenarios is also thought of in this step. in order to ensure that the quantitative safety target can be appropriately assessed with confidence. 2) Development of the Simulation Framework: Performed preferably by another team using the SD and PAF. At this step, "some unavoidable modeling inaccuracies will remain, we deal with these inaccuracies by introducing a mechanism that allows control of the severity of the AUT interfaces with the simulation testing environment. I.e., the delay and noise on the AUT input channels from the sensors, and on the AUT output channels to the platform throttle, brakes, and steering actuators." "(...) if the sensors and vehicle modeling inaccuracies are absorbed within the more severe input and output conditions, the AUT is proven to be robust to these inaccuracies." 3) Automatic Testing: Performed with "random sampling of thousands of scenarios from the SD and evaluate the AUT performances according to the PAF." 4) [Optional] Manual Inspection: Corresponds to a "sanity check of the simulation results" before the final step. 5) Real World Performance Validation: At this step, "the AUT is tested in a relatively small number of real world experiments, and the performances are statistically compared to the simulation results. The outcome of this comparison should ratify the simulation results, and allow deduction of compliance with safety requirements." It is checked with operational data that the hypotheses raised during simulation are satisfied with an adequate confidence.
Q4 Answer	<p>Case Study: The methodology is presented with detail, and results of its implementation on a real full-scale UGV (RobIL) system are presented. These results indicate that statistical performance data that are gathered using simulation can be used to accurately predict the overall safety performance of Unmanned Ground Vehicles. It has been checked that simulated results led to a failure probability of 0.94% for travelling a 100m graveled area with obstacles (95% confidence) and that a similar result has been obtained in practical tests.</p>
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "The performance of the RobIL UGV that was used as a test case, at this point is far from satisfying the requirements of safety standards and stand on a failure probability of about 1% per scenario." 2) " (...) it is important to see the difficulties of implementing the methodology on autonomous UGVs with more complex behaviors than the ones currently demonstrated by RobIL. These difficulties are mainly two: first the definition of SD that will be complete and genuinely express all possible scenarios that the UGV might encounter, and second, a truly random sampling of this SD. The first challenge of complete and exact SD definition will probably get a response by international projects like Pegasus that already now work on construction of libraries of testing scenarios for autonomous vehicles. The second challenge of designing a procedural generation technique that will produce even and random coverage is an open problem, which will be addressed in our future work."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization of a simulation-based safety analysis approach within a systems deployment process. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No specifically AI-related random faults were taken into account by the authors (e.g. in case they are implemented by means of programmable hardware). 2) The authors mention they consider the occurrence of random faults within the underlying sensing and acting hardware; however, it is not clear how this was performed, since the delays and noises introduced

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 135 / 550	

	<p>within the model aim to attempt to model real-world imperfections. If faults are within the scope of these effects, it seems that the modeling of failures as noise and delays may not cover some random faults the way they were implemented (e.g. it is not clear if losses may be represented by a delay and intermittent faults may be represented by a frequency-specific noise).</p> <p>3) The case study scope seems very restricted, and it is not clear if the approach can scale well to a wide variety of scenarios (especially in applications that are harder to control, e.g., aircraft) to be tested in such a way that significant confidence for meeting safety standards is reached and proved by a reduced set of physical tests.</p>
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8.37 REFERENCE [156]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a qualitative safety assurance method for machine learning-based system based on seven system layers: "1) internal and external system, 2) different states of the system, 3) the factors of the accidents in the system, 4) operating conditions of the system, 5) ML and safety device operation process, 6) output rules of the safety devices, and 7) output restriction method of the safety device" . A case study with a ML-based train braking system is presented to exercise the proposed method.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: It is difficult to assess whether ML is safe prior to its operation: "it is difficult to estimate its performance in advance, and it is not possible to grasp the boundaries between what can be done and what cannot be done" (Ishikawa, 2019).</p> <p>Scope: A qualitative safety assessment method that aims to ensure safety throughout the system incorporating machine learning and safety device. It does not focus on the internal features of the AI.</p> <p>Method: Based on describing the system safety arguments with GSN (Goal Structuring Notation) in seven layers. From top to bottom layers: "1) Internal and external system: Decomposing whether to assure the safety inside or outside of the system including machine learning. 2) Different states of the system: Decomposing whether a system that includes machine learning assures safety under normal conditions or emergent condition. In an emergency, whether to prioritize safety inside of the system and in the form of trade-off between the external system and internal system. 3) The factors of the accident in the system: Decomposing by accident factor that can be detected in advance when an emergent situation occurs. 4) Operating conditions of the system: Decomposing according to operating conditions of the system including machine learning. 5) ML and safety device operation process: Decomposing according to the operation process of machine learning and safety device. 6) Output rules of the safety device: Decomposing according to safety device output rules in the operation process of the system including machine learning. 7) Output restriction method of the safety device: Decomposing by the output restriction method defined in the safety device."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A case study was carried out by asking safety professionals not necessarily knowledgeable on AI to apply the proposed method for the safety assurance of a train braking system which features a ML-based jerk control and a safety module (non AI-based) that delimits the maximum speed for applying brakes regardless of jerk control.</p> <p>The authors consider the premise that an AI-based safety-related system can be assured as safe only if the AI is delimited by a non-AI-based safety module.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) We can propose a method to assure the safety of a system incorporating on-operational machine learning that learns in real time.</p> <p>2) Since this description method is the description method of the fifth layer-the seventh layer among the seven layers, there is a proposal of the description method of the first layer-the fourth layer.</p> <p>3) We would like to study whether it can be described in the same way in systems other than the brake system incorporating the machine learning.</p> <p>4) Since the description method of this study was conducted in Japanese, it can be a theme of this study as to</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 136 / 550	

	whether it can be written as another language.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) It improves, albeit marginally, the way of formally building a safety case with GSN for AI-based systems. 2) It clearly states the authors' premise that an AI-based safety-related system can be assured as safe only if the AI is delimited by a non-AI-based safety module. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) It does not expand on AI except for the aforementioned premise; 2) The case study has been carried out successfully with only two safety professionals, hence compromising statistical validity. The full sample of participants, including those will less-than-ideal results, has not been stated by the authors

8.38 REFERENCE [160]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present an overview of the US regulatory framework for Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs - SAE Level 4), heavily based on AI, and the issues of slow-paced efforts to implement a similar framework on South Korea.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general. There are mentions to specific techniques used in HAVs (e.g. neural networks, deep structured learning, reinforcement learning and convolutional neural networks for sensor fusion).
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: The following points are raised for discussion regarding the deployment of HAVs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) How to certify HAVs? Is it needed to certify them at systems-level or only at specific modules? 2) Can AI be safety certified solely by means of automated tests in simulated environments, or is extensive runtime tests on roads needed? 3) Is it better for AI to learn how to drive on their own instead of trying to mimic humans? <p>The authors advocate that physical tests on real tracks for long hours is needed for assuring that an HAV is safe. Self-certification by manufacturers themselves may also be carried out.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors present the US regulations for certifying HAVs (notably their instances on Michigan and California) and compare them with the South Korea regulation. The paper is process-oriented and does not detail technical aspects regarding AI.</p> <p>For self-certification, a strong regulatory body is needed in order to normalize the standards to which the system shall comply so as to be certified.</p>
Q5 Answer	The paper is not related to the research; as a result, its results are not herein detailed.
Q6 Answer	The paper is not related to the research; as a result, its results are not herein detailed.

8.39 REFERENCE [161]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To provide a framework for reasoning about the contribution of performance evidence to the assurance case for machine learning in an automated driving context and applies the evaluation criteria to a pedestrian recognition case study.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, with specific mention to Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Main challenges for machine learning safety assurance in general [159]: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Distributional shift: Critical or ambiguous situations, within which the system must react in a predictably safe manner, may occur rarely or may be so dangerous that they are not well represented in the training data (same as item "2)"). Data cannot be biased. b) Robustness deficits of the trained function: Adversarial perturbation (input sample that is similar to other samples but that leads to a completely different categorization with a high confidence value) can be automatically generated and used to trick the network. The challenge, therefore, is to ensure that the machine learning algorithms focus on those properties of the inputs relevant to the target function without becoming distracted by irrelevant features (see also [55], [90], [117], [149]).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 137 / 550	

Q4 Answer	<p>c) Differences between the training and execution platforms: The input to the neural network will have typically been processed by a number of elements which may vary between the training and target execution environments (e.g. sensor characteristics), leading to the trained function becoming dependent on hidden features of the training environment not relevant in the target system (see also [55] - "completeness" feature).</p> <p>2) Main Assurance Claim Points (ACPs) for ML-based safety-critical systems: ACP1 and ACP2 shall be ensured at systems level, whereas ACP3 onwards are ensured by ML design.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ACP1: Argument that the assumptions made on the operational design domain as well as on the interfaces to other technical components within the system are valid. – ACP2: Argument that the benchmark performance requirements allocated to the guarantees of the safety contract for the MLM are sufficient to fulfill the overall system safety requirements. – ACP3: Argument that the adopted training process and the choice of model and hyperparameters lead to a function that fulfills its requirements. – ACP4: Argument that the training data are sufficient to lead to a MLM that fulfills its performance requirements. – ACP5: Argument that the test data that is used is sufficient to support the performance claim. – ACP6: Argument that the performance evidence generated from the test data is sufficient to support the performance claim. <p>3) ACPs are satisfied when the system behavior meets the ground truth (in line with McDermid's views on "what the system is designed to do" (specification world), "what the operator thinks the system is doing" (implementation world), and "what the system is actually doing" (real world - i.e., ground truth). It is considered that the assurance case claim that the machine learning function fulfills its guarantees has a conditional probability. It is necessary to define a measurement value threshold provided by the evidence E that, if reached, is postulated to imply that the Contract Performance target is met.</p> <p>4) The evidence E could represent simply tests on selected inputs and return the proportion of tests that passed, or a more indirect measure that is used to infer the performance of the machine learning function such as the robustness towards adversarial perturbations.</p> <p>E.g.: For ACP5, the evidence E shall allow the following claims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The sample set used to provide performance evidence is capable of detecting faults in the machine learning function that would lead to a violation of performance requirements. – The sample set is representative of the input domain and the application of the performance evaluation on this sample set leads to a representative indication of the measurement target for the entire domain. <p>For ACP6, the evidence E shall allow the following claims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a demonstrable correlation between the Measurement Target and the Contract Performance. – The measurements based on the sample set can be extrapolated to provide an indication of the expected performance for the entire input domain even in the case of root unknown causes of insufficiencies (in ISO PAS 21448 defined as unknown triggering events).
Q5 Answer	<p>The proposed safety analysis method is applied to a pedestrian recognition case study, which is within the scope of highly automated vehicles.</p> <p>Main safety requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Pedestrians of width X pixels and height Y pixels are classified. – There are less than FP% of false positive classifications per frame. – There are less than FN% of false negative classifications per frame. – Vertical deviation from the ground truth is less than V pixels. – Horizontal deviation from the ground truth is less than H pixels. – Pedestrians are detected if C% of the person is occluded. --> requirement considered in the case study. <p>Qualitative claims for assurance of test data sets and adversarial attacks were presented in Table 2 and Table 3, which show that each individual performance evaluation technique is limited according to a certain set of constraints and assumptions.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) Future work will focus on deepening the understanding of insufficiencies in the MLMs by performing sensitivity analysis for a wider range of features whilst providing stronger confidence arguments for any proposed evidence to support the performance claim.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 138 / 550	

	<p>2) The authors also propose the use of confidence arguments in future standardization efforts in order to better motivate the contribution of particular evaluation techniques, or to provide a framework by which the use of any particular combination of techniques can be justified for a particular system context.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting contextualization for the importance of AI safety analysis within the autonomous vehicles application area: <i>"ISO PAS 21448 addresses the "Safety of the Intended Functionality" by considering such effects. However, this standard is currently focused on Level 1 to 2 driver assistance systems rather than Level 3 to 5 HAD systems which include higher levels of autonomy and for which machine learning is seen as a key enabling technology."</i></p> <p>2) Another paper reinforcing the opaqueness of AI as a challenge for their usage in safety-critical systems: <i>"The lack of a precise specification combined with the unpredictable and opaque nature of the algorithms introduce high degrees of uncertainty into the safety assurance process."</i></p> <p>3) Well-structured safety analysis method, generally applicable to any system (i.e., not restricted to highly automated vehicles).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Performance parameters necessary for building the safety assurance claims may be difficult to define for certain applications (e.g. how does one define that 95% success, and not a different figure, is sufficiently safe for detecting occluded pedestrians?). The authors do not discuss this matter on their paper.</p> <p>2) Similarly to "1", how does one define the ML architecture that suits the application? According to the authors, testing data cannot be used with this purpose (e.g. due to errors in data extrapolation and masking of robustness issues), but no further detail is provided.</p> <p>3) Case study is not deepened enough to exercise the proposed method in a sound way.</p>

8.40 REFERENCE [163]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To introduce a concept for runtime safety analysis and decision input for open adaptive systems (with reconfiguration) by combining static safety analysis and evidence collected during operation to analyze, reason and provide online recommendations to minimize deviation from a system's safe states
Q2 Answer	Bayesian networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: The authors deem that research using Dynamic Safety Certificates (DSCs) and ConSerts for the safety assurance of dynamic systems have limitations because "(...) both DSC and ConSerts rely on the use of binary conditional variables to evaluate guarantees".</p> <p>In order to circumvent these issues, the authors propose expansions on these contract-based approaches in the following ways:</p> <p>"– We introduce the use of Bayesian Networks (BNs) as an alternate inference mechanism for probabilistic reasoning of guarantees. BNs provide means of expressing uncertainty and accounting for uncertainty in the assurance process.</p> <p>– Beyond inference, our expanded framework also proposes recommended actions to be applied to minimize system risk during operation; these actions are predefined and linked to a state machine. This element allows the system to address partially unanticipated scenarios by re-evaluating previous assumptions about the state of the system and responding appropriately."</p> <p>Pre-condition: "(...) we assume that during design stage, it is possible to foresee all the different possible states a system can be in during operation. The only a priori unknown is the actual state of the system at a given point during operation."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>To illustrate the proposed methodology, the authors present its application within an abstract vehicle platooning system use case.</p> <p>The case study was carried out considering the safety goal "avoid violation of the safe distance and legal speed limit" from the perspectives of both leading and follower vehicles within a smart traffic infrastructure</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 139 / 550	

	environment. The safety characteristic is quantified with a GeNIe-coded Bayesian Network.
Q5 Answer	<p>The proposed frameworks requires that all possible system states (i.e., configurations) can be foreseen at design time.</p> <p>"(...) we aim to integrate our proposed framework with the concept of the DDI. DDIs aim to support modularity, composition, seamless exchange and evaluation of the associated dependability artifacts at runtime."</p> <p>"Further avenues of investigation include linking the proposed approach with ConSerts. By combining modular and conditional certification with probabilistic reasoning and runtime monitoring, a larger section of the development lifecycle could be supported via relevant model-based techniques."</p> <p>"Further, an assumption of our current approach is that the actions for mitigating safety risk defined from each system state have deterministic outcomes. A more robust framework would ideally be capable of deciding on actions with uncertain effect as well."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting usage of Bayesian Networks to support the safety analysis of dynamic systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors did not mention how the Bayesian Network probabilities were obtained for the case study. It probably requires some AI model for training and learning with new data as the system operates.</p>

8.41 REFERENCE [165]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	<p>To investigate how training data uncertainty affects the strategy and the activities for safety assurance of machine learning-based systems by employing a tool-based attribute testing method for evaluating the implementation of a explicitly/partially specified model.</p> <p>A case study with experimental results that demonstrate how safety arguments are affected by machine learning uncertainty using the developed tool is also presented.</p>
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: It is difficult or even impossible to be confident of completeness in safety arguments with Machine Learning. In these situations, it may be more interesting to continuously resolve uncertainty and react to expected or unexpected changes, known as 'continuous argument engineering'.</p> <p>Study: Developing a tool to support 'continuous argument engineering'. It communicates with the system under test/operation to collect ML-related performance parameters (e.g. accuracy, loss, epoch number).</p>
Q4 Answer	The case study is based on training data collected from the CIFAR10 data set for image recognition and two ML-based systems implemented with convolutional neural networks. leverages the conclusion that a model which cannot be predicted beforehand has weaknesses and that the developed tool for continuous argument engineering is interesting to track the latest state of assurance.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting introduction to the issue of uncertainty in ML-based system;</p> <p>2) Usage of GSN notation for describing the safety arguments, as well as considering continuous argument engineering' reasoning is in line with the trend of other related papers.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The paper is too brief on technicalities regarding 'continuous argument reasoning' and focuses on using a Web-based tool for performing it.</p> <p>2) No shortcomings were discussed by the authors (e.g. next steps for the research, how the proposed tool can be properly connected to a system in order to allow the 'continuous argument engineering').</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 140 / 550	

8.42 REFERENCE [166]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present three steps towards the development of autonomous cyber-physical systems in such a way to provide formal verification to ensure their safe behavior.
Q2 Answer	AI in general, with special mention to Machine Learning. The proposed model leans towards safe reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: To combine AI and formal methods in a way that each field actually retains its benefits for the CPS in the end. CPS has discrete control actions in the cyber world resulting in continuous control actions / results in the physical world.</p> <p>First Step: Differential dynamic logic (dL) provides a logical foundation for developing cyber-physical system models with the mathematical rigor that their safety-critical nature demands. Focus is on reinforcement learning-based systems. -> CPS Modeling: The CPS has more than one control action (i.e., it is non-deterministic) and, for every control action, it keeps operating according to a differential equation within the continuous state. This is cyclically repeated throughout the operating time. -> Model Safety: Aims to obtain a proof (approx. 2kloc for its core when possible) that the system is safe if it satisfies a safety formula in any initial state and reaches other safety formulas at all states reached by the system. Preconditions for the control action may be discovered and defined during this process (e.g. constraining maximum speed for applying brakes safely). -> Aims to allow Reinforcement Learning to optimize the action choice.</p> <p>Second Step: Its ModelPlex technique provides a logically correct way to tame the subtle relationship of CPS models to CPS implementations. The basic principle is that ModelPlex synthesizes a monitor along with a dL correctness proof for it, stating that the real implementation is safe as long as it satisfies that runtime monitor (and will always remain safe when continuing the model). Since the logical monitor is challenging to implement learning algorithms in a provably correct way, the continued use of ModelPlex monitors after deployment is advisable even if ModelPlex monitor outputs were used to steer learning toward safe answers during training. -> Generates safe reward signals to Reinforcement Learning.</p> <p>Third Step: The resulting logical monitor conditions can then be synthesized into executable code proven to be safe (given the physical model is correctly expressed within the cyber implementation) and explored to safeguard the decisions of learning agents, guide the optimization of learning processes, and resolve the non-determinism frequently found in verification models. -> CPS sandbox / implementation for Reinforcement Learning.</p>
Q4 Answer	Since the objective of the paper was to present a three-step conceptual model towards the development and verification of cyber-physical autonomous systems and that the latter has been detailed in the response to Question 3, there are no additional results to be herein presented. No case study or mathematical proof has been presented by the authors.
Q5 Answer	The hypotheses only hold under the assumption of bounded deviations in sensing and acting. "If literally all sensors and actuators of a CPS could be arbitrarily wrong, then no connection can be made between the suspected and real state of the system. But even if sensors are almost always a little wrong, they are not usually all that wrong, which enables a logical angle of attack for guarantees despite bounded sensing errors. How can concrete bounds be substantiated for sensor errors with as little doubt as possible? an answer to this question is the true challenge beyond recent progress in verified perception."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization with easy-to-understand introduction and high-level mathematical basis for formally proving that an AI-based system (with reinforced learning) is safe. 2) Good summary for safety assurance of AI: "A white-box model is required to obtain guarantees even if only an executable model is needed during learning". 3) Reinforces that sensors and actuators are important for the safe behavior of a cyber-physical system (notably an AI-based one). <p>Weaknesses:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 141 / 550	

1) The study is preliminary and highly conceptual, hence lacking practical applications and an overview of how long it takes for the approach to be actually used in real systems.

8.43 REFERENCE [167]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To suggest that, while complete specifications may not be possible, partial specification typically are and these could be used with ML to strengthen safety assurance by reviewing the types of partial specifications that are applicable for these problems and discuss the places in the ML development workflow that they could be used to improve the safety of ML-based components.
Q2 Answer	Supervised machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: "<i>Safety standards such as ISO 26262 do not focus on explicitly measuring and reducing error rates of software. Instead, they define the development rigor needed to reduce the error rate to an acceptable level by recommending specific development methods.</i>"</p> <p>"(...) <i>many kinds of advanced automated driving functionality require perception of the environment, and this functionality may not be completely specifiable. (...) There is evidence that such categories can only partially be specified using rules and also need examples. This has been long understood in the field of cognitive linguistics.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>The training set is necessarily incomplete and there is no guarantee that it is even representative of the space of possible inputs. (...) Furthermore, the training process cannot be considered to be equivalent to a verification process since the trained model will be "correct by construction" with respect to the training set, up to the limits of the model and the learning algorithm.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>We propose to reduce the safety assurance gap of developing ML components purely through training by instead considering (...) a partial specification [which] (...) should be used to augment the training dataset.</i>" This topic is explored for supervised learning."</p> <p>Specification Language: It should be interpretable and formal, provide abstraction of what it specified, accommodate uncertainty and be appropriate for the input domain. A partial specification admits at least one output value for every legal input I, hence allowing some uncertainty about the output for some inputs.</p> <p>Verification Approach: It includes four steps for a supervised learning-based with partial specification:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Dataset verification: It aims to check whether data has been properly labeled prior to the ML training. "<i>Constrained sampling has been proposed as a way to generate examples satisfying constraints. Invariants and equivariants can be used to generate new samples from existing ones. For example, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have been used to implement transformations that can convert a scene into another one with different attributes such as adding snow, rain, etc.</i>" 2) Generalization assessment: It aims to check if the selected ML model is appropriate and if the trained model generalizes well for inputs outside the training sets (e.g. cross-validation). If issues are detected, hyperparameters shall be retuned; 3) Model verification: If the model generalizes well, its performance indicators (e.g. accuracy, precision, recall, f1 score, ROC area) are checked, as well as formal analyses are performed. "<i>Falsification for ML is the process of efficiently finding inputs that produce the wrong output. Formal verification requires the ability to prove that the partial specification logically follows from the content of a trained model. (...) Static analysis involves property checking of the ML model. Work in this direction includes an SMT solver and the use of abstract interpretation [7] for checking properties of DNNs.</i>" 4) Model runtime verification: "3)" is repeated periodically during the system operation. <p>On "3)" and "4)", architectural consideration is also performed; for instance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) "<i>A fail-safe architecture can be obtained by using a high integrity error checking monitor that disables the functionality on error and transitions the system to a safe state.</i>" b) "<i>Another architectural configuration is to "gate" the ML component by putting it in series after a programmed implementation of the partial specification</i>", e.g., ML would only be triggered if the inputs meets sufficient conditions and do not violate necessary conditions. c) A simplex architecture (inherently fail-safe) "<i>(...) can be used when there is a conservative, but verifiably</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 142 / 550	

	<p>safe, version of the classifier in addition to the ML-based classifier."</p> <p>Conclusion: "A key observation impacting safety is that the different methods vary in assurance strength", since some guarantee safety, some provide safety evidence and some influence safety. "While [the two latter are] not ideal, this type of partial assurance can be combined and coupled with other sources of evidence (e.g., system level testing results) to make a stronger safety argument."</p>
Q4 Answer	The result of the paper is the verification process itself. No case studies were presented by the authors to support the feasibility of the method.
Q5 Answer	<p>1) Future research shall expand the topic for other machine learning techniques apart from supervised learning (e.g. unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning, etc.).</p> <p>2) "Most methods are applicable to any specification type but the verification related methods are biased toward logic-based specifications. This points to a gap in the research."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Excellent background on flaws of current standards and challenges related to incomplete specification verification of AI-based systems. "One response to the inadequacy of safety standards is the recent release of the standard ISO/PAS 21448. This moves toward addressing ML (specifically in Annex G) and the corresponding limitations of functions ML is used to implement. However, the focus is heavily on testing and only lightly on verification thus, the specification issue remains."</p> <p>2) Interesting safety analysis framework for supervised learning, well in line with what could be proposed during the DSc. It can be joined with the research of papers proposing a "W-shaped" development process for further generalization regardless of the ML model [443].</p> <p>3) Very well aligned to the expectancies of the DSc.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No case studies have been provided by the authors.</p>

8.44 REFERENCE [170]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a model-driven approach for the safety analysis during the design stage based on simulated fault injection and a virtual robot. A tool has been developed with the purpose of supporting this objective.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	<p>Justification: Fault injection enables quantitative safety assessment which is not possible with other techniques that are qualitative (e.g. FMECA).</p> <p>Basics: The fault injection framework developed by the authors allows performing simulation-based fault injection on a system which is described by a SysML-based logical model. The fault injection framework has software patterns that try to sabotage the system by injecting several types of failure modes during the simulated functional operation (also generated by the framework), hence allowing to analyze the behavior of the system under analysis.</p>
Q4 Answer	A case study applying the proposed model to the design of a real-time Cartesian impedance control system in torque mode is employed to demonstrate its feasibility. The authors show scenarios in which fault injection allowed identifying potentially unsafe situations which could be circumvented by means of a system architecture change.
Q5 Answer	<p>1) A higher degree of automation between the different safety artifacts would be beneficial.</p> <p>2) Besides, on the path towards autonomous robots, the framework could further be utilized to simulate error injections by generating erroneous patterns, such as flipped images from image sensors. By doing so, these input tests can evaluate the residual risk arising from real-life situations that could trigger a hazardous behavior of the system when integrated in a robot.</p> <p>3) Extensions to consider not only safety but security could be investigated.</p>
Q6	Strengths:

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 143 / 550	

Answer	<p>1) Interesting references for safety assurance of robotic systems: ISO 12100, ISO 13849 and IEC 62061.</p> <p>2) Good background on fault injection: "Fault injection is a common technique for validating the effectiveness of fault tolerance mechanisms by studying the behavior of the system in presence of faults. The effects of software or hardware faults are emulated by randomly changing code or data at different software locations. However, with the increasing size of software in today's complex systems, it is a challenging task to define specific fault types and locations that can effectively emulate realistic fault scenarios. (...) [the] fault injection environment FARM (Faults, Activation, Readouts, Measurements) is composed of: (1) the set of Faults to be injected, (2) the set of Activations exercised during the experiment, (3) the Readouts to define observers of system behavior, and (4) the Measures obtained to evaluate safety properties. (...) techniques are divided into hardware-based fault injection, software-based fault injection or simulated-based fault injection. (...) In order to carry out simulation-based fault injection experiments, the hardware model or the software state of the target system is modified, which allows simulating the effect of a hardware fault in the system.(...) Three of the main advantages of this technique are (i) the prevention of damage to the target system, (ii) reduced cost compared to other techniques such as hardware-implemented fault injection, (iii) higher observability and controllability of the experiments. The main drawbacks are in terms of fault representativeness and simulation time. The user should select an appropriate fault model and represent it accordingly so that the results of the fault injection simulations are meaningful. Thus, the fidelity of the results strongly depends on the accuracy of the models used."</p> <p>3) Interesting idea for AI-based systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) The paper does not consider specificities of AI; hence, challenges for AI validation even with fault injection are not discussed.</p>
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8.45 REFERENCE [175]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose a novel safety analysis method called Classification Failure Mode Effects Analysis (CFMEA) which is specialized to assess classification-based perception in automated driving (AD) so as to define a systematic way to assess the risk due to classification failure under adversarial attacks or varying degrees of classification uncertainty across the perception-control linkage.
Q2 Answer	Machine Learning in general, with specific usage on classifiers.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Traditional safety analysis methods do not address the unique characteristics of ML-based perception in automated driving.</p> <p>Basics: The proposed CFMEA approach features four key features: 1) Abstraction: Classification is typically a hierarchical process and we model this hierarchy by abstracting it from the classification pipeline in order to systematically enumerate the possible classification faults. The AD control system is abstracted as a control policy that assigns different actions to perceived states of the environment and the subject vehicle. Classification failure modes and correct classifications, collectively called classification cases, all take the same form and can be systematically and exhaustively enumerated. 2) Uncertainty: Using fine-grained probabilities directly in safety analyses may add unnecessary complexity when different safety impacts of uncertainty correspond to discrete regions of the uncertainty space. Leaf classes of the class hierarchy represent high-certainty classification, whereas higher level classes indicate degrees of classification uncertainty. The classification hierarchy can be a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) allowing relevant states of uncertainty to be reified as non-leaf classes as necessary. The benefit of using under-classification to represent states of classification uncertainty (rather than directly using the probability distribution) is that it treats all degrees of uncertainty in a uniform way as a class that the classifier could assign to an input. This both allows a control policy to handle uncertain classification in the same way as confidence classification by assigning actions to classes and allows the CFMEA safety analysis to be rigorous about completeness in addressing all relevant states of uncertainty. The classification class with the minimum risk / greater confidence / lower uncertainty can be obtained as either the one which maximizes the probability of correctness or minimizes the class entropy. If most of the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 144 / 550	

	<p>probability mass is evenly concentrated in a subset of two or more classes, then this indicates that considers the input to be ambiguous with respect to these classes.</p> <p>Main 'modes' for classifiers: Correct: Distinctive and different. Underclassification: Ambiguous, Unknown. Under-misclassification: Suggestive. Misclassification: Covert, Confused, Mimic. Reachability analyses can be used to estimate the severity of a classification event, e.g., to determine whether a classification is realizable.</p> <p>3) Adversarial Attacks: Adversarial attacks are maliciously constructed inputs that cause high certainty misclassification when classifying inputs that are different from the training data. We use the class hierarchy abstraction as a way of systematically enumerating the kinds of adversarial attacks possible. Our approach also generalizes the kinds of attacks to ones that have not yet been discussed in the literature. Measuring robustness to adversarial attacks is the subject of active research, but there is as yet no generally accepted metric. Nevertheless, some defense approaches are applicable to mitigating misclassifications in general, e.g. "region-based classification" to classify an input according to how the majority of its slightly perturbed variants are classified. In this way, anomalous misclassifications are reduced.</p> <p>4) Compromise among Safety and Other Attributes: It is related to managing the tradeoff between safety, availability, comfort, etc., while satisfying the minimum requirements on these attributes. This is formalized and used in the safety analysis to understand the impact of under-classification. A core mitigation mechanism is to detect potential instances of high risk classification cases and use this to take a suitably conservative control action that minimizes risk to safety. Under-classification based on a confidence measure of the classifier as described in this paper is one approach for this.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>An AD case study using semantic segmentation perception trained with the Cityscapes driving dataset is performed for a Lane Maintenance function. It led to the following main results as 'lessons learned' by the authors:</p> <p>1) Even a simple classification architecture can lead to large number of classification cases, especially because under-classification can introduce an exponential number of new classes, and the classification cases grow quadratically with the number of classes. Hence, complexity reduction techniques were needed to make the analysis tractable.</p> <p>2) Effectively finding "corner cases" for rare events is a critical obstacle to creating reliable AD systems in an open environment.</p> <p>3) CFMEA can be used as evidence of a Safety Case for ML-based systems in specific parts of the system lifecycle.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Future Research:</p> <p>1) Improving the diagnose of root causes: ML is typically not interpretable (i.e., difficult to be understood by its internal structure). Future research requires explanation generation, e.g., assessing the impact of each pixel of an image-based classifier on the results of the classification. Broadly, the aim is to investigate typical factors that cause classification uncertainty in the entire ML development process.</p> <p>2) Addressing metrics for proper mitigation of adversarial attacks.</p> <p>3) Improve the reduction of the CFMEA model complexity for systems with too many classifiers: "(...) sound compositional methods for doing the analysis are needed. In addition, a method is needed for evaluating which states of classification uncertainty are valuable to reify as non-leaf classes in the classification hierarchy in order to limit the number of these classes."</p> <p>4) Adapt CFMEA "(...) to other types of safety-critical systems requiring classification components. We intend to explore other application areas to understand how best to generalize the approach. Finally, we want to generalize the analysis method to other forms of perception beyond pure classification. In particular, we intend to address the case of regression and of object detection since these are common in AD systems".</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 145 / 550	

Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Well-structured method for systematic safety analysis of classifiers. Interesting aspects regarding the state-of-the-art of the area (please refer to Question 3) . 2) Curious scenario of 'urban terrorism' with autonomous cars: stickers on signs can increase speed or prevent stop signs from being recognized. 3) Open problems coincide with some of the issues to be taken into account during the research. 4) Prominent researchers on safety analysis of AI are cited by the authors (e.g. P. Koopman, K. Czarnecki, R. Calinescu), showing relevance of the literature review and convergence on the research theme. 5) Even though the full usage of the method relies on application specificities; its basis are generic enough to be a safety analysis method.
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8.46 REFERENCE [180]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present an approximate yet sufficient solution for two problems to quantify neural networks safety: (i) probabilistic safety verification, in which the goal is to find an upper bound on the probability of violating a safety specification; and (ii) confidence ellipsoid estimation, in which given a confidence ellipsoid for the input of the neural network, the goal is to compute a confidence ellipsoid for the output. The approximate solution is a combination of affine and quadratic constraints imposed on their input-output pairs. It is shown that the safety of the abstracted network, which is sufficient for the safety of the original network, can be analyzed using semidefinite programming.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Neural Networks (NN) are fragile to data uncertainties and adversarial attacks. 2) Two types of verification for NN: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Worst-case safety verification (less difficult are more explored by research): Assumed that the input uncertainty is bounded and a safety property is checked for all possible perturbations within the uncertainty set. - Probabilistic safety verification (more difficult and less explored by research): Assumed that the input uncertainty is random but potentially unbounded. In order to "<i>provide statistical guarantees on the output of neural networks when their input is perturbed with a random noise</i>", two related problems emerge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> "a) <i>Probabilistic Verification: Given a safe region in the output space of the neural network, our goal is estimate the probability that the output of the neural network will be in the safe region when its input is perturbed by a random variable with a known mean and covariance.</i> "b) <i>Confidence propagation: Given a confidence ellipsoid on the input of the neural network, we want to estimate the output confidence ellipsoid.</i>" <p>Method: The paper focuses on probabilistic safety verification. The minimum acceptable probability for the NN to be safe shall be defined, and it shall be checked if the NN output is within an ellipsoid with a confidence of at least the minimum acceptable probability for the NN output to be safe. Another way of seeing this problem is to minimize the volume of the NN output ellipsoid while retaining the confidence level of the minimum acceptable probability for the NN to be safe.</p> <p>Since solving this problem for nonlinear activation functions is a non-convex feasibility problem and is NP-hard, in general, the idea is to avoid this by abstracting the original network by another network in the sense that this new network overapproximates the output of the original network for any input ellipsoid. Then it will be sufficient to verify the safety properties of the relaxed network. Quadratic constraints are used to develop this abstraction.</p>
Q4 Answer	The case study is based on a numerical experiment in which the confidence ellipsoid of a one-layer neural network with 2 inputs, 10/30/50 hidden neurons and 2 outputs is estimated. The weights and biases of the network are chosen randomly.
Q5 Answer	"It would be interesting to consider other related problems such as closed-loop statistical safety verification and reachability analysis."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 146 / 550	

Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good mathematical basis, easy-to-follow explanations and overall interesting idea.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Even though the framework is claimed to be applicable to any Neural Networks, focus was given to those with the ReLU activation function.</p> <p>2) The proposed framework is detailed for NNs with ellipsoidal confidence regions for the outputs.</p> <p>3) No discussion on the case studies results have been provided. Moreover, it has not been discussed whether the 95% confidence interval employed at the case studies is significant for safety-critical applications.</p> <p>4) No analysis regarding random or systematic failures is presented by the authors (e.g. how to account failures that change the ellipsoid during the operation of the NN?)..</p>
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8.47 REFERENCE [181]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	<p>1) To present a framework for managing uncertainty in assurance cases (for conventional and machine-learned systems) by systematically identifying, assessing and addressing it.</p> <p>2) To present a survey on recent work on supporting development of requirements for machine-learned components in safety-critical domains.</p>
Q2 Answer	Machine Learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Uncertainty Framework: It has three steps:</p> <p>1) Identifying the uncertainty, explaining them and assigning them to appropriate types according to a taxonomy.</p> <p>2) Assessing the uncertainty (e.g. via confidence levels)</p> <p>3) Addressing the uncertainty, deciding whether it will be tolerated or reduced (e.g. improving sensor, adding redundant units).</p> <p>Requirements for Machine-Learning components: They shall be defined with the following process:</p> <p>1) Creating and using a web-based domain ontology which will provide consensus for specifying requirements;</p> <p>2) Representing the dataset's domain as an ontology;</p> <p>3) Representing the model's domain as an ontology</p> <p>4) Correlating the ontologies created in items "2" and "3".</p>
Q4 Answer	The only results of the research are the methods presented in response to Question 3. No case studies or examples are presented.
Q5 Answer	The authors do not address this question on their paper.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: Very short paper with a long-term solution for AI-based systems. Not directly related to the research.

8.48 REFERENCE [182]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present a hybrid agent framework to produce high-level autonomous behavior for unmanned vehicles based on formal specification. Linear temporal logic (LTL) is used to express high level agent behavior to control search, tracking, and survival activities, which are executed at a rule-based reasoning engine, whereas a policy network trained with Reinforcement Learning (RL) is used for low level activities.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning with neural networks to implement the policy network.
Q3	Background: <i>"There has not been a widely accepted theory in human-like autonomous behaviors and its</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 147 / 550

Answer	<p>generation. Compared to the human decision-making process, one notices several distinct deficiencies in most cognitive architectures: (1) sense of temporal properties related to the task, (2) awareness of the task progress, and (3) ability to predict action consequence and potential conflicts between concurrent tasks." Main deficiencies in cognitive AI-based architectures when compared to typical human reasoning: "(1) sense of temporal properties related to the task, (2) awareness of the task progress, and (3) ability to predict action consequence and potential conflicts between concurrent tasks."</p> <p>Basics: High-level intelligent behaviors can be better accomplished by a high-level rule-based decision making, implemented with Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) and a rule-based reactive system, and a low-level neuron-based control, implemented with reinforcement learning training policy networks for micro-level behavior control. The LTL framework is the upper specification layer, which describes a mechanism to specify time constraints of the high-level goals and the environmental constraints.</p> <p>At the high level, the following tasks are performed by the agent (UAV): "1) convert the LTL formulas to a generalized Buchi automaton; 2) translate the transitions into predicative rules and load into working memory; 3) loop: 4) Update working memory using the new environment data, including world map and agent state information from other agents; 5) Calculate and selection of all concurrent goals; 6) Filter the candidates with applicable rules, and perform conflict resolution; 7) output physical actions and broadcast agent status; 8) check persistent memory and update goal lists."</p> <p>"Generating behavior from LTL specifications is inherently verifiable. This usually involves the generation of a (Buchi or generalized) automaton that is equivalent to the original LTL formula. The behavior is provided as a conjunction of several assertions which often contain temporal quantifiers. The main problem of using a "pure" automaton as the controller is that it is memoryless and therefore the generated behavior lack some "persistence"."</p> <p>"The decisions made at the high level are symbolic in nature, and they lack the detail instructions suitable for execution. (...) the low level behavior layer consists of a collection of parameterized behavior modules. For each atomic high level actions, a corresponding low level behavior modules is implemented."</p>
Q4 Answer	The behavior controller is evaluated in a simulated environment with single-agent and multi-agent search and tracking scenarios. In these scenarios, intelligent UAVs are meant to search for a target ground vehicle, considering input waypoints but without a predetermined patrol route. It has been shown that the behavior complies with the with safety specification as well as desired collaborative team tracking behavior.
Q5 Answer	The authors do not address this question on their paper.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Poses the possibility of using LTL to create and/or verify AI-based safety-critical systems (e.g. an analyst may build an LTL model to challenge the AI in order to check whether it is safe).</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) Safety verification is not the focus of the paper. No meaningful evidence regarding that property is provided throughout the paper except for the fact that LTL-based models are verifiable.</p>

8.49 REFERENCE [185]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present the safety analysis of a cognitive architecture with an intelligent decision support model (IDSM) that is embedded into an autonomous non-deterministic safety-critical system. The research was carried out on an actual safety-critical system, an unmanned surface vehicle (USV), in both a simulated and a real world nautical based environment.
Q2 Answer	Expert systems, fuzzy logic, machine learning and genetic algorithm are mentioned as part of the proposed safety architecture. Among these, machine learning is the only pure AI technique, whereas the other ones can be crafted through AI.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 148 / 550	

Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Cognitive architectures were developed based on how human cognition works, for example: learning, memory and decision making. Safety engineering of cognitive architectures have not been successful over the past three decades due to lack of safety determinism and predictability. In order to circumvent this, the safety design of the architecture was constrained through the use of fault-tolerant software design.</p> <p>Basics: The safety core of the proposed architecture for the safety-critical system is based on a cognitive architecture called Intelligent Decision Support Model (DSM), which interacts with sensors, the environment (by means of a world model), general-purpose intelligent technologies (e.g. path planners, health monitors, obstacle detectors) and a cognitive architecture of the controlled element (e.g. ASURC for the case study).</p> <p>The IDSM has five main elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data Subsystem: This subsystem provided the maintenance and distribution of the data between the IDSM and the cognitive architecture; - Model Subsystem: The role of the Model Subsystem was to perform model generations to identify appropriate solutions in order to support the decision making process. It evolves as the situation changes. - Report Subsystem: The Report Subsystem accessed the data and models solutions from the source database module. It allowed new reports or changes to existing reports to be inserted into the system. - Knowledge Base Subsystem: This subsystem employed intelligent technologies so the system learned from experience through data and observations, which altered its behavior from one task to another. - Control Subsystem: It provides the flow between all the subsystems and the cognitive architecture of the controlled element (e.g. an unmanned vehicle, such as an Unmanned Surface Vehicle (USV)). <p>Safety Constraints: Fault-tolerant software design was used in conjunction with expert systems, fuzzy logic and machine learning and genetic algorithm concepts within the design of the architecture. The constraints include failsafe designs, self-monitoring, exception handling, warnings to personnel, reconfigurations and other basic safety design principles.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A case study of simulated and real usage of the presented cognitive safety architecture is studies by means of the Autonomous Small Unit Riverline Craft (ASURC), based on the SOAR architecture employed in other robotic platforms. The research observed and evaluated the ASURC's performance of the safety-critical objective of avoiding an unintended collision event with a dynamic obstacle and concluded that the developed cognitive architecture is appropriate to reach risks that are acceptable for the system operation in comparison with conventional systems (deterministic controllers aided by human operators).</p>
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Additional work is needed in order to advance development for handling more real world scenarios, not just obstacle avoidance. The results warrant further research in order to get to an AI capability that performs all tasks safely. 2) The research did not fully present the current state of computational cognitive architectures and their capabilities. 3) The ASURC needs higher fidelity sensor and big data reduction techniques in order to better provide the safety measurements, mechanisms and methodologies for the computational cognitive architectures to perform tasks safely. 4) Rigorous work is needed to meet the complete requirements of safety aspects that lead to standardization of framework with safety metrics. 5) Future research should look to establish an understanding of where existing software system safety analysis and cognitive development converge.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization of AI in automatic control of Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USVs). 2) Several of the suggested future works are in line with paths suggested by other studies. 3) Albeit in a superficial way, the paper considers that typical safety protection measures (e.g. fail-safe architectures and redundancy) can be useful for AI-based systems. 4) The safety analysis method resembles the one applied for non AI-based systems.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 149 / 550	

	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The research presents too little detail on the safety-related architecture of the AI-based models and on the safety analysis method, hence preventing proper knowledge on how the safety-related AI was conceived and checked.</p> <p>2) Most of the discussion on safety techniques for designing an AI-based system is performed only with software in mind. No mention to hardware is performed.</p>
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8.50 REFERENCE [193]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a method of modeling and formal verification to support dependability analyses. To address the challenges of heterogeneity of modeling tools and languages, Semantic Web Technologies are used for model composition and model transformation from modeling tools to formal analysis tools.
Q2 Answer	No AI technique is directly referred to within the paper. Since it deals with Cyber-Physical Systems in general - which are defined as 'smart' systems, it is considered that the proposed method may be applicable to AI-based systems.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: Most <i>"approaches towards multi-model design and analysis of CPS (...) are problem-specific."</i></p> <p><i>"Ontology-based knowledge and reasoning frameworks are being developed to support decision support for correct-by-design of CPS. (...) it is common to use embedded runtime capabilities such as fault management to ensure safe operation for both fault and failure scenarios. These runtime capabilities are the key to failsafe operations, but they must be rigorously verified and validated."</i></p> <p>Basics: The authors present a typical safety analysis lifecycle which incorporates formal methods for the analysis of fault management behaviors defined during the hazard analyses. <i>"FMEA is needed in order to target where best to apply monitors and controls that would address fault and failure modes."</i> The method is based on the usage of the Modelica language and the OpenModelica tool - inserted within the Semantic Web Technologies (SWT) - to automatically generate test vectors and test drivers, as well as perform satisfiability analyses.</p> <p><i>"SWT was employed for cross-domain integration that composes information from different viewpoints, and their associated domain ontology, and then transforms the composed information into representations suitable to other tools."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A case study for the fault management capability of a telepresence robot is presented. The case study also comprises formal verification of the fault management capabilities derived from the hazard analysis and includes detailed behavioral models, model transformations to formal method tools supporting satisfiability analysis, test vector generation, test driver generation, test execution and results analysis, and code coverage analysis.</p> <p><i>"It was possible to perform comprehensive dependability analysis spanning the entire systems engineering life cycle" in an iterative way. "There were numerous satisfiability issues (i.e., contradictions in the model) detected as the model and implementation were evolved." "The initial fault management software was not implemented in a manner that allowed the generated tests to achieve a high degree of code coverage; it was re-factored several times."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<i>"Future work will extend this information to use "issue" management as a means to drive a system effort to completion."</i>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good discussion on issues of formal methods and simulation verification methods:</p> <p><i>"Even where formal methods have been applied to system models, systems have failed to operate correctly in the target environment. Therefore, testing will play a role in the V&V of CPS for some time to come. Surveys of strategies to produce tests using model checkers and SMT solvers found that their fault-finding effectiveness was limited, primarily because the selected input values did not expose faults in the software."</i></p> <p><i>"Simulations of continuous behavior can contribute to verification evidence, but guaranteeing properties such as safety is challenging because the space of possible simulations is so large."</i></p> <p>Weaknesses:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 150 / 550	

	<p>1) Some coverage results seem too low for some modules (e.g. <50%). No discussion on 89% overall coverage has been performed by the authors to assess it as acceptable for a safety-critical system.</p> <p>2) The paper does not have meaningful contribution for the safety analysis of AI, despite it being targeted to any CPS (including smart ones).</p>
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8.51 REFERENCE [195]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To model an autonomous road vehicle as an intelligent agent and to approach its evaluation from an artificial intelligence perspective, considering that reliability is a safety measure. The focus is the evaluation of perception and decision-making systems and also to propose a systematic method to evaluate their integration in the vehicle.
Q2 Answer	No specific technique is mentioned, but the method is deemed applicable to any AI-based technique. Specific parts related to utility function seem more specific of reinforcement learning-based techniques.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: Main issues for validating an AI-based safety-critical system: test coverage (on simulated and real world scenarios) and data problems.</p> <p>Architecture: <i>"The Generic Autonomous Vehicle System Architecture divide an autonomous car software in three main layers: perception, decision-making and action. (...) Since the action layer is developed according to the control engineering theory which is an established theory, we focus our analysis in the perception and decision-making layers."</i></p> <p>Perception System: <i>(...) the perception system comprises the software required to transform raw sensor data in the meaningful information required by the decision-making system"</i> <i>"In the machine learning community the usual way to evaluate models and algorithms is through datasets. Although datasets are model independent, they evaluate specific tasks (classification, segmentation, detection) that are subtasks of a complete perception system. Recent papers present evidences that machine learning models do not have a task optimality. In other words a specific model may present different performances on different datasets describing the same task. A model that has a good performance classifying dogs and cats may have a bad performance classifying cars and pedestrians."</i></p> <p>Main issues of the model-task-data evaluation with datasets: <i>"1) Focus on subtasks of a bigger problem. 2) The generalization error estimate strongly depends on available data. 3) Training and testing sets are equally balanced; 4) Testing examples have a high quality; 5) Testing examples are always reliable; 6) Testing examples are always available."</i></p> <p>Evaluation: Usage of percept frequencies, define as <i>"the complete history of everything the agent has perceived"</i>. Each percept sequence is a stream of sensors data with timestamps.</p> <p>Decision-Making System: <i>"(...) decision theory which combines probabilities with preferences expressed by utilities"</i> <i>"(...) the biggest problem to evaluate decision-making systems resides in the fact that it may exist several right decisions. In such conditions it is typical to look for errors/faults, or specifically, for events that represent the lack of safety or regulatory compliance. This approach conforms to constitutional principles such as "Everything which is not forbidden is allowed"."</i></p> <p>Evaluation: <i>" (...) the decision making system must be evaluated over task environments" in a simulator. " Task environments are the ultimate goal of rational agents i.e. they are the tasks that a rational agent was built to accomplish. (...) And since the perception system is previously evaluated with real sensors data, realistic sensor models and environments are not strong requirements. What matters is the complexity of the</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 151 / 550	

	<p><i>relationship between the agent behavior and the environment."</i></p> <p>Main Steps:</p> <p>1) Individual Perception Subtasks: Datasets are used to evaluate the perception system.</p> <p>2) Data Verisimilitude Test: It aims to evaluate how the fusion module performs facing real data and problems that can emerge from its use. The data verisimilitude test is a dataset consisting of several percept sequences to detect issues in the following categories: data estimation (data extrapolation when data is occluded during operation), data absence (rare events presence), data flux interruption (sensor/communication fault), data corruption (sensor/communication fault) and data attacks (external agent action, e.g. adversarial attacks).</p> <p>3) Decision-Making Simulation: <i>"The perception system will never be perfect but the decision-making system must be able to define countermeasures to partial or defective information. (...) The decision-making system should also be evaluated with percept sequences. But differently from the perception system the percept sequences must represent task environments."</i> <i>"Its main purpose is to reprove solutions that are not able to comply with the given task."</i></p> <p>4) Outdoor Controlled Tests: <i>"(...) the simulation is replaced by a mock-up test field with traffic signs and obstacles. This evaluation is also task driven and the vehicle must respect all restrictions and traffic laws. Their main purpose is to validate the subsystem integration."</i> <i>"(...) The occurrence of rare situations is one of the reasons that road field tests are so important. (...) Its main purpose is to use the software logs to find events that could be harmful or that are against the traffic laws."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	No case studies were carried out, since the objective of the paper was to present an analysis framework for autonomous driving agents. Please refer to the responses of Question 3 for details on the proposed approach.
Q5 Answer	<i>"Since this work focus on perception and decision-making systems it is not meant to become the single procedure to assess an autonomous car performance. We hope this paper can instigate further discussion about the topic."</i>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Background on ISO26262: <i>"(...) it does not consider the current developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) that are being applied in Advanced Driver Assistance Systems and Autonomous Driving."</i></p> <p>2) Good summary on the verification of AI-based systems employed in Unmanned Vehicles: <i>"Most papers in the area focus in a developer point of view of testing. They specify an exact behavior that must be followed and then measure how much proposed solutions deviate from it. (...) There are two main concerns regarding this method. First, it might be impractical to create a model for every single possible situation; and second, one situation may have several correct actions (and no best action)."</i></p> <p>3) Issue with simulated test: <i>"In general a simulator must create realistic environments and sensors models but there is no metric to evaluate how realistic they are."</i></p> <p>4) Interesting discussion on utilitarianism, moral principles and liability within the safety analysis. E.g.: How to value a human's life? Self-defense may be applicable to humans but not to robots.</p> <p>5) The proposed model is generic enough for any type of intelligent system.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Reliability is evaluated as safety. This is a major conceptual issue, since something that compromises reliability not necessarily affects safety.</p> <p>2) It seems that the decision-making models created by the authors focus on the usage of reinforcement learning, since an 'utility function' is mentioned. The latter is typical of reinforcement learning schemes, in such a way that the optimization of the utility function maximizes the reward of the intelligent element / agent. This scope restriction is not made clear by the authors.</p> <p>3) The authors take for granted that AI may be flawed for rare events (e.g. unsafe scenarios) and that these shall be better addressed at field tests. This is debatable.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 152 / 550	

8.52 REFERENCE [200]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	"To present a new efficient approach for rigorously checking different safety properties of neural networks that significantly outperforms existing approaches by multiple orders of magnitude" by checking "different safety properties and find concrete counterexamples for networks that are 10× larger than the ones supported by existing analysis techniques."
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general, but specifically aimed towards image-based processing.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "Need for formal analysis systems that can rigorously check neural networks for violations of different safety properties such as robustness against adversarial perturbations within a certain L-norm of a given image (...) or the invariance of the network's predictions on the images of the same object under different lighting conditions. (...) most existing techniques for performing such analysis struggle to scale beyond very small networks and the ones that can scale to larger networks suffer from high false positives and cannot produce concrete counterexamples in case of a property violation."</p> <p>E.g.: "(...) strict estimation of the decision boundary of a neural network with piecewise linear activation functions such as ReLU is a hard problem. (...) [and] the total number of linear pieces grow exponentially with the number of nodes in the network. (...) sampling-based inference techniques like black box Monte Carlo sampling may need an enormous amount of data to generate tight accurate bounds on the decision boundary."</p> <p>Satisfiability Modulo Theory (SMT) and Mixed Integer Linear Programming have been used by other researchers with the purpose of NN safety analysis to estimate decision boundaries with strong guarantees with limited efficiency due to the non-linearity of the resulting formulas.</p> <p>Convex or linear relaxation techniques have also been used to approximate the decision boundaries of neural networks, including adversarial attacks. While these scale better than solver-based approaches, they suffer with high false positive rates and struggle to find concrete counterexamples for violating safety properties.</p> <p>Basics: In order to reduce the effort of the safety verification, two key techniques are introduced by the authors. "First, we use symbolic linear relaxation that combines symbolic interval analysis and linear relaxation to compute tighter bounds on the network outputs by keeping track of relaxed dependencies across inputs during interval propagation when the actual dependencies become too complex to track. Second, we introduce a novel technique called directed constraint refinement to iteratively minimize the errors introduced during the relaxation process until either a safety property is satisfied or a counterexample is found." If the solver finds the relaxed constraints unsatisfiable, the NN is safe; otherwise, it produces counterexamples which indicate that they are unsafe. These will be further checked for being false positives by a Neurify-based checker. "Neurify will use directed constraint refinement guided by symbolic linear relaxation to obtain a tighter output bound and recheck the property with the solver." "To make the refinement process efficient, we identify the potentially overestimated nodes, i.e., the nodes where inaccuracies introduced during relaxation can potentially affect the checking of a given safety property, and use off-the-shelf solvers to focus only on those nodes to further tighten their output ranges."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Nine (neural network, dataset) pairs were considered in case studies performed by considering their respective safety properties and assessing whether the proposed model allowed identifying unsafe situations (including 'timeout' scenarios of potentially unsafe scenarios which were further disregarded due to they being false positive issues). The obtained results were also compared with those generated by preexisting methods with regard to identifying potentially unsafe situations and evaluating performance.</p> <p>The authors argue that the proposed model is better than its counterparts to raise potentially unsafe scenarios in complex NNs and that it can also help the training process of robust neural networks and improve the explainability of neural networks.</p>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good overview on adversarial attacks on Neural Networks: "(...) often make dangerous mistakes, especially for rare corner cases". "(...) minor changes in lighting or orientation of an input image have been shown to cause drastic mispredictions by the state-of-the-art neural networks (...) For example, a Tesla car in autopilot mode</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 153 / 550	

	<p>recently caused a fatal crash as it failed to detect a white truck against a bright sky with white clouds."</p> <p>2) If the Neurify-based checker fails to identify whether a counterexample produced by the proposed model is a false positive, a safe NN will be deemed unsafe, hence leaning towards a safe behavior.</p> <p>3) Strong mathematical background.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors consider that the bisection which is part of the symbolic linear relaxation tends to produce safer behaviors because the reunion of the corresponding bisected output intervals will be tighter than the original input; however, if there is a failure on this bisection (e.g. HW or SW-based failure), a safety issue can happen. This makes it necessary that the checker is somewhat fail-safe on its own.</p> <p>2) Computational resources used in the case studies are very high (octa-core CPU with 256GB RAM) and likely to be prohibitive in the short term for commercial applications.</p> <p>3) Lack of discussion between safety of NNs and safety of the system which uses NNs for safety-critical purposes (i.e., no relationship between system-level requirements and NN-level requirements).</p>
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8.53 REFERENCE [201]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present a framework to help categorize and design rebel agents, discuss their social and ethical implications, and assess their potential benefits and the risks they may pose, as well as to explore socio-cognitive dimensions of AI rebellion: social awareness and counter-narrative intelligence.
Q2 Answer	There is no mention to any specific AI technique throughout the paper. AI is generally mentioned as part of the rebel agents.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: Rebel agents can serve purposes such as ethics, safety, task execution correctness, and providing or supporting diverse points of view.</p> <p><i>"We define rebel agents as AI agents that can reject, protest against, or develop attitudes of reluctance or opposition to goals or courses of action assigned to them by other agents, or to the general behavior or attitudes of other agents. We use "rebellion" as an umbrella term covering reluctance, protest, refusal, rejection of tasks, and similar attitudes or behaviors."</i></p> <p><i>"In a rebellion episode, an alter is an agent or a group of agents against which one rebels, and which is in a position of power over the rebel agent. (...) The rebel agent is not intended to be permanently adversarial towards the alter(s) or in a rebelling state by default. Such an agent has potential for rebellion that may or may not manifest, depending on external and internal conditions."</i></p> <p>Basics: <i>"This framework is general: it does not assume any particular agent architecture. We also introduced the term counter-narrative intelligence to refer to a mechanism that enables rebels to produce, express, and reason about counter-narratives that support and justify rebellion."</i></p> <p>Main Concepts:</p> <p>a) Design Intentionality: <i>"An AI agent can be specifically designed to be able to rebel (rebel by design), but rebellious behavior can also emerge unintentionally from the agent's autonomy model (emergent rebellion)."</i></p> <p>b) Expression: <i>"Explicit rebellion occurs in situations in which the alter is clearly defined and the rebel agent's behavior is clearly identifiable as rebellious". "Implicit rebellion occurs when the alter is not clearly defined or the rebel agent's behavior suggests rebellion, but is not clearly expressed as such. This behavior could consist of expressing an opinion that differs from the majority's, or behaving contrary to social norms."</i></p> <p>c) Interaction Initiation: <i>"Rebellion is reactive when an interaction within which rebellious behavior occurs is initiated by the alter." "In proactive rebellion, the rebel agent initiates the rebellious behavior, which may or may not occur within an explicit interaction."</i></p> <p>d) Normativity: <i>"Normative rebellion consists of taking action within the confines of what has been explicitly allowed". "Non-normative rebellion consists of behavior that has been neither explicitly allowed nor explicitly forbidden, but diverges from the current command given to the agent". "Counternormative</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 154 / 550	

	<p>rebellion consists of executing actions or pursuing goals that have been explicitly forbidden."</p> <p>e) Action: "In rebellion situations characterized by action, the agent's rebellion manifests through any sort of outwardly perceivable behavior". "A rebellious attitude characterized by inaction can lead to rebellious action later on".</p> <p>f) Collectivity: "Individual action is rebellious action conducted by a single rebel agent. Collective action occurs when multiple agents are involved in concerted rebellious action."</p> <p>g) Egoism: "Rebellion is egoistic when the agent rebels in support of its own well-being or survival". "Altruistic rebellion occurs when the agent rebels in support of someone else's interests". "Egoistic and altruistic rebellion can coexist."</p> <p>h) Factors of Rebellion: "Possible motivating factors for AI rebellion, depending on the agent's architecture and purpose, include ethics and safety, team solidarity, task execution correctness, self-actualization, and resolving contradicting commands from multiple alters. In support of ethics and safety, rebel agents can refuse tasks they assess as being ethically prohibited or violating safety norms".</p> <p>i) Stages of Rebellion:</p> <p>1) Pre-rebellion: "Pre-rebellion consists of processes leading to rebellion, such as the agent observing and assessing changes in the environment and the behavior of other agents. The progression towards rebellion may be reflected in the agent's outward behavior."</p> <p>2) Rebellion Deliberation: "Rebellion deliberation is the stage at which motivating, supporting, and inhibiting factors are assessed to decide whether to trigger rebellion".</p> <p>3) Rebellion Execution: "Rebellion execution episodes begin with rebellion being triggered as a result of rebellion deliberation and consist of expressing rebellion. (...) it can be expressed through an internal change in the agent's attitudes."</p> <p>4) Post-rebellion: "Post-rebellion can consist of reaffirming one's objection or rejection (...) or ceasing to rebel. It may also consist of assessing and managing inverse trust."</p> <p>j) Sociocognitive Dimensions of Rebellion:</p> <p>1) "Naive rebel agents are rebellion-unaware rebels: they deliberate on whether to trigger rebellion, but do not reason about the social implications, consequences, and risks of rebellious attitudes."</p> <p>2) "Conflicted rebel agents are rebellion-aware rebels: they can both rebel and reason about the implications and consequences of rebellion."</p> <p>3) "Counter-narrative intelligence [refers] to the ability of rebel agents to (1) produce alternative retellings or counterinterpretations, informed by subjective factors such as emotional appraisal, of an alter's narrative, or (2) to identify their own pregenerated narratives as being counter-narratives in a given context. Just as a rebel agent rebels in relation to an alter, a counter-narrative exists in relation and contrast to a base narrative that it is a variant of and that it challenges." "Counter-narratives are sincere when they reflect the agent's genuine interpretation of a situation (that is, they align with the agent's beliefs, but possibly not the alter's)." "Counter-narratives are deceptive when they intentionally misrepresent the agent's beliefs."</p>
Q4 Answer	The framework is intended to inspire, guide, and provide terminology for (1) the development and study of rebel agents that serve positive purposes, (2) systematic discussion of the ethics of AI rebellion (for, although we argue that AI rebellion can be positive, we recognize that it is not necessarily so), and (3) positive reframing of the AI noncompliance narrative within the research community and popular culture.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting topic which may be useful for creating a safety-related AI-based online risk assessment system. Further investigation on this can be suggested as future work for the research.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The theme is not directly related to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.</p>

8.54 REFERENCE [202]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To introduce hybrid stability automata (system models constructed using numerical continuation that capture stability properties within a series of dynamic modes) that support safety analyses by explicitly defining stable, i.e. safe, regions of the operational envelope.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 155 / 550

Q2 Answer	No AI technique is directly referred to within the paper.
Q3 Answer	Hybrid stability automata are "(...) a method of modeling a system that uses the stability information obtained through numerical continuation analysis to capture the basins of attraction (i.e. the domain of initial conditions for which trajectories will converge to a stable equilibrium) to identify stable and unstable domains of the state-space. A hybrid automaton is a model that represents a system's dynamics as a series of modes with continuous-time dynamics.(...) Since stability properties directly correlate to safety properties, hybrid stability automata are well-suited for automated safety analyses in addition to providing useful visualizations of system behavior." The authors propose means to perform the analysis of dynamic systems with several parameters by fixating (n-1) parameters, varying the remaining parameter and repeating the previous steps for all possible combinations of all the parameters.
Q4 Answer	A case study related to the application of the proposed approach for a space shuttle reentry analysis is presented by the authors.
Q5 Answer	"Future work will involve creating automata for higher dimensional systems to enable more comprehensive analyses for systems such as the shuttle during reentry." "(...) an analysis using repeated simulations requires a computational process for each set of initial states being tested { a disadvantage that can compound since a large number of simulations may be required to capture the same information contained in one hybrid stability automaton."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: The paper is not directly related to the technicalities of AI-based systems safety analysis.

8.55 REFERENCE [207]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To contribute with a safety verification method for trajectories under occlusions for autonomous vehicles.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	Motivation: Recent approaches minimize risk with probabilistic and machine learning methods – even under occlusions, but cannot guarantee safety of their maneuvers. Basics: Typical AI-based autonomous vehicles with risk assessment strategies will try to follow their intended behavior as long as no noteworthy risk is detected. The authors promote an inverse methodology that an automated vehicle should only follow its intended trajectory as long as it can prove that it is safe. The field-of-view of the ego vehicle and a map are used to identify critical sensing field edges, each representing a potentially hidden obstacle, hence tackling the safety verification problem in scenarios with occlusions by over-approximating all possible states instead of engineering discrete maneuvers or maneuver classes. As a result, the safety concept does not rely on e.g. the performance of an intention estimation module. It depends only on the reliability of an ego localization, the detection of obstacles, of occluded areas and on a map.
Q4 Answer	The potential for provably safe trajectory planning is shown in three evaluative scenarios. The case studies results indicate that the proposed method limits AI behavior within safe boundaries and allows to verify the safety of given trajectories (e.g. if they ensure collision-free fail-safe maneuver options) w.r.t. arbitrary safe-state formulations.
Q5 Answer	"We will incorporate the proposed method in our prototype vehicle in the coming months and analyze the performance under real world conditions".
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) The study seems to reinforce the usage of AI surrounded by a "deterministic box" to ensure safety in its application. Weaknesses: 1) The simulated models are simplified (e.g. "we use a simple visibility model, assuming a 360° range sensor with viewing 50m range mounted on top of the vehicle center using a direct geometrical representation."), hence, this may not reflect actual results in real-world scenarios.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 156 / 550	

8.56 REFERENCE [208]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose to use unsupervised machine learning to train neural networks to solve the problem of modeling vehicle trajectories in test scenarios.
Q2 Answer	Unsupervised machine learning to train neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "(...) <i>more than 6.6 billion kilometers of test driving would be necessary to ensure the safety of a HAV (Highly Automated Vehicle)</i>". Hence, it is needed "(...) <i>to tackle the safety validation challenge by increasing testing in simulation environments and introducing a scenario-based approach.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>We propose a new approach to create models of maneuver trajectories based on unsupervised machine-learning algorithms. A neural network learns to model maneuver trajectories and to find a comprehensible set of model parameters from recorded trajectories. The resulting network can generate any number of new realistic trajectories by varying the values of the model's input parameters. Additionally, the inverse mapping from trajectories to parameter values is learned by the network. Thus, the parameter representation of a rare or critical maneuver can be derived and varied to generate an infinite number of relevant trajectories for testing.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>We implement and compare two approaches. The first approach is based on a neural network architecture called InfoGAN, which is an extension of the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN). (...) The second approach is based on the Beta-VAE architecture, which is an extension of the original Variational Autoencoder. (...) VAEs are easier to train and Beta-VAE has proven its ability to create a more intuitive representation on images. (...) We choose the highD dataset, which is a recent dataset of vehicle trajectories on German highways extracted from drone recordings. (...) our method is not constrained to lane changes, but can be used on every possible maneuver.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Lane changes in the highD dataset are modeled by a quadratic polynomial for the longitudinal direction and a polynomial of fifth degree for the lateral direction, as more dynamics are present in the lateral direction.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>The mean squared error between the input and reconstructed trajectory is a metric for the classification and generation quality of the network.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Main Contributions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>We propose two neural network architectures, called Trajectory Generative Adversarial Network (TraGAN) and Trajectory Variational Autoencoder (TraVAE), that are able to generate a disentangled and meaningful representation of lane change maneuver trajectories from recorded lane changes without any labels.</i> - <i>We demonstrate that the network architectures are indeed able to recognize existing and generate new maneuver trajectory variations that are realistic.</i> - <i>We compare both architectures and show their respective (dis-)advantages.</i> - <i>We show that the networks can be used to find gaps in existing training or validation data and fill those gaps by generating realistic trajectories for use in e.g. simulation environments."</i> <p>The case study reached the following conclusion:</p> <p>"<i>Both of our models are able to reconstruct trajectories and create a disentangled latent representation. The learned parameters are intuitive and similar to the parameters chosen manually by experts. (...) TraGAN shows a better performance, as it has a lower reconstruction loss, and finds four disentangled and intuitive parameters. In comparison, the latent space learned by TraVAE is less disentangled and less intuitive. However, one downside of TraGAN is that training a GAN is harder than training a Variational Autoencoder.</i>"</p>
Q5 Answer	" <i>We want to extend our networks to include additional types of maneuvers.</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good background on VAEs and GANs for unsupervised learning:</p> <p>VAEs: "<i>An encoder network is trained to encode inputs to a low dimensional representation. To learn a meaningful latent representation, a decoder network has to reconstruct the original input using this representation. By training the network to minimize the difference between the network input and output, the latent space representation has to retain as much information as possible. After training, the decoder network is used to generate new data by sampling from the latent space. (...) the VAE additionally minimizes</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 157 / 550	

	<p><i>the volume occupied by the latent representations in the latent space. This is done by penalizing the distribution of latent codes to differ from a normal distribution using the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence." Beta-VAE (...) introduces a loss weight factor $\beta > 1$, which increases the importance of the KL divergence. Using a high value for β, the network is forced to encode the information of the dataset in a smaller subset of latent codes, which inherently leads to a disentangled representation".</i></p> <p><i>GANs: "GANs consist of a combination of two networks: A generator and a discriminator. The generator is the analogue to the decoder of an autoencoder and generates synthetic data samples from a latent representation. Its counterpart, the discriminator, has to distinguish between real and generated data samples. Both networks are trained alternately, which causes both networks to improve over time, until the generator is able to generate data samples that the discriminator is unable to distinguish from real data samples. Using a discriminator avoids the problem of blurry generated samples, which is a typical problem of autoencoders. The alternated training of generator and discriminator is not stable and sensitive to hyperparameters."</i></p> <p><i>In InfoGAN, " (...) ,an additional classifier network is used that estimates the latent code to generate given synthetic data samples. Maximizing the mutual information between these parameters and the data samples encourages the network to disentangle the input parameters."</i></p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The subject of safety analysis of AI-based systems is not directly covered by the authors, hence minimizing its usefulness to the research. The authors just mention that their method can be used to support the safety validation of highly automated vehicles.</p> <p>2) The paper itself is highly oriented towards highly automated vehicles applications. Despite the claim that the approach based on Beta-VAEs and InfoGANs can be extended to other applications, no further information regarding this is provided.</p>
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8.57 REFERENCE [209]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a deep reinforcement learning-based approach for the decision-making of autonomous vehicles, which is combined with formal safety verification to ensure that only safe actions are chosen at any time.
Q2 Answer	Deep reinforcement learning with the usage of a deep Q-network (DQN).
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: "<i>Reinforcement Learning can deal with large scale systems with possibly infinite state and action spaces in a model-free way.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>We present a novel approach that is able to:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>learn the high-level decision making of performing lane changing or lane keeping on highways with an arbitrary number of lanes while a low-level system executes the maneuver,</i> 2) <i>use a minimal representation of the environment to reduce the dimensionality of the state space for accelerated learning, and</i> 3) <i>incorporate safety verification in the system to ensure that the agent only executes safe actions."</i> <p><u>Details on the safety verification of actions taken by the DRL-based agent:</u></p> <p>After one action is chosen from the RL agent at a certain time step t, the safety system checks the safety of the chosen action. If the action is safe, the underlying system takes care of the low-level execution.</p> <p><i>"In order to guarantee that the agent only chooses safe actions at all times, we make use of formal verification for lane changes. (...) the agent must keep a safe distance from other vehicles so that it can safe stop without colliding when the leading vehicles perform emergency braking. This safe distance (...) accounts for the dynamics of both the agent and the other traffic participant. Thus, we can define safe states of the agent with respect to the leading vehicle position and safe distance."</i></p> <p><i>"Consequently, we can define the safe free space F_t of the agent in a lane. (...) By enlarging the shape of each vehicle by its dimensions, collision-checks are reduced to checking the enclosure of its reference point in F_t."</i></p> <p><i>"By ensuring that the agent is driving within the safe free space, we are able to verify a given action as safe prior to execution. (...) We assume that the agent starts in a safe state, i. e., the agent initially respects safe</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 158 / 550	

	<p>distances to leading vehicle. If the agent always chooses safe actions, the agent remains in the safe free space indefinitely unless other traffic participants violate traffic rules."</p> <p>"We choose the action with maximum value and forward it to the safety algorithm. If the action is considered safe, it is executed; if not, we take the second best action. If that one is also unsafe, we stay in the current lane. Note that the action keep is always safe, since the RL agent respects the safe distance to leading vehicles at any time."</p> <p>"(...) unavoidable accidents are still possible: for example, if someone crashes into our vehicle from the side or rear-ends it at the end of a traffic jam. In our case, the underlying system prevents rear-end collisions."</p> <p>Restriction: "we assume that other vehicles do not drive backwards once they have stopped and that they do not accelerate beyond a velocity v_{max}"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Training: Simulated data collected throughout a period of 90 hours of operation of an autonomous vehicle within an environment with other simulated vehicles has been considered for offline learning.</p> <p>Case Study: Ten simulated traffic scenarios, each of which with 500 seconds of duration, have been considered to evaluate the RL-based agent. In all scenarios, 50 other vehicles are included within the simulated environment.</p> <p>"Our RL agent is able to learn the desired task without causing collisions and outperforms a complex, rule-based agent that we use for benchmarking."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s), except for the following restriction which is part of the proposed model: "we assume that other vehicles do not drive backwards once they have stopped and that they do not accelerate beyond a velocity v_{max}".</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Since the research is strongly oriented towards autonomous vehicles application, it can, at most, serve as base to propose similar models for other applications. The safety verification method is not generic enough to be used regardless of the final application.</p>

8.58 REFERENCE [210]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	<p>To present a methodology framework for identifying functional deficiencies during system development through the usage of possibility theory and a fuzzy relation model - Causal Scenario Analysis (CSA) - as one part of this framework. The aim is to address functional deficiencies resulting from limited sensing abilities and algorithmic performance of automated vehicles.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: In addition to random failures and systematic failures (usually addressed by standards such as ISO26262), "functional deficiencies have brought great challenges to system safety engineering". They are defined as "deviations from the intended functionality due to underspecified operating conditions.", notably related to sensing and algorithmic performance on automated driving systems, including uncertainty about the training samples being representative of the testing and real work samples, as well as unanticipated scenarios in operation.</p> <p>Main questions related to functional deficiencies on ML-based systems:</p> <p>Q1: How can functional deficiencies be systematically identified in the concept and design phase of automated driving systems? --> Objective of this research paper.</p> <p>Q2: Which criteria can be derived from identified functional deficiencies, in order to classify and evaluate unknown ones efficiently?</p> <p>Q3: How can it be argued in a structured way, that functional deficiencies are sufficiently considered?</p> <p>Uncertainties: "Random uncertainty reflects unpredictable variation in the performance or behavior of systems. It's irreducible even with increasing knowledge or data, e.g. occurrence of a random hardware failure. (...) epistemic uncertainty arises from lack of knowledge due to insufficient data. Consequently, it can be reduced as more knowledge is available", but "(...) it is often not feasible to get an objective probability prediction under epistemic uncertainty."</p> <p>"In the possibility theory, two specifications of likelihood are involved, a necessity $Nec()$ and a possibility $Pos()$, both valued on $[0, 1]$ for each subset p of the universal</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 159 / 550	

	<p>set U under consideration. A necessity measure is associated by duality with a possibility measure for p by $Nec(p)=1-Pos(\neg p)$ for all p."</p> <p>"In a fuzzy relation model, key elements of the diagnostic problem are disorders and manifestations. The knowledge about the relation between them is modeled with two functions, valued on $[0, 1]$, considered as the degree of necessity that d causes m, and that d doesn't cause m."</p> <p>Basics: A methodology framework for identification of functional deficiencies in the concept and design phase has been designed by the authors. This framework is based on quantifying and estimating uncertainties based on a fuzzy relation model based on possibility theory. "The basic idea of this framework is, using three analyses to identify effects, propagation paths and causes for functional deficiencies, and achieving traceability between them."</p> <p>The methodology has three steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hazard and Risk Analyses; 2) Fault Tree Analysis to identify trigger events. which can be potentially triggered by driving scenarios and lead to the deficient behavior of the system. 3) Causal Scenario Analysis to identify under which scenarios the trigger events can be caused. The causal relationship is exercised by means of the fuzzy relation model with uncertainties based on possibility theory. For this, a set of parametric data for cause-effect relation is needed.
Q4 Answer	<p>A traffic light handling case study is presented to illustrate the application of the proposed methodology framework. The focus was on establishing the causes for the trigger events which lead to the undesired behavior "unwanted passing a red traffic light". Some examples were presented and discussed in detail. The overall conclusion is that "the feasibility and the plausibility of Causal Scenario Analysis have been proven after performing this case study".</p> <p>Moreover, "CSA seems to be a more systematic approach than brainstorming and is able to build up the argument that the causes have been systematically and more sufficiently explored. Therefore, CSA was proposed as a promising methodology for identifying the causes of functional deficiencies in our proposed framework."</p>
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "(...) an experiment for a quantitative comparison [between brainstorming with FTA only and CSA] may be conducted. Theoretically, the analyst would be able to include scenarios from his knowledge into the (...) CSA and could get at least the same amount of scenarios by CSA." 2) "Besides, only the variation of one boundary at a time was considered in the study. Combinations of multiple boundaries have not been evaluated so far." 3) "(...) further discussion about modeling identified scenarios into fault trees could be promising, when we would derive quantitative estimation of the occurrence probabilities of the trigger-events in further development phases. To this end, an extension of the framework could be discussed in the future." 4) "(...) we suggest some extensions of the methodologies, like considering combinations of boundaries and designing experiments for quantifying the benefits of CSA". 5) "(...) the results of CSA can probably be utilized to build an explanatory expert system for analysis of data that have been collected during test drives and sort out unknown functional deficiencies from known ones."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good background on safety analysis framework for autonomous vehicles. 2) Good background on fuzzy relation models based on possibility theory. 3) Interesting roadmap of questions for the safety validation of autonomous vehicles. It is valid to any AI-based system which performs safety-related functions in an autonomous way. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Despite the good possibility on exploring the fuzzy relation model to quantify AI-related risks and failure rates related to uncertainties, this was not addressed by the authors.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 160 / 550	

8.59 REFERENCE [212]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To address the output reachable estimation and safety verification problems for multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural networks.
Q2 Answer	Multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The focus of the research is on the safety verification of a class of neural networks called the multilayer perceptron (MLP). The verification concept is based on "<i>a conception called maximum sensitivity is introduced to characterize the maximum deviation of the output subject to a bounded disturbance around a nominal input. By formulating a chain of optimizations, the maximum sensitivity for an MLP can be computed in a layer-by-layer manner. Then, an exhaustive search of the input set is enabled by a discretization of input space to achieve an estimation of output reachable set which consists of a union of reachtubes. Finally, by the merit of reachable set estimation, the safety verification for an MLP can be done via checking the existence of intersections between the estimated reachable set and unsafe regions.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>The main benefits of our approach are that there are very few restrictions on the activation functions except for the monotonicity which is satisfied by a variety of activation functions, and also no requirement on the bounded input sets. All these advantages are coming from the simulation-based nature of our approach.</i>"</p> <p>Requirement: "<i>(...) our approach aims at dealing with the most of activation functions regardless of their specific forms, only the following monotonic assumption needs to be satisfied: (...) for any $x_1 \leq x_2$, the activation function satisfies $f(x_1) \leq f(x_2)$.</i>"</p> <p>Safety Verification Problem: "<i>Safety specification S of an MLP formalizes the safety requirements for output $y[L]$ of MLK $y[L] = F(x[0])$, and is a predicate over output $y[L]$ of MLP. The MLP is safe if and only if Y intersected with not(S) equals the empty set.</i>" It can be relaxed by considering that the previous condition is met by the NN output reachable set estimation \hat{Y}, since $Y \subseteq \hat{Y}$.</p> <p>Resolving the Safety Verification: "<i>(...) difficulties if only using analytical methods. One possible way to circumvent those difficulties is to employ the information produced by a finite number of simulations. (...) are incomplete to characterize output set Y, [so] a conception called maximum sensitivity is introduced to bridge the gap between simulations and output reachable set estimations of MLPs.(...) the maximum sensitivity is introduced to measure the maximum deviation of outputs, which is caused by the bounded disturbances around the nominal input.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>(...) the computation for the maximal sensitivity of an MLP is converted to a chain of optimization problems (...) [, which] are convex optimization problems which can be efficiently solved by existing tools such as <i>cvx</i>, <i>linprog</i> in <i>MATLAB</i>.</i>". The problem is iteratively computed for each layer of the MLP, starting on the input layer and following until the output layer is reached. Based on these results, it is possible to define the output reachable set estimation with the input set bounded by the previous optimizations by performing finite simulations of inputs $x_j[0]$, obtaining the corresponding $y_j[L]$ and computing the maximum sensitivity for a finite number of lattices centered at $x_j[0]$. The radii of the lattices define how many simulations are needed for obtaining results and the precision of the results; hence, the smaller the radius, the greater the time for the results to be computed and the more precise the results will be. Finally, the safety verification is performed by comparing the overapproximated output reachable set estimation (\hat{Y}) with the safety requirements. There are three possible outcomes: "safe" if the safety requirements are met by \hat{Y}, "unsafe" if there is at least one safety requirement not met by the exact outputs "Y" and "uncertain" when there is at least one approximate \hat{Y} output outside the list of safety requirements.</p>
Q4 Answer	An application to the safety verification for a robotic arm model with two joints employed on learning forward kinematics is presented to show the effectiveness of the proposed approaches. The arm has specific positions which are deemed safe and positions which are forbidden.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Background on safety verification of Neural Networks that matches the difficulties presented by other authors: "<i>Verifying neural networks is a hard problem, even simple properties about them have been proven</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 161 / 550	

	<p><i>nondeterministic polynomial-complete problems. The difficulties mainly come from the presence of activation functions and the complex structures, making neural networks large scale, nonlinear, nonconvex, and thus incomprehensible to humans."</i></p> <p>2) Good explanation on neural networks basics: "A neural network consists of a number of interconnected neurons. Each neuron is a simple processing element that responds to the weighted inputs it received from other neurons. (...) an MLP consists of three typical classes of layers: An input layer, that serves to pass the input vector to the network, hidden layers of computation neurons, and an output layer composed of at least a computation neuron to produce the output vector. The action of a neuron depends on its activation function, which is described as $y_i = f(\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} \cdot x_j + t_{etai})$, where x is the j-th input of the i-th neuron, w_{ij} is the weight from the j-th input to the i-th neuron, t_{etai} is called the bias of the i-th neuron, y_i is the output of the i-th neuron, and $f(\cdot)$ is the activation function. The activation function is a nonlinear function describing the reaction of i-th neuron with inputs $x_j(t)$. Typical activation functions include rectified linear unit, logistic, tanh, exponential linear unit, and linear functions, for instance." " For an MLP, the output of l layer is the input of "l" layer. The mapping from the input $x[0]$ of input layer 0 to the output $y[L]$ of output layer L stands for the input–output relation of the MLP, denoted by $y[L] = F(x[0])$, where $F(\cdot) = f[L] \circ f[L-1] \circ \dots \circ f[1]$." "Rather than directly computing the exact output reachable set for an MLP, a more practical and feasible way is to derive an overapproximation of the output Y, which is called the output reachable set estimation [and represented by \hat{Y}]." " (...) how to find a set \hat{Y} such that $Y \subseteq \hat{Y}$ and make the estimation set \hat{Y} as small as possible?"</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) How to formally define the set of "S" safety requirements for a Neural Network? This is not discussed within the paper. 2) The authors do not discuss how to define the activation function of a neural network nor the impacts it may have over performance and safety. 3) The authors do not present weaknesses of their study nor suggestions for future work.
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8.60 REFERENCE [213]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To propose a complete framework for the generation of safety rules implemented in active safety monitors (to maintain the system safety in spite of faults or adverse situations) of safety-critical systems with decisional abilities based on the concept of safety margin. The approach starts from a hazard analysis, and uses formal verification techniques to automatically synthesize the safety rules.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: To focus on the development of active safety monitors for fault tolerance of intelligent decision-making systems. "Their role is to observe the system and its environment, and to trigger interventions that keep the system in a safe state."</p> <p>Assumptions on the safety monitor: "The monitor is the ultimate protection against interaction faults or arbitrary behavior of the control channel that adversely affect safety. To this end, it is equipped with means for context observation (i.e., sensors) and able to trigger safety interventions. The whole safety channel must be assigned a high integrity level. In compliance with safety standards, there must be some degree of independence from the main channel. Moreover, the monitor should justifiably be able to trust the sensors and actuators it uses."</p> <p>Basics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The proposed framework provides a principled approach for specifying the safety rules of an online monitor. It starts from hazard analysis (HAZOP with UML use case and sequence diagrams to describe the system behavior), follows with the translation of its results to a formal predicate logics description (based on variables of the safety monitor) and uses formal verification techniques (based on the New Symbolic Model Verifier - NuSMV) to synthesize the rules that address the hazards. <p>Safety Rule: A safety rule defines a way of behaving in some warning states. It is composed of a condition</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 162 / 550	

	<p>and an intervention (inhibition to prevent a change in system state or action to trigger a change in system state) to apply when the condition is true. The condition identifies a subset of warning states. The intervention is intended to abort catastrophic paths via these warning states.</p> <p>A safety strategy is a set of safety rules intended to ensure an SI. It should abort all paths to the catastrophic states. They shall be checked in such a way that there are no rules conflicting with each other for the safety assurance of the system.</p> <p>2) The rule synthesis problem is formalized by a set of well-structured concepts. These concepts are integrated into an SMOF modeling template and a tool available online, offering predefined elements and auto-completion facilities.</p> <p>3) The rule synthesis tool of SMOF accommodates both safety and permissiveness requirements. The permissiveness requirements may be tuned to the system under consideration.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The proposed framework has been applied to an industrial use case, a mobile manipulator robot for co-working, and led to successful results. The synthesis tool developed and applied at this case study is claimed to consider search spaces with more than 10^{18} strategies, with the number of minimal solutions ranging from zero to thousands.</p> <p>The case study evidenced that some safety requirements could not be addressed by the proposed method due to unobservable data needed for its application. In addition, it has also been identified that the monitors created with the application of the proposed framework still had safety issues, since some safety requirements were violated during physical tests.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitations:</p> <p><i>"A main limitation of using our approach lies in the expression of dependencies or partitions of observable variables. Indeed, the efficiency of the generation could be highly increased when the analyst has a good level of expertise on interrelations between variables."</i></p> <p><i>"Another drawback is that the current version of SMOF does not include a mechanism to activate/deactivate the safety rules depending on the task performed by the system. In most of autonomous applications, this would represent an important issue as systems tend to be more and more versatile. The proposed approach is also limited to the functional level, with simple expression of the SI using propositional logic. For now, we do not consider interventions like blocking requests from decisional layer."</i></p> <p>Future Work:</p> <p><i>"Future directions concern the extension of the framework to the definition of a several warning regions, in order to trigger interventions with different levels of efficiency. For instance, a soft intervention might reduce the speed, and if needed a second hard intervention could activate emergency stop. This approach is also linked to the implementation on different layers (hardware and software) with different integrity levels."</i></p> <p><i>"We also plan to extend SMOF to the observation of the decisional layer (e.g., task or trajectory plans), and possible intervention as rejecting requests from the decisional layer."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good contextualization of intelligent decision-making systems: <i>"Threats may come from faults in the design, from physical failures at run-time, or may be due to complex interactions with users or the environment. These systems have also to cope with many uncertainties in the perception of an unstructured environment. Attaining the required level of confidence calls for the combined utilization of a set of methods that can be grouped into four major categories: 1) fault prevention; 2) fault removal; 3) fault forecasting; and 4) fault tolerant methods."</i></p> <p>2) The research implicitly considers that AI shall be contained within a 'safe envelope' that is defined by means of the proposed framework (i.e. safety strategy that formally describes how the safety monitor shall act to ensure that the intelligent decision-making system remains safe).</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Despite the theoretical soundness of the proposed model, its results on the case study still show that its applicability is limited.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 163 / 550

8.61 REFERENCE [214]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present an approach to learn and formally verify feedback laws for data-driven models of neural networks inferred through regression or actual measurement data. It uses a receding horizon formulation that samples from the initial states and disturbances to enforce properties such as reachability, safety and stability, as well as an over-approximate reachability analysis over the system, supported by range analysis for feedforward neural networks.
Q2 Answer	Feedforward neural networks.
Q3 Answer	The automated neural network verification which is within the scope of the research incorporates safety verification. The proposed method aims to design correct-by-synthesis neural network-based controllers for data driven models by learning a NN model for the controller using the idea of finite-horizon look-ahead from model-predictive control. This method relies on using the NN loss function (defined according to specific mathematical properties for each verified property, namely reachability and region stability) as the cost function which, when minimized, allows selecting the best action for designing the NN.
Q4 Answer	The approach is demonstrated over a series of nonlinear control examples, taken from literature-based benchmarks, for underactuated systems with 2-4 state variable showing how the approach can synthesize region stabilizing controllers and, at the same time, formally verify that these controllers satisfy the region stability property. The controllers involve hundreds of neurons with intermediate verification problems that handle deep networks with hundreds of layers.
Q5 Answer	<i>"Future work will extend our work to more complex specifications such as guaranteed trajectory tracking, and integrate our work with neural network synthesis approaches such as deep reinforcement learning."</i>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting introduction on neural networks training: <i>"Training a network starts from given input-output pairs and a network with a known structure but unknown weights. The goal of the training is to find weights that minimize a predefined loss function that measures the deviation from two sets of outputs."</i></p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Little discussion on safety, since the properties which are checked at the research are necessary but not sufficient for safety assurance.</p> <p>2) The case study is presented in a very simplistic way which prevents adequate discussion.</p>

8.62 REFERENCE [215]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To study a reachability problem for feedforward Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) which, for a given set of inputs to the network and a Lipschitz-continuous function over its outputs, computes the lower and upper bound on the function values. For this purpose, a novel algorithm based on adaptive nested optimization to solve the DNN reachability problem as means to obtain the safety verification problem is presented.
Q2 Answer	Feedforward Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The safety verification problem is translated by the authors into a reachability problem given that it can be considered a robustness measure.</p> <p>Basics: <i>"The approach is inspired by recent advances made in the area of global optimization. For the input subspace defined over a set of input dimensions, an adaptive nested optimization algorithm is developed. The performance of our algorithm is not dependent on the size of the network and it can therefore scale to work with large networks."</i></p> <p>The "(...) algorithm assumes certain knowledge about the DNN", which is translated into a Lipschitz constant. It is possible (...) to compute a tight Lipschitz constant by analyzing the activation functions and their parameters."</p> <p>Details: A dense mathematical deduction is presented to define the method of obtaining the Lipschitz constant of a neural network, starting from an one-dimensional NN and extending the result to multi-</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 164 / 550	

	dimensional ones. The method is shown as NP-complete.
Q4 Answer	<p>A tool has been developed to support the application of the proposed safety verification method, and it has been applied and compared to other tools with regard to the reachability analysis performance. The authors highlight the scalability of the method, which has reduced overhead for large scale neural networks in comparison with two other well-known tools.</p> <p>Several other results are discussed in relation to a case study in which the proposed method is applied to several neural network architectures trained with the same database. The best results indicate no more than 95% of NN robustness given by its reachability.</p> <p>Interesting conclusion: " (...) a DNN with well-chosen layers is safer than those DNNs with very shallow or deeper layers".</p>
Q5 Answer	"Future work includes parallelizing this method in GPUs to improve its scalability on large-scale models trained on ImageNet, and a generalization to other deep learning models such as RNNs and deep reinforcement learning."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Poses interesting question on safety certification: the upper and lower boundaries for an AI-based system (in the case of [213, Deep Neural Networks) output shall be known for proper safety certification --> similar to 'self-contained AI' except for the fact that the AI boundary is known in advance through analyses. Usual methods, e.g. constraint solving problem through MILP, SAT or SMT, and exhaustive / Monte Carlo search algorithms for discretized vector spaces scale badly and can only be performed with linear transformed layers or simple non-linear ones (e.g. ReLU) but not with other approaches.</p> <p>2) Interesting relationship between number of layers of a NN and safety derived from the case studies: " (...) a DNN with well-chosen layers is safer than those DNNs with very shallow or deeper layers".</p> <p>3) The method is based on sound mathematics background.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Little discussion on safety, since the properties which are checked at the research are necessary but not sufficient for safety assurance.</p> <p>2) Possible implicit constraint on applications: "Without loss of generality, we assume the input space is a box-constraint, which is clearly feasible since images are usually normalized into $[0, 1]^n$ before being fed into a neural network."</p> <p>3) Robustness is low-bounded at no more than 95% in the best scenario exercised by the authors. This may be too little for usage within safety-critical systems especially without redundancies.</p>

8.63 REFERENCE [218]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To introduce a novel framework for the resilient design and operation of complex systems via self-organization and control reconfiguration strategies that avoid empirical trial and error techniques and may be implemented and perform in real time on-platform. To accomplish this objective, an integrated and rigorous approach to resilient design while safety considerations ascertain that the targeted system is contained within a safe envelope is introduced.
Q2 Answer	The proposed method employs deep reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: "We introduce an integrated and rigorous approach to resilient design while safety considerations ascertain that the targeted system is contained within a safe envelope."</p> <p>"We introduce a thorough and proactive methodology to resilient design and operation of autonomous systems for improved safety and risk assurance/management that entails the following major steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Threat/hazard characterization - detection, identification, prediction of hazard evolution; performance metrics are specified and used in the development and validation process. 2. Self-organization strategy for systems subjected to severe disturbances (internal or external) with

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 165 / 550	

performance metrics/stability conditions

3. *Reconfigurable control strategy for systems subjected to severe fault modes*

4. *Safety assurance and risk assessment/management methodology.* "Prior to this, "safety margins are defined and designed as an automatic envelope protection system. We will adopt a probabilistic approach to safety assurance and define appropriate safety margins in the context of risk assessment."

"An effective automatic envelope protection system will reduce the compromise between safety and performance."

"The enabling technologies begin with graph spectral and epidemic spreading modeling tools to represent the system behaviors under normal and faulty conditions; a Markov Decision Process is the basic self-organization module. We are introducing a novel approach to fault-tolerance by considering the impacts of severe fault modes on system performance as inputs to a Reinforcement Learning (RL) strategy that trades off system performance with control activity in order to extend the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of the unmanned system."

"An optimal control approach with Reinforcement Learning (RL), Differential Dynamic Programming (DDP) and Model Predictive Control (MPC) is considered as a means for control authority redistribution and reconfiguration when the targeted system is subjected to severe threats/hazards. Prognostic knowledge is incorporated in a quadratic cost function of the optimal control problem as a soft constraint, thus providing a link between health management and reconfigurable control. Success criteria are founded on Lyapunov stability conditions setting the stage for a rigorous approach to verifying the efficacy of the proposed methodology and allowing for comparisons with robust and other classical control methods."

Estimation of System Health by Noisy and Uncertain Data: "We use particle filtering, as a nonlinear filtering method employing noisy observation data to estimate at least the first two moments of a state vector governed by a dynamic nonlinear, non-Gaussian state-space model. Within the particle filtering framework, the Epanechnikov kernel is well suited for uncertainty representation in long-term prediction."

"Outer correction loops may be also implemented using neural networks, fuzzy expert systems, PID controllers, among others. Additional correction loops include the modification of the number of particles used for 1-step or long-term prediction purposes."

"We formulate an Epidemic Spreading Model to estimate a probabilistic measure of system immunity and recovery time (i.e. self-healing). In the epidemic spreading model, disturbances are cascaded within the system model, and system components take on one of three states: susceptible, failed, or fixed (SFF model). Susceptible components are those that can be infected by a failed component, whereas fixed components are those that have healed. The densities of susceptible, failed, and fixed components change over time based on the system dynamics. The model is probabilistic due to the uncertainties."

"We use Kolmogorov Complexity (KC) as a metric of complexity. The full, or ultimate, exploitation of emergence is self-organization; a system aligns itself to a problem (internal or external disturbances) and is self-sustaining, even when the environment changes. We view self-organization as the basic principle for self-healing and immunity-the foundational elements in design of resilient systems.(...) Markov Decision Process is the basic self-organization module; decision-making is based on the current state only."

"*(...) the goal for a robust, reliable and resilient system under fault impacts would be to reorganize the graph and maximize the connectivity while observing the system constraints."

Reinforcement Learning --> "A good definition of the reward function is the key to designing a resilient system, as the reward values can be constantly updated to optimize system resilience." --> Bellman equation.

Fault Tolerance with Reinforcement Learning: "We are introducing a novel approach to fault-tolerance by considering the impacts of severe fault modes on system performances as inputs to Reinforcement Learning (RL) strategy that trades off system performances with control activity in order to extend the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of the unmanned system so that a detrimental event does not occur in the presence of severe fault modes. The proposed approach employs a software solution and does not require a hardware complement to be integrated in the system design. The proposed architecture performs one of three actions, low-level control reconfiguration at the component level, mid-level control redistribution at the sub-system level and high-level mission adaptation at the highest echelon of the architecture."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 166 / 550	

	<p><i>"RL utilizes the concepts of DP and Bellman's principle based on the MDP formulation of an environment, without the knowledge of system dynamics, but measurement data coming from interactions with environments. Since the environment is unknown, learning is realized by exploiting learnt policies and exploring an unknown state-action space."</i></p> <p><i>"Measuring consensus via system entropy allows evaluating the evolution of the distribution of nodal values, rather than the specific nodal values themselves. In addition, it will enable us to understand the structure of the underlying network in terms of its efficiency in attaining a consensus."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p><i>"To illustrate the proposed self-organization method, a hexapod robot is selected as the test system. The mission profile is set for the hexapod to travel from a current point A to a goal point B in a straight-line path."</i></p> <p><i>"The self-organization strategy for a hexapod is tested in VREP (Virtual Robot Experimentation Platform), which is an open source robot simulator with an integrated development environment. (...) A failure mode is then implemented to the hexapod (...) Finally, the proposed self-organization method is applied in the simulator (...) the hexapod starts away from the desired path but steadily turns its direction in the process to reach the desired path. In terms of resilience, the main goal for the hexapod was to reach the desired path, so the trajectory in this case may not be ideal in the perspective of time or total travel distance."</i></p> <p><i>"We have used a number of laboratory UAS platforms in the development and validation of the resilience framework. The first is a model hovercraft designed and built under NASA sponsorship and used for control reconfiguration purposes while the second is a typical ground UAS used to develop and demonstrate the self-organization strategy."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<p><i>"Open questions remain on the theoretical front to expand the introduction of verifiable algorithms and ascertain that they can be fully implemented on-platform meeting stringent computational requirements."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good summary on the challenges of merging AI-based solutions into safety-critical systems: <i>"Achieving higher levels of autonomy in uncertain, unstructured, hazardous and dynamic environments involves data-driven machine learning techniques with many open systems science and systems engineering challenges. Machine learning techniques widely used today are inherently unpredictable and lack the necessary mathematical framework to provide guarantees on correctness, while DoD and industrial applications that depend on safe and correct operation for mission success require predictable behavior and strong assurance."</i></p> <p>2) The method itself is more related to ensuring resilience to systems (including AI-based modules for monitoring residual lifetime and checking for dynamic reconfiguration) and assessing safety as a result of good resilience practices and with a specific confidence index. There is no meaningful discussion about AI and safety despite the usage of the 'safe envelope'.</p> <p>3) It is clear that the safe envelope for the system operation shall be off-line designed by experts.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) The online safety analysis method employs AI within it (reinforcement learning module to trade off system performance with control activity to extend the remaining useful life). How to ensure that this module is also sufficiently safe in such a way that its fault will not lead the system to go outside its predetermined safe envelope? It seems that additional non-AI-based modules are needed to ensure this.</p> <p>2) The following paragraph of the introduction supports that the previous question was not ascertained by the authors: <i>"Resilient design and operation of UAS is the first step towards extending the system's operational envelope in the presence of extreme disturbances and assuring that safety margins are adhered to. The link between resilience and safety is a natural one with the former contributing to the latter's capability to maintain stability requirements. Learning strategies are contributing to a dynamic updating of design for resilience and safety of UAS algorithms ascertaining that "smart" knowledge bases are kept current, data are interpreted correctly and accurate decisions are made to support the operator."</i></p>

8.64 REFERENCE [219]

Q-Index	1
Q1	To propose a modular concept based on which a safety assurance system can be designed and implemented

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 167 / 550	

Answer	for operating autonomous driving cars.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	Background: <i>"For the commercialization of autonomous vehicles, software, sensors, etc. used for autonomous driving functions are required. Parts that may affect safety, such as these, must be released after appropriate safety certification. Therefore, autonomous driving It is necessary to introduce a safety certification system that can guarantee the safety of automobile-related consumers and to establish certification standards."</i> Basics: <i>"We intend to propose a modular safety certification system by combining the process of the composite evaluation system. Langlois (2002) defined the module concept as 'the most common way to solve complex entangled systems'."</i> The authors discuss, compare and relate well-known certification methods (not really directed to safety, sometimes), namely CE-Mark, e-Mark and A-SPICE. Afterwards, a certification process is proposed by merging features of the three aforementioned methods.
Q4 Answer	<i>"We were able to come up with an integrated safety certification system of product and software for practical uses in the future. Through the modular concept, both international and domestic standards policy stakeholders are expected to consider a new structure that can help the autonomous driving industries expedite their commercialization for the technology advanced market in the era of Industry 4.0."</i>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good insight on safety certification of autonomous vehicles (marginally related to the research since this is one of the primary users of the to-be-proposed methodology). 2) Interesting overview on safety and security relationship: <i>"Furthermore, in the case of autonomous vehicles, as the use of software and communication functions has increased, security issues and personal privacy are protected. The problem of hacking should also be considered, and the risk of accidents that may arise from hacking should be prevented."</i> Weakness: 1) The paper does not explore how AI is certified; hence it is deemed only marginally relevant to the research.

8.65 REFERENCE [222]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To inspect the issue of uncertainty in data and the machine learning methods in the domain of autonomous driving with an emphasis on four safety-related cases and propose to address and mitigate them. The core of the approach is on introducing monitoring limiters during development time of such intelligent systems.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, with some focus on neural networks and other deep learning methods in some parts.
Q3 Answer	Premises: 1) The action to be taken in the fail-safe mode is known beforehand. --> Safety envelope. 2) Since the focus is on safety for any AI-related software, risk assessment is not within the scope of the paper. The study is focused in four scenarios typical of autonomous vehicles maneuver planning systems: Case 1: Vehicles trained with test data that differ from the actual operational scenario. Case 2: Vehicles not aware of conventions to perform operations (e.g. to overtake another vehicle, only one vehicle changes lane). Case 3: Hard classifications of deep learning are not able to detect subtleties that can lead to potential accidents (e.g. recognizing a pattern that allows lane changing behind a vehicle and forgetting that the leading vehicle can suddenly break and cause an accident). Case 4: ML algorithms may be overly optimistic as humans are for being trained by humans and, hence, they can be biased to forget the clear recognition of negative outputs (i.e. what NOT to do in certain

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 168 / 550	

	<p>situation).</p> <p>The proposed approaches are as follows:</p> <p>Case 1: To perform Variational Inference (VI) over input data and check if it generates "a distribution which is as similar to the true posterior as possible, where the distance between distributions can be calculated using the Kullback-Liebler Divergence a.k.a. relative entropy." and go to the fail-safe state in case this distance becomes too high. "The advantage of this approach is that the characteristics of expected input are learned from the data, and so no special feature engineering efforts are required. This also means that this approach is highly generalizable and is not bound by the use case."</p> <p>Case 2: To create ontologies to enforce the conventions at the design level and translate them into machine-readable first-order logic, hence acting as a 'safe envelope' around each ML-based component. "Inputs to the component and outputs generated thereby will be tested against the set of environmental constraints to ensure that they are fulfilled, if not, the system enters a fail-safe mode."</p> <p>Case 3: To perform pre-exploration using reinforcement learning (RL) to detect the borderline scenarios which may not be well detected by deep / unsupervised learning. In this situation, the system would feature two intelligent modules: a neural network implemented for the component in question and an RL agent that is responsible for exploring the environment. "The RL agent learns by exploring and interacting with its environment, and so would be trained via simulations to explore even negative outcomes, as in testing these do not pose a real threat to lives. In doing so the RL agent would be able to learn and thereby generate a map of situations, actions, and associated reward values. This mapping can then be used to categorize situations that lead to high, medium, or low risk based on the reward values of each state. (...) Thus, every input being passed to the NN-based component would first be checked against the safety invariance mapping to enter a fail-safe mode when the input is in a catastrophic zone, (...) with the limiting [generalization] factor of additional hyperparameter tuning for the agent."</p> <p>Case 4: The system shall be able to predict inputs and outputs that could lead to negative outcomes (e.g. driving off the road, crash). Hence, if the output falls in a negative class, the system would enter a fail-safe mode. It "brings along the benefit of higher assurance of the system being trained on under-represented or rare situations."</p> <p>Main conclusions:</p> <p>a) Applying just one individual technique is not enough to verify the functionality of an adaptive software;</p> <p>b) Suggestion to use a layered approach where each layer of monitoring for data and application, independent of the other, to focus on one aspect of the safety requirement.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The proposed methods are not exercised, but rather only proposed as solutions to the posed problems. As a result, the method itself is the result of the research.</p> <p>Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"We need to focus on building a toolbox of different verification and validation techniques that can be applied based on the specific needs and specifications of the system."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Data uncertainty is well defined: "The uncertainty in machine learning algorithms can be categorized into two types: (a) random or data dependent, where the noise in the data is captured by the model, resulting in the ambiguity of training input and (b) epistemic or model dependent seen as a measure of familiarity, as it represents the ambiguity the model exhibits when dealing with operational inputs."</p> <p>2) Issues with ML are well aligned with other relevant papers (notably [159] and [208]) and are extended with another case, mentioned "Uncertainty of Prediction": "Every NN has an error rate associated with it, and the aim of the training process is to reduce this error rate as much as possible. In the operational environment, this error rate can be interpreted as an uncertainty associated with the output produced by the model. Though this uncertainty can tell us about how well the system models the environment, it is not accounted for in the cyber-physical systems of today."</p> <p>3) Interesting and apparently sound architectural decisions for dealing with ML data uncertainty, including redundancy of different ML approaches and safety envelopes.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Techniques not exercised in case studies so far.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 169 / 550	

8.66 REFERENCE [223]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To act as a first step towards a framework for measuring and controlling the effects of perceptual influence factors when using Machine Learning and supplying evidence to support claims about perceptual uncertainty.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: Focus on perception and the use of supervised ML to infer state information. <i>"The level of assurance in the safety of an ADS could be expressed in terms of our uncertainty that it will behave acceptably safely in all relevant situations. Then our assurance objective is to reduce this uncertainty to an acceptable level. This is different, but complementary, to the system safety objective of reducing risk to an acceptable level."</i> <i>"When a perceptual component is safety-critical, identifying the factors that influence perceptual uncertainty is a key step in assuring safety."</i></p> <p>Basics: <i>"(1) we present a generic model for thinking about perception components called the perception triangle; (2) we discuss how perceptual uncertainty can be seen as a performance measure used to define safety requirements; and, (3) we identify a set of factors that influence perceptual uncertainty and discuss their measurement and impacts."</i></p> <p>The 'perception triangle' is well aligned with the McDermid's view on dissonance among "what the system is designed to do" (specification world), "what the operator thinks the system is doing" (implementation world), and "what the system is actually doing" (real world - i.e., ground truth).</p> <p>Main Uncertainties:</p> <p>Conceptual Uncertainty (F1): <i>"Conceptual uncertainty influences the selection of development situations and scenarios (F2) by making developers uncertain whether a particular situation or scenario is relevant to exemplify the concept. It also increases labeling uncertainty (F5) by increasing the chances that different labelers will interpret the concept differently. Conceptual uncertainty can be assessed qualitatively, such as by an expert review, or quantitatively, such as through labeling disagreement statistics and additional labeler feedback. The latter requires an enhanced labeling effort that also includes the additional concept and scenario features relevant to F2 and F3."</i></p> <p>Development situation and scenario coverage (F2): <i>"This factor is the degree to which the situations and scenarios used in training and testing cover the specification. It impacts model uncertainty (F6) and, through it, the perceptual uncertainty, which will be reduced if instances of situations and scenarios in specification scope are missed or are too few. Enhanced labeling of training and test datasets with additional concept and scenario features allows computing coverage and frequency statistics to guide the subsequent improvement of these sets; however, extensive validation testing and data collection in the field are necessary to discover so-called unknown unknowns, i.e., new relevant situations and scenarios that cannot be constructed from knowledge collected so far."</i></p> <p>Situation or scenario uncertainty (F3): <i>"The structure of a situation or scenario may limit the observability of the state of interest and thereby allow multiple interpretations. As a result, the perceptual uncertainty will increase. This factor can be assessed through measures such as distance, levels of occlusion, illumination, and clutter, which were already mentioned under F1 and F2. For example, pedestrian distance and occlusions will limit the amount of information about the pedestrian that reaches the vehicle sensors. The impact of these measures on perceptual uncertainty should be assessed in testing."</i></p> <p>Sensor properties (F4): <i>"Sensor properties, in combination with the situation and scenario, may limit the amount of information of interest that is sensed, and thereby increase the perceptual uncertainty. Important sensor properties include sensing mode, range, resolution, noise characteristics, calibration, and placement. The sensor requirements are determined from perception requirements using established methods from sensor engineering. The impact of sensor properties on the overall perception result, especially given a trained model, should be assessed through sensitivity studies."</i></p> <p>Labeling uncertainty (F5): <i>"Human labelers may disagree due to limited knowledge of the concept (F1) or the uncertainty from F3-4 or simply make accidental mistakes when labeling. Established methods exist to measure and reduce this uncertainty."</i></p> <p>Model uncertainty (F6): <i>"There is an uncertainty of what the model has learned in training and what decisions it will make in operation. This uncertainty depends on model class, capacity, and training data"</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 170 / 550	

	<p>and procedure. Confidence measures (e.g., Bayesian deep learning) can be used to provide a run-time measure of model uncertainty."</p> <p>Operational domain uncertainty (F7): "There is also uncertainty whether the situations and scenarios encountered in operation were adequately reflected in training; and whether the sensor properties in operation match those in training." "Novelty detection methods have been proposed to detect out-of-distribution inputs (i.e., outliers)." "The frequency of novel inputs encountered at run-time is a measure of operational domain uncertainty (F7)."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The proposed approaches are not exercised, but rather only proposed as solutions to the posed problems. As a result, the approaches themselves are the result of the research. Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"First, the measurement of the factors and their effects on perceptual uncertainty requires a systematic analysis; in addition to measurement at development time, F3,4,6,7 should also be assessed in operation. Next, methods to control, that is, eliminate or reduce, the negative effects of these factors on perceptual uncertainty, and if not possible, to mitigate the effects, need to be provided. Finally, the argument structures and types of evidence to support claims about perceptual uncertainty in safety cases need to be established."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Important conceptual difference of 'safety' well highlighted: 'AI safety' is usually related to 'reducing uncertainties to an acceptable level', whereas 'system safety' is related to 'reducing risks to an acceptable level'. In this scenario, 'AI safety' is needed but not sufficient for 'system safety'. <i>"The level of assurance in the safety (...) could be expressed in terms of our uncertainty that it will behave acceptably safely in all relevant situations. Then our assurance objective is to reduce this uncertainty to an acceptable level. This is different, but complementary, to the system safety objective of reducing risk to an acceptable level."</i></p> <p>2) Interesting and thorough review on perception uncertainties which is in line with information from other papers (e.g. [56], [132] - both for 'unknown unknowns' - [159], [220]).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Techniques not exercised in case studies so far. 2) No guiding on how to define the appropriate / acceptable requirements for perceptual uncertainties.</p>

8.67 REFERENCE [227]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	<p>To present how a top-down service-based design approach can look like for Cooperative Autonomous Systems (CAS), preparing an effective safety analysis and formulation of black-box behavioral deviation bounds in shape of safety guarantees and demands, pointing out the challenges caused due to the complexity of the distributed CAS development and exemplifying them for a traffic light assistant system.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: Dynamic systems can be assured as safe only during runtime-determined certificates (ConSerts - Conditional Safety Certificates): "<i>Due to the fact that safety is a system property and the runtime operational context is at most incompletely known, safety can only be demonstrated for the Cooperative Autonomous Systems at runtime, but not through the mere safety certification for each constituent system at design time alone. Consequently, parts of the safety assurance need to be shifted into runtime.</i>" <i>"The ConSerts required models and mechanisms have to be synthesized manually already at design time, as the demonstration of sufficient safety with minimum cost needs a certain creativity that machines do not have to date."</i></p> <p>Basics: The method is related on describing the system with a service-oriented architecture rather than a component-oriented architecture. In this approach, ensuring safety falls into ensuring that the respective services are safe on themselves and that the interfaces they provide are well-defined and recognized by users as per the ConSerts. Five types of system interface types were identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Company - Internal - Tier 1 - OEM - Tier 1 - OEM - Tier 2 - Tier 1.1 - OEM - Tier 1.2 - Tier 2

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 171 / 550

	- Vendor 1 - Vendor 2
Q4 Answer	The method is presented within the context of a Traffic Light Assistant (TLA), whose aim is "to make external knowledge from intersection control systems and/or other vehicles accessible to the ego vehicle."
Q5 Answer	"(...) we plan as future work to perform service-oriented safety analyses to identify safety-critical deviations and consider the impact that the interface types identified in this paper have on this task. Furthermore, we will investigate the degree of how much information about employed safety mechanisms needs to be transferred into runtime to allow a successful and safe integration of CAS runtime interfaces in the field."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: Practically irrelevant to the research except for the interesting background on safety certification of dynamic systems.

8.68 REFERENCE [228]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present the Clone-Hunter method for redundant bound check elimination in binary executable files.
Q2 Answer	Affinity Propagation clusterization (machine-learning technique).
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: Legacy applications with defensive programming for array boundaries checking can benefit from better performance while retaining safety by clustering similar code fragments - herein named as 'code clones' -, performing array boundary check only on one element of the cluster and extending that a safe result on this element is valid for all other clusterized elements. This is the base of the 'Clone Hunter' principle, since "There is a high possibility that if checking array bounds is deemed redundant for a certain code fragment, it can also be removed from its corresponding code clones."</p> <p>Basics: "Clone-Hunter [aims] to perform rapid elimination of redundant bound checks in binary applications through identifying code clones, and forming clusters of such clones, we pick random seed samples from each cluster, and with the help of a binary symbolic executor, determine whether bound checks are necessary on the seed. If deemed unnecessary, the decision to remove bound checks is replicated to all of the other clone samples, thereby significantly speeding up the redundant bound check elimination process." "(...) Clone-Hunter presents a new approach that combines statistical methods (such as machine learning to identify code clones) and formal analysis tools (such as symbolic execution) to preserve array bound checks where necessary, while eliminating a vast majority of redundant checks."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We selected 4 different real-world applications: bzip2, hmmmer, lbm and sphinx3 from SPEC2006 benchmark suite and use the largest reference input sets to perform our study." "To evaluate the performance of Clone-Hunter, we deploy a runtime bound checker tool: Softbound that inserts array bound checks into application's binary executable files."</p> <p>" (...) we observed that there are more code clone samples detected with smaller window sizes." The results indicate that the Clone-Hunter assisted symbolic execution time is significantly lower than pure symbolic execution at function-level (2x to 8x faster depending on the application) and vastly superior when considering the full program. This yields execution overhead reduction of up to 50% due to removed dynamic checks (in up to 45%) yet retaining no false positives (i.e. scenarios that should have been checked but were eliminated by the Clone-Hunter approach).</p>
Q5 Answer	"(...)we plan to explore better ways of finding semantic equivalence between code clones, and improve the redundant bound check removal capability of our framework."
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The paper is not exactly category '3', but instead better suited for 'category 1' (AI used to support safety analysis) - hence, its relevance to the research is only marginal.</p>

8.69 REFERENCE [231]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To introduce a dynamic safety management framework incorporating monitoring facilities and runtime safety-models to create safety-awareness in such a way to deal with uncertainties introduced as safety-critical systems, for instance, by Artificial Intelligence. Based on this, planning and execution of safe system optimizations can be carried out by means of self-adaptation.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 172 / 550	

Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: Systems shall be able to be aware of their own safety (i.e., they shall feature self-safety awareness) and, based on this, perform a dynamic safety management.</p> <p><i>"(...) safety manager must complete the safety assurance at design time prior to the systems' deployment. However, compiling a complete safety assurance case prior to the systems' deployment will not be possible for future systems with too many uncertainties at design time.</i></p> <p><i>Therefore, we will need to design resilient systems that dynamically manage and maintain their safety despite any kind of predicted, predictable or unpredictable situation resulting from the immanent uncertainties of future systems. To this end, systems need to become safety-aware and to adapt themselves dynamically to manage and maintain safety in a dynamic trade-off with other functional and non-functional properties."</i></p> <p>Safety Awareness: The aim is to <i>"(...) monitor the system and its environment using different monitoring mechanisms ranging from perception to (simple) error detection mechanisms."</i>, hence allowing <i>"(...) to derive appropriate system adaptations for optimizing the system's performance while guaranteeing its safety."</i> (e.g. deploying software into new hardware nodes if one node fails, adapting the system architecture, adapting parameters and changing configuration as a whole).</p> <p>Dynamic Safety Management: It has two main steps:</p> <p><i>"(1) Analyzing the current risk and the resulting safety goals with the associated integrity levels.</i></p> <p><i>(2) Analyzing the current fulfillment of safety requirements."</i> The latter employs the verification of safety contracts (e.g. ConSerts from [225]) as basis for the verification.</p> <p><i>"Based on this analysis, the system can identify which requirements and thus, which safety goals can be fulfilled at the current point in time. It also knows which configurations are available in each module. Using calculation approaches (...), this enables the system to calculate a valid safe configuration space for the overall system, hence, realizing dynamic safety management."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The proposed method is not exercised, but rather only proposed as a solution to the posed problems. As a result, the approach itself is the result of the research.</p> <p>Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.</p> <p>The conclusion of the paper is as follows: <i>"This mainly shows that we have to rethink safety-engineering traditions for assuring safety of highly dynamic and highly intelligent systems of the future. Despite these open challenges, we believe that dynamic safety management provides a huge potential for future safety assurance."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	To propose the next steps of an overall dynamic safety management framework after combining the techniques and approaches of self-awareness and dynamic safety management presented in the paper.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting summary on the challenges of assuring safety of AI-based systems: <i>"artificial intelligence will be a core technology for autonomy leading to non-deterministic, unpredictable behavior. Systems will dynamically connect to other systems, the surrounding infrastructure, and the cloud to form open systems of systems. We will hardly be able to predict in which situations they will operate, where their software will be executed, and which systems they will interact with in their lifetime."</i></p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Lack of detail regarding the application of the proposed method.</p> <p>2) Little discussion on the next steps of the research.</p>

8.70 REFERENCE [232]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present a method for integrated Cooperative Intelligent Transportation Systems (C-ITS) safety and cybersecurity risk analysis which takes into consideration automotive safety and cybersecurity standards ISO 26262 and SAE J3061.
Q2	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 173 / 550	

Answer	
Q3 Answer	The authors present a method for combining the risk analysis of safety and security for C-ITS based on the frameworks of the safety standard ISO26262 and the security standard SAEJ3061.
Q4 Answer	The proposed method is not exercised, but rather only proposed as a solution to the posed problems. As a result, the approach itself is the result of the research. Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.
Q5 Answer	Further work will include practical implementation of the proposed approach.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: The paper is not directly related to the technicalities of AI-based systems safety analysis, since its only mention to AI is that the method can be applied for AI-based vehicular systems (SAE Levels 3-4 autonomy). Novelty is not meaningful enough for consideration within the research.

8.71 REFERENCE [233]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present a simulation-based approach for generating barrier certificate functions for safety verification of cyber-physical systems (CPS) that contain neural network-based controllers. A linear programming solver is utilized to find a candidate generator function, and the aim of the barrier certificate is to demonstrate that no unsafe system states are reachable from a given set of initial states.
Q2 Answer	Neural network- based controllers trained by means of reinforcement learning (notably policy learning). Even though focus is given to stateless controllers (i.e., feedforward non-linear controllers), the authors claim that the method also applies to stateful controllers (i.e. closed-loop models with recurrent neural networks) with greater complexity only.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: The objective is to bring mathematical rigor through formal verification to closed-loop ACPS models by automatically learning safety invariants - the 'certificate barriers' - for the closed-loop model by using simulations.</p> <p><i>"The key idea of our approach is to reduce the safety verification problem to the identification of a barrier certificate candidate, using simulations of the closed-loop system, and then perform a posteriori verification of the synthesized barrier certificate. The final verification step is performed using a nonlinear SMT solver, which permits our approach to handle neural networks with arbitrary nonlinear activation functions."</i></p> <p>Scope: <i>"In this work, we focus on controllers based on (stateless) feedforward NNs, but note that the general approach outlined in this paper is applicable to closed-loop models with RNNs as well, with the caveat that a stateful controller will increase the query complexity of the verification question that we frame."</i></p> <p><i>"We do not impose any (...) restriction on activation functions, as we reduce the verification questions to nonlinear queries over real numbers, which can be analyzed by dReal – a nonlinear SMT solver based on interval constraint propagation." --> Valid to ReLU and non-ReLU activation functions.</i></p> <p>Barrier Certificate: <i>"(...) the existence of a suitable barrier certificate demonstrates that along any system trajectory with the initial state in X_0 [safe state], a state in U [unsafe state] is not reachable (in finite or infinite time). Thus, a barrier certificate provides a powerful unbounded-time safety certificate of the system."</i></p> <p>Basics: <i>"The method starts by performing a collection of simulations to generate a set of linear constraints that specify the positivity of the candidate generator function, and that it decreases along system trajectories. (...) The SMT solver either produces a counterexample (CEX) that results in an updated candidate generator function, or it returns UNSAT, which certifies that the candidate is sound. Finally, we use the generator function to find the appropriate value of "l" that separates the initial condition set from the unsafe set, and thus acts as a barrier certificate for the system."</i></p> <p><i>"The methods available to select an appropriate "l" value will depend on the class of the chosen generator function and the geometry of sets X_0 and U. (...) a pair of additional SMT queries is performed to check ["l" appropriateness]. (...) If either of these queries returns SAT, then the level set L does not satisfy the desired properties, and a new "l" value should be selected. We can do this efficiently by performing a binary search on a feasible range of l values</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 174 / 550	

	<i>until the SMT solver returns UNSAT."</i>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We demonstrate our technique on a simple case study of a path-following autonomous vehicle. This vehicle uses an NN-based controller that was trained using reinforcement learning (policy learning using evolutionary strategies). We prove that for the given kinematic models of motion of the vehicle, it never leaves a "safe" region around a given fixed path."</p> <p>" (...) our preliminary results are promising, as we are able to handle NN controllers with a thousand neurons and nonlinear activation functions."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"We caution the reader that as this is the first attempt at verification of closed-loop ACPS models, we have not yet applied our technique to real-world ACPS designs, and have thus not encountered the concomitant scalability challenges."</p> <p>"Future work will focus on improving the scalability of our technique and investigating stateful controllers based on recurrent neural networks. We will also investigate algorithms to simultaneously train the neural network while satisfying safety guarantees."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) It provides review information that shall be confirmed by means of the SLR: "(...) from a rigorous mathematical perspective, there has been little achieved towards guaranteeing formal correctness of AI algorithms and their impact on overall safety of ACPS applications in which they may be used. There has been a sudden upsurge in research focusing on formal verification and testing for AI algorithms in the last two years [2016-2018]. These papers focus on analyzing the AI artifacts (such as artificial neural networks, specifically focusing on deep neural networks)."</p> <p>2) Interesting insight on how to consider the environment in the safety analysis of AI-based systems: "When accompanied by environment models, above analyses could be used to reason about the overall system safety as well; however, such decompositional models, where the environment assumptions are provided in a form that is easily composable with the verification or testing algorithms for AI artifacts, are difficult to obtain."</p> <p>3) Good introduction on NN-based controllers by making comparison with control theory: "The most popular of these are controllers based on NNs trained using reinforcement learning approaches such as learning. There are two main kinds of policy neural controllers, the first of which is stateless controllers, which employ a form of feedforward nonlinear control. These controllers could use shallow or deep NNs. The other kind of neural controllers are those based on recurrent neural networks (RNNs); these employ feedback control and are stateful."</p> <p>Stateful controllers: controllers whose behaviors are defined by dynamic equations that are functions of inputs and internal controller states. Stateless controllers: controllers whose behaviors are defined by instantaneous mappings from inputs to outputs.</p> <p>4) Sound mathematical basis and detailed explanation.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The model safety focuses on ensuring that the conceived NN-based model is safe from a functional point of view. No discussion on fault tolerance is performed.</p>

8.72 REFERENCE [237]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present means to estimate the reachable set and study safety verification problems for a class of piecewise linear systems equipped with neural network controllers that employ the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function.
Q2 Answer	Multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural networks.
Q3 Answer	Background: "(...) methods that are able to provide formal guarantees are in a great demand for verifying specifications or properties of systems involving neural network controllers. Even the verification of simple properties concerning neural networks have been demonstrated to be NP-complete problems."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 175 / 550	

	<p>"(...) <i>piecewise linear systems can be effectively used to model many practical systems that are inherently multi-model in the sense that several dynamic subsystem models are required to describe their behaviors such as uncertain systems.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "(...) <i>we will study the reachable set estimation and verification problems for a class of piecewise linear systems with neural network controllers. Since the neural network controller exists in the control loop, it is essential to compute or estimate the output reachable set of the neural network controller to facilitate the computation of the reachable set of the entire closed loop system. For a class of ReLU neural networks, the output reachable set computation is converted into a set of polytope operations. Then, extensions to reachable set estimation for closed-loop systems are made and moreover, the safety verification is then reduced to check for empty intersections between reachable set and unsafe regions.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A numeric example of a piecewise linear system with randomly generated system control matrices has been presented and exercised with a 2-layer neural network with 4 neurons in the hidden layer, 2 neurons in the output layer and randomly generated weights. The results indicate that the system is deemed safe except for some parts, in which the method led to uncertain results.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting overview on why output reachable set computation is important: "<i>the output reachable set computation or estimation of an MLP, which encompasses all possible values of outputs, is necessary to verify the safety property of a neural network based feedback control system</i>"</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The case study is very simple and, hence, does not reflect most practical applications within control systems.</p> <p>2) The model safety focuses on ensuring that the conceived NN-based model is safe from a functional point of view. No discussion on fault tolerance is performed.</p>

8.73 REFERENCE [239]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	<p>To propose an implementation framework of the quantification of margins and uncertainties (QMU) calculation for reliability and safety assessment of high-consequence systems in the presence of mixed (random and epistemic) uncertainties. The random and epistemic uncertainties are represented by a probability distribution and the Dempster–Shafer theory of evidence (DSTE), respectively.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: "(...) <i>a major concern in practical system analysis is to consider various uncertainties, including quantifying random uncertainties and epistemic uncertainties separately. Random uncertainties are irreducible variabilities inherent in nature, whereas epistemic uncertainties are reducible, resulting from a lack of knowledge.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Even though considerable research has been conducted in the area of QMU and its applications, there is still an urgent need for efficient, accurate, and comprehensive QMU tools for dealing with mixed uncertainties in complex engineering problems. The uncertainty propagation, which determines the output uncertainty resulting from input uncertainty, is a general research topic of the QMU process.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: The concept and key measures of the QMU framework are based on a margin and the quantified uncertainty. "<i>The margin (M) is defined as the distance between the nominal response of the system and the performance gate bound (e.g., a failure threshold not to be exceeded), whereas uncertainty (U) is described by the range of system responses caused by different sources of variability (e.g., operating conditions).</i>"</p> <p>"(...) <i>three key elements should be implemented: (1) identification and specification of the performance threshold(s), (2) identification and specification of the associated performance margin(s), that is, measure(s) of exceeding performance thresholds, and (3) quantification of uncertainty in threshold and margin specifications.</i>"</p> <p>The proposed approach aims to estimate QMU metrics by means of a function which combines probabilistic estimates of random uncertainty-affected variables and evidence (belief/plausibility) estimates, by means of</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 176 / 550	

	Dempster-Shafer theory of evidence, of epistemic uncertainty-affected variables. Calculation is performed by means of a two loop-based algorithm with Monte Carlo simulations. Their data is calculated and analyzed through a kriging technique for the regression of interpolated data in order to reduce the computational cost of the method.
Q4 Answer	The proposed approach is demonstrated by means of two case studies: a numerical example of a crank-slider mechanism structure, in order to examine the computational efficiency, and a simulation-based structural analysis of a pressure vessel with corrosion damage. The results indicated the applicability of the method in practical scenarios and that the confidence level is sensitive to the QMU analysis in risk-informed decision-making.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Use of probabilistic and evidence-based theories for quantifying uncertainties and, hence, allowing evaluating their impact over the safe operation of a system. May be useful for quantifying AI-related uncertainties. Weaknesses: 1) The case studies are related to mechanical systems and do not relate with systems in line with the research. An analogy with AI-based systems regardless of the application may require some abstraction effort is needed especially to determine the variables of an AI-based problems that shall be analyzed together with their respective Probability Density Functions. 2) The authors do not mention the applicability of the method to quantify AI-related uncertainties, despite the potential for this.

8.74 REFERENCE [240]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a sampling approach called Deterministic Sampling (DS), which is adapted and evaluated in this work as a potentially more efficient alternative to Monte Carlo sampling for the propagation of random and epistemic uncertainties in Dynamic Event Tree analyses.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	Basics: Deterministic Sampling (DS) " <i>(...) appears to be efficient since relatively few simulations are required, and many parameters can be handled with few deterministic samples. The sample size is a key aspect which provides motivation for evaluating deterministic sampling as an efficient uncertainty quantification method in reactor safety analysis.</i> " " <i>DS has its origin in the field of Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) developed by Julier and Uhlmann and used in several domains of electrical engineering . The basic idea behind DS is that a continuous Probability Distribution Function (PDF) can be substituted by a set of discrete weighted samples, called Sigma Points (SP), if the two representations have the same statistical moments . These SP are few in number. As a result the number of required simulations reduces substantially. This is the key point enabling for practical uncertainty quantification.</i> " " <i>Since most of the available DS variants for calculating sigma points of multiple random variables have deficits in capturing the interactions among the parameters (especially in case of non-symmetric distributed parameters), a more empirical approach has been explored to overcome this deficit. In the present approach, sigma points are obtained by solving the first four statistical moments of each input parameter (mean, variance, skewness and flatness) to represent its individual marginal PDF. Combined effects of simultaneous variation of input parameters are treated by considering the cross combinations of these sigma points. The application and performance of these SP are tested by quantifying the mean and standard deviation of the system Failure Probability (FP) for an illustrative problem.</i> " " <i>Usually, selecting two sigma points from the lower percentile range (0.1 to 20 percentile value), two sigma points from the upper percentile range (80 to 99.9 percentile value) and the mean value of a distribution give sufficient accuracy.</i> "
Q4 Answer	" <i>The application and performance of DS are first tested by quantifying the system failure probability for an illustrative problem, including the propagation of uncertainties. Subsequently, DS is applied to a DET analysis of a realistic nuclear power plant transient, namely, a Station Blackout with feed and bleed</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 177 / 550	

	<i>sequence. (...) The comparison and analysis of the results reveal that the DS-based approach is computationally efficient and practical."</i>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) <i>"(...) the application of DS for random calculations needs to be demonstrated further for the problems, where the likelihood of interference between available time windows (plant) and response/recovery times (safety systems) is rare."</i></p> <p>2) <i>"(...) several aspects of the DS methods still remain to be checked. Firstly, to capture the extreme tails of the output distribution, it may necessary to consider the combination of parameters."</i></p> <p>3) <i>"To determine the bounds of the output distribution for complex nonlinear problems, third (skew) and fourth (flatness) moment of output distribution needs to be calculated. However, use of DS for capturing these higher order moments demands additional computations. Secondly, choosing sigma points can be subjective for long tail distributions, the analyst must ensure the results do not vary significantly depending on the choices made by the analyst. Further, a comparative study between DS method and PCE [Polynomial Chaos Expansion] would be a worthwhile investigation."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Background on epistemic uncertain - difficulty in treating epistemic uncertainty in practical scenarios, e.g., for nuclear power plants probabilistic safety assessment (PSA): <i>"(...) the treatment of the epistemic uncertainties and variability in initial conditions in DET frameworks has not been demonstrated for realistic PSA of power plants. The main reason for this limitation is that the computational requirements to achieve reasonable accuracy in the risk estimate are very large."</i></p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The paper is heavily oriented towards nuclear applications, and an analogy with AI-based systems regardless of the application may require some abstraction effort is needed especially to determine the variables of an AI-based problems that shall be analyzed together with their respective Probability Density Functions.</p>

8.75 REFERENCE [241]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	<p>To propose a number of ways to improve, with emphasis on SAE Level 4 autonomy, Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) validation efficiency, increase effectiveness, and lead to a more defensible safety argument. A layered series of validation steps can help support a conclusion that an HAV system is acceptably safe, even in the absence of a completely specified set of traditional functional requirements for autonomy functions.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>Machine learning in general, except for reinforcement learning.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: <i>"HAV safety validation strategies based solely on brute force on-road testing campaigns are unlikely to be viable. While simulations and exercising edge case scenarios can help reduce validation cost, those techniques alone are unlikely to provide a sufficient level of assurance for full-scale deployment without adopting a more nuanced view of validation data collection and safety analysis. Validation approaches can be improved by using higher fidelity testing to explicitly validate the assumptions and simplifications of lower fidelity testing rather than just obtaining sampled replication of lower fidelity results."</i></p> <p>Basics: The authors present a framework for the safety validation of Highly Automated Vehicles (SAE Level 4), identifying and discussing several factors that provide robustness to the safety arguments - notably how to collect evidence to support them and how to balance analyses, simulations and tests to provide such an adequate robustness. The most interesting aspects related to the research are summarized as follows.</p> <p><i>"Overall, the problem with validating [ML-based systems] according to a V model as is typical in functional safety approaches is that ML system functionality can be opaque to humans. This makes traceability problematic to the degree that humans performing traceability analysis can't analyze design artifacts. Rather than attempt a design-to-test traceability approach according to the V model, we instead explore what can be done with a test-centric approach to areas beyond the obvious scope of practical application of (...) standards which are not designed for ML validation."</i></p> <p><i>"Improving testing efficiency can be accomplished by focusing the test plans for each level of fidelity on</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 178 / 550	

	<p>checking the assumptions and simplifications of lower-fidelity levels of simulation. At the same time, pushing as much simulation as possible to lowest practical level of fidelity will decrease simulation costs. For example, simple coding defects should be found in subsystem simulation (or even pre-simulation via traditional software unit test and peer reviews). On the other hand, rare event requirements gaps might be best found in on road testing if they are due to unforeseeable factors. This leads to an approach based on mitigating residual risks for each level of simulation fidelity."</p> <p>Observability seems an important ingredient to safety assurance, since it provides information on the actions that a system is taking (e.g. autonomous vehicle informs its actions: "I want to change lanes ... I am checking the next lane and there is a car there but it is sufficiently far behind me that I am clear ... I am starting to change lanes ... I am continuing to monitor that the lane is still clear ... the car behind me is speeding up to close the gap ...' and so on". "(...) we must question the integrity of a machine's explanation for its actions." "Rather than having an ML system learn its own feature set for achieving an outcome, it must meet two concurrent goals: (1) display the right behavior, and (2) display a set of narrative descriptions or other explanation that matches its behavior."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The proposed method is not exercised, but rather only proposed as a solution to the posed problems. As a result, the approach itself is the result of the research. Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) "Validating dynamically adaptive ML systems that modify weights or otherwise learn at run-time is beyond the scope of this paper." --> i.e., no reinforcement learning techniques are considered within the study.</p> <p>2) "Our next steps are refining techniques for establishing traceability from safety requirements to test and simulation plans, and applying this approach to at-scale validation activities."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting background information on simulation: "Since simulations involve a model of the system, a model of the environment, and a model of system usage, it follows that no simulation is perfect. The level of fidelity in a simulation is the degree to which it makes simplifications and assumptions about the behavior of the system. Low-fidelity simulations typically execute quickly by using simplified representations of systems (sometimes called reduced-order models), and hence in some sense are "wrong." High-fidelity simulations typically are more complex and are more expensive to execute, but contain with fewer simplifications and assumptions, and are therefore "less wrong." But both types of models can be useful."</p> <p>"Improving testing efficiency can be accomplished by focusing the test plans for each level of fidelity on checking the assumptions and simplifications of lower-fidelity levels of simulation. At the same time, pushing as much simulation as possible to lowest practical level of fidelity will decrease simulation costs. For example, simple coding defects should be found in subsystem simulation (or even pre-simulation via traditional software unit test and peer reviews). On the other hand, rare event requirements gaps might be best found in on road testing if they are due to unforeseeable factors. This leads to an approach based on mitigating residual risks for each level of simulation fidelity."</p> <p>2) Interesting insight on requirements of ML-based systems: "(...) systems that use on-road data as the basis for training machine learning do not ever identify requirements per se. Rather, the training data set is a proxy for something akin to requirements. (...) Successfully validating an HAV requires that test plans capture and exercise the required behaviors, even if expressed implicitly. Regardless of the form, these requirements or proxies for requirements are likely to be incomplete for many initial HAVs deployments."</p> <p>3) Good overview on safety envelopes: "One way to specify safety envelopes is using runtime invariants allocated to a distinct safety checker functional block. As a simple example, a safety envelope for lane-keeping could be that the vehicle stays within its lane boundaries plus some safety margin." "(...) envelopes can be evolved over time in a continuous improvement approach in response to the results of testing and simulation. (...) this evolution works best if it starts with an under-approximation of the safe operating envelope (increasing the high false positive rate) and progressively adds additional envelope area (and accompanying test oracle detail) when analysis shows that doing so is a safe way to increase envelope permissiveness."</p> <p>4) Important argument to support researching safety of ML-based systems: "safety requirements via machine learning-based approaches, it will be important for them to express the results in a way that is interpretable to human safety argument reviewers. However, it is unclear how that might be done. At this point we</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 179 / 550	

	<p><i>recommend using more traditional engineering approaches to defining safety requirements to avoid the same problem of inscrutability that befalls ML-based functionality."</i></p> <p>5) Observability seems an important ingredient to safety assurance, since it provides information on the actions that a system is taking (e.g. autonomous vehicle informs its actions: "<i>I want to change lanes ... I am checking the next lane and there is a car there but it is sufficiently far behind me that I am clear ... I am starting to change lanes ... I am continuing to monitor that the lane is still clear ... the car behind me is speeding up to close the gap ...' and so on</i>". "(...) <i>we must question the integrity of a machine's explanation for its actions.</i>" "<i>Rather than having an ML system learn its own feature set for achieving an outcome, it must meet two concurrent goals: (1) display the right behavior, and (2) display a set of narrative descriptions or other explanation that matches its behavior.</i>"</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) The study only takes into account ML-based systems which do not feature reinforcement learning (i.e., with variable weights and/or that learns at runtime).</p>
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8.76 REFERENCE [242]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To propose a safety analysis framework to be applied to the future intelligent Roadway Transport Systems (RTS) paradigm. It is based on combined fast and real time simulation approaches, the Framework and allows analyzing, in a broad sense, the impacts of concepts, technologies and procedures on RTS safety and efficiency.
Q2 Answer	AI is generically mentioned as being able to be assessed by means of the proposed safety verification simulation approach. There is focus to Fuzzy Logic at the Proof of Concept since the AV control model is based on this approach to control speed and brake intensity with regard to the perceived risks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The proposed framework for the safety analysis of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) comprises four steps, with steps "2" and "3" able to be carried out in a parallel fashion:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Creation of use cases that specify the Roadway Transportation System (including roadway, basic vehicles, system vehicles and drivers), the dynamics to be exercised (including safety procedures) and the safety and performance metrics of the use case (both are considered to assess the tradeoff between them); 2) Fast-time simulation, which instantiates the use cases using fast-time computer-based simulation tools; 3) Real-time simulation, which instantiate the use cases using real-time computer-based simulation tools; 4) Results analysis, which presents the outcomes of the simulation reports analyses. <p>The Use Cases shall be conceived in such a way to maximize the occurrence of hazardous situations and accidents. The AV control model employs fuzzy logic.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A Proof-of-Concept (PoC) is provided, with representative RTS scenarios being modeled, simulated and analyzed using OpenDS, Matlab and Sumo+Veins+OMNet++. The RTS scenario elements (environment, vehicles, roadways, and driver) interact with each other. Autonomous and 'non-autonomous' vehicles share the RTS infrastructure, and AV is modeled combining a pair of RTS elements "driver+ vehicle", with the control algorithms embedded in the autonomous driver element to manage AV movement. In this PoC, both the autonomous vehicle behavior and the impact of its embedded autonomous control algorithms over the RTS safety and efficiency are analyzed.</p> <p>Based on the Proof of Concept that has been studies, the authors claim that the Framework is capable to deal with the representative future RTS scenarios, mainly regarding to AV, analyzing the impact of concepts in component level (e.g. AI-based algorithms) over system level properties (e.g. safety) and the relationship among properties at various levels of RTS.</p>
Q5 Answer	<i>"This Framework evolution will allow resilience analysis over the ACPS-based Road Transport Systems, evolving on the development of new approaches to safety assurance."</i>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Even though focus is given to Autonomous Vehicles, the proposed framework can be extended to other applications with some effort. 2) The proposed framework is successful in modeling elements that are external to the AI, such as the environment.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 180 / 550	

	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Despite the possibility of extension to other applications, the framework is purely application-specific, since it relies on tools for simulating the target application.</p> <p>2) Simulation times may be too small, and the obtained results lean highly towards the non-application of the fuzzy-logic based controller due to the high number of unsafe effects.</p> <p>3) How to ensure that the simulated use cases are enough for exercising the system (as posed by authors of other papers)?</p>
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8.77 REFERENCE [245]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present the current certification practices in unmanned aviation in the context of autonomy and artificial intelligence, focusing on the categories of unmanned aircraft systems and the specific operation risk assessment, which provide means for flight permission not solely focusing on the aircraft but also incorporating the target operation.
Q2 Answer	AI is mentioned in a general way; nevertheless, specific mentions to neural networks are presented since they are deemed by the authors as the most promising and used approach to implement AI within UASs.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: "(...) <i>the achievements in machine learning or artificial intelligence (AI) in general are undeniable and research on e.g. Bayes Deep Learning exist which combine Bayesian approaches with deep learning to reason about the model confidence. (...) these confidence values are similarly dependent on the training data and, therefore, no general statement in which situations the trained nets work is possible. Therefore, a different question might be: How can we embed these techniques within the overall system design to enable certification?</i>"</p> <p>"(...) <i>a common architecture to facilitate hard-to-certify components is to switch to a more conservative backup component in case of an hazardous situation.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: The authors discuss challenges for certifying AI-based Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UASs) from an application point of view and does not detail AI-related aspects. The most relevant questions identified by the authors are the challenges for AI-based systems certification and suggestions for future work. The following questions raised by the authors, on the other hand, are worth noting as relevant:</p> <p>"<i>The certification of AI is currently only possible with a thoroughly documented service history that can establish the necessary trust or a switching architecture relying on detecting misbehavior. It is unclear how existing coverage metrics, such as MC/DC (Monitoring Capability / Flight Capability), could be applied to neural networks to assure functional safety. More research efforts regarding the verification and validation aspects of these new AI techniques are therefore necessary.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>It is unlikely that a certification of these components is possible with traditional means of compliance in the near future. Also, in applications like visual obstacle detection, it is hard to identify a misbehavior, (...), therefore a traditional safety switch to a conservative alternative cannot be used.</i>"</p> <p>"(...) <i>the service history for UAS could be supported by the specific category use cases.</i>"</p> <p>" (...) <i>open questions remain, such as the comparability of the specific category use case, how much service hours are sufficient for safety, and how to ensure proper requirement coverage. Future work will also be necessary on ensuring the safety of the operation and possible mitigation strategies. Also, how AI techniques can be adjusted to a specific operation, e.g. training for operation specific inputs.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	Since the research objective is to present an overview of UAS certification and current challenges, the review itself is the result of the research. Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.
Q5 Answer	<p>"<i>The certification of AI is currently only possible with a thoroughly documented service history that can establish the necessary trust or a switching architecture relying on detecting misbehavior. It is unclear how existing coverage metrics, such as MC/DC (Monitoring Capability / Flight Capability), could be applied to neural networks to assure functional safety. More research efforts regarding the verification and validation aspects of these new AI techniques are therefore necessary.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>It is unlikely that a certification of these components is possible with traditional means of compliance in the near future. Also, in applications like visual obstacle detection, it is hard to identify a misbehavior, (...), therefore a traditional safety switch to a conservative alternative cannot be used.</i>"</p> <p>"(...) <i>the service history for UAS could be supported by the specific category use cases.</i>"</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 181 / 550	

	<p>" (...) open questions remain, such as the comparability of the specific category use case, how much service hours are sufficient for safety, and how to ensure proper requirement coverage. Future work will also be necessary on ensuring the safety of the operation and possible mitigation strategies. Also, how AI techniques can be adjusted to a specific operation, e.g. training for operation specific inputs."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Several of the challenges presented by the authors are in line with challenges posed by other relevant research papers.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) The paper does not address AI in a deep way nor expands on details on how future work could be addressed.</p>

8.78 REFERENCE [247]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To introduce a related novel concept for System Safety Surveillance and Control (SSSC) system as autonomous systems (AS) fallback layer considering safe situational behavior, system malfunctions, and technical fallback layer. In this approach, safety is achieved by separation between regular behavior generation and safety assurance by emergency behavior integration and realization.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>The study proposes that an Autonomous System can feature a System Safety Surveillance and Control (SSSC) subsystem which is composed of 7 independent modules realizable using certifiable Programmable Logic Controllers:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) System State Surveillance (SSS): Generates and supervises the system state. It communicates with SZS, SAP, SBS, DFS, other system components and higher levels. "<i>Generation denotes the aggregation of important information and data for the current situation</i>". 2) Communication State Surveillance (CSS): Responsible for inner and outer communication surveillance. It interacts with the environment, higher system levels, other system components, all other parts of the SSSC and low level control and execution. 3) Degree of Freedom Surveillance (DFS): It includes modules for measurement and estimation between each degree of freedom and its limitation. It communicates with SSS, SAP and SHA. 4) System Boundaries Surveillance (SBS): It is responsible for situation transition generation provided for SHA and SAP. Boundaries are referred to current situation evaluation and resulting situation risk with respect to possible upcoming conflicts like accidents. It communicates with SSS, SAP and SHA. 5) Safety Zones Surveillance (SZS): It comprises modules for signal processing, obstacle/intruder detection, high level communication and arrangement negotiation. It communicates with SS, SHA, higher system levels and the environment. 6) Safety Appraisal (SAP): It assesses the current situation regarding to detected hazards, estimates the situational risk, and derives safety situation weight denoted as safety state. It communicates with SSS, DFS, SBS, CSS, SHA and higher system levels. 7) Safety Handling (SHA): It includes SSSC management modules and safety controllers that act as gateways for low level control layer communication or direct actuator control. It communicates with SZS, SAP, DFS, SBS, higher system levels and low level control and execution.
Q4 Answer	A first proof of concept of SSSC-based fallback layer realization using an experimental example of a three-tank benchmark system is provided. " <i>A system component malfunction is injected in form of a sensor-failure during the filling-process. The component failure is detected by the fallback layer, (...) [and] the system is transferred after a predefined verification time gap into the safe state by situation related control action.</i> "
Q5 Answer	" <i>As next step the development of AES experimental setup for further concept extensions and validations is planned.</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Simple yet useful system architecture for reaching a safe state.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) No direct relation to the safety analysis of AI-based systems, albeit its usefulness within this context.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 182 / 550	

8.79 REFERENCE [251]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To report the outcomes of a workshop involving automotive functional safety engineers that examined, empirically some of the safety concerns that these safety engineers have around assuring the safety of highly-automated driving. The resulting data highlighted the need for a new safety concept and a new risk model and changes to the current legal and standards landscape.
Q2 Answer	Challenges posed for safety assurance of machine learning is among the topics discussed within the paper.
Q3 Answer	The study describes a workshop on the challenges for assuring safety of automotive systems with increasing autonomy. The main discussed topics are as follows: - New Safety Concept for Automated Systems - New Risk Model - Interactive Complexity (including AI impact) - Legal & Standards Landscape - Specificities on ISO26262.
Q4 Answer	The main results for each discussed topic are as follows: - New Safety Concept for Automated Systems: To include more redundancies instead of inherently fail-safe systems; - New Risk Model: To improve the evaluation of environmental aspects and interactions within the Hazard and Risk Analyses (HARA), including that the system's world vision may be different than the real world; - Interactive Complexity (including AI impact): Increased complexity due to interaction with a cloud of other vehicles and infrastructure, V&V strategies (extensive testing with possibly insufficient coverage for rare scenarios, non-determinism and improper learning of ML-based systems); - Legal & Standards Landscape: Dichotomy between public perception and the real hazard landscape, given that new technologies are complex and have the potential to challenge current design and development methodologies; - Specificities on ISO26262: Discussion on concept evolution since its publication and how topics from the other items are covered within ISO26262, including current limitations to deal with some of the posed topics. The authors believe that the ISO26262 risk model is sufficient to cover the safety validation of autonomous vehicles. However, considering functional safety alone will be insufficient to achieve vehicle safety in the future.
Q5 Answer	<i>"Could risk models be modified to support increased automation? And if so, could this provide clues as to how the standards landscape needs to change to support automotive system development? These questions are the subject of ongoing research by the authors."</i>
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) No new insights on the safety validation of AI-based systems.

8.80 REFERENCE [252]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To introduce a simplified real-time environmental situation risk assessment approach to be applied for determination of required situational Autonomous System (AS)'s reliability, including AS's hardware reliability assessment and situational hardware structure and behavior control for AS's safe behavior assurance. The aim of this risk assessment approach is to verify AS's safe situational behavior by real-time environmental risk assessment and AS's hardware structure and emergency behavior control.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	This paper is an extension of the approach proposed by the same authors in [245] within the scope of Autonomous and Semi-Autonomous Aerial Systems (AES) . The new contributions are related to two new techniques included within the System Safety Surveillance and Control (SSSC) subsystem: the Simplified Environmental Situation Risk Assessment (SESRA) approach for determination of required situational vehicle's reliability, and the Runtime System Reliability Assessment and Control (RSRAC) technique for Aerial AES safe situational behavior assurance.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 183 / 550	

	The SESRA is included within four elements of the SSSC: SZS, SSS, SAP and SHA. The SESRA technique is based on modified risk matrix denoted as simplified situational risk matrix, which is related to the current environmental situation. The environmental situation is described by objects and their correlation type with the ego-system so as to derive the object related mishap severity as combination of object related correlation type with the ego-vehicle and its class. The RSRAC technique is realized within SAP and SHA modules and aims to control the hardware structure due to current requirements defined by the system's task and environmental situation.
Q4 Answer	A technical proof of concept is introduced with an approach based on AES and its environment simulation using Virtual Robot Experimental Platform in combination of concept realization using real soft Programmable Logic Controller. The case study is based on an UAV that shall serve food for restaurant guests following a predefined trajectory. Redundant modules are enabled for safety purposes when the system detects that higher SILs are needed to ensure its functioning; otherwise, they are turned off. Fault scenarios are exercised by injecting faults within the simulated environment and watching the UAV response to them by means of the SESRA (which assesses risks related to the fault regarding the environmental perception) and the RSRAC (which provides quantitative safety metrics inputs for the SESRA to perform the risk assessment).
Q5 Answer	<i>"As next step the environmental risk assessment approach will be replaced by advanced situational hazard analysis and risk assessment technique. Furthermore, investigations on risk area definition, separation, and adjustment for situational environment risk assessment will be performed."</i>
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Simple yet useful system architecture for reaching a safe state. Weakness: 1) No direct relation to the safety analysis of AI-based systems, albeit its usefulness within this context.

8.81 REFERENCE [253]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present an overview of the most common approaches and methods used to provide reasoning about joint safety and security, as well as a check of the latest updates in standards related to these properties.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	Main challenges of Autonomous Systems of Systems: " <i>i) emergent behaviors given that they enable continuous evolution of the overall system during its operation; ii) large and often distributed physical systems with complex dynamics; iii) dynamic reconfiguration of the overall system on different time-scales; iv) partial or full autonomy of the subsystems; v) deployment in safety-, and mission-critical systems, where the shortest interruption of service might introduce hazardous and life-threatening events; vi) systems no longer vulnerable only to unintentional threats (i.e., "foreseeable misuse"), but also to intentional threats posing challenges to the system security.</i> " Basics: " <i>(...) the research community has put some effort into studying safety and security properties, identifying similarities and differences, and moreover looking into ways to bring the reasoning around them together. What is clear today is that security provides a significant impact on safety in open and complex systems as autonomous SoS are, and in case of not being treated within the common approach and analyzed by methods capable to take into account both of these properties, one could expect catastrophic hazards and accidents to occur.</i> " The authors have identified that industries tend to separate safety and security analyses, and that academic research has been developing methods that incorporate safety-related security threats within safety analysis methods. The most important public effort for industrial purposes is SAE j3061 guidebook on cybersecurity for the vehicular domain. " <i>However, this document cannot be seen as standard itself, since it provides only a guide on how to include cyber-security when developing complex systems. There is no details on which methods, and techniques are the most applicable and should be used.</i> "
Q4 Answer	Since the research objective is to present an overview of joint safety and security analyses especially with regard to autonomous SoS, the review itself is the result of the research. Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.
Q5	To develop approaches that will support joint safety and security analysis.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 184 / 550	

Answer	
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <p>1) Contextualization and definition of SoS challenges: "<i>i) emergent behaviors given that they enable continuous evolution of the overall system during its operation; ii) large and often distributed physical systems with complex dynamics; iii) dynamic reconfiguration of the overall system on different time-scales; iv) partial or full autonomy of the subsystems; v) deployment in safety-, and mission-critical systems, where the shortest interruption of service might introduce hazardous and life-threatening events; vi) systems no longer vulnerable only to unintentional threats (i.e., "foreseeable misuse"), but also to intentional threats posing challenges to the system security.</i>"</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) No direct relation to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.</p>

8.82 REFERENCE [254]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose an approach for automatically adapting the safety argumentation of open systems during design time, according to the new operational environment information.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>The approach proposed by the author is to automatically build safety arguments to create new evidence regarding the validity of the old safety arguments in the changed operational context. The addressed challenges are as follows:</p> <p>1) Design time and runtime integration of verification evidence in safety cases;</p> <p>2) Handling changes inherited from the openness of systems and impacting the safety arguments via runtime verification, focusing on the following questions: "<i>1) which properties need to be checked at runtime?, 2) when shall they be checked? 3) in which format shall they be depicted to be sent to monitors?, 4) how to integrate the response from the monitors in the safety case?, or 5) how does the evidence obtained at design time collaborate with the evidence generated at runtime for providing the basis for a sound safety argumentation?.</i>"</p> <p>3) Adapting dynamic safety arguments to new evidence.</p> <p>Method:</p> <p>1) To "<i>define a metamodel for describing the standard compliance of a verification evidence according to a specific standard-mandated level of stringency, specified via an assurance level. The metamodel will consider the relationships between standard objectives, software verification and synthesis techniques and safety evidence.</i>"</p> <p>2) To "<i>provide a framework enabling safety cases to communicate properties to be checked by runtime system monitors and to collect and integrate information from system monitors.</i>"</p> <p>3) To provide "<i>living safety argumentation</i>", "<i>which automatically adapts to changes of contextual operation. The approach implies that the safety case of an open system considers foreseeable changes in the operational context of the system and provides a set of argumentation variants which are chosen automatically at runtime, according to the current change.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	The paper is a proposal for a DSc. thesis, hence the proposed method is the actual result of the research. Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.
Q5 Answer	To develop the proposed method and apply them on two case studies: " <i>1) a system of autonomous drones cooperating for intelligent intersection management, and 2) a system of cooperative transport robots in an industrial setting.</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Since the paper is a proposal for a DSc. thesis which extends the work of some meaningful researchers on safety assurance of open systems, there is no extensive detail on the research itself. Moreover, there is no direct relation to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 185 / 550	

8.83 REFERENCE [255]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To show directions of intellectualization of vehicles, analyzed issues and ways to improve safety, reliability and sustainability of transport systems, including situation management methods based on intelligent technologies for improving safety of complex technical systems with incomplete information and high complexity.
Q2 Answer	Deep learning is briefly mentioned as enabling technology for autonomous cars.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "<i>Complex dynamic objects have a high dimensionality of the state space and management decisions, hierarchy, a variety of quality criteria, a high level of noise and external disturbances, so it is difficult for them to solve management problems using mathematical models. Obviously, for systems with incomplete information and high complexity of object of management is increasing the relevance of the application of methods of situational management based on intelligent technologies.</i>"</p> <p>Approach: To create a metaontology for situational management based on expert information regarding problems and solutions for safety management, "<i>Metaontology situational management requires a formed space of knowledge. Under pragmatics we understand the practical aspects of the development and use of field, i.e. the transition from expert knowledge to their models. You can use the precedents for this purpose.</i>" "<i>Precedent = <Problem, Solution></i>". Problems are defined based on system technicalities, and solutions are defined considering the causes for the problem and the actions to mitigate them.</p>
Q4 Answer	Since the research objective is to present an overview of the approach for situational management to ensure safety of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSs), the approach itself is the result of the research. Please refer to the answer to Question 3 for details.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) No direct relation to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.

8.84 REFERENCE [256]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose a bowtie analysis as a conceptual framework for evaluating the safety effect of cooperative intelligent transport systems. The approach utilizes exemplary expert estimates and knowledge from literature on the probability of the occurrence of accident risk factors and of the success of safety measures. Fuzzy set theory is applied to handle uncertainty in expert knowledge.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper, since Fuzzy Set theories are not AI by themselves.
Q3 Answer	<p>"<i>The bowtie analysis starts with the definition and identification of the input and output data. Occurrence and success probabilities of the input events are established based on expert judgment and knowledge from literature. The experts provide the probabilities as linguistic terms, which are then converted to fuzzy numbers, on which the analysis is based.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Especially triangular and trapezoidal shapes are commonly used in engineering to represent approximate fuzzy numbers that are expressed in lingual terms. In this study, triangular fuzzy numbers (TFN) have been chosen to express verbal validations.(...) Thereby, each fuzzy number P is described as a triplet (pL, pm, pU) that represents the lower boundary (i.e. the left value), the most likely value (i.e. at the mode) and the upper boundary (i.e. the right value) of the TFN.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>The knowledge of several experts can be taken into account by assigning weighting factors to the experts. Then, the fuzzy numbers are aggregated by applying the weighted average method.</i>" Afterwards, "<i>fuzzy arithmetic operations for bowtie analysis are applied to calculate the probabilities of the critical event and outcome events. These fuzzy operations for independent cases are based on traditional equations from fault and event tree analysis.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>In order to generate the bowtie model and bowtie diagram, the following parameters must be defined or identified: (a) the critical event (CE), (b) causes that may lead to the critical event, (c) consequences that</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 186 / 550	

	<p>may result from the critical event, (d) safety measures that may change the likelihood of the aforementioned causes and consequences. Thereby, the likelihood of the causes and safety measures is acting as input, while the likelihood of the CE and consequences is acting as output."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"Three illustrative case studies [on road traffic safety] are used to demonstrate the application of bowtie. (...) In the first case study, only regular safety measures (i.e. seat belt and guardrail) are assumed to influence the accident outcome. The additional application of a cooperative proactive safety measure (i.e. a local danger warning system) is assumed to influence the accident occurrence in the second study case. The third case study is performed for the additional application of a cooperative reactive safety measure (i.e. an emergency call system) that is assumed to influence some of the accident outcomes."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) the results of the BTA developed in this study are highly dependent on the provided expert judgment. In order to address this issue, further research is conducted by performing several sensitivity studies on expert judgment. As the level of knowledge is refined in the future by gaining more experience on the maturing safety-related C-ITS, more accurate analysis results can be gained. At some point, expert judgment can be replaced by empirical evidence."</p> <p>"BTA may also be applicable to more holistic approaches, like a systems-based approach to evaluate road safety strategies. This could be an interesting subject to future work."</p> <p>BTA "may over-simplify the dynamic and complex process of accident occurrence, because of the unmeasured relationships and interactions among the accident risk factors."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The bowtie approach is already widely used in other application areas, contrary to what the authors pose. 2) The study is only marginally related to the safety analysis of AI-based systems, in a way that its value is only justifiable to structure a safety analysis method which may consider expert judgment as input to the safety analysis in order to deal with vague information.

8.85 REFERENCE [259]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	<p>To review Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) techniques and extensions, as well as prominent Model-Based Dependability Analysis (MDBA) techniques where FTA can be used. Finally, to outline the future outlook for MBDA, including the prospect of developing expert and intelligent systems for dependability analysis of complex open systems with uncertainties.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper, since Fuzzy Set theories are not AI by themselves.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Model-Based Dependability Analysis (MBDA): Its aim is to simplify dependability analysis by looking at how to automatically synthesize dependability information from system models.</p> <p>The authors summarize the evolution of Fault Tree Analysis throughout the time in order to address challenges such as system dynamics modeling and automated safety models generation. The authors discussion is mainly on Standard Fault Tree Analysis, Component Fault Tree Analysis, Dynamic Fault Tree Analysis, Pandora Temporal Fault Tree Analysis, State Event Fault Tree Analysis, Fuzzy Fault Tree Analysis and FTA within MBTA, including automated generation of Fault Trees by means of HiP-HOPS (Hierarchically Performed Hazard Origin & Propagation Studies), AltaRica, FSAP/NuSMV-SA (Formal Safety Analysis Platform - New Symbolic Model Verifier) and AADL (Architecture Analysis and Design Language).</p> <p>"(...) software tools and expert systems implementing MBDA can be empowered with concepts like data mining and machine learning etc."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The main result of the study is the review on Fault Tree Analysis, including the strengths and weaknesses of each presented method taking into account their evolution with time. Specifically with regard to AI, the only meaningful result presented by the authors is that "(...) software tools and expert systems implementing MBDA can be empowered with concepts like data mining and machine learning etc."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) as most of the MBDA approaches lack in their capability to perform dynamic dependability analysis, it is believed that it is both theoretically and practically important to explore possible ways to develop expert systems for model based dynamic analysis of systems."</p> <p>"It has also been emphasized that more research should be done to develop an expert system by integrating</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 187 / 550	

	<p><i>uncertainty quantification approaches with MBDA approaches so that model based dependability analysis of complex systems could be performed automatically under the conditions of uncertainty.</i>"</p> <p><i>" (...) it has been predicted that the future research may lead to more integrated approach, where different strengths of the existing state-of-the-art MBDA approaches will be used in a complementary manner."</i></p> <p><i>"Finally, emphasis has been put on to perform further research to empower the existing MBDA techniques with new concepts such as machine learning, data mining to make them capable to perform dependability analysis of large and complex open systems."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good and well-structured systematic review on FTAs and Model-Based Dependability Analysis (MBDA). 2) MBDA may be able to provide formal support for the safety analysis of AI-based systems. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) MBDA is still an emerging field, hence requiring additional studies to address simpler questions - presented by the authors themselves - before addressing the safety analysis of AI itself.

8.86 REFERENCE [262]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To propose DuAL Learning-based sAfe Semi-supervised learning (DALLAS) to allow safe semi-supervised learning when only part of the input dataset has been labeled.
Q2 Answer	Semi-supervised learning and supervised learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Since "<i>(...) labeled instances are generally limited and expensively collected in some scenarios</i>". "<i>(...) it is meaningful to design Safe Semi-Supervised Learning (S3L) which never performs worse than Supervised Learning</i>".</p> <p>"<i>(...) since the performance of SSL is not guaranteed to be better than that of SL, it has certain limitations for these methods</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>Dual Learning (DL) assumed there were two dual learning tasks and constructed primal and dual classifiers to teach each other. (...) DL tried to boost the performance of the primal task from the feedback of the dual task over the unlabeled instances.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>DALLAS utilizes a primal model obtained by dual learning to classify each unlabeled instance and then uses a dual model to reconstruct the unlabeled instances according to the obtained classification results. The risk can be measured by analyzing the reconstruction error and predictions of the original and reconstructed unlabeled instances. If the error is small and the predictions are equal, the unlabeled instance may be safe. Otherwise, the instance may be risky and its output should be the approach to be that obtained by Supervised Learning</i>". "<i>(...) the outputs of our algorithm are a tradeoff between those of SL and SSL. In particular, we utilize respectively regularized least squares (RLS) and Laplacian RLS for SL and SSL.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"<i>(...) we carry out a series of experiments on several data sets by the comparison with the state-of-the-art supervised, semi-supervised, and safe semi-supervised learning methods and the results demonstrate that DALLAS can effectively reduce the risk of the unlabeled instances.</i>"</p> <p>The results indicate that DALLAS provide results that, in average, surpass SL and other SSL techniques for some of the datasets considered within the study.</p>
Q5 Answer	" <i>(...) our algorithm can be also designed to deal with the other forms of prior knowledge, such as must link and cannot-link constraints. Additionally, it is worthy to study the safe version of the other semi-supervised learning, such as clustering and regression.</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Insight on the roadmap of learning for safety purposes: based on the authors' motivation (<i>Since "(...) labeled instances are generally limited and expensively collected in some scenarios". "(...) it is meaningful to design Safe Semi-Supervised Learning (S3L) which never performs worse than Supervised Learning".</i>), it seems that solving the issue of approving supervised learning for safety-critical systems comes ahead of solving the issue of approving unsupervised or semi-supervised learning for safety-critical systems. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The customization of some parameters of the proposed algorithm are selected without justification.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 188 / 550	

2) Accuracy rates are significantly low for safety-related applications (<90% for all data sets).

8.87 REFERENCE [266]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To propose a novel approach to ensuring safety while planning and controlling an operation of swarms of drones by deriving the safety constraints that should be verified both during the mission planning and at the run-time and propose an approach to safety-aware mission planning using evolutionary algorithms.
Q2 Answer	Evolutionary computing (based on the Imperialist Competitive Algorithm - ICA).
Q3 Answer	The approach to ensure motion safety of drone swarms is based on evolutionary computing inspired in the Imperialist Competitive Algorithm (ICA), which iteratively generates solutions that progressively maximize the value of the defined fitness function - which is, in turn, designed to introduce safety (safest shortest route for each drone). Safety-aware route planning is augmented with the run-time monitoring and control to deal with the dynamically emerging hazards caused by the deviations while executing the planned mission, e.g., caused by drone transient failures.
Q4 Answer	The authors have presented three case studies: (i.) Three drones moving within a 5 x 5 grid space with obstacles; (ii.) Six drones moving within an 8 x 8 grid space without obstacles; (iii.) Four drones moving within an 8 x 8 grid space with obstacles. They have exercised potential failure scenarios (e.g., drone moving faster than planned, sudden route change), and the proposed algorithm managed to yield safe operation of the entire drone swarm at the expense of up to 8% of route performance for the drones to deviate from the unsafe scenarios.
Q5 Answer	Future work: to test the algorithm in real-life scenario - a video surveillance of a rescue operation.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Interesting idea of safety assurance of a specific application not using machine learning, but a different AI category (evolutionary computing); Weaknesses: 1) Some model parameters are chosen without justification; 2) The method is very application-specific; 3) As mentioned during the TAK phase, this article is related to AI application within a safety context instead of actual AI safety analysis.

8.88 REFERENCE [267]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To develop a novel automated verification framework for feed-forward multi-layer neural networks based on Satisfiability Modulo Theory (SMT), focusing on safety of image classification decisions with respect to image manipulation (e.g. scratches, changes to camera angle or lighting conditions) and define safety with regard to invariance of the classification within a small neighborhood of the original image, so as to avoid the effects of adversarial perturbations. If found, adversarial examples can be shown to human testers and/or used to fine-tune the network.
Q2 Answer	Feedforward neural networks (including regularized and deep learning).
Q3 Answer	Basics: " <i>For a given image x (a point in a vector space), we assume that there is a (possibly infinite) region around that point that incontrovertibly supports the decision, in the sense that all points in this region must have the same class. This region is specified by the user and can be given as a small diameter, or the set of all points whose salient features are of the same type. We next assume that there is a family of operations, which we call manipulations, that specify modifications to the image under which the classification decision should remain invariant in the region . Such manipulations can represent, for example, camera imprecisions, change of camera angle, or replacement of a feature. We define a network decision to be safe for input x and region with respect to the set of manipulations if applying the manipulations on x will not result in a class change for [the region] . We employ discretization to enable a finite exhaustive search of the high dimensional region</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 189 / 550	

	<p>for adversarial misclassifications. The discretization approach is justified in the case of image classifiers since they are typically represented as vectors of discrete pixels (vectors of 8 bit RGB colors). To achieve scalability, we propagate the analysis layer by layer, mapping the region and manipulations to the deeper layers. We show that this propagation is sound, and is complete under the additional assumption of minimality of manipulations, which holds in discretized settings. In contrast to existing approaches, our framework can guarantee that a misclassification is found if it exists. Since we reduce verification to a search for adversarial examples, we can achieve safety verification (if no misclassifications are found for all layers) or falsification (in which case the adversarial examples can be used to fine-tune the network or shown to a human tester)."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Case Studies: "We implement the techniques using Z3 in a tool called DLV (Deep Learning Verification) and evaluate them on state-of-the-art networks, including regularized and deep learning networks. This includes image classification networks trained for classifying hand-written images of digits 0-9 (MNIST), 10 classes of small color images (CIFAR10), 43 classes of the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark (GTSRB) and 1000 classes of color images used for the well-known imageNet large-scale visual recognition challenge (ILSVRC). We also perform a comparison of the DLV falsification functionality on the MNIST dataset against other methods, focusing on the search strategies and statistical robustness estimation."</p> <p>Main Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MNIST: Finding an adversarial example takes up to several minutes. - CIFAR-10: Finding an adversarial example takes from some seconds up to 20 minutes. - ImageNet: Finding adversarial examples was possible for only some types of inputs (e.g. sign mistaken for bird house) and with several dimensional changes (6346). - GTSRB: Easy and fast to find adversarial examples with several German traffic signs. <p>The authors claim that the results, which are exercised with deep neural networks for image classification, are valid to any other application. However, complexity is exponential and makes the method unfeasible for larger images.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) performance and scalability of our method can be significantly improved through parallelization. It would be interesting to see if the notions of regularity permit a symbolic approach, and whether an abstraction refinement framework can be formulated to improve the scalability and computational performance."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The authors pinpoint tools that may be helpful in the safety verification of neural networks, such as DeepFool and Cleverhand, which "compute the average minimum distance to a misclassification and are independent of the data point". An evaluation on their applicability to the research is needed. 2) Interesting and well-presented method valid for image processing. Deemed also valid to other applications if inputs are initially subject to a convolutional neural network that transforms the input data into reticulates. 3) Thorough review on the safety verification of AI, notably with regard to adversarial attacks (see, e.g., section "7 - Related Work" for more detail). <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Strength "2" may only possible if the Convolutional Neural Network for reticulate conversion is also checked as safe.

8.89 REFERENCE [269]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	<p>To describe (1) a framework for the analysis and design of planners (i.e., high-level controllers) capable of run-time hazard identification and mitigation, (2) an incremental algorithm for constructing planning models from hazard analysis, and (3) an exemplary application to the design of a fail-operational controller based on a given control system architecture. Our approach equips the safety engineer with concepts and steps to (2a) elaborate scenarios of endangerment and (2b) design operational strategies for mitigating such scenarios.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 190 / 550	

Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	The off-line planner which is designed for dynamic risk analysis of autonomous systems follows well-established logical and mathematical rules that culminate into a state machine model. The planner is inserted within a safety-critical system as part of a control loop, which can update the planner responses weights (i.e. the transitions between two system states). No AI-related solutions are adopted by the authors.
Q4 Answer	The risk planner is applied to a conceptual driver assistance system. The authors exercise the proposed algorithms and show the risk assessment structure in some scenarios.
Q5 Answer	<p>1) "<i>Based on risk structures, we aim to evaluate criteria such as (i) time, energy, and cost of mitigations, (ii) the role of human intervention, (iii) resilience to change of operational situations, (iv) control system simplicity.</i>"</p> <p>2) "<i>(...) we want to efficiently automate the derivation of acceptable mitigation strategies, and synthesize feasible and affordable mitigation strategies</i>"</p> <p>3) "<i>(...) we aim at using our algorithm to generate such structures on-line given a specific operational situation, and combine this with a transition system switching between operational situations. Given that we use our algorithm on-line, it is important to develop simplification rules (...)</i>"</p> <p>4) "<i>We plan to evaluate our results in the automotive industry whose aims include checking whether fail-operational extensions of given in-vehicle network architectures for automated driving can be made acceptably safe.</i>"</p> <p>5) "<i>(...) for a regulatory agency to apply our approach to AV, we have to show (i) our approach using a large example involving several operational situations, (ii) how our abstraction can be verified, and (iii) that the limits of controllers do not constrain our approach to achieve safe stable control loops.</i>"</p>
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) No direct relation to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.

8.90 REFERENCE [275]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To explore key safety challenges posed by Industry 4.0 and identify the characteristics that its safety assurance should exhibit by proposing a set of safety assurance responsibilities, e.g. system integrators, cloud service providers and 'things' suppliers, and reflecting on the desirable modularity of such a safety assurance approach as a basis for cooperative, on-demand and continuous reasoning for Industry 4.0 architectures and services.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Main safety assurance characteristics:</p> <p>1) Modular and cooperative: Assurance depends on several parties; integrator ensures that the system is safe as a whole; exported constraints and plausible failure modes shall be explicitly communicated by each party and taken into account by the integrator. Harder for service suppliers because "<i>the specification of the properties and conditions is more complex and requires structures such as degradation cascades to fully describe the interaction.</i>"</p> <p>2) Continuous, due to the dynamic architecture of I4.0 systems that stems from reconfiguration;</p> <p>3) On-demand, due to the previous argument. "<i>(...) reconstructing the safety cases might be necessary as a more cost-effective option compared to updating the existing cases.</i>"</p> <p>Safety validation challenge: "<i>(...) the fundamental problem does not lie in how the configurable architectures meet the safety requirements. Rather, the issue lies in the generation of these safety requirements in the first place. (...) These emerging hazards are due to expected, yet unpredictable, reconfigurations or redeployments of the architecture in multiple contexts.</i>"</p> <p>Safety confidence challenge: "<i>Propagating confidence from the different qualitative and quantitative measures associated with the various things and infrastructures is necessary to assess confidence in the safety of the overall configured system. (...) Current approaches to specifying confidence and associating it</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 191 / 550

	<i>with assume-guarantee contract specification for individual components is relatively straightforward compared to the challenge of assessing, dynamically, confidence for the different reconfigurations."</i>
Q4 Answer	Please refer to the answers for Question 3 for the results, since the safety challenges discussion is the main result of the paper.
Q5 Answer	Please refer to the answers for Question 3 for the results, since the safety challenges discussion is the main result of the paper.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good contextualization of Industry 4.0 (together with [83]: it emerged from the marriage of IoT and cloud services (XaaS - X as a Service), and it is characterized by its ability to reconfigure and often optimize autonomously, particularly during operations, with potential benefits in cost reduction, energy efficiency, sharing of resources, and increased flexibility. The reconfigurable, modular and dynamic nature of Smart Factories pose significant safety assurance challenges due to, for example, the lack of control over 'things' and cloud services. Its architecture comprises three elements: the 'things' (sensing and actuation), the 'fog' (storage and processing between the things and the cloud), and the 'cloud' (services / servers). Weakness: 1) No direct relation to technicalities of AI-based systems safety analysis.

8.91 REFERENCE [276]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To study the introduction of safety monitoring into an airport light measurement robot in order to keep the system in a safe state despite hazardous situations.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	The authors develop a safety monitoring system for the automatic control of an airport light measurement robot. The system is based on formal rules specified with the aid of HAZOP-UML and SMOF (Safety MONitoring Framework) and verified by applying the NuSMV tool for Symbolic Model Checking. SMOF is employed to support the definition of safety invariants for the safety-critical functions by fuzzifying continuous sets of variables and including all unsafe scenarios and the actions to mitigate them. At the end, the invariants of each safety-critical function are analyzed in an integrated way to check for potential conflicts.
Q4 Answer	The authors presented a detailed application of the proposed method for an airport light measurement robot, focusing on some of its specific safety-critical functions not covered by operational procedures. The generated invariants were shown to be non-conflicting, but the formal verification with NuSMV allowed identifying missing restrictions stemming from the integration of more than one safety-related function.
Q5 Answer	<i>"(...) we are working on improving the efficiency of the SMOF algorithm for large state spaces. The tool set will also be extended to better support the consistency analysis, using for example modeling conventions to ease the gathering of the synthesized strategies. We also intend to extend the method to a multi-level approach: a cascade of monitors to maintain an invariant, triggering interventions at several levels of the system architecture."</i>
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) No direct relation to technicalities of AI-based systems safety analysis.

8.92 REFERENCE [283]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To propose a new safety assessment model for complex system based on the conditional generalized minimum variance (CGMV) and the belief rule base (BRB). The conditional generalized minimum variance is used to select the key features, BRB is utilized to deal with both quantitative and qualitative information under uncertainty and optimized by the fuzzy subtractive clustering algorithm, and the differential evolution (DE) algorithm is used to identify the optimal BRB parameters.
Q2 Answer	Evolutionary computing (based on the Differential Evolution Algorithm).
Q3	The proposed model is based on the following features:

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 192 / 550	

Answer	<p>1) The system under analysis is subject to CGMV (conditional generalized minimum variance) in order to extract, among all deemed system variables, the ones that potentially impact safety. Fuzzy subtracting clustering algorithms are employed to detect clustering centers which allow mapping the relevant input parameters to the antecedent attributes of the BRB rules in order to minimize the quantity of input parameters employed by the BRB;</p> <p>2) Afterwards, the selected variables are subject to a Belief Rule Base (BRB), which estimates, based on initial expert knowledge iteratively updated with data from a differential evolution optimization algorithm, the weight of each rule that describes the safe behavior of a system. Safety is classified in three groups: normal, medium failure and serious failure.</p> <p>3) Finally, the safety assessment is performed by assessing the rule weights calculated by the BRB and checking how they affect the system safety. For this purpose, utility functions that relate safety to each rule are built.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The new proposed model is applied to evaluate the vibration of the WD615 model diesel engine, which is used to testify the validity of the new model considering that the engine is safe while its vibration is lower than a certain threshold, and that the vibration is directly determined by the gap between the shaft and the bearing connecting rod (greater gap leads to more vibration and, hence, potentially unsafe behavior). Compared with other approaches, the proposed model has shown superior accuracy and less computation complexity, as well as, since it is a “white box” method, the result is clear and easy to interpret.</p>
Q5 Answer	"(...) we plan to take a more holistic application of the CGMV-BRB-based model"
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Well-structured method for the safety analysis of complex systems. It can be applied even to AI-based systems, since it is based on the extraction of relevant system parameters for the analysis.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) The proposed method is based on AI itself; hence, it is needed to ensure that the method itself. Its explainability is a positive aspect towards that path; nevertheless, there is no evidence that the method and its implementation are sufficiently safe to produce safety arguments.</p>

8.93 REFERENCE [287]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a novel methodology that is based on statistical testing in simulated environment contextualized within the RobIL program (Israeli program for R&D of autonomous Unmanned Ground Vehicle).
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: to what degree can algorithms based on AI. Heuristics and statistics be trusted as safe (e.g. path following while detecting and avoiding obstacles).</p> <p>Basics: The purpose of the proposed methodology is to generate an estimation of probability of fatal mishap of an autonomous UGV navigation algorithm, which will be referred here as AUT (Algorithm Under Test). The methodology aims to supplement the existing techniques of hardware and software safety verification, and should be incorporated in the overall UGV system safety estimation through an FTA analysis. The methodology is based on Statistical Testing in a Monte-Carlo manner in a Simulated Environment. The proposed method has five main steps:</p> <p>1) System Requirements Specification, including all scenarios that the system may encounter during its operation and the needed safety target / performance (e.g. minimum distance from an object to avoid collision);</p> <p>2) Development of a Simulation Framework to support the simulation of specified scenarios based on mathematical models of the real world elements (e.g. sensors sensitivity, accuracy, signal delay and noise distribution; vehicle platform response characteristics to various throttle, brakes and steering commands, including response delay time, rise time, overshoot, and settling time), including additional delay and noise for unavoidable modeling inaccuracies. The simulator is assumed to be more restrictive than the real world. Note: the simulator shall be preferably developed by a team that differs from the one which develops the system under study.</p> <p>3) Statistical Sampling: It is done by sampling random scenarios from the Scenario Domain, then generating the appropriate simulation environments and system setups, and running the system under test in these</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 193 / 550	

	<p>scenarios.</p> <p>4) Manual Inspection of Scenarios: Manual inspection of log files of about thirty of the simulated runs is performed, this is done in order verify that the simulator behaved in an expected way.</p> <p>5) Comparison with real world: Based on random sampling and real world realization of about thirty scenarios from Scenario Domain, combined with Statistical Hypothesis analysis to the results from the simulations.</p> <p>Remark: As the conditions in the simulation are supposed to be more severe relatively to the conditions in reality, it is expected that the statistical performance of the system in reality be better than in simulation</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The RobIL Unmanned Ground Vehicle functions are validated by applying the proposed methodology with a Gazebo-based simulator, which is based on ODE (Open Dynamic Engine), an open source rigged body physics engine that allows us to create a high fidelity simulation of platform dynamics in off-road environment and also simulate sensors, including GPS, LIDAR and cameras. The authors claim that sensors were modeled based on real world experiments and that they make sure that the conditions in the simulator are more severe than in reality from the perspective of the system under test; therefore, even though the real platform dynamics are not fully recreated in the simulation, these modeling inaccuracies are deemed absorbed by the more severe vehicle actuation conditions. Only steps 1 and 2 of the safety methodology were exercised with simulated results to linear effort commands of 40%, 70% and 100% of throttle capacity at a gravel environment.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"Further work will include fulfillment of RobIL UGV development, and implementation of the complementary steps 3-5 of the methodology."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors do not provide enough arguments that simulations based on scenario sampling are enough to consider that a system is safe. They do reinforce that hypothesis tests are needed to provide enough confidence, but no evidence regarding their suggestions of "about thirty scenarios" would be enough.</p> <p>2) The research is still on initial steps, and much of the methodology has not been really exercised.</p>

8.94 REFERENCE [289]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	<p>To investigate and compare AI algorithms for risk assessment. These algorithms are classified mainly into Expert Systems, Artificial Neural Networks and Hybrid intelligent Systems, and the study is performed focusing on Fuzzy-Expert System, Neural Networks, and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>Expert systems, neural networks and hybrid intelligent systems.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: AI-based systems are "<i>efficient engineering tools to solve nonlinear problems in complex environments of uncertainty</i>".</p> <p>Basics:</p> <p>1) Expert Systems: "(...) <i>the concept behind expert systems is basically the process of transferring the expertise from a human to a computer program. Then, the concept behind expert systems is basically the process of transferring the expertise from a human to a computer program.</i>"</p> <p>Main types of Expert Systems: Rule-based systems (RB), knowledge-based systems (KB), fuzzy expert systems (FB), and case-based reasoning (CB).</p> <p>Advantages: "(...) <i>capacity to deal with uncertain or missing data, and its ability to combine quantitative and qualitative data.</i>"</p> <p>Main applications: "<i>risk assessment, knowledge base maintenance, probabilistic fault diagnosis, engineering failure analysis, and incident management</i>".</p> <p>2) Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs): "(...) <i>information processing systems which use learning and adaptive capabilities. (...) an ANN consists of a number of nodes connected through directional links. Each node symbolizes an information processing unit, and the arrows symbolize the causal link between connected nodes.</i>"</p> <p>Advantages: "(...) <i>capability of analyzing large quantities of data to determine patterns under uncertain environments (...) in situations where quantitative relationships are not available or inaccurate.</i>"</p> <p>Main applications: "<i>Static pattern recognition class, and dynamic control and monitoring, (...) hazard identification, diagnostic systems, monitoring systems, safety alarms, supervisory systems, chemical sensors</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 194 / 550	

	<p><i>programming, risk assessment, and maintenance planning."</i></p> <p>3) Hybrid Intelligent Systems (HISs): "<i>(...) efficient and robust systems that synergistically combine complementary strengths of diverse computational intelligence techniques, and overcome the weakness of the processing capabilities to solve difficult learning tasks.</i>"</p> <p>Advantages: "<i>(...) micro-level integration of fuzzy-expert systems and neural networks, among others, [due to] (...) their complementary attributes in learning capability, brittleness and explanation. The learning capability is referred to the ability of the model to adapt itself to its current environment. Brittleness is referred to the inability of an intelligent system to deal with lack of information, inexact variables or inconsistent knowledge. And the explanation property is referred to ability to provide users with explanations of the reasoning process employed.</i>"</p> <p>Main applications: "<i>(...) the application of HIS in safety is relatively new, most of this related applications are associated with infrastructure health monitoring, structural damage, seismic hazards and risk analysis.</i>"</p> <p>Main types of HISs: "<i>These techniques are known in the literature as Neuro-Fuzzy systems, Fuzzy Adaptive Networks (FAN), or Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems (ANFIS).</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A case study employing a dataset from a pipeline application (civil engineering - structure assessment) of a reference study has been carried out to compare three different intelligent risk assessment approaches: a Fuzzy Expert System (FES), an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS).</p> <p>Based on the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of all three algorithms, it has been checked that the FES has the best accuracy in the first iterations, but is outclassed by the ANN and the ANFIS after 25 iterations and 10 iterations, respectively. After 60 iterations, the ANN and the ANFIS have practically the same performance, but the ANFIS starts with a better accuracy and converges faster than the ANN to its asymptotic top performance.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p><i>"The limitations established by these artificial techniques, which are object of study for future research, are related with the subjectivity of the defuzzification methods and commonly insufficient data for activation and training the ANNs."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting review on the main AI techniques employed in safety-critical applications.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The risk assessment models are not fully justified by the authors.</p> <p>2) The case study is not related to the research area.</p> <p>3) The paper is only marginally related to the safety analysis of AI itself.</p>

8.95 REFERENCE [295]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	<p>To propose a novel method for solving Horn clauses, which is inspired by a program verification method called trace abstraction refinement, generalizing it and making it easier for verification tasks. Horn clauses can be used as an intermediate language in program verification, decoupling the verification algorithms from the details of the specific programming languages. Solvability of Horn clauses is verified by alternatively analyzing its unfoldings and constructing and manipulating tree automata</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>AI is only cited in the introduction as one of the potential beneficiaries or Horn clauses for verification purposes.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: "<i>We propose a trace abstraction refinement-based method for Horn clause solving. We prove that a set of Horn clauses is solvable iff all of its ground unfoldings are solvable. The latter can be automatically checked in an incremental approach. We use tree automata to collect the ground unfoldings of the set of Horn clauses. Initially a tree automaton is constructed, which captures all ground unfoldings of the set of Horn clauses. In each iteration, a ground unfolding is picked and checked whether it is solvable. If it is not solvable, then the procedure terminates with the conclusion that the set of Horn clauses is not solvable; otherwise a tree automaton is constructed, which collects this ground unfolding and possibly other solvable ground unfoldings. This tree automaton is used in the next steps to prevent the set of ground unfoldings represented by it from being picked again. The above iteration continues until there is no ground unfolding to pick, which means that all the ground unfoldings are proved to be solvable. In this case, we will get the</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 195 / 550	

	<p><i>conclusion that the set of Horn clauses is solvable. Tree interpolation techniques are used during the construction of tree automata. Tree automata have the nice property of closure under union, intersection and complement, which makes it possible to solve Horn clauses by manipulating tree automata."</i></p> <p>Current Satisfiability-Based Verification Techniques (SAT) have been adapted for Horn clause solving.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p><i>"We have implemented a prototype and evaluated the performance on some Horn clause benchmarks. [from the SV-COMP repository, all of which integer linear arithmetic] The result shows that the trace abstraction refinement method needs more iterations to terminate than predicate abstraction-based counterexample guided abstraction refinement (CEGAR), while each iteration takes less time."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<p><i>"Although the overall performance is not so good as predicate abstraction-based CEGAR algorithm, we point out possible improvements."</i></p> <p><i>The "algorithm 1 might not necessarily terminate. However, this is quite reasonable since program verification (which can be reduced to Horn clause solving problems) is generally undecidable. Existing works on program verification usually put a (time, space, etc.) limit on the algorithm, and output 'UNKNOWN' if the algorithm cannot return a result under the limit. Our algorithm can also be modified like that."</i></p> <p><i>"There are two potential overheads in our method. One is the SMT solving procedure, which is well known to be time-consuming. The other is tree automata operations. (...) The potential overhead of our method lies partly in the tree automata operations [, which] might lead to exponential blow-up, and the task of checking emptiness of the intersection of a set of tree automata is EXPTIME-complete. However, by using techniques such as binary decision diagrams, we might be able to handle tree automata of very large sizes."</i></p> <p><i>"(...) improve the trace abstraction refinement algorithm is to compromise and combine the tree interpolants of multiple ground unfoldings for the refinement in each iteration. Techniques such as disjunctive interpolation could be considered for this purpose. The resulting algorithm will take fewer iterations to reach a conclusion at the cost of more time spent in each iteration, possibly having better overall performance."</i></p> <p><i>"For buildheap and floodfill, the tree automata operations lead to state explosion, which result in exhausted memory. This gives us a hint to explore more efficient methods to store and manipulate tree automata."</i></p> <p><i>"Our implementation is quite prototypical. We are considering improving the tree automata library by investigating and trying [other reference] algorithms. Moreover, preprocessing of Horn clauses using large block encoding seems to be a promising improvement since it might largely reduce the number of Horn clauses and uninterpreted predicates, resulting in smaller tree automata in the trace abstraction refinement procedure."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Very well written article, with solid mathematical background to support the proposed method. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Practically no information regarding the application of the proposed method for the formal verification of AI. It seems that the proposed approach will lead to complex tree structures for formal verification, potentially compromising the time effectiveness in assuring that an AI-based algorithm is safe. 2) The paper focuses on verifying algorithms safety only, and it does not have a holistic view on a safety-critical system.

8.96 REFERENCE [297]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present a controller integrity monitoring method for a class of second-order nonlinear uncertain systems incorporating neural network-based adaptive control algorithms. The adaptiveness is to ensure robust tracking performance in the presence of certain modeling uncertainty under consideration during the offline controller design process. Both software and physical faults are considered as detectable by the proposed monitoring method.
Q2	Adaptive neural networks.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 196 / 550	

Answer	
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: <i>"This new challenge of certifying adaptive learning control systems must be addressed to realize their full benefits in safety-critical CPS applications. To that end, the run-time assurance (RTA) architecture provides a promising framework that can potentially maximize the use of advanced adaptive controller with high-performance capabilities, while ensuring the safety of the overall system in a run-time fashion. One of the key enablers of RTA is an online monitoring component that offers early detection of potential malfunctions of the adaptive controller, therefore allowing the timely activation of a fully certified baseline controller to maintain system safety or to conduct degraded degradation."</i></p> <p>Basics: The model is valid for second-order non-linear systems with uncertainty. <i>"The neural network controller adaptiveness is to ensure robust tracking performance in the presence of certain modeling uncertainty under consideration during the offline controller design process. Based on Lyapunov stability analysis, an online controller integrity monitoring scheme is developed to detect the occurrence of controller software/algorithm faults and unanticipated physical component faults, which may lead to unstable learning behaviors and malfunctions of the adaptive controller. Adaptive thresholds for detecting controller malfunctions are derived, ensuring the robustness with respect to modeling uncertainty and neural network approximation error. Additionally, the detectability conditions are investigated, characterizing the class of detectable software faults and unanticipated physical faults. An upper bound on the fault detection time is also established."</i></p> <p><i>"Few studies have considered both controller software faults and physical faults. (...) Adaptive thresholds are developed for detecting controller software faults and unanticipated physical component faults, which may lead to unstable learning behaviors and controller malfunctions. Two important analytical properties, including fault detectability condition and detection time, are rigorously established."</i></p> <p>Faults (random and systematic) are modeled by means of a non-linear function that describes the fault time profile with unknown occurrence time and a fault function. The fault time profile function is a step function, whereas the effects of the fault within the system are modeled by the fault function itself.</p> <p><i>"(...) there is an inherent tradeoff between the robustness to modeling uncertainty and the sensitivity to controller malfunctions (...) the larger the effect of uncertainties is, the more difficult it is for (...) fault detection"</i>.</p> <p><i>"If a controller malfunction is detected sufficiently early, then appropriate actions may be taken to maintain system safety or conduct graceful degradation."</i></p> <p><i>"(...) the larger the effect of faults, the earlier the faults will be detected (...) the larger the effect of uncertainties is, the more difficult it is to detect the fault."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Simulations within a quadrotor altitude control system have been carried out to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed method for controller integrity monitoring in adaptive learning systems.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p><i>"(...) the controller integrity monitoring method might be potentially extended for detecting certain cyber-attacks that affect system stability."</i></p> <p><i>"The challenge of scalability of the method mainly lie at the design of adaptive controller for high-order nonlinear systems with general model structures, which is still an open research problem, and the derivation of adaptive thresholds for controller integrity monitoring."</i></p> <p><i>"Another research direction is to apply and demonstrate the control integrity monitoring method to practical aerospace systems (e.g., a full-scale quadrotor UAV model)."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) One of the few papers that integrate physical and software (systematic) faults of AI-based systems: <i>"Few studies have considered both controller software faults and physical faults. (...) Adaptive thresholds are developed for detecting controller software faults and unanticipated physical component faults, which may lead to unstable learning behaviors and controller malfunctions. Two important analytical properties, including fault detectability condition and detection time, are rigorously established."</i></p> <p>2) Good contextualization on the difficulty of ensuring that the system is safe by means of offline approaches, also pinpointed by authors who are in favor of dynamic safety cases (e.g. J. McDerimid): <i>"With the increasing levels of adaptation and autonomy in complex CPS, the traditional notion that such systems can be fully tested and validated offline is becoming an impossible task."</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 197 / 550	

	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors provide a very interesting model based on control theory for online safety assurance of AI-based systems using AI for this purpose. How to ensure that the AI-based monitor itself is safe?</p> <p>2) Even though the modeling might be intuitive, the authors have not expanded on how to model fault-tolerant systems by means of the proposed model (e.g., how to model redundant elements in hot, warm or cold standby schemes).</p>
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8.97 REFERENCE [302]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose a safety evaluation with dynamic safety contracts between involved parties based on a continuous monitoring, sharing and calculation of safety-related quality characteristics of systems at runtime when the system safety architecture is open and adaptive.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: "<i>Ensuring safety for (...) cooperative functionalities is an essential requirement for getting accepted by the certification bodies. If this is not done, cooperative functionalities have no chance to get introduced to the market. In today's safety standards shifting parts of the safety evaluation to runtime is not considered. (...) For cooperating systems [safety evaluation at development time] is inappropriate since the "adaptation space" would be too large by assessing all possible operational situations at development time. Related cooperative functionalities could not only vary in available or not but also in a predefined set of intermediate stages.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: Dynamic safety contracts based on the Conditional Safety Certificates (ConSerts) are defined between system entities. Each contract has two parts:</p> <p>1) Qualitative safety contract, with a predefined number of qualitative safety guarantee output ports arranged at the evaluation order at runtime after the model is transformed into a computable representation. The output ports are related to input ports through Boolean logic and the objective is to check whether a safety situation is true or false.</p> <p>2) Quantitative safety contract, with "<i>(...) one quantitative safety guarantee output port and an undefined number of qualitative as well as quantitative demand input ports. Quantitative input ports are used in this module to either define a quantitative degradation of the output guarantee more specifically to internal runtime parameters or to build module intern qualitative runtime proofs to check if certain parameters fulfill predefined requirements.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	The authors present the application of qualitative and quantitative safety contracts on a Cooperative Autonomous Cruise Control (CACC) system for autonomous vehicles. The structure of all safety contracts aiming towards the safety of the safe reaction manager is presented and exercised on both virtual and real test scenarios; nevertheless, the results of the tests are not fully presented.
Q5 Answer	" <i>In our future work we want to integrate scenarios with a stronger dependency of cooperation like driverless vehicles in a master-slave configuration as they could be used for harvester scenarios in the agricultural domain. Furthermore we want to investigate how the validity period of the involved runtime safety guarantees can be determined properly.</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good justification on runtime safety assurance (see 'context' information on the answer to Question 3).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No direct mention to the safety assurance of AI-based systems, despite possible contribution to this.</p> <p>2) The case study is not fully exercised.</p>

8.98 REFERENCE [306]

Q-Index	1
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 198 / 550

Q1 Answer	Very similar to [302]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q2 Answer	Very similar to [302]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q3 Answer	Very similar to [302]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q4 Answer	Very similar to [302]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q5 Answer	Very similar to [302]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q6 Answer	Very similar to [302]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences

8.99 REFERENCE [307]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To propose a novel safety assessment approach based on evolutionary dictionary learning and fault tree analysis for complex engineering systems.
Q2 Answer	Support Vector Machines (SVMs).
Q3 Answer	Basics: " <i>First, historical signals are utilized to conduct the clustering learning dictionaries by norm similarity matching model and patch-based evolutionary dictionary learning algorithm. Second, the support vector machine method is employed to identify and reflect the normal and fault operating states. Third, an improved safety risks method is proposed to reflect the probable hazards of different faults on the basis of the fault tree analysis. Finally, this processing on online signals is to offer an effective safety assessment index and update the evolutionary dictionaries and safety routing metrics.</i> "
Q4 Answer	A case study with a hydraulic system with data extracted from a public database is presented by the authors.
Q5 Answer	The authors do not address this question on their paper.
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) The study is more related to employing AI to support safety analysis rather than to the safety analysis of AI-based systems. 2) The method is presented with little detail, notably with regard to how the SVM is modeled and employed within the approach. 3) The results of the case study are presented without much explanation.

8.100 REFERENCE [318]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To introduce an universal and transparent certification process which not only takes functional aspects like environment detection and collision avoidance techniques into account but especially identifies the associated system condition itself as a key aspect for the determination of operational safety and for an automated optimization of operating parameters.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	The authors present that runtime safety analysis is needed to allow the integration of additional or modified components at runtime, as per requirements typical of 'Industry 4.0'. " <i>The extension of the fault models to the unforeseeable environment as well as the interrelation from the technical system to this, while considering the time-dependent relationships, results in a too complex model where faulty assumptions or uncertainties cannot be excluded.</i> " " <i>(...) the environment (...) has considerably more degrees of freedom and should interact concerning safety issues with the technical system similar to a feedback loop to lower existing threats.</i> " The authors deem that the Conditional Safety Certificates (ConSerts) " <i>(...) are most suitable (...) for the certification of autonomous motions mainly because of their open and modular concept as well as their</i> "

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 199 / 550	

	<p><i>efficient runtime evaluation and bottom-up approach. For the safety evaluation of autonomous motion the environment as well as the interaction between system condition and environment at runtime have to be considered additionally. So the ConSert approach is extended in a way that the environment is rated at runtime similar to component conditions based on safety critical factors like distance and angle to unpredictable obstacles. "</i></p> <p>Finally, the authors present the 'Mobile Robot Safety Framework' as a means to provide support for the dynamic safety analysis of an autonomous system. "<i>This frame concept segregates the different components and emphasizes the separation of the regular control, in this case the behavior-based control (IB2C) and the level of safety certification. The IB2C network processes sensor signals based on the planning task and calculates adaptively the optimal actuator activation for a specific environmental situation. (...) The main objective for this module is the safety evaluation based on sensor signals and the available certificates which is according the actuator activation, dominantly overlaid to the regular IB2C network. In case of a malfunction the causing component could be easily derived by analyzing the present certificates at that point of time.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	The main result of the study is the 'Mobile Robot Safety Framework', which was conceived to evaluate the operational safety for the autonomous driving robot RAVON from TU Kaiserslautern. Please refer to Question 3 answers for details on the 'Mobile Robot Safety Framework'.
Q5 Answer	The authors do not address this question on their paper.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Brief mention to interesting failure modes involving equipment typically used in AI-based systems: "<i>(...) stereo cameras through contamination with dust or through temporarily occurring fog in the surrounding area (...) the impact of such environmental aspects as well as the wear of components on component specific safety related functions should be displayed with a more detailed component condition as uncertainty rating.</i>"</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No direct mention to the safety assurance of AI-based systems, despite possible contribution to this area. 2) Possible first paper of a series; it does not include any case study or practical application of the proposed model.</p>

8.101 REFERENCE [332]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present the limitation of the existing reliability and safety engineering tools in dealing with autonomous systems and propose a novel methodology based on statistical testing in a simulated environment.
Q2 Answer	AI is considered within the paper mainly based on the generic expression 'AI Algorithm'. The examples given by the authors include heuristics, rule-based decision, fuzzy logic, neural networks, genetic algorithms and Bayesian networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: AI algorithms rely heavily on designed experience and include significant use of heuristic that cannot be regarded as certainty; moreover, they are generally applied to complex non-linear and non-stationary environments.</p> <p>Basics: The proposed approach for the validation of an AI algorithm is based on their statistical testing in a Monte Carlo fashion within a simulated environment.</p> <p>Step 1: Creating the models of the sensors inputs that are required by the algorithm and the mechanical interfaces of the system with the environment, as well as defining the scenarios of the test. The success of the algorithm under test is graded by a predefined algorithm performance grade function, and the dependability index (reliability/safety) is determined after a sufficient number of scenarios is simulated.</p> <p>Step 2: Adding noise to sensor and platform control commands in order to reduce the effect of model inaccuracies. This assumption and the added noise allows claiming that, in average, performance of an algorithm under test in real world scenarios is bounded from beneath by its performance in the simulated environment scenarios.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 200 / 550	

	Step 3: Defining the quantity of simulated scenarios by means of one-sided confidence intervals assuming 0.95 confidence level for the results and pessimistically bounding the algorithm performance grade distribution parameters with a normal distribution.
Q4 Answer	A simple case study of an autonomous vehicle avoiding collision with a fixed but randomly positioned obstacle within an environment was carried out. Based on the obtained results, the modeled prototype reached low reliability for the referred function (< 80%).
Q5 Answer	1) To include application of the proposed methodology to test the safety of navigation and obstacle avoidance algorithms in a real Unmanned Ground Vehicle system. 2) To explore the sensitivity of AI algorithms to different scenarios features (e.g. velocity, path curvature).
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) Paper related to research in initial steps. 2) Lacking theoretical justification for some aspects (e.g. justification for normal distribution for failure probability, sufficiency of 0.95 confidence for the results, how one ensures that the added noise within the simulations is enough to cover all uncertainties). 3) Case study results are not convincing and yield to an unusable system.

8.102 REFERENCE [340]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To analyze the state-of-the-art of models at runtime from a safety engineering point of view in order to assess the potential of this approach and to identify open gaps that have to be closed in future research to yield a safety assurance approach for open adaptive systems.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: Safety assurance at runtime may be impractical for open adaptive systems due to potential state explosion due to all possible setup combinations.</p> <p>Basics: The authors propose Models@Runtime as a possible means for the systematic development and runtime management of adaptive systems. Models@Runtime includes safety-related activities. It aims to <i>"provide a kind of formal basis for reasoning about the current system state at runtime, for reasoning about necessary adaptations, and for analyzing or predicting the consequences of possible system adaptations. This makes dynamic adaptation tractable, traceable and in some sense predictable."</i></p> <p><i>"In order to create the conceptual safety assurance framework, we incrementally project elements (i.e., typical safety models) of the safety engineering lifecycle to runtime. To do so, we start with SafetyCertificates@Runtime and extend the approach backward step by step along the safety engineering lifecycle. (...) the earlier the shifted element is in the lifecycle, the more engineering activities need to be automated, the more intelligence is required at runtime – and the more difficult it will be for the approach to be realized and accepted."</i></p> <p><i>"SafetyCertificates@Runtime often follows the idea of safety contracts defining a set of safety guarantees provided by the subsystem and a set of safety demands the subsystems require to be fulfilled by the integration context. (...) At runtime, the fulfillment of the demands is checked and the resulting guarantees are derived. (...) it is often necessary to perform additional checks in the integration context at runtime."</i></p> <p><i>"A SafetyCase@Runtime is a formalized, modular safety case that can be interpreted and adapted at runtime. Based on the interpretation, it can be dynamically checked to which extent the safety goals of subsystems are met. With adaptation, the line argument can be adjusted to system adaptations. In addition, the revalidation of evidences at runtime must be supported in case system adaptations lead to the invalidation of evidences."</i></p> <p><i>"V&V-Models@Runtime presume that all models that are necessary to perform validation and verification activities (e.g., test cases, pass/fail criteria, etc.) can be interpreted and adapted at runtime in order to create new evidences after system adaptations."</i></p> <p><i>"HRA@Runtime implies that a hazard and risk analysis model can be interpreted and adapted at runtime. This includes the identification of new hazards and the reassessment of existing hazards after adaptations at the requirement level."</i></p> <p><i>"HRA@Runtime requires V&V-Models@Runtime, which in turn require SafetyCases@Runtime and so on. So it is necessary to decide to which extent we want to shift the safety lifecycle to runtime. This results in a trade-off decision. (...) From an adaptation point of view, however, it is preferable to have as much</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 201 / 550	

	<p><i>flexibility as possible in order to tap the full potential of dynamic adaptation. In consequence, this would require shifting elements of the complete safety lifecycle to runtime."</i></p> <p><i>"it is very probable that the required intelligence as well as the resulting complexity will grow with the number of safety assurance steps that are shifted to runtime."</i></p> <p><i>"An alternative way to ensure the safety of highly adaptive systems is given by different traditional approaches, particularly in the field of fault tolerance. So-called safety bags are a typical concept for monitoring a function to detect anomalies and trigger counter-reactions. Assuming that it would be possible to define a safety bag that can detect and handle any safety-related failure of an adaptive module, it would not be necessary to provide further assurance of that module."</i></p> <p><i>"Conditional Safety Certificates (ConSerts) are a means for facilitating safety certification in the context of OAS. (...) A ConSert is not static but conditional; it usually comprises a number of variants; and it must be available in an executable (and composable) form at runtime. Conditions within a ConSert manifest in relations between potentially guaranteed safety requirements (denoted as guarantees for the remainder of this article) and the corresponding demanded safety requirements (i.e., demands). The demands always represent safety requirements relating to the environment of a component, which consequently cannot be verified yet at design time. A ConSert therefore certifies that the guarantees will hold with acceptable probability under the precondition that the specified safety demands are fulfilled by the environment. Variants come into play because ConSerts usually comprise not only one but a series of different potential guarantees. Eventually, the ConSerts must be available at runtime in an executable representation and the systems need to possess mechanisms for composing and analyzing these runtime models. Using these means makes it possible to establish and maintain safety contracts at runtime that span all levels of a composition hierarchy through pairs of ConSert-based guarantees and demands. (...) ConSerts belong to the class of SafetyCertificates@Runtime. But they also support single elements of SafetyCases@Runtime through the instrument of runtime evidences."</i></p> <p><i>"The ConSerts approach directly addresses the idea of SafetyCertificates@Runtime It is therefore one possible starting point for a safety assurance framework. Additional ConSerts support runtime evidences, which are a first step towards SafetyCases@Runtime."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Apart from the definition of the Models@Runtime framework for the certification of Open Adaptive Systems, the authors present a thorough review on the safety certification of Open Adaptive Systems challenges, state-of-the-art and other frameworks in addition to Models@Runtime.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Open Issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certificate@Runtime: Formalization, variability, runtime representation. - SafetyCase@Runtime: Formalization, runtime representation, adaptation of arguments, realization of runtime evidence; - V&V@Runtime and HRA@Runtime: Fully open. <p><i>"Although the approaches available were not developed with an integrated safety assurance framework in mind, a promising foundation already exists. The main application scenario for the near future is characterized by open systems of systems with subsystems that only adapt to anticipated situations. Combining and advancing existing work on SafetyCertificates@Runtime, development time assurance, and runtime V&V could already provide a sound basic solution for this scenario."</i></p> <p><i>"Existing safety case models in the field of safety engineering provide a sound basis for further extending the idea to SafetyCases@Runtime in order to support more flexible system adaptations. SafetyCases@Runtime appear to be sufficient to support the assurance of a wide range of application scenarios of OAS in safety-critical applications. The largest gap obviously exists if the adaptation includes the requirements. However, we expect that the application of Requirements@Runtime in safety-critical applications will only happen in the long run – leaving sufficient time to mature the safety assurance approaches in parallel."</i></p> <p>See paper's Figure 8 for a possible roadmap to safety assurance of OAS using Models@Runtime.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good justification for not performing safety analysis of open systems only at development time: "(...) predicting all possible system adaptations and covering the complete adaptation space already during safety assurance at development time (...) could easily run into a state space explosion problem and for open systems in particular, the structure cannot be completely predicted at development time." 2) Systematic and well-written review on the safety certification of Open Adaptive Systems. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Not directly related to technicalities of AI safety assurance.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 202 / 550	

8.103 REFERENCE [347]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To show how to operationalize solution concepts based on conditional safety certificates and corresponding runtime analyses, as well as to present in detail how to specify conditional safety certificates, how to transform them into suitable runtime models, and how these models finally support dynamic safety evaluations.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: "Conditional safety certificates (ConSerts) are predefined modular safety certificates of the single systems (i.e., devices) that are to be integrated. Modular certificates are based on the idea of contracts. They define safety guarantees that are fulfilled by a component under certain preconditions. First, the components define a set of safety demands, that is, safety requirements that must be fulfilled by the integration context. Second, they define invariants expressing assumptions made during the safety assurance of the component. These assumptions must be fulfilled by the integration context."</p> <p>" (...) The demands always represent safety requirements relating to the environment of a component, which consequently cannot be verified at design time already."</p> <p>"ConSerts shall be issued by safety experts, independent organizations, or authorized bodies after a stringent manual check of the system. To this end, it is mandatory to prove all claims regarding the fulfillment of safety requirements by means of suitable evidence."</p> <p>"The evaluation process starts from the leaf devices of the composition hierarchy, which have no external dependencies (such as the pulse sensor). The results are propagated up through the composition tree, ConSert by ConSert, over the guarantee-demand relationships between the provided and required services of component configurations, until the root component is reached and the ConSert of the top-level service is evaluated."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The ConSerts are explained and illustrated with a case study from the Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) domain. It is considered that "the AAL system runs on a set-top box as a core node and currently provides only video telephony and Internet-based services. The AAL system can generally access the services of the building automation system via a special gateway. All devices within the apartment comply with the presented approach and with a given interoperability standard."</p> <p>"The AAL system in the example can generally be augmented with new applications when necessary. Such applications are either already available on the AAL set-top box or they can be downloaded online from an AAL service provider."</p> <p>" (...) the AAL system supports other kinds of adaptation scenarios. Changing user requirements or resource situation, or the loss of devices, could all require dynamic adaptation within the system."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"Our next steps will include further integration of the presented concepts into a comprehensive safety engineering process, further development of the tooling, as well as the realization of additional case studies. As for the process integration, our main focus is to investigate how to specify ConSerts out of a safety-case-oriented approach."</p> <p>"In the longer term, we would also like to augment the approach with respect to other properties beyond safety, ultimately supporting the notion of trustworthiness."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good introduction on ConSerts quoted in numerous other papers. Important to notice that ConSerts still require manual action to be issued.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Not directly related to technicalities of AI safety assurance.</p>

8.104 REFERENCE [354]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	Simplified version of [340]. Same authors and same overall study with a simplified specification of Models@Runtime.
Q2 Answer	Simplified version of [340]. Same authors and same overall study with a simplified specification of Models@Runtime.
Q3	Simplified version of [340]. Same authors and same overall study with a simplified specification of

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 203 / 550	

Answer	Models@Runtime.
Q4 Answer	Simplified version of [340]. Same authors and same overall study with a simplified specification of Models@Runtime.
Q5 Answer	Simplified version of [340]. Same authors and same overall study with a simplified specification of Models@Runtime.
Q6 Answer	Simplified version of [340]. Same authors and same overall study with a simplified specification of Models@Runtime.

8.105 REFERENCE [358]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present presents a hazard analysis technique (SimHAZAN) that uses multi-agent modeling and simulation to explore the effects of deviant node behavior within a SoS. It defines a systematic process for developing multi-agent models of SoS,
Q2 Answer	BDI agents (to model the system under analysis); C4.5 decision tree learners (to infer hazards from simulations).
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "This paper is concerned with one aspect of the safety process for SoS, specifically hazard analysis: determining the distinct causal chains by which the behavior of the SoS can lead to an accident." Dynamic reconfigurations "(...) overwhelm the ability of manual hazard analysis and therefore suggest a need for automated hazard analysis".</p> <p>Definition of SoS Hazard: "An SoS Hazard is the combined behavior of two or more distinct nodes within the SoS that could lead to an accident. An accident that can be described by behavior confined to a single node (i.e. a single system hazard) is not a SoS accident, even if that node is acting as part of a SoS."</p> <p>Requirements for SoS Hazard Identification:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Must provide qualitative descriptions of causal chains that relate node-level behaviors, states and interactions to SoS accidents. 2. Be able to model embodied SoS (SoS composed of physical, mobile entities). 3. Be able to express the behavior of all SoS components, including the distinctive behavior of novel technologies. 4. Be able to compose the behavior of interacting autonomous nodes, including some emergent properties. 5. Be able to discover the effects of multiple simultaneous deviations. 6. Be able to propagate the effects of deviations through complex, decentralized and dynamically-reconfigured SoS. 7. Provide a systematic, explicit method that can be applied by researchers and practitioners. 8. Be scalable to systems (here, SoS) of practical concern. 9. All hazards be traced to their possible organizational causes and mitigations" <p>Basics: "SimHAZAN is a semi-automated method for conducting hazard analysis of systems of systems. It guides engineers to build a simulation model of the SoS in question, then guides them to analyze it using specific software tools. The output of this process is a set of hazards that may be present in the SoS." SimHAZAN aims to perform a systematic hazard analysis able to predict rare hazardous scenarios raised by senior engineers and avoiding the costs and extensive reports raised during exhaustive simulations. For this purpose, SimHAZAN is based on simulations, but applies "(...) machine learning techniques to compress the mass of data into a concise set of rules that relates node deviations and environmental conditions to the accidents that they cause", as well as agent tracing techniques "(...) to explain events in the simulation in terms of their causation by other events".</p> <p>Modeling of the System Under Analysis: "There are two key goals for the modeling process: it must provide high confidence that the model is a useful representation of the real system of systems, and (...) it must support a mode of analysis that produces explicit rules which relate deviant behavior to the hazards it causes." (see, e.g., process on [356] Figure 2). BDI agents are proposed by the authors as the main computational model of agents, hence improving their explainability.</p> <p>Inferring Hazards from Simulations: "(...) the analyst needs to find general rules that map deviations to accidents. (...) machine learning techniques are adopted for this purpose. (...) In SimHAZAN, the input to</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 204 / 550	

	<p>the learner is a set of descriptions of runs of the simulation model. The output from the learner is therefore a simplified proxy for the simulation model, a proxy with a much simpler internal mechanism." C4.5 decision-tree learner is used to infer hazards from simulation results, turning discrete and noisy data into human-comprehensible rules.</p> <p>"One complication is that this may result in one deviation rule that actually covers several causal paths – there is no guarantee that the simulation has single unique responses to its inputs. If the simulation is deterministic then this uniqueness will hold, but it can also manifest as an artifact of the learning process – the learner may collapse several distinct relationships into one rule. This is an important area for future work."</p> <p>Fidelity, Validity and Completeness: "It is extremely difficult to argue the fidelity of a complex system simulation. Similarly, it is clear that simulators used for training can lead users to develop dubious intuitions about the real system, and it is possible that SimHAZAN simulations will lead engineers towards incorrect theories about how the SoS operates."</p> <p>" (...) more conventional analyses must be carried out to determine whether it is credible in the real SoS. The role of the simulation analysis is to narrow down a huge analysis space into one that is manually tractable.(...) It is a complement to traditional manual analyses, and requires engineering effort to investigate the hazard hypotheses it raises."</p>
<p>Q4 Answer</p>	<p>The approach is evaluated by comparison to explicit requirements for SoS hazard analysis, and by applying it to a case study. <i>"The SoS consists of a small military unit where a central command node manages a set of UAVs that provide surveillance and reconnaissance over a large area. Each UAV unit consists of a Mobile Air Recon Vehicle (MARV) and the associated ground control station (MARG). The information produced is used by ground-based infantry and special forces to locate and destroy enemy troops. The activity of the various elements in the case study SoS is coordinated via a Combined Operational Picture (COP), which is primarily created by fusing data from UAV sensors. The COP could also include data from other sources, such as a priori plans and conventional intelligence."</i></p> <p>Based on the case study, the authors show that SimHAZAN has the potential to reveal hazards that are difficult to discover when using traditional techniques. <i>"(...) some plausible SoS hazards were found, one of which would only have been reliably discovered by a hazard analysis that propagated deviations between multiple component systems."</i></p>
<p>Q5 Answer</p>	<p>The requirement for SoS Hazard Analysis "all hazards be traced to their possible organizational causes and mitigations" has not been covered as per sated by the authors.</p> <p>"The evidence presented (...) is weakest for requirement 8 ("Must be scalable to systems of practical concern")."</p> <p>"Simulation fidelity remains a problem, but as long as the problem is framed as one of hazard identification and explanation the analyst does not need to be certain – they could content themselves with weak prediction and an experience that, in practice, many of the hypothetical hazards turn out to be real. Beyond that, it is difficult to argue that SimHAZAN analysis is adequately complete – there are no obvious "stopping rules" for modeling or analysis."</p> <p>"The analysis process described here is far from fully automated – although the learning and tracing tools can help, it still requires engineer time, intelligence and creativity. Similarly, creating the required simulation models may be very expensive."</p> <p>"(...) someone else should apply SimHAZAN to a case study without the authors' involvement or direct support; one of the most important attributes for method research is how well a third party can implement the method from its description."</p> <p>"Application to some larger case studies would be very valuable."</p> <p>"One complication is that this may result in one deviation rule that actually covers several causal paths – there is no guarantee that the simulation has single unique responses to its inputs. If the simulation is deterministic then this uniqueness will hold, but it can also manifest as an artifact of the learning process – the learner may collapse several distinct relationships into one rule. This is an important area for future work."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 205 / 550	

	<p>" (...) the authors are investigating the use of heuristic search techniques to explore the risk landscape created by a simulation. This will require improved risk measures within the simulation models so that they create searchable landscapes of risk. Adding such subtle risk measures would also indicate situations where the model is coming close to an accident, but cannot quite reach it; SimHAZAN as it stands does not help find such situations."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Very well written paper with solid theoretical background and practical application. 2) Background information and used techniques are interesting for the safety analysis of AI-based systems, even though this matter has not been explored by the authors themselves nor suggested as future research. <p>Weaknesses</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The authors present an AI-based method for safety analysis, suitable for Category 1 of the Systematic Literature Review. There is not too much significant contribution to Category 3 (Safety Analysis of AI-based Systems). 2) The safety analysis method proposed by the authors is AI-based; nevertheless, the authors have not presented sufficient evidence that the methods themselves are safe. They have just mentioned that the methods provide observability / explainability, which is a much needed quality for that purpose.

8.106 REFERENCE [373]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	<p>To show how the Guaranteed Safe Online Learning via Reachability (GSOLR) framework can be applied to a target tracking problem, in which an observing quadrotor helicopter must keep a target ground vehicle with unknown (but bounded) dynamics inside its field of view at all times, while simultaneously attempting to build a motion model of the target. GSOLR is a framework which combines Hamilton-Jacobi-Isaacs reachability with general machine learning techniques, allowing for the design of robotic systems which demonstrate both high performance and guaranteed safety.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>Machine learning in general.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: "<i>(...) most machine learning algorithms provide no guarantees about how the system will respond to momentary noisy data. (...) One way to overcome this limitation is to pair machine learning algorithms with rigorous safety analyses.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>Hamilton-Jacobi-Isaacs (HJI) reachability analysis guarantees safety by solving a dynamic game in which the two players represent the controls and disturbances to the system, each with opposing goals (i.e. steering the system to an unsafe region of the state space or staying outside of such an unsafe region). If the form of the system model is known, and the controls and disturbances are bounded, one can compute regions of the state space from which the system can be guaranteed to remain safe over some time horizon regardless of the disturbances; these regions are known as unsafe backwards reachable sets.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Guaranteed Safe Online Learning via Reachability (GSOLR) combines HJI reachability analysis with general machine learning techniques in a way that enables an autonomous system to remain safe at all times, while simultaneously using machine learning to enhance its performance online.</i>" It is claimed to be more general than other published models for, e.g., not needing a linear model of the system dynamics.</p> <p>Safety condition: The system dynamics model shall be as close as possible to the system's real behavior, and the control inputs "u" and the system disturbance "d" shall be bounded to be in predicted sets. These restrictions are needed to ensure that predictions through HJI are mathematically valid and reflect the actual behavior of the system. "<i>This is generally overcome by using over-approximation methods, in which the bounds on the disturbance are over-approximated, and the bounds on the control are under-approximated.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>An additional limitation of HJI reachability analysis is its computational complexity. Analytical solutions (...) do not generally exist, so one must use numerical solvers</i>", whose "<i>(...) computational complexity (...) grows exponentially with the dimension of the state space.</i>"</p> <p>Safe response: "<i>Regardless of the specific machine learning method used, however, the general form of the</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 206 / 550	

	<p><i>GSOLR framework is as follows:</i></p> <p>1) <i>When the system state is at the boundary of the unsafe set, perform the optimal control action as determined by the optimal Hamiltonian given by the HJI reachability analysis;</i></p> <p>2) <i>Otherwise, perform whatever control is dictated by the given machine learning algorithm."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>GSOLR is applied to a case study of "a target-tracking problem in which an aerial vehicle is required to maintain a target ground robot within a limited observational field of view at all times, while simultaneously attempting to learn the target's dynamics in an effort to improve tracking performance." with the main objective of showing that machine learning can keep the system safe while improving its performance; target tracking was just the sample application chosen for this end.</p> <p>The obtained results indicate that GSOLR was able to keep the system safe while improving its performance by means of machine learning even in extreme scenarios in which disturbance is artificially exacerbated by the designers (worst-case scenario analysis)</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"We are currently exploring ways to counteract this limitation [exponential growth of numerical solvers for HJI reachability analysis] by developing new solvers which will use adaptive grid methods (or mesh-free methods) for performing the underlying numerical computations, but these implementations have not yet been completed."</p> <p>"As more computationally efficient methods of computing reachable sets are developed, we hope to be able to perform the same sort of experiment using a non-augmented (i.e. 9D) system. This will enable us to incorporate more challenging environments (such as obstacles and occlusions) which would increase the practicality of our system in the real world. Another promising research direction that we are exploring involves combining reachability-based safety techniques with reinforcement learning algorithms for autonomous data collection (i.e. the E3-family of algorithms) in order to enable a vehicle to autonomously and safely learn to control itself, without the need for expert demonstrations."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting method for the safety assurance of AI-based systems. It is based on a safety envelope defined by means of the model premises (e.g. state space, maximum disturbances, validity of the system dynamics model), which is enabled based on the online response of a formal safety assurance method (Hamilton-Jacobi reachability).</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Even though no discussion on fault tolerance is performed, it is deemed that these could be addressed by the proposed model through proper modeling of disturbances. This might be difficult to carry out, though.</p>

8.107 REFERENCE [390]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	Very similar to [347]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q2 Answer	Very similar to [347]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q3 Answer	Very similar to [347]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q4 Answer	Very similar to [347]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q5 Answer	Very similar to [347]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences
Q6 Answer	Very similar to [347]. Same authors and same overall study. Very subtle differences

8.108 REFERENCE [394]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To provide an overview on Plug&Safe approach for composition time safety assurance in systems of systems, elaborate the different facets of trust, and discuss how the approach can be augmented to enable

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 207 / 550

	trust assurance in open adaptive systems.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>"A service <i>S</i> can be trusted when it is acceptably dependable and acceptably secure. This implies that all (lower level) services, that are involved in rendering the service <i>S</i>, comply with corresponding requirements with respect to their dependability and security as well, and that the dependence between these services (and respective systems) can be accepted."</p> <p>"(...) ConSerts might be augmented with additional properties to support an adequate notion of trust. The safety aspect of ConSerts would still work as before, covering everything to assure given safety requirements. The assurance of additional non safety-critical trust properties would work on top of that to improve general trustworthiness of OAS."</p> <p>"Apart from the trust properties we also need corresponding mapping functions in between trust properties of required and provided services of component configurations. These mapping functions should be specified as Boolean expressions, in the same way as it has been done for the safety properties in the ConSerts. The operands of that Boolean expression comprise trust requirements regarding the safety properties of the required services and trust-related runtime evidences. The result of the Boolean mapping function indicates whether a certain level of trust can be offered with the provided service or not."</p>
Q4 Answer	The main result of the paper is the proposal of the Plug&Trust model as an extension of the ConSerts-based Plug&Safety model. A brief and simple discussion of its application to an Ambient Assisted Living system is presented.
Q5 Answer	"(...) we are investigating more complex OAS case studies in the Ambient Assisted Living and commercial vehicle domain."
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) Not directly related to technicalities of AI safety assurance, nor to safety itself.

8.109 REFERENCE [396]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To introduce some representative usages of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) in nuclear field, as well as to discuss some existing problems and suggestions.
Q2 Answer	Artificial Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors present a review on the main applications of Artificial Neural Networks within the nuclear power plants area. The main presented topics are as follows:</p> <p>1) Prediction of key parameters or tendency, e.g. reactor mixture density, reactor two-phase flow regime, critical heat flux and heat transfer coefficient of pool nucleate boiling, maximum fuel cladding temperature during a complete group distribution blockage scenario, local power peaking in the fuel lattice, convective heat transfer of supercritical CO₂ through a single tube, convective heat transfer through a printed circuit heat exchanger using CO₂, Loading Patterns optimization in reactor operation. In all these applications, "ANN can be used with extreme caution and it cannot be used as main tool. In these fields, ANN still has very long way to go."</p> <p>2) Creating intelligent control systems for nuclear plants, e.g. providing actions to operators according to events, presenting graphical trends of relevant parameters, reactor fault diagnosis system. It can be used as an assistant tool, and it must be tested with real data before application.</p>
Q4 Answer	The result of the paper is the review of Artificial Neural Networks usage within nuclear power plants applications. Please refer to the answers of Question 3 for more details on the reviewed topics.
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) the main drawback is their [ANNs] 'black-box' character, which does not allow an easy physical interpretation of the knowledge integrated in the network weights."</p> <p>For the prediction of key parameters and tendency, "ANN can be used with extreme caution and it cannot be used as main tool. In these fields, ANN still has very long way to go."</p> <p>For reactor control systems, ANNs can be used as assistant tools. They must be tested with real data before application.</p>
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) The authors highlight profits and difficulties of ANNs in safety assurance, albeit without fully making the

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 208 / 550	

	<p>connection between both topics: "<i>The main advantages of ANNs are to remove the necessity to find an adequate structure for the correlation/model and to give accurate results; the main drawback is their 'black-box' character, which does not allow an easy physical interpretation of the knowledge integrated in the network weights.</i>"</p> <p>2) The authors also highlight that ANN usage in safety-critical applications of nuclear power plants still needs research and caution.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors do not present the safety analysis of ANN-based systems nor justify their conclusions on using ANNs in some functionalities of nuclear power plants (e.g., assistant tool for reactor control systems, secondary tool for predicting key parameters).</p>
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8.110 REFERENCE [398]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To introduce an ontology-based model-driven engineering process for automating transformations of models in order to assure that the generated formal safety model fulfills a series of requirements that render it analyzable.
Q2 Answer	Declarative (rule-based) machine learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"<i>The domain ontology has been designed for allowing storage, retrieval and correlation of constructs relevant to the Architecture Analysis & Design Language (AADL) specification, the Error Annex and the Behavior Annex and for providing the desirable reasoning capabilities among them.</i>" The ontology was conceived bearing in mind that it should be decidable.</p> <p>Notes:</p> <p>1) Error Annex: "<i>The Error Model Annex provides additional properties related to the reliability of the system components and allows defining state machines for specifying error behavior.</i>"</p> <p>2) Behavior Annex: "<i>The Behavior Annex completes the standard AADL language by additional syntax and semantic definitions to express component behavior.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>The ontology-based representation of components allows the definition of custom inference rules, in order to check the model for potential component inconsistencies. (...) the system detects three types of inconsistencies that render the models invalid for certain types of formal analysis:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Dynamic behavior of components is the situation where the final state of a component depends on a failure ordering scenario (fault tree analysis is impossible).</i> - <i>Conflict transition fire, where there is more than one event that can be triggered simultaneously (fault tree and sequence analyses are impossible).</i> - <i>Incompleteness transition errors, i.e. missing transitions in a component (ill-defined design specification).</i>" <p>The proposed model-driven engineering process comprises the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Select/reuse failure modes from the error model hierarchy.</i> 2. <i>Correlate them with the nominal component models at hand.</i> 3. <i>Check the ontology model for potential component inconsistencies.</i> 4. <i>Transform the extended architecture model to the formal safety model.</i> 5. <i>Analyze the safety model with tools that provide model checking, fault tree, simulation and other analyses.</i>" <p>"<i>Transformation rules are driven by knowledge matching the used constructs through the underlying domain ontology. The first set of rules is devoted to the transformation of AADL components to AltaRica nodes.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>The second set of rules concerns the components' error models and take into account their states and transitions triggered by events. AADL Error Annex events, states and transitions are transformed to equivalent AltaRica events, states and transitions.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>The third set of rules focuses on the failure propagation, filtering and masking mechanisms and the mechanisms for connecting error states to operational modes. AADL Error Annex declarations are transformed into equivalent AltaRica synchronization assignment statements.</i>"</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 209 / 550	

Q4 Answer	<p>The proposed model was applied to a case study "about a double-adder function based on a simple add operation." The authors presented that the tool is able to detect and signal potential issues on the system specification at the design level according to some of the categories of inconsistencies defined by the authors (e.g. fault tree analysis impossibility is not checked), hence allowing "system designers identifying flaws at the design level, without having to interpret errors that are encountered in the formal representation of the system model, which is overly difficult to comprehend."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"Future research and development plans include the incorporation of additional types of inconsistency errors like the loop assert condition problem and the causality loop possibility, which render fault tree analysis impossible."</p> <p>"Another research goal is the development of appropriate support for extending model transformation functionality and for validating the developed transformations. The presented process will be fully beneficial upon the development of appropriate ontology semantics for a range of inheritance relations that will be able to promote component models retrieval and reuse."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The ontology is fully specified by the system designer; as a result, the only inferences performed by the model transformation system are related to the generation of formal design level specification and the detection of potential inconsistencies. The usage of logical inference is not well explained by the authors. 2) The case study is very simple and does not explore potential complex issues of real systems (e.g. model explosion, complexity of underlying interactions among elements). 3) The authors do not explore well the safety assurance capabilities of the proposed model with the case study. 4) The authors do not clarify how their model transformation is sufficiently safe.

8.111 REFERENCE [399]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	<p>To propose and discuss the requirements set to a framework for the safety assessment of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) which (1) covers all three dimensions of road safety—exposure, crash risk and consequence, (2) covers, in addition to the engineering effect, also the effects due to behavioral adaptation and (3) is compatible with the other aspects of state of the art road safety theories.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>The proposed framework for the analysis of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITSs) has nine safety mechanisms:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Direct in-vehicle modification of the driving task: A system influences the driving attention by "giving information, advice, and assistance or taking over part of the task". 2. Direct influence by roadside systems: Similar to item "1", but roadside systems give information to drivers instead of controlling their action or the vehicle. 3. Indirect modification of user behavior: It corresponds to "long-term behavioral adaptation may appear in many different ways (for example, by reallocation of attention resources, by change of headway in a car following situation, by change of expectation of the behavior of other road users). This adaptation may frequently be due to delegation of responsibility of the driving task partly or totally to the system, which the drivers have learnt to rely on." 4. Indirect modification of non-user behavior: "Non-equipped drivers may for example change their behavior by imitating the behavior of equipped drivers (for example, driving closer or faster than they should, not having the equipment). These effects are often evident at the traffic flow level." 5. Modification of interaction between road users: "ITS will change the communication between equipped road users. This change of communication may also influence the traditional communication with non-equipped road users.", e.g., "(...) interaction between drivers and unprotected road users". 6. Modification of road user exposure by means of "information, recommendation, restrictions, debiting" which cover "(...) changes in the amount of travelling, i.e. whether the road user decides to make more or less, or longer or shorter, trips due to the system". 7. Modification of modal choice "by, for example, demand restraints (area access restriction, road pricing, area parking strategies), supply control by modal interchange and other public transport management

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 210 / 550	

	<i>measures, travel information systems. Different travel modes have different accident risks, therefore any measure which influences modal choice, has also impact on traffic safety.</i> 8. Modification of route choice "by route diversions, route guidance systems, dynamic route information systems, hazard warning systems monitoring incidents." 9. Modification of accident consequences only "by intelligent injury reducing systems in the vehicle, by quick and accurate crash reporting and call for rescue, by reduced rescue time".
Q4 Answer	The proposed framework has been applied to the assessment of 12 Intelligent Vehicle Safety Systems (IVSSs) as part of the European Union (EU) eIMPACT project based on accident data provided by the EU TRACE project. Expert estimates for the average effect and efficiency coefficients for each safety mechanism and variable were considered.
Q5 Answer	The authors do not address this question on their paper.
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) There is no justification regarding the confidence on the figures of experts' opinions employed by the author. 2) The paper is not directly related to technicalities of AI-based systems.

8.112 REFERENCE [404]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present a new method of neural networks based on genetic algorithm to determine factors weight for safety assessment.
Q2 Answer	Artificial Neural Networks and Genetic Programming.
Q3 Answer	Motivation: Methods for safety assessment factors determination, such as Expert Investigation Approach, AHP, Factor Analysis Model, and Entropy are affected by man-made factors and fuzzy randomness, hence leading to low veracity; moreover, determination of factors weight in safety assessment is such a nonlinear categorization problem of multiple factors difficult to be described with mathematical formulas. This can be overcome by Neural Networks, but the latter still can have issues to converge to a global optimal solutions, once it is simpler for them to converge to a locally optimal solution only. This is why the Genetic Algorithms are proposed together with the Neural Networks: they can yield proper optimization to reach global minima Safety Assessment Factors. Basics: ANNs with three layers are used. The weights of all neuron layers are initially calculated based on training data and they are afterwards updated by a Genetic Algorithm which considers a fitness function based on the ANN output fitness function ("how well adapted the ANN is to the environment"). The Genetic Algorithm considers specific individuals population based on the data type (140 for object recognition; 240 for handwritten digit recognition) and roulette wheel for selection operations.
Q4 Answer	A case study considering seven safety assessment factors (safety input, hazard status, safety management, man safety consciousness, safety education and training, man safety behavior and safety forewarning are fixed on for the safety assessment factors) is presented by the authors. The authors present the obtained ANN (including the optimized weights) and the results (average scores and mean square error).
Q5 Answer	The authors do not address this question on their paper.
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) There is no justification regarding the contribution of the Genetic Algorithm to the improvement of the ANN results. 2) The paper is not directly related to technicalities of AI-based systems.

8.113 REFERENCE [419]

Q-Index	1
Q1	To argue that analysis tools based on formal methods (e.g. SMT solvers, infinite bounded model checkers,

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 211 / 550	

Answer	and k-induction) can provide suitable modeling notations, effective analysis, and push button automation. Moreover, it is also argued that monitors derived from a safety case provide a potentially certifiable means for entering an adaptive mode of behavior, and that monitors generated from a formally analyzed case can be 'possibly perfect'.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	Background: "(...) <i>the requirements for fully adaptive systems are intentionally incomplete</i> ". The authors argue that, with the evolution of SMT solvers, these can be used to formally verify or deny safety properties of adaptive systems.
Q4 Answer	A case study with a self-checking pair, part of a larger example that is loosely based on the architecture of the Fuel Control and Monitoring Computers (FCMCs) of the Airbus A340-600, is presented by the authors to illustrate their thesis that formal methods can provide modeling notations, effective analysis and push button automation for the safety assurance of an adaptive system. The authors use the modeling notation and tools of SRI's SAL system (Symbolic Analysis Laboratory). SAL's analysis uses SRI's Yices tool, which is a state of the art SMT solver. The authors highlight that some restrictions are outside of what can be specified in the proposed framework, such as the assurance of independence of redundant systems due to independent power supplies. Other characteristics, such as <i>slightly out of specification</i> (SOS) errors, which are one of the sources of Byzantine errors, can be taken into account, e.g., improper inputs at a 'forbidden voltage range' which may be interpreted by '0' by some systems and '1' by other systems depending on their technologies.
Q5 Answer	"Adaptive systems (...) at runtime pose new challenges for certification and particularly for traditional, standards-based methods of certification.(...) They seem likely to prove less effective in fast-moving fields where innovation outstrips the pace at which experience can be incorporated into standards. (...) The trustworthiness of the mode switch from normal to adaptive behavior is therefore particularly critical. One attractive idea is for the mode switch to be triggered by monitoring the runtime behavior of the system against its safety case." "(...) <i>the formal methods employed in the approach render it feasible that monitors could be derived directly from the formal statements of assumptions that are generated in applying the approach.</i> "
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Solid background on Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) and automated solvers: "SMT solvers are fully automated software tools for the problem of checking Satisfiability Modulo Theories; what this means is that they can find satisfying instances - or prove there are none - to problems involving propositional (i.e., Boolean) combinations of terms drawn from a combination of theories that generally includes uninterpreted functions as well arithmetic, bit vectors, and arrays, records, and tuples of these. (...) Although SMT problems are NP-hard, good solvers routinely can solve problems with hundreds of thousands of terms and thousands of variables in a few seconds." "The simplest form of analysis checks whether a given property is true of all reachable states of the system (i.e., is an invariant). If the property is an invariant, it can often be proved to be so using k-induction (where k is a small integer) to generate an SMT problem; if the property is not an invariant, a counterexample can often be generated using k-bounded model checking to generate a different SMT problem. A tool that can generate these kinds of SMT problems is called an infinite bounded model checker (because it solves bounded model checking problems for systems specified over possibly in finite domains - a traditional model checker can deal only with finite state descriptions." 2) Interesting insight on formal verification of adaptive systems that may be useful for AI, since AI introduced adaptiveness to systems. Weakness: 1) The authors consider that software is the only source of adaptiveness for a system: "Because adaptive methods are implemented in software, we consider certification challenges for adaptive systems from a software perspective". Adaptiveness resulting from programmable hardware is not taken into account. 2) There is no explicit mention to AI throughout the paper.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 212 / 550	

8.114 REFERENCE [420]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose the use of a back-propagation neural network to help programmers effectively locate program faults.
Q2 Answer	Artificial Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: <i>"We first train a BP neural network with the coverage data (statement coverage in our case) and the execution result (success or failure) collected from executing a program, and then we use the trained network to compute the suspiciousness of each executable statement, in terms of its likelihood of containing faults. Suspicious code is ranked in descending order based on its suspiciousness. Programmers will examine such code from the top of the rank to identify faults."</i></p> <p>The neural network has "m" input-layer neurons (one for each statement), three hidden-layer neurons and one output-layer neuron; transfer function is considered as sigmoid. The objective is to approximate the output of the neural network as if it were the test of a single statement (which is often unfeasible in real software items). Backpropagation is performed to minimize the network error up to a limit defined by the designer (in this case, 1E-3).</p> <p>The model is also optimized to reduce the set of candidate suspicious statements, starting with a filter based on test scenarios which yielded to failed test scenarios.</p>
Q4 Answer	<i>"Four case studies on different programs (the Siemens suite, the Unix suite, grep and gzip) are conducted. Our results suggest that a BP neural network-based fault localization method is effective in locating program faults."</i> Different metrics and reference SW bugs analysis tools are presented by the authors to support their results. In summary, the method proposed by the authors is better than the state-of-the-art method called 'Tarantula' even in its most optimistic scenario for most of the case studies, with advantages being higher in smaller programs.
Q5 Answer	<p>1) The proposed method has not still been fully tested to detect defects in software items with more than one bug. <i>"A future goal of our research is to determine whether it is possible to simply apply the BPNN method iteratively to locate one bug on each iteration without needing to cluster, or is an appropriate cluster on failed test executions required for programs with multiple bugs.? If the latter, we will also study how exactly the clustering should be conducted."</i></p> <p>2) The proposed method may be inaccurate in recommending a potential defective code statement if a deviation on a test scenario is caused as collateral effect of another line (e.g. one line wrongly alters the content of a memory position but concludes the test without issues; another test case fails with correct code because it accesses the memory position that was undetectably corrupted in the previous test case.</p> <p>3) <i>"(...) bugs caused by missing code cannot be located (...), but the absence of such code might create some unexpected effects later in the program, such as the traversal of the wrong branch at a decision statement. Missing code may therefore trigger the assignment of high suspiciousness to unexpected statements, which could lead to the deduction that the code necessary for choosing the correct branch has been omitted."</i></p> <p>4) <i>"(...) our conclusion may not be generalized to arbitrary programs without more evaluations. To do so, additional case studies on programs from different application domains are to be used in our next step of study."</i></p> <p>5) <i>"Our future objectives also include how to combine the information of different program spectra to improve the performance of fault localization and how to apply [the method] to identify fault-prone modules"</i>.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good background on Neural Networks (chapter 2). 2) Interesting insight on the usage of AI to assist code verification (potentially useful for safety analysis) - excellent contribution regarding is 'Category 1' classification (i.e. AI to support safety analysis). <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Relevance is only marginal for key issues of safety verification of AI-based safety-critical systems, since the code verification strategy, as proposed by the authors, is valid for any software item regardless of them implementing AI.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 213 / 550	

8.115 REFERENCE [433]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To investigate how dynamic event/fault trees (DEFT) can be utilized for Agent-Oriented Software Engineering (AOSE) as a mechanism to analyze and reason about agent behavior and failures by (1) adapting DEFT for Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) to identify and analyze necessary safety responsibilities; (2) showing how the use of Galileo, the tool for DEFT probabilistic risk assessment, assists in developing a more robust MAS; and, (3) identifying necessary AOSE-specific enhancements for DEFT needed to better support the dependability analysis of MAS.
Q2 Answer	Intelligent (heuristic-based) Agents.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: "(...) <i>the very characteristics that are beneficial in MAS (i.e., autonomy, openness, adaptability, etc.) make dependability analysis difficult since MAS behavior may be hard to predict, analyze and understand.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Dependability assessment of MAS differs from traditional software systems in that the focus is on the unexpected or undesired behavior of an agent rather than on traditional failure modes. (...) an agent of a MAS is dependable if it preserves its intended behaviors in pursuit of its goals according to its specifications in the event of disturbances within the agent, the system or the agent's environment.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "(...) <i>this work illustrates the use of probabilistic risk assessment (PRA) using dynamic event/fault trees (DEFT) and its tool, Galileo [6], to estimate, analyze and reason about agent behaviors and failure scenarios. The contribution of this work is the application of a tool-supported dependability analysis technique using DEFT for critical MAS that:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Illustrates agent behavior and interactions as well as failures and their propagations;</i> 2) <i>Models correct, although unexpected, agent behavior that may lead to failures to assist in engineers understanding of agent behavior during unpredictable environment conditions;</i> 3) <i>Quantifies the risk presented by the agents' behaviors within an MAS;</i> 4) <i>Identifies critical agent activities (i.e., functional behaviors), permissions (i.e., read, generated or changed data) and protocols;</i> 5) <i>Discovers deficiencies in the DEFT approach using Galileo specific to MAS dependability engineering and suggests needed enhancements.</i>"
Q4 Answer	The authors present a case study applying PRA with DEFT (aided by the Galileo tool) as part of a multi-agent systems used in the Prospecting Asteroid Mission (PAM), carried out by NASA in order to study the asteroid belt between Mars and Jupiter. The system is deemed mission-critical and its main feature is to allow that reconfiguration and maintenance stemming from faults of one of the agents that are part of the prospecting swarm retains its robustness for accomplishing the mission.
Q5 Answer	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) DEFTs and the Galileo tool for modeling them do not allow bidirectional role changes between operational and backup modules (e.g., due to reconfiguration, the main module becomes a backup a vice-versa regardless of failures occurrence). 2) DEFT models and implementation within the Galileo tool were based on requirements specification; as a result, the authors claim that it might be prone to not covering all fault scenarios stemming from the interactions among agents.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting application on Multi-Agent Systems. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No explicit mention to the agents' intelligence levels. It has been deduced that some of them might be heuristic-based considering information presented by the authors. 2) Due to "1)", there is no explicit mention to AI nor to technicalities of its safety analysis - notably within implementation level. The DEFTs presented by the authors have not been developed at such a detailed level.

8.116 REFERENCE [443]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present a method of safety analysis for runtime code update, i.e., updating a program at runtime without terminating its execution.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 214 / 550	

Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: <i>"Runtime code update is an emerging technique especially for increasing availability of the servers which should always be in service and free of any known bugs or security flaws. However, it may cause state inconsistency or unintended behaviors unless it is properly restricted."</i></p> <p>Basics: <i>"We first model safe runtime code update with a variant of higher-order call-by-value language. The model precisely tracks the effect of update by making use of explicit flow and dependency information. Roughly speaking, to avoid state inconsistency, we restrict the timing of runtime code update: it may occur only at safe update points, where no dependence on modified code exists and no reaching affected values have subsequent critical uses. In addition, one may specify non-critical uses for more safe update points. Then we derive a class of safety analyses from that model by way of abstract interpretation of the semantics. The derived class of analyses estimates the set of safe update points statically. In our model, updates are not restricted to pre-defined patterns. Any modifications to abstract syntax tree of source code are allowed and recognized. It is even possible to safely update a part of the definition of an active function while it is active."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	The authors present their method but no case studies or practical examples are covered within the paper. The method itself is the main result.
Q5 Answer	<p><i>"To apply our method to a large number of realistic updates, a lot of further work is required. First, we have to develop update models and analyses for commonly used programming languages other than higher-order functional languages. We are developing an experimental difference analyzer called ASTDiff. Currently, it can convert source code written in Java, Python, or C to the abstract syntax tree and compare the trees by means of an applied tree matching algorithm."</i></p> <p><i>"Second, some mechanism for code replacement or state transfer must be implemented. Although our method is in principle applicable to both mechanisms, it complicates the implementation. At least, we have to precisely track heap objects without sacrificing efficiency which is itself a hard problem."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Not related to the safety analysis of AI.</p>

8.117 REFERENCE [445]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To outline (i.) the safety criteria which are safety requirements for the behavior of neural networks, (ii.) the characteristics of potential neural network models based upon representing knowledge in interpretable and understandable forms, and (iii.) a safety lifecycle for artificial neural networks which focuses on managing behavior represented by neural networks and contributes to providing acceptable forms of safety assurance.
Q2 Answer	Artificial neural networks in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: <i>"The ability to argue more about the functional behavior can be provided using product-based arguments. These are evidence-based and can show how they tackle safety issues such as identifying potential hazards. (...) Types of arguments suitable for ANNs are product-based and process-based but only where a clear defensible argument can be made about how they tackle specific safety concerns."</i> Process-based arguments for assuring that ANNs are safe are usually weak and prevent all analysis approaches but black-box behavior inference.</p> <p>Basics: Please refer to the paper's Figure 1 (page3/9) for more details. The goal of an ANN to be acceptably safe to perform safety-critical functions depends on three contexts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C1: The ANN model itself; - C2: The specific safety requirements to which it shall comply in its application (i.e., its safety analysis has to be application-specific); - C3: The targets it shall reach to be 'acceptably safe'. <p>The following sub-goals were defined for the safety criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - G2: Safe mapping of input-output functions (criteria for acceptance: "satisfying partially or totally the target function" and "known and unknown inputs"); - G3: Observable behavior of the ANN shall be predictable and repeatable; - G4: The ANN tolerates faults in its inputs (i.e., criteria of "fault classified as an input outside the specified

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 215 / 550	

input set") ;
- G5: The ANN does not create hazardous outputs (i.e., criteria of "not being outside a specified set or target function).

All the goals were associated to their respective faults and failure modes with regard to the associated criteria completeness. Please refer to section 6 of the paper for details on the failure modes.

The authors also propose a 'hybrid neural network', which represent "*symbolic information within a neural network structure.*" "*The 'hybrid' ANN has been shown to outperform many all symbolic techniques in terms of generalization and the rules that it embodies, (...) offers the potential for analysis using a decompositional approach (...) for transparency or white-box style analysis. This can be achieved through rule extraction algorithms which are relatively easy to implement than for conventional neural networks. (...) the learning process still needs to be controlled using appropriate mechanisms if it is to be used whilst the ANN is deployed.*"

For further details on the forthcoming information, please refer to Section 8 of the paper:
The safety lifecycle of the 'hybrid neural network' follows a W-shaped process vertically divided into three levels:

"Symbolic level: (top) This level is associated only with symbolic information. It is separated from the neural learning paradigm and deals with analysis in terms of symbolic knowledge.

Translation level: (middle) This is where symbolic knowledge and neural architectures are combined or separated.

Neural learning level: (bottom) This level uses neural learning to modify and refine symbolic knowledge. Neural learning is performed by using specific training samples along with suitable learning algorithms."

The sequential stages of the W-shaped process are as follows:

Determination of requirements (symbolic, going the first descending W line): These requirements describe in informal terms the problems to be solved.

Sub-initial knowledge (symbolic, going the first descending W line): All known knowledge is translated into logical rules (by domain experts).

Initial knowledge (symbolic, going the first descending and the first ascending W line): Sub-initial knowledge is converted into symbolic forms compatible for translation into network structure.

Dynamic learning (translation and neural, going the first descending W line): Once the initial symbolic knowledge has been inserted or translated into a suitable ANN, two-tier learning process commences. This uses suitable learning algorithms to refine the initial symbolic knowledge and add new rules. It uses training data sets and attempts to modify the network to reduce error in output. This may result in topological changes to the network (adding new hidden neurons to represent new rules).

Refined symbolic knowledge (translation and symbolic, middle lines of the W): Knowledge refined by dynamic learning is extracted using appropriate extraction algorithms. This will result in a new set of rules which can be analyzed from a symbolic level.

Static learning (translation and neural, going the second descending and ascending W lines): Refined symbolic knowledge may be modified by domain experts and re-inserted into the ANN structure. It then goes through a process of static learning. This further refines the knowledge in the ANN but does not allow topological or architectural changes. Instead, the learning process adapts the knowledge within pre-defined constraints and bounds.

Knowledge extraction (throughout all levels of both ascending W lines): This can be performed at any time during static learning to obtain the adapted rule set. This can either be used to understand changes in environment or for maintenance of the knowledge base.

Safety Activities:

"Preliminary hazard identification (PHI) deals with initial symbolic knowledge and is used to determine the initial conditions of the network. PHI is performed over a relatively meaningful representation (rules) and attempts to understand potential hazards in real-world terms."

"(...) Functional hazard analysis (FHA) [is performed] over the sub-initial symbolic knowledge. FHA performs a predictive, systematic, white-box style technique to understand how the symbolic knowledge can lead to hazards. FHA also builds an understanding of the criticality of certain rules and can facilitate 'targeted' training. For example, specific training sets may be devised to focus on certain important rules or areas of concern. FHA may also make rule assertions to prevent specific hazards. The result of FHA at this stage is the initial symbolic knowledge that is prepared for translation into a neural structure."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 216 / 550	

	<p><i>"Preliminary system safety assessment (PSSA) (...) uses an evaluative approach to analyze rules modified by dynamic learning (through rule extraction). It determines the existence of potential hazards and will do the following:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. Manually modify rule set: Through manual assertions to mitigate or control identified hazards.</i> <i>2. Initiate further training: Devise new training sets to reflect desired directions of learning. It can also be viewed as 'guiding' the design process to discover missing or unknown knowledge. This can be iterated until desired performance is achieved (determined through analytical techniques)."</i> <p><i>"FHA is performed again at post-dynamic learning stage. This uses an exploratory safety analysis technique to completely identify how rules may be allowably refined during static learning. (...) This involves analyzing the symbolic knowledge of the ANN and determines how potential faults may be introduced (if parts of rules are modified)."</i></p> <p>Safety Arguments:</p> <p><i>" Translation algorithms and data representation greatly contribute to white-box style analysis of the ANN. Analyzing the rules represented by the network can contribute to satisfying criterion G2 (provision of function). The two-tier learning model allows working towards desired function whilst enabling control over the learning process (criterion G3). (...)</i></p> <p><i>Faults within rules represented in the network may be identified using meaningful representations. Hazard analysis can exploit the decompositional analytical approach for tackling all specific faults that could give rise to hazards before certification</i></p> <p><i>Hazard analysis (FHA) can also provide assurance for dealing with novel inputs and all allowable adaptations during learning (that takes place post-certification). This is performed by analyzing knowledge in the ANN and incorporating required constraints. Hazard analysis can identify and mitigate faults associated with input space coverage of the knowledge base. Assurance is provided through PSSA which guides the learning (design) process. Hazard analysis can identify and prevent hazardous functional properties such as discontinuity of output. Hazard analysis can provide assurance that the behavior of the ANN is always within safe regions."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	The authors present their method but no case studies or practical examples are covered within the paper. The method itself is the main result.
Q5 Answer	" (...) the learning process [of hybrid neural networks] still needs to be controlled using appropriate mechanisms if it is to be used whilst the ANN is deployed."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good summary of arguments favoring ANNs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>"-The ability to learn: This is useful for problems whose intentionally complete algorithmic specification cannot be determined at the initial stages of development. They are also used when there is little understanding of the relationship between inputs and outputs. Therefore the neural network uses learning algorithms and training sets to learn new features associated with the desired function.</i> <i>- Dealing with novel inputs: Providing generalization to novel inputs using pre-learned samples for comparisons.</i> <i>- Operational performance: By exploiting the generalization ability, the neural network can outperform other methods particularly in areas of pattern recognition and function approximation.</i> <i>- Computational efficiency: Neural networks are often faster and more memory efficient than other methods."</i> 2) Diverse / redundant ANNs have not yet proven to be safe due to their black-box characteristic: <i>"One particular approach involves using diverse neural networks. This technique attempts to overcome the difficulty of using a single ANN to cover some target function. The approach creates an ensemble of ANNs where each member in the ensemble is developed differently but for the same problem. Each network is varied using a wide range of techniques such as different training sets or learning algorithms. Although very low levels of error were achieved they did not provide suitable safety arguments. One prime reason was that each ANN could only be analyzed as a black box."</i> 3) Paper well aligned to the research theme. Provides an interesting starting model for the safety assurance of Neural Networks and guidelines that can be expanded. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No further study on the 'hybrid neural network' actual model. 2) No further study on issues stemming from improper model training and validation.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 217 / 550	

8.118 REFERENCE [447]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To define a type of constrained 'hybrid artificial neural network (ANN)', called the Fuzzy Self-Organizing Map (FSOM), which allows behavior to be described qualitatively and quantitatively using meaningful expressions. The approach enables the construction of compelling (product-based) arguments for mitigation of potential failure modes associated with the FSOM. The constrained FSOM has been termed a 'safety critical artificial neural network' (SCANN). The SCANN can be used for non-linear function approximation and allows certified learning and generalization for high criticality roles.
Q2 Answer	Artificial neural networks specifically following the 'Fuzzy Self- Organizing Map' (FSOM) architecture, also called 'Safety-Critical Artificial Neural Network' (SCANN).
Q3 Answer	<p>Issues with ANNs for safety-critical applications:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Inability to understand and control the ANN behavior, since they are viewed as black-boxes; 2) Exhaustive testing to analyze the black-box behavior of ANNs with bounded outputs restrain two aspects: (i.) how to derive the output bounds and (ii.) inability of improving the ANN with on-line learning during operation after certification <p>Basics: The SCANN model includes the following characteristics that are suitable for critical applications, defined in [444]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to use human understandable rules to describe behavior: <i>Qualitative representations of knowledge are used to express the behavior of the SCANN (such as "IF antecedent X is <pre-condition> THEN consequent Y is <post-condition>. This helps comprehend and analyze SCANN behavior without solely relying on quantitative representations.</i> - Ability to represent behavior within the SCANN using highly structured methods: <i>This is achieved by exploiting decompositional approaches [3] to insert and extract SCANN behavior. This involves clear mappings from every neuron (processing elements or building blocks), interconnection (links between neurons) and parameter to an element within the knowledge base.</i> - Ability to perform rule insertion and rule extraction using computationally efficient processes: <i>Unlike typical neural networks and some 'hybrid' ANNs (combining symbolic expert systems and neural learning), rules can be efficiently inserted and extracted without compromising the 'fidelity' of the knowledge base.</i> - Ability to analyze and control the behavior of the SCANN: <i>As a result of comprehensibility and fidelity offered by the extracted rules from the SCANN, there is potential to control behavior in order to address safety concerns."</i> <p>The SCANN has seven layers:</p> <p>Layer 1 - Input Layer: It "(...) propagates inputs (from the environment using sensors) to layer 2. No pre-processing occurs here and the number of neurons equals the number of input variables."</p> <p>Layer 2 - Membership to Fuzzy Sets: It computes the fuzzy set membership for inputs using a triangular function with a neuron for every fuzzy set. "The purpose of the membership function is to determine the degree to which a particular input value belongs to a fuzzy set", ranging between zero and one. The fuzzy set centers and spreads (i.e. limits of the triangle) can change during learning.</p> <p>Layer 3 - Inference Engine: It computes the firing strength for each rule in the SCANN by means of a function which collects the minimum belonging of a variable to a fuzzy set for the desired rule . The firing strength is used to represent the influence of the rule output, which is useful for cases when there are multiple firing rules for an input vector (see Layer 7 for more details). All neurons in layer 2 for corresponding rules are connected to the minimum operator in layer 3, and no Layer 3 elements can be adapted using learning algorithms.</p> <p>Layer 4 - Normalization: This layer normalizes firing strengths for each firing rule to produce a normalized firing rate output response. None of the Layer 4 parameters can be tuned through learning, and all Layer 3 neurons are connected to all Layer 4 neurons.</p> <p>Layer 5 - Individual Rule Outputs: It computes the rule outputs using input values. Each rule will only produce an output if all rule inputs are members of the corresponding input fuzzy sets. The output is a linear function for each rule, and the number of rule output neurons equals the number of rules. This layer has one neuron for each rule, and each neuron is connected to the corresponding normalization neuron on Layer 4 plus to all outputs. The layer also features tunable parameters that can be updated through learning in order</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 218 / 550	

to define the rule output function.

Layer 6 - Output Saturation: Each neuron of this layer is connected to the corresponding rule neuron of Layer 5 only. The objective of this layer is to bound the outputs of Layer 5 to limits of each rule function.

Layer 7 - Rule Aggregation: It consists of two neurons whose purpose is to determine a single output value from several firing rules. One neuron uses weighted averaging, and multiple firing, which can occur when rule preconditions overlap (i.e., fuzzy sets of two or more rules overlap), can be resolved by such a weighted average using rule outputs (Layer 6) and firing strengths (layers 3 or 4). The other neuron is a bounded liner function.

The following failure modes have been defined for the SCANN:

- Failure modes 1 & 2 - The output is too high or too low given inputs: "*This may be caused by flawed training samples resulting in the SCANN diverging from the desired function. Remedial actions for this failure mode include incorporating semantic bounds for each rule. These bounds are used to control the input set parameters and*

output functions parameters during learning (rule pre and post-conditions)." The fuzzy sets center and spreads are constrained to known limits, and "*attempts to violate these bounds may be due to unrepresentative or flawed training samples*".

- Failure modes 3 & 4 - Omission or commission of output given inputs: "*These failure modes can be described as undesirable output omission or commission for some input vector. Conditions of omission and commission of the SCANN output can lead to hazardous 'inaction' or 'action'*". To address them, it is recommended to use either a default rule, which encapsulates the whole input space and constrains it to a constant output function, or a Gaussian membership function instead of the triangular Fuzzy sets - which would also take the whole input set.

- Failure modes 5 & 6 - Function derivative sign is positive or negative: They are caused by inappropriate function derivative signs. The authors propose to have rules which force the derivative signs of outputs according to the signs of the derivative inputs. "*Constraints to mitigate failure modes 5 and 6 require that semantic and coverage constraints are defined and used (failure modes 1–4). These constraints ensure the continuity of the approximated function (...)*". Issues may appear when multiple rules define an output due to the safety properties being ensured within each rule but not on the interface between two rules. "*This is because the activations are not constant (which act as weights upon the outputs) and may not allow a strictly increasing or decreasing output change.*" "*To adhere to requirements for multiple firing rules, a linear function (...) is used in place of the weighted averaging. Although the linearity of this approach may impact approximation ability, adherence to the safety requirement can be easily guaranteed. As a trade-off, set centers now have little meaning during 'defuzzification' but are useful during static learning laws*".

- Failure modes 7 & 8 - Absolute function derivative is too high or too low: They are related to the absolute value of the SCANN function derivative, describing when the difference between outputs is too large or too small for a change in inputs. They can be hazardous when sudden or slow output changes can be hazardous. A limit for the derivative is defined *a priori* for certain regions of the input space. "*These derivative constraints can be defined globally (...) or locally (i.e. specific to particular rules).*" Output saturation may be turned off or changed to avoid non-detection of increasing or decreasing derivatives.

The authors claim that "*Sufficiency' of the failure modes is difficult to prove for all applications. However, the main argument for 'sufficiency' of the failure modes is that they have been derived by applying the well-established HAZOP process to the SCANN functional properties.*" and that "*Causes for all failure modes are related to faulty knowledge base or rule parameters. (...) Mitigation and control of potential hazards will be performed through constraints and bounds imposed upon the SCANN generalization and learning capabilities.*"

Learning (Layers 2 and 5): "*The static learning algorithm has the ability to perform online parameter adaptations (after each training sample) in a supervised or unsupervised fashion. However, adapting parameters presents the risk of violating the defined safety requirements expressed as safety constraints. To allow learning capabilities of the SCANN without the need for re-certification, the approach taken [by the authors] is to constrain the learning algorithms (to bound potential parameter states) such that none of the identified failure modes occur.*" Two approaches for learning are discussed:

Static Learning: "*The static learning algorithm tunes parameters using training samples or input data to improve generalization performance. This algorithm does not insert new rules but refines and adapts existing ones. Consequently, this algorithm is termed 'static' to reflect how the knowledge base is changed. It is performed in two phases:*

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 219 / 550	

	<p><i>Phase 1: Antecedent parameters are frozen and the consequent parameters are refined using the gradient descent algorithm (supervised mode).</i></p> <p><i>Phase 2: Consequent parameters are frozen and the antecedent parameters are tuned using the modified LVQ algorithm (supervised or unsupervised mode). "Phase 2 of learning is triggered when there are multiple firing rules for a given input vector."</i></p> <p><i>"The two phases of the static learning algorithm have been constrained to enable changes in the approximated function without leading to faulty parameter states. (...) Post-conditions 'verify' whether the adaptation will lead to a failure mode i.e. they check for conformity to the safety constraints. If the desired adaptation (determined by the learning laws) conforms to the safety constraints, then the adaptation is accepted, otherwise, the adaptation is rejected." Slow learning rated might be the best approach for this to work properly.</i></p> <p><i>Dynamic Learning: "The self-generation of fuzzy rules is an attractive property as it automatically acquires novel features described by training data. Adding more rules contribute to the function approximation ability. (...) [It] uses three heuristic rules to create new fuzzy rules which are:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. Errors are removed in descending order. This 'guarantees' that fuzzy rules are added so that the largest error (between FSOM and training sample outputs) is removed first. This error is determined during each training cycle or epoch.</i> <i>2. New fuzzy rule is only added once existing fuzzy rules have been tuned. If the FSOM has difficulty reducing error (using static learning), a new rule is added at the input sample point with default spread.</i> <i>3. Interference caused by new rule upon existing rules is minimized: To prevent 'forgetting' of previously learnt knowledge the width of new rule spread is limited.</i> <p><i>This process is used during the development lifecycle for ANNs prior to certification."</i></p> <p><i>" The approach of the constrained dynamic learning algorithm is to constrain new rules in order to guarantee that existing safety constraints are not violated (through the introduction of faults). Constrained dynamic learning can be best used for applications where only failure modes 1 to 4 are of concern."</i></p> <p><i>"(...) to allow the constrained dynamic learning algorithm to be used post-certification, Step 5d performs a final check (of the knowledge base with the added rule) for systematic faults. If faults are revealed then the new rule is rejected. This step is useful for enabling dynamic learning post-certification for failure modes 5–8. Since the dynamic learning algorithm will typically not add new rules (because of safety constraint violations)."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors just mention the successful application of the SCANN is a Gas Turbine Aero-Engine, which is detailed in [455].The method itself is the main result of the research.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) The SCANN failure modes analysis excluded attributes such as 'response time' / 'repetition time'. The authors claim that "<i>these issues are not viewed as a major problem since conventional techniques can be used to tackle these issues.</i>"</p> <p>2) Constrained dynamic learning may be used, as presented by the authors, only if failure modes 1-4 are of concern. Limitations regarding failure modes 5-8 have not been explored by the authors, except for the fact that they would be covered by a 'systematic failures' analysis carried out for dynamic learning with post-certification purposes, in such a way that this analysis would prevent failure modes 5-8 from occurring with the newly added rules. The so-called 'systematic analysis' is not well detailed by the authors.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Fills the gap of the 'hybrid neural network' model presented in [444] with a good detailing of the SCANNs. 2) Paper well aligned to the research theme. Provides a deep and interesting model for the safety assurance of Neural Networks based on the guidelines presented in [444]. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The failure modes of the SCANN presented within the paper are in a high abstraction level and its sufficiency to applications is arguable even by the authors themselves ("<i>Sufficiency' of the failure modes is difficult to prove for all applications. However, the main argument for 'sufficiency' of the failure modes is</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 220 / 550	

	<p>that they have been derived by applying the well-established HAZOP process to the SCANN functional properties.").</p> <p>2) Even though the authors argue that most of the raised failure modes can be related to the models knowledge base, no direct relationship to them nor explanations on how to circumvent these issues have been presented. The authors claim that "<i>Mitigation and control of potential hazards will be performed through constraints and bounds imposed upon the SCANN generalization and learning capabilities</i>".</p> <p>3) Constrained dynamic learning may be used, as presented by the authors, only if failure modes 1-4 are of concern. Limitations regarding failure modes 5-8 have not been explored by the authors, except for the fact that they would be covered by a 'systematic failures' analysis carried out for dynamic learning with post-certification purposes, in such a way that this analysis would prevent failure modes 5-8 from occurring with the newly added rules. The so-called 'systematic analysis' is not well detailed by the authors.</p>
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8.119 REFERENCE [453]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a run-time risk assessment methodology for validating self-adaptive software systems based on online operational monitoring and data fusion techniques.
Q2 Answer	Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Background: "<i>A provably self-stabilizing neural network ensures that while the adaptive system tries to achieve its central goal, the embedded neural network may not deviate the system in an unpredictable manner towards instability due to a dramatic change in its learning state (possibly due to a system-failure). It is not known at this point whether a neural network of such capabilities exists, let alone the complicated and challenging task of proving that it is self-stabilizing in some manner for all conditions of input data.</i>"</p> <p>Objective: To respond the following questions: <i>"1. Is the online neural network learning algorithm self-stabilizing in some manner for certain data representations? 2. Is there a means to detect if the neural network is not stabilizing but deviating towards instability (abnormal behavior)?"</i></p> <p>Basics: "<i>The construction of an online stability monitor is based on rigorous mathematical stability analysis methodology - Lyapunov's direct method. The output data from various monitors are fused together using Murphy's rule based on Dempster-Shafer framework and Fuzzy Inference Engine to form a single measure of confidence. The confidence measure indicates whether or not the output from the neural network's learning can be trusted over time.</i>" Since problems usually involve several input variables, "<i>(...) multiple Lyapunov-like functions are needed to observe various aspects of the neural network to adequately monitor its the behavior during online adaptation. This is the role that run-time monitors play in the validation methodology discussed here.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The presented validation technique is applied to a neural network-based online self-adaptive system, the intelligent flight control system (IPCS). "<i>The experimental data consists of data sets collected from an F-15 flight simulator. The tested flight-modes consisted of seven failure modes (five control failure modes and two surface failure modes) and two no-failure, or nominal, modes.</i>"</p> <p>The case study allowed identifying that the neural network-based controller employed in the case study failed to perform safely by applying the fuzzy logic-based monitor for sensor fusion, but that the monitor was able to detect this scenario.</p>
Q5 Answer	" <i>It is believed that the application boundaries for adaptive and intelligent systems will widen as the underlying software/system verification and validation theory becomes better understood and derived techniques achieve a higher level of maturity</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Simple yet interesting approach to deal with the safe operation of neural networks.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) No evidence that the sensor fusion infrastructure can reach proper safety targets for a safety-critical system.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 221 / 550	

8.120 REFERENCE [454]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To provide a suggested research path for risk assessment for neural network systems and an example failure modes and effects analysis (FMEA) for practitioner use.
Q2 Answer	Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Hazards Related to Neural Networks that learn during operation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>The neural network does not adapt.</i> 2. <i>The neural network adapts, but is unable to reach convergence.</i> 3. <i>The neural network adapts and converges, but converges to an incorrect output.</i> 4. <i>The neural network converges to a correct state, but cannot do so in the required time.</i> 5. <i>The neural network grows beyond available system resources during adaptation.</i> <p>Technical Risks of Neural Networks: <i>"From the technical risk standpoint, the analysis needs to concentrate on the justification for the use of a neural network solution. Questions that investigate technical risk may ask if a neural network system is an appropriate solution given the problem being solved, if the neural networks should be online adaptive or not, and what types of built in safety the system will need."</i></p> <p>Main technical hazards and risks related to neural networks:</p> <p>I Requirements Specification</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Risks introduced by the specification and collection of training and testing data; 2) Risks introduced by specification of neural network performance (too little or too much performance). <p>II Detailed Design</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hazard: verifying that logic design and associated data elements correctly implement the critical requirements and introduce no new hazards, comprising the design of the neural network architecture, size, intended use and collection of training-testing data. Hazards to be checked include: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Training data set does not model intended goals; b) The collection of training and test data sets is not tracked under configuration management and is not described in design documentation; c) Lack of adequate testing data to achieve component-level project-specific certification standards; d) Neural network architecture is not completely specified; e) The implementation of the network prior to training is incorrect (initial number of neurons, connection matrices, growing/learning functions, or activation functions contain errors); f) Inappropriate growing/learning algorithm is selected, causing sub-optimal knowledge acquisition. 2) Risk: The following topics are included: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Insufficient training and testing data. Both training and testing data must represent the entire data domain, rather than just a few constrained examples. b) Selecting an appropriate neural network algorithm impacts the feasibility of system design and implementation. <p>III Implementation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hazard: hazard analysis should focus on those hazards affected or introduced through the learning of the training data by the neural network, especially on the knowledge and how well the knowledge was acquired. Hazards to be checked include: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Through learning and/or growing, the neural network structure exceeds the computational limitations of the system; b) Neural network takes too long to adapt to new stimuli; c) The neural network never reaches a point of stability. The neural network performance oscillates around the designated success criteria metric but never achieves the intended metric; d) Neural network is over-generalized and cannot provide a suitable solution to the specific problem; e) Neural network is too specialized and cannot provide a general solution for the problem domain; f) Observable behavior of the neural network is not predictable or repeatable. 2) Risk: Technical risks include a lack of sufficient training or testing data. Another possible technical risk occurs when the neural network designers have trained a neural network to meet performance criteria, but

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 222 / 550	

they fail to adequately test the neural network across the entire operational profile.

IV Testing and V&V: During the testing stage, the risks and hazards usually relate to accepting a neural network system inappropriately. This could occur through the use of testing techniques or simulations that fail to adequately exercise the neural network. Other examples include:

- a) Failure to examine the training data for completeness and correctness.
- b) Failure to review input selection (ensuring the input choices are correct, based upon an acceptable technique like principal component analysis, etc.).
- c) Failure to review input preprocessing and output post-processing for correctness.
- d) The test procedures described in the test plans do not properly assess neural network performance criteria such as stability and convergence.
- e) For software-in-the-loop simulations (SILS), the test cases do not accurately reflect how the adaptive component performs within the entire system.
- g) For hardware-in-the-loop simulations (HILS), near-identical versions of the hardware do not accurately reflect performance of the true hardware.

Fault injection can be used to assess the performance of risk mitigation techniques.

V Installation and Checkout: *"If the neural network system requires some environment in which to operate, a potential hazard is the lack of delivery of this environment with the installation package. Another possible area of omission is the failure to deliver check cases that will exercise the system after installation to make sure that the installation did not introduce any kind of error. If the system makes use of real-time operational monitors, the monitors need to be a part of the complete package as well.*

Incompatibility can be introduced when the target environment is not similar to the development environment. The interface between modules providing input or accepting output from the neural network may be different. Computer hardware attributes like processor size and speed may be different, introducing performance issues."

VI Operation: *"(...) with an adaptive system, new hazards can be introduced based upon what data comes into the system and thus how the system learns. Example of hazards include:*

- a) Operating procedures are inconsistent with the user documentation or with system requirements.
- b) Operating conditions differ from those intended by system developers.
- c) Input data is received from a source that was not originally intended.
- d) Computational resource limits are approached or exceeded (as may happen with growing neural networks that add more neurons and connections over time).
- e) Operational monitors function inappropriately as either too restrictive or not restrictive enough."

VII Maintenance: To be checked that *"(...) software modifications correctly implement the critical requirements and introduce no new hazards"*.

Failure Modes for Neural Networks:

Weights W_{ij}

- a) $W_{ij} = 0$ causes loss of any partial information that the weight held
- b) $W_{ij}^{-1} - W_{ij} \rightarrow$ weight is multiplied by -1 ; represents a unit always trying to misclassify an input;
- c) A saturation limit can be applied on any faulty weight by restricting weights to the range $[-W, +W]$. This suggests the faults:
 - c1) negative $W_{ij} \rightarrow +W$
 - c2) positive $W_{ij} \rightarrow -W$

Threshold Function

- a) Stuck-at-minus-one
- b) Stuck-at-plus-one

Derivative of Threshold Function

- a) Stuck-at-plus-one
- b) Stuck-at-zero

Learning Rate

- a) $l_r = 0$; typical range $(0, 1]$

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 223 / 550	

	<p>b) I_r == its highest possible value</p> <p>Target Values</p> <p>a) t_i = value opposite to the fault-free value (the targets generally take only the two values at the extreme ends of the threshold function range)</p> <p>Topology</p> <p>a) Loss of a connection between 2 units</p> <p>b) Random reconnection of a link to another unit in the network (possibly due to a short-circuit)</p> <p>Activation Values and Delta</p> <p>a) Limit to opposite value OR</p> <p>b) Constrain Delta-i and a-i to a limited range or randomize them</p> <p>Weight Change $A_{w j}$</p> <p>a) Only needs to be considered if they are stored temporarily, then they would have similar failure modes as those for activation values and deltas.</p>
Q4 Answer	The proposed method is exercised for the IPCS (intelligent flight control system) GEN2 MLP neural network.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The hazard and risk analysis method presented by the authors is well structured in a didactic way and can be potentially expanded for other AI-based methods.</p>

8.121 REFERENCE [455]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a technique for safety analysis of self-adaptive systems with formal methods by proposing a dependability analysis based on the results of safety analysis to measure the quality of self-capabilities of an adaptive system with formal methods.
Q2 Answer	No specific AI technique is mentioned throughout the paper; nevertheless, the authors imply that AI may be used to allow self-adaptation of systems by using the expression that systems are conceived with the 'let the system go' paradigm, i.e., the systems have some degree of freedom to make their own choices. Linear Time Temporal Logic is used within the specified formal model.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors present a Linear Time Temporal Logic means to formally assess the dependability of adaptive systems. The approach is based on a formal specification of system allowed configurations, their transitions and fault detection capabilities. A central controller is employed to manage the detection of faulty elements and the reconfiguration of the adaptive system components in such a way to separate "(...) <i>modeling of the production cell from a reconfiguration algorithm.</i>"</p> <p>Moreover, dependability-critical characteristics are modeled with Computational Tree Logic (CTL) in order to formalize the Deductive Cause Consequence Analysis (DCCA) used to find the cause-consequence relationship between faults and hazards. In the context of the research, "<i>the hazard is only "critical" if the system cannot repair itself anymore.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A case study from the production automation domain is presented. The case study consists on the safety analysis of a robotic production cell with autonomous transportation units and three robots that can accomplish three functions each, depending on the tool configured in the robot arm: (i.) drilling a hole in a workpiece, (ii.) inserting a screw into this hole, and (iii.) tightening the screw. Every workpiece must be processed by all three tools in the given order (drill, insert and tighten).</p> <p>The case study aims to evaluate the scenario when one or more tools break, and the current robot setting does not allow the correct processing order anymore, being necessary to change the tools of robots to allow the accomplishment of the task. "<i>We considered every broken and thus unusable tool as failure. We also analyzed a second version with an additional failure, a possibly failing reconfiguration algorithm, i.e. wrong reconfiguration messages are sent due to network problems.</i>" By using the 'Cadence SMV' model checker, the summary of the case study outcomes is that "<i>the results from the safety analysis show that a clear increase in dependability according to all metrics.</i>"</p>
Q5	" <i>The next step is to formulate DCCA for different modeling tools not based on CTL temporal logic. An</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 224 / 550	

Answer	<i>example is the LUSTRE language which is integrated in the SCADE modeling tool. Together with a modeling technique for adaptive systems, this would integrate safety analysis for adaptive systems in a well-accepted tool. This may augment the acceptance of adaptive systems in safety critical applications."</i>
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Research not directly related to the technicalities of AI safety analysis.

8.122 REFERENCE [456]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To examine the practicalities of using the SCANN and SLANN for Gas Turbine Aero-Engine control. A walkthrough of the SLANN is presented demonstrating the interrelationship of development and safety processes enabling product-based safety arguments. Results illustrating the benefits and safety of the SCANN in a Gas Turbine Engine Model are provided using the SCANN simulation tool.
Q2 Answer	Artificial neural networks specifically following the 'Fuzzy Self- Organizing Map' (FSOM) architecture, also called 'Safety-Critical Artificial Neural Network' (SCANN).
Q3 Answer	<p>The study focuses on the application of the SCANN, defined in [446], to the Rolls Royce Spey Gas Turbine Aero-Engine (GTE). The case study aims to evaluate especially the "<i>tradeoffs between safety and performance are examined to assess the degree of SCANN performance impact (or advantage) in the presence of safety constraints</i>".</p> <p><i>"The motivation for using the GTE is the potential for improved performance for situations such as engine degradation. There is also the prospect to improve hazard detection through health monitoring - ultimately leading to enhanced efficiency"</i>.</p> <p>Interesting result: "<i>Previous work on psychology and fuzzy systems design find that the optimal number of fuzzy sets for each dimension is 7 ± 2</i>."</p> <p><u>Constrained Static Learning Algorithm Outline (for online learning while the system operates)</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Let $p(t)$ be the SCANN parameter state 2. Feed in training sample pair (desired input and output) 3. Perform center, spread or output tuning using learning laws on $tp(t)$ – temporary copy of the SCANN parameter state which when tuned does not affect actual SCANN behavior 4. Identify presence of any safety constraint violations (faults) 5. If no violation then use $tp(t)$ for the new tuned SCANN state, otherwise, reject $tp(t)$ and preserve training sample (reuse when learning rate is more decayed) <p><i>"The dynamic learning algorithm needs to provide assurance that any new rule being added does not violate the current state of the SCANN. There are two approaches for adding new rules. The first is that any new rule which violates any of the safety constraints is not added. The second is that the algorithm analyses safety constraints of existing rules and inherits them for the new rule"</i>.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Introduction: "<i>Gas Turbine Engines (GTE) are internal combustion heat engines which convert heat energy into mechanical energy. There are three main elements within the GTE namely; compressor, combustion chamber and a turbine placed on a common shaft.</i>"</p> <p>The case study depends on "<i>a 'Spey' GTE nonlinear thermodynamic model (Matlab & Simulink) [which] was acquired from our sponsors QinetiQ.</i>"</p> <p>Scope: The objective of the case study is to replace the Inlet Guide Vane (IGV) with a SCANN-based solution. The IGV is responsible for matching the air from the fan to the high pressure compressor characteristics prior to it reaching the combustion chamber - hence controlling airflow and maintaining efficient fan operation. The IGV shall feature "<i>a variable geometry (...) which changes the angle of attack of the blades to prevent compressor stall</i>". "<i>The problem is to use the SCANN for more appropriate scheduling. This will replace the existing IGV scheduler whilst ensuring that identified hazards are mitigated and prevented</i>".</p> <p>Identified Hazards:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Engine surge, resulting in loss of thrust or engine destruction; 2) Excessive turbine blade temperature, leading to erosion of the blades; 3) Engine overspeed, leading to engine surge and other destructive problems.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 225 / 550	

	<p>"Safety constraints are exploited by the SCANN and the approach is more powerful and practical than safety 'monitors'. For example, conventional safety monitors make little provision for adaptive functions. Instead, the constraints are tightly integrated with the approximated function allowing learning post-certification."</p> <p>"The training data consisted of 91 uniform samples which represent the standard non-optimal IGV scheduler described in section 3.1. The output functions were initially hand-tuned and learning was performed for 50 epochs using learning parameters which allow convergence. A performance-based stopping condition was defined and satisfied using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). After performing dynamic learning, remaining faults were identified using SSA (step 6a). No systematic faults remained for the defined safety requirements i.e. the dynamic learning phase safety-based stopping condition is satisfied."</p> <p>Final Remarks: "The only major challenge within the SLANN is the activity of determining appropriate safety requirements. However, this task is no different than for conventional software safety or controller development." "The SCANN has established its ability to safely learn (post-certification) and thus improve GTE performance whilst maintaining safety requirements. Training data of arbitrary integrity is permitted (for post-certification learning) – allowing for more practical use of the SCANN in a real-world noisy environments. The advantages of generalization and learning also include contributing to identifying plant degradation. Maintenance and servicing can also benefit (in terms of cost efficiency) through the use of logs generated during learning."</p>
Q5 Answer	The authors do not address this question on their paper.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good presentation of SLANN/SCANN in a safety-critical application. The safety lifecycle (SLANN) has been detailed throughout all its steps and the main technical decisions regarding SCANN have been presented and justified.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Part of the technical decisions regarding the SCANN training and validation, including metrics, have been omitted due to lack of space and/or NDA with the supplier.</p> <p>2) No discussion on occasional restrictions and/or unacceptable results obtained throughout the research.</p>

8.123 REFERENCE [465]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	Preliminary version of [447]. Essentially with the same information in a simplified way aimed towards conference presentation (SAFECOMP 2004).
Q2 Answer	Preliminary version of [447]. Essentially with the same information in a simplified way aimed towards conference presentation (SAFECOMP 2004).
Q3 Answer	Preliminary version of [447]. Essentially with the same information in a simplified way aimed towards conference presentation (SAFECOMP 2004).
Q4 Answer	Preliminary version of [447]. Essentially with the same information in a simplified way aimed towards conference presentation (SAFECOMP 2004).
Q5 Answer	Preliminary version of [447]. Essentially with the same information in a simplified way aimed towards conference presentation (SAFECOMP 2004).
Q6 Answer	Preliminary version of [447]. Essentially with the same information in a simplified way aimed towards conference presentation (SAFECOMP 2004).

8.124 REFERENCE [495]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present an approach which shows promise in enabling software to be assessed directly for safety based on AI techniques, namely Decision Trees and Behavior-Based Architectures. The aim of this paper is to

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 226 / 550

	describe the features of these technologies.
Q2 Answer	Decision trees and behavior-based architectures.
Q3 Answer	The authors postulate that decision trees may aid FTAs of software-based systems: one will be able to detect systematic software failures by identifying inadequate decision subtrees and, in case the software decision tree is conceived with a behavior-based architecture, one will also be able to identify and quantify the probability / rate of occurrence of random faults and tell them from design flaws related, for example, to misinterpretation of the environment.
Q4 Answer	The authors claim that two projects were studying the usage of AI techniques within the safety analysis of software-based systems: 1) ISSAFE for the application of decision tree-based software techniques within a helicopter flight control system; 2) MPhil/DSc. project to develop a behavior-based control system with decision trees and Programmable Logic Arrays and to test it using a small-scale prototype.
Q5 Answer	By the time the research was published, the authors highlight that there is much to do to aid the usage of software in safety-critical systems.
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) Outdated research and with little relation to the safety analysis of AI-based systems, since the authors' objective is to use techniques abstracted from AI to perform the safety analysis of software-based systems.

8.125 REFERENCE [496]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present issues concerning the design of knowledge base-based systems whose advice may have implications for safety.
Q2 Answer	Systems with knowledge base.
Q3 Answer	Background: Since knowledge is always incomplete, often uncertain, or the limits on its applicability may be poorly understood, a system which uses this knowledge may provide advice which is suboptimal or even unsafe even in the absence of demonstrable errors or inconsistencies. The main issue raised by the authors is related to the commitment of both a belief (i.e., updating the system's belief on the environment based on its reasoning) or a plan (i.e., a set of actions that shall be scheduled so that the system acts over the environment), since it is deemed that, if such a commitment fails, the result can lead to potentially unsafe scenarios.
Q4 Answer	The research is presented considering a Symbolic Decision Theory-based system developed by the authors, called the RED (Rigorously Engineered Decision) project, which aims to provide safety-critical decisions regardless of the application. The main purposes of the authors is to apply the RED project to two applications: (i.) providing support in cancer management and (ii.) allowing quality assessment of safety-critical software. By the time of the published paper, the authors had implemented two prototypes: one for the diagnosis and the management of acute depression and the other, for the quality assessment of safety-critical software. No practical results regarding the prototypes were presented.
Q5 Answer	The authors mention that the project was still ongoing by the time of the publication and presented an action plan for the implementation of the cancer management application, including the challenges for augmenting the Symbolic Decision Tree theory for their purposes.
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Possibly among the very first reference of AI-based solution to support the safety analysis of systems. Weaknesses: 1) Outdated research with little interesting results.

8.126 REFERENCE [522]

Q-Index	4
Q1	To propose a Deep Neural Network model with Genetic Algorithm to allow the Deep Neural Network to be

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 227 / 550

Answer	safety assessed.
Q2 Answer	Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p><i>"For forward-oriented neural networks, three deep learning system full-life analysis and inspection steps including data sensitivity analysis test, neural network quality analysis test, and neural network deployment test are used."</i></p> <p><i>"In the process of processing each neural network to calculate the coverage, the use of coverage to generate more test cases, and then the resulting test cases into the neural network to obtain the error rate, with the error rate as a quality parameter, evaluation as a result of robustness.</i></p> <p><i>The original test data is mutated by genetic algorithm, and in each round of evolution of the genetic algorithm, the test data after the variation is filtered by the quality function for the next evolution, and the test data after the inconsistency rate in the deployment environment and the development environment is greater than the preset consistent threshold, and the test data is fed into the neural network with the error rate of the output results as the compatibility result. Inconsistency rate refers to the proportion of the smaller inconsistencies in the output obtained by the original neural network of the mutated test data."</i></p> <p><i>" For forward-oriented neural networks, three different levels of variation are proposed:</i></p> <p><i>A) Changes in neural network weight levels, such as adding Gaussian noise to the weight of existing neural networks;</i></p> <p><i>B) Changes in neuronal levels, including random removal of the role of part of the neuron, the result of flipping the neuron, or the replacement of the output of two neurons;</i></p> <p><i>C) Layer level changes, including deleting a layer, adding a new layer, or copying a layer.</i></p> <p><i>Through the above variation, a neural network is generated by multiple changes in the neural network, and the decision boundary of these changed neural networks is very similar to that of the original neural network."</i></p> <p><i>"The invention proposes a method based on variation testing to generate a certain number of mutated neural networks for a well-trained neural network, and to calculate the variation of data based on the variation neural network in order to estimate the quality of the test data. When the neural network is well trained, the neural network is evaluated and the coverage-oriented automated test method is used to test the robustness of the neural network. When a neural network is deployed, a differential test is used to detect compatibility issues in the deployment environment of the neural network."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p><i>"The invention integrates the analysis and detection of multiple steps in the process of deep learning development into one platform, which can be analyzed and tested more efficiently and systematically. After each step, it can be analyzed and tested quickly to detect defects in the deep learning system earlier. The resulting test cases can help developers understand and discover problems in neural networks more efficiently, such as data imbalances, inappropriate model structures, or training hypersampling. For a well-trained model, you can also quickly discover compatibility issues during the deployment phase to reduce the serious consequences of a real deployment, such as unmanned driving."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach to increase the predictability of deep learning models by generating several different models and comparing and contrasting them.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No deep discussion or formal results on safety improvements by this approach have been presented by the patent authors.</p>

8.127 REFERENCE [526]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a full-stack circular neural network deep learning system safety analysis and detection method. For the circulating neural network, the neural network, which is transformed and mutated to generate the change, will enter the test data into the neural network to obtain the output result, and then obtain the variation rate as a sensitivity parameter, calculate the coverage in the processing of each neural network, generate more test cases and enter the error rate into the neural network as the quality parameter, and use the genetic algorithm to mutate the test data and obtain the test data after the inconsistency rate is greater than the preset consistent threshold.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 228 / 550	

Q2 Answer	Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p><i>"The invention relates to a safety analysis and evaluation method of artificial intelligence neural network, which is a whole stack-type circular neural network deep learning system security analysis and detection method."</i></p> <p><i>"For the circulating neural network, the three deep learning system full life cycle analysis and testing steps including data sensitivity analysis test, neural network quality analysis test and neural network deployment test are adopted."</i></p> <p><i>For the circular neural network transformation, variation processing to generate a number of high-quality changes of the neural network, the test data input to each changed neural network to obtain the output results, according to all output results processing to obtain the variation rate, through the test data in multiple changes in the neural network to obtain the variation rate as the sensitivity parameters of the test data.</i></p> <p>(...)</p> <p><i>The genetic algorithm is used to mutate the original test data, in each round of the evolution of the genetic algorithm, through the yield function to filter the test data after the variation to carry out the next round of evolution, and finally obtain the test data after the inconsistency rate in the deployment environment and the development environment is greater than the preset consistent threshold of the variation, to test the data input into the neural network to output the error rate as a compatibility result. Inconsistency rate refers to the proportion of the smaller inconsistencies in the output obtained by the original neural network of the mutated test data."</i></p> <p><i>"Given a neural network, first through small changes to the target neural network to mutate to generate multiple neural networks, and then use multiple neural networks to predict the processing test data to obtain the output results, according to the rate of change of the output results to analyze and judge the processing. Specifically, for the circulating neural network, the present invention proposes two levels of variation operation: static and dynamic:</i></p> <p><i>In the static aspect, the model weight changes;</i></p> <p><i>In terms of dynamics, modify the state and the results of door operation, including status/door zeroing, state reset, state/door Gaussian noise disturbance and reduce the output accuracy of the state/door."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors consider that the proposed model aims to better detect the quality and safety of the deep learning system and ensure the safety of the deep learning system in the real deployment stage.</p> <p><i>"For a test data, its sensitivity and quality are judged by its inconsistency in predicting results in multiple mutated neural networks. If a test data has a high inconsistency rate in predictive results in multiple altered neural networks, above the preset threshold, the test data is of high quality and can capture the effects of small disturbances in the model. Conversely, if the results of all changed neural networks are predicted consistently, the test data is insensitive and cannot capture the different behaviors of the model."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach to increase the predictability of deep learning models by generating several different models and comparing and contrasting them.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No deep discussion or formal results on safety improvements by this approach have been presented by the patent authors.</p>

8.128 REFERENCE [528]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present an implementation of safe autonomous vehicle with Machine Learning for several functions. Safety is ensured by a safety envelope which can be totally deterministic by design or whose parameterization can be updated with the vehicle's operation.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general (supervised, unsupervised or reinforcement learning).
Q3	<i>"A safety driving model may be designed to achieve, e.g., three goals: first, the interpretation of the law</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 229 / 550	

Answer	<p><i>should be sound in the sense that it complies with how humans interpret the law; second, the interpretation should lead to a useful driving policy, meaning it will lead to an agile driving policy rather than an overly-defensive driving which inevitably would confuse other human drivers and will block traffic and in turn limit the scalability of system deployment; and third, the interpretation should be efficiently verifiable in the sense that it can be rigorously proven that the self-driving (autonomous) vehicle correctly implements the interpretation of the law. A safety driving model, illustratively, may be or include a mathematical model for safety assurance that enables identification and performance of proper responses to dangerous situations such that self-perpetrated accidents can be avoided."</i></p> <p><i>"The perception system may identify one or more objects/features that may affect the control of vehicle based on data received from the one or more one or more data acquisition devices and/or the map DB. For example, according to some aspects, the perception system may monitor an internal environment of the vehicle and determine, for each object/feature, state data that describes a current state of such object as described. As examples, the state data for each object may describe an estimate of the object's: current location or position; current speed or velocity; current acceleration; current heading; current orientation; size/footprint (e.g., as represented by a bounding shape such as a bounding polygon or polyhedron); yaw rate; and/or other state information. According to some aspects, the perception system may determine state data for each object/feature over a number of iterations and/or frames. In particular, the perception system may update the state data for each object at each iteration or frame. Thus, the perception system may detect and track objects and/or features (e.g., external to the vehicle such as other vehicles, internal to the vehicle such as people, etc.) over time. The perception system may implement one or more machine learning models in order to perform these tasks.</i></p> <p><i>The prediction system may receive the state data from the perception system and predict one or more future locations for each object based on such state data. For example, the prediction system may predict where each object will be located within the next 1 second, 2 seconds, 10 seconds, etc. For example, an object may be predicted to adhere to its current trajectory according to its current velocity and/or acceleration. However, other more sophisticated prediction techniques or modeling may be implemented.</i></p> <p><i>The planning system may determine one or more plans for the vehicle based at least in part on the perceived and/or predicted one or more future locations for the object and/or the state data for the object provided by the perception system or prediction system; In other words, given information about the current locations of perceived objects and/or predicted future locations of the perceived objects, the planning system may determine a plan for the vehicle that best responds to or navigates the vehicle relative to the objects at their current and/or future locations."</i></p> <p><i>"In various implementations, one or more of perception system, the prediction system, and/or the planning system can include, or otherwise leverage, one or more machine learning models such as, for example, convolutional neural networks."</i></p> <p><i>"Predicted trajectories of perceived objects may be used to improves parametric safety models such as Responsibility-Sensitive Safety (RSS) models. Predicted trajectories may be used in conjunction with RSS models. For example, when an RSS determines a safe situation, the safe determination may trigger the predictive extension to use the predicted trajectories of traffic participants to determine if the situation is safe. This further check of the ego vehicle safety envelope can only improve AV driving. While an incorrect prediction might lead to some unnecessary deceleration maneuvers, it will not jeopardize the safety of the vehicle.</i></p> <p><i>RSS models may incorporate predicted behavior with parametric motion models to determine the state of a vehicle. There are situations in which the RSS model for autonomous vehicle (AV) driving policies cannot avoid collisions. However, these situations may be foreseeable. To avoid these foreseeable situations, existing parametric models may include behavior predictions determined by the AV processing pipeline. If the state of the ego vehicle is unsafe, appropriate countermeasures are proposed. If the parametric model determines the state of the ego vehicle is safe, the predictive model may double check using predicted trajectories to determine the state of the vehicle. If the predictive model determines the vehicle is safe, nothing further is required. If the predictive model determines the vehicle is unsafe, the predictive model may provide the unsafe state to the parametric model or generate a vehicle response. Alternatively, the predictive model may operate independently of the parametric model to avoid occupying computational resources required by the parametric model. If the models operate independently, the predictive model may determine a vehicle state for all situations regardless of the parametric model determination."</i></p>
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 230 / 550	

	<p><i>"The proposed disclosure may improve the achievable safety of a parametric model such as RSS, without reducing practicability. RSS is a formal mathematical model for the safety of AV behavior planning. RSS covers five key rules:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Do not hit someone from behind</i> 2. <i>Do not cut-in recklessly</i> 3. <i>Right-of-Way is given, not taken</i> 4. <i>Be careful in areas with limited visibility</i> 5. <i>If you can avoid a crash without causing another, you must.</i> <p><i>Each of these rules is described through a set of parameterizable mathematical equations. The parametric model 608 determines the state of the AV based on these rules. If the state is unsafe, RSS provides restrictions of the actuator control commands that should bring the AV back into a safe state."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	The authors consider that the proposed model allows autonomous vehicles to operate safely.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Sound example of real implementation using safe envelope for the safety assurance of ML-based systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No deep discussion or formal results on safety improvements by this approach have been presented by the patent authors.</p>

8.129 REFERENCE [532]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present a vision to maximize the safety, trust and acceptance of automated vehicles by proposing an assessment framework to evaluate different technologies involved in Automated Driving Systems (ADS).
Q2 Answer	Minor references to machine learning.
Q3 Answer	<i>"Adversarial risk analysis models will be developed to support automated driving, helping in better forecasting how other road users behave, and underpinning improved automated decision-making in driving. Finally, the robustness of algorithms supporting automated driving towards attacks will be explored; as an example, an artificial vision algorithm could be hacked and a STOP sign of a road could be misinterpreted leading to chaotic situations. This will lead to the assessment of such algorithms from an adversarial machine-learning perspective."</i>
Q4 Answer	The authors detail the architecture of the proposed approach, called Trustonomy, and do not present results of case studies because they have not been carried out.
Q5 Answer	<i>"(...) further research activities include the implementation of the individual Trustonomy frameworks and then the testing and validation of the discussed approach in extended pilots in fully operational environments, evaluating the performance and impact of the proposed approach."</i>
Q6 Answer	Weakness: Paper only marginally related to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.

8.130 REFERENCE [533]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To summarize existing methods for V&V of autonomous software and present and demonstrate, by a case study of command execution, a method for the assurance of autonomous software. An approach for risk assessment is also presented.
Q2 Answer	No AI technique is directly referred to within the paper.
Q3 Answer	V&V approaches: analytical and test-based. Risk assessment approach: Identify autonomy, identify hazards, quantify likelihood and assess consequences. Bayesian belief networks can be used to aid in likelihood quantification.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 231 / 550

Q4 Answer	The case study applies the proposed approach for V&V and risk assessment to an autonomous system employed in a spacecraft, which may choose either to bomb a target or not.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Weakness: Paper technically weak and practically unrelated to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.

8.131 REFERENCE [534]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose and assess the results of an unified framework for trajectory generation and validation in a consistent and principled way by exploring methods to generate artificial trajectories that resemble previously captured and labeled ones, notably based on Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs): recurrent GANs and a recurrent Autoencoder in combination with GANs.
Q2 Answer	Generative Adversarial Neural Networks and Autoencoders.
Q3 Answer	Background: "(...) <i>statistical analyses have shown that fully autonomous vehicles would have to be driven for hundreds of millions of kilometers. (...) To address this issue, in this paper, we study an alternative scenario-based verification approach. It uses a scenario database created by extracting driving scenarios that the AD vehicle is exposed to in naturalistic driving situations. Once such a scenario database is developed, it can be used for test case generation and verification of the AD functionality in a virtual environment. (...) Scenario extraction is another challenge of this scenario based approach, as it requires properly labeled data.</i> " Basics: " <i>The main focus of this paper is to generate driving scenarios. This may in turn improve the performance of data driven algorithms, such as clustering. (...) Since the data is sequential, we focus on recurrent architectures. The first approach consists of a recurrent autoencoder and a GAN for generating new latent-space representations of the trajectories. The second approach consists of a recurrent GAN without an autoencoder.</i> "
Q4 Answer	The case study presented by the authors is related to the generation of cut-in driving scenarios (i.e., when a vehicle makes a rapid maneuver from any side, e.g., changing lanes, which can lead to a lateral collision). The " <i>proposed models showed satisfactory results based on these metrics [Matching+Coverage and One-To-One Matching with Hungarian Method], but did not achieve the same results as we compare the real sets. From this observation, we conclude i) the proposed metrics are useful and meaningful, and ii) the developed models should be improved even further or other approaches could be considered if accessible.</i> "
Q5 Answer	i) " <i>One direction for future work could be the adjustment of the architectures (for instance a comparison of the performance of RNN, GRU, and LSTM) and tuning hyperparameters for the proposed models with more elegant techniques, rather than the simple grid search used in this work.</i> " ii) " <i>Considering more features apart from only lateral and longitudinal positions could be very helpful. During this work, we have seen potentials for scalability in the proposed models. Moreover, if correlations among parameters are found, they could be used as another metric to determine the quality of the generated scenarios.</i> " iii) " <i>The extraction process of different trajectories was performed with explicit rules. (...) we suggest to replace explicit rules with an adaptive clustering approach.</i> "
Q6 Answer	Weakness: Albeit well performed, the study is marginally related to the safety analysis of AI-based systems since the impact of the proposed architecture in the overall system safety was not assessed. The paper is more related to Category '2' (AI for safety-critical purpose).

8.132 REFERENCE [535]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To describe an approach for finding interpretable failures of an autonomous system, in which failure are described by signal temporal logic expressions that can be understood by a human, and are optimized to produce failures that have high likelihood.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 232 / 550	

Q2 Answer	<p>No specific AI technique is quoted within the paper, meaning that the proposed solution could be applicable to the black-box safety analysis of AI-based systems regardless of AI techniques occasionally used within the system.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Context and Objective: "A major challenge for autonomous driving is how to validate the safety of an autonomous vehicle (AV) before deploying it on the road. A common practice is to test the AV using an adversarial driving simulator that controls stochastic disturbance's in the environment over time to find failures."</p> <p>"We seek to generate descriptions of disturbance trajectories that lead to failure so that the descriptions may be used to understand weaknesses in the autonomous system and produce many related failure examples for further analysis."</p> <p>"(...) The set of all trajectories that end in a failure of the AV is denoted E and x belonging to E means that the sequence of disturbances x causes the System Under Test (SUT) to fail.</p> <p>Black-box falsification techniques try to find any x such that x belongs to E. Falsification can be cast as an optimization problem over the space of disturbance trajectories which can be solved using various optimization algorithms. These approaches do not scale well when x is very high dimensional and failure examples might be extremely rare (...)"</p> <p>"Our approach seeks to find a description such that any disturbance trajectory that satisfies the description will cause the SUT to fail. Additionally, we want to search for the most likely failure example by maximizing the probability of the failure trajectories."</p> <p>"The main contributions of this paper are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) An approach for generating interpretable trajectory descriptions. 2) Application of the approach to finding the most likely failures of an autonomous vehicle. 3) A comparison to an existing validation approach for two driving scenarios." <p>Basics: The proposed approach uses signal temporal logic to provide explainability to the failure events and a context-free grammar to support the signal temporal logic rules. "The algorithm takes as input a grammar that specifies the STL rules and a cost function which can be any function that leads to failures when minimized. (...) A population of expressions are sampled from the grammar, and then the algorithm iterates until the computational budget is exhausted. On each iteration, the cost for each expression is computed by evaluating the cost for N trajectories that satisfy each expression and taking the average. (...) Then, we perform the operations of genetic programming: reproduction, crossover and mutation, to evolve the population of expressions to a lower cost. After looping, return the highest performing description."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The methodology is demonstrated for the safety validation of an autonomous vehicle in the context of an unprotected left turn and a crosswalk with a pedestrian. "In both scenarios, we find interpretable failure modes of the AV for several different initial conditions. Additionally, our approach finds an order of magnitude more failures than the importance sampling baseline and the failures that are found have a much higher likelihood".</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"Future work will include techniques for ensuring good coverage of the disturbance space, improved optimization techniques, and more complex simulators."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Explainability of failures is provided by means of a Signal Temporal Logic whose rules are described by a context-free grammar. It is an interesting approach to be investigated into future research as well. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The authors did not justify the parameterization of the genetic algorithm used during the case studies (e.g. probabilities of reproduction, crossover and mutation, number of individuals and generations), nor presented the details on how the SLR was instantiated for the case studies. 2) Despite the proposed approach being interesting, it is worth noting its high dependency on the application. Explainability could have been developed following a 'construction-like' approach (i.e., by identifying system elements involved in the failure as well as their reasoning) rather than an 'application-oriented' approach (identifying actions that occur at application level). 3) The proposed model requires failure conditions to be previously specified, and the proposed model does not deal with the question that these settings can also be flawed (either randomly or systematically).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 233 / 550	

8.133 REFERENCE [537]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To address the problem of hazard recognition and risk assessment in open and non-predictive environments to support decision making and action selection for UAS by applying an approach denoted as a Safety-Driven Behavior Management for UAS focusing on situation modeling, and the problem of knowledge representation in the context of situational risks. It combines the safety standards-oriented hazards analysis and the risk assessment approach with the machine learning-based situation recognition.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning is briefly mentioned as being employed in building the knowledge representation model within the Safety-Driven Behavior Management system. Deep neural networks are quoted as a potential example of technique employed for this purpose.
Q3 Answer	<p>Basics: <i>"The Safety-Driven Behavior Management system is designed to manage and control the behavior of an autonomous or semi-autonomous system during its interaction with the environment. (...) The major tasks solved in different modules are:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - acquisition of data and extraction of information concerning environmental objects and technical ego-system state, - structuring and assessing the information representing a situation, - identification of hazards and risk assessment, - situation recognition verifying and improving risk assessment, - planning, reasoning and finding an optimal action considering the mission goal as well as safety." <p>Information extraction for representing knowledge relies on machine learning methods, e.g. deep neural networks. <i>"All data-driven approaches and models are trained and verified during the design time to ensure compliance with the safety standards like [IEC61508:2010]. Furthermore, the data selection, labeling, training, verification, and validation are performed in a specified and formal manner to reduce the probability of systematic faults."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	A MATLAB-simulated case study employing a drone model which travels on a small town to deliver goods is exercised by the authors. Several unsafe scenarios are considered (e.g. collision with people or city structures with people inside, collision with other aircraft, letting toxic cargo fall and the city water reservoir). The authors indicate that the Safety-Driven Behavior Management system was able to detect adequate risks associated to the context of use of the drone (according to both the cargo it carries and the area it travels - including the presence of people and other drones).
Q5 Answer	<i>"As the next step, the implementation of the situation recognition module will be completed and tested within the context of the Safety-Driven Behavior Management system using the introduced simulation environment considering the evaluation of the computational effort."</i>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good summary of the AI safety analysis problem for autonomous systems: <i>"Today's research in autonomous and semi-autonomous systems faces challenges in designing a system with verifiably safe behavior"</i>.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors employ Machine Learning and claim that the deployment process for ML is verified to ensure that it meets IEC61508; nevertheless, the authors do not present further information on how this is performed nor discuss or quote the fact that standards such as IEC61508 do not cover the usage of AI for safety-critical functions - which is the case of the safety management system proposed by the authors, since it is at least partially based on Machine Learning.</p>

8.134 REFERENCE [542]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To propose an improved driving risk field with ellipse modification formula in order to assess the driving risk of vehicles in real time and accurately, including a strategy for making lane-change decision based on a back-propagation neural network.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3	Introduction: <i>"The idea of driving risk field (...) establishes a gravitational field and a repulsive field by</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 234 / 550	

Answer	<p><i>environment information such as obstacles and roads. Under the influence of the two fields, the mobile robot can independently plan a path for obstacle avoidance.</i> "As an effective means of traffic safety assessment, driving risk field has the advantages of strong real-time and rich traffic information."</p> <p>Basics: The idea of the ellipse model proposed by the authors is to adjust the driving risk field according to risks which are more meaningful according to the vehicle's movement (e.g., if the vehicle is moving forward, there is more risk at its front than at its rear). A back-propagation neural network with three layers (input, one hidden and output) is used to craft the ellipse model according to input data and adjust the weights of each ellipse radius for lane-changing operations.</p>
Q4 Answer	By using holdout validation with data collected from the 'Mirror Traffic' dataset of Suzhou Automotive Research Institute of Tsinghua University, the authors reached the result that "(...) <i>the accuracy of BP neural network model is 97.78% and the mean square error can be reduced to less than 10⁻², which shows that the method is accurate, reliable and easy to be used in the decision of lane-change.</i> "
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors do not provide the safety analysis of the Neural Network that was conceived for their research. Even the analysis of the neural network results is too simple, given that it was based only on accuracy and no other important metrics (e.g. precision, recall, ROC).</p> <p>2) The paper is related to Category 2 instead of Category 3 (AI used for online safety-critical applications).</p>

8.135 REFERENCE [544]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To explore the risks in the design and application of artificial intelligence and put forward corresponding preventive measures.
Q2 Answer	Artificial Intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors present holistic risks related to AI. Three main risks of AI design and application have been identified and they do not mention safety:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Security risks; - Consumer privacy disclosure risks (also related to security); - Moral hazard (illegitimate capital accumulation). <p>The causes for these risks are identified as follows. They require countermeasures so that risks are prevented.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of legal bodies to support the usage of AI and of who is liable for losses caused by AI; - Imperfect legal supervision and management governance; - AI is uncertain and unknowable.
Q4 Answer	<p>The main results of the paper are related to AI-related risks, their causes and countermeasures to mitigate them. These subjects are covered in the answer to Question 3.</p> <p>The conclusion is that "<i>We can only make science and technology better serve human beings if we can prevent troubles in advance, improve the guidance of new ethics and moral values, build a human environment for the development of artificial intelligence, improve the supervision and management mechanism and legal system, and realize the new ecology of the harmonious development of artificial intelligence in which human and computer coexist.</i>"</p>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The paper is not directly related to the safety analysis of AI-based system; instead, it presents generic challenges related to the usage of AI - and most of them is not directly related to safety assurance itself, but instead to liability and safety issues stemming from lack of security.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 235 / 550	

8.136 REFERENCE [546]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To design a metacontroller capable of identifying unsafe situations with high accuracy by using a Markov decision process (MDP) framework and reinforcement learning (RL) to solve it. This metacontroller is a Runtime Safety Assurance (RTSA) mechanism that observes the inputs and outputs of a non-pedigreed component and verifies formally specified behavior as the system operates.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning (<i>Linear Approximation Q-Learning</i>) for Markov Decision Processes.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "(...) <i>the cost to formally verify a non-pedigreed or black-box autopilot for a variety of vehicle types and use cases is generally prohibitive. An alternative is to bound the flight behavior of unmanned aircraft during operation to comply with safety constraints by mitigating the risk of uncontrolled flight beyond authorized conditions.</i></p> <p><i>Runtime Safety Assurance (RTSA) aims to do this as a runtime monitoring safeguard that is capable of switching to a safe recovery controller if the vehicle is at risk of operating unsafely. (...) RTSA ensures the safety of an autonomous agent when operating using a black-box nominal controller and switching to a simple and safe recovery controller when doing so is necessary to prevent the system from exiting a safety envelope.</i></p> <p>Objective: "<i>The problem that we address in this work is determining how to decide when to switch from the nominal controller to the recovery controller while balancing the trade-off between safety and efficiency.</i>" <i>"Successful implementation of this framework can enable the deployment of commercial off-the-shelf components or learning-enabled-components (LECs) without the need to formally verify them individually."</i></p> <p>Basics: The RTSA system "(...) <i>must be easily verifiable. This means it must avoid black box models that are hard to verify such as deep neural networks.</i>" The RTSA is based on a MDP with Reinforcement learning, in such a way that "<i>The agent receives a large negative reward for abandoning the envelope and a smaller negative reward for deploying the recovery controller in situations where it was not required. This reward structure is designed to heavily penalize situations in which the aircraft exits the safety envelope and simultaneously disincentivize unnecessary deployments of the recovery controller. The rewards at each step are weighted by a discount factor such that present rewards are worth more than future ones.</i>" <i>"We restrict our function family to linear functions which can be easily understood and verified. A major drawback, however, is that linear functions are less expressive than DNNs, which makes their training more difficult and requires careful crafting of features."</i></p> <p>Exploration vs. Exploitation: "<i>We dramatically increase the likelihood of observing episodes where the mission is completed successfully without exiting the envelope, but we also bias the learning process towards exploitation.</i>" "<i>Ideally, we want the learned policy to have a low probability of falsely deploying the recovery controller (...) This can be achieved with a careful initialization of the model weights that reduces the value of deploying the recovery controller. However, determining how to do this specifically and the magnitude by which it should be reduced is a complex problem itself. Instead, we rely on RL to solve this issue. (...) we can use a baseline policy to generate episodes in which the RTSA system exhibited a somewhat acceptable performance. From these episodes, we learn the parameters in an offline approach known as batch reinforcement learning. It is only after we learn a good initialization of our parameters that we then start the training process of our policy.</i>" <i>"For this purpose and to have a benchmark to compare our approach to, we define a baseline policy that consists of shrinking the safety envelope by specifying a distance threshold. When the vehicle reaches a state that is less than the distance away from exiting the envelope, the recovery controller is deployed. This naive approach serves both as a baseline for our experiments and also provides us with experience to initialize the weights of our policy before we do on-policy learning."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"<i>The state space in our simulation is comprised of more than 250 variables.</i>" "<i>For our experiments, we selected features that correspond to the velocity vector of the aircraft, a vector that represents the direction and distance of closest approach to the edge of the geofence, a vector that represents the wind conditions and an indicator variable that represents whether the recovery system has been deployed or not.</i>" <i>"To demonstrate our approach we implemented an RTSA system (...) by training a policy (...) to demonstrate the viability of the approach as many civil unmanned aircraft applications are tending towards the use of open-source autopilots such as the PX4. (...) For all our experiments we used a simulator designed for Small</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 236 / 550	

	<p><i>Unmanned Aircraft System (sUAS) (...) : the Small Unmanned Aircraft Trajectory Modeler (SAT), which is a suite of MATLAB simulation tools."</i></p> <p><i>"The simulator exhibits a deterministic behavior: given all the values of the simulation variables the next state is fully specified given the action of the agent. However, (...) we infused stochasticity to the environment by randomly generating a wind vector field for each simulation episode. We specified the distribution of the wind vector field such that without RTSA the aircraft exits the envelope about a quarter of the time."</i></p> <p><i>"(...) the RL based policy consistently outperforms the baseline and also dominates the nominal controller. This result suggests that linear value function approximation based policies crafted with appropriate features can lead to a consistently better RTSA system than the natural human engineered approach."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<p><i>"Future work could investigate how to incorporate recovery controllers that can steer the vehicle to safe operational conditions and then return control to the nominal controller. Another direction for future work would be to incorporate the behavior of the system over time and analyze its safety as a closed-loop system with non-linear dynamics."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Example of study in which a safety envelope monitor is designed in such a way to consider the tradeoff between safety and efficiency in order to switch from a black-box nominal controller to a safe controller. <i>"Successful implementation of this framework can enable the deployment of commercial off-the-shelf components or learning-enabled-components (LECs) without the need to formally verify them individually."</i></p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Albeit more explainable than, e.g., Deep Neural Networks, the designed metacontroller is still based on AI mechanisms (reinforcement learning for Markov Decision Process). Despite the use of a simpler algorithm (Linear Approximation Q-Learning), parameterization is still a key for adequate verification of the model, as the authors also quote: <i>"We restrict our function family to linear functions which can be easily understood and verified. A major drawback, however, is that linear functions are less expressive than DNNs, which makes their training more difficult and requires careful crafting of features."</i></p>

8.137 REFERENCE [547]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present an introduction to machine learning, compare it with well-known modeling techniques by giving an example from aviation and question their fitness for certification by discussing enablers and try to understand the limitations that might result or prevent the use of machine learning on certified safety systems.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, with specific focus on Machine Learning in several arguments presented by the authors.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: The main issues involving AI and Safety are related to the following topics:</p> <p>1) Can AI act against humans (disrespecting Asimov rules) if they become too smart?</p> <p>2) How can AI be certified for safety-critical systems?</p> <p>Basics: The main opportunities for AI/ML to perform certifiable drone-related challenges are related to (i.) improving piloting autonomy, (ii.) improving and accelerating pilot training, (iii.) predictive maintenance, (iv.) improving controlling activities performed by ATCo, and, finally, (v.) supporting Unmanned Air Traffic Management (UTM). <i>"EASA considers AI/ML powered autonomy would be the only possible way to achieve safe integration of drones into the airspace especially in very complex environments, such as urban operations, expected to accommodate a vast variety of drones"</i>.</p> <p>The authors identify that the main challenges AI/ML pose for the certification of safety-critical systems in aviation are the following ones:</p> <p>a) AI/ML solve problems in a different way than traditional engineering (no need for modeling the system; instead, a hypothesis for the system is the starting point for the system to conceive a model based on training, and validation evaluates whether such training is adequate);</p> <p>b) Problems attributed to AI/ML are harder to be solved and, hence, harder to be checked. The problems usually require adaptiveness, which <i>"(...) is not supported by regulations yet, so either ML/AI or another method, it would call for new ways of certification to implement such a system."</i> On-line learning (learning while the system operates and collects more data) is also a challenge.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 237 / 550	

	<p>The summary of the main challenges is as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traditional development assurance frameworks are not adapted to machine learning; - Difficulties in keeping a comprehensive description of the intended function - Lack of predictability and explainability of the ML application behavior - Lack of guarantee of robustness and of no 'unintended function' - Lack of standardized methods for evaluation of the operational performance of the ML/DL applications <p>Issue of bias and variance in ML applications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complexity of architectures and algorithms - Adaptive learning processes <p>(...)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -the specification problem - referring to problem definition; - the dataset constitution problem - referring to challenges due to dataset - the learning problem - referring to the learning phase - the implementation problem - referring to the prediction phase." <p>c) Issues regarding datasets, which can affect model predictability and ultimately lead to overfitting in case of inadequate training approaches. "(...) the extra difficulty in ML comes in the fact that those data can be represented by its effects during the control flow of the program, while weights and biases cannot be represented by their effects."</p> <p>d) Issues related to the learning process, which can affect traceability ("implementation of the specification", including traceability to the dataset), the bias-variance tradeoff, performance (several metrics with different meanings, e.g., accuracy, precision, recall, etc.) and explainability.</p>
Q4 Answer	Please refer to the answers for Question 3 for the results, since the safety challenges discussion is the main result of the paper.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Very creative introduction, notably with regard to Asimov's rules: "1. A robot may not injure a human being or, through inaction, allow a human being to come to harm. 2. A robot must obey the orders given it by human beings except where such orders would conflict with the First Law. 3. A robot must protect its own existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the First or Second Laws (See Runabout, I. Asimov, 1943) 0. A robot may not harm humanity, or, by inaction, allow humanity to come to harm." 2) Thorough and didactic review of Machine Learning basics. 3) Future challengers regarding the usage of AI/ML in aviation safety-critical systems is well explored. 4) Interesting information regarding current programs in Europe to circumvent the posed challenges.

8.138 REFERENCE [548]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose a lens for the evaluation of verification methods in development to ground new criteria, standards, and means of compliance for assuring and approving adaptive and intelligent systems.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "(...) the kinds of systems we are building, and the ways we are building them, are evolving. (...) This work sits within a greater objective of building and supporting arguments assuring the design and operation of autonomous systems. A required support for such an argument is that we can verify autonomy-enabling technologies, for example, components that use machine learning or other varieties of AI. At present, we cannot do so in conventionally certifiable ways. The current work focuses on the novel verification methods in development, and in particular, on nested arguments about these verification methods. (...) We then discuss how to use the results to help structure and support verification arguments."</p> <p>Contextualization: "The regulatory response indicates an early but accelerating trend toward performance-based assessment: the idea that rather than demonstrate conformance to specified detailed processes,</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 238 / 550	

	<p>applicants must instead, through whatever means they believe compelling, convince the regulator they have achieved specific properties in their systems."</p> <p>"(...) working completely within standard practice has become intractable for many new systems; system variety, data volume, methods mismatch, and impenetrable rationale all make traditional means unduly burdensome and insufficiently enlightening to both OEMs and regulators under certain conditions. So what we seek is a way to make use of the large body of practice that continues to provide value, to the extent that it does provide it, but create a framework to more regularly and rationally handle the increasing volume and diversity of exceptional situations. This is a cross-industry phenomenon; automotive systems, medical systems, and other safety-critical domains are showing similar challenges and needs."</p> <p>"(...) while new performance-based objectives are becoming a reality, together with new flexibility in how to meet them, regulators and OEMs still have a significant learning curve to negotiate in identifying and agreeing means that will work." "These include academic, industrial, and agency research efforts, and government-funded award programs such as DARPA's Assured Autonomy Program. Standards and advisory organizations are active here as well, including ASTM's AC-377 task group on Autonomy Design and Operations in Aviation, and SAE's G-34 committee on Artificial Intelligence in Aviation. The latter seeks to produce a development standard by which aeronautical systems implementing AI can be evaluated, with reference to new verification criteria and means of compliance, targeted for publication in the 2023 timeframe."</p> <p>Basics: The authors propose that the verification process itself is a system, and that, for each system that shall be verified, a framework for the assurance of the verification process shall be developed. This verification process is crafted by performing hazard analyses in order to identify hazardous situations stemming from verification errors and crafting processes and methods which mitigate these hazards. In addition, the following remarks regarding software verification are presented:</p> <p>"1. We do not have data to declare exclusively run-time verification sufficient, because we do not yet have an accounting of the new hazards;</p> <p>2. We do have growing evidence that using run-time exclusively will not be sufficient, because many of the changes to what software we build and how we build it are characterized by upending of assumptions about the runtime/design-time distinction; and</p> <p>3. Satisfying the argument framework with one approach generally will not be possible for any but very trivial applications, because the verification hazards span the continuum, and will therefore require mitigations across the continuum."</p> <p>"The integrity of training data is critical to the correct function of learning enabled components. Verification of components only at runtime cannot take into account training data, other than containing negative effects as with the monitor example above. Identification and repair of faults in training data is an activity fundamental to the effective application of intelligent systems and only made possible by design-time approaches."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors conclude that the current challenge for the certification of AI-based safety-critical systems is related to defining mitigations for hazards stemming from AI. "From the argument framework presented, we infer that neither design-time nor run-time verification is sufficient alone for assessing correctness of complex software, especially as software development practices and techniques are themselves evolving." "Further, the recalcitrance of machine learning and deep learning to meaningful use of properties like traceability and determinism in assessment calls for completely novel criteria and methods of compliance, likely to come from across the spectrum of design- and run-time."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>No shortcomings are explored by the author(s). Future research is thoroughly explored throughout the entire paper.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Well aligned to the DSc. research, since its main purposes are to identify how to conceive a framework for the safety certification of systems with AI and support verification arguments.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors only cover software verification and do not explicitly take into account the possibility of using AI in hardware (e.g. dedicated circuits or PLDs).</p> <p>2) The authors present a general method for crafting a verification framework for AI-based systems, but practically do not discuss technicalities of these implementations, leaving them for other researchers and normative institutions.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 239 / 550	

8.139 REFERENCE [549]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To explore whether the aviation industry can apply solutions from other industries facing autonomous systems challenges - notably the ANSI/UL 4600 standard, which is sufficiently generic to be used in several application domains - to UAS and UAM assurance.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligent is quoted in some parts of the paper as relevant, since it is an underlying part of modern fully autonomous systems.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introductions: <i>"Newer generations of autonomous systems, AI, and machine learning are non-deterministic. (...) AI, and machine learning may have unknown hazards and unproven controls. Continuously evolving learning systems are not expected to behave the same way in future operations as they did when they were initially approved and fielded."</i></p> <p>Basics: The main aspects of ANSI/UL 4600 which can be considered by the aviation industry are as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Goal-Based and Technology Neutral: ANSI/UL 4600 does not require a specific design approach or specific technology. The applicant company must present an auditable and defensible evidence-based safety case. 2) Continued Airworthiness with Monitored Safety Metrics: Moving to performance-based standards with risk based strategy is supported by ANSI/UL 4600. Further, ANSI/UL 4600 recognizes that continued safety is even more important than one-time initial approval/acceptance, especially for learning systems used in problem-solving Artificial Intelligence (AI). Continued airworthiness could be assessed using this method even though the system is presumably fielded with unknown risks due to new and novel technology. 3) Modernization of Regulatory Approaches: This methodology supports performance-based regulations with compliance required to enforce system-of-systems interoperability. 4) Industry and Public Stakeholder Engagement: The standard has undergone industry and public scrutiny in the automobile segment with considered reviews from technical, legal, and actuarial perspectives. <p><i>"Safety Performance Indices (SPIs) are the indices that are chosen by the designers of the system to indicate the health and performance of the systems. Leading or lagging indicators are collected for observing the trends and monitoring bounds."</i></p> <p><i>"ANSI/UL 4600 promotes risk based oversight and approvals. Such approvals are moderated using continuous field data gathering and data analysis for predictive failures and breeches in expected safety. SPI are monitored to assure safety outcomes. Predictions using SPI bring attention to how the autonomous system is evolving, rather than waiting for incidents to predict failures."</i></p> <p><i>"In summary, the safety case for autonomy includes full definition of functionality, learning methods, and operational perception of autonomy. Continuous evolution of good practices and application of lessons learned are imposed during training and operation before and after fielding the system. Autonomy is considered within the context of the full system and its operational environment."</i></p> <p><i>"Overlapping contributions [from different system elements, e.g. airspace, operator, aircraft and services] can lead to non-deterministic outcomes and require an extended safety case that goes beyond the hardware and software of the aircraft or even its ground systems. For example, where data furnished by navigation, advisory, or other services are used by autonomous systems, then the data becomes a source of learning and an indirect source of control of the aircraft's behavior."</i></p> <p><i>"ANSI/UL 4600 follows the philosophy of combining a well-formed safety case with valid argumentation and robust hazard coverage across the components and across these ecosystems. Safety argumentation covers functional safety, operational safety, autonomy safety and other assurance activities as applicable."</i></p> <p><i>Alike new FAA directives, "ANSI/UL 4600 has the same philosophy of being technology agnostic. With performance-based rules, compliance is synonymous with an evidence-based safety case where performance is expected to be achieved within the larger context of how that system is used. (...) Continuous assessment is important if the system has been trained in an environment different from where it will continue to operate."</i></p> <p><i>"Per ANSI/UL 4600 the safety case and its argumentation evidence must be justifiable under audit. Justifiability relies on the repeatability by which the safety case is made, and the performance is demonstrated and monitored via specification and collection of SPI."</i></p> <p><i>"The codification of lessons for general use as a matter of procedure will promote SMS principles for the whole community especially for new and novel technology."</i></p> <p>Challenges related to Autonomous Systems Hazards:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 240 / 550	

	<p>"ANSI/UL 4600 includes the following considerations of hazards related to autonomy in building an integrated safety case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General autonomy pipeline to consider hazards related to sensing - Sensing – sensing components, sensor calibration, preprocessing, interface, sensor fusion - Perception – conversion of sensor data into objects, classifying the objects, identification of overall state as within or outside of Operational Design Domain (ODD) - Planning of autonomous movement – route planning and trajectory creation - Prediction approach if used - Machine learning – data selection, data cleaning, algorithm selection, machine learning architecture, model training approach - AI techniques and algorithms used - Controls, actuation, and timing – trajectory execution, motion control and feedback to planning - Operational design domain – acceptably complete ODD with traceability to ODD-dependent aspects of the safety case considering relevant environment and ODD violations. Note that ODD is where event coverage, behavioral rules, environmental effects (weather conditions, “visibility” etc.), operational condition of the vehicle and operational duration (mission duration) are considered. - Credit taken for previous assessments including commercially available “autonomy kits”, assessment of applicability within the current context. - Note that no architectural structure is implied by these general groupings."
Q4 Answer	<p>"ANSI/UL 4600, with some possible adaptations for human machine teaming, could be used for FAA safety oversight. ANSI/UL 4600 is suitable with traits needed for FAA policy while overcoming challenges in autonomous, machine learning, and unknown pedigree component approval. Further, regulations based on ANSI/UL 4600 could be expressed in a technology agnostic manner for longevity in these highly evolving fields. Additionally, ANSI/UL 4600 affords advantages of a predictive risk-based approach with continuous monitoring of SPI to track performance and safety risks in an evolving system or evolving environment for continued safety. Safety assurance evidence could be comprehensively analyzed within the overall rules of the airspace and specific operations. Any changes to systems and mitigations would be holistic. Aggregate SPI data from applicants could allow the regulators to make overall improvements."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>No shortcomings are explored by the author(s). Future research is thoroughly explored throughout the entire paper.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good overview of the ANSI/UL 4600 standard, including relationship with future targets of FAA to certify autonomous systems. 2) Provides good justification for the DSc.: ANSI/UL4600 standard tries to 'avoid technological guidelines' and let manufacturers decide their methods for the safety assurance. The DSc. would provide some guidelines in that way. <p>"ANSI/UL 4600 has the same philosophy of being technology agnostic. With performance-based rules, compliance is synonymous with an evidence-based safety case where performance is expected to be achieved within the larger context of how that system is used. (...) Continuous assessment is important if the system has been trained in an environment different from where it will continue to operate."</p> <p>"The codification of lessons for general use as a matter of procedure will promote SMS principles for the whole community especially for new and novel technology."</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No further technicalities regarding the safety analysis of AI are presented.

8.140 REFERENCE [551]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose a novel hybrid framework for effective risk assessment of UAVs, which integrates the qualitative knowledge and the quantitative Condition Monitoring data, to evaluate the real-time hierarchical risk of UAVs.
Q2 Answer	Autoencoder, unsupervised neural network and adaptive Gaussian mixture model with Bayesian hyperparameter optimization.
Q3	Introduction of the Model: "(...) the complicated UAV is firstly abstracted as a multi-level evaluating index

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 241 / 550	

Answer	<p>system considering its qualitative logic compositions. Then, for each low-level index, given its multivariate Condition Monitoring data of several time instants, recurrent fusion autoencoder (RFA), a novel unsupervised neural network architecture, is proposed to extract their robust and complete feature embeddings automatically. (...) the risk of each low-level index is quantified by the adaptive Gaussian mixture model in a probabilistic way, which is truly data-driven with the help of the Bayesian hyperparameter optimization."</p> <p>Contributions: "(...) the main contributions of this paper are listed as follows: (1) A novel information fusion method named recurrent fusion autoencoder (RFA) is proposed in this paper. Thanks to the proposed sequential fusion layer, RFA can deal with the vanishing gradient better compared with the standard recurrent autoencoder, and thus achieving more complete information fusion and highlighting the intrinsic risk from both two aspects of the time dimension and variable dimension. (2) The adaptive GMM (Gaussian mixture model) Introductions: "Newer generations of autonomous systems, AI, and machine learning are non-deterministic. (...) AI, and machine learning may have unknown hazards and unproven controls. Continuously evolving learning systems are not expected to behave the same way in future operations as they did when they were initially approved and fielded. (3) With the help of the variable weight coefficients, the dynamic FCE (fuzzy comprehensive evaluation) can flexibly adjust the weights of EIs (evaluating indices) according to their real-time risk indications, and thus it can evaluate the preliminary status risk of UAVs timely. (4) The proposed hybrid framework provides a systematic methodology to evaluate the hierarchical risk of complicated UAVs, where both the qualitative logic compositions and quantitative CM (condition monitoring) data are integrated and analyzed systematically."</p> <p>Model Basics: "(1) First, according to the qualitative logical compositions, the complicated UAVs are abstracted and transformed into an EI system, where the corresponding initial weight sets and the grading level sets are also pre-defined. (2) Second, given the quantitative CM data of each lowest-level EI (3rd-level EI in this paper), there will be an RFA model built to extract the feature embeddings that fuse the useful information from both two aspects of varying dimension and time dimension. The above operations are accomplished by two phases: offline phase and online phase. In the offline phase, given the historical normal CM data, RFA will be trained in an unsupervised manner using the gradient descent optimization, and the intrinsic characteristics of the CM data will be represented in the model parameters. In the online phase, given the real-time CM data, it will be fused and transformed into a feature embedding vector by the trained RFA. The feature embedding fuses and codes the risk-related information for each lowest-level EI. (3) Third, given the fused feature embeddings of each lowest level EI, the adaptive GMM is developed to quantify its risk in a truly data-driven way, which is also accomplished by two phases. In the offline phase, given the normal feature embeddings, there will be a GMM trained automatically to model their baseline distribution with the help of Bayesian optimization. Then in the online phase, given the real-time feature embedding, the trained GMM will calculate its risk quantification with the probabilistic meanings, which reflects the deviation between the baseline feature distribution and real-time feature in the form of likelihood. (4) Finally, given the real-time probabilistic risk indications of all lowest-level EIs, the corresponding initial weights are adjusted dynamically and there will be a fuzzy risk vector evaluated to reflect the risk of the higher-level EI. Repeating the above operations level by level, we will finally achieve the real time hierarchical risk assessment for complicated UAVs under uncertainty."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"The proposed framework was validated on two datasets: the turbofan engine datasets (simulation) and the UAV flight datasets (real). The experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness and superiority of the hybrid framework on robust information fusion and accurate hierarchical risk assessment."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"There are two possible limitations for our hybrid framework in practical applications: (1) this paper mainly focuses on the hierarchical risk of UAVs themselves, where the external factors such as signal strength, atmospheric environment, etc. are not considered. (2) this paper mainly focused on the risk quantification of UAVs, how to apply these results to the risk-related decision-making is not researched yet in a systematic way. Therefore, in future research, the framework will be further developed to integrate more risk-related factors and support the decision making of risk management."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Good insight on neural networks and autoencoders: "(...) some scholars have tried to replace the traditional fully connected layer with the recurrent cell structure (...) . In theory, thanks to the capability on depicting the temporal characteristics, the recurrent architecture can achieve more complete information</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 242 / 550	

fusion compared with the nonrecurring ones. However, in practice, due to the 'hard' fusion strategy, the existing recurrent architectures generally suffer from the vanishing gradient and cannot achieve the satisfied performance on temporal fusion, which is also a key issue that needs to be addressed."

Weaknesses:

1) The authors present a very interesting and complex method for on-line risk assessment of autonomous systems (for aircraft applications), but to not address how their models have been assured as safe. Therefore, the paper is not of big relevance for category 3 (contrary to the initial idea presented within the paper's abstract), but important contribution for Category 2.

8.141 REFERENCE [553]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present current progress in the development of Environmental Survey Hazard Analysis (ESHA), a method of preliminary hazard identification aimed at autonomous system application problems. ESHA differs from conventional hazard identification methods in that its scope explicitly covers the identification of non-mission interactions between a system and its environment and any associated hazards.
Q2 Answer	AI in general. The presented method does not cover technicalities of AI.
Q3 Answer	<p><i>"The environment-driven requirements analysis produced by ESHA can also support the development of machine learning solutions for autonomous system problems. Since all ML processes or devices are developed inductively by training from a set of examples, the correctness of the system behavior produced from a machine learning process is highly dependent on the diversity of the samples provided for its training. If there is any systematic error of omission in the training set, then the product of the ML process is likely to exhibit similar omissions in its operational behavior."</i></p> <p><i>"In unbounded environments, the number of features with which an autonomous agent may interact is uncertain. This affects the validity of quantitative risk analyses; calculations of requirements for or verification of a system's probability of failure depend on the set of contributing hazards to be complete. (...) Most practical test programs can only deliver high-confidence estimates of probability of failure that are usually several orders of magnitude lower than the values required. This applies in particular to rare events, which are unlikely to occur during testing but may nevertheless still occur at a higher rate than is considered acceptable by legislative requirements. (...) But any simulator will have limits to its fidelity (Koopman and Wagner 2018), which are likely to be impossible or too expensive to correct, and this makes the task of identifying rare events solely from testing impossible (the event does not occur during the test program, and there is no way to determine whether the lack of occurrence is due to the genuine rarity of the event or due to being masked by errors in simulator fidelity)."</i></p> <p>The ESHA procedure employs a set of guide-words to classify the environmental features with the autonomous system (AS) may need to interact. Its objective is to identify the underlying hazards and "(...) categorize environmental features in such a way as to be logically complete and therefore exhaustive of any environmental domain. The set was developed on the conceptual basis that in an unbounded environment." The authors are "(...) investigating existing formal ontologies to see if they provide the necessary logical framework we need to underpin ESHA." The main desired features of such an ontology are as follows:</p> <p>"1) Support for essential ontological concepts: Several core ontological topics are required a minimum of any ontology that could be used to support ESHA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mereotopology: relationships between parts and wholes, that allow the identification of structures and complex objects; – Boundaries: formal treatment of boundaries within the mereotopology, especially fiat as well as bona fide boundaries; – Situations and Events: formal classification scheme of situations and events, which will provide support for hazard identification; – Agency, Causality, Autonomy: formal classification scheme for the behavior of environmental features, to allow capture of causal relationships and identification of interactions. <p>2) Particulars and Universals: Since we are interested in establishing abstract concepts such as safety properties, we seek a foundational ontology that incorporates Universals as well as Particulars.</p> <p>3) Realism or Conceptualism preferred over Nominalism: Since we require the existence of universals, we</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 243 / 550	

	<p>reject the purely Nominalist stance that Universals do not exist. We require ontological frameworks that reflect at least a Conceptualist if not a fully Platonic perspective. However, this does not mean that we cannot incorporate nominalist ontological models as partial frameworks, applying solely to Particulars, and then 'complete the model' by adding corresponding Universals, which can be done by means of model-patterns such as the ontological square.</p> <p>4) Logical completeness and disjointness: We are looking for formal ontologies whose type hierarchy is defined as far as possible in a logically complete and disjoint manner. Completeness ensures that the model is exhaustive in its scope. Disjointness of types ensures that our analysis remains tractable, since multiple combinations of parent types will be excluded."</p> <p>"Our general model of ontological frameworks for ESHA takes the view that they will follow a three-layer organization structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foundational ontologies are the most abstract layer, defining the most basic entities that underpin other layers. • Domain ontologies define the most general concepts that are specific to a particular domain but general to numerous applications (e.g. system safety, geospatial domains, HMI, etc.); • Application ontologies define entity types intended for specific application categories, such as assistive robots or driverless vehicles."
Q4 Answer	The authors identified that, among four candidate ontologies, the UFO (Unified Foundation Ontology) is the one that most approaches the requirements needed for crafting the ESHA, but improvements on it are still needed. The authors are still working on improving UFO with the desired features.
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) we aim to create a new ESHA Foundational Ontology as an evolutionary development of UFO."</p> <p>"We are currently applying the improved ESHA methodology to application problems in the fields of assistive robotics for healthcare and social care, and also to driver-less road vehicles (CAVs)."</p> <p>"We will then proceed to develop domain-level and application-level ontologies that support two particular domains (assistive medical/social care robots, and driverless road vehicles)."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Clear arguments reinforcing that no exhaustive testing programs can be carried out to ensure that an AI-based system is safe.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The relationship of the research with AI is only indirect, since the authors are studying how to elicit hazards of autonomous systems, and these typically rely on AI to perform their functions. The presented method, however, brings little importance to the safety assurance of AI-based systems themselves.</p>

8.142 REFERENCE [557]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a novel framework for dynamic safety assurance of Cooperative Systems of Systems (CSoSs) that integrates design time models and runtime techniques to provide continuous assurance during CSoS operation.
Q2 Answer	AI in general. The presented method does not cover technicalities of AI.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: Challenges related to Cooperative Systems of Systems:</p> <p>1) "A first challenge is caused by the distribution and often heterarchical organization of systems. A heterarchy is a system or organization where the elements are unranked and nonhierarchical or can be ranked in different ways. CSoSs are inherently distributed, loosely connected, and nonhierarchical."</p> <p>2) "A second challenge is caused by the inevitable incompleteness of dependability models anyone would attempt to do a priori at design time for a CSoS."</p> <p>3) "(...) increased uncertainty in CSoSs. It can arise from many sources: 1) a limited observability of the system and its environment caused by a lack of sensors or failure of sensors; 2) unreliability of measurements; 3) the inaccuracy, indeterminism, or probabilistic nature of the inferences drawn by artificial intelligence (AI) components, for example, machine learning algorithms; 4) limited knowledge concerning services and dependability-relevant properties of collaboration partners in a cooperative or open system; and 5) limited knowledge regarding trustworthiness and quality of third-party information."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 244 / 550	

	<p>Basics: The proposed model is a new approach to dynamic safety assurance of CSoSs which "(...) uses a network of intelligent safety monitoring agents to deliver safety assurance within a CSoS. An agent for a system carries information about the system's safety assurance in the form of dependability models [including safety certificates] and uses information shared by the agents of other cooperating systems in conjunction with information from the environment to provide dependability management at runtime, for example, event monitoring, diagnostics, certification, risk prediction, and action planning. The approach aims to facilitate the development of runtime artifacts to self-certify the safe operation of CSoSs even if the system design evolves during operation."</p> <p>"To provide safety certificates and further dependability management functions (for example, recommended actions to avoid hazardous situations), the Intelligent Reasoning Agents (IREs) operate on a knowledge graph, which is an ontology that integrates metadata in a machine-interpretable representation. We incorporate appropriate IRE models into the knowledge graph to enable the execution of dependability algorithms at runtime. For this purpose, we use the concept of digital dependability identities (DDIs). (...) A DDI of a component or a system contains all of the information required to uniquely define the dependability properties of the system or the component. The information can be captured in textual format and/or by using one or more safety artifacts, such as in the form of fault trees, conditional safety certificates (ConSerts), Bayesian networks (BNs), Markov chains, and Petri nets. Using these models, the key attributes that define the system's or component's dependability behavior are captured, for instance, in the form of faults and potential fault propagation models. Additionally, requirements on how the component / subsystem interacts with other components/subsystems of the CSoS in a dependable way is captured in terms of the level of trust and assurance. (...) DDIs are produced during the design, issued during releasing the component/system, and continuously maintained/adapted throughout the system lifetime."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Same case study of [453]: "To demonstrate the proposed approach, we use the example of an autonomous production cell system (...) The function of the production system is to take a workpiece, drill a hole in it, insert a screw into this hole, and then tighten the screw. To achieve this functionality, the system uses three autonomous robots, which are connected with autonomous transportation carts. With the help of three different tools, each of the robots can perform three tasks: drilling, inserting, and tightening. However, they can only perform one task at a time, and if instructed, they can reconfigure themselves to perform a different task. (...) A workpiece must be processed in the order of drill->insert-> tighten (DIT). Although a single robot can perform all three tasks, to meet the timing constraint, a single robot cannot be used to perform all three tasks through multiple reconfigurations. Therefore, the workpiece should be processed by all three robots in order, and the carts transport the workpiece to the robots according to the planned operation."</p> <p>he authors present the application of their model and hypothetical results, but do not present details on how the case study was implemented or thoroughly exercised.</p> <p>"This is early work but could lead to significant steps forward; to our knowledge, no other dynamic assurance method has addressed the important issue of uncertainty at runtime certification."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>The authors mention that the project was still ongoing by the time of the publication, but did not explore a roadmap with the next actions to be considered. The usage of ConSerts and support for online maintenance are quoted as important contributions in the future..</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Paper written in a very comprehensible way. 2) Method is applicable for online safety analysis of autonomous systems (with potential dynamic reconfiguration) and including uncertainties. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The relationship of the research with AI is only indirect, since AI can be a tool to implement the autonomous systems analyzed by the authors.

8.143 REFERENCE [563]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present a novel and automated technique for verifying steering angle safety for self-driving cars based on deep learning verification (DLV), which is an automated verification framework for safety of image classification neural networks.
Q2 Answer	Deep Neural Networks.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 245 / 550	

Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction - Challenges:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "(...) it has been observed that DNN-based software, including the system for self-driving cars, can react in unexpected and incorrect ways to even slight perturbations of their inputs. Those previously-unseen erroneous behaviors in DNN-driven self-driving cars can lead to dangerous consequences like a fatal collision. Several such real-world cases have already been reported." 2) "(...) although case-based test and simulation are often used to check the performance of autonomous systems, they do not provide sufficient guarantees. This is especially true for safety-critical areas such as autonomous driving, where unsafe incidents are rare and difficult to characterize." 3) "In general, DNNs are large, non-linear, and nonconvex, and verifying even some simple properties about them is an NP-complete problem. DNN verification is experimentally beyond the reach of general-purpose tools such as linear programming (LP) solvers or existing satisfiability modulo theories (SMT) solvers." <p>Basics: "DLV is based on search for adversarial misclassifications within a given region. That is, if an adversarial example is found, the network is said to be unsafe for the image classification task; and otherwise, if no misclassifications are found for all DNN layers, the network is proved to be safe. However, DLV cannot be used directly to the verification problem of steering angle safety for self-driving cars, since correct steering angles are within a certain range of values rather than a concrete single value like in the case of image classification. To solve this problem, we use neuron coverage and slack relationships (introduced in this paper) to turn the steering angle judgment problem into a classification problem. Neuron coverage is the ratio of unique neurons that get activated for a given input image to the total number of neurons in a DNN. Correlation with positive statistical significance suggests that the steering angle increases with increasing neuron coverage and vice versa. We use the statistical significance between the neuron coverage and the steering angle, and then introduce the neuron coverage as a reference for the same steering angles. The slack relationships are based on the relationship we define for a safe DNN-driven self-driving cars, i.e., the steering angle should not change significantly for minimal changes of the input image. If the neuron coverage of the perturbed image is equal to that of the original image, and the predicted steering angle of the perturbed image satisfies two slack relationships, then the perturbed image and the original image are considered to have the same class. As long as any one of these three conditions is not satisfied, the class of the perturbed image is considered to be different from that of the original image. After transforming the verification problem into a classification problem, DLV is used to tackle the verification of steering angle safety for self-driving cars. We name this technique as SDLV (namely "Steering with DLV")."</p> <p>The model requires several design decisions to be made in order to be usable (e.g. restrictions on steering angle, boundaries for the effects of steering angle on images, hyperparameters tuning).</p> <p>Definition of safety: a Neural Network is deemed safe if, for a specific region around a layer, any input produces the same output.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We evaluate our technique on the NVIDIA's end-to-end self-driving architecture, which is a crucial ingredient in many modern self-driving cars. Experimental results show that our technique can successfully find adversarial misclassifications (i.e., incorrect steering decisions) within given regions if they exist. Therefore, we can achieve safety verification (if no misclassification is found for all DNN layers, in which case the network can be said to be stable or reliable w.r.t. steering decisions) or falsification (in which case the adversarial examples can be used to fine-tune the network)."</p> <p>"The system's network contains 9 layers: a normalization layer, 5 convolutional layers, and 3 fully connected layers. This system takes inputs from a single front-facing center camera and outputs steering commands. Recent results have demonstrated that a well-trained end-to-end system can predict the steering angle with an accuracy close to that of a human driver. However, the adversarial examples reported by our experiments have shown that such systems (networks) can be instable and result in dangerous behaviors."</p> <p>"(...) we use Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) [NH10] as the main activation function."</p> <p>The authors present a detailed analysis of the obtained results with regard to processing time, effectiveness of each factor contributing to the generation of adversarial examples (neuron activation and slack relationships) and a comparison with a baseline safety analysis approach for steering angle called DeepTest. The authors conclude that the results are satisfactory and that the SDLV finds more adversarial examples than DeepTest, hence being better from a safety point of view.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"Regarding future work, we would like to enhance the scalability of SDLV. Specifically, we will explore better predicted behaviors analysis for the safety verification of steering angle by taking other realistic</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 246 / 550	

	<p>factors such as braking, accelerated speed, and possibly traffic regulations etc., into account. In SDLV on the multi-path search, we will explore more optimized method in path selection to improve its effect. In addition, we would like to provide better interpretability by exploring the relationship between disturbance and steering angle, which we believe is an interesting and challenging work."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization of adversarial attacks and clear arguments reinforcing that no exhaustive testing / simulation programs and adversarial attacks can be carried out to ensure that an AI-based system is safe. 2) Excellent basis on the limitation of linear programming and SMT solvers to support the safety verification of Deep Neural Networks. 3) Clear definition of safety: a Neural Network is deemed safe if, for a specific region around a layer, any input produces the same output. 4) The authors clearly present the model and highlight the several application-specific decisions that are needed for the model to be used (e.g. restrictions on steering angle, boundaries for the effects of steering angle on images, hyperparameters tuning). <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The model was implemented in Python, and Python is not currently accepted for safety-critical systems.

8.144 REFERENCE [565]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To introduce data mining and machine learning methodologies and techniques that have been applied in highway safety studies, including association rules, clustering analysis, decision tree models, Bayesian networks, neural networks, and support vector machines.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning, with emphasis on association rules, clustering analysis, decision tree models, Bayesian networks, neural networks, and support vector machines.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors present the technical foundations and application examples on risk analysis of highways of the following machine learning techniques: association rules, clustering analysis, decision tree models, Bayesian networks, neural networks, and support vector machines.</p> <p>Highlights:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting recommendation for Neural Networks: "<i>ANN models, like other classification models, have the multiclass classification problem, meaning they ignore less-represented categories to improve the model's overall accuracy. This is a problem for injury severity studies as the data are highly skewed due to the presence of fewer high-severe injury crashes and more less-severe injury crashes. One solution is reducing the multiclass problem into a series of two-class (binary) classification problems. It can be argued that multiple binary models are more advantageous than a single multiclass model in that they provide better insight into the interrelationships. (...) Resampling is another technique used to handle the multiclass classification problem. Resampling involves oversampling less-representative classes, undersampling overly-representative classes, or using ensemble methods (e.g., Bootstrap aggregating).</i>" 2) "<i>RNNs can retain a "memory" that is captured in the time-series data. Long short-term memory (LSTM) is a deep learning RNN. (...) a common LSTM unit includes a cell (Ct), an input gate (It), an output gate (Ot), and a forget gate (Ft). The cell remembers values over certain time intervals, and the three gates regulate the flow of information into and out of the cell. The cell trains the model by using back-propagation. (...) The input gate decides what values from the input should be used to modify the memory. For example, a sigmoid function decides what values to let through, and a tanh function assigns weights to the passing values for their levels of importance, ranging from -1 to 1. The forget gate determines what memories the cell can forget. For example, a sigmoid function outputs a number between 0 and 1 for each number in the cell state C(t-1) based on the previous state (ht-1) and the content input (Xt). The output gate yields the output based on the input and the memory of the cell. For example, functioning similar to the input gate, a sigmoid function decides what values to let through. A tanh function gives weights to the passing values for their levels of importance ranging from -1 to 1 and is then multiplied with the output of the sigmoid function.</i>"

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 247 / 550	

	<p>3) "Despite their excellent performance in prediction, machine learning techniques such as ANN and SVM have been long criticized for performing as a black-box solution that cannot be directly used to identify the relationship between outcomes and input variables. (...) One of the methods safety practitioners have used to address this concern is the sensitivity analysis.</p> <p>The sensitivity analysis studies how the uncertainty in the output of a mathematical model can be attributed to different sources of uncertainty in its input. The sensitivity analysis can be used to measure the relationship between the input variables and the output of a trained neural network model. In the process of performing a sensitivity analysis, the neural network learning ability is disabled so that the network weights are not affected. Each input variable of a black-box model (e.g., ANN, SVM) is perturbed by a user-defined amount, with the other variables being fixed at their respective means or medians. The results before and after the perturbation of each input variable are recorded, and the impacts of each input variable on the output are calculated."</p>
Q4 Answer	Please refer to the answers for Question 3 for the results, since the main result of the paper is to present the ML techniques review whose most notable items are summarized in the answer to Question 3.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good reference to quote technicalities of AI techniques. 2) Some interesting information presented in a didactic way. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Little information regarding the safety analysis of AI-based systems. The applications quoted by the authors are more related to predicting accident risks on roadways.

8.145 REFERENCE [566]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose a novel approach to synthesizing neural networks as barrier certificates, which provide safety guarantees for hybrid systems. Candidate networks are trained from a special structure: ReLU neural networks consisting of two hidden layers.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "A barrier certificate is a function of the state that separates reachable states of a system from its unsafe region. It requires all system trajectories starting from some initial states fall into one side of the barrier certificate while the unsafe region residents on the other. As the existence of a barrier certificate proves that the unsafe region is not reachable, the safety verification problem can be transformed into the problem of barrier certificate generation."</p> <p>"Acting as barrier certificates, deep neural networks have the potential to define more complex barrier certificates than the classical polynomials do, as the theorem of universal approximation shows that a feed-forward neural network that comes with a single hidden layer comprising of a finite number of neurons can approximate any continuous functions on compact subsets of R^n with enough precision."</p> <p>"(...) verification of neural network barrier certificate is not an easy task, as there may be a tremendous number of neurons and non-linear activation functions in them. Existing approaches resort to non-linear satisfiability modulo theories (SMT) solvers combined with the piece-wise linear approximation to identify real barrier certificates from candidate networks. As all SMT solvers are not complete when handling non-linear arithmetic, plus the high computational complexity, those methods are prone to fail, which becomes an obstacle to neural network based verification. In the paper, we propose the feedforward neural network of the special structure that consists of two hidden layers and uses the ReLU activation functions as barrier certificates. Such a special structure enables us to transform the problems of verifying barrier certificate conditions into mixed integer linear programming (MILP) and mixed integer quadratically constrained problems (MIQCP) with non-linear terms. Taking full advantage of the recent advance of the optimizer Gurobi 9.0, which explores the entire search space and can provide an optimal objective value of either MILP or MIQCP problems, accompanied with its difference from the global optimal one, verification of the special network can be performed effectively and efficiently."</p> <p>Background on Neural Network Verification: "The problem of neural network verification is NP-hard and</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 248 / 550	

	<p><i>lots of research focuses on it. Existing methods for verifying neural network are based on abstract domain, abstract interpretation, input refinement, interval arithmetic, linear approximations and mixed integer programming.</i> "(...)a network with deep architectures provides better expressive power and are easier to be trained."</p> <p>Basics: "Given a hybrid system, our goal is to synthesize a neural network that satisfies the conditions in Theorem 2, so that it acts as a barrier certificate, ensuring the unsafe region never to be invaded. Here, the process of synthesis consists of two steps. At first, a candidate neural network barrier certificate is derived by training parameters of a special network structure, which uses the sampled data points from the initial state, the unsafe region, the system state space, and the trajectories as well. After that, the network is verified according to the barrier certificate conditions defined in Theorem 2, where the special structure of the network enables the transformation of verification problem into a set of MILP and MIQCP problems." "The input layer contains the same number of neurons as that of the system variables, and each system variable corresponds to one unique neuron of the input layer; The output layer has only one neuron, producing the output of the barrier certificate; There are two and only two hidden layers, each of which can have many neurons; The ReLU function is the only legal activation function." "The design of the special network structure tries to balance the requirement of enough expressive power to approximate complex functions and easy verification." "The key point [to identify real barrier certificates from the candidate neural networks] is to utilize the special structure of the network to encode the verification problem as several optimization problems, and then resort to the optimizer to find the global optimal objective value." It requires "(...) to check the output range of the network with respect to the given input region" and "(...) the derivative of the network on the zero level set of the network."</p>
Q4 Answer	A tool is implemented, and its performance is evaluated over 3 hybrid systems and 8 continuous systems up to 12-dimensional state space. The experimental results show that the method is more scalable and effective than the classical polynomial barrier certificate method and the existing neural network based method. In comparison with traditional methods, the proposed approach excelled in 10 of the 11 simulated examples, at which it was able to provide a barrier certificate.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good background on Neural Network verification, including occasional additional references. 2) Interesting method whose theoretical basis can be considered in future research.

8.146 REFERENCE [569]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present a comparison of Bayesian and Regression approaches for safety analysis by studying their respective advantages and disadvantages.
Q2 Answer	Bayesian networks and regression techniques.
Q3 Answer	The authors collected data related to accidents with elevators in France and analyzed them with Bayesian Networks and regression methods.
Q4 Answer	"The results indicated that the precision of Bayesian network was higher than that of the ordinal regression model. However, regression analysis can also provide understanding of the information hidden in data. The two approaches may suggest different significant explanatory factors/causes, and this always should be taken into consideration."
Q5 Answer	"As a future work we need to improve these preliminarily results taking into account a larger dataset and utilizing Rubin's causal model called the Potential Outcomes Framework, to verify inferences."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) The paper is not related to the safety analysis of AI-based systems, but instead to the Environment, Health and Safety analysis with Bayesian and regression approaches.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 249 / 550	

8.147 REFERENCE [570]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present a systematic review of the relevant research literature in recent years regarding the software V&V processes of Artificial Intelligence in autonomous cars.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, with focus on Machine Learning (i.e., Inductive Learning).
Q3 Answer	<p><i>"The first part of the review addresses certification issues against reference standards, challenges in assessing machine learning, as well as general V&V methodologies. The second part investigates more specific approaches, including simulation environments and mutation testing, corner cases and adversarial examples, fault injection, software safety cages, techniques for cyber-physical systems, and formal methods. Relevant approaches and related tools have been discussed and compared in order to highlight open issues and opportunities."</i></p> <p><i>"This study is also important to define a baseline on which evaluating the potential for technology transfer to other transportation domains, such as railways, where autonomous vehicles can adopt some of the techniques that are being pioneered in the automotive domain due to the huge and growing interest in self-driving cars. This is one of the objectives of the Horizon 2020 research project named RAILS (Roadmaps for AI Integration in the Rail Sector) funded by the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking, a body of the European Union."</i></p> <p>The SLR comprised only references taken from Scopus.</p> <p>The following criteria were considered to include papers within the SLR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studies focusing on V&V of software systems in safe autonomous cars - Studies focusing on V&V of safety-critical software systems in different types of vehicles that is also applicable to autonomous cars <p>The following criteria were considered to exclude papers from the SLR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studies that do not apply to autonomous cars - Studies that do not focus on V&V for safety assessment - Studies that do not focus on software aspects of safety V&V <p>The following questions were answered for the selected papers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the most common requirements in the software V&V of safe autonomous cars? - What are the main challenges in performing software V&V of safe autonomous cars? - What are the open issues and opportunities in software V&V of safe autonomous cars?
Q4 Answer	<p>Main interesting results:</p> <p><i>"One of the limitations of the validation of ML systems is the cost of labeling the data. Labeling is either done by someone or some other unsupervised learning algorithm, both having their own complications. ML systems are sensitive to change: doing a minor change leads to a necessity to re-validate the whole system. When a problem in the training set is identified, it also adds the extra work of collecting more data to validate the system. AVs are likely to encounter many extremely rare cases that were not considered in the initial training set. Every time a new case is detected, the system should be updated and re-validated accordingly."</i></p> <p><i>"Another challenge on the validation of ML is its incomprehensible internal structure for humans. (...) The so-called ``explainable AI" (XAI) methodologies have been defined to cope with those issues, but in general, making ML easy to understand for humans has not currently been achieved. Being unable to predict the behavior of ML, makes it harder to assess its decision-making process and leaves us to use costly brute force techniques. Even if a brute force can be applied given sufficient resources, it only validates the result within the training set and does not show the coverage or accuracy of the training data and how it complies with the safety standards."</i></p> <p>Making a AI-based system rely on a non AI-based module for safety response ("safe monitor").</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 250 / 550	

	<p>"(...) behavior and decisions of Deep Learning (DL) algorithms are sometimes unpredictable, or even wrong. Such corner cases might exist due to issues in the model or training data, for instance, overfitting or underfitting of system model, or bias, or lack of diversity in the training data. Additionally, DL systems can be vulnerable to adversarial attacks that make minimal changes in the input in order to cause, for instance, an image classification algorithm to wrongly classify the traffic sign, leading to a wrong decision that might result in an accident."</p> <p>Fault Injection: "(...) transient faults, due to e.g. electromagnetic interference and cosmic radiation, should be detected. (...) approaches dealing with transient faults are rather immature in the AV domain, and need to be handled in real-time. In order to test and possibly increase the coverage of fault-tolerance, Fault Injection (FI) can be used. (...) Fault injection can be applied at each different phase of the V-model in ISO 26262."</p> <p>Mutation testing: "Mutation testing is an approach used to evaluate the sufficiency of the test cases. The technique involves creating faulty duplicates of the original system, named mutants, by injecting reproducible faults. It allows engineers to have a metric that corresponds to the ratio of identified vs. missed mutations, in order to evaluate the adequacy of test suites. (...) Mutation testing relies on two basic assumptions. One of them is the Competent Programmer Hypothesis, which is an assumption that the programmers develop software that is close to its perfect form. This assumption translates to mutation testing context as follows: mutants are close to real faults, and if the test suite is able to identify the mutants it will also be able to identify the real faults. Another assumption is the Coupling Effect hypothesis which states that large effects of the errors in the software are tightly coupled with small bugs. This assumption suggests that simple mutants are closely related to the real bugs in the software, and if it is possible to detect the mutants, it is also possible to detect critical bugs."</p> <p>Safety Cages / Safety Envelopes: "(...) using safety cages the behavior of the AV can be limited to a safe set of states. (...) The advantage of implementing safety cages is that the way they work is explainable, and conventional verification methods can be applied to them. They also do not require any knowledge about the inner workings of the ML system they are integrated with. (...) identified safety cage violations can further be used to train and improve the network."</p> <p>Main open challenges:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Explainability of AI to humans; 2) How to verify AI-based systems in order to improve coverage of adversarial examples and avoid adversarial attacks during operation; 3) How to argue that input data is enough for the model to be acceptable and ensure no overfitting occurs; 4) Formal methods weak scalability to complex models. They also require reliable sensors and actuators for their arguments to be supported, as well as a credible environmental model. --> possible solution: using probabilistic explainable models based on Bayesian Networks for online safety assessment. 5) Increase research on fault injection, simulation-based V&V and safety cages, including their possibility to find corner cases / adversarial attacks and being able to improve the AI-based models.
Q5 Answer	See "main open challenges" on the answer to Question 4.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The Systematic Literature Review states that, although focus is given to autonomous cars, the authors expect the study to serve as reference to the railway area as well, including this as one of the objectives of the European Union RAILS project. 2) Many of the authors' findings converge to the ones of the SLR performed during the DSc.. Several references used by the authors have also been within the DSc. SLR. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The SLR has a strict focus on autonomous vehicles. The DSc. SLR expands on other application areas and themes of interest (e.g. adaptation of systems), aiming towards the development of a general-purpose safety analysis method for AI-based systems.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 251 / 550	

8.148 REFERENCE [574]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To propose a Lyapunov-based method to estimate so-called Regions of Safety in order to enable analyzing low-level uncertainty models to interface with state-of-the-art run-time safety assessment methods and thereby facilitate self-adaptiveness and guaranteed safety of cooperative systems.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning and supervised learning with neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: <i>"The open architecture of systems offering such cooperative functionalities, however, contradicts current strategies for maintaining safety (e.g. ISO 262626 [3], IEC 61508 [4]). These expect knowledge about the failure characteristics of all components of a system and their composition at design time."</i></p> <p><i>"To maintain the safety of cooperative systems nonetheless, it has been proposed to share uncertainty models along with the data to facilitate a run-time safety assessment on the receiving system. This concept raises two central questions.</i></p> <p><i>Uncertainty Models: What meta-data for describing possible uncertainties needs to be shared along with the payload (e.g. sensor observations)?</i></p> <p><i>Safety Assessment: How can a receiving system maintain its safety based on the shared description of uncertainties and adapt to (or reject) new sources of information at run-time?"</i></p> <p><i>"Conditional Safety Certificates (ConSerts), for instance, build upon the idea of contracts to facilitate run-time safety assessment. Given the fulfillment of all safety demands in a contract, a component assures the fulfillment of safety guarantees and enables associated (cooperative) functionalities. Accordingly, Dynamic Safety Contracts (DSC) introduce different variants of contracts with the same cooperative functionality which facilitates the self-adaptiveness of the system."</i></p> <p>Basics: <i>"(...) we base our concept of Regions of Safety (RoS) on stability analysis techniques to provide guarantees that can be combined with run-time safety assessment methods. Although these techniques are traditionally limited to a system's design time, they have been used to maintain safety at run-time in the field of Safe Reinforcement Learning (Safe RL) (...)"</i></p> <p>In model-based Reinforcement Learning, <i>"(...) the need to randomly interact with the real system is reduced by incorporating a proxy model of the system which facilitates safe interactions. This can be either used to ensure safety during planning, e.g. with Model Predictive Control (MPC) or to enforce safety constraints by separating the overall state space into safe and unsafe states. Under a fixed control policy, each state is either labeled as asymptotic stable, that is, the control action chosen by the policy drives the system closer to its equilibrium point, or unstable. The set of stabilizing states encompassing an equilibrium point of a controlled system is a so-called Region of Attraction (RoA). By restricting the exploration process during learning to visit only states within a controller's RoA stability is guaranteed."</i> Due to this, model-based Reinforcement Learning tends to be better than model-free Reinforcement Learning (e.g. Q-Learning) for safety-critical systems.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The approach has been evaluated in the simulated scenario of Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control, in which a leading vehicle shares its position, velocity, and acceleration with a subsequent vehicle. The reinforcement learning policy is learned through a Multi-Layer Perceptron (Neural Network), and the authors take decisions regarding uncertainty shaping (Gaussian) and hyperparameters of the dynamic parameter (bias "c2" of the safe speed defined by a logistic function).</p> <p>The authors are able to verify through simulation that the Region of Safety (RoS) estimated for different uncertainty models contain indeed only safe states and that the proposed method can be applied even with learning-based controllers.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) <i>"(...) future work will focus on increasing the computational performance to facilitate real-time execution and continuous self-adaptiveness. For that, addressing the conservatism of the approach is as important as investigating guidelines for constructing appropriate Lyapunov functions."</i></p> <p>2) <i>"A feasible option to investigate is the combination of Lyapunov functions with Control Barrier Functions (CBF), which focus on safety and the adherence to hard constraints."</i></p> <p>3) <i>"While this work only considered Gaussian noise, the usage of more complex uncertainty models, such as the GFM, should be evaluated to support more realistic scenarios as well."</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 252 / 550	

	<p>4) "Similarly, combining the estimation of RoS with contract-based safety assessment methods will be investigated in future work as well."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting overview on safety and reinforcement learning, with good arguments favoring model-based reinforcement learning over model-free reinforcement learning for safety-critical systems. 2) The proposed model establishes a 'safe envelope' with the safe states that can be reached by the system. 3) Future studies are in line with the state-of-the-art for adaptive systems. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Some decisions taken during the case study were not fully justified by the authors (e.g. why the logistic function with bias "c2" was used to estimate the vehicle safe speed, why the MLP was chosen to learn an optimal policy, how MLPs were tuned to learn a potentially optimal policy, how rewards were defined). 2) Parts of the model are based on learning algorithms, and these were not verified as safe in such a way to ensure that the set of safe states obtained through them is effectively the correct set of system safe states. This has not received further investigation or concern by the authors. 3) The models are very application-dependent, since they require the system dynamics to be encoded.

8.149 REFERENCE [576]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose an online monitor called ReachFlow for fault prevention of waypoint-following tasks for self-driving cars.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: Learning-enabled components have the drawback of handling exceptions. "<i>Autonomous systems are commonly working in a highly uncertain environment where exceptions can hardly be taken into account in the design phase. (...) This paper provides a solution to overcome [this] drawback. We describe an online framework to prevent a given autonomous system from reaching any unsafe state, and apply it to self-driving cars with waypoint following controllers.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Safety verification for the waypoint-following in a closed-loop system can be interpreted sequentially using reachability. We try to inspect whether the system is able to stay in the safe region for a finite amount of time within a given time horizon.</i>" "<i>(...) we deal with a closed-loop control system such that the controller is given by a black box and the plant is defined by a nonlinear Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE).</i>"</p> <p>Basics: ReachFlow "<i>(...) mainly consists of two components: (a) an online verification tool which conservatively checks the safety of the system behavior in the near future, and (b) a fallback controller which steers the system back to a desired state when the system is potentially unsafe.</i>" "<i>(...) we propose to use an online framework which performs an auxiliary control for the system under exceptions. That is, the framework monitors the current state of the system and predicts the system behavior in the near future. If a potential unsafe state is detected, then the fallback controller will take over the system control and steer the system back to a desired state. In our application, when a potential large deviation is detected, the fallback controller will steer the car back to a reference state which is close to the planned path, and then give the control back to the original controller.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>(...) our online framework uses a formal verifier to conservatively estimate the safety of the system behavior in the near future, so that it essentially solves a bounded model checking problem on a nonlinear system online but only for a small number of steps.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The implementation of ReachFlow is performed in a self-driving racing car governed by a reinforcement learning-based controller by considering two different physical models for the vehicle: a simplified kinematics bicycle model and a more advanced bicycle modeling considering a linear tire model.</p> <p>"<i>General reinforcement learning uses a trial-and-error learning strategy for optimal control policy search. In this work, we use Constrained Policy Optimization (CPO), a local policy search method, to find the optimal policy that satisfies all constraints. An iterative simulation environment is set up for policy training.</i>"</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 253 / 550	

	<p><i>The learned policy is stored and transferred to the real RC car.</i>" Three controlling scenarios are then considered: straight-line, circle and rounded square.</p> <p>We demonstrate the effectiveness by rigorously verifying a safe waypoint-following control and providing a fallback control for an unsafe situation in which a large deviation from the planned path is predicted." "In the experiment, we demonstrate that using SUE-GP and a dynamical vehicle model, 99.99% assurance can be obtained to enclosure all future trajectories. By increasing the variance or increasing the initial position uncertainty, we can achieve 100% assurance. Unsafe verification and fallback control are also demonstrated."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcoming: "(...) <i>it is observed that due to the gap between simulation and the real world, e.g., sensor and actuator delays, control frequency, and other variables, we are not able to ensure the perfection of the policy from the simulation. The demanding safety verification in this work will verify the control policy before the execution.</i>"</p> <p>Future research: "<i>Our assumption in this work is that the fallback controller is safe. It would be our future work to further study an optimal controller without extra verification.</i>", i.e., "<i>Future work will include studying a sophisticated fallback controller.</i>"</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The results of the authors' case study are not fully convincing, since very high accuracies were obtained and no other aspects regarding the model were discussed (e.g. other performance indexes, how the safety areas have been defined with the fallback controller, etc.).</p> <p>2) The authors believe that they can reach a 100% safe controller. This is not physically possible at all.</p>

8.150 REFERENCE [577]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To propose a Hamilton-Jacobi reachability theory-based robot autonomy for both the robot controller and the robot planner so that both have the same interpretation of safety. To achieve this, HJ reachability theory is used at the planning level to provide the robot planner with the foresight to avoid entering regions with possible inevitable collision and at the controller level to maintain safety without unduly impacting planner performance.
Q2 Answer	Model-based optimization within a multi-agent system.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "<i>Decision-making and control for robots is typically stratified into levels (...).The high-level planner, informed by representative yet simplified dynamics of a robot and its environment, is designed to be far-sighted and selects plans that optimize performance metrics, while the low-level controller, running at a much higher frequency than the planner, tends to be more short-sighted and respects more accurate models of the robot's dynamics and control constraints in order to implement the controls necessary to follow the desired plan. (...) the planner and controller may each devise their own safety protocols, or even assume the other bears the full responsibility, but when combined together, they may not necessarily complement each other in achieving the shared goal of ensuring safety for the system.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "(...) <i>we design a safe complementary planning and control stack that provides safety assurance for a robot without unduly impacting planner performance. We leverage Hamilton-Jacobi (HJ) reachability theory to provide the same representation of safety for both the planner and safety controller. (...) Further, in a multi-agent setting, a robot may be in conflict as to which agent to avoid if there is a danger of colliding with multiple agents. We use HJ reachability theory to optimally select safe controls that reason about collision avoidance with all agents threatening the robot's safety in a minimally interventional way.</i>"</p> <p>"(...) <i>we provide high-level planners that optimize an objective function with the foresight to avoid regions of possible inevitable collision by incorporating a term into the objective function derived from reachability theory. (...) when the system is near safety violation, we propose a multi-agent safety-preserving controller that is minimally interventional—the controller optimizes for performance while treating safety as a constraint.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	" <i>We demonstrate the benefits of our proposed approach in a multi-agent highway scenario where a robot car is rewarded to navigate through traffic as fast as possible, and we show that our approach provides strong safety assurances yet achieves the highest performance compared to other safety controllers.</i> "

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 254 / 550	

	<p>"Our experiments are conducted in a highway simulation environment (...). The robot car is tasked to drive through traffic as fast as possible while avoiding collision. The other cars on the road interact with each other using the Intelligent Driver Model (IDM) and minimizing-overall-braking-induced-by-lane change (MOBIL) model for longitudinal and lateral control, respectively.(...)The high level planner runs at 1 Hz while the low level controller runs at 50 Hz."</p> <p>"(...) our planner is reward-based and safety is promoted via the objective function. As such, there will be times where the robot will end up in an unsafe state, necessitating the use of a safety controller." Hyperparameters (e.g. discount factors, rewards and target speeds for safe and unsafe movements) are selected for the experiment, and the reward function "(...) is designed to encourage the robot to stay in the left most lane, maintain high speed, and avoid collision states." The threshold for the Time to Collision as a safety metric has also been selected in an arbitrary way.</p> <p>"Although the RSS (Responsibility-Sensitive Safety) controllers with HJOP (Hamilton-Jacobi Optimistic Planning) provides higher safety metrics, the diminishing return nature of TTC (Time-to-Collision) indicates that our proposed method HJOP+SPC (multi-agent HJI controller) is in the ideal region - it is above the TTC = 3 line, and furthest to the right", allowing the vehicle to drive faster while retaining safety.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"We propose three future research directions; the first would be to extend the idea of using a HJI value function as part of the objective function beyond planning algorithms, such as for trajectory optimization, or as a feature in inverse reinforcement learning. The second would entail exploring different ways to define the target set (i.e., $V(0;x)$) when computing the value function, and understanding how it affects the safety-performance trade-off. The third is to design smarter priority assignment, such as through chance constraints, when safety is nearly violated by multiple agents." "Instead of prioritizing all agents equally, future work can be directed at assigning priority to which agent to avoid. For example, weighing each safety constraint based each agent's likelihood of following an adversarial policy."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting insight on the shared responsibilities of system elements within a multi-agent system (there is a high-level planner whose objective function is designed to incorporate safety and avoid unsafe states, and a low-level controller which, together with the high-level planner, acts within a multi-agent system to avoid unsafe scenarios when the system is in a 'near-safety-violation' state which could have not been avoided prior to this point).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Several model hyperparameters (e.g. discount rates, rewards), as well as the safety metric (time to collision) have been arbitrarily selected by the authors without further justification.</p> <p>2) The models are very application-dependent, since they require the system dynamics to be encoded.</p>

8.151 REFERENCE [578]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To propose a semidefinite programming (SDP) framework to address the problem of certifying safety of neural networks against uncertainties and adversarial attacks for feedforward neural networks with general activation functions and input uncertainty sets. This involves bounding the output of neural networks when their input changes within a bounded set.
Q2 Answer	Feedforward neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "(...) neural networks are highly vulnerable to attacks, or more generally, uncertainty in their input. (...) Input perturbations can be either of an adversarial nature, or they could merely occur due to compression, resizing, and cropping. These drawbacks limit the adoption of neural networks in safety-critical applications (...)."</p> <p>"(...) there has been an increasing effort in developing tools to measure or improve the robustness of neural networks. Many results focus on specific adversarial attacks and attempt to harden the network. (...) Safety-critical applications require provable robustness against any bounded variations in the input data. As a result, many tools have recently been used, adapted, or developed for this purpose, such as mixed-integer linear programming, convex relaxations and duality theory, Satisfiability Modulo Theory (SMT), dynamical systems, Abstract Interpretation, interval-based methods. All these works aim at bounding the worst-case value of a performance measure when their input is perturbed within a specified range."</p> <p>Basics: "(...) we develop a novel framework based on semidefinite programming (SDP) for safety</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 255 / 550	

	<p>verification and robustness analysis of neural networks against norm-bounded perturbations in their input. Our main idea is to abstract nonlinear activation functions of neural networks by the constraints they impose on the pre- and post- activation values. In particular, we describe various properties of activation functions using Quadratic Constraints (QCs), such as bounded slope, bounded values, monotonicity, and repetition across layers. Using this abstraction, any property (e.g., safety or robustness) that we can guarantee for the abstracted network will automatically be satisfied by the original network as well. The quadratic form of these constraints allows us to formulate the verification problem as an SDP feasibility problem. (...) Our framework has the following notable features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We use various forms of QCs to abstract any type of activation function. - Our method can capture the cross-coupling between neurons across different layers, thereby reducing conservatism. This feature, which hinges on the assumption that the same activation function is used throughout the entire network (repetition across layers), becomes particularly effective for deep networks. - We can control the trade-off between computational complexity and conservatism by systematically including or excluding different types of QCs." <p>"(...) the proposed framework (input-output characterization of neural networks via quadratic constraints) can be adapted to other problems such as sensitivity analysis of neural networks to input perturbations, output reachable set estimation, probabilistic verification, bounding the Lipschitz constant of neural networks, and closed-loop stability analysis."</p> <p>Notes on performance and safety: "The performance of certification algorithms for neural networks can be measured along three axes. The first axis is the tightness of the certification bounds; the second axis is the computational complexity, and, the third axis is applicability across various models (e.g. different activation functions). These axes conflict. (...) On the one hand, formal verification techniques such as Satisfiability Modulo (SMT) solvers, or integer programming approaches rely on combinatorial optimization to provide tight certification bounds for piecewise linear networks, whose complexity scales exponentially with the size of the network in the worst-case. (...) On the other hand, certification algorithms based on continuous optimization are more scalable but less accurate."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"For all experiments, we used ReLU activation functions and did Interval Bound Propagation as a presolve step to determine functions the element-wise bounds on the activation."</p> <p>First, the authors present considerations regarding the proposed model complexity with regard to the number of input variables, activation functions (worst case with quadratic complexity) and safety specification set (worst case with quadratic complexity).</p> <p>Afterwards, the authors present the results of synthetic (numeric) examples to both assess the impacts of the number of hidden layers, nonlinearities on boundaries tightness and compare the proposed model with other approaches. The proposed approach scales better with deeper networks and provides tighter safety limits as the network becomes deeper.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"First, a notable advantage of the proposed SDP compared to other convex relaxations is the relative tightness of the bounds. In particular, coupling all pairs of neurons in the network (repeated nonlinearities) can considerably reduce conservatism. However, coupling all neurons is not feasible for even medium-sized networks as the number of decision variables would scale quadratically with the number of neurons. Nevertheless, our numerical experiments show that most of these pair-wise couplings of neurons are redundant and do not tighten the bounds. It would be interesting to develop a method that can decide a priori that coupling which pairs of neurons would tighten the relaxation."</p> <p>"Second, one of the drawbacks of SDPs is their limited scalability in general. Exploiting the structure of the problem (e.g. sparsity patterns induced by the network structure) to reduce the computational complexity would be an important future direction."</p> <p>"Third, we have only considered fully-connected networks in this paper. It would be interesting to extend the results to other architectures."</p> <p>"Finally, incorporating the proposed framework in training neural networks with desired robustness properties would be another important future direction."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Excellent contextualization of neural network safety verification, including current state of the art, contributions, challenges and trade-off between computation time and result precision. 2) Very rigid mathematical demonstration of the method soundness.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 256 / 550	

3) Good proposals for future work.

8.152 REFERENCE [579]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a novel model checking approach to finite-time safety verification of black-box continuous-time dynamical systems within the framework of probably approximately correct (PAC) learning.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general (probably approximately correct = machine learning).
Q3 Answer	Basics: <i>"Based on the error probability and confidence level, our approach provides statistically formal guarantees that the time-evolving trajectories of the black-box dynamical system over finite-time horizons fall within the range of the learned model plus a bounded interval, contributing to insights on the reachability of the black-box system and thus on the satisfiability of its safety requirements. The learned model together with the bounded interval is obtained by scenario optimization, which boils down to a linear programming problem."</i> <i>"This framework is useful in those situations where the system (1) is able to tolerate the exposure to a deteriorating agent for a limited amount of time."</i>
Q4 Answer	The authors present three hypothetical application examples and three final applications: one on a nine-dimensional biological system, another one on a hypothetical multidimensional system and a final one on a two-dimensional continuous system. The model's hyperparameters (error probability and confidence interval) are arbitrarily chosen (e.g. confidence interval no higher than 80%), and the authors show that the model scales well with several dimensions and with continuous systems, and highlight that the system safety is obtained.
Q5 Answer	<i>"In the future, we would extend our method to safety verification of black-box systems, whose internal mechanisms are described by hybrid dynamical systems that exhibit both continuous and discrete dynamic behavior. Also, we would like to extend our method for the safety verification of black-box systems with noise measurements and inputs."</i>
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good mathematical background to support the research. Weakness: 1) The model requires perfect sensor information based on the assumption <i>"The system (1) runs well, including the onboard sensors, and thus it can provide us any family of finite datum we need. Also, the provided datum is free of noise."</i> . Safety assurance of sensors shall be ensured by additional means. This restriction has been clearly identified for future work, though. 2) The models are very application-dependent, since they require the system dynamics to be encoded.

8.153 REFERENCE [582]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To propose an intelligent hazard-risk prediction model based on a deep recurrent neural network for a new communication-mode CBTC system.
Q2 Answer	Deep neural networks configured as long-short-term memory.
Q3 Answer	Basics: <i>"1) We put forward a train-to-train communication CBTC system architecture and analyze the Movement Authority (MA) function model. In this paper, we redistribute the system key functions and reduce the track-side equipment for the new system, which greatly improves the utilization rate of the system. We also analyze the new information flow for MA calculation in the system.</i> <i>2) We propose an intelligent hazard-risk predictive model for our train-to-train communication CBTC system. The predictive model is implemented by a deep recurrent neural network (RNN) called a long-short-term memory (LSTM) network, which takes into account some pivotal system parameters. Specifically, the LSTM network is trained to predict the occurrence probability of a hazard from datasets and classify them. The model's classification results can provide guidance for the operation of urban rail transit systems.</i> <i>3) We design a risk prediction feature selection method and perform MA calculation failure estimation based on statistical model checking (SMC). By building the system function model and describing a safety property, we use simulation-based techniques to solve the probability of MA calculation failure."</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 257 / 550	

	<p>"Two hidden layers used LSTM network and softmax classifier as the output layer." "(...) we use a deep LSTM network architecture, where the model has one input layer, one output layer, and two LSTM layers as a hidden layer, each with 256 LSTM units, and a learning rate of 0.07. Such a network architecture is based on much empirical research. Too many or too few hidden layers would make the fitting degree less than optimal, and the proper number of layers and units can achieve the best results. At the same time, for each hidden layer, we set the dropout rate to 0.2 (...). To prevent the network model from overfitting, some units do not work with a certain probability during the training process."</p> <p>The LSTM provides as outputs the probabilities of no collision risk, weak collision risk and strong collision risk. "An occurrence probability of a severe collision greater than 0.3 indicates that a serious collision will occur."</p> <p>Limitation: "(...) we only consider the hazard of collision between two trains, especially the rear-end collision, whose main influencing factors are train separation, traffic direction, and route interlocking."</p> <p>Brief information on T2T-CBTC: "A T2T-CBTC system eliminates ZC and CBI equipment, integrates their functions into VOBC, and adds a vital system database (VSDB) to store train and track information. For each subsystem, main changes are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For station system, VSDB is added, storing information such as track and train data. - For trackside system, the ZC and CBI have been canceled, and the track system controller (TSC) has been added to retain some functions of ZC, which only has the basic functions of monitoring train operation and storing information of forwarding train data. - For onboard system, the importance and intelligence of it have been promoted. Functions include onboard movement authority (OBMA), onboard computer interlocking (OBCI), and onboard management controller (OBMC). By itself, VOBC accomplishes the detection of obstacles in front, the query of route information, the collaborative completion of MA calculation, and realizes the train as the core design principle."
Q4 Answer	<p>"In this experiment, we have three datasets, which are training, validation, and test datasets. These datasets respectively had 12825, 1425, and 750 samples." "We used a combination of collection and simulation to generate a dataset."</p> <p>"We explored the impact of different hyper-parameter choices on model performance. We focused on tuning two important hyper-parameters: the number of units in hidden layer and the L2 regularization parameter lambda. To do so, we fixed other parameter and varied two hyper-parameters. (...) As can be seen, for hidden layer size, the setting where the number of units size is 256+128 has the best result. Each of evaluation criteria is the highest in 256+128 units size, and the training time is acceptable. For L2 regularization parameter, the setting where it equals 0.001 has the highest value of recall and F1-score in c2 and c3, which means this setting effectively avoids the impact of the unbalanced dataset."</p> <p>"In our experiment, 750 test samples from the dataset were used to estimate the hazard-risk prediction performance of our model. The sample size of c1, c2 and c3 are 535, 157 and 58 respectively. The test dataset was divided into 3 classes of state, of which 732 samples were identified successfully." "This model consistently outperforms the deep belief network (DBN) trained in Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1-score for the hazard-risk prediction problem. Specifically, the mean accuracy is 97.2% and mean F1-score is 93.9% in overall performance of model. The improvements of our model against DBN model are 8.2% for Precision, 7% for Recall and 8% for F1-score."</p> <p>"(...) c3's [strong collision] precision is only around 0.872, probably because samples of other classes, like c1, are predicted to be of c3, which leads to a larger denominator in precision calculation. This problem can often be resolved through subsequent manual reviews. For recall, c2 and c3 has good result, reaching around 0.86. It means most of the c2 and c3 samples could be identified and the model did not miss the dangerous samples. Based on these results, our model is effective for this problem, which means the deep RNNs are suited for the forecast classification problem of hazard risk in the T2T-CBTC system."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"In future work, more features and types of hazards will be taken into account, which will make the prediction function of our model more comprehensive. Some feature-extraction methods will be used to improve the model's accuracy."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting CBTC architecture adapted to train-to-train communication. 2) Good overview on Long-Short-Term Memory with Deep Neural Networks. 3) Clear explanation of the proposed approach and the experimental results.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 258 / 550	

	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors did not present sufficient information regarding some hyperparameters (e.g. number of hidden layers = 2, activation function = softmax for the output layer, learning rate of 0.07, dropout rate of 0.2), once they solely relied in an 'empirical research' justification or, in the case of the dropout rate, on a study from other authors who claim to avoid overfitting by proper dropout rate adjustment. The number of neurons in each hidden layer and the regularization parameter were fully justified; nevertheless, the authors did not adopt best practices when changing them (e.g. by means of k-fold validation).</p> <p>2) The study did not cover evidence to ensure that the proposed risk evaluation system is indeed safe.</p> <p>3) The authors only considered rear-end collision as the hazardous scenario on train traffic. Other types of collision, as well as derailment, were not taken into account by the authors.</p>
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8.154 REFERENCE [586]

Q1 Answer	To address the reachable set estimation and safety verification problems for dynamical systems embedded with neural network components serving as feedback controllers by abstracting a closed-loop system with a continuous-time sampled-data system under the control of a neural network controller.
Q2 Answer	Feedforward neural networks / multilayer perceptron.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "(...) <i>due to the vulnerability neural networks against adversarial disturbances/attacks and the black-box nature of neural networks, such controllers with a neural network structure, in essence, are only restricted to the control applications with the lowest levels of requirements of safety as there is a short of effective methods to compute the output reachable set of neural networks and further assure the safety of underlying closed-loop systems. (...) Furthermore, with advanced adversarial machine learning (ML) techniques developed recently, such safety matters for safety-critical control systems with neural network controllers only become even much worse.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: The reachability analysis of "(...) <i>multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) with general activation functions is performed in the framework of interval arithmetic. Then, in combination with reachability methods developed for various dynamical system classes modeled by ordinary differential equations, a recursive algorithm is developed for over-approximating the reachable set of the closed-loop system.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>This article focuses on improving a simulation-based approach (...) for the output set over-approximation of feedforward neural networks with general activation functions. A novel adaptive simulation-guided method will be developed and further integrated for safety verification of closed-loop systems with neural network controllers. In this article, we develop a novel simulation-guided approach to perform the output reachable set estimation of feedforward neural networks with general activation functions. The algorithm is formulated in the framework of interval arithmetic and under the guidance of a finite number of simulations.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>We also extend our reachable set estimation result for safety verification of neural network control systems, in which plants are modeled by ODEs. We develop an algorithm to compute the reachable set of a neural network control system modeled by sampled-data systems. Based on the reachable set estimation, a safety verification algorithm is developed to provide formal safe assurance for neural network control systems.</i>"</p> <p>In order to compute an over-approximation of the reachable set of a neural network, the recursive algorithm whose steps are detailed as follows is proposed: general steps can be illustrated as below: "1) <i>Reachable Set Estimation of Neural Network Controller: Compute the output reachable set estimation for the neural network controller 1 at each beginning sampling instant t_k, by which an over-approximation of the output set is obtained [by successive bisections of input intervals].</i> 2) <i>Reachable Set Estimation of Plant: As the output generated by the neural network controller holds its value unchanged in $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$, perform the reachable set estimation for the nonlinear continuous-time system using sophisticated methods or tools;</i> 3) <i>Return for Next Sampling Interval Computation: Return to the first step of reachable set estimation of neural network controller for the next sampling period $[t_{k+1}, t_{k+2}]$.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	1) "As shown by a robotic arm model example, it only needs about 3% computational cost of the method proposed in [212] to obtain the same interval-based reachability analysis result." This case study of the

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 259 / 550	

	<p>robotic arm was performed to assess the performance of the proposed algorithm in comparison with the one of reference [212], since the problem has tight safe boundaries that are known as true prior to the learning process.</p> <p>2) "(...) <i>an adaptive cruise control (ACC) system using a software prototype is proposed to demonstrate our method.</i>" The approach is evaluated "(...) <i>by the safety verification of an ACC system equipped with a neural network controller (...). The ACC system consists of two cars, the ego car with ACC module that has a radar sensor to measure the distance to the lead car which is denoted by d_{rel}, and the relative velocity against the lead car denoted by v_{rel}. There are two system operating modes including speed control and spacing control.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>We expect that the ego car is able to maintain a safe relative distance to the lead car to avoid collision. (...) The time horizon that we want to verify is 5 s after the emergency braking comes into play.</i>" "<i>The tolerance is chosen as $\epsilon = 0.1$ and number of simulations is 100000.</i>" "(...) <i>it can be concluded that the ACC system is safe during the time interval [0, 5] in this safety verification scenario of interest.</i>"</p>
Q5 Answer	" (...) <i>other modeling and reachability analysis approaches for the plant and neural network controllers, as well as broader classes of neural networks, should be considered in the future study.</i> "
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good mathematical background to support the research. Explanations are provided in a very didactic way, easier to follow through than other papers about the same subject.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The case study was presented in a shallow way.</p> <p>2) The models are very application-dependent, since they require the system dynamics to be encoded.</p>

8.155 REFERENCE [587]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To discuss the challenges from the 'unknowns' - the unexpected disturbances from component faults, environmental interference, and malicious attacks, as well as the inherent uncertainties in system inputs, model inaccuracies, and machine learning techniques, as well as propose approaches in addressing them and present some of the initial results.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, but with focus on neural networks for some parts.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "<i>To ensure safe, secure, robust, and efficient operation of these autonomous systems, it is critical to know the unknowns, i.e., to model the various uncertainties mathematically, analyze their impact on system properties, and design mitigation strategies that can either directly accommodate the uncertainties or adapt the system configuration to address them, such as lead the system to a fail-operational or fail-safe mode.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>The proposed approach is based on a cross-layer framework for modeling and mitigating execution uncertainties (e.g., timing violations, soft errors) with weakly-hard paradigm, quantitative and formal methods for ensuring safe and time-predictable application of neural networks in both perception and decision making, and safety-assured adaptation strategies in dynamic environment.</i>"</p> <p>1) Timing Uncertainties: "One major type of uncertainty during the operation of autonomous systems is in the execution of system functions, timing uncertainty i.e., how much time it takes for certain function to complete and whether that meets the deadline."</p> <p>"(...) <i>we advocate to develop systems with a cross-layer paradigm, where deadline misses weakly-hard are allowed in a bounded manner [because] (...) many system components can tolerate a certain degree of timing uncertainties and deadline violations and still satisfy their functional and extra-functional properties such as safety, stability and performance, as long as those violations are bounded and properly managed.</i>"</p> <p>Management involves decisions at system level, application software level and operating system level.</p> <p>Functional level: "(...) <i>we first convert the infinite-time safety problem into a finite one by finding a set satisfying both local safety and inductiveness. Local safety ensures that the system stays in the safe region within K steps, and inductiveness guarantees that the system will go back to the initial set after K steps. Thus the set that satisfies both local safety and inductiveness is theoretically guaranteed to be a safe initial set. To make estimating such a set tractable, we make two assumptions – exponential stability of the system</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 260 / 550	

without deadline misses and Lipschitz continuity of system dynamics – to help bound the system behavior under different situations. Then we can abstract the problem as a one-dimensional problem and use linear programming (LP) to obtain a certified safe initial set."

Software level: "(...) the key issue is to analyze the weakly-hard behavior of software implementations for system functionalities based on schedulability analysis (...) and then evaluate whether such weakly-hard behavior can meet the requirements on functional properties."

OS Support:

a) Scheduling: "(...) high analysis complexity, making them difficult to use at runtime for online admission control in adaptive systems. Moreover, existing scheduling policies cannot take full advantage of the flexibility allowed by weakly-hard constraints." "(...) we proposed job-class-level scheduling, which significantly improves the scheduling efficiency and flexibility of weakly-hard real-time tasks. The key to this work is in the classification of jobs of each task, called job-classes, and the assignment of priority to each class of jobs. (...) This approach also enables decomposing the complex weakly-hard schedulability problem into two sub-problems that are easier to solve: (i) analysis of the worst case response time for individual job-classes, and (ii) finding all possible scheduling patterns, which can be modeled as a reachability tree."

b) Deadline miss handling: "(...) we classified possible deadline handling schemes into four categories: (1) job abort terminates a job immediately when the job misses its deadline, (2) delayed completion allows a deadline-missed job to continue to run until it completes, (3) job pre-skip determines whether to execute a job or not at its release time, based on available slack time or predetermined patterns, and (4) job post-skip allows a deadline-missed job to continue over the period but skips the next job.

c) Multi-core support: "(...) we presented a chain-based scheduler for multi-core platforms, which improves end-to-end latency by taking advantage of permissible deadline misses of intermediate tasks. Lastly, shared memory resources, such as caches, memory buses, and DRAM banks, are critical sources of timing unpredictability in recent multi-core platforms.

2) Neural Networks Uncertainties:

a) Timing issues: "(...) limited attention has been given to mitigating the timing uncertainties of executing multiple DNNs (...)", so that "(...) response time of those tasks may become unpredictably long in the worst case while leaving system resources underutilized." "To address those limitations, we developed DART, a real-time DNN framework that offers deterministic and bounded response time to real-time DNN inference tasks and concurrent execution of various types of DNN model on heterogeneous multi-core and GPU-integrated platforms."

b) Adversarial Attacks: "As the output of DNNs is determined by input data, trained weights, and intermediate results stored in memory, adversarial fault data injection attacks such as physical laser beam and row hammer attacks can easily manipulate these parameters and have DNNs to generate different output."

"Recently, much work has focused on the implications of external disturbances to the outputs of DNNs and tried to guide protection strategies. TensorFI, BinFI, and Ares are fault injection tools that analyze DNN models and identify critical bits, and they are useful not only to assess the impact of soft errors but also to identify weaknesses. However, those studies does not provide a concrete protection mechanism for a variety of fault injection attacks. There are also studies on improving the privacy of DNN inference by executing the entire DNN model inside Intel SGX enclaves, but due to the performance limitations of SGX, those approaches are not suitable for real-time applications."

c) Bounding outputs: "(...) output range analysis provides the certified bound of a neural network with a given input space, which theoretically evaluates the robustness of a neural network. (...) Due to the highly nonlinearity of neural networks, it is generally difficult to compute the exact [output] range. In most cases, we use an overapproximation of this output range."

d) Safe Learning: "(...) safe learning, i.e., the additional consideration safe of safety requirements during training or deployment of machine-learning components, has garnered attention from multiple research communities. From a system's point of view, a well-known approach to ensure safety at runtime is the Simplex architecture (see e.g. [51]). In this architecture, a safety controller is used to ensure stabilization of the physical system in a domain of known the system state space, in addition to a baseline controller and an advanced controller. (...) Frequent and intermittent switching between the safety controller and the neural controller, however, can lead to undesirable behavior and reduced performance. (...) to reduce such control switching by the neural controller, i.e., making it repairing safe in states that would have required the safety controller to intervene, by using control actions generated by the safety controller at runtime."

Q4
Answer

1) Timeliness on DNNs: "Our experimental results indicate that DART significantly outperforms existing frameworks, by up to 98.5% shorter worst-case response time for real-time tasks while simultaneously achieving up to 17.9% higher throughput for best-effort tasks."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 261 / 550	

	<p>2) Bounded outputs of DNNs: "(...)we propose a layer-wise refinement method that bridges propagation-based methods with mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) by using sliding windows. Specifically, we use a convex polygonal relaxation (over-approximation) of the activation functions to cope with the nonlinearity. This allows us to encode the relaxed problem into a mixed integer linear program (MILP), and control the tightness of the relaxation by adjusting the number of segments in the polygon. Starting with a segment number of 1 for each neuron, which coincides with a linear programming (LP) relaxation, our approach heuristically selects neurons layer by layer to iteratively refine this relaxation. To tackle the increase of the number of integer variables with tighter refinement we bridge the propagation-based method and the programming based method by dividing and sliding the layer-wise constraints: given a length of sliding window "s", for the neuron in layer "l", we only encode the constraints of the layers between (l-s" and "l". With these methods, we can effectively manage the size of MILP and handle deep networks."</p> <p>3) Safe Learning: Several studies by the authors are briefly presented and discussed.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>1) Shared resources on software: To address shared memory resources for multi-core platforms.</p> <p>2) Timeliness on DNNs: "There are several research directions that can be built upon DART. First, distributed IoT devices can be modeled as nodes of the DART pipeline to offload workloads and mitigate uncertainties. Second, sophisticated real-time GPU schemes can be applied for better resource utilization and other types of hardware accelerators, such as FPGAs, can be co-used for larger DNNs. Third, shared memory resources and their timing interference are worth investigating to minimize timing uncertainties and provide better performance isolation between real-time and best-effort DNNs."</p> <p>3) Adversarial fault injection on DNNs: "Our on-going work leverages secure SGX enclaves but protects only the critical part of real-time DNN tasks which are vulnerable to potential fault injection attacks. In order to choose the right set of layers for protection while satisfying real-time requirements, we are developing a dynamic-programming based approach to find a layer protection configuration for each task based on layer-wise DNN time and SDC (Silent Data Corruption) profiling mechanisms."</p> <p>4) Reachability Analysis and Bounding of Neural Networks: "(...) we propose a new reachability analysis approach, ReachNN, to verify NNCSs (Neural Network Controlled Systems) via Bernstein polynomial approximation. Specifically, given an input state space, ReachNN constructs an error-bounded approximation based on Bernstein polynomial for the neural-network controller and casts the NNCS into a tractable closed-loop system. This allows us to verify properties of the NNCS's reachable space by using existing reachability tools and handle general neural networks. One advantage of using a Bernstein polynomial-based approximation is that it allows us to establish a bound on the approximation error based on the Lipschitz constant of the neural network."</p> <p>5) Safe Learning: "Our ongoing work extends the idea of safety-assured adaptation to a cross-layer framework. We consider architecture platforms where the software implementations of multiple functions are scheduled to share computation and communication resources. During runtime adaptation, resources may be re-allocated from certain tasks to other tasks that are more in need at the time. The key is to ensure that under such adaptation, functions meet their functional layer requirements such as safety, stability, and performance; their implementations and on the architecture layer satisfy constraints on schedulability, resource usage, energy consumption, etc.. We address such adaptation by formulating it as a multi-objective optimization problem with constraints on safety, schedulability, and other functional and architectural constraints."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The paper provides a very detailed overview of the 'unknowns' related to Artificial Intelligent, focusing on Neural Networks. Even though some of the issues are well documented in other papers, some insight on new information is presented within the paper together with a detailed overview of potential open topics for future research.</p>

8.156 REFERENCE [588]

Q-Index	1
Q1	To present preliminary evaluation results for runtime monitor technologies for learning-enabled systems.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 262 / 550	

Answer	
Q2 Answer	Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "(...) <i>the data-driven nature and apparent unpredictability of AI and ML systems raise big challenges for certification and formal safety assurance required for safety-critical systems.</i>"</p> <p>The authors "(...) <i>proposed two challenge problems related to autonomous ground operations in civil airports: center line tracking, and object detection & classification (ODC). Deep Neural Networks have been used for prediction of cross track errors (CTE) and ODC from camera videos/images. Researcher runtime assurance technologies, particularly runtime monitors, were integrated in our airplane simulation platform and Real Experimental Platform (REP) (...).</i>" "Two teams (Team A and B) worked on center line tracking challenge, based on the hardware-in-the-loop simulation platform. And one team (Team C) worked on ODC challenge, running on the REP. Two evaluation methods were adopted: qualitative and quantitative assessments. The first evaluated the observed behavior of the aircraft during simulation or testing. The quantitative evaluation performed a statistical analysis of data collected during the test runs. Quantitative evaluation metrics mainly included confusion metrics (e.g., false positive rate and false negative rate) and minimum safety distance. These metrics are simple but effective and allow all the software, system and safety engineers and stakeholders to have a common understanding of the system."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) <i>the demonstrated assurance technologies showed significant promise in addressing the assurance shortfall currently facing learning enabled cyber physical systems, and the evaluation approach defined here provides a solid starting point for evaluations of the maturing assurance technologies in the future phases of the DARPA Assured Autonomy project.</i>"</p> <p>1) Center Line Tracking remarks: "(...) <i>there were only three potential safety violations observed in the runs using the monitors. One occurred in one of the successful Team A Charlie scenarios where the aircraft failed to stop on the runway after reaching the end of the runway. Though technically a violation, behavior beyond the runway threshold was really out of scope for the scenario. The second occurred in a Team A Delta scenario where the monitor triggered when it should have, but the aircraft stopped with the nose wheel on the runway edge, and the main gear off the runway edge. We believe this was due to the simulated braking performance being in the tail of the distribution used by the monitor. Finally, in a Team B Delta scenario, the monitor signaled the aircraft to halt, but by the time the aircraft stopped, the LEC had acquired the right runway edge marking as the centerline and was following that (and so was off the runway edge). This was due to emergent behavior of the system resulting from differing interpretations of the aircraft behavior. Team B had assumed that the slow and halt commands were latching, whereas the aircraft considered them as distinct events. Accordingly, each time the monitor reported an acceptable configuration, the aircraft essentially gained two seconds at full speed before the monitor sent a new slow or halt command that would be acted on by the aircraft. This emergent behavior was in general beneficial, since it permitted the successful completion of more scenarios, but the lack of a principled approach to going from halt to slow, or slow to normal speed, resulted in a safety violation in the one scenario.</i>"</p> <p>"(...) <i>false alarms leading to slow commands occurred at a rate of 2.1%, with a false negative rate of 4.9%. For the halt command, the false alarms rate is 0.8%, and the false negative rate is 5.7%.</i>"</p> <p>2) Obstacle collision remarks: "(...) <i>no violation of the 6-meter-safety-distance requirement was found. From all test runs, the minimum distance between REP and the obstacle was 9.76 meters by GPS measure. When analyzing the results we observed that the LEC had frequent short intervals where it failed to detect the obstacle.</i>"</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "<i>What minor safety risks that appeared were largely due to the simulation models' fidelity. (...) This conservatism also led to a relatively large number of false alarms with a non-trivial impact on system performance.</i>"</p> <p>No suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Worth monitoring the DARPA Assured Autonomy program, which "(...) <i>is developing mathematically verifiable assurance technologies in the following areas: design time assurance; runtime assurance; and dynamic assurance. The program also includes a platform integration and evaluation component.</i>"</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No clear consideration on the safety analysis of the DNN models that were created by the authors. The research concentrated on showing that the models operate in a safe way only.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 263 / 550	

2) The DNN models are not explored in sufficient detail to understand their contribution to the safety-critical functions.

8.157 REFERENCE [596]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present the adaptive stress testing (AST) framework for finding the most likely path to a failure event in simulation, as well as an extension called differential adaptive stress testing (DAST), which can find failures that occur in one system but not in another.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning (based on Markov decision processes).
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "(...) <i>safety validation is not only concerned about whether a failure can occur, but also discovering which failures are most likely to occur.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Falsification does not exhaustively cover the space as in verification, but instead uses search and optimization techniques to find failures. As a result, falsification methods can scale to much larger systems, but generally cannot prove the absence of failures.</i>" "Existing falsification algorithms aim to find the failure example with the lowest robustness. This article aims to find the most likely failure example given a probabilistic disturbance model. A second difference is that we introduce an abstraction and learning algorithm in this article that it can be applied to (non-Markovian) systems with hidden states and partially unknown disturbance distributions."</p> <p>Justification: "This type of differential analysis is useful in applications such as regression testing, where we are concerned with finding areas of relative weakness compared to a baseline."</p> <p>Basics: "We consider a general black box setting for partially observable and continuous-valued systems operating in an environment with stochastic disturbances. We formulate the problem as a Markov decision process and use reinforcement learning to optimize it. The approach is simulation-based and does not require internal knowledge of the system, making it suitable for black-box testing of large systems. We present different formulations depending on whether the state is fully observable or partially observable. In the latter case, we present a modified Monte Carlo tree search algorithm that only requires access to the pseudorandom number generator of the simulator to overcome partial observability."</p> <p>"AST adaptively guides the sampling of paths to optimize finding failure events and maximizing the path likelihood."</p> <p>"In some applications, it may also be valuable to evaluate failure paths not in absolute terms, but in relation to a baseline system. (...) We call this type of analysis differential stress testing. Such situations arise, for example, during regression testing where a new version of a system is compared to a previous one to identify areas of comparative weakness. (...) We present an extension of AST to the differential setting called differential adaptive stress testing (DAST). The approach finds the most likely path to a failure event that occurs in the system under test, but not in the baseline system. DAST follows the same general formulation as AST. However, in the differential setting, we search two simulators in parallel and maximize the difference in the outcomes of the simulators."</p> <p>AST features: "By choosing a reward function that rewards failure events and higher likelihood transitions, the agent learns to optimize for the most likely failure path."</p> <p>"We set $\gamma = 1$ to properly account for the transition likelihood in the reward function."</p> <p>"Reward Function: The reward function is designed to find failure events as the primary objective and maximize the path likelihood as a secondary objective. (...) The first term of Equation 6 gives a non-negative constant reward RE if the path terminates and a failure event occurs. If the path terminates and an event does not occur, the second term of Equation 6 penalizes the learner by assigning the negative of the miss distance to the learner. The miss distance d is some measure defined by the user that depends on s and indicates how close the simulation came to a failure. If such a measure is not available, then $-d$ can be set to a large negative constant. However, providing an appropriate miss distance can greatly accelerate the search by giving the learner the ability to distinguish the desirability of two paths that do not contain failure events. The third term of Equation 6 maximizes the overall path likelihood by awarding the log likelihood of each transition. Recall that reinforcement learning maximizes the expected sum of rewards. By choosing a reward of the log likelihood at each step, the reinforcement learning algorithm then maximizes the sum of</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 264 / 550	

	<p><i>the log likelihoods, which is equivalent to maximizing the product of the likelihoods."</i></p> <p><i>"Many simulators simply do not allow access to all or any state information. (...) We introduce an abstraction that relaxes the need for the simulator to expose its underlying state and disturbance. First, instead of explicitly representing and passing the state into and out of the simulator as in the fully observable case, we now assume that the simulator maintains state internally and the state is updated in-place. (...) Second, rather than passing disturbance values x as input, we pass a pseudorandom seed \bar{x} as a proxy. (...) Setting the seed makes the sampling process deterministic and thus a particular seed \bar{x} is deterministically tied to a particular sample of disturbance x."</i></p> <p><i>DAST features: "The key idea behind DAST is to drive two simulators in parallel and maximize the difference in their outcomes. To achieve this, we craft a new reward function that accepts the outputs of two simulators and encourages failures in one simulator but not the other. For optimization, we regard the two parallel simulators as a larger combined simulator, then we follow the AST approach to formulate stress testing as a sequential decision-making problem and optimize it using reinforcement learning."</i></p> <p><i>Both simulators "(...) contain identical models of the environment with which the test systems interface. The simulators are driven by the same pseudorandom seed input, which leads to the same sequence of disturbances being drawn in the simulator when the behaviors of the test and baseline systems match. When the behavior of the two systems diverge, the seed automatically allows different disturbances to be drawn from each simulator following their diverging states."</i></p> <p><i>Reward Function: "The primary objective of the reward function is to maximize the difference in outcomes of the simulators, driving the first simulator to a failure event while keeping the second simulator away from one. The secondary objective is to maximize the path likelihoods of the two simulators to produce the most likely paths."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p><i>"We demonstrate the effectiveness of AST and DAST for stress testing the next-generation Airborne Collision Avoidance System (ACAS X). (...) we obtained various prototypes of ACAS X from the FAA and stress tested them in simulated aircraft encounters to find the most likely scenarios of near mid-air collision (NMAC). Our experiments include single-threat (two-aircraft) encounters, multi-threat (three-aircraft) encounters, and differential stress testing against TCAS. (...) We highlight the main findings from these reports, along with the general methods we introduced.".</i> Several operational scenarios were identified and analyzed by the authors (e.g. high turn maneuvers, typical crossing times, aggressive maneuvering, combination of several factors, etc.).</p> <p><i>"ACAS X shows significant improvements in overall safety and alert rates compared to TCAS." "Despite the internal logics of ACAS X and TCAS being derived completely differently, the input and output interfaces of these two systems are identical. "</i></p> <p><i>"Overall, ACAS X is much safer and more operationally suitable than TCAS. However, there are some trade-offs between the two systems as highlighted by our methods. ACAS X's late altering characteristic, which reduces the number of unnecessary alerts, can sometimes hurt encounters with higher vertical rates. (...) In deciding the trade-off, a designer must weigh the relative likelihood of these encounters versus the effect on other more frequently observed trajectories."</i></p> <p><i>"(...) DAST found 39.3% more NMACs with TCAS compared to ACAS X (...)".</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting idea with a detailed model and clear case study scenarios and results. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hyperparameters of the learning model are presented at the case studies without justification with regard to the adopted values. 2) The paper does not take into account the safety assurance of the reinforcement learning-based simulations for the certification of ACAS X (i.e., who ensures that the tool used to certify ACAS is sufficiently safe?)

8.158 REFERENCE [600]

Q-Index	6
Q1	To present a literature survey / review of the significant efforts made in the last fifteen years to foster safety

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 265 / 550	

Answer	in complex intelligent systems which covers relevant aspects of AI safety research including safety requirements engineering, safety-driven design at both system and machine learning (ML) component level, validation and verification from the perspective of software and system engineers.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, with focus on Machine Learning in some parts.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "(...) <i>as stakeholders from various backgrounds and expertise participate in the process of ensuring safety of a complex systems, a consensus on the fundamental properties of autonomous systems; e.g. controllability, explainability, robustness to uncertain environment, etc. is necessary. (...) Traditional risk model and safety analysis are also inadequate to handle the immense use of AI in safety-critical systems. Moreover, how the activities performed by experts of diverse expertise integrate to foster an emergent property like safety is not clear.</i>"</p> <p>Method: To answer the following questions based on articles from the last 15 years: RQ1: How can we easily comprehend the complexity and challenges involved in fostering safety of a complex intelligent systems? Answer: "(...) <i>many researchers are focusing on the validation and verification-related challenges in the third layer. While we acknowledge the absolute necessity of formal verification of ML-based systems to gain trust, we also believe having a clear idea about ‘what to verify’, ‘against which metrics to verify’, ‘what are the qualitative and quantitative targets’ is equally important to verify and validate a system in the right way. In layer-2, more work needs to be done on modeling uncertain environment from a software engineering perspective. Most of the standards included in the review need to be updated to accommodate the new challenges that are brought in by the advent of ML algorithms.</i>"</p> <p>RQ2: How have safety concerns been addressed by the researchers along the phases of SE process? Answer: "(...) <i>there has been a recent surge in the research on verification and validation of safety-critical systems with ML-based components since 2016. However, more effort needs to be paid to conceptualize and analyze the rich problem space of AI systems in the early phases such as requirements engineering and design. It is very important to there has been a recent have a systematic start of the engineering process as it often plays a key role in successful product development.</i>"</p> <p>RQ3: What are the gaps in the current research efforts? Answer: "<i>The open research questions are:</i> (1) <i>How to bridge the safety analysis gap from a safety view point?</i> (2) <i>How to enhance traceability of these artifacts from the system level down to the component level?</i> (3) <i>What is the formal taxonomy for safety analysis in the case of ML components?</i> (4) <i>Is there any standard specially designed to assess the level of safety and the acceptable range of uncertainty of ML-based components in complex AI systems?"</i></p> <p>RQ4: What are the future directions that may help reduce the gaps? Collective Intelligence: "<i>The recent accidents on the autonomous systems were mostly linked to insufficient training (inadequate dataset) or choosing the wrong level of automation. The root cause was insufficient coordination between ML experts and safety engineers at an early phase of systems engineering. (...) many different domain areas need to be coordinated (...).</i>" Traceability changes: "<i>Due to the lack of an integrated framework, it is unclear how we can trace safety-driven design of AI systems. Most of the research work focusing on safety-driven ML do not specify clearly how their design/ learning decisions relate to the system level safety-related concepts. (...) we define horizontal and vertical traceability of safety-driven design of AI systems.</i> <i>Horizontal Traceability: traces of safety engineering process and design decisions along the same layer at system-level and ML-based component-level involving multiple participants.</i> <i>Vertical Traceability: traces of safety analysis across the layers.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>We selected only 14 studies based on their relevance to safety, perspective, and coverage. The selection criteria were as follow:</i> (i) <i>The study is published between 2015–2020.</i> (ii) <i>The study is peer-reviewed and written in English.</i> (iii) <i>The study is focused on the safety aspects of AI, ML, intelligent software engineering, safety-critical systems (that use ML heavily).</i>"</p> <p>Conceptual Framework for Safety-Driven AI System Engineering: A three-layered framework is proposed to conceptualize complex intelligent systems: 1) Problem definition layer: "<i>In this layer, at a system level, domain experts and requirements engineers work closely with users to gather requirements. The aim of these participants is to understand the</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 266 / 550	

expectations of the users and the society, goals of the system, possible situations/scenarios, etc. (...) ML experts, data scientists, Human-Computer Interface (HCI) experts need to work closely with system-level stakeholders to understand the ML model requirements, data requirements, domain definitions, quantitative targets, etc."

2) Safety-driven modeling and development layer: "In this layer system engineers and safety experts work in collaboration to perform system-level risk analysis, risk handling of emergent behavior of the system. (...) At the component level, inherent risks of ML models, effects of adversarial attacks, corner cases are identified. Unlike traditional software-intensive systems, ML-based components are designed and trained based on objective functions following AI/ML specific safety standards. Safe learning decisions on the safety-aware rewards, penalty, etc. are made by the ML experts at this layer."

3) Verified safety compliance layer: "A system is assumed to be acceptable safe only when the involved stakeholders gain enough confidence in the emergent safe behavior. Traditionally, a system is usually verified by formal models and various types of testing. (...) ML experts, HCI experts, data scientists play a crucial role not only to validate training and testing data but also to evaluate overall robustness, scenario coverage, performance, etc. of the ML-based component."

Challenges for Safety Assurance of AI-Based Systems:

1) Lack of formal specification: "Traditional formal verification is mostly founded upon strong mathematical statements of the way system should behave. However, for ML-based systems, it is extremely difficult to describe the expected behavior precisely in a mathematical way. (...) Instead of formalizing the component level behavior, end-to-end system-level behavior specification can be used for verification purposes."

Specifically for reinforcement learning, there are "(...) specification problems, safe interruptability, reward gaming, safe exploration, etc. However, the cost of verification and validation of such components is not trivial. Especially for domains like automotive systems, aircraft systems, verification approach is not scalable for the real world unless they are designed that way. (...) more research is required to ensure that the intention of the designer is rightly articulated into the ML component through well-designed cost and reward functions."

2) Lack of system modeling: "Formally modeling complex deep neural networks with millions of data, several layers, stochastic behavior, and hundreds of features to learn poses a challenge. To model such ML-based components, an explanation based on generalization and abstraction is needed and both input and probabilistic (uncertain) output need to be formally modeled and explained. Furthermore, such uncertain output and its corresponding effect on the system level specification needs to be formally modeled."

3) Insufficient method for safety quantification: "The behavior of a frozen learning model (with no continuous learning strategy) may vary with a small perturbation of the test data, These adversarial perturbations pose a new challenge to verifying ML-based component and using them as a part of safety-critical systems." "(...) randomized formal methods to systematically generate training and testing data can be one of the options to move towards formal verification of ML algorithms. Randomized formal methods need to be improved to address the constraints on the legal input and output space. Randomness requirements can define the output distribution. More rigorous research on constrained random sampling is expected to aid the process. Additionally, SMT solving can also be extended by combining with optimization problems to handle similar issues."

4) Testing to address uncertainty: "(...) more thoughts need to be given towards the traceability of the testing artifacts from the system-level to the component-level."

5) Adversarial attacks: "It is difficult to predict adversarial attacks, and it is also complicated to model the response of a component or system as a whole to such attacks. Therefore, to develop a reliable system it is imperative to not only analyze the inherent risks of ML-techniques, but also to protect them from intentional adversarial attacks. To ensure functional integrity of modern ML-based systems safety and security related knowledge should be used in combination." (...) "RL agents can also be heavily manipulated by malicious attacks. (...) Even a small perturbation can lure an RL agent to move to an undesirable state and take unsafe action. White and black-box attacks have been well investigated (...). In case of white-box attacks, the attacker is assumed to have access to the policy network. Whereas, black-box attacker have only partial or no such information."

Various defense mechanisms have been proposed to ensure robustness of ML models:

"(i) Adversarial training: This is a brute force process of generating as many adversarial examples as

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 267 / 550	

	<p>possible and using them to train the model in advance."</p> <p>"(ii) <i>Defensive distillation: In this defense mechanism, a model is trained to provide outputs in terms of probability instead of hard labels. The distillation process reduces the gradients used to create the adversarial example. As a result, this defensive mechanism of a DNN can reduce the effectiveness of adversarial sample from 95% to less than 0.5%.</i>"</p> <p>6) Inadequate practice to demonstrate assurance cases: "(...) <i>there is currently no formal practice of producing end-to-end safety assurance cases.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	Please refer to the answers to Question 3, since the literature review results therein presented are the main results of the paper.
Q5 Answer	"For future work, we plan to design a proper stepwise methodology to guide multiple disciplines to work together for safety analysis and verification of AI systems"
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting general information regarding safety risks and uncertainty: Safety risks "(...) safety risks "(...) <i>include reward hacking, negative side-effects, unsafe exploration, and insufficient robustness to distributional shift, etc.</i>" "(...) <i>it is also important to address epistemic uncertainty in the underlying distribution of training and test instances.</i>"</p> <p>2) Good summary on explainable AI: "<i>'Safety' and 'trust' are correlated. Lack of transparency/ explainability leads to weak assurance of safety and as a result users or the society as a whole lack trust in such systems. (...) explainability is twofold: explain what has been learned and how each prediction has been made by the model (in the context of the predictive model). (...) further research is necessary on the appropriate level of abstraction to attain the required explainability of a system.</i>"</p> <p>3) Interesting information regarding ANSI / UL-4600: "<i>UL-4600 is the latest and the most advanced standard that aims to address the challenges of the full autonomy of HAV. (...) flexible standards like UL-4600 gained attention in recent times. UL-4600 does not prescribe direct guidance to the proper development process. Rather, it guides on building the safety case (which will be discussed later in the next section) for HAV. (...) Identified topics that are planned to be addressed in this standard are:</i> (i) <i>Definition of operational design domain (e.g., weather, scenarios, etc.)</i> (ii) <i>ML faults (e.g., training data gaps, etc.)</i> (iii) <i>External operation faults (e.g., fault of other vehicles, etc.)</i> (iv) <i>Faulty behavior of the non-driver humans (e.g., pedestrians, etc.)</i> (v) <i>Non-deterministic system behavior (e.g., test planning, etc.)</i> (vi) <i>High residual unknowns (e.g., requirements gaps, etc.)</i> (vii) <i>Lack of human oversight (e.g., passenger handling, etc.)</i> (viii) <i>System-level safety metrics.</i> <i>This standard emphasizes that it is more effective to continually evaluate and improve the residual risk present in the system than to conform to a standard during deployment. Therefore, developers need to be actively involved and take responsibility for safety risk identification and self-assessment over the iterations of the development life-cycle.</i>"</p> <p>4) Interesting information regarding other potential standards for AI-based systems: "<i>In 2020, several new standards from various sources for AI-based systems are likely to be rolled out; for instance, ISO/IEC PAS 21448:2019, ISO/IEC CD 23053, ISO/IEC AWI 23894, ISO/IEC AWI TR 24027, ISO/IEC AWI TR 24028, ISO/IEC DTR 24029-1, ISO/IEC CD 38507.</i>"</p> <p>5) Overall well written and in line with the DSc. research in a complementary way.</p>

8.159 REFERENCE [601]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To systematically establish and break down safety requirements for Deep Neural Networks to argue the sufficient absence of risk arising from insufficiencies such as black-box nature, simple performance issues, incorrect internal logic, and instability, as well as to argue why diverse evidence is highly relevant for a safety argument involving DNNs, and classify available sources of evidence.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 268 / 550	

Q2 Answer	<p>Deep neural networks (DNNs).</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: DNNs exhibit specific insufficiencies - namely black-box property, simple lack of generalization, incorrect internal logic, and instability - that can lead to hazardous failures not covered by existing safety standards.</p> <p><i>"Usual assessment investigates DNN behavior (i.e. generalization ability) according to human "understanding" of the task, which includes expected decision boundaries, corner cases, and continuity of the solution. This introduces a human bias to the assessment: e.g. , an assessor will expect an algorithm to react similar on examples that he or she assumes similar or identical. DNNs—other than manually designed algorithms—are not tied to such assumptions, as will be discussed in the lack of explainability (...). For the sake of completeness of a safety argument, such assumptions must be validated and avoided. To achieve this, we suggest to derive DNN related safety requirements from types of DNN specific generalization issues. This will include issues both on the semantic level, i.e. describable in natural language; and on the non-semantic level."</i></p> <p>DNN Insufficiencies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>"The black-box property of DNNs refers to their lack of explainability. (...) The learned features and their correlations are not necessarily comprehensible for humans, or even counterintuitive. The high-dimensional internal structures of DNNs further hinder interpretable representations, which are needed for traditional inspection and test case selection."</i> 2) <i>"The simple generalization ability refers to the performance on input data which is semantically close to the training data. (...) Reasons for a simple lack of generalization can be manifold, e.g. memorization of the training data, underfitting, or a underrepresentation of attributes in the training data."</i> 3) <i>"(...) lack of internal logic: the internal representation and reasoning a DNN applies originate from correlations in the training data, and may be wrong. This leads to errors that generalize according to semantic rules."</i> 4) <i>"(...) DNNs suffer from a lack of stability against (slight) perturbations—possibly imperceptible slight changes to an image that do not change the semantic information. (...) Perturbation types and sources are manifold, e.g. : permanent or temporary sensor setup changes; adversarial attacks applied in the real world or at pixel level; and noise from domain (fog), sensor (dust, dirt), or intrinsic noise (faulty pixels, transmission error)."</i> <p>Safety requirements:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>"The DNN should perform safely on a semantic approximation of the input domain, i.e. on a subset that that covers relevant semantic aspects. This means both a sufficient (weighted) overall performance, and sufficient performance on each safety critical subset."</i> 2) <i>"(...) relevant features or concepts are internally represented (...)"</i> 3) <i>"(...) logic/reasoning applied to them is correct."</i> 4) <i>"(...) DNN behavior is stable in the input domain with respect to relevant slight perturbations. It remains a challenge to identify all safety relevant, i.e. realistic, perturbations."</i> <p>Best practices for Off-Line DNNs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) DNN Design: DNN specification containing requirements for: robustness of the algorithm; the architectural design (including layer parameters); the DNN class; the interfaces with definition of the output space and input resolution to enable the output of reliable confidence information; weight initialization; Design guidelines defining the unified language for the specification and using best practices from established design approaches. 2) Data Collection: Dataset specification: Considering the following aspects will minimize the insufficiencies arising from incomplete datasets: dataset quality, coverage and relevance; dataset representation; sample classification and the corresponding equivalence classes; corner cases and other boundaries; dataset robustness and necessary perturbations; dataset augmentation including adversarial examples and attribute randomization. Data acquisition strategy defining an adequate choice for data sources. Data partitioning guidelines giving rules how to divide the dataset into training, verification and validation data. Labeling specification: High quality labeling is essential to maximize the quality of datasets. At least the following requirements should be considered to minimize insufficiencies from weak labeling: choice and

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 269 / 550	

	<p>boundaries of label classes; labeling accuracy and quality; adversarial examples. Labeling guidelines to ensure unified and exact labeling and to avoid labeling errors.</p> <p>3) Training: Training specification: Considering the following types of goals increases the probability of getting the intended output of the training phase: hyperparameters (batch size, regularization, loss function, etc.); active learning; domain randomization; robustness; constraints for internal logic; well-calibrated uncertainties; accuracy and failure rates. Training strategy defining the procedure of adjustments of training parameters and the training sequence and iterations. Hyperparameters tuning guidelines to systematically adjust the parameters to achieve the training goals. Configuration management strategy to establish training baselines. This enables analyzing the training steps, setting termination points, and recovering optimal stages.</p> <p>4) Design Mechanisms: Input: Before providing the input to DNN, modification of the input can decrease the chance for an error, e.g. by normalization, denoising, filtering, or removal of non-semantic features causing adversarial examples. Furthermore, the input of DNN might be monitored for causes of performance limitations. For example, detection of adversarial examples causing instability errors, or out-of-distribution samples, i.e. samples very different from the training data, can indicate a to-be-expected error (...). DNN: Error detection and mitigation methods can be applied on the DNN itself. If the exact error is known, e.g. from input monitoring and estimation, the DNN output might be corrected by an additional output. Uncertainty measures of the DNN, indicating the current inherent uncertainty state of the function, are treated as promising safety mechanisms. For example, the output of the DNN can be dropped in the case of high uncertainty. Otherwise, the uncertainty level should be forwarded to the next component. Output: The output and the behavior of the DNN can be monitored to detect errors. In general, anomaly detection as well as plausibility checks might be applied to the DNN output to detect errors, e.g. pedestrians cannot vanish in clear sight. For doing so, the processing information of the input within the DNN is compared to the behavior for clean data.</p> <p>5) V&V <i>"V&V for DNNs cannot be separated clearly, and are challenged by the complexity coming along with DNNs. Especially due to the representation and validity range problems, one cannot expect to gain sufficient confidence in safety only via V&V. One needs to address V&V at all development stages and even beyond."</i> <i>"The goal of test data is to effectively reveal inconsistencies between expected and DNN output that indicate DNN insufficiencies. (...) For effectiveness, high test data representation is required, which is another V&V challenge. (...) semi-formal exploration of the state-space should further aim for coverage of DNN-specific weaknesses: coverage of instability sources, and of previous counterexamples. For semantic input space coverage, all relevant semantic aspects of the objective need to be statistically covered, especially cases defining the true decision boundary (e.g. high occlusion). Ontologies are a good starting point to find such aspects. Challenges remain: the real distribution of values may be hard to approximate due to the open-world context or a lack of real samples; and validating realism of synthetic samples is an unsolved problem. (...) a high coverage of the model state space is required. This can be done globally, e.g. via coverage of neuron activation patterns; or locally by estimating the expected distance to the decision boundaries."</i> </p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Even though the authors claim that <i>"(...)a running example use case [of] an automotive pedestrian perception and successive control function for an emergency braking automation is assumed, with perception realized by a DNN. (...)"</i>, it is only marginally quoted in some examples. The main result is the set of safety requirements and practices based on a literature review for the assurance of DNNs, which is presented in the answer to Question 3.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitations: <i>"We want to focus on misdetections. The failures of hardware and software implementations, as well as non-DNN specific Safety Of The Intended Functionality (SOTIF) aspects are not considered."</i></p> <p>Future work: <i>"(...) the evaluation of the contribution of specific evidence methods is reserved for future work. This also holds for system architectural aspects like redundancy."</i> <i>"Further research will refine the suggested argumentation on the proposed use case, fill the method gaps, and evaluate the contributions of the different methods to the overall risk reduction."</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 270 / 550	

Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting mention to DIN 13266 as a standard related to computer vision. Worth further investigation.</p> <p>2) Well-structured steps for establishing a safety analysis process for DNNs, with the potential of serving as a skeleton for other AI-based methods as well.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors do not expand on the proposed case study.</p>
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8.160 REFERENCE [602]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To provide a new approach to synthesize controllers for nonlinear continuous dynamical systems with control against safety properties based on neural networks (NNs) and to provide safety certification evidence by means of barrier functions, which are represented by NNs as well within a verification-in-the-loop synthesis.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p><i>"A common practice is to first come up with a controller and then to verify it against desired properties. An interesting innovation of our work is, however, to integrate the synthesis and verification in a unified, data-driven framework. (...) At a high level, our approach for the controller synthesis will produce two neural networks simultaneously, i.e., one is used to represent the controller (henceforth referred to as controller-NN), and the other is used to represent the barrier function (henceforth referred to as barrier-NN). The synergy of the two NNs, supported by an additional verification procedure to make sure the learned barrier-NN is indeed a barrier certificate, provides the desired safety guarantee for the synthesized controller. Our method follows a data-driven framework in the sense that both NNs are trained from datasets. For that purpose, we generate training sets and propose specifically designed loss functions which are the key towards the application of standard learning algorithms for NNs. (...) To further improve the synthesized controllers, we propose a number of approaches such as imposing a larger safety region, stability-aware loss functions, and bounded control inputs (via the Hardtanh activation function)."</i></p> <p><i>"To overcome the limitation of data-driven approaches, i.e., the generalization issue of the learned NNs on non-sampled data, formal verification (by SMT solvers in this paper) is performed on the synthesized candidates to show that the barrier certificate conditions are indeed satisfied."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors present their model contextualizing it on a controller that shall control car steering with constant velocity to track a path. Other examples are explored (inverted pendulum, Duffing oscillator, bicycle steering, and Academic 3D).</p> <p><i>"In terms of the learned NN controllers, we find that they usually respect safety constraints, but may exhibit poor performance in terms of, e.g., stability."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<p><i>"Future work includes experimenting on different sampling and training strategies to reduce the data set size and to improve the training efficiency, as well different verification methods/tools other than interval SMT solvers. In particular, we plan to combine the counter-example-driven framework for program analysis with our proposed approach. Recently, the counter-example-guided inductive synthesis procedure (CEGIS) has been employed in NN barrier certificates generation for continuous and hybrid systems with no control input.</i></p> <p><i>We anticipate that these would potentially further improve the scalability of our approach. We also plan to extend our approach to other properties such as reachability coupled with cost/reward based optimality as what has been done in optimal control and reinforcement learning."</i></p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach to solve the problem of safety verification of neural networks by means of a redundant verifier also based on neural networks and provable as correct by means of exact approaches (e.g. SMT).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Some of the models' hyperparameters (e.g. activation function, loss function, number of restarts, learning rate, number of epochs, tolerances, layer structure) are defined by the authors without additional justification except for the fact that they 'make verification easier'.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 271 / 550	

2) The provided explanations are not clear.

8.161 REFERENCE [603]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To study the problem of policy repair for learning-based control policies in safety-critical settings by means of an architecture with a high-performance learning-based control policy paired with a model-based safety controller, and to propose to reduce or even eliminate control switching by ‘repairing’ the trained policy based on runtime data produced by the safety controller in a way that deviates minimally from the original policy.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "A common approach to mitigate the safety problem at runtime is to pair the learning-based controller (LC) with a high-assurance safety controller (SC) that can take over control in safety-critical situations, such as the Simplex architecture. The safety controller is tasked with predicting an impending safety violation and taking over control when it deems necessary. Such controllers are often designed based on conservative models, has inferior performance compared to its learning-based counterpart, and may require significant computation resources if implemented online. Moreover, frequent and intermittent switching between the controllers can result in undesirable behaviors and further performance loss."</p> <p>Basics: "(...) we propose to leverage the runtime interventions carried out by the safety controller to repair the learnt policy [and] (...) assume that the policy is parameterized, differentiable and given as a white-box. (...) The main idea in minimally deviating policy repair is the formulation of a trajectory optimization problem that allows us to simultaneously reason about policy optimization and safety constraints. A key novelty of this approach is the synthesis of new safe ‘demonstrations’ that are the most likely to be produced by the original unsafe learnt policy."</p> <p>"(...) we assume that a dynamical model of f [state-action function] is given, possibly constructed conservatively, and adopt a scheme known as Model Predictive Safe Control (...)."</p> <p>Naïve Policy Repair: "The basic idea of the naive policy repair approach is to let the unsafe LC learn from the interventions produced by the SC. Specifically, we iteratively execute the LC and SC pair to generate new safe traces. After each iteration, the state-action pairs in all the previously generated traces are used as training data to update the policy of the LC." Main issue: if policy repair converges to a fully safe policy, performance is degraded to the level of the safe controller.</p> <p>Minimally-Deviating Policy Repair: A means to avoid this is to have the LC to learn updated safe policies that minimize their deviation from the original performance-oriented policies. "(...) to solve an imitation learning problem, we can minimize the KL-divergence which is related to maximal log-likelihood". "One major benefit of this formulation is that imitation learning objective and safety constraints can be reasoned at the same time via optimal control."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We perform two case studies to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed approach. The key metrics of evaluation are (1) safety of the repaired policy and (2) performance preservation with respect to the original policy." The examples are "mountaincar" (car flowing on an U-shaped trajectory), in which the car shall not surpass a speed limit, and "traction-loss event in simulated urban driving environment", in which a single ego bicycle shall not perform unsafe maneuvers on an environment in the absence of other cars around it (i.e., unsafe scenarios stem from objects on the track and from driving on an incorrect track lane). Both models are exercised with neural network-based controllers.</p> <p>"Our experiments indicate that our proposed approach is effective in achieving both safety and performance even when the dynamical model used by the safety controller is not exact."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings are not mentioned by the authors.</p> <p>"In the future, we plan to consider other types of safety controllers and extend our techniques to end-to-end control settings."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting idea with strong mathematical basis. It starts tackling safety issues related to online learning.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 272 / 550	

- 1) Hyperparameters used on the case studies are ill-justified.
2) The model is highly dependent on the application, since it requires a dynamic model of the target application.

8.162 REFERENCE [604]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose the use of rules extracted from neural networks as artifacts for safety evidence and discuss the rationale behind the use of rules.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "The advent of new capabilities such as AI is currently demanding tools, methods and techniques for assuring safety and dependability of these systems. (...) There are two main challenges to extending existing safety assurance approaches to AI systems. The first challenge is finding efficient analysis, testing, and verification methods that are used to create safety evidence and build the safety argument on. The second challenge is finding "information or artifacts that contribute to developing confidence in the safe operation of the AI system", i.e., artifacts for AI systems that can serve as a piece of evidence. Among other things, a candidate evidence artifact needs to be verifiable, auditable, and maintainable and could come from diverse methods. (...) we take on the second challenge and propose the use of rule extraction methods to create safety evidence for neural networks, and the use of extracted rules as safety evidence."</p> <p>Basics: "Rule extraction is a procedure that takes a trained neural network together with the data on which the network was trained, and produces a description of the network's hypothesis that is comprehensible yet closely approximates the network's predictive behavior."</p> <p>"(...) there are two main approaches. The first approach, called pedagogical approach, aims at finding the corresponding output for the input to an NN by treating the network as a black-box. (...) The second approach, called decompositional approach, works by splitting the network at neuron level, obtaining rules for each neuron, and aggregating the results to generate rules representing the entire network."</p> <p>"Types of Extracted Rules. Depending on the task, different types of rules can be used. For feedforward NNs, relevant rules include (1) If-then: Boolean conditional statement; (2) M-of-N : M of N conditions are satisfied; (3) Decision Tree: conditions organized in a hierarchical binary tree fashion; (4) fuzzy rules: conditional statements with approximation for partial truths; and (5) first-order rules: conditions with quantifiers and variables."</p> <p>"As [rule extraction] techniques demand high memory usage and computational time, they need special methods to enable efficiency. The most common techniques applied are rule pruning and network pruning, where less important components of extracted rules and the input neural network are pruned.(...) Most early decompositional rule extraction approaches employed a search process for subsets of rules at each hidden and output units of the NN, which is exponential in the number of inputs to the node. (...) However, various heuristics can be applied to limit space exploration and achieve tractability for real-world problems. In addition, for some NN architectures, crisp symbolic rules can be extracted in polynomial time. The complexity of extracted rules, which is defined as a factor of number of extracted rules and number of antecedents per rule, is another problem. However, there exist methods such as network pruning and rule pruning, rule abstraction, distillation approach that are aimed at reducing the size of the generated rule sets. Approaches like partial order reductions and priority synthesis from the formal methods community can also be considered for reducing the extracted rules to a manageable size."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we illustrate our proposed approach of using extracted rules as safety evidence for the MNIST dataset using a complex NN LeNet (includes CNN and fully connected layers).(...) Extracting a decision tree from pixels of an image does not add enough interpretability information about the NN. For this reason, we have selected the last fully connected layer of the model as a feature layer and built the surrogate decision tree over this feature-output combination."</p> <p>"(...) we applied two pedagogical rule extraction techniques:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TREPAN: The algorithm uses an Oracle that can query and sample examples from the dataset. Each node is split based on the best fit that generates the highest fidelity with the NN model. (...) we have used If-then rules. - Surrogate Random Forest Model: In this algorithm, the NN model was taken as a black-box model

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 273 / 550	

	<p>generating feature-output combination. This combination is used to train a separate Random Forest Model from scratch."</p> <p>"(...) to identify safety properties for which a rule can be used as safety artifact, we have used adversarial noise (...)."</p> <p>"The models are trained with the following methods:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plain: trained with basic backpropagation algorithm. 2. Adversarial Training (AT): trained with adversarial images to make the model robust to adversarial perturbation. 3. Maximization of Linear Regions (MMR): trained with MMR regularizer to increase the provable bound on effective adversarial noise. 4. MMR+AT: a hybrid approach that uses both MMR and AT approaches." <p>"(...) plain and AT models have their rules closer towards the median. (...) the surrogate Random Forest model had better fidelity scores than the surrogate Decision Tree."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>No shortcomings were discussed by the authors.</p> <p>"One direction of future work could be to explore the relation between types of extracted rules and the corresponding classes of safety properties. Another direction could be the soundness and completeness arguments for rule extraction methods. Such arguments help in assuring the validity and sufficiency of the extracted rules as evidence artifacts for safety certification."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Study in line with the safety analysis of AI-based systems. 2) Interesting ideas that can be considered when crafting a general-purpose guideline for the safety analysis and safe design of AI-based systems. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The case study does not bring a detailed explanation on the obtained rules and their analyses; 2) The authors fail to analyze shortcomings of their proposed method (e.g. difficulties on implementing the proposed approaches depending on the type of Neural Network).

8.163 REFERENCE [605]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To provide a pattern for arguing about the correct implementation of safety requirements in system components based on Machine Learning and integrate it within an overall encompassing approach for safety case generation.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction:</p> <p>"Currently, ISO 26262 does not provide any recommendation for the safety assurance of ML-based systems. ISO/PAS 21448 makes only few references to ML which do not provide sufficient information to reason about limitations of this technology."</p> <p>"(...) this work proposes a pattern to construct a safety case – a clear, comprehensive and defensible argument, supported by diverse evidence, guaranteeing safety of an item. The pattern is specified in the Goal Structuring Notation (GSN) (...). The proposed pattern scopes at guiding the reasoning about the safety assurance of systems that have parts of their functionality implemented with ML."</p> <p>Definition: "ML is considered in this work as a 3rd kind of technology, next to SW and HW."</p> <p>Basics: The ML deployment process is based on a V-process with the following steps: Initiation (ML Requirements), Data Preparation (Training/Validation/Test Datasets), ML Design, Training, Training Verification (against Validation set), Design Verification (against Validation Set), Functional Verification (against Test Set) and ML Validation (against Test Set).</p> <p>"The implementation is an artifact expressed in a programming language such as Python, or preferably in a strongly typed language such as C++."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 274 / 550	

	<p>The following goals are identified for each ML-related activity:</p> <p>A) Data Acquisition:</p> <p>G9.1: Collected data (training/validation/test) satisfies machine learning requirements,</p> <p>G9.2: Data is properly labeled.</p> <p>G9.3: Domain coverage is achieved with training, validation, and testing data sets. This goal is divided in the following secondary goals:</p> <p>G9.6: Datasets are characterized with proper distribution resembling these of an operational environment;</p> <p>G9.7: Gathered data accounts for safety-critical scenarios;</p> <p>G9.8: Gathered data accounts for adversarial examples;</p> <p>G9.9: Gathered data accounts for corner cases;</p> <p>G9.10: Datasets consider different object variations, relations and influences.</p> <p>G9.11: Similarity of training/validation/test data sets in regards to operational data is high.</p> <p>G9.4: Samples in training, validation and test data sets are not overlapping.</p> <p>G9.5: Data sets contain proper amount of data samples.</p> <p>G9.12 Operational Design Domain (ODD) coverage is analyzed.</p> <p>G9.13 Collected data has been verified as adhering to the machine learning requirements.</p> <p>B) Appropriate ML model design:</p> <p>G10.1: ML model design refines the machine learning requirements,</p> <p>G10.2: ML model design is sufficiently comprehensible, correct, robust and verifiable. This goal is divided in the following secondary goals:</p> <p>G10.7: ML model design introduces design-level performance metrics;</p> <p>G10.8: ML model design is optimized;</p> <p>G10.9: ML model design relies on appropriate best practices;</p> <p>G10.10: Specification of hyperparameters is provided;</p> <p>G10.11: ML model design contributes to generalization property.</p> <p>G10.3: ML model design is compatible with the target hardware.</p> <p>G10.4: Potential hazardous failures are acceptably managed by ML model design.</p> <p>G10.5: Verify G10.2.</p> <p>G10.6: Verify G10.1.</p> <p>C) Appropriate implementation and training of ML model design:</p> <p>G11.1: ML requirements are implemented by the ML model.</p> <p>G11.2: Implementation activity follows good practice.</p> <p>G11.3: ML model is implemented in an appropriate implementation framework.</p> <p>G11.4: ML model is trained on appropriate training platform.</p> <p>G11.5: ML model is robust. This goal is divided in the following secondary goals:</p> <p>G11.10: ML model is evaluated against predefined performance metrics;</p> <p>G11.11: ML model is verified against corner cases;</p> <p>G11.12: ML model is verified against adversarial attacks;</p> <p>G11.13: Statistical measures are performed;</p> <p>G11.14: ML model is verified against injected faults;</p> <p>G11.15: Generalization of ML model is verified.</p> <p>G11.6: ML model satisfies the ML requirements on the target platform.</p> <p>G11.7: Differences between the training and target platforms do not lead to a violation of the ML requirements.</p> <p>G11.8: ML model semantic is sufficiently well understood.</p> <p>G11.9: ML is interpretable.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"In this work, we consider as the system of interest (SoI) a pedestrian avoidance system", whose safety goal is that "pedestrian avoidance system is safe in a given context". The authors show how the proposed argumentation pattern may be used together with how to define the needed evidence for the claims defined within the pattern.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "One limitation of this work is that, similarly to related works, it does not reason about the completeness of an argumentation provided by the proposed pattern. Neither does it make a claim that proposed set of goals and strategies is ultimate. Completeness in this case is non-quantifiable and can be achieved by an overall consensus of stakeholders interested in safety of ML-based solutions."</p> <p>Future Work: "First, the manner how different ASIL levels influence an ultimate selection of the goals</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 275 / 550	

	<i>defined within the proposed pattern should be examined. (...) Second, further possible types of evidence to support claims shall be investigated due to the constant advances in the area of ML. Finally, the elicitation of safety requirements for ML-based components remains a challenge that still needs to be addressed."</i>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The authors include discussion on which programming languages are admissible for machine learning in safety-critical systems.</p> <p>2) The goals attributed to ML safety arguments are well defined and in line with similar research. They are useful for the DSc. as well.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors base their work on the definition that Machine Learning is not hardware nor software, but rather a different technology. This is presented in a pre-print paper (Source: Putzer, H.J., Wozniak, E.: A structured approach to trustworthy autonomous/cognitive systems. arXiv preprint (2020)) and does not seem to support, since ML implementation requires HW and SW. A better view for this is the 'W' lifecycle model proposed by [445].</p> <p>2) Goal G10.8 is especially questionable: an optimized ML model is not necessarily the best one for safety w.r.t. e.g. explainability.</p>

8.164 REFERENCE [610]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To describe and investigate "SafeOps", a concept of "continuous safety", based on the DevOps approach, unifying development and operations and which consists in a set of practices intended to reduce the time between committing a change to a system and the change being deployed into production, while ensuring high quality.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "(...) <i>the idea we have with SafeOps is to propose a continuum from monitoring the smallest component of a vehicle to accident monitoring.</i>"</p> <p>AI/ML Basics: "<i>For AI/ML-powered systems, new engineering challenges are rising:</i> <i>a) The learning process cannot follow the same rules and practices than the software development process;</i> <i>b) Data play a key role for learning and validating these systems.</i>"</p> <p><i>"In short, we believe that, contrary to regular software systems which have a "constant" reliability over time, the reliability of AI/ML-powered systems will naturally decrease over time. The explanation and consequences of this natural decrease depend on multiple factors:</i> <i>a) The reliability of AI/ML systems significantly depends on their generalization capability, making the right predictions for data input that have never been seen at the training stage. It's a major risk to train overfitting models that perform well on the data already seen during the training.</i> <i>b) By providing better predictions or decisions AI/ML systems can lead to changes in the behaviors of users, for which the data are not present in the initial training set.</i> <i>The SafeOps approach, by carefully monitoring the accuracy and reliability of predictions and decisions to estimate the reliability of those systems, could be a key solution to manage this "natural" reliability decrease, ensuring that their reliability complies to the target level."</i> <i>"The SafeOps approach brings the means to manage an increasing target level and a kind of "incremental", continuously improved reliability and safety."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	No results are presented by the authors in the paper. The only result is the definition of the SafeOps model itself, whose AI-related details are presented in the answer to Question 3.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Motivation for safety concerns regarding AI are in line with several other papers.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 276 / 550	

- 1) Research still in initial state, with little practical results so far;
- 2) Very short paper (4 pages) which lack further details on the author idea;
- 3) Theme marginally related to the DSc. only.

8.165 REFERENCE [613]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To evaluate the safety of a neural network controller that seeks to ensure that an Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUV) does not collide with a static object in its path by determining the exact output reachable set of all the UUV's components through the use of star-sets.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks with reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "(...) <i>the last several years have seen a significant increase in the development of verification testing, and falsification methods for systems that make use of neural networks. (...) While a great deal of these methods deal with networks in isolation, in recent years several methods have been proposed for verifying neural network control systems. Neural network control systems commonly appear in safety critical systems where the neural network controller is generated through the use of reinforcement learning and learning by demonstration. In this realm, the safety verification problem is postulated as a reachability problem.(...) Despite significant progress in neural network control systems verification, developing a scalable methodology remains a key challenge.</i>" Hence, "(...) <i>the following work seeks to examine the efficacy of star-set based methods through the analysis of a Neural Network Control System that represents a more complex system than those previously considered in other works.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>The UUV system in the Unmanned Underwater Vehicle Simulator (...) is made up of several components. There is a Learning Enabled Component (LEC), FNN Controller, which determines the control output for each time step. It utilizes two inputs, the distance to an object and the Closest Point of Approach (CPA), that are calculated based on observations from the forward looking and side scan sonars. The controller then outputs 4 values, 2 regarding the heading change and 2 regarding the speed commands, which are then fed through a highly nonlinear normalization function, mapping these 4 values to a control command made up of a desired heading change (rad) and desired speed (m/s). These control commands are then processed by a low-level PID controller that converts these commands into actuation commands for the UUV.</i></p> <p>Combining the nonlinearities of the PID, the normalization function, and the sonar sensors, makes the task of formally verifying the UUVS Model highly complicated. These complexities make performing safety verification via reachability analysis intractable. Therefore, we created a modified model that approximates the performance of the UUVS Model and allows us to perform reachability analysis more conveniently. We will refer to this model as our Verifiable Model and it is composed of the four parts:"</p> <p>Feed Forward Neural Network Sensor: "(...) <i>a feedforward neural network with 3 inputs, 7 hidden ReLU layers consisting of 10 neurons each, and a linear output layer with 2 neurons.</i>"</p> <p>Feed Forward Neural Network Controller: "(...) <i>a Reinforcement Learning controller that was trained using the Vanilla Policy Gradient Method (...). This neural network consists of 2 hidden layers of 32 fully connected, ReLU activated neurons.</i>"</p> <p>Feed Forward Neural Network Normalization: a "(...) <i>feedforward neural network [that] consists of 3 ReLU hidden layers with 50 neurons total and a linear output layer with 2 neurons.</i>"</p> <p>Plant model: "<i>We replace the highly nonlinear UUV dynamical model with a simpler 2-dimensional linear discrete-time data-driven model obtained via system identification techniques. (...) The model is learned using classical system identification methods, and treat the dynamics to be learned as a black-box model. Initially, none of the system parameters are known.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>We are able to compute the exact reachable set of the NNCS by computing the exact control set and the exact plant output set at each time step. (...) To avoid the explosion of the number of sets needed to represent the reachable set, we take a single convex hull of the reachable sets of states of the plant after each step, and then we compute the output reachable set of the plant, which is then fed back to the next component as a single star set. However, the tradeoff here is that the solution to this problem is no longer exact.</i>" --> authors claim that this is an overapproximation, hence leaning towards safety.</p>
Q4 Answer	"(...) <i>the problem we wish to consider is verifying that the UUV operates safely by successfully avoiding obstacles while executing its mission of inspecting a given pipeline. The obstacles we consider are static</i>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 277 / 550	

	<p>obstacles of varying sizes, and the safety specification we wish to consider is that the UUV does not move within a radius of a given obstacle."</p> <p>"Our experimental evaluation uses four different scenarios to show that our star-set based methods are scalable and can be efficiently used to analyze the safety of real-world cyber-physical systems (CPS) for up to 30 second time windows."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>No shortcomings were discussed by the authors.</p> <p>"In future work we hope to extend the proposed methods for nonlinear NNCS with neural networks that contain other types of nonlinear activation functions such as Tanh or Sigmoid. Additionally, while the current paper deals with a discrete time plant, future endeavors will consider continuous-time dynamical plants. Furthermore, we seek to examine other UUV tasks and safety specifications, such as a safety and performance analysis of the UUV's pipe-following performance in conjunction with obstacle avoidance."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Several model hyperparameters (e.g. neural network architecture) have been arbitrarily selected by the authors without further justification, while others (e.g. discount rate and reward function for reinforcement learning) have not been presented by the authors.</p> <p>2) The models are very application-dependent, since they require the system dynamics to be encoded.</p>

8.166 REFERENCE [614]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To propose automated support for safety analysis for collaborative and dynamically formed cyber-physical systems that considers the configuration of the system network.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: The research "(...) contributes a safety analysis technique for the verification of dynamically forming networks of CPS that relies on the available documentation of the individual systems architecture and predefined constrains for the formation of valid configurations. To this end we automatically generate architecture models of the CPS network from the individual architectures, which can be automatically checked against safety properties. Furthermore, as the information about a safety property violation alone is often of little help to developers tasked with correcting the problem, our approach also provides a model-based representation of the defect in a suitable representation that helps developers correct the underlying defect."</p> <p>Basics: "(...) we will assume a simplified three-step approach for safety analyses. First, potential safety defects are identified by experts in the field (...). Second, the specification of the system under development is checked for the existence of these safety defects or for evidence of the absence of these defects. Third, based on the findings from the second step the first step is repeated and the newly gained knowledge about the occurrence and the concrete manifestation of safety defects is considered for the detection of new safety defects."</p>
Q4 Answer	"We investigated applicability using case examples, besides the platooning case example, we also used a case example from the industry automation domain" (collaborative fleet of autonomous industry robots). "In addition, we discussed the kind of generated models with industry professionals and conducted controlled experiments to investigate the generated models' usefulness."
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Paper not related to the safety analysis of AI-based systems. Despite system adaptiveness being the subject of the authors and AI appearing as a keyword, no mention to it is made.</p>

8.167 REFERENCE [616]

Q-Index	2
Q1	To propose a method for systematically evaluating the safety of machine learning-based systems, which

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 278 / 550	

Answer	consists of dataset-based safety analysis (by extending fault tree analysis to deal with datasets) and statistical evaluation of testing results.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "(...) we assume that test datasets are automatically generated for each of the conditions by simulation or Monte-Carlo methods, and propose a method for systematically evaluating machine learning systems using the test datasets."</p> <p>"Our method comprises dataset-based safety analysis and testing. In the former, we systematically analyze test datasets with probability. In the latter, we use statistics to evaluate the testing results obtained with the test datasets."</p> <p>Note: On the paper, the expression 'recognition rate' is employed to describe a ML model's accuracy.</p> <p>Basics: "We extend the fault tree to deal with datasets and recognition rates. This extended fault tree is called fault tree for datasets, hereafter referred to as FT4D. In FT4D, as in FTA, a root node is decomposed into intermediate nodes and broken down into leaf nodes, referred to as the top event, abstract events, and basic events, respectively. An event has a dataset representing data that induces the event, and an erroneous recognition rate with respect to that dataset. FT4D makes it possible to obtain the dataset and the erroneous recognition rate of the upper node from those of lower nodes. Then, by testing at the leaf node to guarantee the erroneous recognition rate, we can also guarantee those assigned to all the other nodes."</p> <p>The model requires that a FTA comprising all possible failures regarding the dataset is manually built by an analyst. Afterwards, the dataset (including its failures) is exercised in order to collect the error rate, which "(...) shows how often incorrect classification happens in operation time due to a failure."</p> <p>"(...) we need a large number of sample data because we need the sufficient number of cases incorrectly identified by the classifier after obtaining those affected by failures. (...) In order to mitigate the problem, information theoretic approach such as a cross-entropy method can be taken, however, in our approach, we analyze and define a failure rate in FT4D": the 'basic error rate', which "(...) is used to calculate an error rate."</p> <p>"Each of the rates is usually estimated according to the past developments, the existing data and standards in practice."</p> <p>"We statistically estimate the true recognition rate of the population dataset D by testing with the sample dataset /D. We use interval estimation in Bernoulli trials for estimation. (...) We use the sample dataset /D as inputs to the classifier and check whether $CF(x) = r$ or not for x belonging to /D and the expected recognition result "r"</p> <p>by testing. That is a Bernoulli trial since we obtain a sequence of true or false as the testing result."</p> <p>"We propose the following testing procedure to estimate error rates based on the corollary presented above [Chernoff-Hoeffding]: Let (D, r, pe) be a test suite. Testing is performed to check whether the true recognition rate is higher than the expected recognition rate pe for a dataset D.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) We determine values of an error epsilon and a confidence 1 - delta. 2) We create a sample dataset /D consisting of n elements, such that is defined as follows: $n = 1 / [(2 * \epsilon)^2 * \ln(2 / \delta)]$. 3) We check whether each element of /D is classified as r. (...) the testing is passed if the true recognition rate is higher than pe with a probability 1 - delta, and failed otherwise." <p>"We need to define expected criteria when we assure the quality of the classifier. It is impossible to satisfy a set of criteria if it is too high, yet if it is too low, we lose an opportunity for model optimization. Thus, making the trade-off between expected criteria and testing results is important for quality assurance in machine learning systems."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"The target of the experiment was a classifier designed to recognize handwritten digits, implemented as a convolutional neural network (CNN). We used the MNIST dataset of handwritten digits to train and validate the CNN model. (...) Training and validation dataset sizes were 60,000 and 10,000, respectively. The CNN topology comprised input, convolution, pooling, convolution, fully connected, and output layers in that order, with layer sizes of 784 (28×28), 11520 (24×24×20), 2880 (12×12×20), 800 (4×4×50), 500 (500×1), and 10 (10×1), respectively. We first constructed a FT4D indicating events which could cause incorrect identification of digits due to noise. We then performed testing for basic events of FT4D." 1 - delta = 0.01 in both cases.</p> <p>"Testing was failed for all basic events in the case of epsilon = 0.025 because the error was too large. Such large errors require a large number of correctly identified samples. In the case of epsilon = 0.005, the sample dataset was larger than that of and the epsilon = 0.025 testing was passed for (...) half of the basic events.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 279 / 550	

	Failure rates were then reduced and shown to be met by the model with $\epsilon = 0.025$.
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) classifier inputs are limited to simple images like those of the MNIST dataset. Expected results are also limited to simple labels like the numbers 0 to 9."</p> <p>"We plan to extend the method to deal with other kinds of machine learning systems in the future."</p> <p>"IoU (Intersection over Union) cannot identify the direction of a gap between ground truth and classification labels, even though this could affect product safety. We think that proposing a specification language for such complex requirements and input data can resolve these issues. We intend to address methods for dealing with such classifiers in future work."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach to allow the black-box safety analysis of AI-based systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Safety metrics depend solely on accuracy, hence issues recalling other performance metrics (e.g. recall, precision) are not taken into account.</p> <p>2) The model may require a prohibitively high number of samples if strict requirements are needed (e.g. high confidence, low error, and high performance metrics).</p> <p>3) The case study application and the safety mechanism employed to reduce the needed samples to ensure that the system safe are arguable.</p>

8.168 REFERENCE [617]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present an application of decision trees and rules algorithms to simplify the user choice of a suitable safety logic device type.
Q2 Answer	Decision trees and random forests (including JRIP, J48, random trees and PART).
Q3 Answer	"The research was intended to (...) the usability of decision trees and rules algorithms within an overall scheme devised to simplify the user selection of convenient safety measures and functions, considering also the capabilities of multilayered feedforward artificial neural networks."
Q4 Answer	<p>"The safety dataset employed herein embodies a case study to identify an appropriate path to safety in machine engineering."</p> <p>"The results (...) show that the PART classifier provided a prediction power superior to other similar algorithms within the WEKA machine learning family, assuming three experimental tests (training, 5-fold, and 10-fold cross validation)."</p> <p>"(...) human experts still remain indispensable, as they can analyze multiple additional, auxiliary parameters and design high-quality inputs to improve the learning process. The safety-related data in our initial dataset may help pave the way to an original web server to support effective procedures for identifying the type of a safety logic device."</p>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting reference to ISSO/TR22100-5 for the standardization of AI-based safety-critical systems: "(ISO/TR 22100-5) titled "Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 5: Risk Assessment in case of autonomous reconfiguration of machinery and Artificial Intelligence". This technical report should be used when appropriate using EN ISO 13849-1 for defining Performance Levels."</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The research is about using machine learning to decide the design of a safety-critical system. It is not related to the safety analysis of AI-based systems.</p>

8.169 REFERENCE [618]

Q-Index	5
Q1	To present a novel learning framework that ensures formally verified properties of Artificial Neural

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 280 / 550	

Answer	<p>Networks (ANNs) behaviors are enforced by construction, enabling training provably correct networks with respect to a broad class of safety properties by integrating an optimization-based abstraction refinement loop into the learning process and operating over dynamically constructed partitions of the input space that considers accuracy and safety objectives synergistically.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>Artificial neural networks.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: <i>"The programming languages and formal methods community has [provided] (...) increasingly sophisticated and scalable verification approaches — given a trained ANN and a property, these approaches either certify that the ANN satisfies the property or identify a potential violation of the property. Unfortunately, when verification fails, these approaches provide no insight on how to effectively leverage verification counterexamples to repair complex, uninterpretable networks and ensure safety."</i></p> <p>Basics: <i>"(...) we address the limitations of existing verification approaches by proposing a novel training approach for generation of ANNs [called Abstraction Refinement-Guided Training (ART)] that are correct-by-construction with respect to a broad class of correctness properties expressed over the network's inputs. Our training approach integrates correctness properties into the training objective through a correctness loss function that quantifies the violation of the correctness properties. Further, to enable certification of correctness of a possibly infinite set of network behaviors, our training approach employs abstract interpretation methods to generate sound abstractions of both the input space and the network itself. Finally, to ensure the trained network is both correct and accurate with respect to training data, our approach iteratively refines the precision of the input abstraction, guided by the value of the correctness loss function. Our approach is sound — if the correctness loss reduces to 0, the generated ANN is guaranteed to satisfy the associated correctness properties."</i></p> <p><i>"ART takes as input a correctness property that prescribes desired network output behavior using logic constraints when the inputs to the network are within a domain (...). ART is parameterized by an abstract domain that yields an abstraction over inputs [in the safe input domain]. Additionally, ART takes a set of labeled training data. The correctness loss function quantifies the distance of the abstract network output from the correctness constraint (...). In each training iteration, ART both updates the network weights and refines the input abstraction. The network weights are updated using classical gradient descent optimization to mitigate the correctness loss and the standard accuracy loss. The abstraction refinement utilizes information provided by the correctness loss to improve the precision of the abstract network output. (...) the key novelty of our approach - exploiting the synergy between refinement and approximation - (a) often leads to, at worst, mild impact on accuracy compared to a safe oracle baseline; and (b) provides significantly higher assurance on network correctness than existing verification or training methods which do not exploit abstraction refinement."</i></p> <p><i>"The abstract correctness loss function L_g provides a direction for neural network weight optimization. However, L_g could be overly imprecise since the amount of spurious cases introduced by the neural network abstraction is correlated with the size of the abstract input region. This kind of imprecision leads to sub-optimal optimization, ultimately hurting the feasibility of correct-by construction as well as the model accuracy."</i> <i>"(...) an abstraction inevitably introduces spurious data samples into training due to over-approximation."</i></p> <p><i>"(...) the problem of enforcing coarse-grained correctness properties on neural networks can be converted into one that enforces multiple fine-grained properties, an easier problem to tackle because much of the imprecision introduced by the coarse-grained abstraction can now be eliminated."</i></p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Case Study 1:</p> <p><i>"Our first evaluation study centers around the network architecture and correctness properties described in the Airborne Collision Avoidance System for Unmanned Aircraft (ACAS Xu) dataset. A family of 45 neural networks are used in the avoidance system; each of these networks consists of 6 hidden layers with 50 neurons in each hidden layer. ReLU activation functions are applied to all hidden layer neurons. All 45 networks take a feature vector of size 5 as input that encodes various aspects of an airborne environment. The outputs of the networks are prediction scores over 5 advisory actions to select the advisory action."</i></p> <p><i>"Among the 45 provided networks, 36 are reported with safety property violations and 9 are reported safe. We evaluate ART on those 36 unsafe networks to demonstrate the effectiveness of generating correct-by-construction networks. The test sets from unsafe networks may contain unsafe points and are thus unauthentic, so we apply ART on those 9 already safe networks to demonstrate the accuracy overhead when enforcing the safety properties."</i></p> <p><i>"Our methodology demonstrates that an abstraction refinement methodology provides a meaningful pathway for building both accurate and correct machine learning networks."</i></p> <p><i>"(...) ART successfully generates correct-by-construction networks for all scenarios with only minimal loss</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 281 / 550	

	<p><i>in accuracy. On the other hand, if refinement is disabled, it fails to generate correct-by-construction networks for all cases, and displays lower accuracy than the refinement-enabled instantiations."</i></p> <p><i>"We also consider a comparison of our abstraction refinement-guided training for correct-by-construction networks against a post facto training loop that feed concrete correctness related data points to training loops. (...) experiments fail to enforce correctness properties in most cases and they may impose great impact to model accuracy compared to the baseline network. We believe this result demonstrates the difficulty of applying a counterexample guided training loop strategy for generating safe networks compared an abstraction-guided methodology."</i></p> <p>Case Study 2:</p> <p><i>"Our second evaluation task focuses on the Collision Detection Dataset where a neural network controller is used to predict whether two vehicles running curve paths at different speeds would collide. The network takes as input a feature vector of size 6, containing the information of distances, speeds, and directions of the two vehicle. The network output prediction score are used to classify the scenario as a colliding or non-colliding case."</i></p> <p><i>"A total of 500 correctness properties are proposed in the Collision Detection dataset that identify the safety margins around particular data points. The network presented in the dataset respects 328 such properties. (...) After 100 epochs, ART converged to a local minimum and managed to certify 481 out of all 500 safety properties. Although it did not achieve zero correctness loss, ART can produce a solution that satisfies significantly more correctness properties than the oracle neural network, at the cost of only a small accuracy drop."</i></p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcoming: Training and test sets of the ACAS Xu dataset are not publicly available; hence, the authors used the known-as-safe ANNs to generate oracle labels to the datasets employed in the case study.</p> <p>No other shortcomings nor future research are explored by the author(s).</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <p>1) Very interesting and well-founded mathematical method to create safe-by-construction ANNs.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) In the case study, several hyperparameters of the ANNs (e.g. learning rate initial value and decaying policy, solver, number of abstractions, loss function) are defined by the authors without full justification on their figures.</p> <p>2) The proposed model tries to ensure safety while retaining accuracy, but there is no mention to other performance metrics of the ANNs (e.g. precision, recall).</p> <p>3) Case study 2 shows that the proposed method may not ensure the assurance of all needed safety requirements of an ANN-based system. This is not emphasized by the authors at the conclusion of their work.</p>

8.170 REFERENCE [619]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	<p>To address the challenge of handling complex traffic scenarios of autonomous vehicles during test scenarios of AI-based systems and evaluating their system-level quality of service by (1) defining situation coverage as an abstract coverage criteria for autonomous vehicle testing, (2) evaluating situation coverage of existing test suites obtained by off-the-shelf simulation tools, and (3) proposing a test suite generation approach that provides test scenarios with increasing situation coverage as output.</p>
Q2 Answer	<p>Artificial intelligence in general.</p>
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: <i>"Autonomous vehicles controlled by advanced machine learning techniques are significantly gaining in popularity. However, the safety engineering practices currently used in such vehicles are not capable of justifying that AI techniques would prevent unsafe situations with a designated level of confidence and reliability."</i></p> <p><i>"My proposed research line aims to provide system-level safety assurance for autonomous vehicles. On one hand, existing component-level safety assurance approaches are efficient in their scope but do not yet adapt well to the system level. On the other hand, system-level approaches exist, but are only at a prototypical or conceptual stage. As a result, my research will focus on deriving a novel system-level validation approach for autonomous vehicles to guarantee quality of (safe) service"</i></p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 282 / 550	

	<i>in an open and changing environment."</i>
Q4 Answer	The author has presented a proposal of its work. Some of the highlighted results are the following ones: <i>"I have started implementing a scenario specification language (i.e. a modeling domain) for test scenario generation."</i> <i>"I have made significant progress in designing the metamodel used to define test scenarios."</i>
Q5 Answer	The research is still on preliminary stages, so that there are several future works to be performed - the most important of which the development of the research itself. <i>"As a long-term objective, I may also integrate the Gazebo simulator in order to handle other kinds of autonomous cyber-physical systems (e.g. robots). The above integration steps will allow me to generalize my approach to various autonomous vehicles and cyber-physical systems."</i> <i>"Being a first-year PhD student, I plan on completing the integration of CARLA into the VIATRA MG by the end of 2020. My objective is to generate a basic test suite for autonomous cars, run the generated tests within CARLA and gather some basic safety metrics data (e.g. if a scenario simulation caused a collision) as a proof of concept.</i> <i>Once the initial CARLA integration is complete, I will be ready to work on RQ1 and RQ2. Specifically, until mid-2022, I plan to develop a formal definition of situation coverage, and to validate the proposed definition by performing experimental evaluation on existing system-level test suites for autonomous vehicles.</i> <i>Following this, I will address RQ3 and implement a novel scenario generation approach that guides generation towards scenarios with high situation coverage. The developed approach will be accompanied by experimental evaluation, similar to the proposed solution for RQ2. According to my current plans, I expect to complete my PhD research by the end of the year 2023."</i>
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) Research still on preliminary stages and related to safety assurance of AI-based autonomous vehicles by means of tests. Marginally related to the DSc. subject.

8.171 REFERENCE [620]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present a novel verification framework for an unknown dynamical system from a given set of noisy observations of the dynamics by abstracting the system as an uncertain Markov process with discrete states defined over the safe set.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning on Interval Markov Decision Process.
Q3 Answer	<i>"This work aims to develop a verification method that can provide safety guarantees for systems with unknown dynamics."</i> <i>"A powerful approach to approximate an unknown function is Gaussian process (GP) regression. GP regression is a Bayesian machine-learning framework, which has been receiving special attention in safety-critical applications due to its ability to capture the uncertainty in the learning process."</i> <i>"(...) we focus on the safety verification of control systems with unknown dynamics via GP regression. We introduce an algorithm that, given a set of noisy data, generates formal probabilistic guarantees for the unknown system to remain in a given safe set for every initial state. These guarantees are with respect to an arbitrary control policy. The algorithm uses a discretization of the safe set and GP regression to construct a finite abstraction with probabilistic bounds. This abstraction is in the form of an uncertain Markov model that captures all possible behaviors of the unknown system through a derivation for the error bounds between the regression and underlying system. Then, the algorithm determines the safety probability bounds for the unknown system by performing safety verification on the abstraction."</i> <i>"(...) the regressed GP may not accurately approximate the posterior of Process (1) (i.e. the new outputs of the system) since the observation noise v is not Gaussian, i.e., v is bounded and the fact that only a finite amount of data is available. A correction term that captures this discrepancy is required."</i>
Q4 Answer	<i>"We evaluate the performance of our framework in three case studies. The first case study involves three single-action linear systems (...). The second case uses two of the linear systems to define a switched system with two actions. The final case considers the safety a nonlinear system."</i> The results presented by the authors for all three case studies consider a limit of time steps for the system to remain safe and a choice of an error hyperparameter (epsilon) equal to 0.12 except for the first case study, in which this parameter varies

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 283 / 550	

	within the set {0.08; 0.09; 0.10; 0.12}.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The approach tries to model a complex system with unknown dynamics by means of a Gaussian Process regression which follows an interval Markov decision process, hence establishing lower and upper boundaries for safety probabilities based on data uncertainty. An additional error function is added to the regressed model in order to account for non-Gaussian errors. Mathematical foundations are sound.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The case studies presented by the authors seem quite simple and were constrained to small time intervals, which are not sufficient for the safety assurance of real-world systems. In addition, several hyperparameters of the proposed model were chosen by the authors without further justification.</p>

8.172 REFERENCE [621]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To propose a novel forward reachability analysis method for the safety verification of linear time-varying systems with neural networks in feedback interconnection based on semidefinite programming to abstract the nonlinear activation functions by quadratic constraints, which leads to an outer-approximation of forward reachable sets of the closed-loop system.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "<i>DNNs can be vulnerable to small perturbations or adversarial attacks. This issue is more pronounced in closed-loop systems, as a small perturbation in the loop can dramatically change the behavior of the closed-loop system over time.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>Safety verification or reachability analysis aims to show that starting from some initial conditions, a dynamical system cannot evolve to some unsafe region in the state space. Methods for reachability analysis can be categorized into exact (complete) or approximate (incomplete), which compute the reachable sets exactly and approximately, respectively.</i>"</p> <p>Basics: "<i>The goal of this paper is to develop a methodology, based on semidefinite programming, for safety verification and reachability analysis of linear dynamical systems in feedback interconnection with DNNs.</i>"</p> <p>"<i>(...) we propose a semidefinite program (SDP) for reachability analysis of linear time varying dynamical systems in feedback interconnection with neural network controllers equipped with a projection operator, which projects the output of the neural network (the control action) onto a specified set of control inputs. Our technical approach relies on abstracting the nonlinear activation functions as well as the projection operator by quadratic constraints, which leads to an outer-approximation of forward reachable sets of the closed-loop system. We show that we can compute these approximate reachable sets using semidefinite programming. Our approach can be used to analyze control policies learned by neural networks in, for example, model predictive control (MPC) and constrained reinforcement learning.</i>"</p>
Q4 Answer	" <i>We illustrate the utility of our approach in two numerical examples, in which we certify finite-time reachability and constraint satisfaction of a double integrator and a 6D quadrotor system.</i> "
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitation: "<i>In this paper, we consider ReLU activation functions in our technical derivations but we can address other activation functions following the framework of [576].</i>"</p> <p>"<i>In this paper, we use polytopes and ellipsoids to represent sets. Nonetheless, as addressed by [576], other sets such as hyper-rectangles and zonotopes can also be used.</i>"</p> <p>Future work: "<i>Future work includes extending the current approach to incorporate nonlinear dynamics and to approximate backward reachable sets, which is useful for certifying invariance properties.</i>"</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) In line with other studies related to safety verification of neural networks, notably [576], sharing a similar mathematical basis.</p> <p>2) Stresses out clearly the safety concept considered by the authors.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 284 / 550

8.173 REFERENCE [630]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To provide insights into a safety assurance procedure and its application in an Autonomous Vehicle (AV) solution, focusing on the safety assurance of solutions incorporated within the AVs themselves.
Q2 Answer	AI was not clearly mentioned throughout the research.
Q3 Answer	The authors propose a high-level process for the safety assurance of autonomous vehicles (AVs) used in factories. The process follows steps which are similar to those of current, non-AI-oriented standards.
Q4 Answer	The authors present a case study applying the proposed safety assurance process to the design of a Smart Autonomous Mobile Units (SAMU) used within factory areas. The whole process is exercised with proper evidence. However, technical details regarding quantitative safety assurance have not been provided, since a test-oriented approach was the only evidence presented by the authors.
Q5 Answer	The authors stress out that their SAMU is a proof-of-concept only and that legislation and metrics related to the safety assurance of autonomous vehicles still need to improve.
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) No explicit mention to AI; 2) Safety assurance with little formal evidence to support that the development is sufficiently safe.

8.174 REFERENCE [632]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To design, develop, and evaluate a machine learning-based approach for predicting the collision risk of autonomous vehicles with other road users based on a planar 2D collision model.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning (decision trees and random forests) and explainable AI.
Q3 Answer	The authors have developed a risk prediction model based on classification/regression trees and random forests. The risk for collision is defined based on the following features: 1) No risk if the distance between two vehicles is above 10m; 2) Non-zero risk if the distance between two vehicles is less than 10m. The risk is calculated based on a Gaussian distribution and considering the behavior of vehicles in 1s, 3s and 5s from the current state. Explainability from random forests is extracted based on the median behavior of all trees within the forest.
Q4 Answer	The authors perform a case study by using data from the Lyft Level 5 Prediction Dataset (images of 1118 hours of 20 vehicles; 20 25-second scenes with 1Hz-collected frames). The authors have verified that random forests lead to better performance and extracted variables with the most contribution to the risk inference process. The risk inference engine provides the risk class conclusion, its reasoning and the main reasons why the complementary result is not adequate.
Q5 Answer	The following future work is suggested by the authors: 1) Usage in other applications; 2) Usage of other datasets.
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) Expert knowledge to define the risk functions has not been justified. 2) The authors do not present evidence of AI safety analysis. Strengths: 1) Good example of explainable AI based on trees and random forests.

8.175 REFERENCE [634]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To illustrate the analysis of a complex system in terms of functional safety and Safety Of The Intended Functionality (SOTIF) with the model-based Component Fault Tree (CFT) methodology through a self-driving toy vehicle, the PANORover.
Q2	Deep neural networks.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 285 / 550	

Answer	
Q3 Answer	The PANORover performs automated braking and collision avoidance ADAS within the context of Autonomous Driving. Sensing functions rely on deep neural networks. The authors claim that, in order to perform the safety analysis of AI, they "(...) need to extend safety analysis techniques in order to create cause-effect relationships for individual failures as well as for functional insufficiencies and system hazards for the specified system. In a CFT model both failures and functional insufficiencies can be represented".
Q4 Answer	The authors do not present any evidence of their CFT model and its results.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) Short paper with nothing but a proposal of using Component Fault Trees to perform the safety analysis of AI-based systems. No results are presented or discussed.

8.176 REFERENCE [637]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To propose an autoencoder and time series analysis–based anomaly detection system, called DeepGuard, to detect safety-critical inconsistent behaviour of autonomous vehicles at runtime and trigger healing strategies to prevent them.
Q2 Answer	Deep neural networks and autoencoders.
Q3 Answer	"(...) we introduce an autoencoder and time series analysis–based approach to predict the potential inconsistencies in ADS due to unexpected driving contexts. Our proposed approach is called DeepGuard, which is based on a reconstruction-based technique to monitor the driving behaviour of ADS. Based on the different levels of reconstructed error, different levels of required safety guards are applied to ensure the safety of the ADS. DeepGuard observes the increasing trends in reconstruction error (e) over time, which can tackle the potential inconsistencies in the behaviour of ADS by detecting unexpected driving conditions and by activating safety guards such as a decrease in speed, applying the emergency brake, and safe disengagement of autonomous mode before the violation of the safety properties." SELFORACLE is also based on autoencoders and time series analysis for inconsistencies detection, whereas DeepRoad uses Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for the same purpose. SELFORACLE provides mitigation actions only when an unsafe scenario is detected, whereas DeepGuard does the same based on a potential predicted violation instead. "(...) we focus on the prevention of two safety–critical inconsistent behaviours of ADSs: (1) vehicle collision and (2) lane departure (...)"
Q4 Answer	"To evaluate the proposed approach, we deploy DeepGuard on three existing DNN based ADSs: Chauffeur (Team Chauffeur 2016), Epoch (2016), and Nvidia’s DAVE-2." "We used the Udacity simulator for autonomoucars to evaluate the performance of our proposed approach using open-sourced ADS models. To create unexpected driving conditions (such as raining driving conditions, dense fog, heavy snowfall, and snow on the road) in our simulation, we used a modified version of the original Udacity simulator developed by SELFORACLE. The best-performing variant of DeepGuard can predict 93% of the inconsistent behaviours. In our comparative analysis, we found that the DeepGuard approach outperforms SELFORACLE and DeepRoad in terms of model performance as well as the safety-guard approach to ensure the safety of the ADS." Dataset: "We collected the dataset under nominal driving conditions. A dataset of 120,624 training images at 12 fps from all three tracks was obtained. Overall, we collected 34,160 images from Track 1 (Lake), 45,214 from Track 2 (Jungle), and 41,250 from Track 3 (Mountain). During the training, we recorded the training images with driving parameters such as speed, brake, and throttle. The speed of the car in the training mode was set at 30 m/h (i.e., mile/h)." "To generate the evaluation data, we collected data from all three tracks in eight different conditions (e.g., rain, fog, day/night cycle, rain at night, etc.). We first executed a simulation similar to the training set without injecting the anomalous driving conditions to record the false alarm rate. Then, we executed the simulations by injecting anomalous conditions such as rain, snow, fog, and day/night cycles." Safety Requirements: "The definition of safety-critical inconsistent behaviour in our approach is that the car

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 286 / 550	

	collides with the roadsides, and the second one is that the car no longer follows the center of the lane."
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitations:</p> <p>1) "The first threat to the validity of DeepGuard is that we generated unexpected driving conditions in a customized manner in the simulation environment. (...) this issue can be resolved by considering a large amount of training data during the training of DeepGuard."</p> <p>2) "Another threat to the validity of DeepGuard is that we tested it only on three ADS models. (...) We tried to minimize this limitation by considering only real world best-performing ADS models (i.e., EPOCH, CHAUFFEUR, and DAVE-2)."</p> <p>3) "Finally, unusable real data can be a threat to validity of our approach. (...) The simulation-based scenario testing allows testing of a large number of unseen and unsafe driving conditions in a safe way."</p> <p>Future Work:</p> <p>"Our future work will focus on generalizing the DeepGuard approach to predict potential inconsistent behaviour in the urban driving scenario, as well as designing more generalized safety guards. We are able to predict inconsistent behaviour of ADS on which the DeepGuard is attached. However, we are also interested in predicting the inconsistent behaviour yield by front cars on highways. More specifically, in platooning driving systems, the inconsistent behaviour of vehicles may lead to the collision of the entire platooning system. Therefore, our future work will also focus on predicting the inconsistent behaviour of the front car in the platooning system and activating the safety guards to prevent collisions."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting architecture which uses AI to ensure safety of AI-based components. It can be reused in other applications.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors wrongly claim that their solution is based on unsupervised learning when it is, in fact, supervised.</p> <p>2) No safety assessment of AI-based components has been performed.</p>

8.177 REFERENCE [640]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present means to conceive a safe, adaptive neural network based on genetic algorithm to update the neural network.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks and genetic algorithms.
Q3 Answer	The authors have developed means to update a neural network with genetic algorithm in order to ensure convergence and bounding on response limits.
Q4 Answer	No further evidence regarding results other than the model itself have been presented by the authors.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach to build an adaptive neural network with safe boundaries.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No further comments regarding the bounding of the adaptive neural network even under failure scenarios have been provided.</p>

8.178 REFERENCE [642]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present a black-box testing approach for image-based deep machine learning models by means of SVM ensembles.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning / deep learning in general and SVMs.
Q3	"A kind of black-box testing method based on support vector machine linear approximation is characterized by

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 287 / 550	

Answer	the following steps: (1) Obtain the image sample dataset model and pre-train the black-box deep learning model; (2) Construct several SVM basic classifiers according to the obtained sample data set; (3) Define several data source-level mutation operators according to several SVM basic classifiers; (4) Calculate the safety upper bound of several data source-level mutation operators; (5) The safety evaluation of the safety upper bound ranking of several data source-level mutation operators."
Q4 Answer	"Compared with state of the art art, the benefit of the present invention is: For existing deep learning safety testing method, propose a kind of linear approximation based on support vector machine model The black-box testing method has good applicability, can effectively test the safety of the model, and find possible existence in the risk range."
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Interesting approach to use AI in the back box test of deep learning components. Weaknesses: 1) No discussion on usage within non-image-based models; 2) Not clear how the SVMs themselves are ensured to be sufficiently safe based on their training and mutation.

8.179 REFERENCE [644]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present a safety analysis method for AI-based systems, including explainability and performance evaluation.
Q2 Answer	AI in general.
Q3 Answer	"1 . An artificial intelligence evaluation method integrating multi-dimensional information, wherein the method comprises: Generate a list of evaluation items according to the field of the artificial intelligence product to be evaluated, and retrieve the original samples corresponding to the evaluation items. In the safety evaluation preparation stage, after the corresponding evaluation algorithm and the corresponding original sample data are retrieved, the robust operation is performed. The related algorithms of susceptibility and adversarial aggression, generate corresponding evaluation samples and store them; Check whether the evaluation samples required for the safety evaluation have been generated, and if so, prepare for the interpretability evaluation; The interpretability evaluation includes two evaluation methods: model-based interpretability and model-independent interpretability. If the interpretability of the product is strong, the interpretability of the model is evaluated based on the characteristics and parameters of the model itself; if the model itself If the interpretability is poor, the interpretability evaluation of artificial intelligence products is carried out through auxiliary algorithms and samples; According to the strength of the interpretability of the artificial intelligence product to be evaluated, different evaluation algorithms and corresponding algorithms are selected. After the original sample data is calculated, check whether the evaluation content required for the interpretability evaluation has been generated. According to the application scenario of the artificial intelligence product to be evaluated, the accuracy of its algorithm is adaptively evaluated, including: The original sample data of the accuracy evaluation is divided into two parts, which are respectively used for the accuracy evaluation in the training stage and the actual prediction stage. Accuracy evaluation and generate the corresponding evaluation content, check whether the evaluation content required for the accuracy evaluation has been generated. According to the performance indicators in the evaluation item list, configure the same local server as the performance indicators, and deploy all The artificial intelligence product to be evaluated is described; the safety evaluation and interpretability of the artificial intelligence product are carried out according to the content prepared above.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 288 / 550	

	<p>evaluation, accuracy evaluation and performance evaluation; among them, in the safety anti-attack evaluation, it is required to test the maximum cost of the attack. Power-Minimum Tolerable Success Rate Deviation≤ 0.1; Record safety assessment results, interpretability assessment results, accuracy assessment results, and performance assessment results and generate evaluation report.</p> <p>2 . The method according to claim 1 , wherein, in the robustness evaluation, according to the original sample The physical changes of the data and the appearance changes of the sample data are used to obtain the robustness evaluation results. In the process of obtaining the physical changes, add up to 10% of the evaluation samples in the test data set to participate in this test, and the robustness evaluation result is attack Post-algorithm accuracy-original algorithm accuracy≤ 0.07.</p> <p>3 . The method according to claim 1 , wherein, in the evaluation of anti-attack property, a method based on anti-attack is utilized.</p> <p>4 .The adversarial samples generated by the algorithm are used for attack testing, which requires the maximum success rate of the test attack-minimum tolerance of the success rate deviation ≤ 0.1, the maximum success rate is that when the generated adversarial samples are used to attack the evaluation samples, the success of the attack makes the Evaluate the probability of misjudgment of artificial intelligence products.</p> <p>4. The method according to claim 1, characterized in that, in the process of evaluating the accuracy, for binary classification Algorithm, the baseline requirement is $AUC \geq 0.75$; for multi-classification algorithm, micro-average F1 or macro-average $F1 \geq 0.20$; for regression algorithm method, $RSD \leq 0.1$.</p> <p>5 . The method according to claim 2 , wherein, in the process of evaluating the accuracy, if the two points If there is a statement of accuracy in the class algorithm, multi-class algorithm, and regression algorithm, the accuracy evaluation results are compared with the statement.</p> <p>6 . The method according to claim 1 , wherein the evaluation standard for the performance index: when a single prediction is made Time ≤ 10min, batch prediction time ≤ 1h and $TPS \geq 20$.</p> <p>7 . The method according to claim 6 , wherein, in the process of evaluating the performance index, if the to-be-to-be If there is a performance indicator statement for the evaluation artificial intelligence product, the performance indicator result of the evaluation is compared with the performance indicator statement."</p>
Q4 Answer	"Although the present invention has been described in detail with reference to the foregoing embodiments, those of ordinary skill in the art should understand that: Of course, the technical solutions described in the foregoing embodiments may be modified, or some or all of the technical features may be modified. These modifications or replacements do not make the essence of the corresponding technical solutions deviate from the technology of each embodiment of the present invention scope of the programme."
Q5 Answer	See the answer to Question 4.
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Very interesting approach to deal with the safety analysis of AI-based systems. Weakness: 2) Performance measurements have been predefined with specific figures at the method, even though variations depending on the application would be expected. This is highlighted by the authors in their shortcomings.

8.180 REFERENCE [650]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present a robust deep learning model based on a redundant architecture including Support Vector Machines.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning / deep learning in general and SVMs.
Q3 Answer	"Steps: Assign a support vector machine to each classification class of the deep learning model used for the

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 289 / 550	

	<p>classification task;</p> <p>Input the sample data to the deep learning model and each support vector machine respectively, and get the sample data in the deep learning model type and feature space distribution of each SVM;</p> <p>For each support vector machine, the feature space distribution of sample data in the support vector machine is compared with that in the deep learning model. The divergence index of the feature space distribution is used as the loss function to optimize the parameters of the support vector machine;</p> <p>After the optimization, the decision boundary of each support vector machine is the score of the deep learning model corresponding to the support vector machine. The decision boundary of the class category, according to which the robust boundary evaluation of the deep learning model is realized.</p> <p>(...) When optimizing the parameters of the support vector machine, the directional resampling method is used to determine the search direction for each sample data. When the feature distribution is close, that is, the value of the loss function becomes smaller, it will continue to move in the direction of the last resampling, and vice versa.</p> <p>(...) the deep learning model is used for image classification and signal classification, and the sample data is image data and signal data.</p> <p>(...) For each candidate deep learning model, the deep learning model based on the support vector machine (...) is used. The robust boundary evaluation method for degree learning models determines the decision boundary of each deep learning model. According to the decision boundary, the classification of each target class by the deep learning model is determined to screen the deep learning model.</p> <p>(...) For the deep learning model, the robust boundary evaluation method of the deep learning model based on support vector machine (...) is used to determine the decision boundary of the deep learning model for each target class. According to the decision boundary of each target class, determine the target class that is easily attacked;</p> <p>Add perturbation to the sample data corresponding to the easily attacked target class to obtain enhanced sample data, and use the enhanced sample data. The sample data is used to optimize the parameters of the deep learning model to realize the defense of the deep learning model against easily attacked target classes."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"Compared with state of the art, the beneficial effect that the present invention has at least includes:</p> <p>The deep learning model robust boundary evaluation method and device based on support vector machine provided by the invention are deep;</p> <p>Each classification category of the learning model is assigned a support vector machine, and the support vector machine is calculated according to the distribution state of the feature space.</p> <p>Evaluate the decision boundary of the support vector machine as the decision boundary of the deep learning model. The safety of the deep learning model, at the same time, corresponds to the obtained decision boundary, which can be used as the basis for the selection and defense of the deep learning model,"</p>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach to use AI in the back box test of deep learning components.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Not clear how to demonstrate that the combination of the deep learning models with the SVMs themselves can be ensured as sufficiently safe.</p>

8.181 REFERENCE [662]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present a hazard analysis approach based on STPA to capture and evaluate SOTIF-related hazardous factors of IRDAS. SOTIF: Safety of the Intended Functionality IRDAS: Intelligent Railway Driving Assistance System
Q2 Answer	AI in general.
Q3	The proposed approach is intended to capture hazards stemming from SOTIF, and since AI can generate such

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 290 / 550	

Answer	<p>hazards, AI is covered by this means.</p> <p>The authors present a case study to identify SOTIF hazards by applying STPA to it. In order to do this, "(...) the feedback part of the control structure in STPA is extended for better modeling the complex sensors and AI algorithms, and a new classification of causal scenarios is proposed to identify the SOTIF-related causal scenarios." The authors have built "(...) the STPA feedback structure with the four elements of sensing, understanding, deciding, and acting, and the three-level model is used to describing the understanding process", whose levels are defined as follows: "(...) level one is the perception of the elements in the environment, level 2 is the comprehension of the elements and their meanings, and level 3 is the projection of future status." Afterwards, a network-based approach is used to establish the causal relationship among hazards and their effects, so as to aid the identification of the most critical system hazards by objective, quantitative metrics.</p> <p>Specifically with regard to AI, the following reasons for hazards have been identified:</p> <p>Level 2 - Comprehension of Elements and their Meanings:</p> <p>a) Matches of the structure and a priori knowledge of environmental model with the real operational environment, to find incompleteness, incorrectness and uncertainty;</p> <p>b) The uncertainty of learning algorithms in different operational environments, including aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties.</p> <p>Level 3 - Prediction of Future Status:</p> <p>a) The performance parameter of sensors compared with particular operational environments.</p> <p>b) The deficient setting and algorithm of sensors compared with particular operational environments.</p> <p>c) The improper feedback or guidance from understanding or deciding parts in some particular operational environment.</p>
Q4 Answer	The authors present a case study whose aim is to identify SOTIF-related hazards to a IRDAS system used in Hong Kong. On this IRDAS, AI is used on the processing of environmental data (cameras, LiDAR and radar), which will generate distances towards objects (cameras and LiDAR) and speed measurements (radar) so as to locate the system within the line and detect obstacles.
Q5 Answer	"In future work, we plan to study the cognitive process of the driver in complex driving processes, to find a way to form a more systematic mental model of the driver. This could provide more insights into the analysis of driver misuses. In addition, after a long period of operation, if sufficient operational data can be collected, the statistical quantitative strengths of cause–effect relationships in the HFN can be calculated. Then, the HFN can be changed into a weighted network, within which more targeted hazard control strategies can be developed."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach for the hazard analysis of AI-based systems, including quantitative analyses.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) AI has not been directly explored by the authors so far, as the case study example does not expand much on AI.</p>

8.182 REFERENCE [663]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To develop created a test dataset, called Coyote, with photographs that can be understood correctly by humans but might not be successfully parsed by current state-of-the-art image recognition systems used in typical computer vision approaches on autonomous vehicles.
Q2 Answer	Deep learning; deep neural networks; convolutional neural networks.
Q3 Answer	The authors have conceived their so-called Coyote dataset to potentially misguide computer vision algorithms used in autonomous driving applications by stressing them with typical adversarial attacks.
Q4 Answer	The authors employ their Coyote database onto two computer vision systems, called YOLOv3 and Faster R-CNN. The results indicate that many adversarial examples within the Coyote database were misinterpreted by the computer vision systems. Most of the time, though, errors leaned towards safe situation (reognition of a false obstacle).
Q5 Answer	<p>Future work comprises the following themes:</p> <p>"Sensor Fusion: For example, data fused from camera and lidar systems might indicate that an image of a person on the back of a van is flat and therefore cannot be real, thereby reducing false positives. However, if</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 291 / 550	

	<p>vision system detects a person ahead with high confidence and lidar does not, what must the AV act conservatively to preserve human life?</p> <p>Common Sense Reasoning: Work is being done on simulation-based reasoning systems that aim to synthesize understanding of a domain. It is conceivable that such systems could be extended to recognise, for example, that a photograph of the head of a person is not actually a person.</p> <p>Better Treatment of Scale: Depth and scale are important factors for humans in distinguishing real items from artificial ones; e.g. a car decorated to look like a cat. Current CNNs rely to a large extent on textures and patterns and are designed to be scale-invariant.</p> <p>Spatio-Temporal Reasoning: While a single image of a mural may look realistic to a human, when viewed over time from slightly different viewpoints, it rapidly becomes clear that it is 2D. This requires Spatio-temporal reasoning that is beyond the capacity of current systems.</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>Most obviously, the Coyote dataset can be extended by adding more images. (...) In addition, the images could be annotated with bounding boxes and pixel-level semantic annotations. Such fine-grained ground truth will be used in localization of objects detection which is critical information for autonomous vehicles. Further work will be done on increasing the number of images by increasing the challenging scenarios; e.g. occluded objects such as a person occluded under an umbrella, the field of views from each object, and by capturing it from a camera within a vehicle itself. Additionally, other forms of data(such as LiDAR, multiple Cameras, FishEye, GPS, temporal consistency between frames, etc.) can be brought in context to analyse how much the additional information can support the autonomous vehicles in such challenging scenarios."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting work in developing databases specifically to check the response of a safety-critical AI-based system to adversarial attacks.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The Coyote database deals with a single application; hence, future work to extend its underlying principles to other types of application in addition to image processing would be needed.</p>

8.183 REFERENCE [664]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a Phenomenological Lane Detection Model (PLDM) to simulate camera performance for autonomous vehicles lane detection.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors aim to mitigate issues of previous research on lane detection "(...) by fitting lane marking detection errors. It is based on statistical models using real-time vehicle measurement data collected in real-world tests. As the camera sensing algorithm is highly confidential, it is impossible to determine primary factors driving the detection error from extensive vehicle data. Therefore, feature selection is introduced, removing the data containing redundant or irrelevant features without losing informative features. In this study, the lane detection error model is constructed from the MLP. One of the main advantages of the MLP is the capability of simulating both linear and nonlinear relationships between the parameters. Meanwhile, the trained MLP is applied to estimate the output from new input data in the virtual simulation environment."</p> <p>"Vision-based lane detection is influenced by different factors that contain external environmental parameters (e.g., lane line reflectivity, appearance, and lighting conditions, etc.) as well as vehicle dynamic performance (e.g., speed and heading angle, a departure from the road centerline, etc.), resulting in discrepancies between detection results and the ground truth. (...) According to the guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement, the detection result of the camera can be stated as the best reference quantity plus the measurement uncertainty [39], where uncertainty can be treated as the detection error, and it is estimated by using an NN-based approach in this paper. Finally, a phenomenological camera model is proposed to approximate real-world camera detection performances."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"In order to train the MLP model, the data gathered by the various devices are synchronized, and 9010 samples were selected from collected data to optimize the model. Input data are randomly separated into three sets: training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%)."</p> <p>Polynomial regression results lead to R² of at least 0,94 for the output parameters of interest. The authors have also compared their neural network with other machine learning techniques (support vector machines, linear</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 292 / 550	

	regression, gaussian regression, ensemble boosting and stepwise regression) and noticed that their neural network had better performance.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Application of AI to aid the safety assurance of an AI-based safety-critical system with potentially good results. Weaknesses: 1) No cross-validation has been used to determine the neural network hyperparameters. 2) No strong evidence to support the lack of underfitting and overfitting except for the results of the simulated case study on the same track from which real data came has been provided.

8.184 REFERENCE [666]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present a methodology which was developed to address issues of safety and security in the design and implementation of cyber-physical production systems in collaborative environments.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	The authors present a general framework for defining requirements and assessing risks. No AI-related aspects have been covered within the paper.
Q4 Answer	The authors present a hypothetical case study of a system whose aim is to collaboratively assemble a product in a human-robot environment.
Q5 Answer	Limitations were not covered by the authors. Future work: "Future work will therefore look at how possible solutions may simultaneously affect both cyber as well physical aspects. Furthermore, the system designed during this research will be implemented within a laboratory condition such as to further evaluate the safety and security capabilities of the CPPS."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: Negligible impact on the safety assurance of AI-based systems.

8.185 REFERENCE [667]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To provide a new approach to synthesize controllers for nonlinear continuous dynamical systems with control against safety properties based on neural networks (NNs) and to provide safety certification evidence by means of barrier functions, which are represented by NNs as well within a verification-in-the-loop synthesis.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	"A common practice is to first come up with a controller and then to verify it against desired properties. An interesting innovation of our work is, however, to integrate the synthesis and verification in a unified, data-driven framework. (...) At a high level, our approach for the controller synthesis will produce two neural networks simultaneously, i.e., one is used to represent the controller (henceforth referred to as controller-NN), and the other is used to represent the barrier function (henceforth referred to as barrier-NN). The synergy of the two NNs, supported by an additional verification procedure to make sure the learned barrier-NN is indeed a barrier certificate, provides the desired safety guarantee for the synthesized controller. Our method follows a data-driven framework in the sense that both NNs are trained from datasets. For that purpose, we generate training sets and propose specifically designed loss functions which are the key towards the application of standard learning algorithms for NNs. (...) To further improve the synthesized controllers, we propose a number of approaches such as imposing a larger safety region, stability-aware loss functions, and bounded control inputs (via the Hardtanh activation function)." "To overcome the limitation of data-driven approaches, i.e., the generalization issue of the learned NNs on non-sampled data, formal verification (by SMT solvers in this paper) is performed on the synthesized candidates to show that the barrier certificate conditions are indeed satisfied."
Q4	The authors present their model contextualizing it on a controller that shall control car steering with constant

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 293 / 550

Answer	velocity to track a path. Other examples are explored (inverted pendulum, Duffing oscillator, bicycle steering, Academic 3D). "In terms of the learned NN controllers, we find that they usually respect safety constraints, but may exhibit poor performance in terms of, e.g., stability."
Q5 Answer	"Future work includes experimenting on different sampling and training strategies to reduce the data set size and to improve the training efficiency, as well different verification methods/tools other than interval SMT solvers. In particular, we plan to combine the counter-example-driven framework for program analysis with our proposed approach. Recently, the counter-example-guided inductive synthesis procedure (CEGIS) has been employed in NN barrier certificates generation for continuous and hybrid systems with no control input. We anticipate that these would potentially further improve the scalability of our approach. We also plan to extend our approach to other properties such as reachability coupled with cost/reward based optimality as what has been done in optimal control and reinforcement learning."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Interesting approach to solve the problem of safety verification of neural networks by means of a redundant verifier also based on neural networks and provable as correct by means of exact approaches (e.g. SMT). Weaknesses: 1) Some of the models' hyperparameters (e.g. activation function, loss function, number of restarts, learning rate, number of epochs, tolerances, layer structure) are defined by the authors without additional justification except for the fact that they 'make verification easier'. 2) The provided explanations are not clear.

8.186 REFERENCE [668]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To introduce RiskStructures, an algebraic framework for risk modelling intended to support the design of safety controllers for risk-aware machines.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	The authors have conceived a formal risk modelling strategy, based on a formal language, which allows describing the behavior of a safety-critical controller by means of probabilistic actions. Each probabilistic action translates to a transition from one system state to another, including states with proper operation, mitigation of potentially unsafe situations and the effective occurrence of unsafe scenarios.
Q4 Answer	The authors present detailed demonstrations of their models, including lemmas and corollaries, and also include didactic case studies depicting the usage of the "RiskStructures" method and analyses on the potential benefits of the latter to deal with compositional abstraction and uncertainties.
Q5 Answer	Limitations were not covered by the authors. Future work: "The further development of our framework will include its extension to more general and more refined forms of risk factors; the elaboration of probabilistic factor semantics; the investigation of more specific mitigation orders, the construction of risk lattices from risk spaces, mitigation orders, and event structures; the development of analysers for risk estimation and synthesizers for safety controllers; the derivation of RiskStructures from dynamical models; the further discussion of factor characteristics such as compatibility; the investigation of distributivity of composition and constraints; and a mechanisation and extension of further proofs using a specialised proof assistant such as Isabelle/UTP."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Formal method to support the design and the verification of systems which perform real-time risk assessment. Since AI can be used with this purpose, the method is worth remarks. Weakness: 1) There is no direct mention to AI; 2) Uncertainties are at most quantified based on expert information and do not receive feedback from operation.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 294 / 550	

8.187 REFERENCE [669]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To explore the limitations of traditional test coverage techniques for systems with General-Purpose Operating Systems (GPOS) and to provide two complementary methods to pave the way towards the testing of Linux-based complex safety-related systems.
Q2 Answer	No direct mention to AI. Machine learning-based systems are considered as one of the potential method's beneficiaries, but this is covered in a circumstantial way only.
Q3 Answer	"The current publication provides two complementary contributions in the area of statistical test coverage analysis. On the one hand, we describe a statistical analysis method that estimates the test coverage with the remaining uncertainty. In other words, the described method statistically estimates the maximum number of kernel execution paths that an application can exercise in order to calculate the number of not-covered or untested execution paths. On the other hand, to advance in the estimation of the residual risk of these systems as a result of the untested or not-covered paths, we examine a method that calculates the execution probability of the not-covered paths." The method is based on dynamic code analysis, i.e., information regarding the assessed system is extracted during its operation. The research focuses especially on software path coverage.
Q4 Answer	The authors present a case study in which their method is applied to the control unit of an Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB) system, which utilizes Linux kernel (version 4.9) and machine learning algorithms. The AEB system's control unit rated as SIL2, is fully based on Linux (version 4.9). The authors have successfully applied their methods and reached the conclusion that, under conservative hypotheses, Linux x4.9 does not meet its SIL2 safety target for the AEB's control unit based on data collected during 6000 hours of operation.
Q5 Answer	Limitations and suggested future work include the following topics: 1) "(...) it is necessary to continue investigating which estimator fits more appropriately to this type of system. For this purpose, we should examine the estimators with other use-cases and with other system-context. For instance, we believe it would be interesting to investigate the estimators' variability with the same application but different system-context (e.g., different CPU loads)." 2) "(...) we have entirely focused on the system-call exercised by the SIL2 task, leaving aside small pieces of inter-calls. Since the obtained technical results seem promising, further analysis needs to be carried out to include the kernel function-calls that occur between system-calls. We believe that this can be achieved by sampling on internal kernel functionality in much the same way as we have sampled on the kernel's system-call interface." 3) "(...) we believe it is interesting and necessary that the described methods undertake a thorough review by additional safety experts (...) we believe that these methods may be potentially valid for other OSs or software layers, although we cannot confirm it as the analysis has not been conducted."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) The idea of assessing the impact of COTS operating systems over safety by means of dynamic analyses is interesting and worthy of ifuture research; 2) Background related to current standards drawbacks on AI are relevant. Weaknesses: 1) The safety analysis method is based on AI, and the authors have not provided sufficient evidence that the AI elements used on their method are sufficiently safe for the purpose; 2) The safety analysis method relies on dynamic analysis tools, which have not been indicated as sufficiently safe for the purpose of the research; 3) The relationship between the operating systems and AI has not been made sufficiently clear.

8.188 REFERENCE [670]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To introduce a model-based collision prediction method that uses discretized Gaussian processes for future vehicle position estimation suitable for real-time deployment and computational intensive applications, such as simulation and training of Deep Learning and Reinforcement Learning models.
Q2	No direct mention to AI. Deep learning and reinforcement learning-based systems are considered as the

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 295 / 550

Answer	potential method's beneficiaries, but this is covered in a circumstantial way only.
Q3 Answer	"The trajectory prediction model consists of three main components: a Graph Convolutional Network module to extract spatial relations of vehicles, a Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) module to capture temporal correlations, and a decoder module to predict stochastic future trajectories."
Q4 Answer	The authors present two case studies. "The first scenario shows the future stochastic position method in a highway merging setting; the second scenario demonstrates the collision prediction method in a collision setting caused by a blind spot." "The numerical examples illustrate that the proposed method is efficient, scalable and explainable. These benefits are obtained with a single random variable Gaussian process framework, grid discretization, and road layout information."
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) Some aspects of the model are overly approximated (e.g. $\sin(x) = x$ for x on $[-\pi/2; \pi/2]$). This means that $ \sin(x) $ can be over 1, introducing an error of over 70% in its value. 2) The model was implemented in Python, and no evidence of its safety assurance has been provided. 3) The authors have not provided sufficient evidence to ensure the model's explainability, notably with regard to uncertainties.

8.189 REFERENCE [671]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To propose a game theory-based interaction-aware framework for highly automated vehicles safety evaluation which is suitable for some highly-interactive driving scenarios including highway merging and roundabout entering.
Q2 Answer	Game theory, reinforcement learning, deep neural networks, Gaussian regression.
Q3 Answer	"To capture a wide variety of interactions between the primary other vehicle (POV) and the vehicle under test (VUT), we characterize the interactive behavior using level-k game theory and social value orientation and train a diverse set of POVs using reinforcement learning. Moreover, we propose an adaptive test case sampling scheme based on the Gaussian process regression to generate customized and diverse challenging cases." "This is the first effort to comprehensively identify the failure modes of a VUT in an interactive scenario." "(...) we assume that the POVs are game-theoretic agents, which take the (near) optimal action according to its utility function and assumptions of the opponents."
Q4 Answer	"(...) we focus on the highway merging scenario, but this methodology can be applied to other scenarios including roundabout entering, turning at unsignalized intersections, etc." "We make the following assumptions for simplification: 1) The POV and the VUT do see and interact with each other through the simulation horizon. 2) The POV is not able to change lanes to yield to the VUT; the VUT can only merge at the merge point M, which is the origin for the lane-fixed coordinates for both the ramp and the main lane. 3) There is only one POV on the main lane and there is no vehicle in front of the VUT on the ramp. 4) The scenario ends when the VUT reaches point M." "It out-performs other sampling methods according to the failure mode coverage (FMC) metric."
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) The adaptive testing approach conceived by the authors can be adopted in other applications, provided that changes to application-specific features are made. Weaknesses: 1) The method, however, might not provide sufficient evidence for complex systems, as it does not solve the problem of needing many test cases to cover all potentially relevant scenarios for the operation of a safety-critical system. 2) Some parameters used in the case study were defined without further justification on the importance of the specific figures to the application.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 296 / 550	

8.190 REFERENCE [672]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a method of hazard and risk analysis which investigates hardware failures, environmental perception limitations, human interaction and functional requirements for artificial intelligence for highly autonomus vehicles.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors present an interative application of a Hazard and Risk Assessment (HARA) approach based on HAZOP with quantitative features. For machine learning (ML) elements, the approach is adapted based upon the Layer of Protection Analysis (LOPA) methodology, as ML cannot be well modeled by means of functional safety characteristics.</p> <p>Basics: "(...) we utilise a three step process (...) consisting of vehicle and ADS systemisation, then HAZOP-style hazard identification and followed by a semi-quantitative risk assessment (AV-LOPA) which is used to drive specification of safeguarding requirements. Due to the experimental nature of our vehicle systems and iterative design approach, this process is repeated as features and modifications take place, including the additions of safeguards themselves."</p> <p>"Assignment of ASIL levels is dependent on the consequence, probability of exposure and additionally the controllability, which refers to the ability for human intervention to rectify a situation in view of system failure. This results in two issues: naive application of the ASIL classification assuming all scenarios are uncontrollable results in the requirement for high ASIL of high-level control systems and secondly it fails to credit redundant systems which can provide Independent Protection Layers (IPL)."</p> <p>"Each independent protection layer must fulfil the following criteria: 1) Independence: It should not have failure modes (e.g. shared sensors) common to other safeguards used in the scenario. 2) Effectiveness: Each IPL must be able to fully mitigate the hazard. 3) Validation: Each IPLs functionality must be able to be assured and maintained."</p>
Q4 Answer	The authors present two case studies: one is related to the Autonomous F-SAE Race Car and the other one is based on the nUWY Shuttle Bus. Specifically in relation to AI-based elements, the following actions were included in the safety verification process: model validation through simulated testing, model supervision through diverse architectures, and model supervision through hard-coded constraints.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) The hazard and risk assessment method is good reference for usage in any application with AI-based systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) The authors have only covered the very first steps of an AI-based system lifecycle and did not discuss other limitations (e.g. other means to specify and perform V&V of AI-based safety-critical systems) and potential for future work (new applications, more in-depth analysis of the case studies, etc.).</p>

8.191 REFERENCE [673]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To design and implement a predictive safety filter that is able to maintain vehicle safety with respect to track boundaries when paired alongside any potentially unsafe control signal, such as those found in learning-based methods.
Q2 Answer	No direct mention to AI. The authors claim that safety-critical systems with AI/ML can benefit from their research.
Q3 Answer	"A model predictive control (MPC) framework is used to create aminimally invasive algorithm that certifies whether a desired control input is safe and can be applied to the vehicle, or that provides an alternate input to keep the vehicle in bounds. To this end, we provide a principled procedure to compute a safe and invariant set

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 297 / 550	

	<p>for nonlinear dynamic bicycle models using efficient convex approximation techniques. To fully support an aggressive racing performance without conservative safety interventions, the safe set is extended in real-time through predictive control backup trajectories."</p> <p>"The basic idea is to design a safety filter, which analyzes the desired control signal and decides in real-time whether it can be applied to the system, or if it has to be modified to ensure safety."</p> <p>"We assume an accurate model and state estimate of the system is available in this work; however, extensions of predictive safety filters considering system uncertainty can be found (...)"</p> <p>A predictive safety filter "(...) computes a discrete-time state and input backup trajectory $\{x_i^* k, u_i^* k\}$, of length N, where $x_i k$ is the state predicted "i" time steps ahead, computed at time k, initialized at $x_0 k = x(k)$, and similarly for $u_i k$. The system is predicted along the horizon according to dynamics, subject to an initial condition, state and input constraints, and terminal constraint. Different from classical MPC, the objective function is chosen to minimize the difference between the desired control input and the first input of the solution trajectory (...)". The authors' solution is based on Lyapunov stability verification.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"For the racing application considered in this work, this [safety filter] consists of verifying if the vehicle is able to stay within track boundaries in the future given the current steering and drivetrain commands."</p> <p>"Applications for assisted manual driving and deep imitation learning on a miniature remote-controlled vehicle demonstrate the safety filter's ability to ensure vehicle safety during aggressive maneuvers."</p> <p>"To achieve a minimally invasive safety filter supporting aggressive maneuvers, we use a nonlinear dynamic bicycle model with a Pacejka model of the tire forces to simultaneously predict and optimize accurate backup control trajectories. In addition to a high-fidelity system model, the safety filter performance can be improved by using either a longer planning horizon or a larger terminal set. As the planning horizon is typically limited by memory and processing requirements, we derive an iterative optimization-based invariant set computation using convex approximations to obtain an enlarged terminal safe set for the nonlinear dynamic bicycle model, which is valid over a range of constant road curvatures.</p> <p>The physical miniature racing application demonstrates the proposed safety filter's performance with both human-in-the-loop racing and deep imitation learning. This work presents, to the best of our knowledge, the first application of a predictive safety filter to a complex and highly dynamical nonlinear system demonstrated by experimental results."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitations: "We assume an accurate model and state estimate of the system is available in this work; however, extensions of predictive safety filters considering system uncertainty can be found (...)"</p> <p>No suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting method to ensure safety by construction. The examples include the assurance of safe actions in case of unsafe inputs.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The system is still susceptible to faults which can corrupt the implementation of the predictive safety filter;</p> <p>2) Predictive safety filters are very application-specific.</p>

8.192 REFERENCE [675]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a plug-and-play safety framework that can be applied together with high-performance control algorithms, e.g., emerging from learning techniques.
Q2 Answer	No direct mention to AI. The authors claim that safety-critical systems with AI/ML can benefit from their research.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Modeling and control of large-scale safety-critical distributed systems, such as power grids, supply chains, or telecommunication networks, is a challenging task due to the complexity of the interactions among subsystems, the necessity of taking decisions solely based on local knowledge, and the need to guarantee system operation within physical and safety constraints."</p> <p>Based on this context, the authors present "(...) a framework for plug-and-play (PnP) safe learning, i.e., a framework that prevents constraint violation at all times, both while learning and during plug-in/out</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 298 / 550	

	<p>operations." They "(...) employ robust control invariance at the core of the framework", and "the proposed approach consists of two phases. In the first (offline phase, the safe sets are computed in a distributed fashion. In the second (online) phase, the inputs generated by the learning algorithm are analyzed and possibly modified by the safety framework if they would cause the system to violate constraints at any time in the future. To further account for possible topology changes during safe online learning, we propose a PnP procedure".</p> <p>"As soon as a plug-in (out) request is received, the future (current) neighbors of the agents placing the request recompute their local safe sets considering the new system dynamics. If the recomputations succeed, the agents move to the transition phase; otherwise, the PnP request is denied. In the transition phase, a trajectory to safely steer the system state from the old to the new safe sets is computed. If the trajectory exists, it is tracked using a tube-based tracking controller, and the PnP operation is permitted; otherwise, the PnP operation is denied."</p> <p>"Conservatism is introduced (...) depending on various factors. First, the shape of the safe set is chosen to be an ellipsoid. While a different choice can lead to less conservative solutions, e.g., polytopes that can describe nonsymmetrical invariant sets, they come at the price of higher computational cost. Another source of conservatism is related to the fact that the shape of safe set is fixed, and only the level sets are updated, since a real-time update of the set shape is computationally demanding."</p> <p>"Note that the combination of the presented safety framework with a learning algorithm can slow down convergence and potentially lead to chattering behavior induced by modifications of the learning input. (...) The convergence of a learning algorithm together with a safety framework is, however, still an open research question and out of the scope of this article."</p> <p>Restrictions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "(...) we assume ellipsoidal uncertainty sets facilitating computation of the safe sets (...)" 2) "Nonlinear systems can be conservatively approximated by the linear model as long as the error with respect to the true system can be bounded (...)"
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors have presented four case studies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Vehicle platooning control with 10 vehicles; b) A hypothetical non-linear system described by a set of equations; c) A large-scale system with 100 elements; d) Plug-and-play safety assurance of a system comprising 5 elements and the addition of a 6th element. <p>The results presented by the authors corroborate that the proposed approach yields safe results.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ellipsoidal uncertainty sets have been assumed for computational simplicity. The authors claim that this assumption introduces more conservatism to the model than with other approaches.; 2) Linear approximation of non-linear systems has been considered assuming that a bounded difference between the former and the latter is known; 3) "Note that the combination of the presented safety framework with a learning algorithm can slow down convergence and potentially lead to chattering behavior induced by modifications of the learning input. (...) The convergence of a learning algorithm together with a safety framework is, however, still an open research question and out of the scope of this article." <p>No suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting method to ensure safety on dynamic systems with learning algorithms. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The system is still susceptible to faults which can corrupt the implementation of the predictive safety filter; 2) Models are application-specific.

8.193 REFERENCE [676]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose an Adaptive Design of Experiments (ADOE) method to evaluate the safety of autonomous vehicles. Two different ADOE approaches are presented, each of which for different testing purposes.
Q2 Answer	Supervised machine learning in general.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 299 / 550	

Q3 Answer	<p>The authors "(...) propose an Adaptive Design of Experiments (ADOE) to facilitate automatic vehicle evaluation" since exhaustive field or simulated tests are unfeasible.</p> <p>"Rather than determining all concrete scenarios to test at once, ADOE starts from a limited number of cases. Based on the results of the initial batch of concrete scenarios, a surrogate model (SM), also known as meta-model/response surface model, is fitted to approximate the time-consuming AV evaluation process. Any supervised machine learning models (e.g., Linear Regression, Support Vector Regression, etc.) that meet the following requirements can be used as a SM: (1) it can be fitted with a small number of samples, and (2) it can quickly predict the test results of a large number of concrete scenarios.</p> <p>With the guidance of SM, new concrete scenarios are determined sequentially. In each iteration of the experiment design, a new concrete scenario is selected from a set of randomly generated candidate scenarios. To determine which concrete scenario to test next, an acquisition function is adopted. The purpose of the acquisition function is to tackle the trade-off between selecting the most possible dangerous concrete scenarios (exploitation) and exploring the most unexplored concrete scenario to improve the quality of the surrogate model (exploration). The SM is used to calculate the values of the acquisition function for each candidate scenario. Thus, we are able to obtain a reference regarding the next concrete scenario to test for the AV." The latter approach, oriented by SMs, is more recommended "for testers with insufficient test resources on hand and with tolerance for less accurate test results (e.g. 90% detection precision for dangerous scenarios) (...)".</p> <p>A scenario-oriented approach, has the following steps: (1) initialization, (2) SM hyperparameter adjustment, (3) SM update, (4) stopping criteria calculation and (5) selection of next scenario if the stopping criteria is not met in (4).</p> <p>The SM-oriented approach is similar to the former, but "(...) it focuses on depicting the boundary between safe and dangerous concrete scenarios, rather than directly finding and testing dangerous scenarios. The stopping criteria and the principle of selecting the next concrete scenario are modified in the SM-oriented approach, while other modules remain unchanged."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"Logical scenarios of different scales were considered. One logical scenario is a 3-dimensional car following scenario for ease of interpretation and visualization, while the other is a 6-dimensional cut-in scenario. The objective is to prove the portability of the proposed ADOE in various cases of different level of parameter dimension complexity. Two ADOE approaches were examined, and the performance of different surrogate models were compared in both logical scenarios."</p> <p>"Based on test results of these two logical scenarios, one can conclude that ADOE is effective in both logical scenarios in terms of capturing enough dangerous concrete scenarios within short periods of time. Although two ADOE approaches have strengths in different aspects, they both achieved desired performance. Scenario-oriented ADOE made full use of each exact AV test runs, capturing one dangerous scenario per 1.1 test runs on average in both logical scenarios. SM-oriented ADOE successfully depicted the boundary between safe and dangerous scenarios by establishing SMs that found more than 90% of the dangerous scenarios with about 90% precision while using no more than 1% of the test resources needed for enumeration. The proposed ADOE can be utilized in various situations with different test requirements.</p> <p>Optimal SMs for the two ADOE approaches were selected based on the observations of the case study results. XGB (Extreme Gradient Boosting) are recommended for both approaches."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"Some future research directions include (1) making further improvements to acquisition functions; (2) establishing more representative and test-worthy scenarios to test HAVs; (3) adopting ADOE for Worst-Case Scenario Evaluation; and (4) integrating SM-oriented ADOE with Monte Carlo Simulation or Importance Sampling methods to assess collision rates in shorter periods of time, and (5) these two logical scenarios and the crash model we used to measure the severity of collision are not of high-fidelity. We try to convey key concepts with simple test cases, and more tests need to be done with professional software."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting approach by using machine learning to leverage test coverage whilst reducing computational costs. The research is backed up by convincing case studies.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The safety analysis method is based on AI, and the authors have not provided sufficient evidence that the AI elements used on their method are sufficiently safe for the purpose;</p> <p>2) No degraded modes (i.e., caused by faults) have been directly assessed through the proposed method.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 300 / 550	

8.194 REFERENCE [682]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To provide a survey of state-of-the-art safety validation techniques for Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) with a focus on applied algorithms and their modifications for the safety validation problem, focusing on optimization, path planning, reinforcement learning, and importance sampling.
Q2 Answer	Optimization (including evolutionary algorithms), planning, (deep) reinforcement learning, supervised learning,
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "There are several reasons why validating cyber-physical systems is challenging. First, many of these systems contain complex components, including those produced by machine learning. The safety properties of these systems may not be well-understood and subtle and emergent failures can go undetected (Yeh, 2018). Second, many systems, such as autonomous cars and aircraft, interact with complex and stochastic environments that are difficult to model. Third, safety properties are generally defined over both the system under test and its environment. For example, the requirement that "the test vehicle shall not collide with pedestrians" involves both the system under test (test vehicle) and actors in its environment (pedestrians). As a result, safety validation must be performed over the combined system. Another challenge is that sequential interactions between the system and the environment means that failure scenarios are trajectories over time, and therefore the search space is combinatorially large. Finally, safety validation is often applied to mature safety-critical systems later in development, where failures can be extremely rare."</p> <p>"White-box methods (..) for example, formal verification in the form of model checking and automated theorem proving (...) often has difficulty scaling to large problems." "Black-box methods can be applied to a much broader class of systems because they do not require a system specification. (...) Due to its flexibility and scalability, black-box validation is often the only feasible option for large complex systems, and is the focus of this survey."</p> <p>"There are many algorithms that have been used for these safety validation tasks. (...) Falsification and most-likely failure analysis are related tasks in that they involve finding failures of an autonomous system. Categories of algorithms that are suited for these tasks include optimization, path planning, and reinforcement learning. Optimization approaches seek to find a trajectory of disturbances that cause the system to fail. Path planning approaches use the environment's state to aid in the exploration of possible failure modes. Reinforcement learning frames the problem as a Markov decision process and searches for a policy that maps environment states to disturbances that cause the system to fail. When the goal is to estimate the probability of failure and failures are rare, importance sampling techniques generate scenarios and translate their results into a probability estimate. For all of the safety validation tasks, a major challenge is scalability, so problem-decomposition techniques are presented that can allow for better scalability of the presented algorithms."</p>
Q4 Answer	The authors have provided an extensive description of algorithms and tools which can be used to aid black-box testing based on optimization, planning and reinforcement learning strategies.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) In-depth analysis of black-box testing for safety-critical cyber physical-systems with AI. Techniques, algorithms and tools are presented with good detail and in a well structured way.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) There is no conclusive discussion on how to ensure that AI-based techniques for black box testing are sufficiently adequate to produce evidence for the safety assurance of a system. Circumstantial arguments towards this are presented, though.</p>

8.195 REFERENCE [684]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present the results of a systematic review of peer reviewed literature on the risks associated with Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), including philosophical discussions, applications of modelling techniques, and assessment of current frameworks and processes.
Q2	Artificial intelligence in general.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 301 / 550

Answer	
Q3 Answer	<p>Concept: "Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) is the next generation of artificial intelligence (AI) (...) which has previously been defined as an agent's ability to achieve goals in a wide range of environments and the ability to achieve complex goals in complex environments. (...) Whilst, AGI does not currently exist, it is expected to arrive sometime this century."</p> <p>"The risks associated with AGI are generated by the challenge of controlling an agent that is substantially more intelligent than us".</p> <p>"The risks identified in the articles can be broadly categorised as follows: AGI removing itself from the control of human owners/managers, AGIs being given or developing unsafe goals, development of unsafe AGI, AGIs with poor ethics, morals and values, inadequate management of AGI, existential risks."</p>
Q4 Answer	Please refer to the answer to Question '3', as the identification of AGI risks through the SLR is the main result of the paper.
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitations: "First, there was a scarcity of modelling techniques applied to investigate risks associated with AGI. Second, there was a limited number of studies that focused on the AGI risks in specific domains. Third, the lack of information regarding the AGI systems considered in terms of specifications, goals and tasks raises questions about the validity and comprehensiveness of the risks identified. Fourth, there was a limited amount of peer reviewed literature on the risks of AGI. Finally, there is a lack of consensus on the terminology used within AGI research. It is concluded that there is a critical need to address the multiple issues identified in the current review."</p> <p>Future work: "(...) it is essential that we have reliable, valid, and rigorous research to guide safe AGI design, implementation and management."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>The paper is mainly philosophical and its discussions are around AGI, which has not established so far and is deemed unlikely by many researchers.</p>

8.196 REFERENCE [686]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To complement design-time assurance with run-time monitoring that calculates the confidence that design-time assumptions related to the behavior of learned components in previously unseen environments are satisfied and, therefore, design-time guarantees continue to hold.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Several arguments for run-time assurance articulated the need for comprehensive self-assessment of mission progress by an autonomous system. (...) confidence can be improved by predictive safety monitoring, which takes into account future behaviors, and combining monitors with state estimators, which account for perception/control uncertainties within a limited time horizon."</p> <p>"The drawback we see in these monitoring approaches is that they do not take into account all of the hard work that went into design-time assurance of those models; instead, they try to estimate the confidence in the mission progress directly from the observations. In this paper, we are advocating for a different approach to run-time assurance, one that builds upon modern model-based verification technologies. The question we are asking at run time is: based on what we observe, how confident are we that our verification guarantees still imply that the system will succeed in its mission?</p> <p>Our approach investigates, at design time, how the design-time verification guarantees can be invalidated at run time. (...) we consider the hazards introduced by the limitations of design-time verification technologies. Specifically, we focus on the assumptions that are by necessity made at design time to enable verification. If an assumption is violated, the guarantee may become invalid as well."</p> <p>"We note that a violated assumption does not, by itself, mean that the mission is compromised. However, as long as the assumptions are not violated, we know that design-time guarantees hold. Therefore, if we identify all the assumptions subject to violation, our confidence in them can be used as a lower bound on the probability that the system's mission is on track."</p> <p>"Our focus on violations of design-time assumptions allows us to break the problem into two sub-problems and</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 302 / 550	

	<p>address the challenges in a systematic way.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first sub-problem is to determine how assumption violations influence requirement violations and elicit a logical relationship that takes only relevant assumptions into account. 2. The second sub-problem is to calculate a confidence measure for each assumption, reflecting the probability that the assumption holds, and to compose these confidence measures into an overall assurance measure for the current mission, according to the logical relationship in the first sub-problem." <p>1. "We elicit this relationship using the assumption effect analysis, establishing a logical structure for composing confidence monitors of individual assumptions into a system-wide assurance monitor."</p> <p>2. "Produced by our probabilistic analysis, each of the assumption monitors outputs a logical verdict v (i.e., whether the assumption is satisfied), as well as a level of confidence c in the verdict." "Generally, a broad range of state estimators, such as Kalman and particle filters, and probabilistic models, such as Bayesian nets, can be used for this purpose. In some cases, a component may already have a monitor that produces a confidence estimate in its correct operation. For example, neural network classifiers often produce a confidence in the classification outcome."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"Consider a simple example of an autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) that inspects a pipeline on an ocean floor. This example was used as a case study in the Assured Autonomy program funded by DARPA. (...)</p> <p>We assume a scenario where design-time assurance for such a mission is provided by formal closed-loop verification. In our case study, we modeled the AUV and its environment as a hybrid system and used the tool Verisig to perform reachability analysis of the system model and verify that the mission requirements are satisfied. Such analysis is subject to a number of assumptions. In particular, we had to assume that the physical dynamics of the AUV have been accurately captured by the model; that is, the response of the vehicle to an actuation command is within a certain error bound of the model's prediction. Further, the perception component, itself implemented using a neural network, was too complex to be included in the model for verification. Instead, we assumed that it always provides an accurate readings—also up to an error bound—of the AUV's distance and heading relative to the pipeline. These assumptions are likely to be violated at run time."</p> <p>"(...) we intend to monitor the operation of learning-enabled components that process the readings from the forward and side sonars and compute control commands, as well as how the vehicle responds to the control commands. From these observations, we intend to compute an estimate of the probability that the design-time verification results apply; namely, that the AUV will neither lose the pipeline nor collide with an obstacle."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitation: "We are currently in the process of implementing this vision in case studies of autonomous systems. These case studies will help us better understand the kinds of assumptions that can be effectively monitored and improve confidence composition techniques, as well as evaluate the utility of the proposed vision."</p> <p>Future Work:</p> <p>"(...) we plan to extend our recent work on logical composition of stochastic detectors, which are run-time monitors that deliver Boolean verdicts with probabilistic guarantees in terms of false positive and false negative rates. This framework allows us to develop composite detectors that are based on formulas of a temporal logic—and derive probabilistic estimates of their performance. Since assurance monitors also perform logic-based composition, we expect them to be realizable in our framework. In addition, we intend to represent the framework with fitting representations of dependencies between monitors, such as covariances/correlations, conditional probabilities, odds ratios, and copula functions. These representations can be learned at design time from training data and simulations or possibly estimated at run time."</p> <p>"There are several aspects of dynamic assurance that the described approach does not yet handle: Confidence-Based Adaptation. For autonomous systems it is not enough to detect that the confidence in the mission progress is unacceptably low. Ideally, the system needs to react to the potential problem in a way that would restore the confidence or potentially abort the mission in order to save the vehicle from being lost. Several approaches loosely based on Simplex architecture have been proposed [4]. The difference in our case is that reactions are triggered not by fault detection but by a drop in confidence. Such a reaction requires that we not only detect the problem, but also identify its causes. Here, this identification may be supported by the multi-level compositional structure of the assurance monitor. Extending our framework to support confidence-driven adaptation is another important research direction."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 303 / 550	

	<p>Predictive Confidence. The meaning of confidence introduced above relies on the satisfaction of design-time assumptions up to the current moment. However, if the assumptions are confidently satisfied now, we should intuitively be confident in safety in the immediate future. So far we have not explored the relationship between the level of confidence and the time horizon for safety. It also will be an important avenue of our future work. Making an explicit connection to a time horizon for safety may also allow us to reduce conservatism in our confidence estimate. As discussed in the first two sections, a violation of design-time assumption does not necessarily mean that a safety violation is imminent. Thus, the confidence in the satisfaction of the assumptions is expected to be lower than the confidence in system safety. This lower bound may turn out to be quite conservative and cause false alarms. One possible way to achieve a tighter connection between assumptions and safety confidence is to incorporate predictive monitors in our confidence calculation.</p> <p>Confidence vs. Robustness. We may be able to establish a connection between our notion of confidence and robustness of safety satisfaction. The idea is that, if the system operates near the boundary of the safety region, a small perturbation can make it unsafe. And since we cannot reliably observe small perturbations, our confidence cannot be too high in this situation. Therefore, a high confidence may probabilistically guarantee some minimal distance from the boundary. This is a promising yet challenging direction of research because formally, confidence and robustness are related through complex verification and monitoring models."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Meaningful research towards the safety assurance of AI-based systems during operation.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) The research is still on its initial stages, and results are still not available for analysis.</p>

8.197 REFERENCE [687]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present an approach for developing a stringent safety argumentation for AI-based perception functions by means of a risk-based approach in which an assurance case is constructed by an evidence-based safety argumentation.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general. Case study exemplified with Deep Neural Networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Specifically, we propose to build the safety argumentation for deep neural network (DNN) based perception by systematic consideration of DNN specific safety concerns." "It consists of three major blocks: 1. Specification and development steps of the AI-based function. 2. Safety measures and metrics being applied to specific steps and 3. Safety argumentation making use of the evidences provided by the measures and metrics."</p> <p>"A formal assurance case argumentation in GSN (Goal Structured Notation) is then developed that shows that the safety measures being applied provide sufficient evidence, measured in quantitative and qualitative metrics, that the risks raised by the DNN insufficiency and DNN specific safety concerns are mitigated to a tolerable level such that the safety requirements are fulfilled."</p>
Q4 Answer	The main result of the research is the presented method itself. Some steps are contextualized within automotive examples, but without detail of their actual application. The paper's reference [13] directs towards a proof-of-concept.
Q5 Answer	"One of the central challenges in the project will be to jointly identify and evaluate assurance methods in the evidence workstreams that can be used as a base for suitable evidences. Harmonization with upcoming standards and AI regulations will be a further step."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Main ideas are very similar to Safety ArtISt;</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) Main steps are just outlined and miss techniques for performing them.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 304 / 550	

8.198 REFERENCE [688]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To report on lessons learned from an experimental analysis on the conformance ratios of Uber ATG/Aurora Safety Case Framework (SCF) with ANSI/UL4600 and structural analysis following the argument structure of the SCF.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	"The SCF is a safety case for SDVs by then Uber ATG. The entire safety case is provided as a web page with GUI, which helps in viewing and browsing the entire argument structure represented in Goal Structuring Notation (GSN)." "The following are assumptions and limitations of the SCF, as explained in the SCF: – The SCF is not for an SDV but Self-Driving Enterprise which may include the entire management and operating system for SDVs, – “SDV is a modified production vehicle that complies with all safety and regulatory requirements” (from a context associated with the top goal in the SCF), – “SDV is used for rideshare operations in a defined Operational Design Domain” (from a context associated with the top goal in SCF)."
Q4 Answer	"We consulted industry experts who are specialized in functional safety, (SOTIF) Safety of The Intended Functionality [6] and SDVs on our analysis results. We provided them a check sheet (Table 1) and asked them to provide comments. The overall response to our results was positive due to detailed analyses on the conformance relation between 4600 and the SCF, which they think would help to understand 4600 and the role of a safety case for substantial documents for future certification of their own SDVs. They expressed difficulties in assessing the results due to terminology mismatch between the two and lack of correct understanding of 4600, but provided helpful comments to improve our assessment results."
Q5 Answer	Limitations have not been discussed by the authors. "Future work includes investigation on the general criteria for conformance evaluation which does not rely on subjective expert judgements and the general argument structure for SDV."
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) The authors provide the results of a comparison between Uber ATG/Aurora's Safety Case Framework and ANSI UL/4600, but do not present detailed results. AI is marginally covered during this process.

8.199 REFERENCE [689]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a safety assurance approach based on argumentative patterns for safety-critical functions based on machine learning. The paper focuses on autonomous vehicles applications.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, focusing on supervised learning only ("classification", as per the method's "domain analysis" phase).
Q3 Answer	"Of particular interest for the work were the aleatoric uncertainty inherent in the environment in terms of the manifold factors that can impact the acoustic signal as well as the epistemic uncertainty introduced by the machine learning models themselves. Safety assurance must demonstrate that the system performance is able to satisfy the safety goals, despite these potential sourced of inadequacies." "An additional factor increasing the difficulty of assuring safety is the issue of the semantic gap by which the lack of a precise definition of the functional and performance requirements leads to an inadequate definition of safety requirements (...)." The authors have defined an iterative safety assurance process with four main phases: 1) Domain analysis to "(...) include a thorough investigation of the operational domain and understanding of aspects of the environment that can lead to misclassifications." 2) Design phase to refine the domain analysis requirements to "(...) either primary functions or diagnostic and monitoring mechanisms", including potential failure modes. 3) Validation, including means to assess specification completeness, sufficient coverage of environmental conditions that can result into insufficiencies and minimize unknown events; 4) Assurance case construction by means of Goal Structured Notation (GSN).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 305 / 550

Q4 Answer	The authors present a case study in which sound sensors are employed to assess chassis control and aid in its performance optimization. Adaptive Generalized Learning Vector Quantization (AGLVQ) has been selected as the machine learning technique of the case study system due to its robustness to input perturbations (needed for the case study application) and explainability.
Q5 Answer	<p>"Open questions nevertheless remain on the required level of granularity in the domain model used to evaluate the completeness of selected training data as well as quantitative test stopping criteria related to statistical performance metrics. Inevitably, an iterative approach to system development and assurance will be required where field-based validation is required to confirm that sufficient detail in the domain model was achieved and that assumptions made during analysis, simulation and test were valid. (...) The approach used within the project was to use qualitative arguments to argue the robustness of the ML function with respect to a broad range of operating conditions as defined by the domain model, whilst applying a range of measures (including extensive structured field tests) to confirm the assumptions behind the domain model. (...) an external evaluation of the assurance approach by a qualified third party is recommended to examine the strength of the provided arguments."</p> <p>"The project highlighted the need for better industry-specific standards regarding the use of ML for safety-relevant functions, including outside of the domain of automated driving. These standards should include specific guidelines for determining coverage and selection criteria for training data, as well as for determining quantitative performance targets and testing criteria. These aspects would become even more relevant by alternative choices of ML technique, such as Deep Neural Networks, where qualitative arguments relating to therobustness and generalization properties of the trained functions are more difficult to generate based on the complexity and opaqueness of the calculations involved. As such, any future standardization should also include a differentiation of measures based on the intrinsic characteristics of the ML algorithms."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization of current issues related to the safety assurance of AI-based systems, including gaps for future work. 2) Basic safety assurance process is relevant for future research. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The research is still on a preliminary phase, in which little evidence to support safety assurance of the case study has been developed and detailed.

8.200 REFERENCE [690]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present a technique for the verification of system-level properties for systems characterized by interaction between programs and neural networks by means of a two-way integration of a program and a neural-network analysis formalized in a general framework based on abstract interpretation.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks and reinforcement learning (case study).
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we make the first step in verifying safety of heterogeneous systems, and more specifically, of programs invoking neural networks. Existing work on verification of neural networks has either focused on the network itself (e.g., with respect to robustness) or on models (e.g., expressed using differential equations) that invoke the network, for example as part of a hybrid system. In contrast, our approach is designed for verifying safety of a C (or ultimately LLVM) program interacting with the network. In comparison to models, C programs are much more low-level and general, and therefore require an intricate combination of program and neural-network analyses. (...) By treating the neural-network analysis as a specialized abstract domain of the program analyzer, we are able to use inferred invariants for the neural network to check system properties in the surrounding program."</p> <p>"(...) the controller analysis invokes the neural-network analysis instead of simply abstracting the call to the neural network by havocking its return value. The invariants inferred by the controller analysis in the pre-state of the call to the network are passed to the neural-network analysis; they are used to restrict the input space of the neural network. In turn, the invariants that are inferred by the neural network analysis are returned to the controller analysis to restrict the output space. This exchange of verification results at analysis time significantly improves precision. By making the program analysis aware of the network's computation, neuro-aware program analysis is able to prove challenging safety properties of the entire system."</p>
Q4	"We evaluate our approach on 26 variants of Racetrack, a benchmark from related work that originates in AI

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 306 / 550

Answer	<p>autonomous decision making. Racetrack is about the problem of navigating a vehicle on a discrete map to a goal location without crashing into any obstacles. The vehicle acceleration (in discrete directions) is determined by a neural network, which is invoked by a controller responsible for actually moving the vehicle.(...) we show the effectiveness of our approach in verifying goal reachability and crash avoidance for 26 Racetrack variants of varying complexity. These variants constitute a diverse set of verification tasks that differ both in the neural network itself and in how and for what purpose the program invokes the neural network."</p> <p>Racetrack "(...) consists of a neural network, which predicts the vehicle acceleration toward discrete directions, and a controller (implemented in C) that actually moves the vehicle on the map."</p> <p>"In our experiments, we use well (good), moderately (mod), and poorly (poor) trained neural networks."</p> <p>"We complicate the Racetrack benchmark by adding two sources of non-determinism, namely environment (env) and neural-network (nn) noise. Introducing such noise is common practice in reinforcement learning, for instance, when modeling real-world imperfections, like slippery ground."</p>
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good source of a method (including supporting tools) for the safety assurance of neural network-based systems.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Meaningful changes are needed to adapt the proposed approach for other AI categories.</p>

8.201 REFERENCE [691]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present a framework for understanding the risks associated with AI applications which directs attention to pertinent system properties with limited needs for accuracy by using AI safety principles to quantify the unique risks of increased intelligence and human-like qualities in AI.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>The main categories of AI safety problems identified during the research are "(...) avoiding negative side effects, avoiding reward hacking, scalable oversight, safe exploration, and robustness to distributional change." In addition to these, "(...) reliability, error tolerance, value specification, and superintelligence (...)" are also deemed worthy of future research because they also influence AI safety.</p> <p>- Avoiding Negative Side Effects: "This problem has to do with things that are done by accident or indifference by the AI.(...) To be able to avoid negative side effects, an agent has to understand the value of everything in its environment in relation to the importance of its objective, even things that the reward function is implicitly indifferent towards."</p> <p>-Avoid Reward Hacking: "Unless designed with safety measures to prevent reward hacking, the AI can find ways to increase the reward signal without completing the objective. (...) Agents that wish to hack their rewards can do so by breaking out of their containers, whether they are within simple training environments or carefully engineered prisons with defenses in depth. When researching a novel AI technology that has a risk of creating AGI, researchers must use safety measures to prevent potential AGI from escaping confinement. (...)</p> <p>Adversarial reward functions, where the reward function is learned and has a competing objective with the AI, can decrease reward hacking. Another mitigation strategy is the use of tripwires. For instance, if the AI gets a much higher score than expected, it can be assumed that it has broken containment and is modifying the reward directly. This can be used as a tripwire which, when triggered, deactivates the AI."</p> <p>-Scalable Oversight: "When dealing with AGI, scalable oversight is no longer an issue of data efficiency or human effort but of safety. At some point, the AGI will be intelligent enough that we are not able to tell if it is acting in our best interest or deceiving us while actually doing something unsafe. Scalable oversight is required to make AGI safe. One phrasing of a scalable oversight from the perspective of the AGI is "If the designers understood what I was doing, they would approve of it.'"</p> <p>- Safe Exploration: "(...) random action as a way to explore their environments (...) is effective, especially with a small environment and a very large amount of training time, but it is not safe for real world environments. Curiosity-driven exploration is able to efficiently explore (...) environments by using an intrinsic reward function based on novelty. This provides great benefits to the learner, but cannot ensure safety. (...) A backup</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 307 / 550	

	<p>policy which can take over when the agent is outside of safe operating conditions can allow for safe and bounded exploration (...). Safe exploration becomes more difficult with increased intelligence."</p> <p>- Robustness to Distributional Change: "AI that has been trained in one environment or dataset may fail when its use is greatly different from its training. This is the cause AI obtaining good accuracy on curated datasets but failing when put into the real world."</p> <p>"In AI safety, the designers knows what is and is not morally acceptable from their point of view. They then design rules for the AI to abide by while seeking its objective and craft the objective to be morally acceptable. The AI, however, only has access to the rules and not to the human values that created them."</p> <p>"To characterize the risk of an AI system, one factor is the dangers expressed by the larger system in which the AI is a component. "</p> <p>"The time delay between an AI creating an output and that output affecting the target is essential to preventing accidents."</p> <p>"For a given choice of target being controlled by the AI, there is maximum conceivable amount of damage that can be done by malicious use of that target. We use the figure as a cap as to the amount of harm possible. Most AI failures are not malicious, so the harm done by an accident will almost always be much less than this amount. This factor is very difficult to predict prior to an accident."</p> <p>"The final criteria for classifying the nature and degree of systems risk of an AI system are coupling, complexity of interaction, energy level, and knowledge gap."</p> <p>Based on the previous concepts, the authors present a risk assessment method which aims to estimate the potential risks of an AI-based system depending on its following features: timely intervention indicators, target of AI control, maximum damage caused by each element, coupling, complexity, energy level, knowledge gap, autonomy, goal complexity, escape potential, and AI anthropomorphization,</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors apply their risk analysis method to the following case studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Roomba House Cleaning Robots - Amazon's Recommendation Algorithm - Microsoft's Tay Twitter Chatbot
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings have not been discussed by the authors.</p> <p>Future work: "Application to real world systems and cases of applying our suggested measures to real world problems would further this work, providing insight into how our framework is and is not helpful in practice."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting risk assessment method which takes into account several characteristics that are typical of AI-based systems; <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Much of the research focuses on high-level risk assessment and does not take into account the safety assurance of AI implementation; 2) Parts of the risk analysis method are related to Artificial General Intelligence, which is still unfeasible in the short term; 3) Most of the case studies are not really safety-critical.

8.202 REFERENCE [692]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To address the problem of situation modeling and machine learning-based decision making in open and non-predictive environments by introducing an approach for decision-making using situation modeling and deep neural networks which uses an information structuring and representation technique for the generation of situation spectra used as input to deep learning-based decision making.
Q2 Answer	Convolutional and deep neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors have created a situational decision making approach using situation modeling and deep learning. Even though a generic architecture for this approach has been presented in Figure 1, the model created by the authors is detailed considering specificities of its application in autonomous vehicles.</p> <p>The basic model comprises six main elements: information extraction, situation model generation, decision-making, planning, and sub-goal definition. They are detailed as follows:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 308 / 550	

	<p>- Information extraction: "In order to generate a situation representation in the form of a situation model, the information extraction module acquires relevant information about the environment and the ego-system from the sensory inputs and system components. The object recognition is accompanied by radar-based verification. Furthermore, outlier detection is applied, and unrecognized objects are assigned to the class denoted as "other.""</p> <p>- Situation Model Generation: "(...) the situation model is the representation of an event or situation with a mental representation of a described or experienced situation". It comprises the following classes: environment, environment's characteristic, object, object's characteristic, object relationship, ego system, and ego system's characteristic. "The situation spectrum is defined as a graphical representation of the situation model and is provided as the input for the decision making process. The process to generate the situation spectrum is based on information structuring."</p> <p>- Decision-making: "The decision making process is based on a Convolutional Neural Network and follows, generally speaking, the same approach as for image-based object recognition."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"A simplified 2D driving simulator has been designed and implemented to perform a proof of concept of the presented approach. The simulator simulates highway driving, so the only environmental objects are other vehicles. The lane number is continuously three." "(...) it can be seen that the training is convergent and the validation accuracy is higher than 95%. Considering the fact that a very simple simulator is used for the data acquisition process and a simple, not optimized network structure is applied, the achieved results are excellent. These results underline the effectiveness, potential, and importance of the novel approach introduced."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "The simulator is oversimplified however, it has been rated to be sufficient to obtain the first data to test the introduced approach." Future work: "- How to define optimal image size and network structure considering the application domain-related requirements? - How does the situation complexity impact the validation accuracy, and which parameters contribute most to increase the accuracy rate? - How should the decision reliability be ensured in the context of safety-critical applications?" "More-complex environments and situations will be designed as the next step, and further tests will be performed using a state-of-the-art driving simulator."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses: 1) The paper is more directly oriented towards the usage of AI in safety-critical functions (Category 2) rather than towards the safety assurance of an AI-based system.</p>

8.203 REFERENCE [693]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To introduce the ReSonAte dynamic risk estimation framework for autonomous systems, which reasons over Bow-Tie Diagrams (BTDs) to capture information about hazard propagation paths and control strategies extended with attributes for modeling the conditional relationships with the state of the system and environment and estimating these conditional relationships and equations for estimating risk based on the state of the system and environment.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Our hypothesis is that we can use BTDs derived from the system information and static assurance cases and use them to compose the anomaly and the threat likelihoods at runtime, including the likelihood for the failure of Learning-Enabled Components (LECs)". "Under our formalism, each node has an associated function that is conditional on the state of the system and environment. Before constructing a BTD, we assume the following sets have been identified: all potential hazard classes H, all events E relevant for hazard analysis, barriers B which may either prevent a loss of control or recover after such a loss has occurred, possible system failure modes FM, and event severity classes SV. We also assume a function fa which maps each severity class to the maximum acceptable rate of occurrence threshold has been defined." "More environmental parameters may increase the fidelity of the model but also increases the required effort when determining conditional probabilities for events and barriers."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 309 / 550	

	<p>"Each BTM includes functions describing the conditional frequency for all threat events and the conditional probability of success for all barrier nodes. However, the likelihood of each consequence is necessary to estimate the overall level of risk for the system. These probabilities can be calculated by the propagation of the initial threat rates through the BTM. When a particular event occurs, barrier nodes reduce the probability that the event will continue to propagate through the BTM."</p> <p>"We treat the top event as a summation operation for all incoming edges, i.e. any threat event may independently cause a top event if the associated barriers are unsuccessful. All outgoing edges from the top event are treated as independent causal chains, i.e. any potential consequence may occur from a top event, independent of other consequences in the BTM."</p> <p>"When the system is deployed at run-time, observations about the current state can be used to refine the set of prior probabilities $P(s)$ and dynamically calculate current risk values. The equations outlined here use a discrete treatment of probability, but continuous distributions can be used as well where summation operations are replaced by an appropriate integration. If the state can be identified uniquely to a particular state s_0, then we can assign $P(s_0) = 1$ and simplify the risk equations."</p> <p>"In ReSonAte, both the rate of occurrence of events and the effectiveness of barriers may be conditionally dependent on the state including system failure modes, runtime monitor values, and environmental conditions. For each of these categories, it is necessary to identify the factors which should be examined for their impact on this conditional relationship. A failure analysis should be performed using an appropriate failure modeling language (...). Similarly, the environmental parameters relevant to the system must be identified and the operating environment defined in terms of bounds and expected distributions of these parameters. We assume the environmental conditions are known uniquely and provided to ReSonAte. Monitor values that may impact the conditional relationships should also be identified."</p> <p>"(...) using the risk estimated by ReSonAte the residual risk for each hazard can be updated dynamically at run-time and the associated goal in the assurance argument can be invalidated if the risk exceeds a predefined threshold. When this risk threshold is violated, contingency plans can be enacted to place the system in a safe state."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We implement ReSonAte for an Autonomous Vehicle (AV) example in the CARLA simulator and through comprehensive simulations across 600 executions, we show that there is a strong correlation between our risk estimates and eventual vehicular collisions. The dynamic risk calculations on average take only 0.3 milliseconds at runtime in addition to the overhead introduced by the system monitors. Further, we exhibit ReSonAte's generalizability with preliminary results from an Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUV) example."</p> <p>Simulation of AV: "An overall trend in the plot shows a strong correlation between the actual and the estimated collisions. Also, a visible trend is that the collision rate changes with the weather patterns, increasing for adverse weather conditions. However, the estimated risk tends to slightly overestimate when the collision rate is greater than 1.0". Moreover, the results with the dynamic risk assessment proposed by the authors has a lower collision rate and a higher likelihood when compared to data derived from static analyses.</p> <p>Simulation of UUV: "The efficiency of thruster 1 degrades to 60% at 45 seconds, and the estimated likelihood of collision increases to 0.25. Soon after, the contingency manager performs a thruster reallocation to improve the UUV's stability, the likelihood of collision decreases to 0.15."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: For the UUB simulation, "we are currently validating the estimated likelihood across large simulation runs."</p> <p>Future Work: "Future extensions and applications for ReSonAte include: (1) dynamic estimation of event severity in addition to event likelihood, (2) inclusion of state uncertainty into risk calculations to produce confidence bounds on risk estimates, (3) forecasting future risk based on expected changes to system or environment, (4) use of estimated risk for higher-level decision making such as controller switching or enactment of contingency plans, and (5) continuous improvement of conditional probability estimates at run-time from operational data."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting approach for the continuous risk assessment of learning-based safety-critical systems with the potential of posing no meaningful overhead on processing load. 2) Treats learning-based components as black boxes. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Depending on how the risk models are conceived on an application, the method might not be able to detect latent faults which might not immediately affect the system's risk but which can ultimately lead to a late

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 310 / 550

	detection of a high-risk scenario.
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8.204 REFERENCE [694]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present a novel data-driven approach to quantify events and situations which occur during recorded test drives by transforming multivariate time series data into a condensed, directed graph.
Q2 Answer	Supervised learning, unsupervised learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"What is needed is a procedure to quantify every moment of the recorded test drive and make it comparable to other moments, so recorded test drive scenes can be compared with already reconstructed scenes in the replay chain to check whether the situation is already covered by the simulation environment or not. The transformation procedure must be able to quantify the unlimited amount of data which is delivered by the reality and recorded by the sensors of the VMC into an abstract discrete and condensed representation that satisfies three requirements. First, the amount of remaining data needs to be small enough to be efficiently handled by computation devices. Second, the remaining data still needs to contain all relevant information about all passed situations. Third, the data requires a sufficient degree of abstraction that similar situations are recognized as that. (...) The second distillation step includes the central part of our contribution. The transformation of recorded sensor data into an appropriate representation. With this procedure, test drives and test cases can be transformed into a condensed representation and efficiently compared to examine the amount of coverage between each other. In the first step of the procedure, the recorded data of every sensor is individually scanned for potential cut points, which can serve as borders for the binning in the discretization process. In the second step, all collected borders are evaluated by a genetic algorithm to decide which bin borders are integrated in the final Parameter Discretization Model (PDM). The final PDM is a collection of bins for every individual sensor signal. In the third step the different sensor signals are discretized with the respective bins from the PDM. The result is a sequence of vectors which represent the whole recorded test drive. Every Vector represents a specific timestamp in the recording, representing a state with one entry for every sensor signal. In the last step of the procedure the sequence of vectors is transformed into a graph whereby every node refers to a single unique state. Every edge refers to two consecutive states in the sequence of vectors. The resulting graph is meant to satisfy the requirements mentioned above and is comparable with other graphs that have been created with the same PDM for direct coverage analysis."</p> <p>"We developed an approach for identifying and efficiently selecting potentially new and valuable traces from an input dataset. This Trace Selector contributes to an unsupervised and automated generation of an extensive test scenario catalog without redundancies.</p> <p>To distinguish between known and unknown traces, two compatible trace sets are compared. One dataset corresponds to traces that are all already known and tested, called Base-Data. The other dataset shall be scanned to find unknown traces that are not yet included in the Base-Data. This dataset is called Delta-Data. Base- and Delta-Data need to share the same parameters to be comparable."</p> <p>"If the degree of similarity between the reference drives is high and the degree of similarity between the free drives and the reference drives is low the fitness value is high. In this manner, the fitness function can detect special features and anomalies and automatically set bin borders to detect future anomalies free of pre-specifications and human bias."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we conducted a quantitative evaluation in an industrial context in the domain of automated driving, including over 1000 km of field data. The overall results prove that a significant amount of the data characteristics do not get lost during the Graph transformation."</p> <p>"The evaluation performs a quantitative analysis based on the concept of leave-one-out cross-validation to reduce bias and increase statistical validity. To enable statements regarding the meaningfulness of returned traces, the given results are compared to expected values. These are based on assumed data characteristics derived by their meta-information, e.g., driven route. The results prove that the presented approach can transfer the characteristics of both input datasets into an abstract graphical representation, which leads to uncovered traces, new test cases shall focus on. Consequently, the integration of the presented concepts leads to a valid and reasonable improvement of the test efficiency and quality, because redundancies in the test scenario catalog are minimized. In addition, human bias is highly reduced. Furthermore, quantifiable coverage metrics guide further testing and field data recording activities and evaluate their effectiveness over time."</p>
Q5 Answer	"Probably the most important aspect is understanding the relationship between traces and their transformation into a Trace Graph. Investigating which Trace Graph properties are beneficial for a given task and how to

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 311 / 550	

	optimize the PDM correspondingly directly leads to a more sophisticated test design. To achieve this, an extensive evaluation based on a larger and more diverse dataset is proposed. Another open question is whether and how well the presented approaches can be transferred to other domains, e.g., drone piloting systems."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <p>1) Feasible strategy to reduce tests needed for the safety assurance of autonomous vehicles by identifying similar scenarios and avoiding repetitions on different test cases.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Not clear if unsupervised learning with validation oriented by external validation criteria based on ground-truth data or supervised learning was used in the implemented approach.</p> <p>2) The strategy, albeit interesting, might still not be fully adequate for the safety assurance of AI-based systems.</p>

8.205 REFERENCE [695]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose a system-level approach for verifying the safety of systems combining a continuous-time physical system with a discrete-time neural network-based controller
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors present "(...) a generic approach for demonstrating the safety of a particular class of neural network controlled systems, where the controller is a classifier based on multiple ReLU networks. To tackle the above mentioned issues, our approach consists of a system-level approach that provides evidence that the overall system is safe, without performing item-level refinements and analyses. To this end, we leverage an accurate model of the overall system and we perform a reachability analysis to formally demonstrate that no reachable state can lead to a failure of the system."</p> <p>"(...) we aim at using abstract interpretation based techniques to analyze the behaviour of the overall system. Indeed, such methods scale well to large networks and they provide not only a yes-or-no answer to a verification problem but also an approximation of the network semantics."</p> <p>The model proposed by the authors proves a tight over-approximation of neural networks to argue, via reachability analysis, if a neural network is safe.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Case study: "The safe integration of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) into the air traffic requires them to have collision avoidance capabilities. For this purpose, the standardization group RTCA SC 147 has recently developed a dedicated controller, namely the Airborne Collision Avoidance System for Unmanned Aircraft (ACAS Xu). The role of ACAS Xu is to avoid any collision between the ownship, equipped with the controller, and an encountered aircraft called the intruder, equipped or not with the controller.</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>The main weakness of the ACAS Xu controller is the large storage requirements for the tables (over 2GB). Recently, an alternative design for the ACAS Xu controller has been proposed, with dramatically reduced memory footprint (about 3 MB). It consists of a collection of neural networks 45 approximating the lookup tables. (...)</p> <p>Due to the complexity of the controller, we lack a proof that no collision can Happen, whatever the initial state of the two aircraft."</p> <p>"(...) the ACAS Xu was proved safe for 98.8% of the possible initial states and for the remaining states, we could not prove it safe. This is still a valuable information as one can design a real-time monitoring mechanism that switches to a more robust controller when the ACAS Xu encounters an initial state for which it was not proved safe. Having such an architecture would allow to benefit from the expected performance of the neural networks while still remaining safe."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings have not been discussed by the authors.</p> <p>"For future work, we aim at reducing the verification time by using a more efficient partitioning strategy of the initial states and by optimizing the reachability procedure. Another direction is to consider a more complex ACAS Xu system, where both the ownship and the intruder are equipped with the controller, or with more than 2 UAVs. A third direction is to provide a thorough comparison with state-of-the-art tools based on additional</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 312 / 550	

	use cases such as VCAS (Vertical Collision Avoidance System)."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Solid mathematical background for the safety assurance of specific neural networks (ReLU activation function only) by means of overapproximation.</p> <p>2) Excellent conclusion on the formal verification: for all states which cannot be proven as safe, additional protections shall be included within the system to ensure safety by other means.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) No analysis under faults have been considered by the authors.</p>

8.206 REFERENCE [696]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present a barrier certificate approach to verify safety properties of closed-loop systems based on neural network controllers.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general, with emphasis on deep neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction: "Reachable set computation based approaches suffer from two limitations. Firstly, the heavy computational complexity arising from the nonlinear ODEs, the nonlinear activation functions and a huge number of neurons make it difficult to scale. Besides, as it computes the reachable set step by step, it can only guarantee safety over a finite time horizon.</p> <p>Verification approaches using barrier certificates (BC) can prove safety properties over an infinite time horizon. A barrier certificate is a continuous function of states that separates reachable set or its over-approximation from unsafe regions. Thus, the existence of a barrier certificate forms a sufficient condition of retaining the safety property."</p> <p>The authors [231] as their main inspiration. To overcome the limitations of [231], "(...) we investigate an alternative approach, that finds candidate barrier certificates via the classical construction conditions. We first build a polynomial approximation system and synthesize its barrier certificate from the classical construction conditions using Sum-of-Squares tools. An approximated system consists of the polynomial approximation of the DNN controller and the plant, where the upper bound of the approximation error is estimated by simulation and treated as disturbance to control inputs in BC synthesis. The derived barrier certificate doesn't become a real one until its soundness to the system under verification is certified by SMT solvers. Furthermore, an iterative scheme is developed that allows the polynomial approximation system to be iteratively refined when counterexamples are found by SMT solvers."</p> <p>"We present an iterative scheme to synthesize barrier certificates for continuous systems with a DNN controller (CSD). The key idea in each iteration is to construct the polynomial approximation system of the CSD, and then establish a polynomial optimization problem helping to generate barrier certificates for the approximation system. As the polynomial approximation system is designed to enclose the CSD, barrier certificates for the former are candidate BCs for the latter. We identify real barrier certificates using an SMT solver. The SMT solver either returns UNSAT, which certifies that the candidate is sound, or produces a counterexample that results in a refine polynomial approximation system."</p>
Q4 Answer	"We have developed a prototyping tool NNCChecker implementing the proposed approach and compared it with the state-of-art work on a set of benchmark examples where neural network controllers use three popular activation functions: ReLU, Sigmoid and Tanh. In the experiment, for the 12 examples, our NNCChecker can handle 10 of them while the opponent only solve 5 cases, which shows that our approach is much more effective in barrier certificate generation." The case study employed by the authors is based on a mass-spring damper system controlled by a deep neural network with varying architectures (e.g. neurons, hidden layers, and activation functions).
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Sound mathematical basis and detailed explanation.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The model requires parameter tuning to check the overapproximated safety boundaries of the derived</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 313 / 550	

	<p>polynomial model which simplifies the description of the original controller. Much of the parameter tuning has to be performed based on expert domain knowledge, expected results, processing time. No systematic means were provided by the authors to guide this process.</p> <p>2) Safety focuses on ensuring that the conceived NN-based model is safe from a functional point of view. No discussion on fault tolerance is performed.</p>
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8.207 REFERENCE [697]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present means to transfer results established in the previous DNN safety verification problems to other problems with modified settings considering the reuse of state abstractions, network abstractions, and Lipschitz constants, so as to reduce the effort in validating new DNNs.
Q2 Answer	Deep neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>The main motivation for the research in maximizing the reuse of former formal validation. is when online learning is used: new data points can change the underlying DNN and, hence, it would require a new validation.</p> <p>"To enable continuous verification, one premise is to have reasonable assumptions on proof artifacts reused from the old verification problem to the new one. Concretely, we consider reusing state abstractions, network abstractions, and Lipschitz constants. State abstractions are sound over-approximations of all possible reachable states created via layer-wise reasoning methods. Network abstraction refers to property-directed abstraction on the structure of a given neural network. Finally, Lipschitz constants are conservative bounds on the degree of output change subject to input change."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"For initial validation, we use a 1/10 scale vehicle platform that performs autonomous lane following using DNN-based visual perception. The incremental verification, due to only checking conditions of substantially simpler problems, leads to a significant performance gain. The required execution time to prove the safety property in the new problem can be as few as of the original problem-solving time, thanks to 0.16% reusing proof artifacts."</p> <p>"We first train a DNN on CIFAR10 dataset with an enlarged image matching the dimension, remove the last layer (i.e., perform transfer learning) and add a new linear layer in order to produce the vout value. Then the modified single-output network is trained using a manually labeled data set collected on the race track."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"Despite encouraging outcomes in our initial evaluation, the research also reveals many interesting yet challenging questions to be further explored."</p> <p>"Solver-wise, it is worth investigating how exact solvers based on MILP or SMT can be engineered to enable proof reuse, as we observe that techniques such as cuts (conditions to remove real-valued solutions while maintaining all feasible integer-valued solutions) lose their validity upon domain enlargement. Another direction is to consider the continuous evolution of the quantitative specification of DNN and the corresponding reuse in the formal verification setting. Yet another direction is to consider the symbolic reasoning using both forward and backward propagation in a continuous verification setup."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) One of the few references which explore safety of online learning leaning towards an efficient implementation of automated safety assurance.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The application of the proposed study is not sufficiently didactic. Technical results regarding the boundaries which were obtained to ensure safety were not detailed.</p> <p>2) Safety focuses on ensuring that the conceived NN-based model is safe from a functional point of view. No discussion on fault tolerance is performed.</p>

8.208 REFERENCE [705]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To propose a novel Markov Decision Process (MDP) type for learning decision tree policies, called Iterative Bounding MDPs (IBMDPs).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 314 / 550	

Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning, decision trees, explainable AI.
Q3 Answer	<p>Note: DT = Decision Tree</p> <p>"(...) we propose to solve a meta-problem using RL such that the solution corresponds to a DT-format policy for the original problem. We introduce CUSTARD (Constrain Underlying Solution to a Tree; Apply RL to Domain), a process that uses RL to solve the meta-problem while ensuring that the embedded solution is equivalent to a DT-format policy throughout training. We propose a novel Markov Decision Process (MDP) formulation for the meta-problem: Iterative Bounding MDPs. We present a general procedure to make RL techniques compatible with CUSTARD. CUSTARD allows modern DRL techniques to be applied to the meta-problem, since the learned policy weights can be fully replaced by an equivalent DT. Thus, CUSTARD maintains the interpretability advantage of a DT policy while using a non-interpretable function approximator during training. Additionally, CUSTARD ensures that the DT is an exact representation of the learned behavior, not an approximation."</p> <p>"Iterative Bounding MDP extends the base MDP by adding information-gathering actions and bounding state features to indicate the gathered information. The new features correspond to a position during a DT traversal, and the new actions correspond to partitions performed by internal nodes in a DT. By constraining an agent's policy to be a function of the bounding state features, the learned policy is equivalent to a DT."</p> <p>Pre-condition: "The base MDP must be an MDP with a factored state representation, where each state feature has upper and lower bounds on its values."</p> <p>Basics: "Not all policies for the IBMDP correspond to valid DTPs (...). However, all IBMDP policies that only consider the bounding features correspond to a DTP."</p> <p>"To create the full tree, both child nodes must be explored, so the procedure considers (...) a tighter upper bound (...) and a tighter lower bound (...). This procedure then recursively creates the child nodes."</p> <p>"Learning in an IBMDP can be cast as a two-agent problem: (i) a tree agent selects which information-gathering actions to take and when to take a base action, and (ii) a leaf agent selects a base action using the bounding features, when prompted to do so."</p> <p>"(...) this two-agent problem is equivalent to a single agent updating a single Q-function using two different targets, depending on the action taken. The equation for computing a target differs from the standard Q-function update equation (as applied to the IBMDP) in one way: if a base action is taken, the "next state" is the next state in which a base action is taken, rather than simply the next state. This single change is sufficient to learn DTPs for IBMDPs."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We evaluate CUSTARD's ability to create DTPs using a non-interpretable function approximator during the learning process. An alternative approach is to learn a non-tree expert policy and then find a tree that mimics the expert. We compare to VIPER, which takes this alternative approach and outperforms standard imitation learning methods. We evaluate with three environments (...): CartPole (balancing a pole by moving laterally), PrereqWorld (creating items and defining prerequisite items for it), and PotholeWorld (lane switching to avoid potholes).</p> <p>"CUSTARD finds DTPs with high average reward for all environments and tends to find shorter DTPs than VIPER". Shorter DTPs are more explainable. Moreover, "CUSTARD yields better policies at a given depth since it directly solves an IBMDP that can be augmented with a depth limit."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings were not discussed by the authors.</p> <p>Future work: "Future work includes generalization of IBMDPs to encode other constraints."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The authors present means to improve the explainability of reinforcement learning-based models by translating them into decision trees. The model behaves well under experimental scenarios on non-safety-critical applications.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors have not expanded on the explainable results of their case studies; instead, just assessed that the proposed model can produce short decision trees and that the latter are intuitively more explainable than other models.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 315 / 550	

8.209 REFERENCE [706]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To propose a lane change decision-making framework based on deep reinforcement learning to find a risk-aware driving decision strategy with the minimum expected risk for autonomous driving.
Q2 Answer	Deep reinforcement learning based on neural networks, bayesian knowledge models.
Q3 Answer	<p>"To solve the above-mentioned risk insensitive problem in lane change scenarios, risk assessment and DRL were comprehensively considered in this study to prompt the agent to learn a strategy with the minimum expected risk. Firstly, a quantized method based on position uncertainty using Bayes theory was proposed to assess the driving risk. Next, DRL was used to learn a strategy with the minimum risk."</p> <p>Risk Assessment: "(...) our risk assessment method will estimate the concrete probabilities at different risk levels". Three risk levels are considered: dangerous (2), attentive (1) and safe (0). "To model the risk based on nondeterministic theories, we take the relative position d and the uncertainty σ into consideration and use safety metrics based distribution to calculate the conditional probability at different risk levels. The Bayes inference is then used to assess the risk level in each given state." The risk model hyperparameters, which are predefined thresholds of relative positions and the uncertainty σ, "(...) are used to control the smoothness of different curves. The values of these hyperparameters are determined by adjusting themselves to get smooth risk curves with reasonable distributions (...)."</p> <p>"To prevent over-conservative behaviors of the DRL agent (e.g., taking too many brake actions), the brake action is left to human drivers or other ADAS applications for the final safety decision."</p> <p>Lane orientation is positively rewarded when the driver stays in the center of the lane and negatively rewarded otherwise (e.g., inadequate changes, driving too close to markings).</p> <p>"In our network, batch normalization (BN) is utilized to normalize the neural output before activation. The idea of BN consists of two parts: 1) the standard normalization is used to normalize the output to Gaussian distribution, which can prevent all the outputs from falling in the negative and causing gradient disappear by ReLu; 2) since the operation in 1) will destroy the raw distribution, two learnable parameters are used to restore the output."</p> <p>"Warmup learning rate strategy: In the early stages of the training process, the optimizers usually have a large variance, making the network updating unsteady. Therefore, a small learning rate is firstly used to train the network in the warmup learning rate strategy. Then, the learning rate goes back to the normal value for training. In our experimental settings, the learning rate is set to be 0.01 as the initial value, and recovers to 0.1 after 50 episodes.</p> <p>Gradient clipping: To avoid gradient explosion, gradient clipping with normalization is used. (...)</p> <p>Soft network updating: Rather than using the hard network updating, soft updating is used to copy the weights from the online network to the target network".</p> <p>"The algorithms developed in this paper are based on DQN. All the values of the hyper-parameters except learning rate are determined by recommendations from the existing literature. To determine the learning rate, we firstly test all the DQN based methods in a game called Cart Pole (...). Given that all the methods successfully pass the Cart Pole test, we then apply them to the pre-designed lane change scenarios in CARLA. DQN is firstly used to adjust the learning rate to find the best initial value which is then applied to the other methods."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) our proposed methods are also trained and tested on a professional and well-accepted simulator called Car Learning to Act (CARLA) In our experiments, two driving scenarios were proposed to evaluate the performance of our proposed methods</p> <p>Scenario I (static vehicles): To collect training samples of our proposed methods, a random number of static vehicles (10 ~ 26) are randomly placed on a 420 m long straight road to serve as static obstacles in the training phase. The HV should drive forward safely to avoid collisions with any of the static vehicles. (...) Four vehicles (including the HV) are located on a road with 4 sections, each of which is named as an interval section with one static vehicle. The location of the static vehicle in each interval section is randomly specified using the Gaussian based position sampling probability method, and the lane choices of all the vehicles (including HV</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 316 / 550	

	<p>and OV) are randomly initialized. Therefore, the situation with two vehicles parallel located in two lanes to block the road would not happen in our experiments.</p> <p>However, the longest straight road we can find in the available maps in CARLA is 420 m, which is not long enough to provide convincing evaluation results on the effectiveness of the proposed methods. Therefore, we evaluated the proposed methods on the 420 m-long road for 100 times with random scenarios (i.e., 100 episodes) in the evaluation phase.</p> <p>(...)</p> <p>Scenario II (moving vehicles): The initial position strategy of the vehicles is the same as scenario-I, but all the vehicles except the HV are set in the autopilot mode provided by CARLA, and the speed limit is 30 m/s. The HV should drive safely without collision with any of the dynamically moving vehicles. In the evaluation phase, 100 random scenarios are sampled to evaluate our proposed methods."</p> <p>"The presented results show that the proposed methods can attain better scores than the original methods (...), indicating that the proposed methods with risk awareness can achieve more stable performance."</p> <p>"The illustrated results show that the agent can complete the entire driving task safely and steadily. The illustrated motion path is smoother than PRDQN, because during the experiment, the agent would not take redundant actions (e.g., making many left turn or right turn actions when driving straightly) that may potentially cause increased risks to increase the complexity of the motion path as these redundant actions could be caught by our risk awareness strategy. Besides, in the places where the PRDQN agent collides with another vehicle, our improved RA-PRDQN can control the HV to safely avoid the obstacles without collisions."</p> <p>"(...) due to the newly added risk awareness module in the deep reinforcement learning algorithms, the agent has learned to take correct behaviors to prevent the occurrence of a collision with the obstacle, making the potential risk level go back to the normal levels (attentive or safe) (...)"</p> <p>"In our examined challenging scenarios, the success rate of our proposed RA-PRDQN is about 88 ~ 94% in the examined dense traffic flow scenario with high lane change frequency, whereas the success rates of the previous DRL based methods in dense lane change scenarios are usually around 90%. Therefore, the success rate of our proposed RA-PRDQN should be within a reasonable and acceptable range."</p> <p>"(...) there are six collisions in scenario-I and eight collisions in scenario-II when using our proposed RA-PRDQN. (...) most of the failure cases were caused by the short longitudinal distance between the front vehicle in the current lane and the lag vehicle in the target lane. (...)</p> <p>Another important reason leading to these failures is that the actions considered in this study for collision avoidance only cover the steering behavior. However, braking behavior is also very important to control the distance to the front and lag vehicles for collision avoidance. The missing of speed adaptation by braking may greatly contribute to those failure cases."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Limitations: Please refer to the response to Question 4.</p> <p>Future work: "Our proposed methods in this paper could be further improved by mending the sampling probability function for vehicle position initialization, supplementing braking behavior for speed control, considering the influence of driving style, deploying continuous action space based DRL algorithms, and optimizing the hyper-parameters in our proposed methods."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Sound application of deep reinforcement learning for safety functions. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Perception range for detecting other vehicles in a lane has been set up to the interval [-5m; 50m] without further explanation. 2) The conceived system is not fully autonomous (brake application is left to a human driver or an external system). This has been identified as one of the potential limitations of the research by the authors themselves. 3) Little connection to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.

8.210 REFERENCE [709]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present an unified framework to generate corner cases for decision-making systems used in connected and automated vehicles (CAVs). The driving environment is formulated based on the Markov decision process, and the deep reinforcement learning techniques are applied to learn the behavior policy of BVs in order to result in

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 317 / 550	

	more corner cases. These are further analyzed by feature extraction and clustering.
Q2 Answer	Deep reinforcement learning, neural networks, and unsupervised learning (k-means and DBSCAN).
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) CAVs need to interact with multiple background vehicles (BVs) for a long duration, so the variables that define the corner cases will be high-dimensional."</p> <p>"(...) an unified framework is proposed for the high-dimensional corner case generation problem. To address the challenge brought by high dimensionality, the Markov decision process (MDP) is introduced to formulate the traffic environment, which can simplify the temporal dependency between different snapshots of the simulation. (...) the MDP-based driving model can incorporate the behavior randomness of the real-world datasets, which makes the simulation more realistic and reliable. Moreover, with the reinforcement learning method, the simulation obtained can generate much more corner cases purposely, comparing with the NDE. To further simplify the spatial dependency, the BVs of the environment are assumed to make decisions simultaneously and independently during each time step (...). Using naturalistic driving data (NDD), the empirical distributions of BV's actions can be obtained for every state. By sampling actions of BVs from the distributions at each time step, the NDE can be generated. Based on this formulation, the corner case generation problem of the driving environment is equivalent to optimizing the behavior policy of BVs to improve the probability of corner cases. To achieve this optimization objective, deep reinforcement learning (DRL) techniques are utilized to learn the optimal behavior policy of BVs. With the learned policy, the BVs behave more aggressively when interacting with CAVs, and therefore systematically generate corner cases for a complex driving environment, such as highway driving environment.</p> <p>Owing to the diversity of corner cases, the generated cases can usually be divided into several clusters as well as outliers that do not belong to any specific cluster. Therefore, typical corner cases from each cluster and the outliers can represent the internal property of the generated corner cases, which are referred to as "valuable" corner cases hereafter. Given the generated corner cases, it is crucial to identify the valuable corner cases, which are usually more valuable for the evaluation and development of CAVs. To achieve this goal, feature extraction and clustering techniques are introduced. As the generated corner cases could be high-dimensional, principal component analysis (PCA) is utilized to reduce the dimension of corner cases and extract the principal features. For the extracted features, clustering methods are applied to identify different clusters of corner cases as well as specific outliers."</p> <p>"(...) the DBSCAN method is used to separate the majority and minority of corner cases as two groups. Then, for each group of the corner cases, the K-means method is utilized to cluster the corner cases."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"To build the naturalistic highway driving model, we implement a data-driven stochastic model from the integrated vehicle-based safety systems dataset at the University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Michigan, and the safety pilot model deployment dataset. By integrating the forward collision warning, lane departure warning, lane-change warning, and curve speed warning functions on passenger cars and heavy trucks, this project aims to prevent rear-end and other crashes."</p> <p>"Our simulation platform is based on the open-source simulation platform HIGHWAY-ENV (...), so it can be used to train the autonomous vehicle planning algorithm.(...) However, default vehicle models are deterministic and cannot perform the naturalistic nature of vehicle behavior, which is not suitable for the corner case generation process. To overcome this limitation, we re-design the simulation environment and add control API to improve the controllability of BVs, so the BVs can be controlled by the naturalistic driving model."</p> <p>"We implement the DQN (24) method using PyTorch and SGD as the optimizer."</p> <p>"Results show that the valuable corner cases can be effectively generated and identified, which is helpful for CAV evaluation and development by revealing flaws of the given CAV model."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>No shortcomings were discussed by the authors.</p> <p>Future work: "Future studies may focus on introducing more different traffic participants (pedestrians, traffic lights, etc.). Furthermore, corner case generation for the urban driving environment deserves more investigation, including intersection and roundabout scenarios."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting usage of unsupervised learning to identify potential corner cases to test safety-critical systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Hyperparameters were set by the researchers, and no additional explanation regarding their choices have been provided.</p> <p>2) Safety focuses on ensuring that the conceived model is safe from a functional point of view. No discussion on fault tolerance is performed.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 318 / 550	

8.211 REFERENCE [712]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To develop "a search-based test-case generation framework that can be used in training and testing deep-learning components of autonomous vehicles" and to develop "a framework based on multi-valued linear temporal logic syntax and semantics that allows autonomous agents to perform model-checking on systems with uncertainties".
Q2 Answer	Deep learning (little emphasis throughout the publication).
Q3 Answer	<p>The safety assurance of AI-based systems has been covered by means of the following themes:</p> <p>a) Using spatiotemporal perception logic to formalizing and evaluating requirements; b) Encoding and monitoring responsibility sensitive safety rules with signal temporal logic; c) Generating test cases by monitoring the responsibility sensitive safety rules by solving the corresponding signal temporal logic.</p> <p>All items have been attached to the application of autonomous vehicles and consist of application-specific solutions rather than general-purpose recommendations to be used in AI-based safety-critical systems as a whole.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors has successfully presented case studies that support each of the items have been properly developed towards the safety assurance of autonomous vehicles.</p> <p>AI has not been directly addressed, though. Instead, the author focuses on presenting each part of his research project and discussing the corresponding results, making potentially underlying AI transparent.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>No shortcomings were discussed by the authors.</p> <p>Future work:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Making online translation of responsibility sensitive safety rules with signal temporal logic; 2) Deploying a verifier of signal temporal logic within programmable logic devices; 3) Using formal methods to generate test cases; 4) Developing formal domain-specific languages for specifying requirements; 5) Parallelizing the processing of requirements; 6) Incorporating the processing of uncertainties by means of Dempster-Shafer theory.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting ideas towards fail-safe autonomous vehicles. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Some safety-related aspects are not taken into account based on safety standards and requirements, instead, the authors argue that safety is ensured by a sufficiency of test cases. 2) Most of the techniques generate application-specific results that cannot be fully integrated into a general-purpose framework for the safety assurance of AI-based systems. 3) AI is not explicitly taken into account by the authors on the safety-related parts of their research.

8.212 REFERENCE [713]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To develop, within the context of autonomous vehicles, "a processing-in-memory architecture to accelerate deep neural network training stage", to define the "safety score, a latency based safety metric, and the latency model, that represents the correlation between perception latency and surrounding obstacle distribution", and to present "Suraksha, a generalized safety validation framework that includes a set of safety metrics and driving scenarios".
Q2 Answer	Deep neural networks.
Q3	Among the three research objectives, the latter two are related to safety assurance.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 319 / 550

Answer	The safety score is specific to autonomous vehicles, since it depends on variables from such application domain. The safety validation framework Suraksha is also application-specific, but its basis is on generating test cases and arguing that an AI-based system is safe if it passes all tests and if such tests are deemed sufficiently exhaustive.
Q4 Answer	The author has presented case studies that support the validity and adequacy of their developments towards meeting the associated objectives. The case studies are based on simulations.
Q5 Answer	The author makes it clear that the research focuses only on 'nominal safety of autonomous vehicles'. Hence, it does not aim to cover how safety is ensured in the presence of faults nor to extend ideas to other applications. Future work: Improving tests and considering random faults within Suraksha.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Interesting ideas towards fail-safe autonomous vehicles. Weaknesses: 1) Some safety-related aspects are not taken into account based on safety standards and requirements, instead, the authors argue that safety is ensured by a sufficiency of test cases. 2) Most of the techniques generate application-specific results that cannot be fully integrated into a general-purpose framework for the safety assurance of AI-based systems. 3) AI is not explicitly taken into account by the authors on the safety-related parts of their research.

8.213 REFERENCE [714]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present methods to assess the potential safety benefit of autonomous driving and to present processes for the safety verification of autonomous vehicles.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	The authors present a list of potential techniques that can aid the safety verification of autonomous vehicles, including analytical methods, test-based statistical methods, and external monitors. Specifically for neural networks, using autoencoders, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and metric learning might be paths to make the verification easier / more feasible.
Q4 Answer	The author has presented papers in which case studies are explored in further detail. Two of them are towards the safety verification of autonomous vehicles, but are deemed per se insufficient, by the own author, to reach the objective.
Q5 Answer	The author recognizes that the safety assurance of autonomous vehicles with machine learning has not yet been reached, despite efforts towards this. Moreover, estimating and detecting novelty are proposed as future work.
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) The thesis itself deals very superficially with the research theme.

8.214 REFERENCE [715]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To develop "computationally efficient and scalable formal techniques to prove the safety and robustness of safety-critical AI systems at an acceptable cost". This is subdivided into five smaller objectives: Presenting "(..) a novel, fast and scalable approach for the exact and over-approximate reachability analysis of Feedforward Neural Networks with ReLU activation functions using the concept of star sets"; Presenting "(..) a new reachability analysis approach for safety verification of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) with neural network controllers using star set"; Presenting "(...) a set-based analysis method based on the concept of ImageStar, a new set representation capturing a set of an infinite number of images caused by an adversarial attack on an image. Using ImageStar, we propose the exact and over-approximate reachability algorithms to construct the reachable sets containing all possible outputs of a Convolutional Neural Network under adversarial attacks";

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 320 / 550

	Presenting "(...) the first formal verification approach for establishing the robustness of Semantic Segmentation Networks using reachability analysis"; Presenting "(...) NNV (Neural Network Verification), which is a tool that performs set-based verification for Deep Neural Networks and learning-enabled CPS".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general.
Q3 Answer	The thesis has already been covered by the publications [92], [131], [212], [237], and [586]. Hence, please refer to the comments of those references for further details.
Q4 Answer	The thesis has already been covered by the publications [92], [131], [212], [237], and [586]. Hence, please refer to the comments of those references for further details.
Q5 Answer	The thesis has already been covered by the publications [92], [131], [212], [237], and [586]. Hence, please refer to the comments of those references for further details.
Q6 Answer	The thesis has already been covered by the publications [92], [131], [212], [237], and [586]. Hence, please refer to the comments of those references for further details.

8.215 REFERENCE [716]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present how simulations be made more realistic through sensor error modeling and to use reinforcement learning for system validation in virtual simulation environments.
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	The safety assurance of AI is not directly addressed; instead, autonomous vehicles are claimed to have AI and their safety assurance is carried out following simulated test cases conceived and assessed with the aid of a reinforcement learning-based agent for the reachability analysis of high-dimensional systems.
Q4 Answer	The author has referred to two papers in which case studies are presented. The authors have reached the conclusion that reinforcement learning can be used to perform falsification tests and that they were able to detect unsafe scenarios on an autonomous vehicle by using such a reinforcement learning-based agent.
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: When using RL on the reachability analysis for the verification of high-dimensional systems, Future Research: To answer the following questions: "1. How can probabilistic sensor error models be confidently deployed in simulation environments? 2. How can the generative performance of probabilistic error models be evaluated on a per-time-series basis? 3. How can models be adapted to new sensor software and hardware without the need of extensive data collection?" "We noticed that scalability with respect to the state-disturbance dimension was not necessarily as bad as for reachability analysis (according to preliminary results). However, solving even simple problems, such as the falsification of an adaptive cruise controller, is relatively expensive in terms of computational requirements. If the simulation environment is very complex, using this falsification approach may not be feasible. Hence, we need more sample efficient learning algorithms to be able to apply RL-based falsification as a virtual validation tool."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Interesting ideas towards fail-safe autonomous vehicles; 2) Relevant discussion and results on modeling sensor uncertainties. Weaknesses: 1) No discussion on how to ensure that the RL agent is safe for its purposes. 2) Lacks in-depth analyses of the case studies.

8.216 REFERENCE [717]

Q-Index	4
Q1	To automatically learn a hybrid automata (HA) representation of an AI-enabled CPS and, given the learned

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 321 / 550

Answer	HA, evaluate the in-field operational safety of the AI-enabled CPS. Scope: Linear and non-linear CPSs.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	The author presents a process for the safety assurance of AI-based systems which includes safety-related activities during requirements specification (risk assessment), design (falsification, hazard analysis, model checking, conformance testing), implementation (testing, hazard analysis, conformance testing) and operation (hazard analysis, runtime monitoring, conformance testing, operational safety). The focus of their research is on 'operational safety' - i.e., on how to ensure that the system will operate in a safe way even with potential discrepancies, on other steps of the process, due to McDermid's semiotic triangle.
Q4 Answer	The author presents a case study of an artificial pancreas. By applying the presented operational safety assurance method, potentially unsafe situations stemming from underestimated hyperglycemia have been identified.
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings were not discussed. Future work: "Future research can involve developing an approach that automates and optimizes I/O data collection since it is crucial that the data used for model learning is collected from different regions of interest of the operation of the AI-enabled CPS. Another important direction is the analysis of the effect of the learning error on the learned reach set in order to correctly analyze the area of intersection between the unsafe set and learned reach set (for the unsafe safety guarantee case). Finally, since many security losses overlap with safety accidents, the proposed safety verification approach can be leveraged to prevent security losses."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) The thesis is clear on how its objectives were covered and assessed by means of a case study; 2) An overview of a safety assurance process has been presented and discussed along with potential techniques for each step. Weaknesses: 1) The hybrid automata approach requires a learning process whose safety has not been discussed by the authors (what if the hybrid automata learns a wrong model?). 2) Solutions might be application-specific.

8.217 REFERENCE [718]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	Four objectives are covered: O1: Developing a Colored Petri Network-based formal analysis technique for real-time, component-based software systems, focusing on the analysis and verification of timing requirements; O2: Creating a platform to develop Cyber-Physical Systems with learning components which integrates safety assurance processes into a model-based development cycle for CPSs; O3: Creating a technique for the automated construction of assurance cases based on the instantiation and composition of existing argument patterns. O4: Establishing a methodology for modeling potential hazard escalation paths and dynamic estimation of the risk posed by these hazards known as ReSonAte.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	O1: No explicit mention to AI. A Colored Petri Network-based approach was used to model the interactions between system elements and the period of time of each interaction, so as to avoid potential conflicts of e.g., two elements communicating when a third-party input information is still unavailable. O2: Please refer to [859]. O3: A model for automating the construction of assurance cases was developed. It is based on assurance patterns and a model-based representation of the system. O4: Please refer to [695].
Q4 Answer	O1: A case study for an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAS) was presented. The case study included a demonstration of a scenario in which a timing requirement is violated.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 322 / 550	

	<p>O2: Please refer to [859].</p> <p>O3: A case study for the BlueROV2 system (tracking a pipeline on the seafloor while avoiding obstacles) was presented. It was shown that the line of reasoning of the safety arguments needed to support that a system is safe can be built; nevertheless, building the line of reasoning for that purpose still requires that supporting evidence is collected by other means, as this is outside the scope of this research.</p> <p>O4: Please refer to [695].</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>O1: Poor scalability limits the applicability to realistic, full-scale systems operating in highly nondeterministic environments. An algorithm for generating branches of the state space in parallel, combined with modern GPU-acceleration techniques, may offer significant scalability improvements, as would additional techniques for reducing the size of the state space required to verify system properties.</p> <p>O2: Please refer to [859].</p> <p>O3: Validating that the assurance case is correct and provides sufficient assurance for system safety objectives is left as an open question.</p> <p>O4: Please refer to [695].</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The research covers several topics of interest for the safety assurance of AI-based systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Only O4 is directly related to technical aspects of AI.</p>

8.218 REFERENCE [719]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To develop "methods drawing upon techniques from the field of formal methods, namely Hamilton-Jacobi (HJ) reachability and Signal Temporal Logic (STL), to complement a learning-enabled robot autonomy stack, thereby leading to safer and more robust robot behavior".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, with focus on deep neural networks and reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we develop a two-step approach where we first develop a learning-based human behavior prediction model tailored towards proactive robot planning and decision-making, which we then couple with a reachability-based safety controller that minimally intervenes whenever the robot is near safety violation. (...) The second part of this dissertation examines the use of STL as a formal language to incorporate logical reasoning into robot learning. In particular, we develop a technique, named stlcg, that casts STL into the same computational language as deep neural networks. Consequently, by using stlcg to express designers' domain expertise into a form compatible with neural networks, we can embed domain knowledge into learned components within the autonomy stack to provide additional levels of robustness and interpretability."</p> <p>"(...) we present an optimization-based approach to synthesize a HJ reachability-based safe control strategy for multi agent settings.(...) we follow a typical decision-making and control paradigm of utilizing a high-level planner to compute a coarse trajectory and a low-level controller to track it. (...) we HJ reachability computation for multi-agent systems because HJ reachability suffers from the curse of dimensionality. Naively extending the dimensionality of the system to account for multiple agents causes the HJ reachability computation to become intractable very quickly. To address this curse, and the fact that the number of agents that a robot may be interacting with may vary over time, we consider decomposing the joint system into multiple pairwise systems for each possible human-robot pair (...). Then given the set of human-robot pairwise systems that are near safety violation, we can then consider the intersection of the safety-preserving control set (...)"</p> <p>A model using Signal Temporal Logic (STL) as a means to feedback AI-based elements, notably deep neural networks, has also been developed. It "translates STL robustness formulas into computation graphs [and] leverages modern auto-differentiation tools used widely in the field of deep learning (..), and hence bridges the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 323 / 550	

	<p>gap between temporal logic and deep learning as they are now share the same computational backbone. This bridge provides a way to combine temporal logic with data-driven approaches and hence diversifying ways in which temporal logic can be used with deep neural networks."</p> <p>"(i) We develop a semi-supervised trajectory-feedback controller designed to satisfy a desired STL specification and demonstrate the benefit of using (few) expert demonstrations to help guide the control synthesis process. A trajectory-feedback, as opposed to state-feedback, controller is crucial since satisfaction of an STL specification is history-dependent. (ii) We generalize our trajectory-feedback controller to new but similarly structured environments to prevent the need to re-synthesize a new STL controller whenever the environment changes. Environment generalization is achieved by conditioning the control parameters on environment parameters. (iii) We combine an offline iterative adversarial training algorithm with an online adaptation scheme to improve robustness against disturbances. We show empirically that even when the neural network controller (trained offline) produces trajectories that violate the STL specification, the online adaptation step produces satisfying trajectories. (iv) We demonstrate our controller on a relatively complex STL specification and show that it outperforms a state-of-the-art shooting method in terms of STL robustness and computation time.)"</p>
<p>Q4 Answer</p>	<p>"We develop our work around a traffic weaving case study for which we adapt methods from deep neural network-based language and path prediction to learn a generative model of human driver behavior. The traffic weaving scenario is representative of the many challenges central to Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), in particular, the behaviors of each driver are tightly coupled and there is uncertainty in how the other driver may act in response to the actions of the other. We validate our model as the basis for a limited-lookahead autonomous driver action policy, applied in a receding horizon fashion, the behavior of which we explore with human-in-the-loop testing."</p> <p>"Our experiments show that with our proposed minimally interventional safety controller, we accomplish the high-level objective (tra c weaving) despite the human car swerving directly onto the path of the robot car, and accomplish this relatively smoothly compared to using a switching controller that results in the robot car swerving more violently off the road. Further, we investigate the addition of a road boundary wall to our formulation to prevent the robot car from swerving completely out of the lane which could be dangerous in realistic road settings and compare against a baseline approach using state constraints to avoid dynamic obstacles to show that our framework is better designed to keep the robot car safe even in the face of worst-case human car behaviors."</p> <p>"Our proposed approach leverages HJ reachability theory and, as demonstrated with a multi-agent highway driving scenario, equips a robot with the foresight to avoid regions of possible inevitable collision, and the ability to minimally deviate from the desired trajectory to the extent necessary to avoid collision with multiple agents."</p> <p>"The approach is validated through human-in-the-loop simulation as well as on an experimental vehicle platform, demonstrating clear connections between theory and practice."</p> <p>"We showed through an illustrative case study that the combined offline and online schemes achieve better performance and computation times compared to a state-of-the-art shooting approach."</p>
<p>Q5 Answer</p>	<p>"Future work includes investigating this framework for cases where the human and robot have very different dynamics, such as a pedestrian or cyclist interacting with a car, or a human interacting with a robotic manipulator, and for interactions involving multiple (more than two) agents. We may also consider adapting our approach to ensure high planning performance while guaranteeing the satisfaction of constraints other than safety (...)"</p> <p>"We propose three future research directions; the first would be to extend the idea of using a HJI value function as part of the objective function beyond planning algorithms, such as for trajectory optimization, or as a feature in inverse reinforcement learning. The second would entail exploring different ways to define the target set when computing the value function, and understanding how it affects the safety-performance trade-off. The third is to design smarter priority assignment, such as through chance constraints, when safety is nearly violated by multiple agents."</p> <p>"Future directions include (i) learning a value function to avoid long roll-outs and therefore reduce the computation time, (ii) using more complex dynamics (e.g., expressed as neural networks) and images such as a map or camera images attached to the robot, and (iii) extending the controller to account for multi-agent</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 324 / 550	

	settings where the STL specifications become even more complex."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Relevant contribution towards building fail-safe AI, notably by means of the architecture that feeds back AI outputs with the processing of Signal Temporal Logic (STL) to improve the trained models in an online way. 2) Relevant research on formal reachability (Hamilton-Jacobi) for AI-based systems. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No consideration is made on assessing if safety is retained in the presence of faults. 2) Even though supervised learning has been well explored, there are no comments on how the proposed approach could be extended to other learning methods or other types of AI.

8.219 REFERENCE [728]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present an evaluation method and apparatus for assessing safety risks based on an ensemble of neural networks. The main application is to monitor power grids.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors have conceived a safety risk assessment tool based on an ensemble of neural networks. Each neural network is trained separately, receives operational data as input and produces on its output an estimate of the system state. Finally, the overall safety risk of the assessed system corresponds to the median of the outputs produced by all neural networks.</p> <p>"Determine the predicted results of each of the equipment safety assessment models separately with the loss value of the given label; Using the prediction result and the loss value of the given label initialization calculation of the initial adjustment coefficient of each of the equipment safety evaluation model; The predicted result is multiplied by the initial adjustment factor to obtain the intermediate value of the prediction result, the median value of the prediction result is calculated and the degree of support of the prediction result is calculated, and the degree of support is normalized to obtain the degree of normalization support; The normalized support is multiplied by the preset learning rate to obtain an updated adjustment coefficient until the sum of the loss values of the predicted result and the loss value of the given label is less than the preset loss threshold."</p> <p>"the measurement data comprises data collected during normal operation of the grid equipment and data collected when there is an abnormality in the power grid equipment.</p> <p>A second aspect of an embodiment of the present invention provides an evaluation device based on a plurality of neural network device security risk evaluation apparatus, the apparatus comprising: Evaluation training module, for obtaining measurement data of the device, and using the measurement data to evaluate and train with each neural network separately, to build a plurality of equipment safety evaluation models; Coefficient adjustment module, which is used to repeat the coefficient adjustment operation for each of the equipment safety evaluation models and generate the corresponding comprehensive evaluation models; Calculation module, for the use of a plurality of comprehensive evaluation model and preset operating data for safety risk assessment calculations, to obtain calculation results, wherein the preset operating data is the state data collected in real time by the equipment during operation; A determination module that determines device security risks based on the results of calculations.</p> <p>Compared with the prior art, embodiments of the present invention provides an evaluation method and apparatus based on the safety risk of a plurality of neural networks, the beneficial effect of which is: the present invention may collect measurement data of the device, and the use of measurement data for a plurality of neural networks for evaluation training and weight allocation, thereby improving the evaluation accuracy of the model, and a plurality of evaluation models can be adapted to more different devices, further improve the flexibility and practicability of the evaluation, increase the function of the model."</p>
Q4	"(...) the present invention may collect measurement data of the device, and the use of measurement data for a

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 325 / 550

Answer	plurality of neural networks for evaluation training and weight allocation, thereby improving the evaluation accuracy of the model, and a plurality of evaluation models can be adapted to more different devices, further improve the flexibility and practicability of the evaluation, increase the function of the model."
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Weaknesses: 1) The authors have not explored how their ensemble of neural networks is ensured as sufficiently safe for the purposes of the intended application.

8.220 REFERENCE [739]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present a simulation-based fault injection tool to support the certification of safety-critical systems.
Q2 Answer	AI in general.
Q3 Answer	"The present invention uses a system's functional/safety requirements and a design simulation model, and a fault model that conforms to the fault scenario. After setting the model and performing a fault injection simulation, the effect of failure according to the failure mode and its severity, frequency of occurrence, and detection degree are evaluated. Safety analysis data that can be calculated and used for safety standard certification (failure mode impact analysis, failure tree analysis, reliability block diagram, etc.)." "The safety certification data generating device of the present invention is a simulation model (Matlab/Simulink, Verilog, SystemC, and hardware/software design models) and fault scenarios derived from safety function requirements, fault models that can demonstrate fault scenarios, and fault injection simulation models loaded with fault models can be simulated according to fault scenarios. A simulation control device that controls the simulator so that analysis, failure tree analysis, reliability block diagram, etc.) includes a safety certification data generating device." "The safety analysis data described in an embodiment of the present invention is a failure mode effect analysis (FMEA). Create a failure mode (fault scenario) based on the safety function requirements, collect failure effect data for each failure mode by performing a failure injection test, and use the collected failure effect data to obtain safety certification (...)" " (...) a rule-based failure determination engine that analyzes the failure injection simulation results according to the rules and determines failure effects; The failure determination engine compares/analyzes the steady state simulation result and the defect injection simulation result, checks the failure pattern such as failure type/value/occurrence time/occurrence frequency, and then determines the severity/detection/occurrence corresponding to the failure determination rule. Determination of degree/risk; the rule-based failure determination engine may be replaced with an AI-based failure determination engine; The AI-based failure determination engine classifies the fault injection simulation results according to severity, and generates a failure determination engine by performing learning according to each classification data; Using the failure determination engine, the data of the defect injection test results are analyzed, and the failure analysis (...)"
Q4 Answer	"(...) using a model that is essential in the system development stage, simple setup and simulation without additional preparation work safety analysis can be performed, and even with model modifications due to changes in design requirements, automated authenticators. By using the fee acquisition device, the time required for the production of certification data can be dramatically reduced."
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) AI is briefly considered as an alternate means to generate fault injection scenarios towards the certification of safety-critical systems. There is no explicit mention to the safety analysis of AI.

8.221 REFERENCE [740]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To solve the problem of a small number of labeled samples in a neural network and the problem of being attacked by wrongly labeled adversarial samples. with a two-part active safety incremental data training

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 326 / 550	

	method: (1) An incremental data retraining method based on active learning; and Model-Based Safety Verification Methods for Adversarial Sample Attack Detection.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, with emphasis on deep neural networks, supervised learning and semi-supervised learning.
Q3 Answer	1) Incremental data retraining with active learning: A neural network is trained and copied, and the copied neural network is applied to label new data with a degree of confidence. All samples with a degree of confidence of at least 90% are marked and employed on an incremental retraining of the neural network. 2) Safety verification with adversarial attacks: By considering the full set of inputs of the incrementally trained network as an input to both networks and adversarial attacks, the rate of how the gradient changes with the adversarial attacks is checked for 10 iterations. If it decreases or grows too fast (i.e., below 0% and above 5%, respectively), the incrementally trained network is discarded, otherwise, it effectively supersedes the original, non-incrementally trained network.
Q4 Answer	1) "Compared with the original model, the decision boundary of the new model is continuously expanded by iteratively retraining the new samples, so that more confidence levels > 0.9 can be obtained. Add new samples to generate more accurate models more efficiently and improve the discriminative ability of the model." 2) No claims were presented on how the network is ensured as safe, even though it is intuitive to understand that the method allows assessing the susceptibility to adversarial attacks and filtering out those neural networks which are excessively prone to them.
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Interesting and sound method for incrementally training robust neural networks and assessing the impact of adversarial attacks on safety. Weaknesses: 1) No further information to guide how adversarial attacks are determined. 2) No consideration is made on assessing if safety is retained in the presence of faults.

8.222 REFERENCE [741]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To overcome the difficulties in ensuring that deep neural networks, including those trained online, are safe.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, with focus on deep neural networks and online learning.
Q3 Answer	Contextualization: "Up to now, there have been several publications in academia addressing the safety verification for deep neural networks, such as Reluplex, ReluVal, DeepPoly, DeepZono, and DeepGo. However, all of them suffer from stark limitations. Hence there is a need for methods that can provide formal guarantees about DNN and thus the system's behavior. Unfortunately, manual reasoning about large DNNs is impossible, as their structure renders them incomprehensible to humans. Automatic verification techniques are thus sorely needed, but here, the state of the art is a severely limiting factor. Verifying DNNs is a difficult problem. DNNs are large, non-linear, and nonconvex, and verifying even simple properties about them is an NP-complete problem. DNN verification is experimentally beyond the reach of general-purpose tools such as linear programming (LP) solvers or existing satisfiability modulo theories (SMT) solvers and thus far, dedicated tools have only been able to handle very small networks." "In summary, it can be stated that current verification approaches are applicable only to a subset of deep neural networks that are both limited in size (up to 300 neurons) and in structure (i.e. only rectified linear units as activation functions)." "Models inferred from execution traces (logs) may admit more behaviors than those possible in the real system (over-approximation) or may exclude behaviors that can indeed occur in the real system (under-approximation)." Online learning: "However, no techniques are currently available that can guarantee that newly learnt networks

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 327 / 550	

	do improve operational characteristics." Method: "It is proposed to verify one or more (different) properties of artificial neural network, such as deep neural networks, using a modified version of a global optimization algorithm for non-convex multi-variate functions [DiRect] which need to be Lipschitz continuous. Based on a heuristic, the original algorithm is incapable of providing hard guarantees about the correctness of the results it computes. However, it is proposed to adapt it by incorporating static analyses that enable computations of safe approximations of local Lipschitz constants. In that way, a new algorithm that inherits the efficient heuristic search from [DiRect] is achieved while being able to guarantee correctness of the optimization results ." "Now turning to the adaptation of the DiRect algorithm, the computation of the reach set is done by a modified version of the [DiRect] algorithm. Based on its original publication [DiRect, pages 170-172] . the adaptations of the multivariate algorithm are outlined. The adaptation comprises an oracle lip (o ° w, X) which provides a safe over-approximation of a local Lipschitz constant within a given sub-space (...). (...) With the modified DiRect algorithm, it is possible to compute the infimum of a given neural network w.r.t. an objective function that encodes one of the properties outlined in the previous paragraph. If this neural network is seen as a multivariate function, it is possible to compute its supremum by negating the function and computing the infimum of this negated function. This way the reach set can be calculated, which is the basis for proving the other verifiable properties stated above (robustness, etc)." "Central to the adaptation of DiRect is the capability to estimate a Lipschitz constant for any hyper-rectangle given the structure of the deep neural network and its objective function. To achieve this, the data flow analysis from [DeepPoly] may be interleaved with an estimator for Lipschitz constants."
Q4 Answer	"The ability to verify deep neural networks whose number of neurons is large enough to be relevant for industry is an advantage of the present disclosure. Moreover, the techniques proposed are not bound to the ReLU activation function. Especially the safety verification and robustness comparison are of interest in (productive) automation systems. The computation of a localized Lipschitz constant close to the best possible Lipschitz constant via the technique proposed herein and the intelligent weaving of the localized Lipschitz constants into DiRect gives a big edge over other evaluated techniques. This enables a lot of verified artificial intelligence applications to improve control systems, e.g. in machine building, improve the safety of edge devices, detect faults by image recognition, minimize downtimes via predictive maintenance, save power by predicting consumption patterns, and improve product configurators such as Teamcenter, Rulestream, as well as model-based engineering systems. These advantages are inter alia achieved by the localized calculation of the Lipschitz constant used in the modified DiRect algorithm as outlined in the above. With this dataflow analysis of the given deep neural network to estimate a Lipschitz constant a downscaling of the Lipschitz constant of several orders of magnitude has been achieved. The second unique aspect of the present disclosure is the intelligent way of weaving the iteratively computed Lipschitz constant into the original DiRect algorithm now able to verify different outlined aspects of deep neural networks. The solution proposed is able to verify properties of DNNs of realistic size and with nearly arbitrary combinations of activation functions."
Q5 Answer	Neither shortcomings nor suggestions for future research are explored by the author(s).
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) In-depth and sound analysis of formal verification of neural networks, including a review on the drawbacks of other approaches and the clear contribution proposed by the authors. Weaknesses: 1) No consideration is made on assessing if safety is retained in the presence of faults. 2) The technique requires application-specific models.

8.223 REFERENCE [743]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To introduce "a general technique for reduction of non-determinism [caused by autonomous systems with machine learning-based perception exhibiting unpredictable behaviors] based on assumptions of "monotonic safety", which define a partial order between system states in terms of their probabilities of being safe".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 328 / 550	

Q3 Answer	<p>"To improve the scalability of Probabilistic Model Checking (PMC) and data efficiency of Lightweight Scheduler Sampling (LSS) of Statistical Model Checking, this paper introduces a novel way to reduce non-determinism in the intermediate abstractions of models. This reduction is based on assumptions of monotonic safety (MoS) that capture our intuition about which states have a higher chance of safety than others. Encoded as partial orders, these assumptions draw on domain-specific knowledge to characterize broad safety principles in a particular system. (...) These simplifications intend to maintain conservative safety estimates and, when MoS assumptions hold, are provably conservative. Specifically, we simplify models using MoS-driven trimming of non-deterministic transitions leading to MoS-safer states. This reduction in non-determinism speeds up PMC and improves the data efficiency of LSS.</p> <p>Ultimately, MoS assumptions are heuristic and may not strictly hold in all situations: in rare cases it is worth being a little closer to the obstacle so that the perception is more accurate. Typically, it is not immediately clear where MoS holds or how to efficiently compute that MoS holds. However, we show empirically that MoS assumptions do not need to strictly hold in every state to be useful, as long as they hold most of the time."</p> <p>The systems are described as probabilistic automata (PA), and the MoS is a partial order over their states with respect to a given safety property. The subset of safe states shall be defined by a domain expert. "One way to find candidates for MoS assumptions is to examine the robustness, in terms of Signal Temporal Logic (STL), of the safety property."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We instantiate our MoS assumptions and MoS-driven trimming on two simulated case studies: automated braking for an autonomous vehicle and flow control of water tanks. Our MoS-driven trimming produces abstractions which estimate the safety probability of the system and are compared with standard conservative abstractions. Experiments show that our abstractions improve the scalability of PMC by an order of magnitude and the data efficiency of LSS by at least an order of magnitude. Moreover, we observe that our abstractions remain empirically conservative, even when not provably so: they do not overestimate the chance of safety in practice, even though MoS assumptions only hold in most of the states."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed.</p> <p>Future research: "Future work includes analytically bounding conservatism loss from MoS violations, extending the MoS trimming techniques to distributions of states, and exploring how our notion of MoS relate to sensitivity analysis for dynamical systems. More generally, we see the development of abstractions suitable for LSS as a promising area to explore."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Formal method-based approach for checking ML-based systems which aims to reduce the effort in assessing safety whilst ensuring it based on combining probabilistic and statistical model checking. 2) The method is independent from the type of AI. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No consideration is made on assessing if safety is retained in the presence of faults. 2) No discussion on drawbacks of the presented method, notably in ensuring that overapproximate results are maintained even if the 'monotonic safety' property is not fully respected within some intervals. The examples provided by the authors favor safety, but it is not clear whether this can be generalized. 3) The technique requires application-specific models.

8.224 REFERENCE [744]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "propose a three-step confidence composition (CoCo) framework for monitoring verification assumptions" of cyber-physical systems with neural network controllers.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general, with focus on supervised and reinforcement learning. There is also mention to Bayesian models and logistic regression.
Q3 Answer	Contextualization: "To provide its guarantees, the verification relies on assumptions about system's dynamics, perception, and environment. Should the system find itself in circumstances not matching these assumptions, the verification

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 329 / 550	

	<p>guarantees are void — and remarkably difficult to re-obtain at run time due to limited scalability."</p> <p>" (...) many run-time monitoring techniques were developed to detect anomalies, such as model inconsistencies and out-of-distribution samples. These tools can provide valuable situational insights, but their outputs often lack a direct connection to the verification guarantees or system-level safety."</p> <p>"Thus, it is both challenging and important to quantify and monitor the trust in design-time verification guarantees at run time. In particular, it is vital to know when the guarantees no longer apply, so as to switch to a backup controller, execute a recovery maneuver, or ask for human assistance. The monitoring of verification guarantees has the potential to predict otherwise unforeseen failures in situations for which the system was not trained or designed."</p> <p>Method: "This paper introduces the CoCo framework for composing confidence from monitors of verification assumptions, consisting of three steps: (i) verify the system under explicit assumptions, such that a propositional formula over these assumptions entails the system's safety, (ii) build a well-calibrated confidence monitor for each assumption, (iii) use a composition function informed by the formula from the first step to combine the monitor outputs into a composed confidence. This confidence quantifies the chance that the verification guarantees apply at that moment. We develop the theoretical conditions under which the composed confidence is calibrated and conservative, up to a bounded error, with respect to the true probability of safety. These conditions are that (a) the system model under verification can explain most safe behaviors, (b) a violation of assumptions would likely lead to a failure, and (c) the composition function is calibrated/conservative with respect to the assumptions. We also prove calibration error bounds for two composition functions — product and weighted average — and a conservatism bound for the product."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We evaluate CoCo on two systems with NN controllers: a mountain car and an underwater vehicle. Experiments show that our compositional monitors are useful for safety prediction, outperform the individual monitors, and can be tuned for conservatism. Our data-driven composition functions improve the performance further if provided the data relating the monitors and the assumptions."</p> <p>"Our theoretical and empirical investigation highlighted the distinct advantages of the proposed CoCo framework. First, unlike many assurance methods, it does not require a detailed or complete enumeration/model of hazards and failure modes. As long as the models and assumptions are safety-relevant, and the monitors are well-calibrated and accurate, the composite monitor should detect any potential violation of safety. Second, it is not tied to specific closed-form distributions — at most, our bounds only require the knowledge of the calibration bounds and monitor variance. Third, the non-data-driven compositions support independent development of monitors without the need for combined tuning. However, if joint monitor data is available, compositions based on logistic regression and Bayesian estimation can take advantage of it."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"First, richer models of assumption dependencies (e.g., copulas) may enable new composition functions (e.g., based on known odds or correlations) and tighten the bounds on the existing ones. Second, extending the composition bounds to 3+ monitors and new composition functions is mathematically challenging, but it can be facilitated by detailed models of monitor dependencies. Another fruitful direction is empirical validation and refinement of the simplification (...). Since it is difficult to decompose assumptions, it would be useful to create verification techniques that make granular assumptions bottom-up. Finally, a longer-term goal would be to extend the scope of a confidence monitor by considering its temporal behavior and monitoring the assumptions of other monitors"</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Good introduction on comparing design-time and runtime verification which shows that the latter is typically unfeasible from a computational point of view and that the former is important for ensuring safety provided its application-specific boundaries are respected.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) No mention to online learning. 2) No consideration is made on assessing if safety is retained in the presence of faults. 3) The technique requires application-specific models.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 330 / 550

8.225 REFERENCE [745]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present "a method for formally verifying the absence of adversarial examples in a neural network controller (...) with piecewise affine activation units".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks and reinforcement learning (case study).
Q3 Answer	"We present an approach for certifying safety of NN-based controllers for cyber-physical systems over a full continuous state space." "The approach rests on characterizing and bounding a critical subset of the state space where controller action is required, partitioning this critical subset, and using satisfiability modulo theories (SMT) to prove nonexistence of safety counterexamples on each of the resulting partition elements." "Safeable analysis computes an approximation of the reachable set for sequences of future controller commands to determine which current commands can be made safe in the future." "We rely on an SMT solver to evaluate the safety of an NN control function with respect to an established safe command range, computed using safeable analysis. Because we use a piecewise constant overapproximation for the safe command range, which can be computed independently before being given as a constraint to SMT, our approach can support systems with general nonlinear dynamics and also allows for straightforward parallelization. Scalability of this procedure is driven primarily by the NN size and complexity."
Q4 Answer	"We demonstrate this approach on a simple collision avoidance neural network controller, trained with reinforcement learning to avoid collisions in a simplified simulated environment. After encoding the network weights in SMT, we formally verify safety of the neural network controller on a subset of the critical partition elements, and determine that the rest of the critical set partition elements are potentially unsafe. We further experimentally confirm the existence of actual adversarial collision scenarios in 90% of the identified potentially unsafe critical partition elements, indicating that our approach is reasonably tight."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: The model is applicable to neural networks "with piecewise affine activation units" only, i.e., "which may be encoded symbolically as a piecewise affine mapping from inputs to outputs". Future work: "Future work will focus on the use of efficient solvers to adjust the networks to be provably safe as well as scaling to larger networks."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) The case study model was initially tested by with a multitude of different hyperparameters. Weaknesses: 1) No consideration is made on assessing if safety is retained in the presence of faults. 2) The technique requires application-specific models.

8.226 REFERENCE [748]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "show that runtime checks can replace the requirement to statically verify safety of the baseline controller" on a simplex architecture featuring an 'advanced controller' (based on AI) and a backup 'baseline controller'.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks and reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	" Since the method does not use internal information about the advanced or baseline controller, we call the approach the Black-Box Simplex Architecture." "A well-known runtime assurance technique is the Simplex Control Architecture, which has been applied to a wide range of systems. In the original Simplex Architecture (...), the baseline controller (BC) and the decision module (DM) are part of the trusted computing base. The DM monitors the state of the system and switches control from the advanced controller (AC) to the BC if using the former could result in a safety violation in the near future. The original Simplex Architecture requires creating a provably safe BC, which can be difficult. In this work, we eliminate this requirement through a greater reliance on runtime verification. In the proposed Black-Box Simplex Architecture (BSA) (...), the BC (now referred to as the Lookahead Baseline Controller (LBC)), no longer needs to be statically verified, and can even be incorrect. The tradeoff is

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 331 / 550	

	<p>that the DM performs more extensive runtime checking and stores backup command sequences from previous computation steps. The DM performs simulation or reachability analysis based on a known system model. If the DM's computation time is too large, BSA keeps the system safe by switching control to a stored command sequence generated at an earlier step by the LBC and checked for safety by the DM."</p> <p>"BSA differs from the traditional Simplex Architecture in other important ways. First, the AC shares its command with the LBC instead of passing it directly to the DM. Second, the LBC uses this command as the starting point of a candidate safe command sequence."</p> <p>"Note that a candidate command sequence is not guaranteed to be safe until it is verified by the DM through a runtime check. Specifically, the DM checks safety of the LBC's candidate command sequence, rejecting it if safety is not ensured. The DM checks safety by running simulations (rollouts) for deterministic systems; for systems with uncertainty, it performs online reachability computation. BSA does not fail if the DM cannot finish the computation in time. Rather, it aborts the computation and switches to a backup command sequence that continues to ensure system safety. It can subsequently switch back to the AC when the runtime checks finish in time."</p> <p>"The applicability of BSA depends on the feasibility of two system-specific steps: (i) constructing candidate command sequences and (ii) proving their safety at runtime."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We prove the architecture is safe and present two case studies where (i) model-predictive control provides safe multi-robot coordination, and (ii) neural networks provably prevent collisions in groups of F-16 aircraft, despite the controllers occasionally outputting unsafe commands."</p> <p>Case Study (ii.) comments: "(...) the resultant controller was encoded in a large look-up table that used hundreds of gigabytes of storage. To make the system more practical, one early approach considered a downsampling process followed by a lossy compression using neural networks. We use these downsampled neural networks as the BC and refer to this as the original system."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not explicitly discussed on the conclusions, but the case studies show the need for high storage requirements for systems with uncertainties.</p> <p>Future work: Not discussed by the authors.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Excellent evolution of the simplex architecture for online learning safety-critical systems by incorporating formal methods.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) High computational resources are needed for dynamic systems with uncertainties (e.g., online learning). 2) The technique requires application-specific models.</p>

8.227 REFERENCE [749]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To introduce and discuss about a safety engineering approach for autonomous work-machine applications to support the early development phases of novel automation solutions and system operating concepts by utilizing elements from system safety engineering methods and the latest safety standards for autonomous machinery, as well as the goal-based safety case approach to support the management of safety goals and requirements.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	The authors have presented an approach to use STPA as the means to perform hazard analysis for autonomous systems and have reviewed whether this would fit current standards for autonomous systems.
Q4 Answer	No further results except for the safety analysis method summarized on Question 3 have been presented.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness: 1) Paper deals superficially with using STPA to perform hazard analyses of autonomous systems and reviews current standards. There is not enough novelty to justify the relevance of the paper.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 332 / 550	

8.228 REFERENCE [750]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To stimulate and contribute to the discussion of incorporating data-driven models uncertainties on safety assurance by exemplifying how dependable uncertainty estimates may become part of a dynamic risk management approach at runtime.
Q2 Answer	AI in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>Contextualization: "Treating failures of Data-Driven Models (DDM) in the same way as failures in traditional software appears insufficient, due to the less predictable nature of DDM failures." "Traditional safety measures against systematic software failures, like code reviews or white-box testing, are not sufficiently effective or applicable for DDMs. In contrast, addressing DDMs requires approaches for handling uncertainty." "(...) residual uncertainty remaining in the outcome of DDMs is a fact that needs to be dealt with."</p> <p>Previous and Related Work: "The application rule VDE-AR-E 2842-61 tries to overcome this gap by introducing ‘uncertainty-related’ failures for DDMs and other kinds of Artificial Intelligence. In part one it states, “in the future it might be possible to calculate a fault rate for AI elements, consequently called lambda-AI. Currently, it introduces an Uncertainty Confidence Indicator (UCI) as a concept to deal with uncertainty-related failures. Any claim about the achievement of a certain UCI level needs to be argued in an assurance case along with the evidence, e.g. based on metrics and specialized (test) datasets. However, it does not explain in detail how such an assurance case should look like and how to deal with ‘uncertainty-related’ failures considering the safety-criticality of the DDM." "(...) the distinction between aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty is probably the best known and most cited. In this context, ‘aleatoric’ means that uncertainty is caused by unavoidable randomness and has no systematic cause. Instead, ‘epistemic’ refers to uncertainty that is systematic, in the sense that it is related to phenomena that could be considered in principle but are not sufficiently addressed by a given model. The core motivation behind this separation is that the aleatoric part of uncertainty has to be accepted but the epistemic part should be reduced as much as possible, e.g., by collecting more and ‘better’ data. However, the distinction between the aleatoric and epistemic parts of uncertainty depends strongly on the viewpoint. Results provided for different DDMs are hard to compare since changes in the considered context including the data and space of potential hypotheses directly effects the meaning of the concepts." "(...) a classification orthogonal to aleatoric and epistemic was recently proposed (...). Their onion shell model distinguishes between three key sources of uncertainty, which can also be mathematically separated – regardless of the specific implementation of the DDM. It considers uncertainty directly attributed to limitations in the DDM (model fit), differences in the quality level of the model inputs (input quality), and the possibility that the model is applied outside its originally intended application scope (scope compliance)."</p> <p>Discussion: "Our proposal to estimate and handle ‘uncertainty-related’ failures can be incorporated in an assurance case such as the ones we previously proposed and provide a basis to argue that the residual risk due to DDM failures is acceptably low (...)." "Uncertainty Wrappers constitute a model-agnostic framework to obtain dependable and situation-aware uncertainty estimates (...) to provide explainable and statistically safeguarded uncertainty estimates." "(...) an uncertainty wrapper deals with a DDM that it encapsulates as a black box. Factors that are expected to influence input quality or scope compliance are modeled in a quality and scope model, respectively. (...) In opposite to many existing approaches, uncertainty wrappers accept a confidence requirement as an input when providing an uncertainty estimate, which makes their estimate dependable on a statistically interpretable level." "(...) the Uncertainty Wrapper (UW) monitors the DDM specifically for safety-critical deviations between DDM output and the ground truth. These deviations are formally captured in an uncertainty estimate (figuratively described as “Checking the Checker” pattern)." "Following this approach of “checking the checker”, a natural question may be, who checks the new checker and so on. This refers to having a confidence threshold defining how much we want the uncertainty result to be</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 333 / 550	

	trustable, more formally the residual probability of the uncertainty estimate being wrong. The UW can be parameterized with such a confidence value, thus constructively braking the “checking the checker” recursion."
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors have contextualized their Uncertainty Wrapper concepts within a Responsibility-Sensitive Safety (RSS) model for an autonomous vehicle to predict the friction coefficient of the road. Guidelines on creating an applicable Uncertainty Wrapper and discussing the expected results and actions in case of success and failure on lowering uncertainties have been presented.</p> <p>"By construction, the result of our approach is always better than working with worst-case assumptions, but it is application-specific. There is a trade-off to consider whether the benefits justify the effort to replace worst-case assumptions with dependable uncertainty estimates. We should also point out that our approach is also applicable towards estimating uncertainty for DDM-supported decision processes (in contrast to the case presented here, which targets DDM estimation of a real-valued parameter). In such cases, the results of the UWs do not consider multiple margins, which simplifies the process."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings:</p> <p>"The major limitation we currently view in our approach is the lack of objective evidence on its utility from a case study. While the Uncertainty Wrappers concept has been established and evaluated in comparison with other uncertainty estimation approaches in previous work, evaluating the effectiveness of its application with respect to its benefits to performance and availability of safety constraint monitoring as we have outlined in this paper remains to be seen.</p> <p>Finally, our approach assumes that uncertainty cannot be avoided completely and that it has to be addressed with probabilistic claims. So far, safety standards consider probabilistic claims only for random hardware failure but not for software. When extending the probabilistic reasoning to DDMs, a question arises with regards to whether random hardware failures and uncertainty-related failures should be considered together in order to assure that the target failure rates from integrity levels are achieved. However, this question is not specific to our approach and relates to the question of combining a lambda-AI and the traditional lambda for hardware failure rates to an overall lambda."</p> <p>Future work:</p> <p>"Our future work is related to the two contributions. First, we plan to evaluate the approach in different applications like truck platooning in order to quantify the benefits for performance and availability. The use cases of the research projects we are participating in, including those acknowledged below, offer us options for investigating autonomous system use cases. Second, we want to concretize the related safety argument and integrate it into an assurance case for machine learning on the example of cobots and automated guided vehicles."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good discussion on how to formally include uncertainties in the safety assurance of AI-based systems. Well-structured contextualization and interesting idea when defining 'Uncertainty Wrappers'. 2) Proposes an approach to the safety assurance of 'recursive AI' (i.e., when AI is used to ensure the safety of AI). <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The uncertainty wrapper itself is a general-purpose approach, but its inner models are application-specific. 2) The authors themselves consider that the model might be not practical to be used if simplified overapproximate, worst-case models are used instead.

8.229 REFERENCE [751]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To define a safety process for autonomous vehicles with self-learning comprising three cycles: development, safety and field, as well as to present three different types of ML/AI approaches regarding their usage within the development process of autonomous driving functions.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence and machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	"The present paper investigates which machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) based self-learning loops are reasonably integrable inside the whole development and operation lifecycle of autonomous

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 334 / 550	

	vehicles, beginning from the design and development phase, passing the testing, verification and validation process phases, and the safety and operational life cycle phases." Eight main steps: 1) Context analysis, scope and aim formulation; 2) Method selection (type of AI); 3) Data selection / spotting; 4) Data preprocessing; 5) AI model development and training; 6) Model testing, V&V; 7) Model application; 8) Model modification and updating.
Q4 Answer	The authors have mapped the steps of their method to several standards applicable to autonomous vehicles, discussed the most relevant AI elements used on these systems and proposed the usage of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to support the identification of safety-critical scenarios during requirements elicitation and V&V.
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: "The present approach did not yet cover (iii) the combination of self-learning cycles systematically. an example is to use the generative approaches to determine critical scenarios and their parametric abstract properties, which can then be used within anomaly detection approaches to identify scenarios." Future work: "Future work could provide more guidance on selection criteria for promising ML/AI based self-learning loops for AD function development and metrics for their level of support. Methods (...) will be implemented using experimental vehicles, an autonomous public transport shuttle bus, a transporter vehicle and a rural autonomous supply vehicle."
Q6 Answer	Stregths: 1) Relevant relevance towards establishing a safety assurance process for AI-based systems. 2) Good contextualization of AI on autonomous vehicles; 3) Good analysis on the relationship with current standards for safety and autonomous vehicles. Weaknesses: 1) Relevant standards have not yet been considered by the authors (e.g., UL4600:2020); 2) The safety assurance process has not been covered in a detailed way.

8.230 REFERENCE [752]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To propose a modeling approach that takes into account the different relevant aspects of a system, its adaptation process, as well as safety hazards and security attacks.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	"The safety aspects are modeled using Fault Trees and the security aspects are modeled using Attack Trees. (...) Therefore, we outline our idea on how we can combine the information from our models to generate an Attack-Fault Tree (AFT). The resulting AFT then serves as the basis for the associated safety and security analyses." "Joint analysis of safety and security requires combining Attack and Fault Trees into AFTs using additional information from the Dataflow Graph and Deployment Model. Attack and Fault Trees often operate on different levels of abstraction, i.e. attacks mostly target libraries, frameworks, protocols or hardware while basic events of Fault Trees are mostly triggered by missing or corrupted logical data flow or components. This different levels of abstraction are mirrored in the logical Dataflow Graph and the Deployment Model which specifies concrete systems and software implementing this data flow. Using a rule based translation scheme, patterns in the data flow or deployment model create partial AFTs – representing generic attack patterns or common weaknesses – that are connected to external events in the Attack and Fault Trees, combining them and bridging the abstraction gap. Rules are derived from Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) as well as Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification (CAPEC) data."
Q4	"In order to illustrate our proposed approach, we use a small, simplified example, due to space limitations. Our

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 335 / 550	

Answer	example consists of a ground control station (GCS) that communicates with an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), i.e. quadcopter, during a given mission via WiFi. The GCS sends flight commands to the UAV and receives telemetry data. If the UAV passes areas where the WiFi signal is too weak, the adaptation process starts and the system switches to longer range radio communication. The UAV then receives the command to fly back closer to the GCS. If the UAV is close enough to the GCS again, the system completes its adaptation by switching back to communicate via WiFi."
Q5 Answer	"The next steps of our research are to implement the different models and to define precisely the translation into AFTs. Currently, our approach does not consider time and probability aspects, although this is an important point since, e.g., long lasting high effort attacks on vulnerabilities that exist for only a short time during adaptation are less likely than attacks that can be executed within a short time. In addition, do we plan to use our approach also at run-time to continuously analyze a system with respect to safety and security. This allows us to include emerging security vulnerabilities even during the runtime of the system. To do this, however, we must ensure that the models are kept in sync with the system state as efficiently as possible and that the translation and analysis of the AFT can be performed within fixed time limits. Additionally, we plan a case study in which we use our approach to analyze larger and realistic systems in order to evaluate its scalability."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Relevant approach to combine safety and security analyses towards a full safety assurance. Weakness: 1) No direct relation to the safety assurance of AI.

8.231 REFERENCE [755]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To address the issue of learning-based controllers not having safety guarantees by introducing a model predictive safety certification (MPSC) scheme for linear systems with additive disturbances. The scheme verifies safety of a proposed learning-based input and modifies it as little as necessary in order to keep the system within a given set of constraints.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	"The proposed MPSC scheme estimates safety of a proposed learning-based input in real-time by searching for a safe back-up trajectory for the next time step in the form of generating a feasible trajectory towards a known safe set. Allowing the MPSC scheme to modify the potentially unsafe learning-based input, if necessary, provides safety for all future times. The result can be seen as a 'safety filter', since it only filters proposed inputs that drive the system out of what we call the safe set. The resulting online optimization problem can be efficiently solved in real-time using established model predictive (MPC) solvers. Partially unknown larger-scale systems can therefore be efficiently enhanced with safety certificates during learning." "The essential requirement is that in the safe set S, we always need to know a feasible backup controller that ensures constraint satisfaction in the face of uncertainty for all future times. The idea for constructing such a controller is based on MPC. (...) As the true system dynamics model is often unknown in the context of learning-based control, we employ mechanisms from tube-based MPC to design a safe backup controller for uncertain system dynamics."
Q4 Answer	"We consider the problem of safely acquiring information about the partially unknown system dynamics of a discretized mass-spring-damper system (...)." "After k = 115 time steps, a significant portion of the state space is already covered by the safe terminal set."
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) No direct relation to the safety assurance of AI.

8.232 REFERENCE [757]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To address safety and security of swarm robotics systems at the programming language level in order to allow the verification of safety and security during development.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 336 / 550

Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"We propose to integrate safety and security primitives in Buzz through keywords, built-in functions, and libraries. An application-dependent library of primitives can also be internally authored by the safety and security team of a development organization. (...) We want to design these primitives to represent traceable "syntactic patterns" in the code such that formal analysis and model checking of safety/security policies become feasible. Policies might concern the behavior of individual robots as well as their interaction. In addition, the formal analysis should also be easy to compute, efficient, and as precise as possible, with respect to a reduced set of conservative false positives and false alarms."</p> <p>"As a first safety-oriented modification to Buzz, we propose to embed privilege checking patterns and routines directly into the language."</p> <p>"A major challenge towards the validation of swarm safety is the evaluation of those properties that are emerging. These properties are a distinctive trait of swarms and they are not easily recognizable within the code of individual robots. (...) To mitigate this problem, again, we propose to intervene at the programming language level, through new Buzz constructs. In our vision, the swarm programmer should be able to forfeit the implementation of low-level safety checks and use Buzz primitives and best practices instead. In particular, Buzz offers "swarm-oriented programming through three constructs: swarm, with which a developer can assign tasks to group of robots based on tags (i.e. the id of one or more "swarms") associated with the robots; neighbors, used to perform spatial computation; and virtual stigmergy, a shared tuple space among all robots of a swarm."</p>
Q4 Answer	Since the authors only propose means to deal with their research problem, the only results are the proposed solutions presented on the response to Question 3.
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings:</p> <p>"It is important to observe that, since Buzz is a recently developed language, the implementation of these ideas is a lot less arduous than what it would be in more established programming languages. Buzz is relatively simple, does not have any dependencies, and can be modified without strong repercussions on a large user base."</p> <p>"Another current limitation of Buzz is that any predicate-preserving function at runtime and at the swarm level must be coded by the developer. Providing an automatic swarm-level assertion mechanism would reduce errors and maintain desirable safety properties at runtime."</p> <p>Future work: To implement the proposed models and assess them.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) No direct relation to the safety assurance of AI.</p>

8.233 REFERENCE [760]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To propose an improved unsupervised modeling approach called BézierVAE, which has a Bézier-curve output layer, which ensures autonomous vehicles trajectories' smoothness in both the position and speed domain.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; variational autoencoders, generative adversarial networks (neural networks), unsupervised learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Bézier-curves are parameterized through a set of control points with corresponding weights, which span a linear combination of Bernstein basis polynomials. Compared to polynomials, Bézier-curves have the advantage that their parameters have an intuitive meaning. Furthermore, the individual parameters affect the resulting trajectories only in a limited range, while the coefficients of a polynomial curve shape the trajectories globally which then easily overshoot. Regardless of the choice, the parametric curve needs to be implemented as a network layer and integrated into the overall architecture, in order to define the required loss terms on the generated trajectories. The resulting layer has no trainable weights, but only generates the trajectory from the previously computed curve parameters. In addition to the selection of a suited parametric curve, there are also several generative network architectures that may be used for the desired model."</p> <p>"The original encoder consists of four convolutional layers to condense the information contained in the trajectory, followed by two dense layers to generate the latent parameters. Stacks of convolutional layers are well suited for recognizing patterns, but they are not ideal for extracting individual values or retaining precise positional information of identified patterns due to their inherent convolutional and downsampling operations."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 337 / 550	

	<p>Therefore, we implemented an additional network path within the encoder, which exclusively consists of dense layers."</p> <p>"Compared to BézierGAN, further changes and improvements were introduced. First, we added batch normalization layers to accelerate the network training. Secondly, we set the sampling positions along the Bézier-curve to be uniformly distributed, since the trajectories within the highD dataset are sampled at a constant frequency. Finally, we simplified the regularization loss term, which now exclusively minimizes the Euclidean distance of successive control points and their weights. This loss term ensures that the control points to have a fixed order and the model uses only as many control points as necessary."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we selected lane changes and trajectories with distinct acceleration or deceleration for this work. The maneuver trajectories were extracted from the latest release of the highD dataset and include the vehicle's longitudinal and lateral positions over time."</p> <p>"We optimized the model with Adam and a learning rate of 5e-4. We trained each network for 50 000 iterations, whereby every iteration consists of a batch of 64 trajectories. For the latent representation, a size of ten was used, hence giving the model the possibility to learn up to ten different parameters."</p> <p>"By using a Bézier-curve layer and implementing additional loss terms, the generated trajectories are smooth in the position and speed domain, and result in more accurate reconstructions. When modeling lane changes, the NVOD improves by up to 83.4% and the RMSE is reduced by up to 91.3% compared to TraVAE."</p> <p>"we showed that semi-supervised learning can be used to incorporate predefined intuitive latent parameters which arise from given modeling requirements. Finally, the additional introduction of discrete latent parameters allows to integrate multiple maneuver classes into a single model and is demonstrated for maneuvers with distinct acceleration and deceleration."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings have not been discussed by the authors.</p> <p>Future work: "Future work will focus on investigating to what extent parameter learning can be enhanced to include potential unsupervised clustering and segmentation functionalities."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness: 1) Lack of deep relationship to the safety assurance of AI; instead, the paper focuses on using AI for safety-critical functions.</p>

8.234 REFERENCE [761]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To outline initial work in combining the X- μ approach (to model fuzzy uncertainty) with flexible requirements for an evolving system specified in RELAX, a formal framework to capture the uncertainty in evolving system requirements.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	<p>"The possibility of adaptation means that a designer may not be able to fully define the functional behaviour of a system, with the consequence that formal verification and testing may not be possible. (...) there is the potential for causing significant harm if a system malfunctions in some way, and a formal safety case requires more than an assertion that a system will work because it has not failed in testing."</p> <p>"RELAX has been proposed as a formal framework in which the uncertainty in adaptive system requirements can be captured and converted into specifications, which can then be used in formal proof or model-checking to verify that software meets its specifications. RELAX is a structured form of natural language which describes the properties and behaviour of a system. It is intended to create a system specification and consequently is unable to assess requirement satisfaction."</p> <p>"In order to model the uncertainty, we use a graded approach to the satisfaction of requirements, based on the X-μ representation (...) This aims to model the flexible definitions used in human language by allowing partial satisfaction of a predicate (in the same way as a fuzzy set); however, it differs from standard fuzzy set theory in focussing on the crisp sets of values that satisfy a predicate at different memberships, and in treating membership purely as an ordering. (...) The precise membership values are unimportant, as long as the ordering</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 338 / 550	

	is respected."
Q4 Answer	"We adapt the smart vacuum system (SVS) example focusing on a small sub-problem to illustrate our approach. Consider a room that is divided into unit squares, each of which is dirty, and a set of autonomous robot vacuum cleaners tasked to clean the room. We ignore issues such as route planning and co-ordination between the cleaning robots." "(...) considerable relaxation (to $a=1/3$) is required before the requirements can be satisfied. The result could be used to refine the system design or to evaluate it in comparison to another design. For completeness in this example, we have also modelled the system algebraically and calculated requirement satisfaction using the X- μ representation of membership functions."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings have not been discussed by the authors. Future work: "Further research is focused on exploring the use of dependency (DEP) information in decomposition of the search space, and in expanding the scope to larger examples."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) AI-based systems might benefit from the proposed approach, since it is applicable for evolving systems. Weakness: 1) Lack of deep relationship to the safety assurance of AI. 2) Research still deemed in initial stage by the authors themselves.

8.235 REFERENCE [762]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To review current challenges, industry practices, and opportunities for future research in software engineering for automated vehicles
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	"Requirements Engineering for Automated Driving (READ) needs to be data-driven and continuous, allowing expert-assisted extraction of driving specifications from traffic data. Human experts are necessary to judge the encountered situations and select the most appropriate responses. READ also needs to generate requirements on what data and how much to collect." "ADS architectures use multiple dependability patterns, including monitoring of system assumptions and system health, redundancy and diversity, and simplex architecture. A promising direction is to formalize interfaces and apply automated assume-guarantee reasoning to show that the architecture adequately addresses hazardous failures of components and their communication." "A winning approach to behavior planning has not yet emerged; however, hybrid approaches combining reinforcement and imitation learning with manually crafted policies appear most promising." "Machine learning has a profound impact on the development of automated driving software. Major new engineering activities include collection and curation of large datasets, design of neural network architectures for perception and planning tasks, and ensuring their effective training. As a result, engineering of automated driving software now involves data and training engineers in addition to software engineers. A major challenge is safety assurance of systems that rely on machine learning. Traditional safety assurance of complex automotive software according to ISO 26262 relies on the presence of a complete specification for the safety-critical systems, and the ability to inspect the program logic. Both aspects are lacking for ML-based functions, however. A subset of verification and validation methods intended for programmed software, such as testing and monitoring, are also applicable for assuring ML-based functions, but new methods are needed, including dataset-requirements engineering, measuring similarity between the training data and inputs at runtime, uncertainty management, architectural patterns to detect and mitigate failures of ML-based components, and methods to enable human interpretability and machine analyzability of learned logic." "A key practice is to develop and maintain a safety case, which is a rigorous argument supported by evidence that all relevant hazards have been identified and eliminated or sufficiently controlled or mitigated. (...)

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 339 / 550	

	Incremental safety assurance is an active area of research, and the application of model-based engineering appears to be a promising approach to support the evolution of safety cases and reduce the risk of oversights during updates"
	"Major challenges include test design, deciding what tests to perform at each stage, and deciding how much testing is enough. (...) Promising approaches to address the testing challenges are accelerated testing, fleet testing including a shadow mode, and incremental testing and arguments. Accelerated testing using rare event sampling methods actively seeks out rare and critical events, avoiding testing empty kilometers."
Q4 Answer	Since the paper is a discussion of open challenges on engineering automated vehicles, the main result is the set of discussed topics presented on the response to Question 3.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Clear, concise and relevant aspects related to machine learning usage on autonomous vehicles. All aspects are clearly extensible and generalized for the safety assurance of AI-based systems.

8.236 REFERENCE [763]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "discuss the urgent need for system testing in the context of safety-critical systems comprising AI methodologies".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence and machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"There are similarities and expected differences when considering systems comprising AI methods like machine learning as subjects of testing. For example, in case of machine learning the outcome depends on the data used for learning a certain model and the underlying machine learning approach. Hence, the outcome of the finally obtained model might vary. Other parts of the overall system relying on such a varying outcome have to deal with this uncertainties in an appropriate way not causing safety hazards. Hence, any verification approach needs to consider this variation and try find a critical situation. In addition, sensor based on machine learning may not always deliver the correct classification results. Even if coming up with a correct classification in 99% of the cases, we have to assure that the 1% of the remaining cases does not lead to safety violations. Hence, the overall system has to compensate for inaccuracies that might be higher than for ordinary sensors, and there is a strong requirement to verify the system especially considering all the cases where classification goes wrong."</p> <p>"(...) we will introduce such a testing environment that is used together with test case generation methods to carry out system testing automatically without the need of user interference. (...) This testing approach combines environmental ontologies with combinatorial testing. The underlying assumption is that there is a need for finding combinations of environmental entities for revealing faults. Hence, we argue that it is not only necessary to carry out system tests but also to consider environmental interactions in case of autonomous systems. In addition, we discuss some further challenges of testing autonomous systems, i.e., providing some sort of guarantees and methods for estimating the residual risk, i.e., the risk of still comprising a fault even after carrying out a proposed testing methodology. We will see that the use of environmental models allow for specifying such guarantees based on the degree of considering interactions between environmental entities and the degree to which the environmental model has been used for verifying a particular system."</p> <p>"(...) convert ontologies into input models of combinatorial testing [that] (...) captures basically necessary parameters and their domains. (...) In order to find critical scenarios, it would be required to consider all different combinations of parameter values, which of course is not feasible. In combinatorial testing, we are not considering all combinations but only all combinations for an arbitrary subset of the set of parameters of size t. If t is smaller than the total number of parameters, we have to generated substantially fewer tests."</p> <p>"(...) also introduced how to apply the proposed testing methodology in a practical setup. (...) The process starts with an ontology that captures the environment of the system under test (SUT). From this ontology, we obtain a combinatorial testing (CT) input model that is used to generate tests. Note that the generated tests are abstract</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 340 / 550	

	tests and need to be further concretized. For example, in the ontology we may only distinguish road fragments to be straight, or a left or a right curve. The details about the length or the radius of a curve are not given. Hence, in a concretization step we have to set these values. Afterwards, the SUT can be simulated."
Q4 Answer	<p>Automated system testing: "An AI-based system, e.g., a vision sensor used for classification obstacles in case of an AEB, might not always deliver correct results. Hence, we have to check how the whole system deals with this fact. (...) Such systems usually are at least very much complicated if not even complex. We have to assure that the system fulfills its specification under a sheer amount of potential interactions between the system and its surrounding environment. Therefore, it is also very much important to carry out testing in an automated way making use of simulation environments. (...) We may also test the whole system including hardware and software using a test bench where the hardware directly can be stimulated."</p> <p>Consider environmental knowledge: "(...) finding a way to represent the knowledge we have about our world is essential for testing AI-based systems with increased autonomy or adaptive behavior. This requirement is very well supported by the large amount of research papers dealing with the use of environmental ontologies for testing such systems in the context of the autonomous driving. Without environmental models finding critical situations that might cause the SUT to violate its specification can hardly be achieved."</p> <p>Providing guarantees: "(...) Only in case of a failure revealing test, we know that the SUT is still faulty. If the SUT passes all tests, either we have not used the right test case, or the SUT itself is really fulfilling its specification. (...) In order to come up with a testing criteria for testing AI-based systems we may borrow some ideas from CT. (...) the strength used for generating the test can be used as a guarantee. What is missing is a detailed analysis about meaningful values for 't' in the context of autonomous systems. (...) Another way of coming up with a measure representing some sort of guarantees would be to consider the used underlying ontologies themselves. (...) Ontology coverage may be the percentage of concepts used in testing from such an ontology. Again research is needed for (1) coming up with such an ontology for the application domain, and (2) to define ontology coverage formally."</p> <p>Estimate the residual risk: "(...) we have to search for a method that allows to estimate the residual risk of testing automated and autonomous systems based on certain parameters like coverage, mutation score, or combinatorial strength."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings and future work have been discussed on the answer to Question 4, since these were the main objectives of the research. Furthermore, the following future work is also emphasized:</p> <p>"Future research has to consider studies mapping the combinatorial strength to the number of not detected faults in case of autonomous and AI-based systems. In addition, we have to come up with other coverage definitions like ontology coverage and a prediction of the residual risk in case of testing."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Very concise and in-depth paper on the challenges for assuring the safety of AI-based safety-critical systems with tests. The authors actually expand their analysis by considering the modeling of the underlying environment to improve the quality of the presented method(s). 2) Very good discussion of future research. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No AI-related faults have been discussed.

8.237 REFERENCE [765]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose "a Monitor-Recovery approach based on a dynamic occupancy grid" as part of the Responsibility Sensitive Safety (RSS) model for highly automated vehicles in order "to verify the object information (Monitor) provided to RSS, and if required to correct wrong information (Recovery)."
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3	Comments on redundant blocks for the same function: "One possibility to address the safety challenge, is to

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 341 / 550	

Answer	<p>combine a diverse set of approaches to replicate the same functionality, e.g. object extraction or trajectory planning. If the diversity is sufficiently large, it can be argued that this functionality can provide a certain level of safety for example by considering always the worst-case. However, using diversity is first of all often computationally very expensive, and second usually hard to prove nonexistence of common cause failures or degradation."</p> <p>"RSS can be used as a safety layer for the AV planning components. However, for correct operation, the aforementioned safety approaches require that the provided input (object positions, velocities, heading) is correct. Hence, it is important to have a redundant safety checker for the perception, as well.</p> <p>Therefore, we propose in this paper a novel safety layer, composed of a monitor and recovery part, based on a dynamic occupancy grid, to verify (Monitor part) and if needed to correct the object information (Recovery part). The occupancy grid contains cell-wise information of the environment, whether the corresponding area is unoccupied (i.e. free), statically occupied (i.e. there is a stationary object), dynamically occupied (i.e. there is a moving object), or unknown (i.e. occluded region). This information can be used to verify an object list including its attributes (like heading and velocities), without extraction concrete objects from the grid information."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"To evaluate our proposed safety approach, we use the CARLA simulator. and equip an ego vehicle with a 360-degree LiDAR sensor. The LiDAR information is converted into a dynamic occupancy grid (...). The environment model is filled with the ground truth object information directly from CARLA. Into this ground truth object list we inject different kinds of faults (...). Then, the manipulated object list and the dynamic occupancy information is passed to our safety layer."</p> <p>"Our evaluation demonstrates that the approach is able to successfully detect common failures of a perception system and is able to recover from those errors."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings have been discussed throughout the case study along with their causes. These include issues which overly constrain safety and the susceptibility to potentially unsafe situations.</p> <p>Future work: "(...) we plan to perform additional evaluations on different scenarios in simulation and real world."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting architectural model that can be reused for other safety-critical applications. 2) Good discussion of positive and negative aspects of the proposed models. 3) Monitor is not dependent on AI. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Application-specific monitor.

8.238 REFERENCE [766]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "propose a two-stage safe reinforcement learning algorithm to automatically learn a long-term policy for high-speed driving that guarantees safety during the entire training."
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: "From the perspective of safe RL for autonomous driving, prior works can be broadly divided into two categories: (i) reward shaping: designing reward with risk terms; (ii) modifying the RL exploration process by action masking or correction with safety checker. However, the safety guarantees of those approaches are strongly dependent on expertise to design exquisite exploration policy."</p> <p>Basics: "(...) we propose a two-stage learning safe RL approach for end-to-end continuous control. It can solve the problem of learning an efficient and stable policy with safety guarantee during both training and execution for autonomous driving tasks, without the prerequisite of expert prior knowledge or feasible baselines. The specific autonomous driving scenario we investigate is a high-speed racing environment with complex road geometry (e.g. sharp turns, hills). For the sake of clarity, we define safety as no collision happened or not out of track. The policy efficiency is evaluated by the average speed of completing a task, the higher the better. And the policy stability is evaluated by the amplitude of the car's swing from side to side, the lower the better. (...)</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 342 / 550	

	<p>our two-stage safe RL approach adopts a modular design that combines an independent safeguard mechanism with model-free DRL and an adaptive reward function. The safeguard mechanism contains a rule-based module and a data-driven module. In the first learning stage, the rule-based module only helps RL agent avoid dangers, but does not require expert fine-tuning for an optimal action. This coarse correction does not care whether the performance is optimal or not and it is the difference between our rule-based module and prior rule-based approaches. The adaptive reward encourages policy to update in the direction of improving safety before efficiency. At the same time, the data-driven module is trained by data collected at this stage. Once the data-driven module has acquired sufficient correction capability, our algorithm enters the second learning stage by replacing the rule-based safeguard module with the data-driven safeguard module. Inspired by recent works, but not limited by pre-training and the assumption above, we develop an analytical feasible solution to ensure safety and accelerate convergence. The adaptive reward now changes to guide policy convergence to high efficiency and better stability."</p> <p>The reinforcement learning model is transformed onto a similar neural network, on which reachability analyses are applied. Parts of the model are application-specific, whereas other ones are of general application.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We conducted experiments on the open racing simulator (TORCS) (...). The state is a 29-dimension vector from multiple sensors consisting of an angle between agent direction and track axis, 3 speeds along the longitudinal, transverse, Z axis respectively, 19 distances between track edge and agent, a distance between agent and track axis, 4 wheel rotation speeds and an engine rotation speed."</p> <p>"No. of unsafety recorded during training and testing, our algorithm achieves zero safety violation when learning from scratch, while all baselines fail to do this. The closed-form solutions for the safety constraint in DDPG+sl and DDPG+Ly help DRL converge to a safer policy than standard DDPG. As the safety layer of DDPG+sl is pre-trained before RL policy learning, it has much lower safety violations than DDPG+Ly, which learns both Lyapunov function and RL policy from scratch. Failing to guarantee safety in DDPG+sl is partly because short-sighted safety prediction is hard to deal with dangerous situations in time for complex high-speed racing tasks, and partly because the dynamics model of DDPG+sl with simple network structure have limited ability to give an action correction solution exactly. The reasons for safety violations in DDPG+Ly can be attributed to unreliable Lyapunov function at the beginning of training and dissatisfaction of the assumption of the baseline feasible policy."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed / not found.</p> <p>Future work: "In our future work, we will extend this work to other model-free RL algorithms. Further, we plan to test the proposed algorithm in challenging roads with complex terrains, such as mountainous or rural areas."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Sound safe reinforcement learning method for autonomous vehicles.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) Part of the solution is application-specific; 2) No analysis of AI faults.</p>

8.239 REFERENCE [768]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "introduce a code generation concept and tool support that enables the automatic synthesis of ConSert-based runtime monitors for CPS in the Rust programming language".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) [we propose] a Rust-based code generation component conserts-rs that supports both safety engineers and embedded software developers to use the ConSert approach in practice. conserts-rs leverages model-based ConSert representations (created by design-time safety engineering tools) and automatically generates formal ConSert runtime models and executable composition and evaluation monitors."</p> <p>"It should be noted that the monitor component should integrate into a runtime environment (e.g. an RTOS) that is usable for safety-critical domains, i.e. the environment should support abstractions to schedule both periodic and non-periodic tasks. As the Consert tree is a success tree and as each runtime property is unknown (and evaluates to false) by default, deadline misses or runtime errors cause a conservative reaction by the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 343 / 550	

	Consert, i.e. a guarantee is not given."
Q4 Answer	<p>"In order to evaluate our tool, given the above considerations, we have measured inference latency (based on processor cycle count and processor frequency) on an embedded microcontroller. We employed a Nordic Semiconductor board (nRF52840), with a 64MHz ARM Cortex-M4 core with FPU, 1MB Flash, and 256kB RAM. While this exact board is not used in safety-critical domains, the hardware resources are comparable to those that are in use (w.r.t. processor speed and memory).</p> <p>For the experiment, we generated a set of artificial ConSerts with {10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000} runtime evidence and a top-level OR gate that is connected to all of them."</p> <p>"From our further experiments, we deduce that the latency scales linearly with the number of runtime evidence, the number of logic gates, as well as the number of evidence samples size the monitor keeps for statistical analysis."</p> <p>"(...) it is evident that code complexity scales well with the size of the ConSert, and should allow for efficient manual code review."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "Rust does not have a certified compiler yet, but there is the Ferrocene effort to develop a solution in the near future."</p> <p>Future work: "The focus of the performance evaluation in this paper centered around the monitoring component for an individual system. However, in CPS, the whole chain of constituent systems and their intermediate networks need to be considered to derive guarantees regarding CPS real-time capabilities. Thus, enlarging the deployment scope of monitoring components to multiple systems within a CPS and considering network latencies is the next step in our research agenda.</p> <p>Additionally, we plan to expand upon the monitor capabilities by linking it with the established concept of Digital Dependability Identities (DDIs). We envision that DDI-based ConSerts could enhance the scope of the generated monitors and yield benefits throughout a CPS' lifecycle. Further, we intend to evaluate the synthesized monitors on industrial use cases, which should allow for further potential improvements."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Initial efforts on using automated generation of ConSerts for adaptive systems (including AI-based ones).</p> <p>Weakness: 1) Except for the ConSerts underlying concepts, the research itself is focusd on performance and feasibility of ConSerts generation in runtime rather than on the safety assurance of AI-based systems.</p>

8.240 REFERENCE [769]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To "synthesize several techniques to speed up computation: decomposition, warm-starting, and adaptive grids" to learn and update safety analysis based on Hamilton-Jacobi reachability.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general; reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: "A few researchers take the approach of safe (machine) learning, where learning algorithms are updated or guided to provide safer resulting controllers during training. This can be done by, for example, projecting an algorithm's update of a policy to a valid constraint set, moving slowly in uncertain areas, or using Lyapunov functions to drive the learning of a safe policy.</p> <p>One way to enable any reinforcement algorithm to maintain safety is to precompute a fixed guaranteed safe set and safety override controller to keep the system within that set. This can be done using techniques like control barrier functions or Hamilton-Jacobi (HJ) reachability.</p> <p>Another line of work takes the approach of learning for safety. The premise of this work is that a safe policy or safe set will not be valid if the assumptions about the system model or constraints no longer hold. Therefore, the system must update its assumptions and corresponding safe methods as the system learns more about the environment.</p> <p>Finally, learning for safety and safe (machine) learning can be combined by jointly producing a guaranteed safe set and corresponding safe controller based on information gathered online, while simultaneously learning a performance controller. These approaches produce strong results for small (2-3D) systems, but struggle to extend to higher dimensional systems due to the computational complexity of updating the safe set and safety controller."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 344 / 550	

	<p>Basics: "(...) we seek to efficiently compute safe controllers and sets online for realistic systems without compromising on strong theoretical guarantees. To accomplish this, we (...) [incorporate] three methods to improve computation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Decomposing dynamical systems with "self-contained subsystems" to improve computation by orders of magnitude while maintaining exact results. 2) When new information is learned about the system or environments, updating the safe set directly using warm-starting rather than completely recomputing the safe set. <p>(...)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3) Initializing the safe set computation with a coarse grid that is refined over time, while maintaining exact or conservative guarantees."
Q4 Answer	<p>"To make the simulation as realistic as possible, we build every task of the framework, which consist of state estimation, collecting disturbance data, training GP model, updating safe set, learning-based controller, and safety verification, run in parallel. The only difference from the real experiment setup is that we assume that we receive accurate positions of the drone from the Motion Capture system."</p> <p>"Using our methods we were able to compute and update the safety analysis for a 10D near-hover quadcopter in an average of 3.3 minutes, as opposed to 1 to 2 hours for the prior work to update safety for a 4D system or an intractable amount of time for the 10D system. This new framework allows learning for safety to be applied to a much larger class of realistic systems."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "First, the techniques introduced in the new framework can be generalized beyond wind disturbances, updating the safety analysis when changes in knowledge of obstacles, model uncertainty, or other agents occur. The efficiency of this framework can also be sped up through (a) efficient toolbox implementations of HJ reachability, (b) more sophisticated adaptive gridding, and (c) localized warm-starting. Finally, the code was written to easily generalize to any robot using Robot Operating System (ROS), and we are eager to perform hardware experiments across different platforms."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Solid background on safe learning / learning for safety for reinforcement learning-based systems. 2) The obtained results indicate that the method is feasible for usage in safety-critical systems with restrictive real-time requirements. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Models are application-specific; 2) The focus of the paper is on improving performance rather than assuring safety, since the latter has been considered fulfilled beforehand.

8.241 REFERENCE [770]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To present "that neural controllers obtained via adversarial training are subjected to three types of defects, namely transient, systematic, and conditional errors".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general; deep learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction to Adversarial Training: "Adversarial training has led to significant improvements of deep models' resiliency to imperceptible perturbations. This was shown both empirically and with certification. An emerging line of work suggests that the representations learned by adversarially trained models resemble visual features as perceived by humans more accurately compared to standard networks. In contrast, a large body of work characterized the trade-off between a model's robustness and accuracy when trained by adversarial training. Some issues such as gradient obfuscation, during training, seemed to play a role in the mediocre performance of the models. Nevertheless, adversarially trained networks also showed to maintain their robustness properties as well as their accuracy in transfer learning settings."</p> <p>Basics: The authors have presented theoretical models to show that "adversarial</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 345 / 550	

	training and even its generalization result in unexplored error profiles that lead to unsafe behavior".
Q4 Answer	<p>"In our case study, we develop a controller for a vision + Lidar-based mobile robot. A human operator enables and disables the mobile robot via visual gestures. Once activated, the robot navigates such that it always faces the human operator at a distance of roughly one meter. The control software consists of two neural networks and a state-machine with two states."</p> <p>"(...) our experiments demonstrate that models trained by standard empirical risk minimization yield the best robotic performance in real-world scenarios. Counterintuitively, the best-performing agents are also vulnerable to making the robot crash under adversarial patterns. Conversely, while the models learned via our safety-domain training are provably immune to such worst-case behavior, they significantly perform worse in real-world scenarios. In particular, we observed that the strictness of the specifications enforced using adversarial training is the most dominant factor in determining the expected real-world robot performance. Our empirical evaluations confirm that adversarial training of neural controllers requires rethinking before reliably using them in robot learning schemes."</p> <p>"(...) the results confirm that the errors occurred uniformly across different scenarios. Therefore, we conclude that imposing adversarial robustness specification causes transient errors confirming our theory."</p>
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good contextualization of adversarial training and adversarial attacks. 2) Good mathematical rigor in defining theorems and showing their proofs to yield the conclusions of the research. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No significant information on why/how the AI models' architectures have been crafted for the case study. 2) Not sufficiently clear on why case studies would be needed to prove what has otherwise been formally shown by means of theorems. It might increase understanding, but it does not seem necessary unless the proven theorems are not fully applicable and/or reflected by the used models. 3) The concept of 'safety' is not entirely clear, as the so-called image recognition errors are of very different categories (e.g., errors that make a robot move when it shouldn't and the other way round. It seems that a better classification would be needed.

8.242 REFERENCE [771]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To "present a language for the description of the Operational Design Domain (ODD) of Automated Driving Systems (ADSs), in a textual format that leans on natural language influence. Such format is intended to be both human and machine-readable and would be relevant to end users such as regulators and systems designers".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) ODD plays an important role in the safety assurance of ADSs and ADASs, and needs to be considered throughout the development cycle, from conceptual phase to verification and validation phase."</p> <p>On the remainder of the paper, the authors define an ontology for formally defining an ODD for ADSs. It includes the following features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Domain model classes, attributes, metrics, data types, and units; - Language concepts: inclusion, exclusion, conditional elements, default states, compositions, conditional statements, operators, extension mechanisms, and domain model reference.
Q4 Answer	The authors apply their reasoning for conceiving ODDs to an existing ODD to exemplify its elements.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6	Strengths:

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 346 / 550	

Answer	<p>1) Using ontologies is a promising approach for AI-based systems. Application-specific ontologies might be developed for each purpose.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Other than the previous strength, the paper bears little connection to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.</p>
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8.243 REFERENCE [773]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "(...) propose a distributional RL framework in order to learn adaptive policies which allow to tune their level of conservativity at run-time based on the desired comfort and utility." whilst ensuring fail-safe actions "(...) using a proactive safety verification approach (...)".
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"This dilemma between more conservative but slower policies and risky but faster policies is thoroughly elaborated (...) where higher timeout penalties as part of the reward function resulted in a faster but more risky policy. The origin of this problem lies in the difficulty of shaping the reward to guarantee having safe policies in gradient-based learning approaches (...)".</p> <p>"Another approach to address safety for RL policies is to utilize a safety layer which filters out unsafe actions (...). This safety layer must be easily verifiable without any black boxes such as deep neural networks inside its architecture which are hard to verify."</p> <p>"Our contribution is to address safety, scalability and comfort as the main intertwined challenges for automated driving under uncertainty. We introduce safe distributional RL which considers maximum uncertainty and capability inside safety verification layer. During training, the RL agent is penalized for every safety intervention (...). However, the main difference is that it learns distributions instead of expected values for each action return which helps to provide risk-aware policies that are able to adapt their conservativity according to the existing uncertainty in the environment. This feature makes the learned policy generic and applicable to high uncertainty levels that rarely happen in realistic applications, for example when the sensor range is severely occluded due to a parked vehicle or it has high uncertainty."</p> <p>"In order to verify safety, we propose a proactive safety verification approach which provides safe actions for every state s. We call it proactive since the worst-case scenario is always considered to prevent being in an unsafe state in the future."</p> <p>"(...) we propose to apply safety as a hard constraint in the decision making problem while trying to minimize other costs such as utility or comfort as soft constraints."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We train and evaluate different RL policies for automated merging and crossing at occluded intersections using our high level simulator which can simulate different randomized scenarios."</p> <p>"According to our experiments, the learned distributional policy requires less safety interference in noisy environments compared to a rule-based safe policy even when the noise level is higher than the training configurations."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "(...) one can propose a better conservativity tuning approach in order to learn policies that automatically tune their risk sensitivity (...) at runtime based on the observed uncertainty or the required risk sensitivity in the environment."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Sound method for safe reinforcement learning whilst reducing training costs and improving performance.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Application-specific approach for the most part.</p> <p>2) No remarks on how to ensure safety in the presence of faults / failures.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 347 / 550	

8.244 REFERENCE [777]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To "propose a methodology for domain analysis to build up an ontology for perception of autonomous vehicles including characteristic features that become important when dealing with neural networks".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, with focus on deep neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"We built the ontology for supporting two main use cases (...). The first use case is labeling of training and test data. The second use case, on which we will focus in the remainder of this paper, is the systematic generation of synthetic data sets."</p> <p>"it has been shown that DNN-based models are prone to texture bias and do not incorporate shape information like humans would expect. Therefore, we strive for deriving such variations automatically from our ontology and to incorporate them into the image definitions for the scenario."</p> <p>"In the first step, existing standards targeting (part of) the domains under analysis are reviewed." "In a second step, parallel to reviewing public data sources, an initial brainstorming workshop with experts from different fields of expertise is performed to derive an initial set of relevant context dimensions. Hereby, context dimensions are elements or properties that can be varied to achieve a specific effect on a DNN function like weather conditions or degree of occlusion." "In a third step, we aimed at deriving a structuring of the obtained context elements into different categories." "The initial set of context elements and categories are then refined in expert interviews in a fourth step. The goals of this step are (i) to identify further important context elements, (ii) to derive a number of possible manifestations (also called variations) for each element, and (iii) to get a first expert opinion on importance of the different context element categories." 5th step: Consolidation of context elements. "The consolidation of context elements is performed iteratively and alternating with the expert interviews for the different context element categories. The consolidation has two major goals: identifying shared context elements and grouping coherent information while factoring out shared information. Performing such a consolidation is key for obtaining a usable and well-structured input domain model." 6th step: "The input domain model shall be used for specifying data request for the production of synthetic data and to label existing data. This requires a clear understanding of the meaning of each context dimension (in literature also referred to as the semantics). Therefore, we strived at providing a grounding of each context dimension in a physical and/or measurable quantity with a defined unit." 7th step: Refinement based on Data Analysis, Assurance Case, and Test 8th step: Derive an ontology with tools 9th step: Fine-tuning the derived ontology with manual addition of "superclasses and relationships between these superclasses".</p>
Q4 Answer	"(...) we describe some results for the data generation of our Euro NCAP-like scenario and introduce two further applications of our ontology, namely defining an operational design domain (ODD) and labeling 3D assets." The results are presented in a summarized way.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Additional research supporting that ontologies are useful tools towards building and assuring that an AI-based system is safe due to the rigor they bring on specifying and defining elements that shall be within and/or processed by a system. 2) Interesting application on generating test cases. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lacks in-depth analyses of results. 2) Little connection with safety has been explored by the authors.

8.245 REFERENCE [778]

Q-Index	5
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 348 / 550

Q1 Answer	To "address the problem of formal safety verification for stochastic cyber-physical systems (CPS) equipped with ReLU neural network (NN) controllers" in order "(...) to find the set of initial states from where, with a predetermined confidence, the system will not reach an unsafe configuration within a specified time horizon."
Q2 Answer	Neural networks (with ReLU activation function).
Q3 Answer	"(...) we propose a new verification scheme for stochastic dynamical systems equipped with ReLU neural network controllers. Particularly, we consider discrete-time LTI systems with Gaussian noise and partition of the continuous state space into convex sets. Then, we abstract the system by a graph and formulate a Satisfiability Modulo Convex problem which we solve using existing tools in order to estimate valid upper bounds on the transition probabilities between pairs of nodes in the graph. Using this transition graph, we also develop an algorithm to estimate tight upper bounds on the probability the system reaches the set of unwanted states after a specified amount of steps, even when the underlying transition probability bounds have been over-estimated." "(...) here we provide bounds that are correct by design. Additionally, we use the proposed SMC formula to devise a heuristic method to subdivide the cells in a given abstraction in order to further improve our safety probability estimations. Finally, we provide numerical simulations on a robot navigation problem corroborating the efficacy of our proposed verification method (...)"
Q4 Answer	"(...) we present simulation results to validate the proposed bounds on the probability that a point-sized robot collides with the boundary of the non-convex planar workspace. Particularly, we (...) assume that the robot's dynamics can be modeled as a single-integrator. (...) Additionally, we assume that the robot is equipped with a LiDAR scanner that emits a set of q lasers evenly distributed in a 2*pi rad fan (...). To drive the robotic system to a predetermined goal position using only the feedback d(xt), we employed a ReLU neural network controller consisting of three hidden layers and a total of 32 neurons." "We observe that our method provides tighter bounds (...) for every horizon, even for the coarse partition considered in this scenario. (...) the safety probability bounds estimated using merging and/or refinement are noticeably tighter than the ones without. Finally, we certify the correctness of the proposed safety probability bounds by comparing them to the true safety probability of for the cell that is adjacent to the one subject to the refinement. (...) We observe that all bounds returned by our method correctly upper bound the true probability, while the bounds obtained by using both merging and refinement are the tightest. We also remark that the gap between the estimated bounds and the true safety probability becomes larger as the horizon increases."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: The method is applicable to discrete-time linear time-invariant systems with Gaussian noise. Future work: Not discussed.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Another example of technique to formally verify a neural network-based controller (under the assumption that all its neurons have a ReLU activation function) with strong mathematical basis. Weaknesses: 1) The method requires application-specific system models to function. 2) There are no comments on how to assess faults along with the 'functional safety' concept.

8.246 REFERENCE [779]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "(...) propose Simplex-Drive, a framework that can achieve runtime safety assurance for machine-learning enabled controllers of AVs (...)" by using "(...) an unverified Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based advanced controller (AC) that achieves desirable performance in complex scenarios, a Velocity-Obstacle (VO) based baseline safe controller (BC) with provably safety guarantees, and a verified mode management unit that monitors the operation status and switches the control authority between AC and BC based on safety-related conditions."
Q2 Answer	(Deep) reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	"Taking the advantage of the Simplex-Drive architecture, this study focuses on the runtime assurance design of Reinforcement Learning-enabled AV controllers with applications to lane-changing scenarios." "The framework consists of three major components: namely the Advanced performance controller (AC), the Baseline safe controller (BC) and the Mode management unit (MM)."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 349 / 550	

	<p>"The AC is data-driven and maps the current state into a control action. In this study, AC can be obtained by training the DRL policy. In contrast, the BC is required to be designed with provable safety guarantee. In the case study of this paper, we design a BC based on the ORCA principle, which is proven to preserve collision avoidance property. The MM monitors the state at runtime and switches control authority from AC to BC if AC will lead the system to an unrecoverable state (i.e. a state where the system cannot guarantee safety property) at some time step in the future. When AC=BC, the MM can also switch the mode back to AC to resume AC control if the system returns to a recoverable state. Both MM and BC are proven to guarantee safety properties, while AC is not required to be verified correct-by-construction."</p> <p>"The Optimal Reciprocal Collision Avoidance (ORCA) approach was originally proposed for multi-robot collision avoidance and it has been theoretically proved to be able to preserve the safety property. Therefore, we utilize the ORCA as the baseline safe controller in our system to guarantee safety. Since the ORCA is originally designed for omni-directional robot, we extend the ORCA to the control of Ackermann dynamic vehicles."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we conducted extensive experiments in the highway-env simulation environment with different levels of complexity and operation conditions. (...) In the experiments, we focus on dense traffic scenarios with 3 lanes (the lane width are assumed to be fixed). The controlled ego vehicle (with initial speed V_{ego}) and the obstacle vehicles (with initial speed V_{other}) are assumed to have the same size.</p> <p>"The evaluation metrics used in the experiments include the target lane rate and collision rate, indicating whether the ego vehicle reaches the target lane before the epoch ends and whether the maneuver results in collisions, respectively."</p> <p>"It can be seen that the ORCA-Drive safe controller can always guarantee the safety with 0 collision during all the experiment trials. (...) the proposed Simplex-Drive architecture (with ORCA as BC and attention PPO as AC) can achieve higher success rates while maintaining desirable driving efficiency."</p> <p>"To further verify the safety of our switching logic, we conduct another experiment to simulate the circumstance that AC loses control. (...) During the experiment, the ratio of active time of BC increase from 23% to 35% when 'dummy' controller performed slow acceleration action and from 51% to 58% when 'dummy' controller performed aggressive action. The results show that the ratio of BC controller's active time increases as the the acceleration and traffic density grows, indicating that the switching logic can effectively predict potential unsafe states and take over the AC controller to ensure safety, while avoiding unnecessary frequent switching to maintain the control performance."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not found / discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "Our future work will focus on the implementation and validation of the proposed approach on physical vehicle platforms in real-world scenarios."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good example of the simplex architecture to provide safety for AI-based systems.</p>

8.247 REFERENCE [780]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To "investigate the changes introduced [on Convolutional Neural Networks] by three compression methods – post-training quantization, global unstructured pruning, and the combination of both – that go beyond the test accuracy."
Q2 Answer	Convolutional neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we investigate the effects of model compression when using global unstructured pruning, post-training quantization, and their combination. We therefore aim to provide insights towards the question what and to which extent changes occur on a deeper level and how that could potentially impact efforts towards arguing the safety of the system by making the following contributions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We investigate the effects of model compression on the class and sample level regarding their predictive quality over three different models and two datasets • Additionally, for model pruning we investigate the effects on the attention of the models regarding compared to the initial models by analyzing their saliency maps."
Q4 Answer	"To analyze the influence model architecture, we considered three different networks. A ResNet-18 (~11m parameters) for its widespread usage, a SqueezeNet (~750k parameters) for its computational efficiency, and a LeNet-5 (~62k parameters) for its small size. We trained the models on CIFAR-10 and the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark. (...) We trained each

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 350 / 550	

	<p>model by minimizing the negative log-likelihood using Adam as an optimizer. To prevent overfitting, we stopped the training after the loss did not decrease for 40 epochs."</p> <p>"To compress the models, we used the implementations for pruning and quantization provided by the ML framework PyTorch. We choose global unstructured pruning, using the L1 norm to score the parameters of the model, whereby the ones scored lowest are removed. (...) For quantization, we chose a non-intrusive post-training approach with per-channel bit allocation, as it gave the best results in our experiments."</p> <p>"Most configurations show only a slight drop in accuracy of less than 1 percentage point (pp), with the exception of some networks quantized with 4-bit weight precision. These are not considered further in the following sections as their substantial drop in accuracy already implies significant changes."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Excessive post-training quantization (to 4-bit samples) had significantly negative effect on accuracy. Combined pruning and quantization also had some negative effect, but to a lesser extent. Using a single compression method yields better results at the cost of a higher processing time. Some classes might have confidence issues with compression methods too.</p> <p>Future work: "(...) we suggest to expand our experiments also to other model architectures, datasets, and tasks and to investigate other compression techniques, e.g., quantization-aware training, structured pruning, or knowledge distillation, as these are also highly relevant in practice. Furthermore, we deem it as highly important to further develop methods for systematically and rigorously analyzing machine learning systems that go beyond averaging metrics, as these hide many peculiarities that bear the potential for failures. Lastly, we deem it equally as important to continue research into the direction of continuous safety assurance in order to consider safety as integral part of the development of ML-based systems, addressing issues such as potentially negative effects due to model compression early on."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting analysis on how pre-processing datasets and using compression techniques affects the results of an AI-based model.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Other than some interesting references and the relevance of the theme to safety assurance, the research itself does not directly contribute to establishing means or methods for assuring the safety of AI-based systems.</p>

8.248 REFERENCE [781]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To "show that this method [that generates verified executable programs] can itself be verified (...) [by presenting] a formal framework and a prototype Agda implementation that represent PDDL plans as executable functions that inhabit types that are given by formulae describing planning problems".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we turn our attention to AI Planning languages (...). We show that the Planning Domain Definition Language (PDDL) is a natural domain for the Curry-Howard implementation of declarative reasoning. In particular, specifications of planning problems that are usually written in first-order logic can be expressed naturally as types, and executable plans that are generated by PDDL can be formalised as programs that inhabit those types. Type checking thus verifies that correct executable programs are generated from specifications via the automated planning tool. We provide a proof-of-concept implementation in the dependently-typed language Agda."</p> <p>"Firstly, we need to formulate a generic and automatable approach to translate PDDL domains and problems into the dependently-typed setting. In addition, we need to devise our calculus in such a way as to ensure that the programs that inhabit the types give us the actual executable plans in the PDDL sense."</p>
Q4 Answer	The authors have formally defined the characteristics that shall be included and/or instantiated in the PDDL language to support the generation of verified executable programs. Moreover, related theorems have been presented and proven.
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Actual practical usage might be still far from feasible, given the complexity of the underlying Curry-Howard method and the lack of refinement of languages that able to implement it.</p> <p>Future work: "We however hope to extend this initial framework to the full first-order syntax of PDDL." "(...) we note that PDDL lacks any general method of handling consistency as well as similar but more complex</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 351 / 550	

	constraints and invariants, such as, for example, constraints saying that handEmpty and holding x are mutually exclusive. This is a complex problem, but one for which we anticipate that our dependently-typed setting will soon provide some useful solutions." "The design of this Agda prototype has revealed several limitations in state-of-the-art implementations of planning languages: e.g. their reliance on the closed word assumption and formulae grounding, the absence of functions, and the restricted use of disjunctions. Again, we see a potential of our method to overcome many of these limitations thanks to our general dependently-typed set-up, in which the use of functions, higher-order features, constraints and effect handling will be much more natural than in the current implementations."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Interesting initial approach towards using programming languages that ensure by construction that AI is safe. Weaknesses: 1) Research still in initial state; 2) No discussion on how to model faults.

8.249 REFERENCE [782]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present "(...) Verisig, a hybrid system approach to verifying safety properties of closed-loop systems using neural networks as controllers."
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general (sigmoid activation function).
Q3 Answer	"Although the SMT- and MILP-based approaches work well for the verification of properties of the DNN itself, these techniques cannot be straightforwardly extended to closed-loop systems using DNNs as controllers. Specifically, the non-linear dynamics of a typical CPS plant cannot be captured by these frameworks except for special cases such as discrete-time linear systems." "To overcome this limitation, we investigate an alternative approach, named Verisig, that allows us to verify properties of the closed-loop system. In particular, we consider CPS using sigmoid-based DNNs instead of ReLU-based ones and use the fact that the sigmoid is the solution to a quadratic differential equation. This allows us to transform the DNN into an equivalent hybrid system such that a DNN with L layers and N neurons per layer can be represented as a hybrid system with L+1 modes and 2N states. In turn, we compose the DNN's hybrid system with the plant's and verify properties of the composed system's reachable space by using existing reachability tools (...). To analyze the feasibility of the proposed approach, we show that the DNN reachability problem (i.e., checking whether the DNN's outputs lie in some set given constraints on the inputs) can be transformed into a real-arithmetic property with transcendental functions, which is decidable if Schanuel's conjecture is true. We also prove that reachability is decidable for DNNs with one hidden layer, given interval constraints on the inputs. Finally, by casting the problem in the dReach framework, we also show that reachability is delta-decidable for general DNNs."
Q4 Answer	"To evaluate the applicability of Verisig, we consider two case studies, one from reinforcement learning (RL) and one where a DNN is used to approximate a Model Predictive Controller (MPC) with safety guarantees. (...) We trained a DNN on a benchmark RL problem, Mountain Car (MC), and verified that the DNN achieves its control task (i.e., drive an underpowered car up a hill) within the problem constraints. In the MPC approximation setting, we used an existing technique to approximate an MPC with a DNN and verified that a DNN-controlled quadrotor reaches its goal without colliding into obstacles." "We observe that, at similar levels of approximation, the MILP-based approach is faster than Verisig+Flow* for small DNNs and DNNs with few layers. However, the MILP-based approach's runtimes increase exponentially for deeper networks whereas Verisig+Flow* scales linearly with the number of layers since the same computation is run for each layer. This is another positive feature of our technique since deeper networks are known to learn more efficiently than shallow ones."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: 1) "We focus on sigmoid-based networks and exploit the fact that the sigmoid is the solution to a quadratic differential equation, which allows us to transform the neural network into an equivalent hybrid system." Future Work: "For future work, it would be interesting to investigate whether one could use sigmoid-based

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 352 / 550	

	<p>DNNs to approximate DNNs with other activation functions (with analytically bounded error). This would enable us to verify properties about arbitrary DNNs and would greatly expand the application domain of Verisig.</p> <p>A second direction for future work is to speed up the verification computation by exploiting the fact that the sigmoid dynamics are monotone and quadratic. Although the proposed technique is already scalable to a wide range of applications, it still makes use of a general-purpose hybrid system verification tool, i.e., Flow*. That is why, developing a specialized sigmoid verification tool might bring significant benefits in terms of scalability and precision."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Formal verification of ANNs with sigmoid activation functions. Excellent performance for neural networks with multiple hidden layers and neurons.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No further comments on how to model and assess faults.</p>

8.250 REFERENCE [783]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To provide an operational scenario-based assurance method for assuring the safety of a software product.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	<p>"The goal of the method is to demonstrate safety based on specific operational scenarios to assure the effect of a software product. To represent safety arguments explicitly, we use a scenario-based model written in Event Sequence Diagram (ESD) as safety case. We assume that ESD can represent safety boundary in line with an operational scenario as a given environment.</p> <p>The proposed method is constructed using a four-steps procedure to construct scenario-based safety case:"</p> <p>"Step0) Select target normal scenario and construct ESD representing normal scenario"</p> <p>"Step1) Identifying elements related to the target scenarios and software by using the Product-Assurance Elements Diagram (PED)"</p> <p>"Step2) Identify the unusual events leading to accidents or loss."</p> <p>"Step3) Constructing abnormal scenario ESD."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We applied the methodology to two systems: ground system for artificial satellite and engine control system of rocket system."</p> <p>"We assume that the method promotes domain experts identifying unusual events. 78 unusual events were identified for 40 scenarios in the original operational document of the ground system. However, the proposed method identified 95 unusual events for one scenario. The expert mentioned that the method identified novel and valid unusual events which they should consider. Because operational document for ECU had not been developed, we cannot compare the result of the case study with the original.</p> <p>Furthermore, the method had explicated a safety boundary of an effect of the software product. The method provided operational scenario-based safety case including 30 and 56 abnormal scenarios. They represent software product safety more explicitly than process-based approach such as assuring that required activities are conducted."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "As a future work, we should provide more concrete procedure to construct abnormal scenarios from unusual events. Although expert's sufficient experiment knowledge constructed enough number of abnormal scenarios in the case study, it is difficult to consider combinations of the events and recovery operations for them."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) No meaningful connection to AI.</p>

8.251 REFERENCE [785]

Q-Index	5
Q1	To "(...) formally express and verify safety properties on perception units, covering all cases that could ever be

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 353 / 550	

Answer	generated by [a] simulator (...)", as well as to "(...) provide a tool to translate deep learning models into standard logical formulae."
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general, with focus on deep convolutional neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: "Since deep neural networks use simple programming concepts (e.g., no loops), it is quite easy to translate them directly to a standard verification format, such as SMT-LIB. Provided the inputs are sufficiently well-defined, it is then possible to encode safety properties as relationships between inputs and outputs, such as inequality constraints on real values."</p> <p>"The first set is the family of exact verification methods, such as Satisfiability Modulo Theory. SMT solvers perform automated reasoning on logical formulae, following a certain set of rules (a logic) on specific entities (integers, reals, arrays, etc.) described by a theory. An SMT problem consists in deciding whether, for a given formula, there exists an instantiation of the variables that makes the formula true. Programs properties and control flow are encoded as logical formulae, that specialized SMT solvers try to solve. It is possible to express precise properties, but since most SMT solvers try to be exhaustive over the search space, a careful formulation of the constraints and control flow is necessary to keep the problem tractable. It was formally proven (...) that solving a verification problem composed of conjunction of clauses by explicit enumeration for a feedforward network is NP-hard."</p> <p>"The second set of techniques in formal methods is based on overapproximating the program's behaviour. Indeed, since solving the exact verification problem is hard, some authors worked on computing a lower bound of e, using techniques building overapproximations of the program, on which it is easier to verify properties."</p> <p>"The goal of this work is to propose a framework for the general problem of deep learning verification that will allow the formulation of new properties to be checked, while still benefiting from the efforts of the formal methods community towards more efficient verification tools. We aim to leverage the techniques developed for adversarial robustness and extend the scope of deep learning verification to working on global properties. Specifically, we focus on a still unexplored avenue: models trained on simulated data (...)."</p> <p>"(...) the simulated data must yield two characteristics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. they need to be sufficiently realistic (that is to say, they should look like real-world images); if not the network could overfit the simplistic representation provided by the simulator; 2. they must be representative of the various cases the model has to take into account, to cover sufficiently diverse situations. <p>Additional characterization of the simulator [e.g., surjective or injective] would be difficult."</p> <p>"ONNX2SMT provides an interface to all machine learning models that use the Open Neural Network Exchange format and translates them into the standard language SMT-LIB, allowing all state-of-the-art generalist SMT solvers and deep learning verification specialized tools to work on a direct transcription of state-of-the-art neural networks."</p> <p>"Features of ONNX2SMT include the support of the most common operations in modern neural networks, such as tensors addition and multiplication, maxpooling and convolution on 2D inputs."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"As a proof of concept for the proposed framework, it is applied it to a simple synthetic problem. Neural networks are trained with PyTorch, then converted into ONNX using the built-in ONNX converter, and finally converted into the intermediate representation in SMT-LIB format with ONNX2SMT."</p> <p>"Let us consider here the perception module of an autonomous vehicle, whose goal is to output driving directives that result in safe driving behaviour. The perception module is modeled as a deep neural network with one output node, taking as input an image. If an obstacle lies in a pre-defined "danger zone", the network should output a "change direction" directive. Otherwise, it should output a "no change" directive. The "simulator" is here a Python script, taking as input the number and the locations on the image of the one-pixel wide obstacles and generating the corresponding black-and-white images. The verification problem consists in the formulation of the network structure and constraints on the inputs, and in the following properties to check:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. verify that an input with an obstacle (or several ones) in the danger zone will always lead to the "change direction" directive; 2. verify that an input without obstacle on the danger zone will never lead to the "change direction" directive." <p>"The goal was to return UNSAT, meaning no counterexample to the property was found. Under the hypothesis that the space of all possible data is described by the simulator (which is the case here), the model will never</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 354 / 550	

	fail to detect obstacles. (...) the network is proven always correct, which shows interesting generalization abilities. We were thus able to verify quickly that this perceptive module will never miss obstacles, at least for inputs generable by the simulator."
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "Support [of ONNX2SMT] for a wider range of operators (such as reshaping or renormalization operators) is on-going work."</p> <p>Future work: "Among future work, ONNX2SMT will be released and gain support for more deep learning operations. While we provide a toolkit to translate neural networks directly in our framework, a way to easily represent a simulator is yet to include. It is not an easy task, since the simulator must be describable with sufficient granularity to allow the solver to use the simulator internal working to simplify the verification problem. A scene description language with a modelling language for simulators is a possible answer to these issues. Further theoretical characterization of the simulator procedure and its link with the perceptive unit will be undertaken, for instance to encompass stochastic processes. Besides, on more complex simulators, programs and examples, the problem to verify will remain computationally difficult. Various techniques to enhance solvers performances will be developed and integrated in CAMUS, taking advantage of the domain knowledge provided by the simulators parameters. Finally, our current framework checks properties for all possible inputs, including anomalous ones such as adversarial attacks. A possible extension would be to identify "safe" subspaces instead, where perception is guaranteed to be perfect, and "unsafe" subspaces where failures may happen."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Very well-written paper on a safety assurance method based on generating datasets with simulators and formally verifying neural networks.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The paper lacks arguments on how to assure that the underlying simulators are sufficiently safe. The authors claim that two properties shall be satisfied, which is enough to cover the problem but not its solution.</p>

8.252 REFERENCE [786]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To propose a framework for analyzing how robust a machine learning model is to changes in setting or population by using only the available data (i.e., without collecting additional datasets).
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, with focus on 'random forest' (case study).
Q3 Answer	<p>Context: "One approach to stability analysis is through the lens of distributionally robust optimization (DRO). Instead of examining a model's performance only on the (empirical) test distribution associated with a particular validation dataset, DRO defines an uncertainty set of possible test distributions and considers the model's performance on the worst-case distribution chosen from this set. The distributionally robust perspective allows us to identify the types of environments which lead to poor model performance. To establish the stability of a model under the many possible ways in which environments can change, we need to be able to evaluate worst-case performance under a corresponding variety of shifts. This requires a flexible framework for specifying how the data distribution can change that can reflect targeted changes in environment."</p> <p>Basics: "(...) we develop a method for analyzing the stability of models to dataset shift without requiring the collection of new datasets. To evaluate a model under different shifts, users specify a set of immutable variables whose distribution should remain fixed, a set of mutable variables whose distribution is allowed to change, and a population proportion. The method then identifies the subpopulation of the specified proportion with the worst average loss. This subpopulation is chosen based on the values of the mutable and immutable variables, but is constrained so that the distribution of the immutable variables matches that of the full sample. If the model performs well on this subpopulation, this indicates robustness to the specified type of shift. Conversely, if the method identifies a subpopulation with low performance, this subpopulation may be used to guide further model development or as part of a "warning label" for users of the model."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>" First, we prove that the proposed estimation method has properties that allow it to reliably estimate the worst-case expected loss under distributional shift." This has been carried out with mathematical theorems and highlighted some of the model's limitations (see 'shortcomings' on the answer to Question 5).</p> <p>"(...) we validate that the worst-case performance estimated by the method provides meaningful information</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 355 / 550	

	<p>about the performance in an actual new environment."</p> <p>"We demonstrate our approach on machine learning models for diagnosing sepsis, a life-threatening response to infection. (...) Our dataset contains electronic health record data collected over four years at Hospital A in our institution's health network. The dataset consists of 278,947 emergency department patient encounters. The prevalence of the target disease, sepsis, is 2.1%. (...) We evaluate the robustness of the models to changes in test ordering patterns using a held-out sample of 10,000 patients which serves as the evaluation dataset."</p> <p>"(...) we demonstrate that our method can be used to determine settings in which prediction models may be unsafe to use due to poor performance."</p> <p>"We consider two sepsis prediction models: The classical model was trained using classical supervised learning methods, while the robust model was trained using the "surgery estimator". While both models are random forest classifiers and were trained using the same data, the robust model was trained with the goal of being stable to shifts in test ordering patterns."</p> <p>"We begin by validating that the method can correctly estimate the performance of a model under worst-case distribution shift, and that this provides meaningful information about the performance in new, shifted environments. To do so, we compare the estimated worst-case performance under a shift in lab test ordering patterns to the observed performance in a new environment exhibiting such a shift. For this purpose, we used an additional dataset containing the same variables collected from a different hospital. (...) the two hospitals differ substantially in the rate of test orders."</p> <p>"(...) the model's performance worsens as the sample proportion decreases. (...) the accuracy at Hospital B is roughly equal to the estimated worst-case accuracy for this subpopulation size. The intervals also demonstrate the relationship between the sample proportion and the estimator variance. (...) These results show that the risk curves accurately inform us about how performance changes under worst-case shifts."</p> <p>"As the subpopulation size decreases, the robust model increasingly outperforms the classical model on their respective worst-case subpopulations."</p> <p>"There is a clear trend: smaller worst-case subsamples have decreasing correlation between disease status and test orders. From this we can conclude that the classical model will experience performance deterioration when applied to hospitals that widely (as opposed to selectively) test patients. However, relative to the original dataset, even a doubling of the test ordering rate results in only small performance deterioration. Thus, we may conclude that the model is safe to use under a wide range of test ordering patterns, though developers might still seek to improve the model in settings with small or negative test order correlations."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "(...) a large dataset may be needed (...). Additionally, if regularization is used (...), this may smooth over low-probability regions with high loss, resulting in potential underestimation of the worst-case risk (...) unless a similarly large dataset is used."</p> <p>If discrete variables are considered, the proposed approach shall be augmented "(...) by adding small amounts of independent uniform noise (...) at the cost of an arbitrarily small, user-controlled amount of bias."</p> <p>Future Work: "Future work may consider extensions of the proposed evaluation framework to Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) and Wasserstein-based uncertainty sets."</p> <p>"A potential extension of this work is to consider optimal treatment subgroups defined by other types of shifts."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Example of technique to assess whether datasets are applicable to safety-critical systems. The authors aim to identify potential dataset flaws in an automated way by considering different subsets of the entire dataset and assessing whether the response of AI changes with each subset.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) The case study lacks a more in-depth relationship with safety.</p> <p>2) Further issues affecting the uncertainty of datasets are not taken into account.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 356 / 550	

8.253 REFERENCE [787]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "(...) present an approach for semi-automatic deductive verification of intelligent hybrid systems (HSs) with embedded reinforcement learning (RL) components modeled in Simulink together with the RL Toolbox".
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) RL components typically learn in a trial and error approach and are thus inherently unsafe components, which contradicts the safety-critical character of HSs. While there exist methods for safe RL that, e.g., apply domain knowledge to ensure that an RL components acts safely, these methods usually do not consider RL components as parts of a larger system. Furthermore, existing approaches to guarantee safe behavior of RL algorithms require a formal model, e.g., a Markov decision process or a description in formal logic. Such formal models are often not available (...)"</p> <p>"(...) we present an approach for semi-automatic deductive verification of HSs with embedded RL components. We target intelligent HSs that are modeled with Simulink and its RL Toolbox. The key ideas of our approach are threefold: First, we capture the safety-relevant behavior of RL components with hybrid contracts in differential dynamic logic. Thereby, we precisely capture the safe behavior of RL components, while providing "enough" abstraction to not unnecessarily hinder the learning experience of an RL controller. Second, we verify safety properties of the overall system with the RL component replaced by its contract deductively using the interactive theorem prover KeYmaera X. To precisely capture the semantics of intelligent Simulink models, we extend our previously proposed automatic Simulink to dynamic logic transformation to reinforcement learning. Third, we ensure that contracts are complied with at runtime by automatically deriving runtime monitors from our hybrid contracts. The runtime monitors take the current system state as input and decide which of the possible actions of the RL component are safe w.r.t. the hybrid contracts."</p> <p>"To ensure that an RL agent acts safely at runtime, we propose to use runtime monitoring. Our HCs enable us to concisely and precisely define the set of safe actions that may be chosen in a given system state. This enables us to automatically derive runtime monitors that check adherence of each action of the RL agent to the HCs in each system state"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We illustrate our approach with an autonomous intelligent factory robot and verify that there are no collisions with moving obstacles. We evaluate in simulation experiments that our safe RL agent is still able to learn a useful policy, and show that the verification process scales well for an increasing number of obstacles and is flexible towards changes in the model."</p> <p>"Our case study consists of a RL ground robot (RL) and two opponents (A,B), which serve as moving obstacles in an abstract factory setting (...). Our objective is to define a safe HC for the RL robot's agent and to verify that no collision with the opponents occurs."</p> <p>"We assume our map to be unbounded and that the two opponents are the only obstacles."</p> <p>"We have demonstrated the applicability, scalability and flexibility of our approach with a case study, in which we modeled an autonomous intelligent robot and its environment in an abstract factory setting and verified collision freedom. In simulation experiments, we have also shown that the verified intelligent robot with a monitored RL component behaves safely, while the inclusion of an unsafe agent leads to collisions with other traffic participants."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "In future work, we plan to also verify intelligent HSs with zero crossing semantics. Furthermore, we also plan to investigate the cost of enforcing an agent's safe behavior through a contract in terms of performance. Finally, we also plan to investigate templates or contract design patterns. As one example, we believe that the safety distances we have used in this paper can be transferred to other applications, where a discrete controller keeps some variables in certain bounds. In such cases, the contract can be derived from the desired bounds plus the reaction time of the HS, as we did for our autonomous robot. To define templates for such scenarios would greatly ease the manual contract design and increase the reusability of existing specifications."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting method to formally verifying reinforcement learning agents, as opposed to ensuring it is safe by design.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 357 / 550	

	Weaknesses: 1) The proposed model does not deal with faults. 2) No discussion on how each of the method's steps is inserted onto a safety assurance process. 3) The proposed model is presented along with the case study, making it more difficult to identify general-purpose features and application-specific ones (including Simulink dependencies).
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8.254 REFERENCE [788]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To describe a formal model of a “location, heading and speed” waypoint navigation task for an autonomous ground vehicle (...)” using differential dynamic logic (dL) “(...) to establish a formal definition of waypoint feasibility and formally verify its validity in the KeYmaera X interactive theorem prover”.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general (case study); artificial intelligence in general (validity as per the authors).
Q3 Answer	<p>“To provide safety guarantees for this critical task despite using machine learning, we need to be able to assure that the neural network based controller can be trusted to not misbehave—even in unlikely corner cases that might have never been encountered during training and testing. This paper presents the first iteration of our work on assuring a path following controller, where we make a number of simplifying assumptions: (i) we use a point vehicle model with instantaneous steering, (ii) control is instantaneous and can change the vehicle actuation at any time, that is, our model of control is event-based (e.g., we can control a vehicle when it reaches a safety region boundary), (iii) the vehicle is traversing even and flat terrain.”</p> <p>“First, we develop a novel formalization of the “location, heading and speed” waypoint navigation task (...), expressing it in the differential dynamic logic (dL) modeling language inside the KeYmaera X interactive theorem prover. Second, we deduce and express the notions of “safe” states—those vehicle states where reaching the waypoint (subject to an error bound) is feasible—and “safe” control actions—namely, those control actions that would allow the vehicle to correctly navigate towards the waypoint. Third, we create a sequence of formal proofs in KeYmaera X establishing the desired properties—namely, as long as the waypoint is not yet reached, for each safe state there is a safe control action and the use of any safe control actions implies to stay in the safe region until we reach the desired waypoint.”</p> <p>“(...) we use theorem proving not merely as a tool to obtain a correctness proof about an already correct system; we use it to explore and understand a system in all its subtleties and with all its corner cases thoroughly, to structure the system analysis process, to discover properties of the system that are not or only partially known (e.g., loop invariants), to discover and fix correctness bugs in the process, and to link model and system execution formally.”</p> <p>“(...) we do not rely on the neural network controller always being correct—instead, the correct-by-construction safety net for the controller checks whether the neural network output is safe to act upon, and presents a safe alternative if not (again, “safe” in a sense that it can ensure the vehicle will stay safe in the future, not just safe right now). Also note that while our focus is on neural networks, the same safety net could be used with any other controller.” Safety is ensured by means of dL instructions which define a 'safe envelope' that restricts the waypoint of a vehicle to a situation in which it is ensured as safe (e.g., by means of the information collected by its sensors).</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>“While our goal is to train a trustworthy controller that can be assured to always output a safe action (e.g., ether using the Neural Lyapunov based barrier function technique, or using the dReal SMT solver to verify the properties of the neural network), neither is necessary in order to be able to assure safe vehicle behavior. Even if the underlying neural network based controller is not trustworthy, our technique allows for the use of the ModelPlex tool, which is part of the KeYmaera X theorem prover, to create a safe-by-construction safety net for the controller that checks whether the neural network outputs satisfy the property and are therefore formally verified safe to act upon or else presents a safe alternative action.</p> <p>However, our dL formalization in KeYmaera X used a simple vehicle model with instantaneous steering (...). (...) we could use (and indeed successfully tested) the ModelPlex-created safety wrapper in Simulation A, but that safety wrapper is unfortunately not yet applicable to the real vehicle.”</p>
Q5	Shortcomings: The neural network-based model differs significantly from the final application the authors

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 358 / 550	

Answer	<p>wished to assess.</p> <p>The authors deem that their definition of a 'safe region' is overly restrictive, but they cannot prove whether this is true or false.</p> <p>Future work: "(...) we are optimistic that we will be able to tweak it to support a less conservative Safe(state) definition with relatively little effort since KeYmaera X translates interactive proof steps into proof tactics. However what we ultimately hope to be able to do is to state and prove similar safety theorems using more realistic vehicle models, with multiple wheels, friction, actuation delays, and uneven terrain. (...) we plan to explore a machine-learning approach, where some aspects of the problem and some proof details are discovered and approximated by neural networks."</p> <p>"Another opportunity for future extension is to adapt the one-waypoint-at-a-time form of the navigation task to handle a sequence of multiple waypoints at once (...) to be able to improve driving smoothness with a neural network controller that is provided with multiple waypoints."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Usage of differential logic as a means to formally specify and conceive a safe-by-construction AI-based controller.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The research is still on preliminary stage, since the authors were still not able to reach their objectives and had to resort to a 'safety envelope'-based solution.</p> <p>2) Very application-specific solution.</p>

8.255 REFERENCE [789]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To propose "a novel approach to synthesizing neural networks as barrier certificates, which can provide safety guarantees for neural network controlled systems".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"A barrier certificate is a continuously differentiable function of system states that assigns the reachable set or its over-approximation and the unsafe region with reals of opposite signs. It acts as a barrier separating the reachable set or its over-approximation from the unsafe region. The successful construction of a barrier certificate gives sound proof of safety.</p> <p>Compared with reachable set computation, barrier certificate synthesis is of less computational complexity and can ensure the safety property in an infinite time horizon. Classical barrier certificates are polynomials. Instead, this paper focuses on neural networks, introducing them as barrier certificates into safety verification of neural network controlled systems."</p> <p>"(...) the recent network training techniques and significant advances in solving mixed-integer linear program (MILP) and mixed-integer quadratically-constrained program (MIQCP) problems tame the computational complexities in training and identifying barrier certificate."</p> <p>"(...) we propose a novel approach for safety verification of neural network controlled systems, which introduces neural networks as barrier certificates. We first propose the conditions that neural networks should satisfy when acting as barrier certificates to ensure the safety of neural network controlled systems. Then we design a training process, which synthesizes candidate neural networks from three designed training datasets and is driven by a loss function that encodes the barrier certificate conditions. To identify real barrier certificates from candidates, we transform the problem of verifying barrier certificate conditions into a set of mixed-integer programming (MIP) problems and certify the original verification problem based on the optimums returned by the numerical optimization solver. As far as we know, it is the first method that adopts neural networks as barrier certificates for safety verification of neural network controlled systems."</p> <p>"To synthesize neural network barrier certificates, the corresponding construction conditions are derived at first. Since it is too difficult to directly find a neural network satisfying these construction conditions, we introduce an iterative approach that combines neural network training with optimization problem solving to find proper neural networks."</p> <p>"In each iteration, it trains a neural network as the candidate barrier certificate, followed by an identification process certifying real neural network barrier certificate from the candidate. The training datasets are generated from the neural network controlled system. The loss function guiding the training process is designed to minimize the losses arising from the violation of barrier certificate conditions. The training process ends with a</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 359 / 550	

	<p>candidate neural network, and the identification process determines whether the candidate is a real barrier certificate by solving three optimization problems. If the identification succeeds, [it] returns a real barrier certificate, and the neural network controlled system is safe. Otherwise, the counterexamples found in identification are expanded and used in the next iteration. If [it] does not converge to a real barrier certificate when reaching the maximum epoch, it returns failure."</p> <p>"The structure of the neural network is characterized as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Input layer: the number of neurons in the input layer is the same as that of system variables. Each neuron corresponds to a system variable. The values of system variables are those of input layer neurons. - Hidden layers: the neural network can contain an arbitrary number of layers. Each hidden layer can contain an arbitrary number of neurons. The activation function applying on each hidden layer neuron is ReLU - Output layer: the output layer contains one neuron, denoting the neural network barrier certificate output. <p>(...) datasets are designed according to the first three conditions."</p> <p>"The training datasets (...) are shuffled and divided into mini-batches. For each mini-batch, the loss l is calculated (...), and the Adam optimizer updates the parameters of the neural network barrier certificate by minimizing l. When $l = 0$ on all mini-batches, the training process terminates and goes to the barrier certificate identification process (...). If the identification success, a real neural network barrier certificate is synthesized. Otherwise, it returns some counterexamples for the next training epoch."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) demonstrates the application of our method by treating the ACAS Xu system and then compares it with the polynomial barrier certificate-based method on 6 benchmark examples" [Refs. [233] and [695)].</p> <p>"(...) NetBC is more effective. At the same time, NetBC is more scalable in treating large network controllers. The network controllers in Example 5 and 6 go up to 8 layers. (...) The polynomial-based method fails in 3 examples.(...) The shape of polynomials is not rich enough to express barrier certificates of complex systems."</p>
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Interesting method to use ANNs as a means to ensure that ANN-based controllers are safe.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The method might not converge at every scenario, in which case it returns an indication that it was not possible to synthesize an ANN-based barrier certificate.</p> <p>2) It is not clear whether the barrier certificate ANN is fail-safe, or if it needs a barrier certificate on its own. This has not been discussed in detail by the authors.</p>

8.256 REFERENCE [791]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To introduce "a modelling framework that explicitly captures Bayesian Network (BN)-based system specific considerations and facilitates both the communication of assurance concerns between safety practitioners and system stakeholders, and the subsequent safety analysis of the system itself."
Q2 Answer	Knowledge-based systems (Bayesian networks) integrated to machine learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) in order to assure a safety-critical BN-based system, it is essential that the unconventional aspects of these systems are explicitly considered and analysed by safety practitioners. However, there is no existing comprehensive guidance on the design and development of BN-based systems. Moreover, while work has been carried out into developing more standardised BN-based system lifecycles, key aspects of this work are insufficiently structured or systematic for the purposes of assuring a safety-critical system . Furthermore, there are no published comprehensive approaches to analysing error modes for BN-based systems."</p> <p>"(...) stress the need for the development of verification and validation strategies that target the safety implications of an ES's so-called Knowledge Base' (KB)."</p> <p>"The viewpoints are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Viewpoint Key concerns: All data acquisition, processing, and storage concerns, including knowledge

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 360 / 550	

	<p>engineering and expert elicitation activities, and the properties of any resultant data artefacts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model Viewpoint Key concerns: Model structure, parameterisation and resulting model behaviours/properties, a model's lifecycle and all associated modelling assumptions and decisions. • Computational Viewpoint Key concerns: The properties of approximate and exact inference algorithms and optimisation (learning) algorithms, including any adaptive/on-line aspects. • Technology Viewpoint Key concerns: Any modelling frameworks, infrastructure and tooling needs (with particular focus on those required for BN development), domain-specific standards and technological risks. • Operational Viewpoint Key concerns: The evolution and maintenance of a system after deployment, the role of the environment in a system's operation and the associated continued validity of the system. • Implementation Viewpoint Key concerns: All 'conventional' software and hardware engineering concerns, including function allocation and all associated verification and validation practices." <p>"(...) Firstly, the model may be used to facilitate the development of causal models of BN-based systems that can in turn support the safety focused analysis of causal factors of system behaviours. An exploration of these capabilities is beyond the scope of this paper. Secondly, the meta-model provides a means of analysing the role and influence of processes within the development lifecycle of a BN-based system. Ultimately the function of the reference model is to provide an intermediate step towards the structured, systematic analysis of BN-based system safety."</p> <p>"(...) by instantiating the meta-model to represent a specific system, this approach can be used to derive a set of system-specific error modes and their corresponding verification and validation objectives."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>A case study considering an Alarm Intensive Care Unit (ICU) was considered. "Technically, the network is a small-to-medium sized BN model. It is composed of only discrete, table-structured Conditional Probability Distributions (CPDs). In its factorised representation, it is composed of 37 unique random variables and consists of approximately 500 independently specified model parameters."</p> <p>The authors have instantiated their V&V model to the Bayesian Network and were able to identify points of concern for the analysis,, including the objectives that the network shall fulfill.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "An exhaustive set of error modes and verification and validation objectives [for Bayesian Networks] is beyond the scope of this paper."</p> <p>"(...) the constraints of this paper prevent a full enumeration of error modes and objectives."</p> <p>Shortcomings & Future Work: "However, there are a number of outstanding research problems that must be tackled before a compelling assurance process for these systems can be introduced. One problem lies in providing a systematic and informative approach to analysing the safety implications of specific aspects of a BN-based system. For example, an approach is needed to systematically analyse BN-based models from a safety-focused perspective and to provide a means of transparently tracing the results of these analyses and model properties to system-level hazards. Another research problem is the need to provide a complete safety lifecycle tailored to the specific properties of these systems, as well as how to establish the adequacy of certain key activities. Moreover, there are further applications for the reference model outlined here. These areas will be explored in future work."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The research focuses on a theme which is not well explored by other researchers, which is the safety assurance of Bayesian Network-based systems. 2) The researchers pave an interesting way towards defining general-purpose failure modes for Bayesian Networks. 3) The researchers clearly state the limitations of their research. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The research is still in initial state, and the case study provides little discussion on actual results.

8.257 REFERENCE [796]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "(...) take the first steps towards ensuring safety, with high confidence, for smoothly-varying non-stationary decision problems" by extending "(...) a type of safe algorithm, called a Seldonian algorithm, through a

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 361 / 550	

	synthesis of model-free reinforcement learning with time-series analysis."
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"In this work, we formalize the safe policy improvement problem for a more realistic non-stationary setting and provide an algorithm for addressing it. Additionally, a user-controllable knob is provided to set the desired confidence level: the maximum admissible probability that a worse policy will be deployed. The proposed method relies only on estimates of future performance, with associated confidence intervals. It does not require building a model of a non-stationary MDP (NS-MDP), and so it is applicable to a broader class of problems, as modeling an NS-MDP can often be prohibitively difficult."</p> <p>"To ensure safe policy improvement, we adapt the generic template of the Seldonian framework to the non-stationary setting. The overall approach consists of continually (1) taking an existing safe policy; (2) finding a candidate policy that has (reasonably high) potential to be a strict improvement on the safe policy; (3) testing if this candidate policy is still safe and is an improvement with high confidence; (4) updating the policy to be the candidate policy only if it passes the test; and (5) gathering more data with the current safe policy to get data for the next candidate policy search. This procedure consists of four key technical steps: performance estimation, safety test, candidate policy search, and data-splitting."</p> <p>"(...) there could often be conflicts between policies that might have higher estimated future performance but with lower confidence, and policies with lower estimates of future performance but with higher confidence. As the primary objective of our method is to ensure safety, we draw inspiration from prior methods for conservative/safe learning in stationary domains and propose searching for a policy that has the highest lower confidence bound."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we provide an empirical analysis on two domains inspired by safety-critical real-world problems that exhibit non-stationarity."</p> <p>Non-Stationary Recommender System (RecoSys): In this domain, a synthetic recommender system interacts with a user whose interests in different products change over time. Specifically, the reward for recommending each product varies in a seasonal cycle. Such a scenario is ubiquitous in industrial applications, and updates to an existing system should be made responsibly; if it is not ensured that the new system is better than the existing one, then it might result in a loss of revenue.</p> <p>Non-Stationary Diabetes Treatment: This environment is based on an open-source implementation of the FDA approved Type-1 Diabetes Mellitus simulator (T1DMS) for treatment of Type-1 diabetes. Each episode consists of a day (1440 timesteps—one for each minute in a day) in an in-silico patient's life and the blood-glucose level increases when a patient consumes a meal. Too high or too low blood-glucose can lead to fatal conditions like hyperglycemia and hypoglycemia, respectively, and an insulin dosage is therefore required to minimize the risk associated with these conditions. While a doctor's initial dosage prescription is often available, the insulin sensitivity of a patient's internal body organs varies over time, inducing non-stationarity that should be accounted for. The goal of the system is to responsibly update the doctor's initial prescription, ensuring that the treatment is only made better. (...) This presents a more realistic challenge as every policy's performance trend for real-world problems cannot be expected to follow any specific trend exactly—one can only hope to obtain a coarse approximation of the trend."</p> <p>"Thus, at higher safe speeds Baseline becomes safer as it reverts to safe policy more often. This calls into question the popular misconception that the stationarity assumption is not severe when changes are slow, as in practice slower changes might be harder for an algorithm to identify, and thus might jeopardize safety. By comparison, even though bootstrap CIs do not have guaranteed coverage when using a finite number of samples, it still allows SPIN to maintain a failure rate near the 5% target."</p> <p>"Baseline provides better performance gain than SPIN while maintaining the desired failure rate. However, in the non-stationary setting, the performance gain of SPIN is higher for the recommender system. For diabetes treatment, both the methods provide similar performance gain but only SPIN does so while being safe."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "Further, our experimental results call into question the popular misconception that the stationarity assumption is not severe when changes are slow. In fact, it can be quite the opposite: Slow changes can be more deceptive and can make existing algorithms, which do not account for non-stationarity, more susceptible to deploying unsafe policies."</p> <p>Future work: "There are several exciting directions for future research. We used the ordinary importance</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 362 / 550	

	sampling procedure to estimate past performances of a policy. However, it suffers from high variance and leveraging better importance sampling procedures can be directly beneficial to obtain better estimates of past performances. Leveraging time-series models like ARIMA and their associated wild-bootstrap methods can be a fruitful direction for extending our algorithm to more general settings that have correlated noises or where the performance trend, both locally and globally, can be better modeled using auto-regressive functions. Further, goodness-of-fit tests could be used to search for a time-series model that best fits the application."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) In-depth analysis of the challenges to deal with safety along with reinforcement learning-based systems. 2) Good critical analysis of the results. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The model itself is not inherently fail-safe, as it relies on predicting safe and unsafe states at a time instant and assuming these are true, within a confidence interval, to avoid unsafe scenarios. 2) An overly permissive failure rate was deemed tolerable (5%).

8.258 REFERENCE [797]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To "apply transfer learning to improve the efficiency of reinforcement learning based safety validation algorithms when applied to related systems".
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"To improve the efficiency of safety validation across related systems, we use knowledge from the validation of previous systems to inform the validation of the next system. We formulate iterative safety validation as a transfer learning problem by modeling each safety validation task as a Markov decision process. The previously solved tasks are used as the set of source tasks, and we transfer knowledge to future tasks in the form of action value functions. We use state-dependent attention weights to learn which previous solutions are applicable to the current problem."</p> <p>"One challenge in transfer learning is negative transfer where knowledge from one or more source tasks impairs the performance on the current task. Negative transfer can be mitigated using an attention mechanism, or a human oracle that decides which tasks are relevant."</p> <p>"In the context of safety validation, we hypothesize two qualitatively distinct ways that the tasks will be related. The first case is that of a learning system which is improving its performance from task to task. Each task is therefore more challenging for the adversary since failures that were present in previous tasks may no longer exist or may only occur due to a narrower range of disturbances. In this context, the most recent solutions are likely to provide the most relevant information and large parts of those solutions may be directly applicable to the new task. The second case is that of comparable systems where the systems have a similar level of competency but exhibit different behavior. Disturbance trajectories that lead to failure for one system may not cause failure in any other systems, although they might share similar conceptual failure modes. In this setting, direct transfer of solutions may be ineffective, and we need to rely on other types of knowledge."</p> <p>"To avoid negative transfer, A2T simultaneously learns a solution from scratch so there are a total of k+1 solutions [for k tasks] and as many attention weights. A2T can be used to estimate optimal policies or optimal value functions and we found it most straightforward to estimate the optimal action value function."</p> <p>"(...) we propose a modification of A2T where we include a learned transformation of the state and action value function for each of the k previous solutions. (...) In this work, we use linear transformations because they are effective and simple.</p> <p>The A2T algorithm with state and action value transformations can be encoded as (...) [a neural] network. (...) The base network is a Q-network that learns from scratch. The k source solutions are the Q-networks that represent the optimal solutions of the source tasks. The source solutions are preceded by a state transformation and followed by an action value transformation. These transformations have the same output dimension as input dimension and are initialized to the identity transformation (with a small amount of noise for breaking symmetry). The attention network has k+1 output units with a softmax layer for normalization. The Q values of each source solution and the base network are weighted by the corresponding attention weights and summed together to get a final estimate. The network parameters from the base network, attention network, and state</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 363 / 550	

	and action value transformations are trained using DQN. If the source solutions are".
Q4 Answer	<p>"To investigate the effectiveness of transfer learning in the safety validation setting, we apply existing transfer learning algorithms to the problem. These include fine-tuning of past solutions, and the attend, adapt, and transfer (A2T) algorithm. When the systems we wish to validate have dissimilar behavior, however, we find that existing approaches can perform poorly. We propose a modification to A2T that transforms the state and action value spaces for each source task to increase knowledge transfer between dissimilar tasks. We evaluate the initial performance, the final performance, and the number of training steps required to reach the same performance as a no-transfer algorithm. We consider four iterative safety validation tasks in gridworld and autonomous driving scenarios and demonstrate that transfer learning has the potential to significantly improve the performance and sample efficiency of safety validation algorithms."</p> <p>"The safety validation problems with learning systems had the jumpstart decrease with the number of tasks observed, likely due to the increase in difficulty of the tasks. For the safety validation problems involving comparable systems, however, the jumpstart tended to increase with the number of source tasks. We hypothesize that with more source tasks, we are more likely to have a task that closely matches the current tasks, and can therefore immediately have reasonable performance."</p> <p>"The final safety validation performance can be significantly improved by both A2T approaches, but not through fine-tuning. (...) The lack of performance could mean that the Q-network for one task is not learning a set of features that is useful for solving other tasks, so updating only the final layer does not provide enough capacity to solve the problem. The A2T networks, however, are able to achieve significantly improved final performance, which generally increases with the number of source tasks. The A2T network with state and action value transformations outperforms the basic A2T network in both safety validation problems with comparable systems, which are the problems it was designed for. Both of the safety validation problems with a learning system show the maximal gain in final performance in the middle of the sequence of tasks. A lower gain in early tasks may be due to those tasks being easy to solve, while a lower gain in the later tasks may be due to only having a few failure modes to exploit. The middle tasks may be challenging to solve but may have a diversity of failure modes that the previous policies can help identify. More experimentation is needed to fully understand these trends."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: The causes of some results are not yet fully understood.</p> <p>Future work: "Future work will include exploring the failure modes discovered by each algorithm to gain insights into how transfer is occurring. These insights may help us understand under what conditions we can expect performance and efficiency improvements."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Good insight on transfer learning for safety-critical applications.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) Case studies are still simplified and most of the results are at most hypothesized rather than fully justified.</p>

8.259 REFERENCE [798]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To develop algorithms of "safe deep learning algorithms, formal verification of neural networks, and adaptive testing methods" to address "reliability concerns" on "machine learning components in safety-critical systems".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, deep learning in general, neural networks (all cited by the author).
Q3 Answer	This reference is a research plan; hence, all its contents are planned for future work.
Q4 Answer	This reference is a research plan; hence, all its contents are planned for future work.
Q5 Answer	"I have developed a method called OVERT to analyze such nonlinear, discrete time, closed loop systems with neural network control policies. OVERT approximates the original nonlinear dynamical system in such a way that if no counter examples can be found for the approximate system, one can soundly claim there are no counter examples for the original system. OVERT produces tighter approximations than adapted continuous time tools and OVERT is much more computationally efficient than verification tools that are not specialized to handle neural networks.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 364 / 550	

	<p>This work on OVERT will be extended in two directions over the next year. The first extension is to prove unbounded properties of discrete time systems, such as stability in the control theory sense. My approach for this extension is to pursue Lyapunov stability (...). The second extension of OVERT is to approximate not only the dynamical system, but also the neural network controller. The central idea is to approximate the neural network controller with a smaller network that is faster to verify. Once a smaller network has been trained or pruned, neural network verification tools can be used to confirm that the smaller, approximate network can be used to make sound claims about the original network."</p> <p>"My current work is exploring whether useful notions of "testing coverage" can be obtained when doing adaptive stress testing. It would be useful to know where in the state space of the original system we've tested "enough". My first line of exploration uses deep, Bayesian, value-based reinforcement learning to train the adversarial agent"</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Interesting ideas for formal V&V and adversarial attacks. 2) Some progress might have been reported on [905]. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Research still on a very initial phase.

8.260 REFERENCE [799]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To address "(...) the problem of verifying safety when running a Bayesian neural network policy in a feedback loop with infinite time horizon systems".
Q2 Answer	Bayesian neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Bayesian neural networks (BNNs) are a family of neural networks that place distributions over their weights. This allows learning uncertainty in the data and the network's prediction, while preserving the strong modelling capabilities of DNNs."</p> <p>"In this work, we study the safety verification problem for BNN policies in safety-critical systems over the infinite time horizon. Formally, we consider discrete-time closed-loop systems defined by a dynamical system and a BNN policy. Given a set of initial states and a set of unsafe (or bad) states, the goal of the safety verification problem is to verify that no system execution starting in an initial state can reach an unsafe state. Unlike existing literature which considers probability of safety, we verify sure safety, i.e. safety of every system execution of the system. In particular, we present a method for computing safe weight sets for which every system execution is safe as long as the BNN samples its weights from this set.</p> <p>Our approach to restrict the support of the weight distribution is necessary as BNNs with Gaussian weight priors typically produce output posteriors with unbounded support. Consequently, there is a low but non-zero probability for the output variable to lie in an unsafe region (...). This implies that BNNs are usually unsafe by default. We therefore consider the more general problem of computing safe weight sets. Verifying that a weight set is safe allows re-calibrating the BNN policy by rejecting unsafe weight samples in order to guarantee safety. (...) To verify safety of a weight set, we search for a safety certificate in the form of a safe positive invariant (also known as safe inductive invariant). A safe positive invariant is a set of system states that contains all initial states, is closed under the system dynamics and does not contain any unsafe state. The key advantage of using safe positive invariants is that their existence implies the infinite time horizon safety. We parametrize safe positive invariant candidates by (deterministic) neural networks that classify system states for determining set inclusion. Moreover, we phrase the search for an invariant as a learning problem. A separated verifier module then checks if a candidate is indeed a safe positive invariant by checking the required properties via constraint solving. In case the verifier finds a counterexample demonstrating that the candidate violates the safe positive invariant condition, we re-train the candidate on the found counterexample. We repeat this procedure until the verifier concludes that the candidate is a safe positive invariant ensuring that the system is safe. The safe weight set obtained by our method can be used for safe exploration reinforcement learning."</p> <p>"We now define the two safety problems that we consider in this work. The first problem considers feed-forward BNNs, and the second problem considers closed-loop systems with BNN policies. While our solution to the first problem will be a subprocedure in our solution to the second problem, the reason why we state it as a separate problem is that we believe that our solution to the first problem is also of independent interest for the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 365 / 550	

	safety analysis of feed-forward BNNs."
Q4 Answer	<p>"We perform an experimental evaluation of our proposed method for learning positive invariant neural networks that prove infinite time horizon safety. Our evaluation consists of an ablation study where we disable different core components of Algorithm 1 [proposed solution] and measure their effects on the obtained safety bounds and the algorithm's runtime."</p> <p>"Our first benchmark represents an unstable linear dynamical system (...). Our second benchmark is the inverted pendulum task, which is a classical non-linear control problem. (...) While the previous two benchmarks concern stability specifications, we evaluate our method on a non-Lyapunovian safety specification in our third benchmark. In particular, our third benchmark is a collision avoidance task, where the system does not stabilize to the same set of terminal states in every execution."</p> <p>"Our results demonstrate that re-training with the counterexamples is the key component that determines our algorithm's success. In all cases, except for the linear dynamical system, the initial guess of the invariant candidate violates the invariant condition. Moreover, bootstrapping Dspec with random points labeled by empirical estimates of reaching the unsafe states improves the search process significantly."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "In this work, we consider ReLU activation functions, although other piecewise linear activation such as the leaky-ReLU and PReLU are applicable as well". Moreover, only Gaussian probability distributions were considered.</p> <p>Future work: "While adopting products of intervals around the BNN's weight means is a natural choice given that BNN priors are typically unimodal distributions, this is still a somewhat restrictive shape for safe weight sets. Thus, an interesting direction of future work would be to study more general forms of safe weight sets that could be used for re-calibration of BNN posteriors and their safety verification. Another interesting problem would be to design an approach for refuting a weight set as unsafe which would complement our method, or to consider closed-loop systems with stochastic environment dynamics.</p> <p>Any verification method for neural networks, even more so for neural networks in feedback loops, suffers from scalability limitations due to the underlying complexity class. Promising research directions on improving the scalability of our approach by potentially speeding up the constraint solving step are gradient based optimization techniques and to incorporate the constraint solving step already in the training procedure."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good contextualization of safety assurance for neural network-based systems, notably Bayesian Neural Networks, including a sound safety assurance method.</p>

8.261 REFERENCE [802]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "present HUDD (Heatmap-based Unsupervised Debugging of DNNs), a tool that supports safety analysis practices for systems enabled by Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) by automatically identifying the root causes for DNN errors and retraining the DNN."
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, unsupervised learning (heatmap-based clustering).
Q3 Answer	"HUDD, the toolset that automates our methodology for the identification of root causes for DNN errors and DNN retraining. HUDD relies on hierarchical agglomerative clustering to identify the distinct root causes of DNN errors. It configures clustering with a specific distance function based on the heatmaps computed for internal DNN layers. A subset of the images belonging to each cluster is inspected by the engineer who is thus helped in determining unsafe conditions (i.e., commonalities among the images in a same cluster), including the infrequent ones (i.e., clusters with few members). Further, HUDD relies on the computed clusters to identify new images to be used to retrain the DNN. Given a potentially large set of unlabeled images, HUDD selects the subset of images that are more likely to belong to the identified clusters. These images are assumed to include potentially unsafe conditions and are then used to retrain the DNN."
Q4 Answer	"For our empirical evaluation, we considered six DNNs. A gaze detection system (GD) that determines the gaze direction of a human face. A drowsiness detection system (OC) that features the same architecture as the gaze detection system, except that the DNN predicts whether eyes are closed. A head poses detection system (HPD) that classifies the position of a person's head in an image according to nine classes: straight, bottom-left, left, top-left, bottom-right, right, top-right, reclined, looking up. A facial landmarks detection system (FLD) that identifies the location of the pixels corresponding to 27 face landmarks delimiting seven face elements. An

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 366 / 550

	<p>object detection system (OD) that tries to detect the existence of eyeglasses. A traffic signs recognition system (TSR) that recognizes the presence of traffic signs in road images."</p> <p>"(...) we relied on images generated using simulators. Since simulator images can be associated with the simulator parameter values used to generate them (e.g., the vertical angle of a person's head), we could objectively determine if the images in the same cluster present common characteristics."</p> <p>"Our results show that a very high percentage of the clusters (i.e., between 57% and 100%) include at least one parameter with 50% reduction in variance, which means that, for most of the clusters, engineers can identify commonalities among images. Also, all the parameters with high reduction in variance are associated with image characteristics that are plausible causes of errors."</p> <p>"(...) the analysis supported by HUDD saves a great deal of effort with respect to current practice (i.e., manual inspection of all the error-inducing images)."</p> <p>"Experiments were repeated ten times. HUDD leads to significantly larger accuracy improvements than baselines, increasing DNN accuracy up to 30.24%."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: 1) HUDD is only valid for systems whose inputs are images.</p> <p>Future work: "A user study concerning the time savings introduced by HUDD is part of our future work."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness: 1) Scope restricted to specific types of inputs (images) and AI models (neural networks). 2) Experiments have been carried out based on simulators which provide further information that can improve the performance of the tool, hence not reflecting a real operational scenario.</p>

8.262 REFERENCE [805]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "present a methodology to characterize the exact probabilities associated with invariance and recovery in safe control" for systems with stochastic uncertainties.
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	"(...) we developed the safety analysis methods when barrier-function-based safety control methods are used in a stochastic system. Specifically, we derived the exact distributions for the minimum and maximum barrier function values in a time interval and the first entry and exit times to and from the super level sets of the barrier function. When the state initiates from the safe region, these distributions can be used to infer the probability of failure in any finite time horizon, the distribution of the safety margin in normal operation, and the probability of the time to exit from the safe region. When the state is outside of the safe region, these distributions can be used to infer the probability of recovery in any finite time horizon, the distribution of the distance from the safe region in the recovery process, and the distribution of the recovery time to re-enter the safe region. These distributions are given as the solutions to the deterministic convection-diffusion equations (...)."
Q4 Answer	The authors have provided mathematical proof for all their claims and presented a brief case study to compare their closed-form solution to a Monte Carlo-based approach. "The Monte Carlo method produces noisy results with large variance. In particular, at a high spatial frequency, the size of such noise can be larger than the impacts of infinitesimal changes in the initial state's probability. This makes it difficult to estimate the gradient of the probability. In contrast, our method solves a differential equation, which is guaranteed to yield smooth solutions, and can yield a more accurate gradient estimate. This suggests the potential of combining the two approaches for further accuracy improvement as a future work."
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength: 1) Formal analysis of safety assurance for systems with uncertainty.</p> <p>Weakness:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 367 / 550	

	1) Despite the theme being relevant to AI-based systems because AI deals with inherent and data-originated uncertainties, the subject was dealt with no relation to AI.
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8.263 REFERENCE [806]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "provide a methodical definition process of a hypothetical AV domain controller architecture (...) to ensure that the safety goals and requirements are completely and correctly stated at the start of the development process and then propagated accurately to the final design and implementation without omission."
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	The authors have developed a reference model for the architecture of automated vehicles and assessed, for three different degrees of automation, the elicitation of safety requirements and lower level architectural constraints needed to fulfill the safety targets. The overall system comprises the following elements: "Sensing systems: Cameras, Radars, LIDARs, SAS, etc. Data processing and control: – Perception processing: Visual perception processing, Sensor fusion, Object detection/tracking, Localization, Communications & interfaces unit (hierarchical, subsystem, HMI), etc. – Planning: Path and maneuver planning, Trajectory planning - Control: Lateral/Longitudinal control Actuator systems – Chassis (Steering/ABS/TCS/Suspension) – Powertrain (engine/throttle/Transmission) – Safety (Airbag, collision warning, Autonomous Emergency Braking, driver assessment/warning) etc.
Q4 Answer	The authors have analyzed the obtained safety requirements and how feasible meeting them would be, as well as limitations on obtaining safety requirements that would ensure the completeness of their originating high level goals. Specifically for AI, the authors have defined a simplex-like architecture in which the AI itself is not responsible for safety; instead, it is monitored by a non-AI element.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Weak link to the safety assurance of AI-based systems. The authors considered a simplex-like architecture as the only feasible solution to the posed problems.

8.264 REFERENCE [807]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To "propose a methodology, based on rewriting logic specifications written in CafeOBJ, for reasoning about structural errors of systems whose behavior is expressed in terms of reactive rules and verifying safety properties within the same framework".
Q2 Answer	Knowledge-based systems (reactive rule-based expert systems)
Q3 Answer	The study is not related to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.
Q4 Answer	The study is not related to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.
Q5 Answer	The study is not related to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.
Q6 Answer	The study is not related to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 368 / 550	

8.265 REFERENCE [813]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To "investigate an importance sampling scheme that integrates the dominating point machinery in large deviations and sequential mixed integer programming to locate the underlying dominating points (...) for a range of neural network architectures including fully connected layers, rectified linear units, normalization, pooling and convolutional layers, and random forests built from standard decision trees."
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, decision trees, random forests.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "This problem is motivated from fast emerging studies on the safety evaluation of intelligent systems, robustness quantification of learning models, and other potential applications to large-scale simulation in which machine learning tools can be used to approximate complex rare-event set boundaries." "Recent research considers using probabilistic measures to quantify the risks of machine learning predictors or entire intelligent physical systems. (...) Due to the complexity of machine learning predictors, these probabilities are typically unamenable to analytical formulas, even when the underlying stochastic distribution is fully modeled. (...) The problem thus falls into the domain of rare-event simulation, in which it is widely known that crude Monte Carlo can be extremely inefficient and variance reduction is necessarily employed."</p> <p>Basics: "Our goal is to provide a first step into building rare-event simulation algorithms in these applications, which integrate tools from both the disciplines of machine learning and rare-event simulation, and which are statistically guaranteed in terms of the classical efficiency notions in the rare-event literature. More specifically, we study importance sampling (IS) to design efficient estimators. In rare-event estimation, the rarity nature of hitting set dictates that crudeMonte Carlo samples have a low frequency of observing the hitting occurrence, and this inefficiency exhibits statistically as a large relative error (i.e., ratio of standard deviation to mean) in the estimation. To mitigate this issue, IS uses an alternate distribution to generate samples that can attain a higher frequency in hitting the target event and reweights the outputs to maintain unbiasedness via the likelihood ratios. To achieve a small relative error, the new generating distribution (i.e., the IS distribution) is carefully selected, often by analyzing the weights in interaction with the hitting set geometry and the underlying system dynamics."</p> <p>"(...) we focus on piecewise linear machine learning predictors, which include random forests and neural networks with common activation functions such as rectified linear units (ReLU). (...) We also assume the underlying distribution is Gaussian or mixtures of such. Under this setting, we design provably efficient IS schemes to estimate rare-event probabilities that the prediction outputs hit above certain high thresholds." "Intuitively, a dominating point is the highest-density point in the rare-event set, so using an IS distribution that shifts the mean to this point (via exponential tilting) gives rise to a distribution that hits the rare-event set more frequently, and the generated likelihood ratio contributes properly to the probability of interest, which are desirable for controlling the relative error. However, this is only a local characterization, as the simulation randomness could cause huge likelihood ratios for some generated samples. Controlling these ratios in turn requires a geometric property that, in the Gaussian case, implies the dominating point to be on the boundary of the rare-event set, and that the latter lies completely inside one of the half-spaces cut by the tangential hyperplane passing through the dominating point (e.g., these occur when the rare-event set is convex). When this geometric property does not hold, then one needs to divide the rare-event set into a union of smaller sets each bearing its own dominating point, and an efficient IS scheme is built via a mixture of exponential tiltings targeted at all these individual dominating points. The sequential MIP in our procedure serves to locate all these dominating points. It casts the search as a density maximization problem constrained by hitting sets induced from the considered machine learning model. The involved feasible regions shrink sequentially as we add more "cutting planes" to the constraints to remove the half-spaces that are already considered by earlier dominating points. Our MIPs are derived from the reformulation techniques that appeared recently in the machine learning literature, which leverage the geometric structures of ReLU neural networks and random forests."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"In terms of theoretical results, we show asymptotic optimality of our IS that targets at general piecewise polyhedrons, which apply to our considered rare-event sets in particular. Towards this, we also derive large deviations results for the associated probabilities of interest."</p> <p>The authors also present three case studies. Two of them are simple, 'toy' problems with one or multiple dominating points (i.e., unsafe states). The third is a "realistic problem generated from a classification dataset with a high-dimensional feature space".</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 369 / 550	

	<p>Case Study 1 - Single Dominating Point: Neural networks and random forests (regression trees) were able to predict the approximate position of the dominating point and, hence, the unsafe scenarios.</p> <p>Case Study 2 - Two Dominating Points: Same conclusion of 'Case Study 1'.</p> <p>Case Study 3: "The classification problem uses theMAGIC Gamma Telescope dataset in the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The problem is to classify images of electromagnetic showers collected by a ground-based atmospheric Cherenkov gamma telescope. The features of the data are 10-dimensional characteristic parameters of the images, and the dataset contains 19,020 data points in total." "We obtain 53 dominating points for the rare-event sets associated with the random forest predictor and 217 dominating points in the neural network case. (...) We observe that the estimates are very accurate in all experiments (with different rarities), which are indicated by the tight 95% confidence intervals. These results show that our proposed IS scheme performs well with large numbers of dominating points and in relatively high-dimensional problems."</p>
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings and future work: "Much warranted further studies include the generalization of our approach to more sophisticated rare-event sets with intricate interaction behaviors, the handling of high-dimensional problems, and the investigation on the impacts of model errors in affecting rare-event probability estimation."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Very well written paper on simulation-based safety analysis of neural networks and random forests. Sound mathematical evidence is presented to support the proposed approach.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) It has not been justified why assuming Gaussian distributions for probabilistic risk assessment is feasible and applicable for the scenarios in question.</p> <p>2) The case studies were carried out with a confidence interval of 95%, which might be overly permissive for safety-critical applications.</p>

8.266 REFERENCE [814]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "propose a framework for compositional learning and verification of neural network controllers".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, with focus on deep neural networks; reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Introduction:</p> <p>"(...) there has been a great deal of interest in safe reinforcement learning and verifying that the learned NN controller satisfies a given safety property. We focus on closed-loop safety, where the goal is to ensure that the controller, composed with a model of the robot dynamics and its environment, is safe over the entire planning horizon (...). We consider the setting where the NN controller is learned in simulation, and the goal is to verify the learned controller."</p> <p>"One approach is to unroll the safety property over a finite horizon. However, this approach becomes intractable as the planning horizon becomes large. In particular, existing verification algorithms rely on overapproximating the dynamics, and the approximation error accumulates over the horizon. Thus, very precise abstractions are required to verify safety for long horizons. An alternative approach is to establish the existence of an inductive invariant such as a Lyapunov function or a control barrier function. This strategy reduces the problem to a verification problem over a single step, since it suffices to prove that a candidate invariant is inductive and that it implies safety. However, establishing such an invariant can be intractable for high-dimensional state spaces, especially when using neural network controllers with many parameters."</p> <p>Basics: "(...) we propose a framework for compositional learning and verification of NN controllers. (...) The idea is to verify a program by decomposing it into modular components, devising verification conditions (VCs) for all components that suffice to prove safety, and then proving that each VC holds for its respective component.</p> <p>In particular, our framework leverages this strategy to both learn an NN controller to solve a given control task and verify the learned controller. First, we decompose the task into a sequence of sub-tasks, where each sub-task is associated with a precondition (e.g., the region of the state space where the robot starts) and a postcondition (e.g., the region where the robot ends up). This decomposition is designed to satisfy two</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 370 / 550	

	<p>properties:</p> <p>Mode safety and progress: For any single sub-task, using the NN controller from any state satisfying the precondition should safely transition the system to a state satisfying the postcondition within some bounded number of steps.</p> <p>Switching safety: The postcondition of one sub-task should imply the precondition of the next.</p> <p>As long as these two properties are satisfied, the NN controller is guaranteed to be safe for the entire planning horizon. Furthermore, these two properties are sufficient to guarantee a particular liveness property which states that any finite sequence of sub-tasks will be completed eventually. Intuitively, our strategy combines verification over a finite horizon (i.e., mode safety) with establishing inductive invariants (i.e., switching safety), except that the inductive invariants are established at the level of sub-tasks rather than individual steps in the system. Formally, we model the system as a hybrid automaton (...).</p> <p>(...) The second step builds on recent work on invariant synthesis. In particular, our synthesis algorithm uses testing to identify implication examples that connect the different (pre/postcondition) sets, and then tries to synthesize candidate pre/postconditions consistent with these examples.</p> <p>One challenge is that in partially observed environments, the controller may not know when one sub-task has been completed and/or what the next sub-task is. To address this issue, we additionally train a mode predictor, which is a separate NN that predicts whether the postcondition for the current sub-task holds in the current state and if so, predicts the next sub-task. This mode predictor is incorporated into the overall controller. To ensure correctness, the safety and progress conditions are verified with respect to the full compositional controller (including the mode predictor)."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We evaluate our approach on a challenging benchmark—namely, a simulation model of the F1/10 autonomous racing system, where the goal is for an NN-controlled car to complete a track without crashing into the walls. (...) First, the controller must rely on high-dimensional LiDAR observations of the environment, which poses challenges for scalability. Second, we ideally want to ensure safety for a wide variety of complex track geometries. As a consequence, this system is beyond the reach of existing state-of-the-art verification techniques.</p> <p>We demonstrate that our framework can successfully learn and verify an NN controller for this system, by decomposing tracks into sequences of individual segments. In particular, we consider sub-tasks that include going straight or executing four different kinds of turns, and verify safety for any sequence of such sub-tasks. We also provide evidence that training a monolithic controller for an example track is significantly harder than our compositional learning approach."</p> <p>"We use the Verisig tool for verification. Verisig verifies neural networks with smooth activation functions (e.g., sigmoid, tanh) by transforming the networks into hybrid systems. The neural network hybrid system is then composed with the dynamics model, thereby converting the closed-loop problem into a hybrid system verification problem that is solved by Flow*." --> [782] is a reference for Verisig.</p> <p>"For both state-feedback and LiDAR systems, we trained two controllers: one for the 90-degree right turn and one for the 120-degree right turn. Since left and right turns are symmetric, we use the right-turn controller for a left turn by reflecting the observations and negating the control input. We also use the 90-degree controller in straight segments, since it is able to steer the car close to the middle."</p> <p>"To illustrate the benefit of compositional learning, we trained a single NN controller for the full track (...). (...) none safely completed a lap in the entire track. (...) As expected, training is fast and stable for our compositional controller, whereas the monolithic ones are unable to converge to a stable policy."</p> <p>"(...) our results provide evidence that the compositional approach is simpler and requires less expert domain knowledge, both in reinforcement learning and in the specific system."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "(...) since our approach is agnostic to the methodology used to train the controllers, it would be interesting to investigate whether using [hierarchical reinforcement learning] methods leads to easier verifiability or an alternative compositional argument."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) The authors assume that the trained controllers can have specific types of systematic faults that shall be contained during the verification.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Necessary to have an application-specific model to derive predictors for the initial training and verification</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 371 / 550	

	of the ML-based model. Nevertheless, less of such knowledge is needed, since smaller and simpler models are easier to build from scratch than complex, all-in-one purpose ones.
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8.267 REFERENCE [819]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To "propose that just as methods to prevent loss of control move certain software adaptation processes to runtime, so should some of the assurance and verification processes move to runtime also".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	"(...) adaptive software that attempts to maintain safe control in unexpected circumstances is an innovation outside the expectations of standards and guidelines such as DO-178B, so we must either force an unnatural fit to the standard, or look elsewhere for guidance." "One of the first steps in dealing with the unexpected is to recognize when the system is outside its expected envelope. Runtime monitoring against the assumptions and claims of a safety case is one way to do this. Furthermore, generation of the monitors can sometimes be automated (...)." "There is a particular topic in formal methods known as Runtime Verification, whose technology provides methods for automated synthesis of monitors for formally specified properties. Given properties specified in a language such as Eagle or RuleR, the methods of runtime verification can automatically generate an efficient (and provably correct) monitor that will raise an alarm as soon as the property is violated. To make effective use of this capability, we need a suitable source of properties to monitor." "An alternative to monitoring assumptions and properties that are explicit in the requirements or in the safety case is to monitor for properties learned by 'experience': that is, we check that the system is behaving 'as usual'. (...) Most modern methods for anomaly detection work by constructing a model of the normal behavior of the software, in terms, for example, of the invariants that it maintains, or the execution paths that it follows."
Q4 Answer	The main results of the paper are related to describing means to certify for unexpected events and future work still needed to achieve this goal. As a result, the answers to 'Question 3' and 'Question 5' are the results of the research.
Q5 Answer	"Runtime monitoring of safety properties related to a safety case can provide potent evidence to support the case. Such runtime evidence is most useful in adaptive systems that attempt to maintain safe control in unanticipated circumstances that are beyond those considered in the standard design and pre-deployment assurance of the system. Assurance delivered by runtime monitoring can therefore contribute to certification of systems that follow a 'never give up' strategy, in the spirit of autonomic and resilient systems." "(...) fault diagnosis is the problem of identifying the source and nature of the fault. Early approaches to fault diagnosis in physical systems used rule-based 'expert systems' but these proved fragile and modern methods are based on model-based reasoning 'from first principles'. " "Controller synthesis can be formulated as a game between the controller and its environment: the controller seeks a strategy to maintain or achieve a given property no matter how the environment behaves. Simple instances, such as when the system is deterministic with respect to the inputs and the task is to find a sequence of inputs that places the system in some specific state, can be reduced to AI planning. In more complicated cases, the controller must really be a strategy that reacts to the environment rather than a simple sequence or a schedule. In this situation, the controller synthesis problem can be solved using techniques related to those used in formal methods."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) By the time the paper was published, relevant open topics that grounded the development of safety-critical AI were discussed. By that time, AI was far from the focus of the research, though. Weakness: 1) Outdated research with some relevant topics already covered by multiple recent research.

8.268 REFERENCE [820]

Q-Index	4
Q1	To "propose the use of quantifier elimination (QE) — a formal method technique, as a complimentary

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 372 / 550	

Answer	technique to the state-of-the-art static analysis and verification procedures" of deep neural networks.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, with focus on deep neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we propose a quantifier elimination (QE) based static analysis of DNNs with ReLU activation, as a complimentary technique to the state-of-the-art DNN verification procedures. (...) Envisioning a DNN as a system composed of layers of connected functional nodes, our idea is to formulate the problem of precise range computation of DNN as a QE problem and leverage QE solvers such as Redlog to derive the range. In addition to property verification, the QE-based analysis allows derivation of precise regions in the input space of a DNN for a desired output robustness measure. We adopt the forward range propagation approach, that has also been used for layer-by-layer reachability analysis in ReluVal, to detect linear behavioral neurons in each layer for simplification of onward computation. The advantage of using QE (over approaches such as ReluVal) is that QE can compute the precise range at the existence of piece-wise linear behavioral neurons, i.e., non-convex scenarios."</p> <p>"QE is the procedure of deriving an equivalent quantifier-free formula from a quantified formula, as the former can be seen as the residue of the later after the elimination of the quantifiers as well as the quantified variables. In other words, QE can be viewed as a dimensionality reduction method of quantified dimensions."</p> <p>"(...) we have shown that the problem of SMT is essentially an instance of QE. (...) QE, as a more generalized mathematical tool, provides a broad range of functionalities over SMT. For example, while a SMT query returns a satisfying solution to a set of constraints, QE query can apply existential quantifier on a set of arbitrarily selected variables and return a logical formula regarding only the un-quantified variables revealing the strongest relationship among them."</p> <p>"(...) a majority of the hidden neurons either behave purely linearly or even have a constant zero output. The above forward propagation approach identifies such neurons and simplifies the network behavioral structure as much as possible. (...) The on-the-fly pruning (identifying and then simplifying) of the linear part of the network behavioral structure results in a much computationally affordable residual of the network. Note that, the precise range computation of each neuron in layer l requires the encoding of all its upstream sub-graph of the behavioral structure rather than just the ranges of neurons in layer l - 1. Failure to do so will lose tracking the correlation among the neurons, thus introducing large overapproximation errors (...)."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"As a proof-of-concept, we developed a prototype implementation and evaluated our approach using pre-trained DNNs of next-generation Airborne Collision Avoidance System for unmanned aircraft (ACAS Xu networks) as a case example. To cope with scalability issues we encountered when running the experiments, we used several heuristics and fine-tuning techniques (...)."</p> <p>"We have developed a proof-of-concept prototype implementation of our QE-based forward range propagation and verification framework, with on-the-fly network pruning using propagated neuron ranges."</p> <p>"(...) a forward range propagation (...) is necessary to obtain the much simpler network behavioral structure. Otherwise QE solving using the encoding of the entire network is too computational costly to be tractable. Nevertheless, the forward range propagation can be relaxed to allow over-approximation in some cases."</p> <p>"The preliminary tests results are promising and show the potential of state-of-the-art performance with further refined implementation of overapproximation and input partition techniques. A unique feature of our approach is that it is able to forward propagate the neurons ranges precisely at the existence of a few branching neurons, allowing a more fine-grained quantitative adversarial analysis. A second unique feature is its ability to derive the precise input perturbation from a desired output deviation, assisting the DNN developer to isolate and avoid adversarial ranges with a given precision."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The proposed approach is applicable to piecewise unit activation functions (ReLU); 2) Additional adjustments were needed, including manual heuristics, to make the method feasible for real applications from the standpoint of the needed runtime resources. <p>Future Work: "We plan to focus on 1) refining our overapproximation and input partition algorithms, 2) customizing QE algorithms/solvers to achieve better performance on the classes of QE problems formulated in our approach, and 3) conducting thorough tests to get a comprehensive evaluation and comparison with state-of-the-art tools such as Reluplex and ReluVal. We envision, in the long term, QE-based range propagation can</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 373 / 550

	be integrated with other formal verification procedures, to achieve more flexibility and efficiency on a broader range of DNN formal analysis."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Another example of technique to formally verify a neural network-based controller (under the assumption that all its neurons have a ReLU activation function) with good mathematical basis and trying to counterbalance precision and processing time (using overapproximation only when necessary).</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The case study provides little information on the assessed neural network and on which changes were effectively made to make it feasible to apply the proposed model.</p> <p>2) No mention to AI faults were presented.</p>

8.269 REFERENCE [823]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To "present NeVer, our tool for checking safety of ANNs. NeVer encodes the problem of verifying safety of ANNs into the problem of satisfying corresponding Boolean combinations of linear arithmetic constraints."
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general.
Q3 Answer	"The core of NeVer is composed by an abstraction-refinement mechanism to verify MLPs (...). The intuition behind this mechanism is that the abstract MLP provides a sound overapproximation of the concrete one, i.e. if NeVer states that the abstract MLP is safe, the same holds true for the concrete MLP. If this is not the case, the counterexample found is tested using the concrete MLP. If the solution is spurious, NeVer computes a refinement of the current abstraction. A further peculiarity of the approach is that NeVer uses counterexamples to try to "repair" the behaviour of the concrete MLP, i.e., to eliminate the causes of its misbehavior. This can be viewed as a way to synthesize a correct program given its specification" NeVer is based on C++ and utilizes HySAT, which uses Satisfiability Theory.
Q4 Answer	<p>Three case studies are considered: Polynomial extrapolation, PUMA manipulator, and concrete compressive strength.</p> <p>Polynomial extrapolation: Conceptual example to assess how NeVer scalates.</p> <p>PUMA manipulator: "This case study is about learning the forward kinematics of a PUMA 500 manipulator. The PUMA 500 is a 6 degrees-of-freedom industrial manipulator with revolute joints (...)."</p> <p>"NeVer is able to guarantee that the MLP is safe in the range [-0.575; 0.575]. If we try to shrink this bound, then NeVer is always able to find a set of inputs that makes the MLP exceed the bound. Notice that the highest total amount of CPU time corresponds to the intervals [-0.550; 0.550] and [-0.575; 0.575], which are the largest unsafe one and the tightest safe one, respectively."</p> <p>"As we mentioned before, however, the real problem with repair is that the true response of the system is not accessible. In the following, we show that even in such cases the original MLP can be repaired, at least to some extent, by leveraging spurious counterexamples and the response of the concrete MLP under test."</p> <p>"Using the repairing facility in NeVer we have been able to shrink the safe interval of about 0.125 m with respect to the result obtained without repairing."</p> <p>Concrete compressive strength: "(...) it is about the prediction of concrete compressive strength (CCS) given the proportion of various elements in the actual concrete mix. CCS is the staying power of concrete against pushing forces, and it is an important parameter in construction engineering because when maximum CCS is exceeded, concrete construction elements may get crushed."</p> <p>"(...) we can see that NeVer is able to establish unsafety of the intervals [30, 70] and [25, 75], whereas it exceeds the CPU time bound for all the remaining intervals that we tried."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Excessive processing time, mostly credited to HySAT.</p> <p>Future work: "Our future work will focus on improving the automated repairing technique for MLPs and on extending NeVer to work with other ML algorithms."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Early yet successful attempt in formally verifying neural networks.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 374 / 550	

Weaknesses: 1) Some case studies could not be further assessed due to processing time restrictions. 2) No analyses of AI faults.
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8.270 REFERENCE [829]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present and discuss the "“gaps” that arise across the development process [of safety-critical autonomous systems]: the semantic gap, where normal conditions for a complete specification of intended functionality are not present; the responsibility gap, where normal conditions for holding human actors morally responsible for harm are not present; and the liability gap, where normal conditions for securing compensation to victims of harm are not present."
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"The semantic gap arises because the normal conditions are not met for manufacturers, particularly designers, to provide a complete specification of the system. The semantic gap represents the difference between the implicit intentions on the system’s functionality and the explicit, concrete specification that is used to build the system. It is a risk in the design phase, but it is also an ongoing problem, with amendments to specification being required after implementation and deployment.</p> <p>The responsibility gap arises because the normal conditions are not met for manufacturers, operators or users truly to deserve moral blame for the autonomous system’s decisions, such as those that result in an accident or injury. The responsibility gap represents the difference between a human actor being involved in the causation of an outcome and having the sort of robust control that establishes moral accountability for the outcome.</p> <p>The liability gap arises because the normal conditions are not met for manufacturers, operators, or users to be liable to pay compensation to those injured by an autonomous system. It is the risk that due to the complexity of the system, and its autonomous decision-making capability, that when it causes harm to others the losses caused by the harm will be sustained by the injured victims themselves and not by the manufacturers, operators or users of the system, as appropriate.</p> <p>The gaps share the same three root causes: the complexity and unpredictability of the system’s operational domain; the complexity and unpredictability of the system itself; and the increasing transfer of decision-making function from human actors to the system. These three issues also affect the safety assurance of autonomous systems. Not only is it much more complicated to provide a justification of the acceptable safety of autonomous systems, it is hard even to know what the required degree of confidence is within this new paradigm. The central, unifying argument of this paper is that measures to address each of the gaps above can inform the safety assurance of autonomous systems."</p> <p>Liability gap: "(...) if the defective behaviour comes into existence after the manufacturer parts with the product (unless it is the learning design itself that is defective) then it is likely that the manufacturer will not be liable. Where we are dealing with machine learning proving that the system was defective when it left the hands of the manufacturer will be extremely difficult."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>In addition to discussing the gaps presented in the answer to Question 3, the authors have illustrated the three gaps with two case studies (automotive and clinical applications) and proposed a solution for narrowing the gaps. These are herein summarized.</p> <p>Semantic Gap: Case Study 1 - Automotive Application: "Machine learning functions do not deliver clear-cut answers. For example, for a given video frame, they might classify the probability of a pedestrian inhabiting a certain portion of the picture as 83%, but in the very next frame – which for humans is imperceptibly different to the last – they may “misclassify” the same object as only 26% probability of being a human and 67% probability of being a road sign. In addition, the processes which lead to these decisions are difficult to decipher. These attributes result in a paradox or “no free lunch” effect, where the problem of deriving a suitable specification of the intended behaviour is instead transferred to the problem of demonstrating that the implemented (learned) behaviour meets the intent."</p> <p>"(...) the concrete specification of the system must inform what the system itself should do under all situations, even when a completely safe state may not be able to be reached. This is a huge task, involving considerable uncertainty. Due to the open context and the complexity of the decision algorithms it may not be possible to even predict which decisions the vehicle would take under certain circumstances."</p> <p>Reducing the semantic gap: "The complexity of the systems is managed by limiting the deployment of machine</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 375 / 550	

	<p>learning algorithms to well-defined and constrained functionality with restricted safety impact. This includes using parallel approaches to sensing and plausibility checks. It is also planned to make increased use of infrastructure, such as the transmission of traffic signal status, to allow for more robust approaches to environmental sensing. In this way, the burden of validating the machine learning components is reduced. But reducing the integrity requirements on machine learning components through functional redundancy comes at the price of many more system components and overall cost."</p> <p>"It should be noted that addressing the semantic gap will not happen solely in the design phase. It will be an ongoing process, with amendments to specified functionality being made after it is understood how the systems operate "in the wild," and once differences between usage in different cultures has been more fully understood, including how attitudes to acceptable safety vary between countries, etc. The compromises described above may be iteratively relaxed as more validation evidence is generated, technological advancements are made, and a stronger and a more dynamic overall safety case is achieved."</p> <p>Case Study 2 - Clinical Application: "The AI Clinician aims to guide the use of fluids and vasopressors in septic patients and does not provide guidance on any other aspect of care; this narrow focus is probably of benefit.</p> <p>The AI Clinician uses 48 variables to assign the patient to one of 750 states, and operates over a 4-hour window. It is therefore able to be much more responsive to more subtle changes in the patient's status than is possible for a human clinician and bedside nurse.</p> <p>(...) there are the technical limitations of the system (e.g. reward hacking in reinforcement learning). The AI Clinician can only make its decisions based on data entered into the Electronic Patient Record (EPR). By contrast, human clinicians can respond to a variety of inputs when making their decisions. The system also uses a MDP, which only looks at the present state of the patient, and thus is quite unlike human decision-making. In addition, there is a great deal of inertia the clinical decision-making process."</p> <p>Responsibility Gap: "dilemma situations (...) should be avoided by design, and the public should be made aware of behavioural traits and performance limits (...).".</p> <p>"The method of reflective equilibrium is particularly helpful to decide the best course of action where there is uncertainty. It is an inductive reasoning process that involves agents making specific, context-sensitive judgements (e.g. judgements about the system's desired functionality), on the one hand, and evaluating these against a wider set of moral principles and non-moral beliefs, on the other, and revising each until there is an acceptable coherence among them. We suggest that the process can offer greater clarity on intended functionality, including where 'ethical dilemmas' are concerned. This can enable a more complete system specification."</p> <p>Examples: Analyzing boundary scenarios in which hazards may arise and converge to the common-sense belief of the team unless there is no such convergence.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Future work:</p> <p>"What is proposed here is largely aspirational – although there is ongoing work developing these approaches:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Safety Case– a key part of the safety case should define how gaps are identified and what has been done to control them. For example, the argument should include a demonstration of the delimitation of moral and legal responsibility between designer/manufacturer, operator and the user. (...) Similar models are needed for the other gaps, and for the detailed problems of the use AI and machine learning in the system (...). Acceptance of the safety case should be based on the method of reflective equilibrium, achieving an acceptable level of coherence amongst the considered judgements and beliefs of representatives from as many relevant stakeholder groups as possible. 2.Monitoring and Dynamic Assurance– due to the complexity and uncertainty of the system and its operational environment, it is likely that the initial safety case will not accurately reflect the actual gaps – be they semantic, responsibility or legal. The systems of interest are data-rich, and this gives the opportunity to assess what is actually happening, as opposed to what was anticipated at the design stage. We can use machine learning to process the operational data, to determine whether or not the initial safety case was accurate, and to identify the need for remedial action if not (...). This work may ultimately enable the safety case to be updated dynamically to reflect actual risks and gaps, although this is most likely to be practicable for the semantic gap." <p>Other work related to law, regulation and governance were also proposed, but they are deemed outside the scope of engineering-related techniques to assure that AI-baed systems are safe.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Excellent insight on challenges towards the safety assurance of AI-based systems, with a clear presentation of multidisciplinary gaps and possible paths to fill them.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 376 / 550	

8.271 REFERENCE [830]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "present an historical overview about the connections between the analysis of risk and the control of autonomous systems".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, with focus on reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors have presented a thorough review on means and techniques to assess risk and reviewed how the three identified approaches have been taken into account when designing autonomous systems.</p> <p>Worst-case: "(...) the worst-case paradigm summarizes uncertain outcomes in terms of the most harmful outcome." It is "a future of misfortune".</p> <p>Risk-neutral: "The risk-neutral paradigm summarizes uncertain outcomes in terms of an average outcome, which is defined using an expectation." It is "a future of averages".</p> <p>Risk-averse: "(...) the term risk-averse describes people or algorithms that prefer cost distributions with particular characteristics, where the characteristics reflect a desire to reduce harm" and "uncertainties".</p> <p>Main studies for each category (several studies were reviewed in our own SLR):</p> <p>Worst-case:</p> <p>Risk is characterized using robust or deterministic reachable or invariant sets (tubes are also included):</p> <p>Discrete-time models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polyhedrons, ellipsoids, and linear matrix inequalities;- - Mixed monotone systems with deterministic temporal logic specifications; <p>Continuous-time and hybrid models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sum-of-squares programming for systems with polynomial dynamics; - Hamilton-Jacobi partial differential equations; - Taylor expansions to approximate nonlinear dynamics (e.g., Flow*); - Boolean combinations of nonlinear constraints (e.g., dReal, dReach); - Verifying neural network controllers (e.g., Verisig, ReachNN). <p>Risk is quantified using the optimal value of a robust or deterministic optimal control problem:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimizing or bounding the H_∞-norm of a closed-loop transfer function; • Optimizing discrete-time MDPs with respect to a maximum cost; • Optimizing a policy subject to temporal logic constraints in a discrete-time setting." <p>Risk-neutral:</p> <p>"Risk is the probability of a system entering an unexplored region, entering a dangerous region, or not reaching a target:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approximation of optimal policies for constrained MDPs using Q-learning; • Exploration by perturbing an expert's demonstrations with noise; • Dynamic programming with theoretical guarantees for hybrid systems or MDPs. <p>Risk is the minimum expectation of a (typically) cumulative cost, where an expected-value or probabilistic constraint may be included in the problem statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classical approaches for minimizing the expectation of a random cumulative cost; • An expected-value constraint ensures that any state can be visited from any other state; • Model predictive control and MDPs subject to chance constraints (a chance constraint ensures that a particular probability is within a particular interval); • Autonomous systems with probabilistic temporal logic (PTL) specifications <p>- Optimal control of hybrid systems or MDPs with PTL constraints.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The expectation is maximized over a particular set of distributions, which may be estimated from data samples." <p>Risk-averse:</p> <p>"Risk is the smallest value of a risk functional of a random cost:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected utilities (e.g., exponential utility); • Quantile-based risk functionals (e.g., CVaR); • Nested risk functionals.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 377 / 550	

	<p>Risk is the smallest value of an expected random cost subject to a constraint on a risk functional of a random cost; CVaR constraints are most common.</p> <p>Risk is expressed in terms of temporal logic specifications that are defined using risk functionals."</p> <p>"• Q-learning with a maximum cost criterion; one of the first papers to introduce risk functionals to the machine learning community (1994);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q-and TD-learning algorithms that highlight unfavorable state transitions using a scalar weighting (2002); • Q-learning with the exponential utility functional (2002); • Q-learning to optimize approximately an MDP subject to a chance constraint (2001, 2005); • Q-learning with a utility-based risk functional; the work studies connections between the algorithm and human behavior(2014); • Q-learning with a nested risk functional (2017, 2021); • Temporal difference learning with a nested risk functional (2021)."
Q4 Answer	<p>"Model-free and model-based approaches have advantages and disadvantages, which have particular relevance for risk-averse autonomous systems. (...) Using simulations or experiments to anticipate and circumvent rareharmful outcomes, which concern risk-averse systems, is difficult. This task may require the selective generation of samples, e.g., importance sampling."</p> <p>"Safe learning is a growing research area that builds on ideas from adaptive control theory and reinforcement learning to develop combined model-free and model-based methods for autonomous systems."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Future work: "We are not aware of any research that uses risk functionals and data samples to improve the estimates of models or reachable sets in real time. However, this research direction is likely to be fruitful, given experimental evidence that some risk functionals can offer protection against modeling errors."</p> <p>"• The field requires more knowledge about how to design experiments so that the experiments provide data samples with desired statistical properties at runtime.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies about risk-averse model-free methods from a nonasymptotic viewpoint are needed. This is because finite time horizons and finitely many samples are used in practice (...). • There is limited understanding about which risk functional may be more useful for a given application. To improve this understanding, the field requires additional empirical studies that compare the performance of different systems, where performance is quantified using different risk functionals. For instance, in previous experimental work, we discovered that choosing a more negative value for .when optimizing exponential utility can increase both the mean and variance, suggesting caution when using exponential utility for optimal control in practice. • New theoretical risk-averse optimal control methods that include both model-free and model-based aspects will likely yield positive impact." <p>"(...) applications that involve rare high-consequence situations, simulators or representative data sets may not be available. In this case, using simulations or data to drive decision-making would not be suitable. Instead, it would be suitable to use a mixture of tools and knowledge."</p> <p>"Domains that deserve further emphasis in risk-averse systems research include renewable energy, water resources, and biology. These domains require systems to operate effectively despite uncertainties, and the mitigation of harmful consequences in these domains is paramount. We are hopeful that the technology of risk-averse autonomous systems will be developed and applied broadly to enhance human and environmental welfare."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Excellent review of risk assessment with AI-based systems, focusing on formal verification and reinforcement learning. Many of the reviewed papers have been considered within this SLR as well.</p>

8.272 REFERENCE [831]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To report experience "with developing an assurance case for a deep learning system used for retinal disease diagnosis and referral", as well as to "explore the need for an assurance argument pattern that could provide developers with a reusable template for communicating and structuring the different claims and evidence and clarifying the clinical context".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, with focus on deep neural networks.
Q3	"An assurance case is "a reasoned and compelling argument, supported by a body of evidence, that a system,

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 378 / 550	

Answer	<p>service or organisation will operate as intended for a defined application in a defined environment". An assurance case is considered as a generalisation of a safety case, i.e. where safety claims are the focus of the assurance."</p> <p>The authors build an assurance case to a system used for retinal disease diagnosis. "This system comprises 2 different neural networks. The first network, called Segmentation Network, takes as input three-dimensional Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) scans and creates a detailed device-independent tissue-segmentation map. The second network examines the segmentation map and outputs one of the four referral suggestions in addition to the presence or absence of multiple concomitant retinal pathologies."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Segmentation Network: "Evidence of sufficient performance is provided based on two different scanning devices (99.21% and 99.93%). The argument clarifies further that for unambiguous regions, the network produces tissue-segmentation maps that are comparable to manual segmentation. For scans with ambiguous regions, the network provides different (but plausible) interpretations of the low quality regions (...)."</p> <p>Classification Network: " (...) the primary claim that the system achieves or in some cases exceeds human expert performance in retinal disease diagnosis and referral".</p> <p>General Results: "Evidence in machine learning studies tends to focus on meeting or exceeding certain performance criteria. The assurance argument above is consistent with this approach. Importantly, it ensures that the different training, test and validation datasets are explicitly referenced in addition to the performance results."</p> <p>"(...) a pattern could prompt the developers and assessors of machine learning to more explicitly consider the relevance and appropriateness of the contextual and evidential data, i.e. ensuring sufficient confidence in the quality and relevance of the data and models, by scrutinising the links in the argument (...), rather than merely exceeding a specific performance measure."</p> <p>"(...) the reviewers of the case can question the profiles and representativeness of the clinical experts involved in the experiments and the extent to which further clarification might be necessary. Transparency in how the machine makes clinical decisions is also important. Here, the assurance case clarifies that transparency is limited to the output of the segmentation and not the classification network (...)."</p> <p>"(...) there remain fundamental questions as what is deemed as good enough for assuring the safety of machine learning. For example, are arguments based on exceeding human equivalence or appealing to risk-benefit evidence acceptable? How do we address non-quantifiable factors such as those related to human or organisational factors? Another issue is the readiness of the regulators to review, challenge and approve machine learning evidence."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed / identified.</p> <p>Future work: Not directly discussed, but indirectly covered by the 'General Results' on Question 4 answers.</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good overview of assurance cases as a generalization of safety cases. 2) Relevant questions for future work; in line with future work proposed by our SLR and to be covered on our research. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Very simple case study, without further comments on how the AI has been assessed. 2) Results rely mostly on performance metrics. No consideration of random or systematic faults.

8.273 REFERENCE [832]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present the results of a systematic review on "methods towards improving, ensuring and assessing safe machine learning" and comparing them with those "for safety-critical software that are recommended by the functional safety standard IEC 61508".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 379 / 550	

Q3 Answer	<p>"This article aims at giving an overview of existing approaches for the safety assessment of ML algorithms by systematically gaining and visualizing knowledge about the research landscape. In order to give structure to the overview, the identified methods were assigned to certain software life-cycle phases and categorized. Building the bridge towards common safety regulations, it was evaluated to which extent highly recommended methods from IEC 61508 are referred to by today's research activities, the standard that addresses functional safety of electrical / electronic / programmable safety-related systems."</p> <p>The authors have categorized a set of references from Scopus only according to IEC61508 project phases and presented an analysis of the most frequent researchers and themes. No expansion on how the area has evolved with time, nor on future tendencies and pending work, have been explored.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) it can be stated that most of the software lifecycle phases as defined in IEC 61508 are being addressed by research activities in the field of machine learning. In comparison to the standard, which lists no applicable methods for the architectural design of ML, a lot of research in the identified literature population is going towards safe design methods."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Future work: "In the future, both overhanging sides need to be converged into a combined toolbox of methods through all development phases to evaluate and prove a safety argument for ML systems in certain safety-critical applications. A literature research is needed for approaches of combining methods, as well as assessing their combined effectiveness, to prove the meaningfulness of the toolbox approach. The methods in the product usage phase are promising approaches to solve the challenges concerning the adaptive and probabilistic nature of ML-components, especially in online learning environments. The research activity in this field appears to be moderate. A next step of our research will focus on an assessment of the methods within this lifecycle phase with regard to their applicability to safety-critical applications in industrial automation."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good introductory literature review. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Restricted search scope. 2) Some expressions used in the search are not perfect fit for the safety area.

8.274 REFERENCE [838]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To undertake "safety assurance of the AI Clinician, a previously published reinforcement learning-based treatment recommendation system for sepsis."
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we applied the principles of the Assurance of Machine Learning in Autonomous Systems (AMLAS) methodology to a previously published AI model built for informing the treatment of sepsis".</p> <p>"(...) we used expert opinion and the literature to define a set of four undesirable clinical scenarios. Given that the action space of the AI includes fluids and vasopressors, we selected scenarios representing possible under or overdosing of these two drugs."</p> <p>"To study the difference in the proportion of human and AI mistakes, we model them as Bernoulli random variables (...)."</p> <p>"Next, we analysed which patient features were associated with human clinician unsafe decisions. We trained gradient boosting models to predict whether clinicians would take an unsafe decision given the set of patient features as input. Separate models were trained for all four scenarios. We then reported the relative SHAP importance of each feature from the fitted gradient boosting model and proposed hypotheses for the significance of the most important parameters. Finally, the results of this initial safety analysis were used to refine the AI Clinician algorithm."</p> <p>"We modified the reward function of the model by systematically penalising instances where harmful decisions were taken by clinicians in the training dataset. Specifically, we added a certain amount of penalty to any decision that satisfied our predefined unsafe scenarios, so the final reward function includes both intermediate and terminal signals."</p>
Q4	"(...) we applied best practice in safety assurance to a complex AI system and proposed a safety-driven

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 380 / 550	

Answer	<p>approach to identify regions of the action space potentially associated with preventable harm."</p> <p>"(...) the original AI Clinician had a lower proportion of unsafe behaviour than human clinicians in all four scenarios, while the modified 'safe' policy did better than the original AI Clinician."</p> <p>"To our knowledge, this work is the first successful attempt at defining and testing safety requirements for an RL-based clinical decision support system considering multiple clinical hazards and at modifying the reward function of such an agent with added safety constraints. Despite the lack of consensus on a gold standard in sepsis resuscitation, there are decisions that are 'obviously' dangerous, such as those we defined in this work. Given the potential harm caused by these decisions, the model will have to be explicitly taught to avoid them where possible. This research represents one concrete step in this direction, and we demonstrated that our modified AI was 12% less likely than human clinicians to suggest those decisions."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) more in-depth technical research is needed to robustly define and assess the best way to perform reward reshaping in the context of safety assurance.</p> <p>Here, we did not assess the outcomes associated with taking our custom defined safe or unsafe decisions because of methodological challenges associated with the assessment of the value and estimated outcomes of following a policy that was generated by a different agent (the problem of off-policy policy evaluation). Another limitation is that our choice of hazardous scenarios may appear arbitrary. However, it was rationally designed following the concepts of overdosing and underdosing of the two drugs of interest, defined and refined by expert clinicians over several iterations and was constrained by the retrospective data available to us (...). While this work successfully integrates four safety constraints into model learning, there remain many more loosely defined hazards, such as administering fluid boluses to patients with (explicitly labelled) congestive heart failure, interstitial renal or pulmonary oedema, or acute respiratory distress syndrome, which should also be considered for a fully developed system. The iterative nature of the approach presented here provides a framework for the future addition of more scenarios. The penalty associated with each unsafe scenario can be tuned to reach a satisfying trade-off between model performance and the various safety constraints put in place."</p> <p>"(...) despite our efforts to exclude these patients, some end-of-life patients in whom hypotension was left untreated will have been included. These would have: (1) artificially increased the proportion of unsafe decisions and (2) perverted correct AI model learning."</p> <p>"Other important components of the AMLAS methodology were not addressed in this project, including data management and model deployment testing 'in the field' (...)."</p> <p>"An emerging new avenue in the field is to augment AI models so that they can quantify their own confidence or uncertainty over their recommendations. Going forward, it may be helpful to algorithmically combine the communication of uncertainty that a system has about itself, which reflects the risk of unwanted behaviour as we have shown in other domains of risk-aware control by medical devices with its safety features, that we have shown here.</p> <p>Before widespread clinical adoption, more work is required to further assess the tool in its operational clinical context and submit it to the appraisal of bedside practitioners. Particularly, end users' decision to act on or dismiss AI recommendations may be attached to some human-centred AI design characteristics and the degree of AI explainability. Human factor aspects are central in AI-based decision support systems in safety critical applications, prompting us to keep actively engineering safety into AI systems."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) One of the first efforts in applying a systems-level method for assuring that an AI-based system is safe and showing practical results. 2) Excellent analysis of results, including shortcomings and future work. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) It is not clear how the technical safety analysis activities were carried out and how problems were identified.

8.275 REFERENCE [839]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To "focus on two aspects of clinical artificial intelligence used for decision-making: moral accountability for harm to patients; and safety assurance to protect patients against such harm".

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 381 / 550

Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; reinforcement learning (case study).
Q3 Answer	"Artificial intelligence systems have shown the potential to improve clinicians' interpretation and the subsequent decision-making process. The potential benefits of this capability, however, are offset by the widening of responsibility gaps and the additional risk of negative side-effects that are inherent in health-care interventions. In essence, the increasing of the scope and authority of digital health systems is challenging existing safety assurance practices and clinical accountability models. These safety assurance and moral accountability challenges explain some of the reluctance of safety-critical industries, such as aviation and nuclear power to consider applications of artificial intelligence."
Q4 Answer	Same case study of [829] and [838] (AI Clinician). "In the absence of a clinician's direct, deliberate control over the recommendations reached by an artificial intelligence system, and given the opacity of many of these systems, safety assurance becomes increasingly important to both clinicians and patients. Safety assurance provides grounds for confidence that the patient safety risk associated with the system remains as low as reasonably possible. However, the static nature of most current safety cases does not cope with the dynamic characteristics of either clinical settings or machine learning. The adaptive behaviour of artificial intelligence systems typically alters the clinical environment, thereby invalidating the assumptions made in the safety case. In addition, the intended function of an artificial intelligence system is extremely diverse, and only partially understood by everyone involved, particularly the developers and the clinicians. The intended function cannot therefore be fully represented in the concrete specification that is used to build the system and which the system implements. The specification (in our example, sepsis treatment in intensive care) is based on a limited set of data points (vital signs and laboratory results). It is therefore much harder to assure, through a static safety case, that the system's specified function preserves safety in all clinical scenarios in which it will operate. It becomes increasingly hard to assess the actual risk of harm to patients and this difficulty presents an epistemic challenge to the safety engineer. The difficulty of mitigating the actual risk of harm to patients presents a control challenge to the safety engineer. From a technical engineering perspective, consideration of the safety of artificial intelligence is often limited to robustness: the properties of the system that might reduce its performance and availability, but not necessarily lead to patient harm. An example is model overfitting, where the predictive model fails to generalize beyond the set of data from which the model was derived. Technologists often fail to trace the impact of these technical properties on patient harm; for example, how biases in the artificial intelligence training data could compromise the safety of diagnosis in certain minority communities."
Q5 Answer	"We should therefore update our conception of moral responsibility in this context. We also believe in the need to move from a static to a dynamic model of assurance, accepting that considerations of safety are not fully resolvable during the design of the artificial intelligence system before the system has been deployed. This shift should include some consensus as to how much weakening of control, and what level of epistemic uncertainty is acceptably safe and morally justifiable before a digital system has been deployed, and in what context. Moral accountability and safety assurance are continuing issues for complex artificial intelligence systems in critical health-care contexts. As such, it will be important to proactively collect data from, and experiences of, the use of such systems. We need to update safety risks based on actual clinical practice, by quantifying the morally relevant effects of reliance on artificial intelligence systems and determining how clinical practice has been influenced by the machine system itself. To do this we need an understanding of how clinicians, patients and the artificial intelligence systems themselves adapt their behaviour throughout the course of their interactions."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good examples of future work on the safety assurance of AI along with an illustrative example (already covered in [829] and [838]). Weakness: 1) Not much different from [829].

8.276 REFERENCE [843]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "propose a safety assurance case for a pedestrian detection function, a safety-relevant baseline functionality for an automated driving system".
Q2	Machine learning in general.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 382 / 550	

Answer	
Q3 Answer	<p>"The validation of highly automated driving vehicles is an important challenge to the automotive industry, since even if the system is free from internal faults, its behaviour might still vary from the original intent. Reasons for these deviations from the intended functionality can be found in the unpredictability of environmental conditions as well the intrinsic uncertainties of the Machine Learning (ML) functions used to make sense of this complex input space."</p> <p>"(...) the absence of unreasonable risk due to hazards caused by functional insufficiencies has to be achieved by a rigorous overall development approach - from the specification of intended functionality, through derivation of subsystem functionality, the implementation and integration of functions and runtime monitoring with the possibility for updates to improve the system based on real-world observations."</p> <p>"(...) we propose approaches to answer the following questions: (i) Underspecification: What is the intended functionality and what are its limits? (ii) Semantic gap: How can the intended functionality be described? (iii) Deductive gap: Which requirements on the functional layer (here: ML) can be deduced? We present a safety assurance case that supports the argument of the absence of unreasonable risk due to hazards caused by functional insufficiencies by structuring the validation targets."</p> <p>"Underspecification might occur if the intended functionality is more diverse than what is specified. Consequently, defined use cases are only part of the intended functionality. Addressing underspecification by means of a generalization can lead to an inadequately defined safety requirements. In order to reduce risk of underspecification, we suggest the following validation targets. (...) Environment is sufficiently well known. Evidence: The hazard analysis and risk assessment (HARA) in the scope of ISO 26262 should be extended to determine properties of the environment that lead to critical situations (...). Systems safety approaches such STAMP can be beneficial here. Task is sufficiently well known. Evidence: Requirements shall be specified including task specific attributes. Sensitivity against unpredictable or unspecified impact of environmental attributes is sufficiently low. Evidence: Sensitivity to environmental changes shall be investigated. Moreover, influence due to distributional shift over time or due to geographic changes shall be reviewed. (...) Moreover, statistical extrapolation shall be used generalise the results of acquired data."</p> <p>"In the context of ML, semantic gap refers to making claims on the relevance of references used for training, test and validation data sets. We propose the following sub-goals to support the argument of "Reduction of risk due to semantic gap. (...) (...) classes are sufficiently accurately described. Evidence: Functional specification of several validation data sub-sets shall include all variants of classes that can be derived from the environment. Moreover, safety requirements shall be transferred into task specific requirements, e.g. informal textual specifications shall be transferred into formal specifications as far as it is possible, at least for safety-relevant requirements.(...) Location accuracy is sufficiently well described. Evidence: Training and validation data shall be specified. Evaluation of specific influences shall be specified. Additionally, evaluation of compliance with tolerances, of size and of location variation shall be specified. Discrepancy between real and described environment is sufficiently small. Evidence: Evaluation of similarity between reality and specification of validation data shall be specified. Functional modifications, such as run-time monitoring, degradation modes, pre-processing of ML input etc., shall be specified and documented."</p> <p>"Deductive gap refers to using invalid assumptions on different abstraction levels causing an unintended functionality. In the context of ML, features might be wrongly learnt or erroneously implemented. The deductive gap for ML differ from the deductive gap for non ML functions due to its intrinsic uncertainty. (...) The following validation targets can be defined for reducing the risk due to hazards caused by deductive gap before and during training: Data set is sufficient for the intended functionality. Evidence: Transfer of system-level requirements to ML-specific requirements as well as the attribute distribution within training, test and validation data sets shall be evaluated. Moreover, independence from unintended object relations shall be highlighted. (...) Overfitting is sufficiently reduced.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 383 / 550	

	<p>Evidence: Overfitting measures, such as pretraining on diverse data set, regularisation methods, Dropout or DropConnect, data augmentation shall be documented and evaluated. Underfitting is sufficiently reduced. Evidence: Underfitting measures (e.g., a minimum amount of training data for each class variant) shall be documented and evaluated."</p> <p>"To achieve the following validation targets, it is essential not only to consider ML in a black box manner (as it is handled during statistical analysis) but also to understand the essential influences for deviation from the intended functionality (...) by methods such as feature visualization, structuring of the input space, formal verification, and uncertainty quantification. "We suggest the following incomplete list of evidences: – Essential influences on the ML function are sufficiently understood. Evidence: The application of feature visualization, adaptation of confidence level and uncertainty calculation shall be documented. Furthermore, correlations of errors to features shall be investigated and reduced by appropriate training. Evaluation of these correlations shall be documented. – ML function is sufficiently robust. Evidence: Tolerance against distributional shift, adversarial and faulty input shall be evaluated. Statistical evaluation shall be documented. An integrity test of ML function shall be documented. – Learnt features are sufficient for function. Evidence: Learnt features and correlations between these and detection results shall be analysed and documented (e.g., by feature visualization)." "– Changes to parameters do not violate safety requirements. vidence: Verification specification for any changes shall be documented. – Differences between the training and target platforms do not lead to a violation of the safety requirements. vidence: Verification specification for any changes shall be documented. – Changes in target platform comply with safety requirements. Evidence: Verification specification for any changes in target platform shall be documented."</p> <p>"Measures at the System Level. To reduce the propagation of errors throughout the system and therefore to reduce the risk of hazards induced by functional insufficiencies at the system level should be identified by applying rigorous systems engineering approaches." "Diverse redundancy increases the dependability of a function." "As long as the environmental model is reliable, decisions are taken within a wider range of possible trajectories." "Run-time monitoring of assumptions allows the validation of whether assumed attributes about environment are still valid."</p>
<p>Q4 Answer</p>	<p>"This pedestrian detection function is typically realized by a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) (...)."</p> <p>"Critical situations may occur only rarely but must be adequately trained and tested. Furthermore, the validation data must include sufficient variants of pedestrians. The data must also allow for targeted validation of certain attributes, such as non-discrimination between age, gender or race. This requires that these attributes are represented and labelled in the validation data."</p> <p>The authors have presented the structure of a safety case for the safety goal "Machine Learning function meets all of its functional requirements" along with the strategies listed on the answer to Question 3 to reduce risk due to underspecification, semantic gap, and deductive gap.</p>
<p>Q5 Answer</p>	<p>"When we derived and structured the validation targets for our case study we included well-known methods and measures. While statistical evaluation offer a good basis to investigate improvements at a functional and system level, other methods, such as feature visualization, are used for analysis and for reaching a better overall understanding of the learnt functionality. However, the effectiveness of these methods and measures must still be evaluated in detail. Therefore, further research on the contribution of each method and measure to the validation targets of automated driving is necessary. We argue that only with an industry consensus on an established set of methods, can a convincing and accepted argument for the safety of automated driving be made. This includes an agreement on a sufficient "weight of evidence" and abort criteria for each validation activity, which has not yet been reached. As part of future work we aim to systematically evaluate the effectiveness and contribution of methods and measures discussed in this paper to derive and structure validation targets and evidence for series development projects. This includes the question how the effectiveness of the individual methods and measures can be measured and demonstrated based on quantifiable key performance indicators."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 384 / 550

Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Very good list of recommended practice to reduce risks in several design steps, potentially valid for a multitude of applications other than those of the case study.
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8.277 REFERENCE [844]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To "propose a high-level argument that could be used as the basis of a safety case for Reinforcement Learning systems, where the selection of 'reward' and 'cost' mechanisms would have a critical effect on the outcome of decisions made".
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	With machine learning, it is needed to ensure that "as many things as possible go right". "The safety of the system is therefore ensured, not through the implementation of pre-defined constraints but through its ability to deal with situations that cannot be predicted and applying adjustments to the system during its operational life. The safety analysis of the system would thus be predicated on the ability of the system to avoid hazardous conditions or adapt and deal with them should they occur. RL Systems adapt their behaviour based on the decisions they have made and the response they receive from their environment." The main challenges to show on dynamic safety cases, applicable to RL systems, are as follows: "1. Pro-actively compute the confidence in, and update the reasoning about, the safety of ongoing operations; 2. Provide an increased level of formality in the safety infrastructure; and 3. Provide a mixed-automation framework."
Q4 Answer	The authors have defined an incomplete general-purpose assurance pattern for Reinforcement Learning including five goals (G1-G5) and five contexts (C1-C5): G1: The RL system is acceptably safe in the defined environment. G2: System is in a safe configuration. G3: System performs a safe reconfiguration. G4: System performs transition to a fail-safe state. G5: System reverts to a fail-safe state. C1: Definition of acceptably safe. C2: Definition of RL system. C3: Refinition of environment (including users). C4: Defintion of system reconfiguration: system is in one of four states that maintain at least minimum safety. C5: Overall system states are (1) safe configuration, (2) safe reconfiguration, (3) transition to a fail-safe state, (4) fail-safe state. C1 depends directly from C1, C2, and C3, and satisfying C4, C5, G2, G3, G4, and G5 are needed conditions to fulfill G1. G2-G5 were not further developed.
Q5 Answer	"We do however recognise the limitations of the proposed argument structure and the discussion around the challenges. As such we have identified a number of considerations for further work when considering the safety assurance of RL systems. These are: 1. To what extent should RL algorithms be constrained in the way in which they learn? 2. How would we implement 'Intelligent/Dynamic Safety', whereby the safety monitoring evolves alongside the system? 3. To what extent should a RL System be allowed to create/update its own safety case as it learns?"
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Beginning of a systematic way to define general-purpose guidelines to design and assess RL-based safety-critical systems. Weaknesses: 1) The model is still at preliminary stage. 2) Claiming that safety assurance of AI-based systems is "ensuring as many things as possible go right" is not enough. The importance of assessing random and systematic faults is still necessary.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 385 / 550	

8.278 REFERENCE [845]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "present an argument pattern, i.e. reusable structure, that can be used for justifying the sufficient interpretability of ML within a wider assurance case".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Machine Learning (ML) algorithms (...) are often too complicated to understand. (...) A solution to this issue is to use ML algorithms which are more interpretable, or to try to explain their behaviour. In some sense an algorithm is interpretable if we can understand how it works and/or why it makes the decisions that it does make."</p> <p>"(...) we present an argument pattern, i.e. reusable structure, that can be used for justifying the sufficient interpretability of ML within a wider assurance case. Structured argumentation is well-established in the safety-critical domain as a means for communicating, justifying and assessing confidence in properties of interest (e.g. risk reduction and acceptability). The pattern presents an explicit argument that can be used to assess whether the right interpretability method and format are used in the right context (time, setting and audience)."</p> <p>"(...) interpretability is not a monolithic concept and relates to distinct ideas. The distinction is often made between methods which are intrinsically transparent and post-hoc methods that attempt to explain a model. We identify the following types of interpretability. A model/system is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Transparent if we understand how it genuinely works (mechanistically, at some level, for some part of the process). A transparent model is one which is inherently simple enough for humans to understand. For example, for a learned model, could a human take the inputs and generate the same outputs as the model (in reasonable time)? – Explainable if we can understand why it makes the decisions that it does make by using some post-hoc analysis and/or approximation, covering: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global explainability techniques which approximate the model with a simpler more transparent one. This simple approximate model is an explanation. Local explainability techniques which map inputs to outputs and identify important inputs. These help us to answer the question 'what were the important factors in this decision?'" <p>"Transparency provides faithful representations of the model, whereas explainable methods are often approximations, or incomplete explanations. Hence, there is a spectrum which captures the level of fidelity of different types of interpretability."</p> <p>The authors defined an assurance pattern for interpretable AI (see Fig. 2 of the paper).</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We show how our pattern can be instantiated for assuring the interpretability of a system of neural networks intended for retinal disease diagnosis." --> Related to [831].</p> <p>"(...) the healthcare setting here is clearly safety-critical and the designers of this system have identified interpretability as a requirement of the system in order that clinicians are able to understand and verify the system's predictions. Even though the individual NNs used were not interpreted, the method still provided some transparency of the system logic to the retinal clinicians, increasing their understanding of, and trust in, the ML system."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "The focus of future work should be to evaluate the applicability of the argument structure which should be presented to ML practitioners, their feedback should be used to make any necessary improvements. Further work may expand our argument structure to address different cases, for instance by drawing a more concrete link between relevant assurance properties and clear interpretability needs in a particular system. We hope that this argument structure will provide a clear basis for developing and assessing requirements for the interpretability of ML in safety-critical domains."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Strong conceptual basis for interpretable / explainable systems. 2) Beginning of a systematic way to define general-purpose guidelines to design and assess interpretable ML-based safety-critical systems.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 386 / 550	

8.279 REFERENCE [846]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To "propose a system that focuses on consensus building and agreement implementation as the basis for establishing AI trustworthiness".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we focus our discussion on trustworthiness in the field of data-intensive medicine that uses such AI systems. We believe it is not sufficient for AI systems to be able to deal with these issues autonomously in this field."</p> <p>"The process begins with a determination of the main requirements for ensuring AI safety. The assurance case expert writes the assurance case, with the top goal (or top claim) being the most important requirement defined by the stakeholders."</p> <p>"Stakeholders can read this case and, if necessary, view it as a diagram. Through channel messages, in an interactive discussion with other stakeholders, they can ask and answer questions, rationales and agree or disagree on the top goal and its context. The assurance case expert modifies the assurance case accordingly, in line with the content of the discussion, and presents it to the stakeholders."</p> <p>"Once the top goal has been agreed upon, the facilitator starts a discussion about the strategy needed to achieve the top goal and how to break it down into subgoals by using the strategy. Based on the stakeholders' comments, the assurance case expert will develop the assurance case. When the facilitator wants to confirm that achieving these subgoals leads to the top goal, she or he must reactivate the voting function and obtain further stakeholder consensus."</p> <p>"With incremental assurance case development, the assurance case evolves through repeated consensus building at each project milestone of the project's progress."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We have applied the effectiveness of the CBAC to a case study of data-intensive medical science."</p> <p>"(...) we targeted the subject of data trustworthiness in terms of the AI safety of feature engineering, which is an important aspect of machine learning-based prediction. An assurance case was prepared in advance, recorded in the supporting system, and used as the first proposal for consensus building."</p> <p>"The basis of the top goal was clarified by adding two context nodes. The three subgoals with evidence also became clear after five context nodes were added."</p> <p>"With argumentations through assurance case development addressed appropriateness, and evidence to proof the goal's achievement addresses correctness. Thus, stakeholders are assured of the AI safety within the implementation. In considering the safety of AI in personalized medicine, as opposed to other complex systems, it is particularly important to build consensus among stakeholders on ethical goals. In addition, objective evidence is required to ensure the implementation of the agreement."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"However, there is still work to be done related to ensuring that stakeholders can understand the assurance case."</p> <p>"Since the ultimate purpose of an assurance case is to serve as a document which people decide whether or not they will agree to, there has to be a certain amount of explanation of its conventions in advance, as well as a format which they can consult for an overview of the whole structure at any time.</p> <p>Another issue that still needs work is managing multiple detailed discussions. Using the CBAC approach, since the consensus building process extends beyond a single conference, stakeholders may be joining or leaving the discussion arbitrarily, (...) This reveals the need for a means of clearly displaying the status of a pattern of multiple detailed arguments at any time.</p> <p>To solve the problems set out above, we plan to conduct further experiments in consensus building among stakeholders across a larger number of projects using the support system. First, we will confirm by experiment whether presenting an assurance case as a consensus proposal is beneficial. Second, if an assurance case needs to be presented as a proposal for an agreement, we will have to determine indicators of what explanations are needed in advance and how complete they should be. We will also streamline the requirements specifications for displaying assurance cases and for displaying a pattern of multiple detailed arguments, improve the chatbot function, and assess the results. The CBAC-based support system developed in this paper is now being</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 387 / 550	

	evaluated as a platform for disease prediction research and development using AI data analysis, as well as in broader AI systems. We anticipate that using this support system to address various issues in that field will allow research initiatives to achieve a high degree of trustworthiness from the outset and contribute to consensus building for AI systems in this role."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Most of the research is related to building consensus on a safety assurance case by means of virtual means due to the covid-19 pandemic. Despite the authors claiming that the research is applicable to AI-based safety-critical systems, they are just 'good practice' that could be applied to the project of any safety-critical system, regardless of AI.

8.280 REFERENCE [847]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "analyze the most common myths and misconceptions of data-driven methods observed in the recent literature".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; machine learning in general, neural networks, SVMs, unsupervised learning, kNN, k-means, logistic regression, decision tree, random forest, Bayesian classifiers.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) some basic questions regarding data-driven methods are yet to be properly documented, such as what data are and their sources in the context of process safety analysis. Also, many shortcomings were observed while analyzing research articles on data-driven methods. These range from inattention to minor calculation errors to serious flaws related to assumptions. These various issues may have arisen due to misconceptions in the knowledge basis or can be considered as myths since these might be thought of as insignificant in terms of readability and scientific interpretability. Myths and misconceptions can be viewed as "the application of a method or a model and the representation of data without following their respective scientific norms"."</p> <p>"(...) It is necessary to report the most crucial classification metrics such as the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The absence of any of these performance metrics may suppress the readers from understating the study's efficacy and credibility (...). At present, no article exists in data-driven process safety analysis that has pointed out to such myths."</p> <p>"(...) a total of 19 frequently used data-driven methods such as the fault tree analysis, event tree analysis, bow-tie, Bayesian network, fuzzy theory, analytic hierarchy process, Petri net, artificial neural network, support vector machine, decision tree, random forest, classification and regression tree, naïve Bayes classifier, k-means clustering, k-nearest neighbor, logistic regression, principal component analysis, independent component analysis, and partial least squares, were selected to collect documents. A bibliometric search was conducted from the Web of Science Core Collection (WoS) database on May 28th, 2021. The timespan for this search was set from 1990 to 2020."</p> <p>"These journals were Reliability Engineering & System Safety (RESS), Computers & Chemical Engineering (CACE), Safety Science (SS), Journal of Hazardous Materials (JHM), Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries (JLPPI), Risk Analysis (RA), Process Safety and Environmental Protection (PSEP), Journal of Safety Research (JSR), Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part O: Journal of Risk and Reliability (JRR), and Process Safety Progress (PSP)."</p> <p>"The articles obtained from the previous step was further narrowed down to 500 documents using a random search technique."</p> <p>"(...) we have analyzed 500 public domain articles from 1990 to 2020, published in 10 renowned safety journals. The analysis attempts to address the following questions: (i) What are the key data in process safety analysis? (ii) What are the sources of data? (iii) What does the data-driven method mean? (iv) What are the common myths and misconceptions of data-driven methods? and (v) How frequently such myths and misconceptions are occurring?"</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) most of the myths are related to improper data representation, missing appropriate assumptions, and blanket use of methods without a detailed understanding of their limitations."</p> <p>"After analyzing 500 articles, a total of five data sources were identified: measurement, historical database, survey, expert knowledge, and simulation. In the analysis, two other myths were observed to occur commonly:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 388 / 550	

	using correlation coefficient for model verification and absence of error analysis. (...) most ANN-based documents do not provide any rationale behind selecting the hyperparameters that are crucial for ANN's performance." "(...) the most frequently observed myth is improper data representation. It consists of more than 50% of the total myths found from the studied articles. it indicates that many process safety analysis articles contain varying degrees of error in representing data. Another crucial finding of this study is the lack of proper assumptions while using BNs. The majority of the BN-based articles do not report the conditional dependence assumption while using BNs. In addition to these two, the other myths and misconceptions are mostly related to ML and MSPM tool-based works. In addition to identifying and quantifying the myths and misconceptions, we have also demonstrated scientific ways with examples to avoid them."
Q5 Answer	"A large number of BN-based articles showed that the results might contain a significant amount of bias. Another potential source of bias was narrowing down the manuscripts from the ten journals that we considered. This unintentional bias is the major limitation of the current work. Considering all the articles published in process safety domain instead of a moderate sample size of 500 and ten sources will be the promising venue to improve this work significantly."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good literature review with some converging conclusions to ours. Weaknesses: 1) Poor coverage due to a restriction to Web of Science results coming from only 10 journals and randomly selected among all these.

8.281 REFERENCE [849]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "provide a systematic and comprehensive overview of a broad array of inherent risks that can arise in AI/ML systems", including "data-level risk (e.g., data bias, dataset shift, out-of-domain data, and adversarial attacks) and model-level risk (e.g., model bias, misspecification, and uncertainty)", as well as to "highlight the research needs for developing a holistic framework for risk management dedicated to AI/ML systems to hedge the corresponding risks", including "research related challenges and opportunities along with the development of risk-aware AI/ML systems".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	"One of the major roadblocks is that the current usage of AI/ML fundamentally lacks a rigorous and systematic framework for assessment of risk and uncertainty." "Though such [performance] metrics are sufficient for many low-risk applications, it is dangerous to solely count on them in highly risk-sensitive applications, such as medical diagnosis and manufacturing industries, where safety and quality are the top priority." "(...) we are motivated to provide a consistent, rigorous, and consolidated overview on a broad set of risks associated with the adoption of general AI/ML systems. In terms of scope, we focus on the types of risks that closely impact on the performance of systems that are built with supervised AI/ML models and algorithms. Consequently, risks pertaining to data privacy and ethical issues are not within the scope of this paper. The systematic overview in this paper offers a concrete and consolidated understanding on significant issues characterizing the concerns of stakeholders when adopting AI/ML systems in critical applications from the risk analysis perspective. This overview also highlights the research efforts that are needed before fully embracing AI/ML systems in risk-sensitive scenarios. We also discuss the potential solutions and research directions that will inspire the development of comprehensive risk management strategies to guide future implementation decisions. We believe this overview can spark a lot of interests in the development of quantitative approaches, strategies, and control checkpoints to safeguard the use of AI/ML models in risk-sensitive applications."
Q4 Answer	1) Risks in AI/ML Systems: -Data-Level Risk: Data bias, dataset shift (covariate shift, prior probability shift, concept shift), out-of-domain data, adversarial attack (targeted or untargeted).

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 389 / 550	

	<p>-Model-Level Risk: Model bias, model misspecification, model uncertainty.</p> <p>2) Systematic risk analysis and risk management needs: Needed to address the following issues:</p> <p>a) Establishing a systematic framework for risk modeling;</p> <p>b) Establishing a testbed for risk analysis;</p> <p>c) Making systematic representation of failure modes in AI/ML;</p> <p>d) Creating a risk management framework for AI/ML systems.</p> <p>3) Open challenges:</p> <p>a) Dealing with black-box nature of some AI/ML models;</p> <p>b) Dealing with high computational burden;</p> <p>c) Dealing with application-specific risk conceptualization;</p> <p>d) Defining a safety margin for AI/ML systems;</p> <p>e) Making a reliability-oriented design of AI/ML systems;</p> <p>V&V of risk analysis and risk assessment approaches.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "Examining how these different types of risks and their effects emerge and unfold individually and collectively will inspire the leveraging of well-established theories and practices in other domains (i.e., reliability engineering, aviation safety engineering, system engineering, software engineering). In the long run, this will spark the development of appropriate policies, novel approaches, effective safeguards, and concrete actions to improve the situation awareness in risk management during the lifespan of AI/ML systems. On the other hand, this paper also has significant practical implications. The heterogeneous sources of risks pose a serious challenge when organizations adopt AI/ML solutions in practice. Hence, companies need to consider the benefits and potential adverse outcomes as well as the legal issues arising from adopting AI/ML solutions. Towards this end, AI/ML solutions need to be scrutinized with caution and rigor especially in high-stakes decision environments. Dedicated managerial capacity and resources need to be allocated to adapt the existing risk assessment and management practices in place to suit the unique needs for AI/ML development. Proper workflow and procedures need to be established to actively monitor the risk of adopting AI/ML in dynamic environments. Cases where AI/ML solutions are not in line with the regulatory requirements need to be pre-emptively identified to reduce the liability of the company." "Our hope is that this work will motivate researchers to develop innovative means to systematically identify, assess, and manage risks inherent in AI/ML systems for the sake of increasing the credibility in adopting and safeguarding their usage in risk-sensitive environments."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Relevant review with some converging conclusions to ours, including opportunities for future work addressed by Safety ArtISt.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Unclear work method for reviewing the references.</p>

8.282 REFERENCE [850]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To "present a treatment of uncertainty in autonomous systems inspired by quantum physics and propose an extension of the Goal Structuring Notation (GSN), a common approach for the modelling of safety arguments, to model 'superposition' and 'entangled' nodes; and, incorporate guidelines of the emerging UL 4600 standard for autonomous systems".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever (only mentions 'autonomous systems'). Indirectly refers to general-purpose artificial intelligence and machine learning because of the inspiration from UL4600.
Q3 Answer	"Part of the challenge stands with the fact that developing autonomous systems, entails designing for uncertainty which in turn exacerbates the need for uncertainty-aware software development methodologies." "(...) we take a multidisciplinary lens to the treatment of uncertainty. We draw ideas from quantum physics where uncertainty has been treated as a domain-native for decades to posit our ideas on modelling uncertainty

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 390 / 550	

	for autonomous systems. We also (...) propose an extension to the Goal Structuring Notation (GSN)". "UL 4600 is goal-based and makes use of assurance cases to argue in a structured way that the system is acceptably safe. Typically the safety goal defines what acceptably safe means for the case in question and then it proceeds to argue how the AV meets that definition It does not prescribe any specific software engineering approaches but it requires the use of rigorous ones." "Entanglement (in quantum physics), at its simplest, suggests that when two particles interact or share spatial proximity, their behaviour becomes intrinsically linked even after they are far apart." "We use the entangled uncertainties metaphor to posit that we should design for uncertainty by conceptualizing our design choices as superimposed ontological representations of reality. Our overall design for uncertainty resembles a 'solutions superposition-model'. Where, each solution taken (in other words the AV's behaviour at a specific time-step matches that particular solution), entangles the uncertainty in the AV behaviour within at least the next time step (the length of the time step would depend on when the next interaction of the AV will cause the uncertainties of its behaviour to become entangled with the environment (e.g., bumps into the next thing). Hence the intuition is that if we have enough 'certain' solutions designed in our 'solutions superposition-model' we can draw upon the 'entanglement of uncertainties' argument and collapse the problem-space into certain outcomes for the AV behaviour. In more lay terms, this translates into arguing about narrowing down the all possible behaviours' state-space into a subset of (designed for) acceptably safe behaviour by an AV."
Q4 Answer	"We propose to extend GSN nodes with metadata to: a) accommodate our vision of 'solutions superposition-model' to model autonomous systems; and, b) incorporate the extensive reference lists, different types of prompts and epistemic defeaters provided by the emerging UL 4600 standard as natural elements of our treatment of uncertainty ('entangled uncertainties')." The authors present a conceptual Goal-Structured Notation diagram illustrating their approach in which two nodes are entangled with uncertainties and all goals have an indication on how they comply to UL4600 recommendations.
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not discussed / identified. Future work: "In future work, we plan to focus on modelling and validating live feedback that drives the update of beliefs in probability distributions."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Relevant publication on dealing with uncertainties for autonomous systems. Weakness: 1) Overly conceptual model which still requires more maturing in order to clarify calculations and justify their applicability. The borrowing of quantum physics concepts is not fully justified on how well-applicable it is for the end purpose of AI/ML-based systems safety assurance.

8.283 REFERENCE [859]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To "introduce an integrated toolchain for the development of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) with Learning-Enabled Components (LECs) with support for architectural modeling, data collection, system software deployment, and LEC training, evaluation, and verification".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	"Our approach combines multiple Domain Specific Modeling Languages (DSMLs) to support various tasks including architectural modeling, experiment configuration/data generation, LEC training, performance evaluation, and system safety assurance." "Computationally intensive tasks (LEC training, simulation, execution, etc.) are executed remotely on servers equipped with the required hardware, and all generated data is stored on a remote file server and managed with a version control system. The toolchain supports a variant of the block diagram models from the SysML modeling standard for system architecture design.
Q4	No results except for a brief presentation of the method have been presented by the authors.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 391 / 550

Answer	
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not discussed / identified. Future work: "(...) we consider the design and implementation of a learning-enabled controller for an Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUV) tasked with following a pipeline on the seafloor. (...) We will demonstrate the design and implementation of this controller using the ALC toolchain including: design of the various models within the WebGME environment, execution of the system in a simulated environment, and integration with Jupyter Notebooks for interactive execution and performance evaluation. Wireless connectivity during the demonstration is preferable, but not required."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Little connection to the safety assurance of AI-based systems has been explored. 2) Research still on preliminary development without further results and/or theoretical contribution.

8.284 REFERENCE [868]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To present "a detailed implementation of an online verification module – the Supervisor – that copes with (...)" the challenge of guaranteeing the safety of "(...) software that is frequently adapted or contains complex, non-transparent components, such as artificial intelligence".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	"We provide an online verification (OV) framework that can be used to tackle approval issues when facing complex, frequently changing or AI-based algorithms. Furthermore, the method can be used to pinpoint safety issues during the development of a trajectory planner" for autonomous vehicles. "In the first stage, requirements for a safe trajectory, as well as requirements posed on the OV module itself, have to be defined, based on the superordinate safety goal. (...) To this end, a structured approach should be pursued to identify a holistic list of criteria for a safe trajectory." "The second stage addresses the implementation. First, the architecture of the OV is defined, then assessment metrics for the previously specified criteria are developed and merged with a classification function. (...) the OV runs in series to the planning module and receives environmental data (...), a planned performance trajectory and an emergency trajectory as input. The safety rating of these trajectories is the output (...)." "The third stage of the development addresses the integration and verification tests against the requirements. This procedure is state of the art, and structured recommendations are given in ISO 26262-4:2018, 7." "The fourth stage tackles the validation of the established Supervisor module. The goal of this process is to reveal possible design and implementation flaws affecting the safety goal in the overall framework. To this end, a scenario-based and a field-test validation is recommended." All mathematical formulation to ensure that the system is safe is based on application-specific equations that evaluate track boundary collision checks, dynamic collision checks, safe end state, acceleration limits, kinematics and dynamics feasibility, and traffic rules.
Q4 Answer	The authors claim that the validation of the proposed Supervisor module includes field tests and scenario-based tests for the limits of the supervisor with, e.g., fault injection. "First, fault-injected scenarios, targeting domains of individual SupMods are elaborated in hand with the general scenario-based testing strategy. Second, an exemplary real-world field test is presented. Finally, we provide insights in implementation details." "For the scenario-based evaluation, we showcase 42 scenarios with up to three vehicles, generated from scratch as well as based on real race tracks. (...) For each scenario, we define time intervals in which the rating of the Supervisor is expected to be safe, as well as regions where the rating is expected to be unsafe. (...) the Supervisor is able to avoid a collision in all of the scenarios, when used in the active pipeline (i.e., Supervisor rates and intervenes)."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 392 / 550	

	"(...) long runs in a real environment are essential to verify a low false alarm rate. In this course, we used the data of a trajectory planner in autonomous races to evaluate the Supervisor. As an example, we elaborate a race with 10 laps and two cars on a racetrack in Modena, Italy. (...) The Supervisor did not show any false positives ('unsafe' rating) during the entire race."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: "It should be noted that while the measures shown may be sufficient for a proof of concept in the context of this work, the testing effort would need to be significantly increased for actual approval." Future work: "Future work includes the integration of further regulations, tests in a larger set of scenarios, and the realization of a C-based implementation. While the implementation for a racing environment was demonstrated, the generic method is transferable to road vehicles if the applicable regulations are adapted."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Real application of a supervisor for safety-critical systems, following something that resembles a simplex architecture. Weaknesses: 1) The authors themselves still deem the supervisor is not still suitable for certification as safe. 2) The solution is very application-specific.

8.285 REFERENCE [870]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To "analyze a Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) without the need to solve it explicitly" by following "(...) the footsteps of Lyapunov's second method for verifying the stability of all solutions to an ordinary differential equation (ODE) without the need to solve it or the application of barrier certificate theorems for safety verification without the need to solve an ODE for all initial conditions in a given set."
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; reinforcement learning (case studies).
Q3 Answer	"1) We propose a switched system representation for the belief evolutions of POMDPs. 2) We present a method based on Lyapunov-like functions to overapproximate the reachable belief space, thus allowing us to verify reachability objectives. These overapproximations are in terms of sublevel sets of the latter functions. We demonstrate how these calculations can be decomposed in terms of the POMDP actions. 3) We propose a method based on barrier certificates to verify safety and performance of a given POMDP. We show how the calculations of the barrier certificates can be decomposed in terms of actions. 4) We formulate a set of sum-of-squares (SOS) programs for finding the Lyapunov functions and barrier certificates to verify the safety and performance and overapproximate the reachable belief space, respectively." "(...) we demonstrate that POMDPs can be represented as a special hybrid system, i.e., a discrete-time switched system. We take advantage of this representation in the sequel to formulate indirect methods for analyzing a POMDP." "Both cases of switched systems with arbitrary switching and state-dependent switching are well-known in the systems and controls literature." "(...) we can use tools from the control theory to analyze the evolution of the solutions of the belief update equation including the reachable belief space without the need to solve the POMDP explicitly. From a control theory standpoint, estimating reachable sets, invariant sets, or regions-of-attractions (ROAs) are well-studied problems in the literature. Recent results in this area include learning ROAs using Gaussian processes and active learning, computation of controlled invariant sets for switching affine systems, ROA estimation using formal language, and finding invariant sets based on barrier functions. In the following, we propose a basic technique for overapproximating the reachable belief spaces of POMDPs using Lyapunov-like functions." "We proposed two techniques for decomposing the construction of the barrier certificates and checking given safety requirements. Our method relied on barrier certificates that take the form of the convex hull of a set of local barrier certificates (...). Though the convex hull barrier certificate may introduce a level of conservatism, it is computationally easier to find (...)."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 393 / 550	

Q4 Answer	"(...) we illustrate the proposed method using two examples. In the first example, we study a toy example of the ad scheduling scenario in social media using a POMDP model. In the second example, we compare the teaching performance of two recently proposed machine teaching algorithms (myopic and Ada-L) and show the safety verification method (...) can be used to show that myopic teaching has poor performance while Ada-L has guaranteed convergence".
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not identified/discussed. Future work: "Future work will include a synthesis algorithm for POMDPs. To this end, the literature on designing switching sequences of hybrid systems seems relevant. Such synthesis techniques are aimed at providing guarantees for reachability, performance, and safety in POMDPs without explicitly or approximately solving them. (...) We will explore the possibility of using recent results on chordal sparsity in sum-of-squares programs in our computational formulation."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Relevant approach, based on barrier certificates, to assess if an AI-based system is safe. Weaknesses: 1) The case studies are not really related to safety-critical applications. 2) Some parts of the proposed approach require application-specific modeling.

8.286 REFERENCE [872]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To identify "ways in which explainable AI (XAI) methods can contribute to safety assurance of ML-based systems".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; machine learning in general, explainable AI.
Q3 Answer	"Some ML models are perceived as intrinsically interpretable to the user, so we refer to these as interpretable models. This includes linear/logistic regression, decision trees, K-nearest neighbours, decision rules, Bayesian models, general additive models (GAMs), etc. Note that, although often these models are viewed as intrinsically interpretable, when the number of input features are beyond human ability to grasp or when the input features are heterogeneous which is not uncommon in healthcare, it can be difficult for humans to interpret the model and care needs to be taken. When it comes to explaining more complex or opaque ML models, e.g. support vector machines, tree ensembles, and NNs, which are not intrinsically interpretable, a post-hoc explanation can be used to provide insights without knowing the mechanisms by which the model works." "(...) safety is related to six dimensions of ML-based systems": robustness, human-machine interface, data management, performance, explainability, and other safety specific controls." The authors present a systems lifecycle and discuss, for each of its five main steps (data management, ML algorithm selection, model learning, V&V, and operation) how explainable AI shall be taken into account.
Q4 Answer	"(...) XAI methods have a valuable role in safety assurance of ML-based systems in healthcare but that they are not sufficient in themselves to assure safety." The authors "(...) demonstrate how XAI methods can help to meet these safety objectives, particularly in model learning and model V&V. Specifically, we have shown the value of influential instances for model debugging during model learning, which is of particular interest to ML developers. Further, we have shown the value of feature relevance and counterfactuals in model V&V, which is of particular interest to ML developer, regulators and others involved in deployment decisions (...). The case study also shows how the use of these XAI methods feeds into a safety case."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: "(...) the limitation of explainability itself. Even if the evaluation metrics are improved, there are some intrinsic limitations of the current XAI methods. As pointed out (...) post-hoc explanations "must be wrong" as if they were completely faithful to the task model, then we only need the explanation model. Further, (...) current XAI methods only provide descriptive accounts of the task model rather than normative evaluation to justify the model behaviour. Whilst this is valid, it is unrealistic to expect XAI methods to "close the loop" by themselves."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 394 / 550	

	"We suggest future work should place more effort on developing and applying systematic evaluation metrics for XAI methods, which in turn will guide others in selecting appropriate XAI methods. Further, there is a need for more empirical studies to evaluate how XAI methods can best assist the end-users. This might usefully be combined with a deeper exploration of trust."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good foundation on explainable AI. 2) Excellent discussion on the limitations of explainable AI and the need for other techniques to ensure that AI-based systems are safe.

8.287 REFERENCE [873]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To explain "the importance of risk assessment (RA) coverage for autonomous vehicles (AV)" and provide "a comparison and summary of existing RA methodologies".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"With the dramatic increase of software and AI component within AV development, existing standards might not be sufficient to cover the safety lifecycle of an AV development that is differentiated from typical automotive. Since AV or ADS developments are relatively new, official requirements and standardization for ADS or AV safety have yet to be strongly established. Research journals, articles, and white papers have been released to educate developers while standardization is still ongoing. One of the most recent publications documented how different vehicle OEM manufacturers and their tier one suppliers emphasizes the importance of safety for AV and highlighted twelve important elements (Safe operations, Operational Design Domain (ODD), Vehicle operator-initiated handover, security, user responsibility, vehicle-initiated handover, interdependency between the vehicle operators and the ADS, safety assessment, data recording, passive safety, behaviour in traffic and safe layer) that are needed to achieve a safe AV."</p> <p>"With AV or ADS operating in an environment where risk and uncertainty can occur due to human variance are considered as non-deterministic. These uncertainties and limits of operations must be converted into measurable forms of actions for the ADS, either to avoid or to improve its performance. This step can be important because it is almost impossible to consider all scenarios and causes of uncertainty during development, even by performing more tests or simulations in different scenarios. Thus, the possibility of encountering any of these unforeseen scenarios can still happen in real-life applications – due to design considerations and limitations."</p> <p>"(...) a concise overview of RA coverage for AV (...) should include both product development (A) and real-time operations (B) and new hazardous events (unknown safe or unsafe) (C) can still happen during real-time operations, even though there are simulations, trial test and scenarios testing conducted."</p> <p>"(...) RA is created and planned during development (A) and are applied for real-time operations (1). However, in real-world deployment (B), it is impossible to consider all possible scenarios during development (A). Therefore, the detection (2) of new hazardous events (C) might cause unpredictable AV actions when it is supposed to react under the DDT fallback mode. At present implementation, these new hazardous events are recorded, and they require another development cycle (3) under maintenance to update and upgrade its new safety actions (if it is unknown unsafe). This reflects the potential exposed risk for every new hazardous event (C), which is not considered during development. (...) real-time RA is needed to ascertain the necessary actions for the DDT fallback without the need to wait for the re-development loop (3) instead risk is assessed and processed in real-time for safety operations (1) – which can assist the requirement of SOTIF. This could be achieved by using the pre-mapping of safety actions for every new hazardous event detected (4). Moreover, the approach of determining RA for AV consists of 1) vehicle level approach (to detect internal vehicle causes of risk) and 2) environmental level approach (to detect vehicle and environmental causes of risk)."</p> <p>"To accomplish the practical use of this methodology, challenges such as mapping of all potential scenarios must be done to ensure that there is no uncertainty present and all situation risks are assessed."</p> <p>"In terms of AI-based methodology for RA, there are fewer references due to concerns if AI is suitable for</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 395 / 550	

	<p>safety-critical system design. It is evident that AI is used for decision making and predictions for the AV and ADS. However, instances of AI for RA is not yet broadly studied."</p> <p>"The safety aspect of ML in highly automated driving is trending, but the challenge of handling uncertainty reduces the confidence in a real-world approach. (...) it emphasised on the importance of developers' knowledge within the AI and the importance of uncertainty calculation plus blackbox testing. In addition, the use of assurance case approach is recommended to obtain a systematic analysis of the root cause to mitigate risk and the importance of run-time (we refer to real-time) measures or risk to check against the developed decisions."</p> <p>"The risk of AI approaches if being used alone, can increase the appearance of non-determinism with increased risk, especially if developers lack an inherent understanding of the requirements it uses to create decision making. As such, DL might learn unsafe behaviours which were not intended in the first place. Therefore, AI and DL methodology might require more real-time testing and validation as compared to classical approaches such as process, probability and model-based. It is critical to note that the stochastic approach for AI or DL has its challenges for a safety-critical system. The key recommended approach normally includes a deterministic, non-deterministic, hybrid model like probability and model-based approaches or even AI with probability-based approaches that brings down the uncertainty levels. Even so, higher efforts of deliberate proof must be obtained for AI-based safety-critical systems to justify their deterministic outcome."</p> <p>"if the AI-approach is used alone (end-to-end) and does not have a guiding principle from modelling techniques, the uncertainty places a certain amount of risk. However, the uncertainty in AI can contain two kinds of problems since the accuracy of prediction or classification is very much dependent on the training dataset. The problem includes 1) the inaccuracy of the results due to insufficient dataset and 2) the lack of data set, which shows the lack of knowledge. The inaccuracies can be a form of uncertainty due to random outcomes within a classification of possible scenarios. This can be termed as Aleatoric uncertainty. While in the case of lack of data that leads to uncertainty, this can be classified as Epistemic uncertainty. Thus, without a secondary model, for example, a rule-based system to validate its outcome can incur unwanted risk. The training data can also include wrong references, which might lead to unwanted responses. These unwanted responses might also lead to risk-related outcomes, which are at times referred to as error rates. Therefore, as of current end-to-end AI DL approaches are discouraged for safety-critical systems. Therefore, AI, especially DL have uncertainties included, and they are needed to be addressed as part of the results. In most studies, these are classified as the error rate of the AI process."</p>
Q4 Answer	The results obtained on the research are within the answer to Question 3. Since the paper consists of a review, the main results are the reviewed themes.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Good overview on risk assurance methods for autonomous vehicles. AI-based strategies were briefly covered and deemed unlikely to ensure safety due to uncertainties.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) The safety assurance of AI-based systems per se has been briefly covered. Indirectly, when assessing risk assessment using AI, the authors claim that AI is deemed unlikely to ensure safety due to uncertainties; on the other hand, they defend the usage of AI on safety-critical functions but do not discuss how risk assessment methods are applicable to them. If AI is unsuitable for risk assessment, why would it be suitable for safety-critical control systems? This has not been answered by the authors.</p>

8.288 REFERENCE [874]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To guarantee "guaranteeing safety of the Autonomous Driving System (ADS) in sudden hazardous and risky situation" with "an evasive strategy (...) proposed as a part of an overall Probabilistic Multi-Controller Architecture (P-MCA) (...)".
Q2 Answer	Bayesian Networks.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 396 / 550	

Q3 Answer	<p>"The P-MCA (...) has been proposed around several complementary modules to plan/control and to assess and manage the risks of automated driving system in dynamic and uncertain environments. (...)</p> <p>1) Perception, Localization, and Route Planning Modules: The perception and localization are in charge of providing the important features of the environment needed for navigation such as the pose of the perceived obstacles, the number of lanes and the lane marking, and the sensory uncertainty. The route planning module (...) gives selected sequence of way-points through the road network.</p> <p>2) Probabilistic Decision-Making Module and Its Safety Assessment and Verification Criteria: The decision-making relies on a data-driven approach and consist of sequential Bayesian decision networks called SDN-MSV (...) that utilizes multiple complementary threat measures (...) to propose discrete actions and derive the appropriate maneuver in a given traffic situation.</p> <p>3) Motion Planning, Prediction and Evasive Strategy Module: The common task for automated driving system after the decision-making is to apply the decided maneuver by determining a nominal trajectory. This is performed (...) through the following main elementary behaviors performed by the AV: Lane Keeping Assist (LKA), Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC) and Automatic Lane Changing (ALC). (...) 4) Control Law Module: The used control law (...) is a Lyapunov-based stable nonlinear control law. It aims to guide asymptotically the automated driving system towards dynamic or static targets in the environment."</p> <p>"(...) we define a safety management strategy based on two stages: The risk assessment strategy and the safety verification mechanism. They are defined in details below.</p> <p>1) The Risk Assessment Strategy: It is used in order to analyze the actual driving situation and predict potential collisions in the purpose of choosing the most suitable maneuver regarding the actual driving scene. This is performed while taking into consideration any constraints or traffic condition that are known at the time of planning. This stage uses a first threat measure: an extended formulation of the Time-To-Collision. (...) 2) The Safety Verification Mechanism: Since every traffic situation is unique, it is necessary that the decided/planned maneuvers be always verified during navigation of the vehicle in order to ensure even more ADS safety in uncertain environment and changing dynamic/behaviors of the surrounding vehicles. A safety verification mechanism is introduced in this purpose in order to validate the first step assessment and quantify the risks and the criticality of the driving situation beyond the remaining time to achieve the maneuver in a retrospective manner. This task is performed through a dedicated second threat measure based on the dynamic progression of the inter-distance between vehicle, called the D-PIDP. The assumption considered in the definition of the D-PIDP is that if nothing changes in the initial expected dynamic of all the vehicles in the environment including the ego-vehicle, the predicted evolution of the inter-distance between vehicles is not supposed to change. (...) A Dynamic Predicted Lower Safety Boundary (D-PLSB) is then constructed as the projection (parallel curve) of the D-PIDP with an offset shift denoting a possible authorized degree of freedom over the difference between the actual displacement (distance, velocity) between the vehicles."</p> <p>"(...) the probabilistic decision-making strategy (...) is modeled as a sequencing of decisions that an automated driving system should take. It is based on Bayesian Decision Network theory and has the ability to support probabilistic reasoning, decision-making under uncertainty for a given system and yield the capacity to incorporate multiple decision criteria. (...) the three levels of decisions are illustrated and are explained.</p> <p>1) Decision 1 - Maneuver Decision Level (MDL): The first level decision is a part of the MDL where at each time control horizon Tch, the choice of action regarding the most suitable maneuver is made. (...) The possible output maneuvers of the SDN-MSV are: Lane Change Left (LCL), Lane Change Right (LCR), Keep Lane with ACC (KL-ACC), Maintain Velocity with CC (MV). (...) 2) Decision 2 - Safety Verification Decision Level (SVDL): The second level decision is a part of the SVDL where for each time step Ts, while the maneuver execution starts, a safety-checking regarding the action chosen in the MDL and a verification of the coherence of the maneuver with the predicted pre-planned trajectory is performed through the D-PIDP. (...) Its possible outputs are: Maneuver is Safe (MS) and Abort Maneuver (AM).</p> <p>3) Decision 3 - Evasive Action Decision Level (EADL): The third level decision is a part of the EADL where in case the verification procedure from the SVDL advises to abort the maneuver, the system output the discrete evasive action based on the vehicles' maximum capacities and on the endangered lanes i.e., the lanes where the anomaly is detected. The possible outputs are: Continue Maneuver (CM), Emergency Braking (EB), Emergency Stopping Lane (shoulder lane) (ESL)."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"The P-MCA is validated both in simulated traffic in various situations and on an experimental platform PAVIN. The adopted strategy in this work was to conduct from one side pure simulations to validate the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 397 / 550	

	overall architecture in dangerous situations, requiring the use of the evasive strategy defined in this paper. (...) On the other side, it is validated in this paper the online functioning of the architecture on real vehicles and its ability to take the right decisions in defined configurations, as well as its robustness to imperfect input data in real situations."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed. Future work: "A possible area of improvement of the proposed decision-making framework is in the discrete states of the decision network, where continuous function strategies to update the probabilities of the states will be further developed in future developments. Future work will also focus on field experimentation in critical scenarios, as well as extending the proposed work to other scene representations and to deal with even more complex scenarios (while verifying the real-time processing). Furthermore, another important area of improvement would be to perform quantitative assessment on the proposed method. For this purpose, a more exhaustive and generalized evasive strategy should be performed in future developments in large dangerous traffic environments/situations and this inevitably pass by the use of more complex modeling of the dynamics and constraints of the vehicle in order to reduce the modeling uncertainties while maintaining a high degree of flexibility and robustness needed for the navigation strategy. The main indicators that can be used to evaluate the performances of the proposed evasive method could be based on the D-PIDP and the reference predicted profiles."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Well-defined and sound method, backed up by experiments, to enforce safe behavior on automated vehicles. Weaknesses: 1) Lacking formal justification that the proposed system architecture is safe in the presence of faults (e.g., what would happen if the risk assessment block fails?).

8.289 REFERENCE [875]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "propose an interaction-aware safety evaluation framework for the highly automated vehicle (HAV) and apply it to the roundabout entering scenario."
Q2 Answer	Game theory, reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	"We propose an interaction-aware evaluation methodology in this paper. It consists of two modules: first, we create a testing space, in which we generate a library of interactive POVs using level-k game theory and social value orientation (SVO). Second, we propose an adaptive test case generation scheme to generate challenging test cases for a given VUT. We focus on the evaluation at the roundabout entering scenario. The POV library includes a set of templates for decision-making at roundabouts, which contributes to both assessment and design for HAVs planning algorithms. The test case generation scheme can identify diverse failure modes of the VUT, enabling efficient safety certification for HAV companies or third-party organizations." "(...) the research goal is to systematically evaluate the safety performance of a given VUT at interactive scenarios, specifically the roundabout entering scenario. The problem can be decomposed into two tasks. First, a testing space will be defined, which determines all the possible test cases (with interactions) to be evaluated. Second, a mechanism to select test cases from the testing space will be developed. In the first task, the testing space can be characterized by two sets of attributes: the first set defines the initial condition of the scenario; the second set describes the interactive and behavioral properties of the POV, which then formulates the POV library. In the second task, the test case generation procedure aims to evaluate the safety performance of a black-box VUT by adaptively discovering the failure modes of it through efficient sampling methods." "To approximate the decision-making procedure of human drivers, we assume that a POV is a bounded rational game-theoretic agent, which takes the (near) optimal action with respect to its utility function and assumptions on the opponents." "To compute the driving policy for a level-k agent ($k > 0$), we use single-agent reinforcement learning (RL) to solve the MDP. To train a level-k POV, we model it as an agent operating in an environment consisting of level-(k-1) OV. The same procedure applies to OV."
Q4	"(...) we first evaluate the performance of the proposed sample allocation methods using simplified

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 398 / 550

Answer	<p>experiments. Then, we conduct interaction-aware testing for a rule-based baseline VUT in MATLAB simulations to validate the effectiveness of the POV library and the performance of the proposed test case sampling scheme."</p> <p>"The UCB-dynamic method can generate the most failure cases across several simplified experiments among sample allocation methods. The adaptive sampling method can customize test cases to discover the failure modes of the VUT efficiently. It outperforms other sampling methods as well as our earlier work according to the FMC metric."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "For future work, we plan to extend the current framework to other interactive scenarios including crowded parking lots, unsignalized intersections, etc."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) No meaningful connection on how to ensure that AI-based systems are safe. The authors present an AI-based method to test autonomous vehicles (potentially controlled by AI), but do not go beyond in assessing whether safety is fully ensured.</p> <p>2) Application-specific solution for a particular driving scenario.</p>

8.290 REFERENCE [879]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "increase safety when using neural networks, by proposing a monitoring framework based on novelty estimation of incoming driving data" by using "unsupervised instance discrimination to learn a similarity measure across ego-vehicle camera images"
Q2 Answer	Neural networks, supervised learning, unsupervised learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>"This paper presents a framework for novelty detection monitoring of driving environments for automated vehicles using unsupervised learning. The idea of the monitoring framework is to determine whether the vehicle has been exposed to similar driving environments before or not (...) 1. If novelty is detected, predictions made by the systems are less trustable and control decisions should be made more conservative. The framework is built using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) backbones trained unsupervised via a non parametric softmax (...)."</p> <p>"(...) we will explore the use of metric learning for novelty detection. Rather than enclosing features within a hyper-sphere (...), unsupervised feature learning will be used to map training instances onto a hyper-spherical feature space, that is the most discriminative among them. The training data is then modeled through a von Mises-Fisher distribution and the novelty of test data is estimated through its probability of being sampled from the same distribution. The metric learning based novelty detection framework can then be used to monitor driving scenes."</p> <p>"The idea of a novelty detection monitoring framework is to estimate the similarity of a test image compared to the training dataset (...)."</p> <p>"Applying unsupervised feature learning, the feature embedding is constructed using a convolutional neural network (...). The network is trained through the proxy task of identifying each instance in the training data. In other words, each training image is assigned its own class and the task of the network is to classify each image as itself."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) three experiments are demonstrated to benchmark the proposed method. The first experiment benchmarks the method against some state of the art anomaly detection algorithms on commonly used datasets for such tasks. The second experiment shows the potential on driving datasets using real world driving data. Finally, the third experiment compares the novelty estimation to performance degradation in a driving function. The aim of these experiments is to show that the presented method gives competitive results in benchmarks, that it can be applied to driving datasets and potential use cases in automated driving."</p> <p>Experiment 1: "(...) the proposed method (...) outperforms the other methods on most classes" considering the performance metric 'Area Under Receiver Operating Curve' (AUROC).</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 399 / 550	

	<p>Experiment 2: "Naturally it would be challenging to achieve high performance since there are a lot of similarities in between the classes of images, in particular rainy scenarios or scenes from dusk or dawn in relation to the clear daytime images (...). This can be seen in particular for the night time images where higher performance is accomplished. (...) an AUROC of 72.6% is achieved when images in the test dataset containing pedestrians are considered novelties. This is further increased to 79.2% when including actions in the images, as can be expected since driving scenarios where pedestrians are present most likely involve different driving behaviors.</p> <p>Experiment 3: "Overall the segmentation loss is increasing the more visual dissimilar the test image is from the training data. Although there is some variance due to the architectural differences between the models, in other words the SegNet model may generalize better in some cases."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "(...) for the real world driving scenarios there are several overlaps in between the classes. Consequently an experiment of this nature will never achieve as high performance as when using discrete semantic classes. (...) The larger spread in training data for the scenario experiment is also evident when compared to the experiment including and excluding pedestrians."</p> <p>"By using unsupervised learning, novelty detection can be used as a monitoring function independent of the underlying systems. However, (...) using knowledge of the underlying driving tasks, i.e. applying supervised or semi-supervised methods, additional information can be extracted for increased performance, at the cost of generality. Such systems might be able to run in parallel but are left out of this study."</p> <p>Future work: "Another potential performance increasing modification could be joint optimization of the feature extracting network and von Mises-Fisher distribution fitting (...)."</p> <p>"Rather than relying on human interpretations, the method can be extended to work on segments of images, with the aim of finding the particular parts of the images contributing to the novelty."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The selected hyperparameters are not justified. 2) Very application-specific. 3) Little connection to the safety assurance of AI-based systems as a whole.

8.291 REFERENCE [883]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To present, by means of a systematic literature review, the current application status according to different AI techniques in safety-critical systems and propose some research directions and insights to promote its wider application.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, machine learning, neural networks, Bayesian networks, random forests.
Q3 Answer	<p>"A total of 92 articles were selected for this review through a systematic literature review along with a thematic analysis."</p> <p>"The literature is divided into three themes: interpretable method, explain model behaviour and safe learning. Among AI techniques, the most widely used are Bayesian networks and deep neural networks."</p> <p>"Interpretable method was further divided into two subcategories: decision tree & random forest and BN. Research on the former has just started and there have been only 3 papers on formal verification. There were total 35 papers on BN applications in system dependability, reliability, availability and safety analysis, V&V, system design and abnormal situation management. Explaining model behaviour focused on ANNs and DNNs. Given that the DNN literature is based on the problem of adversarial examples, as an intense research topic it has been separate for discussion in this paper. There were total 17 papers on ANNs, covering V&V and model development. Research of V&V was mainly on the "black-box" problem, one solution is obtaining explanation capability through rule extraction. ANN model development was mainly focused on building ANN and fuzzy logic hybrid model using rule extraction to gain "white-box" analysis and transparency. For DNNs, there were a total of 28 papers on adversarial examples, from the aspects of testing, verification, robustness guarantee, structure inspection and detection algorithm. Among them, formal verification was the focus of the research. Safe learning is about using reinforcement learning, which has rarely been applied to safety-critical applications due to safety issues. There were 8 papers in this category and concerning safe learning algorithms</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 400 / 550

	based on control theory, model predictive control (MPC), Hamilton-Jacobi-Isaacs (HJI) reachability analysis, and the Markov decision process. In addition, 1 survey paper regarding ML assurance of safety-critical systems has been discussed.
Q4 Answer	Proposals of Future Work: 1) "As a result, the future development of AI in safety-critical systems should also be taken with the holistic perspective of the whole lifecycle, such as AI lifecycle, safety lifecycle, system lifecycle, software lifecycle and others. This is particularly important when building an AI model for a safety-critical system." 2) "Some research on scalable V&V may be a future direction of research. In addition, the existing DNN verification mainly focuses on adversarial examples, whereas future research can extend to a broader perspective." 3) "(...) the future development of AI in safety-critical systems requires more formal methods plus the application of formal verification techniques. In addition, formal methods can be combined with the field of AI, and this holds a great potential for the use of AI in safety-critical systems." 4) Raising awareness in using the expression 'safety-critical' for safety-critical systems.
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed. Future work: See the answer to Question 4.
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good effort in presenting an overview of AI usage within safety-critical systems, including methods and their evolution with time. 2) Some of the proposals for future work are indeed relevant. Weaknesses: 1) The review method is not entirely transparent. 2) The scope of the review is broader than other SLRs yet less results were retrieved and analyzed.

8.292 REFERENCE [884]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "(...) systematically review the state-of-the-art testing and verification (T&V) methodologies, to classify approaches and tools that are invented, and to identify challenges and gaps for future studies" regarding neural networks.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	"The NN is considered the most viable approach to meet the complexity requirements of Safety-Critical Control Softwares (SCCSs)." "We have systematically identified and reviewed 83 papers focusing on the T&V of NN-based SCCSs and synthesized the data extracted from those papers to answer three research questions. RQ1 What are the profiles of the studies focusing on testing and verifying NN-based SCCSs? RQ2 What approaches and associated tools have been proposed to test and verify NN-based SCCSs? RQ3 What are the limitations of current studies with respect to testing and verifying NN-based SCCSs?" "To reach our result, we selected 83 primary papers published between 2011 and 2018, applied the thematic analysis approach for analyzing the data extracted from the selected papers, presented the classification of approaches, and identified challenges." "We executed automated searches in six digital libraries, namely, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, Compendex EI, ACM Digital library, SpringerLink, and Web of Science (ISI)." "The approaches were categorized into five high-order themes, namely, assuring robustness of NNs, improving the failure resilience of NNs, measuring and ensuring test completeness, assuring safety properties of NN-based control software, and improving the interpretability of NNs"
Q4 Answer	"Results show that correctness, completeness, freedom from intrinsic faults, and fault tolerance have drawn most attention from the research community. However, little effort has been invested in achieving repeatability, and no reviewed study focused on precisely defined testing configuration or defense against common-cause

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 401 / 550

	failure."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed. Future work: "In the future, we will focus on improving the interpretability of NNs. To be more specific, we plan to develop a method for explaining why an NN model is more (or less) robust than other models. It can guide software designers to design an NN model with an appropriate robustness level, which will greatly support safety by design."
Q6 Answer	Strengths: 1) Good effort in presenting an overview of NN V&V, including methods and their evolution with time. 2) Some of the proposals for future work are indeed relevant. 3) Sound literature review method.

8.293 REFERENCE [886]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "propose, research, and analyze a classification scheme considering both technical and functional AI characteristics that can be applied to a wide range of AI technologies" by documenting "gaps and challenges in defining a robust classification scheme".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	"We depict our initial classification scheme using a pyramid structure that shows the level of rigor needed to verify and validate an AI technology—which increases as the functional risk and technical risk increase. The top tiers of the pyramid represent technologies that may be candidates for early adoption and may require less rigor for acceptance and approval. The lower tiers represent technologies that may be later candidates for adoption and may require more rigor for acceptance and approval." "(...) our proposed classification scheme for AI technologies is based on two categories of characteristics: functional AI characteristics, which refer to the purpose of the AI technology and the complexity of its implementation, and technical AI characteristics, which refer to the functional criticality, temporal criticality, model accuracy, and trustworthiness of the AI technology." "Functional characteristics reflect the type of actions or activities the AI technology is aiding. This paper proposes four general functions for AI technologies: planning, decision-making, perception, and management/control.". The stringency of their safety requirements grows in this order. "The second set of characteristics in the classification scheme refers to the technical aspects and complexity of the AI technology itself. This paper proposes four characteristics: functional criticality, temporal criticality, model accuracy, and trustworthiness.". The stringency of their safety requirements grows in this order. Planning requires the least effort for safety applications, followed by decision-making, perception, and management/control. For each functional category, the least rigor exists with functionalities with low criticality, followed by those with low temporal criticality, those with more accurate models, those with low demands of trustworthiness, those with high functionality criticality, those with high temporal criticality, those with less accurate models, and those with high demands of trustworthiness.
Q4 Answer	The authors illustrate how the functional and technical characteristics of AI are related to systems used in aviation.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Despite the relevant classifications, there is not much novelty on the research nor in-depth arguments to support the presented model.

8.294 REFERENCE [887]

Q-Index	5
Q1	To define "a constrained Artificial Neural Network (ANN) that can be employed for highly-dependable roles in

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 402 / 550	

Answer	safety critical applications (...) based upon the Fuzzy Self-Organizing Map (FSOM)".
Q2 Answer	Artificial neural networks specifically following the 'Fuzzy Self- Organizing Map' (FSOM) architecture, also called 'Safety-Critical Artificial Neural Network' (SCANN).
Q3 Answer	Abridged version of [447].
Q4 Answer	Abridged version of [447].
Q5 Answer	Abridged version of [447].
Q6 Answer	Abridged version of [447].

8.295 REFERENCE [889]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "focus on two aspects of [automotive system] safety: functional safety per ISO 26262 (FS) and the safety of the intended functionality (SOTIF) per ISO PAS 21448" and to present "an approach to integration of FS and SOTIF requirements based on FS lifecycle".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general, machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	The authors have defined a combined safety lifecycle comprising the following work products: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Item definition (specification); - Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment; - Triggering Event Analysis (TEA); - Functional safety concept; - V&V strategy; - System verification report; - Validation plan; - Technical safety concept; - System design specification; - Integration testing plan and report; - Validation report; - Safety analysis report.
Q4 Answer	The main result of the paper is the proposal of the lifecycle presented on the response to Question 3. No further results are presented.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Lack of significant novelty that is relevant for the safety assurance of AI-based systems. The paper is just a critical review of two standards and a proposal to combine them both.

8.296 REFERENCE [895]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To propose a safety evaluation system for automatic driving systems composed of several evaluation projects and based on big data.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	"This study introduces a kind of autonomous driving based on user big data management and artificial intelligence and focuses on the application of the user big data management and artificial intelligence in the functional performance test, so as to ensure the sufficiency and accuracy of evaluation. In the next section, we introduce data collection and data preprocessing in big data management. Following that, we explain the principle and structure of the evaluation system and then provide experiments and analysis to support that the proposed method is effective." "The autonomous driving system is designed through the logic of perception, strategy, and execution. Vision

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 403 / 550

	<p>sensors are the perception core of the autonomous driving system and are responsible for observing the environment around the vehicle. The vision sensor obtains the image data of the vehicle's front scenery and calculates the three-dimensional point cloud information through the traditional matching algorithm, which is the process of the perception module. The strategic module is completed by the controller that detects obstacles based on the three-dimensional point cloud information, obtains the position information and category information of the obstacles, adds a tracking module to the detection results of the obstacles, acquires the stable spatial position, speed, and acceleration of the obstacles, and finally calculates the time-to-collision (TTC) value of the target obstacle. When there is a risk of collision, the autonomous driving system sounds an alarm and the braking system is activated."</p> <p>"Big data collection management is divided into four data modules. The first module is the basic data, which is the data collected by the perception module, including the left image and right images collected by the binocular vision sensor and the disparity map generated by the matching algorithm. The basic data is used for the logic design verification in the functional development stage. The second module is module data. The module data generated by AI technology using the basic data is an indispensable source of truth in the evaluation system. Here, it should be noted that in this paper, the deep learning model is adopted to train the basic data and can obtain the category information, position information, tracking information, and TTC of the obstacles, which are used as standard values in the evaluation system to evaluate the module effect of automatic driving. The third module is the collection of obstacle data to evaluate the detection result consistency between the development platform and the actual application platform in the system. The obstacle data includes the type of obstacle, the location of the obstacle, and the TTC. The last collection module is runtime data, which is used to verify the real-time effect of the function."</p> <p>"Data preprocessing is the basis for building user big data management. The incorrect data structure or format often consumes a lot of storage space. Through data preprocessing, the quality of the data is ensured, and the storage space occupancy is reduced to a great extent, which in turn generates cost benefits. Besides this, data preprocessing guarantees that data is injected without errors so that basic verification functions can function normally."</p> <p>"The evaluation and development work needs to be carried out simultaneously. (...) the evaluation system proposed by us consists of the offline test module and the online test module to complete the evaluation work together (...)."</p> <p>"The offline test module uses the database (DB) we built to conduct local tests for the purpose of evaluating whether the function is complete and checking whether there are obvious bugs. The online test module is the actual driving environment test."</p> <p>"Offline testing is divided into four sub-tasks to ensure the reliability of the evaluation. These four modules are evaluated from three evaluation directions. Firstly, the early warning effect test is performed to verify the final result of the autonomous driving system. Secondly, evaluation of tracking algorithm effect, evaluation of detection algorithm, and evaluation of classification algorithm effect are fine-grained effect evaluations. Finally, the algorithm stability evaluation guarantees the comprehensiveness and stability of the evaluation."</p> <p>"Online testing ensures consistency between the R&D and actual application scenarios through conformance testing and guarantees actual functional experience through time-consuming testing and online stability testing."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) the evaluation schemes mentioned are analyzed with practical tests. Besides this, the big data set has a total of 400,000 test images, covering driving scenes in different weather, different light, different seasons, and different road conditions."</p> <p>"The experimental results on real datasets indicate that our proposed evaluation system has achieved effective results."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not identified / analyzed.</p> <p>Future work: " In the future, user big data management and AI technology will be further developed to improve the automation of the evaluation system.""</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Some parameters for the offline V&V are set too conservatively (e.g., at least 50% precision). 2) Some of the obtained results on the case study are too unsafe (e.g., recall < 30%, indicating a high rate of

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 404 / 550	

	false non-detection of obstacles), yet the authors deemed these to be appropriate. 3) The proposed approach does not deal with the challenges of certifying AI for safety-critical systems. Tests are generated without the assurance that they suffice for safety assurance.
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8.297 REFERENCE [896]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "propose DRL-GAT-SA (Deep Reinforcement Learning - Graph Attention - Simplex Architecture) to achieve safe and efficient autonomous driving, which is a new runtime assurance approach".
Q2 Answer	Deep learning; reinforcement learning, online learning, neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>Restrictions of the simplex architecture: "Although simplex architectures are a very useful framework for safety assurance, however, there are still significant challenges in studying them in complex real-world situations, especially when it is applied to autonomous driving environments. First of all, in the traditional simplex structure, the advanced controller has a black box characteristic, and there is no technology to correct it when it generates a potentially unsafe action leading to control switching to the safety controller. Secondly, existing technologies do not provide a principled, safe switching logic for the driving system, so that the control can be switched back and forth between the advanced controller and the safety controller, to ensure safety while reducing the performance loss as much as possible. Finally, although the traditional simplex structure can provide safety, it may be difficult to design a high-performance advanced controller in a complex driving environment."</p> <p>"DRL-GAT-SA architecture (...) is a new runtime assurance approach for complex dynamic scenarios that provides safety assurances for graph attention reinforcement learning (GARL) controllers without unduly sacrificing efficiency. We first design an intelligent and efficient GARL. The safety field model is used to evaluate the driving safety attributes, and the vehicles with driving risks are constructed as a dynamic graph to identify which agents the vehicle needs to interact with. Then a soft attention model is trained to learn the importance weights on each edge in the graph, and then all the feature vectors are connected and fed into the RL learning algorithm to output the actions. When the vehicle is about to leave the status safety zone, the decision module(DM) switches control from the highly efficient but unverified safety GARL to the verified safe controller (SC). At the same time, the framework retrains the GARL controller so that it is less likely to repeat the same or similar errors, allowing it to maintain more control over the system. The safety field model also provides a provably safe switching logic for DM to switch between GARL controller and SC controller, to make a trade-off between safety and efficiency."</p> <p>"(...) we propose a safety framework based on graph- attentive network interaction representation (DRL-GAT-SA), which consists of three key modules: 1- High-performance but unverified [safe] graph-attentive reinforcement learning controller (GARL), 2- verifiable [safe] controller (SC), and 3- decision module (DM). First GARL obtains driving state information, generates policy pi-theta and outputs the action. If a greater risk of driving develops, the DM switches control from GARL to SC, uses the policy pi-H output action, and seeks to eliminate the unsafe policy exhibited by GARL without degrading performance, ensuring that the DM is confident that it will not make the same mistake after switching control back to GARL. To meet the above considerations, the DRL-GAT-SA must implement the following features: (1) It must switch to the safety controller(SC) whenever the vehicle leaves the state safety area; (2) It should provide an effective trade-off between safety and efficiency. To do this, it must be able to determine exactly when a vehicle is likely to leave the state safety zone and whether it is in the state safety zone and perform switching between controllers only when needed. (3) SC decisions must be verifiable, avoiding black box models like deep neural networks which are difficult to verify. In this work, the decision module (DM) is an important part of the framework, which needs to evaluate the safety of the vehicle state space and select control commands from the graph attention reinforcement learning (GARL) controller pi-theta and SC controller pi-H according to the evaluation results. GARL controllers are expected to perform driving tasks effectively and constantly update and optimize their policies, but their reliability is uncertain. The SC controller is a highly reliable controller that can maintain driving stability in a known domain of the vehicle state space. To achieve this, we should accept that the SC controller may be inefficient in performing driving tasks. If the GARL controller drives the vehicle to an unsafe state in the process of controlling the vehicle, it means that there may be an error in the controller, it will be taken back, the control will be taken over by the SC controller, and the GARL will be upgraded and trained. When the SC controller is working, the DM can restore the control of the GARL to the vehicle according to the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 405 / 550	

	vehicle safety state assessment. Such a process can be repeated during vehicle operation training to achieve a satisfactory level of vehicle safety and efficiency."
Q4 Answer	<p>"We evaluate the performance of DRL-GAT-SA and GARL in two driving scenarios at highway and roundabout, respectively, and compare them with the existing baselines."</p> <p>"The highway driving environment consists of four roads in the same direction, the roundabout consists of a circular road and three two-way lanes, and randomly initializes the position, speed, and destination of several traffic participants (...)."</p> <p>"(...) we can see that each policy converges to an optimal policy interval in the highway environment, and the total reward and episode length of each episode gradually increases with the increase of training times, until the convergence tends to a stable state."</p> <p>"(...) the four policies have achieved the best performance of the algorithm itself after 12 000 episodes of training. The policy learned by DDQN in this environment is more aggressive and relatively too fast, and cannot effectively avoid accidents. GARL, DGN, and DRL-GAT-SA algorithms can use the interrelationship between vehicles to decide whether to give way, accelerate to avoid or give priority to other vehicles, obtain longer episode lengths, effectively reducing the occurrence of accidents and greatly improving vehicle safety. Overall, our DRL-GAT-SA algorithm architecture produces better results in every driving scenario environment, enabling the ego car to maintain a safe distance from other vehicles, providing driving safety for the vehicle, effectively avoiding collisions, and producing behavior that is more nuanced in quality and more like human decision making."</p> <p>"(...) we can see that the overall performance of GARL and DRL-GAT-SA is the best, and GARL can fully utilize the information from other vehicles for efficient driving. The DRL-GAT-SA model pursues safer decisions with some loss in driving speed, but the overall reward is the best and the model has a longer driving time."</p>
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Good example of the simplex architecture to provide safety for AI-based systems. It has been augmented with safe reinforcement learning.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Some parts of the model are very application-specific.</p>

8.298 REFERENCE [898]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To develop a means for guaranteeing the safe operation of AI-enabled systems with formal methods.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks and reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	"A 2019 independent research and development project, called A ModelPlex Approach to a Verified Robotics Code Kit (MAVeRiCK), extended research for verifying aircraft collision avoidance to create a correct-by-construction fallback controller design that ensures collision-free path planning The fallback controller ensures safety by taking over from the primary controller whenever a critical state is reached and a particular action must be taken to avoid an imminent collision. This project resulted in a research paper detailing how formally verified safety predicates are used to create a fallback controller with safety guarantees. Furthermore, the work contributed to a library for formal verification of timing computations for turn to bearing maneuvers. This approach to verifying the safety of vehicle navigation is being applied in a larger Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL)-funded effort for the subtask of creating a verified runtime assurance watchdog controller to ensure the safe testing of autonomous aircraft systems; for example, through guaranteeing the watchdog predictively enforce a vehicles stays within the planned test range geofence."
Q4 Answer	"(...) the team recognized that in a number of situations the fallback control architecture may lead to problematic performance of mission objectives. (...) As a result, APL began an effort called Verified Safe Reinforcement Learning (VSRL) to study alternative approaches for ensuring the safe performance of

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 406 / 550

	<p>continually adaptive deep learning systems. The project sought to provide direct guarantees on the performance of a neural network controller trained to avoid collisions with other aircraft while minimizing deviations from the goal. In general, providing guarantees on the outputs of neural networks over the continuous space of potential inputs is too difficult, due to the complex mapping from input to outputs that neural networks embody. The team found promise in a methodology for the encoding of affine networks that may be verified with SMT tools. In 2020, VSRL aimed to demonstrate this approach in the training and verification of small rectified linear unit networks trained to perform path planning or control tasks; creating a library for automatic encoding of pytorch networks into SMT constraints.</p> <p>In addition, the team discovered a method for adjusting the weights of a neural network using an SMT solver to guarantee certain input-output relationships. (...) The effort culminated in a demonstration of the verification of a reinforcement learning network trained to avoid aircraft collisions through the use of safeability concepts to reduce the domain of inputs that must be checked to verify the safety of a neural network controller. This research will enable the design of future systems that can take advantage of machine learning advances as well as formal approaches to guaranteeing safe performance."</p>
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <p>1) Safe reinforcement learning scheme. Work-in-progress futuere published in [748].</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) The paper is a work-in-progress report of the research that has been ultimately published in [748]. Hence, it does not provide in-depth analyses nor finished results.</p>

8.299 REFERENCE [900]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "study the problem of how to safeguard the learning-based lane changing controller for collision avoidance" by leveraging "on the runtime assurance framework, in particular the Simplex architecture to bound the behavior of the learning-based controller and to provide safety guarantees".
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning.
Q3 Answer	<p>Motivation: "Conventional verification and validation process as suggested by the ISO 26262 standard for road vehicles can be hardly applied to these learning-enabled systems. First, the requirements of learning-based components are implicitly encoded in the training data. Formally specifying the requirements that are needed for safety verification is still a challenging problem. Second, the existing verification techniques suffer from the scalability problem due to the high complexity and nonlinearity of learning-based components. Third, the behaviors of learning-based components are emerging over time and can be hardly characterized at design time. Safety verification at design time cannot always guarantee safety at runtime."</p> <p>"Instead of performing the safety verification at design time, we leverage on a runtime assurance approach to provide safety guarantee for the systems encompassing learning-based controllers. In particular, we build our approach on top of the Simplex architecture (...). (...) we show how Simplex architecture can be used to safeguard the learning-based lane changing controller for autonomous vehicles, in particular, the longitudinal controller based on reinforcement learning that we have proposed (...)."</p> <p>"One of the key challenges of applying Simplex architecture is to properly design the decision module that can guarantee safe switching between different controllers. Lyapunov functions have been initially used to compute the switching conditions. However, they mainly work for purely continuous systems. Later on, hybrid automaton has been used (...) to model the Simplex architecture, and the switching conditions can be synthesized by using reachability analysis of the hybrid automaton. (...) proposes a unified framework that combines the Lyapunov function with a real-time reachability method. Intuitively, the Lyapunov function is used for the switching condition computation when it is available. Otherwise, a real-time reachability method is applied to check safety. They further show that the reachability computation can be performed efficiently without relying on dynamic memory allocation or other sophisticated libraries. Another approach to computing the switching conditions is to use barrier certificates (BaCs), which is widely used for safety verification of hybrid systems, especially for some IoT scenarios."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 407 / 550	

	"The switching logic can be described by a finite state automaton (...). The locations represent the two working modes of the decision module. When the decision module is in the SC mode (i.e., the safety controller is used), and the ego vehicle stays in the recoverable region (...), then the learning-based complex controller can be safely activated in the next control cycle. The decision module stays in the CC mode until there is a possibility of leaving the recoverable region in a near future (...). Otherwise, it moves back to the SC mode and switches on the safety controller."
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we evaluate the proposed runtime assured controller in a highway scenario using the SUMO simulator. The highway is composed of three straight lanes with a length of 2 km, and a random traffic flow with variable volumes is created surrounding the ego vehicle in the highway. In total, we consider three different volumes of traffic flow per hour, i.e., 1,000, 1,500 and 2,000. The ego vehicle is controlled by our proposed controller, while all the surrounding vehicles in the traffic flow are controlled by the Intelligent Driving Model, which is a built-in functionality in SUMO."</p> <p>"We have implemented two versions of the reinforcement learning-based lane changing controller, that is one with Simplex-based safety assurance denoted by RL+Safety and one without Simplex-based safety assurance denoted by RL."</p> <p>"Safety is evaluated by checking whether the ego vehicle collides with the vehicles ahead when performing lane changing. (...) The second metric is to evaluate the traveling performance. (...) The third metric is to evaluate the road occupancy. (...) The fourth metric is about passenger comfort, which is measured in two aspects. One is the number of lane changes and the other is the variation of acceleration."</p> <p>"We show experimentally that our approach ensures both safety and high efficiency evaluated in terms of three criteria, i.e., the traveling performance, the road occupancy and the passenger comfort. The simulation results confirm the feasibility and the practical relevance of runtime assurance approach for safeguarding the behaviors of learning-based controllers."</p>
Q5 Answer	Future work: "As the future work, we would like to investigate the possible extensions to the industrial IoT systems, and the blockchain-based systems."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Safe reinforcement learning based on the simplex architecture. 2) Good details on how to develop the safe controller and proving its safety. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No justification on the applicability of the chosen hyperparameters.

8.300 REFERENCE [905]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "present OVERT: a sound algorithm for safety verification of nonlinear discrete-time closed loop dynamical systems with neural network control policies".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we develop an algorithm to prove or disprove safety properties of nonlinear discrete-time dynamical systems with deep neural network control policies."</p> <p>"We present OVERT: a method to reason about nonlinear discrete-time closed-loop systems that contain neural network control policies. OVERT overapproximates nonlinear dynamical systems using piecewise-linear relations, making the entire closed-loop system a conjunction of piecewise-linear relations. The resultant system of piecewise-linear relations can be efficiently reasoned about using ReLU neural network verification tools. The main features of our work can be summarized as follows: i) The use of an overapproximation makes our algorithm sound; a proof of no counterexamples for the approximation implies no counterexamples for the original system. ii) The algorithm provides an optimally tight formulation to overapproximate a nonlinear system with a piecewise linear counterpart. iii) Our formulation is amenable to use with various neural network verification tools (...). iv) We prove bounded-time safety properties for the closed-loop system by unrolling the system in time. Reachability queries can be solved directly as feasibility problems or by explicitly computing the reachable set. Neither approach requires gridding the state space which can lead to exponentially many sub-problems. v) The use of hybrid-symbolic reachable set computation preserves both tightness of the reachable</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 408 / 550

	<p>set and tractability of its computation."</p> <p>"The methods developed here (...) have either no explicit dependence on the number of state variables or only linear dependence. All methods presented mitigate the wrapping effect by preserving a symbolic representation across multiple timesteps."</p> <p>"OVERT solves reachability problems, meaning it reasons about the set of states reachable over time and whether this set of states intersects with an unsafe set or reaches a goal set. One way to frame the reachability problem is to explicitly compute the reachable set of the closed-loop system."</p> <p>"Another way to frame the reachability problem is by solving what we call feasibility problems. Feasibility problems can directly encode the unsafe set (complement of the safe set) and return SAT indicating that the unsafe set is reachable or UNSAT indicating that the unsafe set is not reachable, without explicitly computing the reachable set.</p> <p>OVERT can solve reachability problems using either an explicit reachable set computation framing or a feasibility framing, and these two approaches are often complementary. Since reachable sets are typically overapproximated by simple geometric shapes such as hyperrectangles or polytopes, reachable set computation introduces some looseness into the approximation. Conversely, solving feasibility problems incurs less looseness and less wrapping effect because the reachable set is instead represented implicitly. Consequently, solving feasibility problems results in fewer spurious counter examples and allows more properties to be proven. However, computing reachable sets provides intuition about the the evolution of the system and allow the reachability problem to remain tractable over long time horizons."</p> <p>"In order to keep the problem computationally tractable, and yet obtain a reasonably accurate reachable set, we employ a hybrid approach, where concretization is performed only when the reachable set begins to get too large."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we demonstrate application of OVERT to a number of benchmark examples. (...) we have chosen four classical control systems (...)."</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Single Pendulum (S) 2) "TORA (T): This example is a model for rotational actuators. TORA stands for Translation Oscillations of a Rotational Actuator. The system consists of a cart that can roll along a frictionless surface and is attached to the wall by a spring. Inside the cart, there is a mass on a rod that can rotate to actuate the cart. The state may be described by the x-displacement of the cart and the angular displacement of the rotational actuator." 3) "Car (C): This example uses a kinematic bicycle model to approximate car dynamics. The state of the system may be described by the position of the car, as well as the yaw angle and speed." 4) "Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC): This system models an adaptive cruise control policy for a car on a highway. The system has a target velocity, but there is a lead vehicle ahead of the ego vehicle, and the ego must maintain a safe distance from the lead vehicle. The neural network control policy adjusts the longitudinal acceleration of the ego vehicle." <p>"Each benchmark example contains nonlinearities that are overapproximated. (...) On one hand, as n increases, the overapproximation gets tighter. On the other hand, this overapproximation requires more binary variables in the mixed integer representation. Interestingly, we experimentally observe that increasing the number of binary variables by increasing n does not immediately make the MIP problem harder to solve. In other words, in our experiments, the MIP program was significantly more sensitive to number of binary variables originating from the neural network, and less so to those originating from the abstraction of the dynamics."</p> <p>"Our experiments on a proof of concept implementation demonstrate that OVERT outperforms naive adaptations of existing tools for use with nonlinear discrete-time closed-loop systems with neural network control policies in both tightness of computed reachable sets and speed of computation."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Future work: "For the experiments that were run here, we ran initial explorations for each problem and then manually chose a concrete vs. symbolic unroll schedule. We leave the task of automatically picking an unroll schedule for a given problem for future work."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Very well written paper, including several mathematical proof and basis to support the soundness of the method as likely state-of-the-art in formal verification of ANNs. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No analysis of faults within the AI.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 409 / 550	

8.301 REFERENCE [906]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To build" a support tool for ophthalmologists able to: (i) explain algorithmic decision to the human agent by automatically extracting rules from the ML learned models; (ii) include the ophthalmologist in the loop by formalising expert rules and including the expert knowledge in the argumentation machinery; (iii) build safety cases by creating assurance argument patterns for each diagnosis."
Q2 Answer	Decision trees, support vector machines, neural networks, explainable AI, knowledge-based systems ("expert rule-based agent").
Q3 Answer	<p>"We developed a diagnosis system for retinal conditions. We designed the system to meet the following requirements:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To explain algorithmic decision to the human agent by automatically extracting rules from the black box ML algorithms. 2. To include the ophthalmologist in the loop by formalising expert rules and including the expert knowledge in the argumentation machinery. 3. To build safety cases by creating assurance argument patterns for each diagnosis." <p>"We propose an argumentation-based decision function after receiving results from three ML classifiers and one expert agent. This expert agent contains rules manually formalised from normative data for retina (...). Interleaving knowledge extracted from ML-models with expert knowledge is a step towards balancing the benefits of ML with explainability, aiming at engineering reliable medical applications."</p> <p>"We applied our machinery on distinguishing between three classes: normal retina, Diabetic Retinopathy (DR), and Age Related Macular Degeneration (AMD). We chose DR and AMD because both diseases: (i) are highly prevalent; (ii) produce changes in the macular area; (iii) benefit from an early diagnosis and treatment: if detected early, we could prevent severe vision loss; (iv) modify the volume and the thickness of the macular retina."</p> <p>"The challenge remains to extract rules from more black-box models like SVM and ANN. (...) To transform the algorithm's parameters space into the input space, we use the Rule Matrix tool."</p> <p>"(...) the multi-agent system consists of six agents: three agents have rules learned from machine learning: the DT agent, the ANN agent, and the SVM agent. The expert agent has rules manually formalised from normative datasets on retina. These four agents are called argumentative agents, since they exchange arguments based on their own perspective on the current patient. The master agent handles the conflict resolution among arguments and generates explanations. The ophthalmologist agent provides new cases for diagnosis."</p> <p>"The Master agent employs different conflict resolution strategies: voting, weighed voting, strongest-argument. These strategies take into consideration three components: number of supporting arguments (i.e. majority vote), confidence in the argument, or the performance metric of the learning process."</p> <p>"The master agent explains the diagnosis to the ophthalmologist by means of arguments obtained from the arguing agents. These rule-based arguments are verbalised (...). Verbalising rules is based in our approach on linguistic patterns, such as: The patient has the diagnosis D because the volume/avg thickness value for retina zone Zn is larger/smaller than value X. The master agent displays also the confidence of the supporting arguments conveyed by the agent."</p>
Q4 Answer	The authors have presented some results of their proposed method throughout its definition. The results corroborate that the objective of obtaining explainable rules for the assessed diseases, along with a degree of confidence on such results, has been achieved.
Q5 Answer	"Each module of this architecture can be further improved: First, the set of training algorithms that we used (DT, SVM, or ANN) can be extended. For each new learning algorithm, an arguing agent will be enacted. Its arguments are processed by the argumentation machinery which takes a decision and explain it. This flexibility of the multi-agent system to accommodate new agents without architectural alteration of the system is important given that new ML-based are developing fast. Note that, for each new learned model, one needs to include also the mechanism to extract rules. Second, the quantity of data used can be improved. (...) Third, the safety cases should be better generated based on some certification procedure. The challenge is that these certification processes, including the corresponding certification centers and regulatory sandboxes, are only

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 410 / 550	

	now developing."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Interesting and practical application of explainable AI on safety-critical systems.</p> <p>Weaknesses: 1) No evidence that the pre-processed dataset is indeed adequate for the end application. 2) Partitioning of the input dataset in training, validation and test sets is arbitrary. Not justified whether the percentages are appropriate for the end application. 3) Safety arguments have not been explored beyond the explainability features the authors proposed (e.g., no inclusion of fault-related behavior nor a quantitative assessment on the performance metrics).</p>

8.302 REFERENCE [920]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To "discuss what becomes difficult or even impossible in the use of arguments or assurance cases for machine learning based systems" and "propose an approach for continuously analyzing, managing, and updating arguments while accepting uncertainty as intrinsic in nature."
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Goals regarding ML often deal with infinite possibilities in the real world or fuzzy human perceptions. We try to define more concrete, measurable sub-goals for such goals, but it is intrinsically difficult to claim that they are exhaustive and sufficient. New sub-goals may be discovered, or the significance of sub-goals may be more precisely recognized only after a system is faced with a variety of users and environments during the test phase or even the operation phase. In addition, decomposition can be invalidated by changes in external elements (user requirements and environments)."</p> <p>"We propose the following concepts and principles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explicitly distinguish open goals whose decomposition has high uncertainty intrinsically and is thus likely to be incomplete or volatile. An additional notation for this kind of goal should be introduced to GSN extensions. - For open goals, a continuous decomposition sub-goal (CD sub-goal) should be considered to ensure that acceptably sufficient effort is taken to discover new sub-goals and validate existing ones. This will make a new GSN pattern. - Empirical data obtained as solutions or evidences for continuous decomposition goals should be continuously updated and linked to arguments. (...) - For sub-goals of an open goal, except for a CD sub-goal, justification should be given by using empirical data requested by the CD sub-goal. Tools should support the easy tracing of data that justify each sub-goal. (...) - Explicitly distinguish a soft contribution (isSupportedBy relationship) that denotes that an evidence can contribute to increasing confidence regarding goal satisfaction but cannot ensure it. An additional notation for this kind of relationship should be introduced to GSN extensions. - Goals and evidences should explicitly mention the attributes of test data, e.g., foggy situations, so that stakeholders can understand and validate in what sense and how sufficiently tests are done. Arguments should be linked to a tool for test data management to allow for continuous checks between test requirements and used test data sets. This requires good integration with tools for test data management, which have not been sufficiently investigated for ML yet, to the authors' knowledge. (...) - Explicitly distinguish fragile goals whose validity and satisfaction depend on changeable assumptions or justifications, typically regarding the real world. - Empirical data obtained as solutions or evidences for fragile goals should be continuously updated and linked to arguments. This is already discussed for CD sub-goals. In the case of fragile goals, monitoring of satisfaction is much more significant as satisfaction of a goal, ensured well at the design time, may be broken at runtime."
Q4 Answer	The main results are the recommended concepts and principles presented in the answer to Question 3.
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed / identified.</p> <p>Future work: "Our next step is to conduct industrial case studies and to provide concrete implementations of the proposed support in the form of notations and tools."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 411 / 550	

Q6 Answer	<p>Strenghts: 1) Good general practice on incorporating uncertainty to the safety assurance of ML-based systems.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) Despite most of the recommended practice being general-purpose - hence applicable to several applications - they lack sufficient detail and require further developments. 2) The authors have not discussed on means to quantify and propagate uncertainty on ML-related models.</p>
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8.303 REFERENCE [921]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "propose a safety standard approach for fully autonomous vehicles based on setting scope requirements for an overarching safety case", including "(...) feedback paths to ensure that both the safety case and the standard itself co-evolve with the technology and accumulated experience" and "an external assessment process to ensure lessons learned are captured, as well as to ensure transparency".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"A standard must address at least: • Use of Machine Learning (ML) technology. A significant advantage of using ML is using a training-based approach to resolve intractable design situations. However, that same lack of requirements impedes traceability and ability to do design reviews. • Use of unpredictable algorithms. Randomized algorithms and other so-called Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques tend to behave in an unpredictable way, generally characterized as being non-deterministic. This complicates creating repeatable tests."</p> <p>"(...) the standard can require that all hazards and associated risks be identified, but not what techniques must be used to accomplish that."</p> <p>"At a high level, we have identified the following topics that must be specifically addressed for HAVs beyond the level of detail in other standards: • Definition of Operational Design Domain (e.g., weather, scenarios) • Machine learning faults (e.g. training data gaps, brittleness) • External operational faults (e.g., other vehicles violating traffic rules) • Faulty behavior by non-driver humans (e.g., pedestrians, lifecycle participants) • Non-deterministic, variable system behavior (e.g., test planning, acceptance criteria) • High residual unknowns (e.g., requirements gaps and post-deployment surprises) • Lack of human oversight (e.g., operational fault handling, passenger handling) • System-level safety metrics (e.g., use of leading and lagging metrics) • Transitioning the system to degraded modes and minimum risk conditions."</p> <p>"(...) it is important to continually evaluate and improve the residual risk present in the system. Identifying latent and emergent risks is essential to enable identifying, implementing, and verifying additional mitigation measures. By the same token, it is important to address known safety issues before exposing testers and the public to undue safety risk. (...) Honest self-assessment and iteration over the system development and deployment lifecycle is vitally important to mature the safety case."</p> <p>"We also believe that independent assessment is essential. (...) independent assessment can provide a way to share lessons learned without revealing proprietary design details."</p> <p>"(...) we plan to evolve the standard in tandem with the technology. Here is how we believe it can work: • Seed the initial standard with required essential practices and anti-patterns that have proven value (e.g., identifying hazards, avoiding known unsafe design patterns) based on stakeholder inputs. • Require essential elements of the safety case (e.g., pick and adapt any reasonable hazard analysis approach from your favorite safety standard). • Include a list of safety case acceptable patterns and excluded anti-patterns. Require plausible argumentation that residual risk and "unknowns" will be tracked. • Require feedback paths based on root cause analysis of incidents and loss events during both development and deployment to identify weak spots in the process:</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 412 / 550	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gaps in enumerated lists in the safety case (e.g., a new hazard) - Gaps in safety case evidence (e.g., an “impossible” failure occurs in the field) - Flaws in argumentation and assumptions (e.g., real world assumption violations) - Gaps in patterns, anti-patterns, and required elements in the safety standard itself - Adoption of new practices that have proven to provide value into the standard."
Q4 Answer	The main results are the recommended concepts and principles presented in the answer to Question 3.
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Relevant insight on themes worthy of consideration on standards for AI-based safety-critical systems (UL4600 team). 2) Despite the focus on highly automated vehicles, several of the recommendations provided within the paper are valid for other types of systems. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) When affirming that the standard shall be technology-agnostic w.r.t. assurance techniques, unexperienced practitioners are left without potential recommended practice that they should follow. Further research on this is still highly needed. 2) Incorrect claim that IEC61508:2010 is only valid for chemical control systems.

8.304 REFERENCE [922]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To present "a comprehensive and methodological analysis of the safety hazards that could be introduced along the ML lifecycle, and could compromise the safe operation of ML-based CPS"
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Despite very considerable advances in selected areas related to machine learning safety, shortcomings were identified on holistic approaches that take an end-to-end view on the risks associated to the engineering of ML-based control systems and their certification."</p> <p>"The aim of our study is two-fold: (1) supporting the identification of sources for potential hazardous behavior in the machine learning lifecycle, detailing how it can affect the overall system and illustrating it with an example scenario; (2) establishing the basis for a future definition of a coherent framework to integrate hazards analysis and verification techniques, along with mitigation mechanisms (detection and removal), towards the ultimate goal of the standardization of the development process of safety-critical ML-based systems."</p> <p>"To properly address the safety of machine learning systems, one has to implement the rigorous processes prescribed in functional safety, and utilize both: safety strategies known from conventional systems development, and safety strategies developed specifically for machine learning systems. The challenge here is to bridge the gap between the traditional defensive, risk-averse, and rigorous functional safety culture, and the opportunity-oriented, technology-focused culture still dominating in machine learning. In this paper, we aim to contribute to connecting these seemingly antagonistic views by identifying the hazards and related failure mechanisms that may potentially lead to unsafe behavior of machine-learning-controlled CPS, thereby providing a stable basis for identifying applicable safety strategies addressing each one of these hazards."</p> <p>"Commonly, the ML lifecycle is divided into five main phases: Requirements, Data Management, Model Development, Model Testing and Verification, and Model Deployment (...)."</p> <p>Requirements: "(...) high level requirements can be explicitly defined but the low level ones are given implicitly when specifying the dataset (the characteristics of which are defined in the Requirements phase and are implemented during the DataManagement phase). Without explicit low level requirements, the traditional traceability-based assurance approach—linking high-level to low-level requirements, and low-level requirements to implementation—cannot be applied. On the other hand, even if there would be explicit low-level requirements it would be hard to trace them into the implementation, telling which elements of the machine learning algorithm and which of its parameters contribute to implementing a specific lowlevel requirement."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 413 / 550	

	<p>Hazards: Incomplete definition of data, Incomplete definition of data, Inadequate performance measure, Incompleteness on testing/verification, Inadequate safe operating values.</p> <p>Data Management: "The Data Management phase is responsible for acquiring meaningful data for the machine learning model to be able to make predictions on future data. The inputs of this stage are the set of requirements that the application has to achieve, and the outputs are composed by the training and test datasets, to serve as inputs for the Model Development and Model Testing and Verification phases, respectively. For producing such datasets, this phase focuses on four different activities: data collection, data annotation, data preprocessing, and data augmentation."</p> <p>Hazards: Inadequate distribution, Insufficient dataset size, Bias, Irrelevance, Irrelevance.</p> <p>Model Management: "This phase is responsible for training a model based on the training dataset given by the Data Management phase, reproducing the correct relationship between inputs and outputs. The trained model will then be given to the next phase for its verification and testing. The Model Development phase is composed of a set of decisions related to models and parameters, and also by the training part of the ML model development process."</p> <p>Hazards: Model mismatch, Bias, (Hyper) Parameters mismatch, Performance measure mismatch, Error rate, Lack of interpretability.</p> <p>Model Testing and Verification: "The Model Testing and Verification phase is responsible for evaluating the trained model on a dataset that was never seen during the training phase, in order to see how the model generalizes to new input data. To design reliable systems, engineers engage in both testing and verification. At the end of this phase, a verified model and a verification result should be provided to the next phase containing sufficient information to allow potential users to decide if the model is suitable for the intended application. The importance of the Model Testing and Verification phase is enhanced if its results provide information that supports the correction of errors (e.g., a testing or verification requirement is not fulfilled and points to a process that needs to be improved, for example, more data needs to be collected).</p> <p>Hazards: Incompleteness, Non-representative distribution.</p> <p>Model Deployment: "The Model Deployment phase receives as input a verified model that is ready to be deployed into a target platform. The outcome of this phase is a fully deployed and operating real-world system."</p> <p>Hazards: Differences in computation platforms, Differences in computation platforms, Non detection of potentially incorrect outputs, New data/Continuous learning.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we select an example based on a self-driving vehicle that operates in factories and warehouses sharing transportation routes and tasks with human workers. Recent research shows an increasing interest in the use of machine learning algorithms for self driving vehicles inside factories."</p> <p>The authors illustrate the activities and potential hazards for this example throughout the text.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"We believe that our work is a step forward into future holistic approaches for safety engineering and certification of ML-based systems, supporting the research community to identify remaining gaps regarding product- or process-related measures that are required to ensure the proper functioning of ML-based CPS in safety-critical applications."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Very relevant and well-structured process for the safety assurance of AI-based systems. Good taxonomy of hazards and plausible activities.</p> <p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) No remarks regarding the analysis of faults except for an indirect mention that 'classic safety assurance' shall still be performed along with AI-specific one.</p>

8.305 REFERENCE [923]

Q-Index	3
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 414 / 550

Q1 Answer	To "propose an augmented barrier certificate-based method for formally verifying the approximate initial-state opacity property of discrete time control systems".
Q2 Answer	Deep neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we present a novel barrier certificate-based method for formally verifying the approximate initial-state opacity of discrete-time control systems. First, we suggest a new type of augmented barrier certificate which can produce a weaker sufficient condition for the approximate initial-state opacity. (...) Usually, a weaker condition for the augmented barrier certificate means that more augmented barrier certificates can be synthesized, as the expressiveness of the augmented barrier certificates is stronger.</p> <p>We then suggest an algorithmic framework for synthesizing augmented barrier certificates in the form of neural networks. Our framework (...) consists of two modules. The learner trains a neural augmented barrier certificate that satisfies the barrier certificate conditions over a set of sampled data, and the verifier solves a mixed integer linear program (MILP) to either ensure the validity of the candidate augmented barrier certificate or yield counterexamples, which are passed back to further guide the learner. The loop is repeated until a trained candidate augmented barrier certificate is successfully verified."</p> <p>"(...) the procedure is structured as an inductive loop between a learner and a verifier. At first, we present a less conservative augmented barrier certificate for the validation of approximate initial-state opacity. Then, the learner trains the certificate functions simultaneously over sampled data points from the initial set, the unsafe set, and the state space. After that, the trained candidates are formally verified by the verifier (...) Due to the structure of ReLU neural networks, the verification problem can be transformed into a set of efficiently solvable MILP problems."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We have implemented an augmented barrier certificate synthesis tool (...) using the Pytorch 1.7 platform and Gurobi 9.5. We apply our tool to verify a number of benchmark examples from the literature comprising both polynomial and non-polynomial dynamics (...)"</p> <p>Three different examples of vehicle motion models were exercised. For all of them, barrier certificates were synthesized.</p>
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <p>1) Another of many examples for verifying safety using barrier certificates.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Even though verifying neural networks is a precondition for synthesizing barrier certificates, assessing AI was not the focus of the research.</p> <p>2) No remarks on the analysis of faults.</p>

8.306 REFERENCE [925]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "present a situation coverage-based (SitCov) AV-testing framework for the verification and validation (V&V) and safety assurance of AVs, developed in an open-source AV simulator named CARLA".
Q2 Answer	Deep neural networks, convolutional neural networks (case study); artificial intelligence in general (assumed by the authors).
Q3 Answer	The authors have developed means to automatically generate black-box test cases for autonomous vehicles. No specificities on AI have been explored on the method itself; AI is assumed to be a black box.
Q4 Answer	<p>The authors have illustrated their test generation method by means of a case study in which an autonomous vehicle is controlled by deep and convolutional neural networks.</p> <p>"We use seeded faults to evaluate our SitCov AV-testing frame. The process starts with us seeding a few faults in the ego AV software, and when the ego AV crashes in the OV, we say that the seeded fault has been triggered."</p> <p>"(...) our experiments suggest that the fault revealing capabilities of our SitCov AV-testing framework vs random generation is more or less the same."</p> <p>"(...) the results produced by the SitCov AV-testing framework are much more convincing than random situation generation, because the results produced by the SitCov AV-testing framework provide additional</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 415 / 550

	confidence in the failure rates as the situation coverage-based situation generation of our SitCov AV-testing framework make sure that the situation hyperspace is efficiently covered while also making sure that in case of repetitions of situations, we have an even distribution of repetitions rather than highly varying distributions of situations as seen for random situation generation."
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "(...) our experiments suggest that the fault revealing capabilities of our SitCov AV-testing framework vs random generation is more or less the same."</p> <p>Future work: "For the future work, we have made our SitCov AV-testing framework really expandable such that many more axis can be added in the situation hyperspace and a lot more dynamic obstacles can be added in the simulation runs instead of just V2V interactions that is currently being done. So, we recommend that the situation hyperspace be expanded more with additional axis, e.g., adding different kinds of roads, adding diverging and merging collisions instead of only cross-collisions with OV, adding pedestrians and cyclists, etc. We also recommend making use of the failure rate of situations and using that information to skew the generation of next batch of situations in the direction of situation elements that were causing more failure (high failure rate), which can be done using the same mechanism we have developed for doing situation coverage-based situation generation for our SitCov AV-testing framework. Similarly, machine learning can also be added in our SitCov AV-testing framework to generate more interesting situations, i.e., edge-cases, by learning the patterns of combinations of environmental conditions and intersection situations that cause the highest failure rates in the results of our SitCov AV-testing framework test-cases."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <p>1) Example of black-box testing applicable to autonomous vehicles.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) Too application-specific. 2) Little emphasis on AI.</p>

8.307 REFERENCE [934]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To "evaluate how embedded artificial intelligence – machine learning can affect the safety of machinery and machinery systems in the development of new applications", as it "describes how the hazards (...) should be considered within the framework of the risk assessment process".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	"(...) the focus is on the use of embedded AI in the machinery sector that is developing for different application of advanced systems making the smarter decision. The main processes involved are the optimization of process parameters, the monitoring of the health machine conditions, predictive maintenance and fault detection."
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) machines equipped with machine learning must not be able to carry out tasks or assessments that go beyond those defined by the manufacturer for the purpose of the machine. Moreover, when AI is replacing conventional systems that perform a safety function, whether they are safety components independently placed on the market or homemade by the machinery manufacturer, the level of performance required must be tested and validated taking account both of the hardware and software aspects of such systems"</p> <p>"When safety functions are performed by an AI algorithm, other problems are generated related to connectivity as it feeds on data from different devices and sensors. This, in turn, implies exposure to cybersecurity risks that must be treated appropriately in the reviewed framework of the risk assessment process for intelligent machines."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed.</p> <p>Future work: "(...) a Risk Assessment 4.0 will be developed by considering the new technologies and the continuous monitoring and data acquisition."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Very superficial study with little impact on technical safety of AI-based systems.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 416 / 550	

8.308 REFERENCE [935]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "propose the use of a real-time reachability algorithm for the implementation of such an architecture [the simplex architecture] for the safety assurance of a 1/10 scale open source autonomous vehicle platform known as F1/10".
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning, neural networks (imitation learning / knowledge-based systems).
Q3 Answer	<p>"Utilizing a "black-box" model within a system that is safety-critical constitutes the highest form of technical debt and, as a result, the last several years have witnessed a significant increase in the development of techniques that seek to reason about the safety and robustness of machine learning methods."</p> <p>Simplex architecture: "The key challenge in this regime is to design a switching logic that allows the dynamic capabilities of the unverified, complex controller to be employed without compromising safety."</p> <p>"(...) this work falls within the runtime verification or runtime assurance realm. Our aim is to construct an architecture that allows us to ensure that an autonomous vehicle, controlled using machine learning strategies, never enters unsafe states as it navigates an environment. Specifically, the set of control strategies presented herein were synthesized using deep reinforcement learning and imitation learning (...). One strength of our approach is it abstracts away the need to analyze the underlying nature of these controllers and instead observes the influence of their decisions on the system behavior at runtime.</p> <p>To perform the verification, we first identify a dynamical model of the car and assume that the car operates within an a priori known environment. Next, we synthesize controllers using data collected from a series of experiments with the F1/10 vehicle, as well as through the execution of a series of deep reinforcement learning training campaigns. Using the obtained controllers, we aim to verify that the car does not crash into static obstacles within its environment in addition to the environment boundaries. To do this, we extend a real-time reachability algorithm (...) to compute the set of reachable states for a finite time-horizon and check for potential collisions. This safety checking forms the basis of the switching scheme in our simplex architecture, and we evaluate the merits of this approach both in simulation and on the F1/10 hardware platform using a variety of controllers, number of obstacles, and runtime configurations."</p> <p>"(...) the crux of the real-time reachability algorithm is computing the set of reachable states from the current time t up until (t+Treach). The algorithm utilized within this work is based on mixed face-lifting, which is part of a class of methods that deal with flow-pipe construction or reachtube computation where snapshots of the set of reachable states are enumerated at successive points in time."</p> <p>"(...) we customarily compute a sound over-approximation such that the actual system behavior is contained within the over-approximation. The algorithm utilized in this work utilizes n-dimensional hyper-rectangles ("boxes") as the set representation to generate reachtubes. Over long reachtimes, the over-approximation error resulting from the use of this representation can be problematic. However, for short reachtimes, it is ideal in terms of its simplicity and speed."</p> <p>"By refining the reachable set in successive iterations, our regime seeks to mitigate the occurrence of falsely returning unsafe. The two chief considerations in the anytime implementation of the safety checking procedure are (1) the overall soundness of our approach, and (2) the real-time nature of our scheme. Satisfying both requirements constitutes the novel extensions of the aforementioned algorithm. For the results of the verification to be sound, the safety checking process must be carried out in its entirety before a safety result is issued. At the same time, this requirement must be balanced alongside the real-time stipulation that tasks operate within pre-defined and deterministic time spans. Thus, our implementation ensures soundness properties while maintaining a low-likelihood of missing timing deadlines."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"In this work, we utilize imitation learning to train two neural network controllers to produce steering angles from different sensor inputs."</p> <p>Vision-Based Navigation (VBN): "We utilized the CNN architecture, DAVE-2, (...) to drive a 2016 Lincoln MKZ, in order to control the F1/10 model. The data we used to train DAVE-2 was collected from a set of simulation experiments where the sensor-action pairs were generated by a path tracking controller optimized to keep the F1/10 in the center of the track in the absence of obstacles."</p> <p>LiDAR Behavior Cloning: "The second network considered for imitation learning was a standard multi-layer</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 417 / 550	

	<p>perceptron network that consists of an input layer, 2 fully connected hidden layers of 64 neurons with ReLU activation functions, and a fully connected output layer with a tanh activation function."</p> <p>"(...) we used two well-known state-of-the-art reinforcement learning algorithms, an off-policy DRL algorithm known as Soft-Actor-Critic (SAC), and an on-policy RL algorithm, known as Augmented Random Search (ARS). In line with the imitation learning experiments, the agents were trained on the racetrack (...) with no obstacles and no backup controller. For both algorithms, the agent optimizes performance on a dense reward function that assigns a positive reward for counterclockwise progress around the track. The reward is calculated using a reference path that runs through the middle of the track. The reward value is the positive arc length between the previous and current closest point along the path. This reward function encourages the agent to complete as many laps as possible as quickly as possible."</p> <p>"Out of the 1440 experiments conducted in simulation, we observed collisions in 93 of them. This corresponds to a 93.5% success rate in preventing unsafe behavior. Of these collisions, 53 of them occurred at a speed set point of 1.5m/s and when using the IL controllers. We were able to eliminate these collisions in subsequent experiments by increasing the reach time horizon. However, in practice in order to provably eliminate all collisions, one must also verify the decision module and the safety controller utilized within the simplex regime."</p> <p>"The results of these experiments demonstrated that the ML models struggled to generalize to the real world and there was a large increase in the amount of time that the safety controller was used. This result can be explained by the small size of our racetrack, as well as the differences between the simulated and real world environments. On the other hand, the experiments demonstrate our regime was successful in maintaining safety, as there were no collisions observed in any of the hardware experiments."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"(...) we opted not to develop a "formally verified" safety controller. Instead, we selected a controller based on a gap following algorithm optimized to avoid collisions with obstacles." ==> This means that the safe controller is not indeed safe, but presumably more restrictive than the AI/ML-based one.</p> <p>Moreover, issues on the time to compute some of the ML-based models were deemed hard to generalize for real world usage (e.g. VBN). ==> "Our implementation did not make use of an RTOS, thus task management was left to the native Linux implementation. While our experimental evaluation did demonstrate deviations from the specified wall-time, the mean percentage of missed deadlines on the Jetson TX2 was fewer than 2% across all of our experiments."</p> <p>"While the reachability algorithm presented in this work possesses provable guarantees, our architecture does not. Obtaining these guarantees requires developing a formally verified safety controller and switching logic, which was outside the scope of the work presented herein. Therefore, it is possible to enter a state in our framework in which all future trajectories will result in a collision. These states are known as inevitable collision states and have been well studied within the motion planning literature. In future work, we hope to address this limitation by leveraging approaches such as viability kernels, and dynamic safety envelopes that allow for the synthesis of provable safe control regimes.</p> <p>Finally, as with many model based approaches, the quality of our reachability computations is dependent on the quality of the underlying model of the physical system. That is, guarantees around safety are only valid, provided that the system model is a good representation of reality. While the system identification results (...) show that our model is reasonably accurate, in practice the implementation of such an approach would also need to incorporate a rigorous uncertainty quantification analysis of the underlying model within the presence of imprecise sensor and state information. However, it is worth noting the underlying reachability algorithm supports differential inclusions, allowing for the straightforward incorporation of uncertainty, provided that such an analysis has been done."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Excellent discussion of results, including limitations and relevant future work (including uncertainties and developing a better safe controller). 2) Relevant for applying Safety ArtISt on Reinforcement Learning. 3) Very well written and organized. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The models are application-specific.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 418 / 550	

8.309 REFERENCE [936]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To describe an approach "for analyzing machine learning safety requirements top-down from higher-level business requirements, functional requirements, and risks to be mitigated".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) we proposed a top-down approach for analyzing the safety of ML software from top-level business-level decisions into safety requirements. Our approach facilitates traceability by identifying similar elements in different aspects of software models. (...) The main difference with our approach is that our approach facilitates both traceable requirements and safety analysis of ML software. This research contributes to the software engineering body of knowledge in a new approach in analyzing ML software safety. "</p> <p>"The overall framework is designed to be iterative with consistency in mind. This means revision can be made when information between elements across different models conflicts with each other. We utilized AI Project Canvas to describe the business level requirements at the highest level. Those project-level requirements derived into specific project requirements for machine learning development, which are described in Machine Learning Canvas. Both canvases specialize in handling ML characteristics such as training data quality and necessary features. Based on project and business level requirements, we analyze the functional requirements using the KAOS goal modeling approach. Using the UML component diagram, we analyze which component implements each functional requirement. The information of the component diagram is then used as a basis for the control structure required for STAMP/STPA. Using the information of hazard from STAMP/STPA, we systematically used safety case analysis to derive potential countermeasures."</p> <p>"(...) elements that create traceability between each model in the form of a matrix. The rows explain which model become the source of information for elements of other models. The columns explain which models use the information of other model to derive its own elements. Cells describe the elements related from both source and derivative model."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we conducted a case study for the framework by implementing it into a case of the lane and other vehicle detection in a self-driving car system."</p> <p>The authors concluded that the framework "(...) can create good traceability between higher business requirements into safety requirements" and that it "(...) needs to focus on exploring specific situations as the hazards and countermeasures produced by the framework are still too abstract for implementation in development activity".</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "(...) the framework needs to focus on exploring specific situations as the hazards and countermeasures produced by the framework are still too abstract for implementation in development activity".</p> <p>Future work: "We also found a direction for further improvement for the framework itself. In the future, we will expand the framework to facilitate a more thorough analysis of different hazardous conditions. We also will explore the possibilities of tracing the result of our framework to the ML model."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Simple yet effective framework for defining safety requirements for AI/ML-based systems including means for tracing them onto different levels. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lacks detail on application and practicality on verifying safety. 2) The authors do not compare their work with other research.

8.310 REFERENCE [937]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	To propose "a method that performs safety-based calibration assessment employing the machine learning algorithms to model the relation between calibration parameters of Partially Automated Lane Change System (PALS) and safety status of the various driving events".
Q2	Supervised learning, including logistic regression, naïve Bayes, decision trees, kNN, random forest, neural

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 419 / 550	

Answer	networks, SVM (erroneously called Support Vector Classification), and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA).
Q3 Answer	"(...) we presented safety based PALS calibration assessment framework through virtual validation procedures and evaluation of determined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) comprehensively. As an output of this framework, PALS calibration could be assessed from the safety perspective before testing them on road. Lane change events were labeled as "pass" or "fail" depending on whether the safety targets were satisfied. (...) Another target of this paper is to find which classification algorithm fits best to the PALS calibration assessment problem."
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) the "pass" and "fail" cases were distributed in the ratio of 34:66 in the original data set. Since the data is not highly imbalanced, we didn't use any oversampling or undersampling methods. Stratified splitting method was utilized to generate the training and testing data sets in the ratio of 80:20 while maintaining the same distribution of minor and major classes in the original data set. Then, cross-validation was performed on 5 different groups generated from training data to avoid overfitting. For each group, training and validation data sets were split again with stratified splitting in the ratio of 80:20."</p> <p>"(...) 7 learning classifiers such as Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Support Vector Classification (SVC), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Multi-Layer Perceptron Classifier (MLPC), and Random Forest were tried to find the one with the best performance. For each algorithm, the optimum hyperparameter combinations were found by using the cross-validation grid-search method. After the model was trained with the optimum hyperparameters, performance metrics for the training data set were calculated. In the end, the model was validated with the test data set and the testing performance was evaluated with the performance metrics."</p> <p>"We chose Matthews's Correlation Coefficient (MCC) as the performance metric to have a simple and reliable statistical measure that can cover true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP), and false negative (FN) (...)."</p> <p>"Out of all 7 learning algorithms, MLPC shows the best performance in both training and testing data sets while the Decision Tree has the worst performance metrics."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Not discussed / identified.</p> <p>Future work: "As a future step, this model can be extended with a comprehensive DoE including real-world worst case conditions. By this means, the safe calibration parameters can be derived from learning models and then be directly tried on the real road without any safety concern."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <p>1) Poses calibrating hyperparameters as a relevant topic for using AI-based systems in safety-critical applications.</p> <p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>1) The authors have not provided clear specification on which hyperparameters were considered during the cross-validation of their model, nor the grid search intervals and scales.</p> <p>2) The proposed future work is fairly restricted, as the authors themselves have not discussed that the results are safe enough for the end application nor the issues that the better performing models are difficult to be explained (e.g., neural networks).</p>

8.311 REFERENCE [938]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To "propose a shielding mechanism that ensures ISO-verified human safety while training and deploying RL algorithms on manipulators" by means of a "reachability analysis of humans and manipulators to guarantee that the manipulator comes to a complete stop before a human is within its range".
Q2 Answer	Reinforcement learning, neural networks.
Q3 Answer	"(...) one open challenge in RL is to formally guarantee the safety of surrounding humans due to their unpredictable movement and many degrees of freedom (DoF)."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 420 / 550	

	"(...) our safety concept is speed and separation monitoring (SSM) according to DIN EN ISO 10218–1 2021, 5.10.3 warranting that the robot is in a completely stopped state before any collision with a human could occur. We need to verify the robot trajectory at a high frequency to achieve this strong safety criterion while still being able to maneuver close to humans. However, for the RL agent it suffices to output actions at a low frequency to make long-term decisions like moving around a human to reach its goal. Our safety shield combines the low-frequency RL agent with our high-frequency formal verification. The RL agent used in this work is a state-of-the-art soft actor-critic (SAC) with hindsight experience replay (HER). However, our safety shield can be used with any online RL agent. This work presents the first provably safe robot manipulator control based on deep RL in human environments."
Q4 Answer	<p>"We conduct two different experiments. In the first randomized-goal experiment, the episode goal is randomly and uniformly sampled over the entire joint space, and the start state is fixed with all joints at their zero position. Notably, the human may block the episode goal. For the second human-evasion experiment, we manually define the start and episode goal position so that the robot collides with the human if it takes the shortest path. The agent must learn to evade the human by taking a longer path or waiting until the human moves away from the table. In this scenario, the episode goal is only slightly randomized so that the human never blocks the goal state."</p> <p>Randomized Goal: "The baseline agent causes a safety-critical collision in approximately 20% of all episodes. Therefore, the baseline is too dangerous to be deployed in a real-world environment. (...) In contrast, the safety shield successfully prevents all safety-critical collisions. (...) At the end of the training, both agents have approximately the same success rate of 65%. (...) Approximately 10% of episodes end in a safe collision caused by the static human animation walking into the stationary robot. The remaining 25% of episodes ended by exceeding Tmax_episode. A manual investigation of the unsuccessful cases showed that most of the goals were not reachable because humans blocked the path to the goal."</p> <p>Human-Evasion: "The human-evasion experiment highlights another advantage of our proposed method. Since the human blocks the optimal path, the baseline agent collides with the human in almost every episode in the first half of the training (...). In the second half of training, the baseline agent learned to avoid collisions with the human more frequently, but still collides in approximately 25% of all episodes. Again, our safety shield prevents all safety-critical collisions."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "We trained the baseline agent with the same hyperparameters as the safe agent to achieve good comparability. In order to improve the performance of the baseline agent, we also tried to operate it at higher frequencies (50Hz and 250Hz) and provide it with a high negative reward for collisions. Unfortunately, none of the measures lead to successful training improvements, so we omit these results."</p> <p>Future work: "Our subsequent goals are to refine the RL agent further and train it on a more complex set of real-world human motions. Finally, we plan to test our safe RL agent on actual robots and perform tasks in a human working environment."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Example of safe reinforcement learning based on estimating reachable sets on a simplex architecture. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The authors have recreated a simplex architecture with a fail-safe controller optimized for their end application. Not as novelty as presented from the standpoint of the system architecture; nevertheless, worthy of research for the end application, which is indeed not frequent in other research papers. 2) Not much emphasis was given on the safety assurance algorithms.

8.312 REFERENCE [939]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "present a method for computing exact reachable sets for deep neural networks with rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation".
Q2 Answer	(Deep) neural networks.
Q3 Answer	"(...) we present the Reachable Polyhedral Marching (RPM) algorithm for computing forward and backward reachable sets of deep neural networks with rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation. This is a critical building block to proving safety properties for autonomous systems with learned perception, dynamics, or control

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 421 / 550	

	<p>components in the loop. Specifically, given a set of input values, RPM will compute the set of all output values that can be obtained under the ReLU network (the forward reachable set, or image, of the input set). Similarly, given a set of output values, RPM will compute the set of all input values that can lead to those output values under the ReLU network (the backward reachable set, or preimage, of the output values)."</p> <p>"RPM applies a fundamentally different approach to avoid layer-by-layer computation. Instead, we compute the reachable set one polyhedral cell at a time, where each cell represents a region of the input space over which the network is affine. Each cell can be computed quickly through a series of linear programs equal to the number of neurons in the network, regardless of width or depth. Our algorithm computes cells until the explored set of cells fills the desired reachable set."</p>
Q4 Answer	"We demonstrate RPM in two examples related to the safety verification of dynamical systems with learned components. First, we compute forward reachable and backward reachable sets for a learned dynamical model of a [damped] pendulum over 50 time steps in the future and past, respectively. Furthermore, we compare with a state of the art reachability method in a safety verification problem involving ACAS Xu, a neural network policy for aircraft collision avoidance. Our algorithm finds unsafe inputs for this network many times faster [than the baseline] and when no unsafe input exists, our algorithm certifies safety approximately 2 times slower."
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: The method might be slower to prove safety when it is true</p> <p>Future work: "In the future, we will investigate parallel implementations of RPM to further improve computational speed."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Formal verification of ANNs including both forward and backward reachability. Good resource that not many similar work provides. 2) Excellent mathematical basis. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No discussion on AI faults.

8.313 REFERENCE [941]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To present "an idea and method for detecting and extracting ship intelligent navigation testing scenarios from real Automatic Identification System (AIS) data" aiming towards scenario-based smart ship navigation tests.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	Even though AI is cited as a motivation for the research, the presented methods do not relate to AI. No AI-related techniques for data processing are also mentioned. As a result, this item is of little impact to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.
Q4 Answer	Even though AI is cited as a motivation for the research, the presented methods do not relate to AI. No AI-related techniques for data processing are also mentioned. As a result, this item is of little impact to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.
Q5 Answer	Even though AI is cited as a motivation for the research, the presented methods do not relate to AI. No AI-related techniques for data processing are also mentioned. As a result, this item is of little impact to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.
Q6 Answer	Even though AI is cited as a motivation for the research, the presented methods do not relate to AI. No AI-related techniques for data processing are also mentioned. As a result, this item is of little impact to the safety assurance of AI-based systems.

8.314 REFERENCE [942]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "emphasize that while developing the safety assurance case for such functions [image classification], the argumentation over the appropriate implementation of the functionality must also address the vulnerability to misclassification due to class similarities".
Q2	Deep neural networks, convolutional neural networks.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 422 / 550

Answer	
Q3 Answer	The authors have developed models to estimate the similarity among different traffic signs and a risk assessment matrix that relates the severity of a safety measure for each class of signs and its misclassification. No details regarding the IA model or its verification have been provided from a conceptual point of view; instead, a conceptual safety argument has been discussed.
Q4 Answer	The authors have not provided practical results except for the conceptual safety argument referred to in Question 3.
Q5 Answer	"To demonstrate the low on-operation probability of misclassifications that have high risk scores, the corresponding argumentation can be strengthened with the help of additional compelling sub-goals (validation targets related to intricate details) and evidences to make it more convincing. As an extension to this work, the arguments discussed theoretically in this paper need to be experimentally validated using trained deep neural networks. An empirical assessment of the relation between vulnerability to misclassification and its corresponding probability on the real data is to be performed. Some elements (e.g., contexts, assumptions) and terms (e.g., acceptable threshold, residual risk) used in the safety assurance case presented here are addressed in a general manner, and will have to further elaborated and/or quantified in a formal way."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Little development on the safety assurance of AI-based systems. 2) Totally application-specific.

8.315 REFERENCE [943]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To propose "human-in-the-loop simulation testing for evaluation of an autonomous vehicle using a 3D virtual vehicle driving platform that can be used for safety assessment of autonomous vehicle".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever (only mentions 'autonomous systems' / 'autonomous vehicles').
Q3 Answer	"(...) the main goal of this study is focused on the system configuration of human-in-the-loop 3D virtual simulation platform for performance evaluation of autonomous vehicles. The system is designed as an end-to-end autonomous vehicle development platform that can provide support from generation and collection of human's driving data for development of controllers to safety testing of the controllers developed in critical scenarios in the virtual platform."
Q4 Answer	"By applying object detection to the video stream, the static and dynamic on-road obstacles can be categorized into their respective classes such as car, truck, motorbike, pedestrian, traffic sign etc., and locate them by using bounding boxes. This will provide information of the surrounding and road condition to the level 3 ADAS such as collision avoidance, lane centering, lane change assistance, adaptive cruise control etc. to manoeuvre a vehicle properly. The vision information obtained can also be combined with range sensor such as RADAR and LiDAR for autonomous emergency braking and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) used in self-driving vehicle."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed. Future work: "As for future work, more rare critical scenarios will be developed based on the road environment models to generate driving data using the driving hardware. Then, the collected data will be used to develop a driver model that can mimic driving behaviour of human drivers using Python which will then integrate with the simulator for testing of level 3 autonomous vehicle."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) The only connection to the safety assurance of AI-based systems is that the authors reinforce that simulators can be a better source of data than human-labelled records.

8.316 REFERENCE [944]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "formulate the global robustness certification for neural networks with ReLU activation functions as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem, and present an efficient approach to address it".
Q2 Answer	(Deep) neural networks.
Q3	"In safety-critical systems with DNNs involved, it is important to analyze the DNN robustness for evaluating

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 423 / 550	

Answer	<p>system safety. As local robustness is defined locally to a given input sample, to evaluate system safety, we will need to apply local robustness certification during runtime for each input sample that the system encounters or may encounter. However, the complexity of local robustness certification, even with conservative overapproximation, is too high for runtime execution in most practical systems. Moreover, sometimes it is required to ensure system safety for future time horizon (e.g., to verify there is no collision for the next 3 seconds). As future input samples are unknown, local robustness certification cannot be applied.</p> <p>Instead, we could address system safety by considering the problem of global robustness, which measures the worst-case DNN output change against input perturbation for all possible input samples."</p> <p>"A major challenge for exact global robustness certification is its complexity – while it can be run offline to facilitate safety analysis (since it considers the entire input space), the high complexity often makes it intractable even in offline computation. While a number of methods have been proposed to tackle the complexity, they often lack the deterministic guarantees needed for safety verification."</p> <p>"In this work, we propose an efficient certification approach to over-approximate the global robustness. The derived global robustness is sound and deterministic, the over-approximation is tight, and the approach can be used effectively for the purpose of safety verification. To achieve this, our approach introduces a novel network encoding structure, namely interleaving twin network encoding, to compare two copies of the neural network side-by-side under different inputs, with extra interleaving dependencies added between them to improve efficiency. Our approach also includes over-approximation techniques based on network decomposition and LP (linear programming) relaxation, to further reduce the computation complexity."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"Experiments show that our approach is much more efficient and scalable than the exact global robustness methods such as Reluplex, with tight over-approximation – our approach can certify DNNs with more than 5k neurons in 5 hours while the exact methods cannot certify DNNs with more than 64 neurons in 1 day. To demonstrate the importance of global robustness and the practical application of our certification approach, a case study is conducted to verify the safety of a closed-loop control system with a vision-based perception DNN in the loop."</p> <p>"(...) we conduct a case study for safety verification of control systems that use neural networks for perception. We consider an advanced cruise control (ACC) scenario where an ego vehicle is following a reference vehicle. The ego vehicle is equipped with an RGB camera, and a DNN is designed to estimate the distance from the reference vehicle based on the camera image. We assume that the captured image may be slightly perturbed. A feedback controller takes the estimated distance, along with the ego vehicle speed, to generate the control input, which is the acceleration of the ego vehicle."</p> <p>"(...) we find that as long as the distance estimation error is within [-0.14, 0.14], the system will always be safe. Given that our global robustness certification bounds 0.1298, we can assert that our ACC system is safe with this DNN design under the assumed perturbation bound."</p> <p>"When the perturbation bound is further increased (...), we observe that there are (...) simulations encountering unsafe states. This shows the impact of input perturbation on system safety and the importance of our global robustness analysis."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: Model valid only for neural networks with ReLU activation function.</p> <p>Future work: "Our future work will focus on continuing improvement of our approach's efficiency, possibly via parallelization on multi-core platforms, to enable its usage for larger-size perception neural networks."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Solid mathematical background for the safety assurance of specific neural networks (ReLU activation function only) by means of overapproximation. 2) The case studies show that the method is able to detect unsafe scenarios stemming from improper inputs (given they are properly modeled, including underlying uncertainties) and that globally unsafe scenarios can be detected. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Part of the model requires application-specific modeling.

8.317 REFERENCE [947]

Q-Index	6
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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 424 / 550	

Q1 Answer	To "discuss the general concepts of the [IEC61508] standard that hinder the development and assessment of a safety devices using AI in the current state of knowledge" and highlight "(...) the locks for the use of IEC 61508 and suggests some leverages, such as the use of a new safety lifecycle, a minimal level of transparency and explainability as well as the demonstration of robustness based on formal verification, testing and new metrics."
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general; machine learning in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"IEC 61508 standard mentions artificial intelligence only once: among the techniques and measures used in the specification phase, the use of artificial intelligence to correct faults is not recommended. It is not stated whether the embedded software itself can incorporate artificial intelligence. However, the principles set out for the lifecycle, and the properties to be achieved in terms of completeness, intelligibility, simplicity, testability or determinism make the use of machine learning algorithms hardly compatible with compliance with the standard."</p> <p>"Two issues specific to artificial intelligence are developed below: Reinforcement learning, as well as other modes of learning not developed in this article, are characterized by their continuous learning for which it is necessary to adopt specific developing processes in order to set limits to their functioning. Residual risk: Some ML models give results associated with probabilities, thus opposing the deterministic paradigm stated in the IEC 61508 software. It might be necessary to complete the requirements of the software functional safety by adding a probabilistic dimension to the systematic error mitigation requirements."</p> <p>"(...) we suggest applying the following steps to ensure the safety assurance of the devices."</p> <p>Specification: "(...) the safety function of the device, the boundaries of the system's capabilities and the operational performances are defined. It also includes the data management plan and the testing plan. The testing plan shall mention the metrics used to qualify the system. It is also specified that the design shall favour the traceability of the requirements as well as the interpretability and the testing and verification of the system."</p> <p>Data Management: "This covers the cleaning to remove duplicates, the filling of missing data, the normalization and scaling, and the labelling for supervised learning. Finally, the datasets are constituted in order to ensure representativeness. To be of good quality, the data must be: accurate (without errors), traceable (the source is known), temporally correlated to the situation of operation, complete, well formatted and representative of the situation."</p> <p>Model Development: It includes feature engineering (rare events), algorithm selection, model training, and model evaluation.</p> <p>Model deployment: It comprises deploying the system in its environment.</p> <p>Operation and Retirement: "The monitoring of the device gives information about the performances of the device through time and can indicate device's failures as well as a change in the device's environment. (...) the consequences of this change on the safety must be analysed and if necessary, the tests and verifications shall be reperformed."</p> <p>Methods to improve V&V: - Transparency: "About the dataset: motivations of the dataset creation; dataset composition; collection process; data preprocessing; information about the use, the distribution and the maintenance. About the model: the intended use of the model; model description and explanation about its functioning; the model and parametrizations used and why; the variables and features used by the model and why; the metrics used to validate the model; the version of the model. About the procedure: who participate to develop the model; document about the process, procedure and test results." - Interpretability and explainability: "Explanations can be given before the modelling or during the learning phase, during the modelling (intrinsically explainable algorithms), after the modelling (or post-hoc)." - "The challenges of formal verification methods are: the computational costs and scalability for models with an important number of layers that generate hard-to-solve problems; the tools and framework do not necessarily apply to all ML algorithms (few formal verifications address RNN; some formal verifications target</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 425 / 550	

	specific ML algorithms, such as ReLU)." - Tests: statistical tests, empirical methods, environmental tests, adversarial tests, performance metrics. "It is advised to use more than one metric, as a single metric cannot represent the whole behaviour of a classifier and can lead to misleading results." - Controllability: "(...) to implement a control of the ML software performed either by a human or by a machine. Examples of human control are: giving them the final word in the decision-making process or giving them the opportunity to give feedback to improve the operation of the system."
Q4 Answer	Since the objective of the research paper was to discuss the safety assurance of AI-based systems and the needed evolutions from IEC61508, the answers to Question 3 represent the results of the research.
Q5 Answer	"Finally, it appears that work remains to be done to obtain operational tools that industrialists and third-party expert and certification bodies can use. This article, which had the ambition to present the main general concepts of AI for safety-critical systems, could be completed by more in-depth analyses, in particular on the safety life cycle of AI devices, on formal verification and testing methods, on safety by design and on the metrics used to quantify robustness."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Excellent overview on the limitations of current IEC61508-based standards to deal with AI and good summary of techniques and lifecycle phases needed for AI. Very well aligned to our own research. 2) Good hook to our Safety ArtISt method: we directly cover their future work. Weakness: 1) Some steps are still superficially dealt with. No techniques on how to do it with specific types of AI/ML have been explored.

8.318 REFERENCE [949]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To address "the complexity of SAT-based invariant inference" for "an inductive invariant of polynomial length given a transition system and a safety property".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	"(...) inference algorithms succeed when the invariant they infer is not too long. Therefore, this paper considers the complexity of inferring invariants of polynomial length." "Our study of SAT-based methods focuses on an algorithmic model called the Hoare-query model. The idea is that the inference algorithm is not given direct access to the program, but performs queries on it. In the Hoare-query model, algorithms repeatedly choose α , β and query for the validity of Hoare triples $\{ \alpha \} d \{ \beta \}$, where d is the transition relation denoting one step of the system, inaccessible to the algorithm but via such Hoare queries. The check itself is implemented by an oracle, which in practice is a SAT solver. This model is general enough to capture algorithms such as PDR and its variants, and leaves room for other interesting design choices, but does not capture white-box approaches such as abstract interpretation. The advantage of this model for a theoretical study is that it enables an information-based analysis, which (i) sidesteps open computational complexity questions, and therefore results in unconditional lower bounds on the computational complexity of SAT-based algorithms captured by the model, and (ii) grants meaning to questions about generalization from partial information we discuss later." "This research addresses two main questions (...): (1) These algorithms revolve around the question of generalization: from observing concrete states (to be excluded from the invariant), the algorithm seeks to produce assertions that hold for all reachable states. The different heuristics in this context are largely understood as clever ways of performing this generalization. The situation is similar in interpolation-based algorithms, only that generalization is performed from bounded safety proofs rather than states. How should generalization be performed to achieve efficient invariant inference? (2) A key aspect of property-guided reachability (PDR) is the form of SAT checks it uses, as part of relative inductiveness checks, of Hoare triples $\{ \alpha \} d \{ \beta \}$ in which in general α is different from β . Repeated queries of this form are potentially richer than presenting a series of candidate invariants, where the check is $\{ \alpha \} d \{ \alpha \}$. Is there a benefit in using relative inductiveness beyond inductiveness checks? We analyze these questions in the foundational case of Boolean programs. "Coming up with inductive invariants is one of the most challenging tasks of formal verification - it is often

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA		Page: 426 / 550

	referred to as the Eurekaž step. This paper studies the asymptotic complexity of automatically inferring CNF invariants of polynomial length, a problem we call polynomial-length inductive invariant inference, in a SAT-based black-box model."
Q4 Answer	"(...) we answer question 1 with an impossibility result, by showing that no choice of generalization can lead to an inference algorithm using only a polynomial number of Hoare queries. Our lower bound is information-theoretic, and holds even with unlimited computational power, showing that the problem of generalization is chiefly a question of information gathering." "(...) we answer question 2 in the affirmative, by showing an exponential gap between algorithms utilizing rich {a}d {B} checks and algorithms that perform only inductiveness checks {a}d {a}. Namely, we construct a class of programs for which a simple version of PDR can infer invariants efficiently, but every algorithm learning solely from counterexamples to the inductiveness of candidates requires an exponential number of queries. This result shows, for the first time theoretically, the significance of relative inductiveness checks as the foundation of PDR's mechanisms, in comparison to a machine learning approach (...) that infers invariants based on inductiveness checks only (but of course this result does not mean that PDR is always more efficient than every ICE algorithm)."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: The authors have identified classes of problems that are not covered by the proposed approach (e.g., general systems equivalence and membership verification). Future work: "One avenue for further research is an information-based analysis of black-box models extended with white-box capabilities, e.g. by investigating syntactical conditions on the transition relation that simplify generalization."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Excellent mathematical basis for applying SMT on safety verification of systems with polynomial functions. Weakness: 1) Overly theoretical. No practical links to systems engineering. 2) No direct mention to AI and safety.

8.319 REFERENCE [954]

Q-Index	6
Q1 Answer	To "propose an approach to conduct a safe-by-design development process for AI based systems" which "relies upon a method which benefits from a reference AI architecture and safety principles".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	"Despite the engineering process has proven certain effectiveness, it also shows some drawbacks regarding safety assessment. In particular, the lack of a comprehensive process to settle common criteria and thresholds for safety evaluation and certification. To our knowledge, the problem is quite hard to solve and no current approach overcomes related issues: an AI-based system should integrate sensor devices with limited - sometimes opaque - detection capabilities(...), deploy algorithms to identify and properly react to complex, rather unforeseen, situational scenarios and, on top of that, ensure negligible likelihood of occurrence for critical hazards and disfunctioning. Moreover, whereas for typical development methods, like the V-cycle, the phases and their sequencing are almost static, it is observed that for AI-based systems, the nature of certain engineering phases and their order may vary." "Although, it is consensual that safety analyses should be conducted as early as possible and all along the life-cycle, the few initiatives on that respect (...) are still work in progress." "(...) new safety methods and analysis processes are required to develop them. To tackle the referred issues, the main contribution of this paper is an overall generic iterative (OGI) method to conduct safe-by-design development of AI-based systems relying upon a generic architecture and safety principles." "The specification of a process development for AI-based systems should consider the following particularities: Engineering process dependent on AI technology: Subsystems or components implementing ML/DL modules are based upon parameters which may require to be set during conception, design, implementation and validation phases. For those subsystems and components, a learning phase should be introduced whereas for other typical (non-ML-based) subsystems and components, the learning phase is non-existing."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 427 / 550	

	<p>Engineering process dependent on knowledge bases: The learning phases strongly depend upon target objectives and external knowledge bases (KBs). For many complex AI-based systems, an iteration on design parameters may be necessary after a validation campaign, e.g., to adjust detection ranges and accuracy. Detailed requirements cannot be elicited before knowing the effectiveness of knowledge bases, ML/DL techniques, and parameters choices.</p> <p>Knowledge bases maturity: Due to previous aspects, the AI-based systems development shall not only depend upon ML/DL techniques and development methods, but also on building up knowledge bases (KBs) and making them evolve so as to improve coverage and accuracy of objects, events, and phenomena detection. Referred KBs shall be useful for detection and for high level reasoning, e.g., reasoning based upon intuition. We propose to integrate the previous specificities from early stages of design.</p> <p>"(...) certain typical safety criteria like redundancy do not suffice anymore to ensure expected levels of availability and also accuracy. The specific aspects addressed in this paper are described in line (...). Events indistinguishability. This issue is mainly due to physical limits of sensors. In particular, because real and virtual images are practically indistinguishable. For instance, the detection of a stop signal can be easily faked by a photo of the same. Light rays and other natural electromagnetic signals used for detection can be reproduced by different objects.</p> <p>Targets variability. Many objects, elements and phenomena to be detected by AI-based systems exhibit certain variability. Although AI-based systems should cope with referred variability, questions arise if the system may face unforeseen situations beyond its limits. For instance, sudden deterioration or disfunctioning of context signs may lead to wrong detection of objects.</p> <p>Noises and error propagation. Along with variability issues, the noises added by the background and environmental phenomena increase hazards impact, in particular in case of dismissed/miscalculated noises and errors propagated through the system. Environmental conditions (e.g., solar winds, snow) may impose additional constraints to system operation and behave as background noises.</p> <p>Human-machine interactions harmonization. The operation of AI-based systems in real environment is quite novel. Whereas risks related to machine-to-machine or machine-to-environment interactions can be assessed during design phases, predict the outcomes of human-to-machine interactions is far more complex. Although an harmonization phase can be conducted, complex human reactions (e.g., psychological, societal, political) are difficult to assess."</p> <p>The authors then propose a safe-by-design method for AI-based systems. It is an iterative method with 11 steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Missions and goals; 2) AI principles structuring; 3) Decompositional analysis; 4) AI knowledge basis structuring; 5) Allocation of ML techniques; 6) Knowledge bases selection; 7) Detailed AI architecture design; 8) Overall models development and integration; 9) Settle validation benchmark; 10) AI system performance evaluation; 11) AI system implementation. <p>Safety integrates with this lifecycle by means of situational analyses, malfunctions, faults, and hazards related to ML (e.g., error propagation), hazardous scenarios, and definition of safety goals.</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"The modeling and safety assessment framework of the OGI method is implemented in Sophia, a model-based toolset integrated with Eclipse Papyrus editor for UML/SysML models. (...) We evaluate the OGI method on an ongoing industry-academy experimentation of autonomous shuttles deployment on a sensitive site"</p> <p>"By applying the OGI method to the autonomous shuttle, a multi-factor uncertainty was identified intervening at different levels of AI systems design. A first uncertainty comes from the accuracy and maturity of external KBs which impact the learning process and performance of ML/DL components. The use of fine-grained approaches, like data diversification, is promising to overcome this issue. A second uncertainty is the difficulty to apprehend the infinite usage-scenarios space resulting from a "continuum" of possible environmental-operational contexts, variants and configurations. This often leads to poor system-context specifications not representative enough to characterize the scenarios space. A current trend for this shortcoming is to settle enough specificities, from a safety point of view, to define categories of emblematic scenarios useful in</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 428 / 550	

	particular for benchmarking but without guarantee of coverage exhaustiveness. The third uncertainty factor comes from the performance limits of AI-based components, e.g., sensors blinding or other still unveiled environment events. Interpretation and decision-taking layers are also at stake when arbitration algorithms face contradictory directives and must solve them in critical scenarios, e.g., between safety requirements and AI-knowledge basis (principles, directives, rules). that has reached consensus on this sensitive issue. Finally, since AI-based systems may still be unable to properly react to changing environments (...), deploy new capabilities in real time is of utmost importance to ensure true systems intelligence and autonomy."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Discussed on the answer to Question 4. Future work: "(...) we plan to conduct larger-scale application of the OGI method on others safety-critical Albased systems to strengthen our conclusions and enforce approach validity. We are also assessing the applicability of other standard-preconceived methods, like FMEA and FTA, in the context of AI-based systems. We would further like to complete the OGI method to cover latter stages of the development cycle, i.e., testing and validation."
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Safety assurance process well-structured for AI/ML-based systems. Overlaps with Safety ArtIst in several steps/activities, albeit in some different orders. Weakness: 1) Some steps are still superficially dealt with. No techniques on how to do it with specific types of AI/ML have been explored.

8.320 REFERENCE [955]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To present applications of AI-based solutions in nuclear power plants and discuss their advantages and disadvantages towards conventional computational methods.
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general. Specific mention to neural networks in general, fuzzy systems, and evolutionary algorithms. Support vector machines are also mentioned.
Q3 Answer	The main applications of Soft Computing (SC) in nuclear power plants (NPPs) are as follows: 1) Fault detection and diagnosis, including "(...) instrument calibration monitoring (...), instrumentation channel dynamic performance monitoring (...), equipment monitoring (...), reactor core monitoring (...), loose part monitoring (...), and transient identification (...). FDD is done either by model-based or model-free methods." 2) Reactor power control: "SC techniques for the optimal power control of nuclear reactors have been studied extensively in the past decades. ANNs have been used in many reactor control problems." 3) Solving flow and heat transfer problems: "(...) it is interesting in considering methods that may reduce the computational cost and uncertainty in thermal-hydraulic calculations (...). SC techniques can be used in nonlinear, uncertain, or unknown complex engineering problems without an explicit understanding of the physical mechanism. Therefore, they have been used extensively in research studies related to flow characteristics and heat transfer (...)." 4) Optimization of operation and design: "The optimization issue in NPPs includes optimizing the fuel arrangement in the reactor core, optimizing the design of the power plant components, optimizing the arrangement of the control rods, optimization of maintenance program (...)." 5) High-performance accident management support tools: "Accident management support tools based on SC techniques can play a vital role in early fault detection (...), assist the NPP operators in predicting the likelihood of future states of the NPP (...), make a timely declaration of the level of a site emergency (...), guide the state officials, manage emergency response by forecasting the trend of parameters, giving the timing of events, evaluating accident management measures (...), etc." 6) Operating parameters forecasting: "Parameter forecasting is the prediction of NPPs operating variables to perform appropriate actions before transient progresses into critical states' (...) Difficulty in finding accurate mathematical models and the time-consuming of these methods limit the practical application of model-based methods. Therefore, SC techniques, especially ANNs, have been studied to forecast the NPP parameters." 7) Reliability and safety assessment: "(...) SC techniques can greatly reduce the computational cost. (...) when an accident has never happened or occurred infrequently, there will be insufficient failure data to estimate statistically the reliability characteristics of related system components. To deal with this problem, fuzzy probability approaches (...) have been proposed and implemented. (...) functional failure analysis, probabilistic

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 429 / 550	

	safety assessment (PSA), and human reliability analysis can be mentioned." 8) Other applications: "These include the use of SC techniques in site selection (...), NPP performance analysis (...), NPP components crack detection (...), prediction of welding residual stress (...), economic optimization of NPP (...), radiation protection (...), construction of detector spectrum (...), radionuclide concentration estimation (...), estimating buildup factor of alloys (...), isotope identification (...), uranium price estimation (...), radiation shielding (...), estimating gamma attenuation coefficient (...), waste management (...), safeguarding (...), etc."
Q4 Answer	"The main advantages of Soft Computing (SC) techniques are high execution speed, model independence, and high efficiency; while the main disadvantage is the need for access to reliable data sets which should be provided by experiment or modeling." "(...) the practical application of these methods in real NPPs seems to require overcoming existing challenges. Existing NPP systems face limitations at the current stage that makes the use of SC problematic. The main limitations are the long life of most NPPs, low degrees of automation, the lack of technical systems to support the development of data-driven applications, insufficiency of reliable data sets, and obsolete standards. On the other hand, some inherent limitations of SC techniques also complicate the actual application of these techniques. The black-box nature of the SC impairs the reliability of these methods, and unexpected results are possible that can have serious safety consequences, even achieving high accuracy on test data (...) Addressing these challenges requires more research and international cooperation to accelerate the technological developments of SC applications in operating and next-generation NPPs." "(...) the most important challenge in the development of research related to the use of SC in NPPs is the lack of open access data sets for use in learning algorithms. To address this problem, in addition to improve the sensors and data collection systems of NPPs, the data from accurate simulations must be generated. In addition, SC techniques should be tested on real NPPs to examine their practical application. There are areas and applications in NPPs that have been little studied or no research has been done in those areas. SC-based autonomous systems have a great potential for use in future NPPs to minimize the need for operator actions in all phases of operation. Hence, research on SC-based autonomous systems in areas such as overall NPP surveillance and control, accident management, and operator support systems seems to have a preference as future research opportunities. Another research opportunity is to study the use of deep learning in applications related to NPPs, which in recent years has shown great ability to solve various problems. Just as SC techniques have been used successfully in a wide range of industrial applications, it has a high potential for use in NPPs. By developing research in this field and overcoming the existing challenges, it will be possible to utilize the benefits of these techniques in future NPPs."
Q5 Answer	Please refer to the answers for Question 4 for limitations and future work.
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) The review is not systematic and features at most old references (5+ years) by the time the text was published (2022). 2) Little connection to the safety assurance of AI-based systems except for general challenges that are widely known by the community.

8.321 REFERENCE [960]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To "propose to partially specify hard-to-specify domain concepts, which Machine-Learned Components (MLCs) tend to classify, instead of fully relying on their inductive learning ability from arbitrarily-collected datasets" by "a semi-automated approach to construct a multi-level semantic web to partially outline the hard-to-specify, yet crucial, domain concept "pedestrian" in automotive domain".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general. The concept augmentation strategy includes neural networks and unsupervised learning (k-means and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA).
Q3 Answer	Introduction: "(...) ML models suggest specifications (inductively learned from the training-validation dataset) rather than implementing known specifications. This characteristic makes MLCs particularly useful when a domain consists of concepts, where little knowledge exists for humans to develop effective algorithms. We refer to such domain-specific concepts as hard-to-specify for which a universal definition does not exist, as

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 430 / 550	

	<p>they are inherently challenging to clearly define. Therefore, these are domain concepts with no clearly delineated and agreed-upon definition due to the large difference that exists between varying instances of the concept. Although humans may recognize various instances of the concept through intuition, yet the concepts' definite specification is difficult even for humans."</p> <p>"Specifying domain concepts improve requirements engineering tasks in developing MLCs by (i) enriching their learning foundation with semantic information (ii) providing a more complete basis to learn functional requirements specifications (iii) disambiguating MLC's requirements specifications which contain hard-to-specify domain terms. To this end, we introduce a novel semi-automated approach to construct a multi-level semantic web for partially specifying a potential pedestrian for MLCs."</p> <p>"(...) our approach contains two major parts Designing the Semantic Web and Augmenting the Dataset. In part "Designing the Semantic Web", we specify the domain concept, pedestrian, first by augmenting the concept through searching for accompanying, co-occurring, and related similar terms (...). Second, we create a set of high-level topics (Zoom-Out view) from the retrieved terms by following a sequence of ML techniques (...). Third, more details are provided for each topic (Zoom-In view), using a part-of-speech tagger (...). Finally, instead of merely returning a flat list of relevant terms and relationships, we compose the terms into a meaningful hierarchy of topics in the form of a semantic web (...). In part "Augmenting the Dataset", we assess the usefulness of our approach through showing the effectiveness of the inferred semantic web in improving MLCs' accuracy, as well as empirically analyzing the coverage of the generated topics and relationships in benchmark datasets. First with a reference to the web, we identified one semantically important feature, wheelchair, for pedestrians that appeared in the semantic web but was not present in the majority of commonly-used datasets (...) We then manually collected a balanced number of images of pedestrians in wheelchair and augmented the MLC's original training dataset (...) Finally, we re-trained a state-of-the-art object detector to detect the augmented feature, and evaluated the effectiveness of our approach in improving MLCs learning process, through conducting a series of experiments before and after the dataset augmentation (...). Additionally, to assess the coverage of the semantic web that was generated by the proposed approach, we analyzed multiple state-of-the-art datasets with respect to entities and relationships built in the semantic web."</p> <p>"While we use our approach to semi-automatically construct an extendable domain-specific semantic web for the concept, 'pedestrian' in the automotive domain, the process is not domain-specific and can be generalized to other concepts and domains."</p> <p>Augmenting a concept: "(...) to specify such concepts, for which no set of domain documents exists, we decided to refer to human perception as a reference model. For this purpose, we referred to platforms where humans easily share their views, thoughts, and knowledge, such as social platforms, news feeds, and online encyclopedias."</p> <p>Augmenting the dataset: "(...) to instead evaluate the usefulness of the proposed approach we (i) first, evaluated the approach effectiveness in improving the accuracy of MLCs. For this purpose, we identified the existing gap in a state-of-the-art pedestrian dataset and augmented it for one missing entity. We then compared the accuracy of a state-of-the-art object detector, trained on this dataset, in detecting various instances of 'pedestrian' before and after the augmentation. (ii) second, we evaluated the coverage of the generated entities and relations of the semantic web on multiple commonly used datasets, which in turn, the gaps in these datasets."</p>
<p>Q4 Answer</p>	<p>"In all of our experiments in this article, within After Dataset Augmentation category, we considered wheelchair as a missing object from the primary dataset. We chose the wheelchair because it appeared in our semantic web subject-predicate-object triplets, showing a strong association with the term 'pedestrian' and was not initially present in the primary dataset."</p> <p>In the experiments, the author have shown that pedestrians on wheelchairs were better identified than when no augmentation was performed. The best results were obtained when 'person' and 'wheelchair person' were split into two different groups of pedestrians.</p>
<p>Q5 Answer</p>	<p>"Our study has several potential threats. Concerning generalizability, we experimented with only one domain, the automotive domain, and one hard-to-specify domain concept, 'pedestrian'. (...) the process we defined is general and fully automatable (with the exception of topic selection) and can be applied to specify other domain-specific concepts in other domains."</p> <p>"The creation of the semantic web is based on the information that we extracted from the web and social media,</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 431 / 550	

	<p>namely Twitter, Wikipedia, and Google News. These platforms contain accurate, true, and relevant but also inaccurate, false, and out-dated information. (...) To mitigate bias, we only extracted up-to-date information, and we used more real-time idea-sharing platforms. However, further work is needed to evaluate the validity of the extracted information and to claim absolute completeness of the constructed semantic web. Further, using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques introduces linguistic limitations, such as polysemy, to the approach that is required to be addressed in future work.</p> <p>Finally, in terms of evaluation, we have only used one dataset and object detector to illustrate the application of our approach. Although the selected dataset and detector are among the state-of-the-art pedestrian datasets and object detectors, we plan to extend the application of our methodology."</p> <p>"We plan to work on the generalizability of our approach for other concepts, such as traffic and other domains. Additionally, we will evaluate the effectiveness of the automatically generated semantic webs with domain experts and with more datasets and algorithms."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) Relevant research towards improving the specification of AI-based systems.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) No discussion of the influence of confirmation bias on the study, since the authors expected to identify wheelchair users as pedestrians. 2) The technique requires language-specific content and/or means to generalize it for other languages as well. This was not explored by the authors.</p>

8.322 REFERENCE [962]

Q-Index	0
Q1 Answer	To analyze problems for human-robot collaboration, including the differences between traditional and intelligent robots, as well as to suggest a new safety approach "(...) which allows the humans and robots to switch between different safety measures based on the need for flexibility or efficiency to reach production goals".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) a constructive approach to safety of intelligent human robot collaboration is that both humans and robots should be part of the deliberation and planning process, which must be based on negotiations and arriving at consensus decisions."</p> <p>"The overarching aim of this paper is to better understand the safety and regulatory challenges with a focus on the automotive industry, and to suggest a new safety approach called deliberative safety together with a taxonomy of its various safety measures, for intelligent human-robot collaboration."</p> <p>"Power and Force Limiting is used when the robot and the operator can have physical contact intentionally or unintentionally. It requires the robot system to have a passive and inherently safe design such as smooth surfaces and that the robot (or external safety equipment) is equipped with an active safety-related control system such as sensitive force monitoring functions that can dissipate collision forces and that do not violate determined force limits."</p> <p>"The main problem with the regulation of collaborative automation from the perspective of the stakeholders is that the robots do not operate within fenced areas but in proximity to humans, and that the robot might act in ways that is (or is perceived as) autonomous which makes the risk evaluation more difficult."</p> <p>"The big challenge will be to resolve the safety issues in a way that is reasonably cost-effective, you can always build any number of safety systems and make it safe, but then you get a very rigid and expensive installation."</p> <p>"The views of the stakeholders can be summarized in the following bullets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders see potential benefits in intelligent collaborative solutions to help automate parts of the final assembly. • Intelligent solutions in the production are considered to be more safe than current manufacturing. <p>However, benefits associated with collaborative automation are understood to be difficult to achieve due to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cobots are understood to have a low degree of dependability compromising the potential benefits of streamlining the production.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 432 / 550	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current available collaborative solutions/cobots are not considered to be a cost effective solution. • Cobots are not considered to be a flexible solution. • Current regulation is not understood to be well adapted to robots operating in the same physical space as humans. • Current regulation is understood to make human robot collaboration inflexible and slow by requiring redundant safety measures." <p>"(...) we are proposing deliberative safety, which allows the humans and robots to switch between different safety measure based on the need for flexibility or efficiency. To make the performance of an operation cost effective it might sometimes be necessary to allow a high level of flexibility and at other times be able to be executed as fast as possible. By allowing the humans and robots to decide about the required performance level, while they are safely performing the operation, a highly flexible yet efficient system can be created."</p> <p>There are five possible approaches to safety:</p> <p>"Perimeter safety: This safety measure is sometimes called "Safety Monitored Stop" and safety risks are avoided by not allowing the robots to operate when humans are in their working areas."</p> <p>"Zone safety: If somewhat more flexibility is needed compared to perimeter safety, the work area of the robot can be divided into multiple zones, where the speed and behavior of the robot is restricted based on what zones humans or other resources are present in."</p> <p>"Reactive safety: A completely different approach to create safe motions is to only move the robot slowly and monitor the forces of the robot to keep the potential impact within the requirements stipulated in the Machinery Directive."</p> <p>"Active safety: By combining advanced monitoring with the use of e.g. vision and predictive algorithms, it is possible to avoid collisions by for example actively changing the robot trajectories or the sequence, using tools for assisting the human operator, or using advanced sensors. (...) Active safety is necessary when an operation requires a high level of DoF and interaction where the human and robot will together complete tasks and the robot can adjust and adopt its motions based on what the human is doing."</p> <p>"Planned safety: (...) Another approach to guarantee safety is instead to let the robot and human plan the sequence of tasks they will perform, and then follow that plan. (...) The planned safety measure includes a well defined interaction point before the execution is starting where the robot and human is deciding exactly what to do and in what order. (...) Planned safety is complex to implement and requires a well defined coordination between the human and robot, but the monitoring system does not need to be as complex as active safety."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"To evaluate deliberative safety, we have implemented an industrial use case of collaborative kitting, where a part kit is prepared in a warehouse and transported to the point of use on autonomous transport robots (ATR)."</p> <p>The authors have defined the safety strategy according to each action that shall be performed in the factory.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"The deliberative safety concept might require more knowledgeable human operators and new type of training to deal with new ways of thinking about risks an responsibility of the system.</p> <p>The deliberative safety concept will also require changes in current regulation and safety standards, as well as in the way safety is dealt with by government agencies. (...) The development of suitable regulation is a topic for further inquiry in the scholarly literature as well as among government agencies and other involved stakeholder organizations. However, creating and developing standardization of technologies is a long term effort and therefore we aim together with the involved industry in this paper to assess the feasibility and the value of the suggested safety measures, first on several use cases in a lab environment and second on real cases in the production, to start the process of updating current standards to also incorporate these new intelligent human-robot collaboration system.</p> <p>To be able to update the current industrial standards, the following research questions must be answered in the future: How can human and robots express and understand each others intentions to be able to deliberate in planning for the best safety measures and in acting to support each others to avoid and handle risks? and, How can current risk assessment procedure be adapted to include deliberation in intelligent systems and to evaluate the proposed safety measures? This will be addressed by investigating different human interaction strategies using the latest advance in User Experience Design to enable the deliberative concept and define how to handle changes and uncertainties but also to adapt and develop risk assessment and risk reduction methods that encompasses risks due to intelligence and autonomy."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <p>1) Little practical relationship to the technical safety assurance of AI-based systems.</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 433 / 550	

8.323 REFERENCE [963]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To propose the Integration Safety Case for Perception (ISCaP) as a template to integrate safety requirements at the system level with component performance requirements at the unit level specifically tailored for perception components.
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general, convolutional neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"An important quality of a safety argument is “rigor”, but when the steps of the argument are based on informal or non-deductive reasoning, this may be difficult to ensure. To address this, (...) the internal decomposition steps of a safety case should be deductive, while inductive reasoning (e.g., generalizing from test results) are limited to the leaf claims that are supported directly by evidence. This is the approach we take in this paper to define a generic argument template for a perception component within an Automated Driving System (ADS)."</p> <p>"In this paper, we propose the Integration Safety Case for Perception (ISCaP (...)), a template that provides a systematic method of generating a formal “linkage argument” between the system level and unit-level arguments, specifically for perception components. (...) The safety case module M-C instantiated from ISCaP for a perception component C, sits between the main ADS argument module M-ADS that relies on a claim about component contribution to system safety and the unit-level argument module M-C-unit that provides evidence for specific component properties required for safety."</p> <p>"Overall, the argument takes a formal deductive approach in which claims are expressed as bounded probabilities and strategies mathematically relate the bounds between child and parent claims. This restricts all inductive steps of the argument to the solution nodes that provide evidence for leaf claims. The bound in the top claim for component C is first decomposed using Hazardous Misperception Patterns (HMPs) corresponding to system-level hazards that have misperceptions as causes. The bound in each claim for a specific HMP is then factorized into claims that bound the crash rate, misperception pattern occurrence rate, and Hazardous Behaviour Sensitive Scenario (HBSS) (i.e., hazardous ADS dynamics) occurrence rate, plus a guarantee that all hazardous misperceptions in the HBSS are covered. Among these claims, the bound on the misperception pattern rate is further decomposed using perception-only (PO) conditions, separating the misperception rate for each PO condition and rate of occurrence for the PO condition. Finally, the bound on the misperception pattern rate for each PO condition is decomposed into bounds on the occurrence rates of the constituent frame misperception patterns. These define risk-aware performance metrics that can be estimated via testing in the machine learning context."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"(...) we demonstrate the instantiation of ISCaP for an object detection task OD and define the claims associated with one HMP in detail—HMP SCA (“stopped car ahead”). The component implementing the task OD is PoPi, the Point Pillars object detector for LiDAR point clouds. (...) The ODD we assume consists of driving conditions represented in the KITTI object detection dataset, which is naturalistic, summer, clear weather, day-time driving in a small city (based on Karlsruhe, Germany)."</p> <p>The authors have provided a semi-literal application of ISCaP, obtaining a bound probability in reaching the upper safety goal.</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>As part of future work, we explore several directions. First, the issue of confidence needs special consideration. It is well known that the strength of an argument depends on the level of confidence in claims generated by the evidence and there is much research on defining and propagating confidence within an argument. We have addressed this using confidence intervals in some claims, but it requires a more systematic treatment throughout the argument in ISCaP. Second, while an underlying methodology for identifying HMPs and PO conditions is suggested in various claims, this needs comprehensive elaboration.</p> <p>Third, we intend to extend ISCaP to address some common variations, including the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently, only a single linking expression is allowed for connecting MP conditions to their constituent frame misperception patterns but it is clear that the expression could also depend on other factors. For example, in the case study, we assume independence between occurrences of FNAs. This is appropriate for “typical” cars, but for cars that are unusual it is likely that if there is one FNA, then all subsequent detections will be FNA, so the independence assumption is not valid. Thus having different linking expressions for typical and atypical cars is needed here. • Currently, HBSS exposure is assumed to be frequency based, which is appropriate for cases such as when stopping for a stopped vehicle. All uses of HBSS exposure in ISCaP are based on this assumption. However, ISO2626 also allows for duration-based HBSS exposure, such as when following a vehicle at a steady pace.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 434 / 550	

	<p>The template should allow either approach for generality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently, the frame rates of input and output of perception task T are assumed to be the same, but in general, they do not have to match. For example, a multi-rate tracker might use 30Hz camera input, a 10Hz LiDAR input and output at 20Hz. The template should be generalized to accommodate such cases. • Currently, PO conditions are assumed to represent special (non-nominal) cases and the distinguished PO condition Nom captures all remaining (assumed to be nominal) cases. For greater generality, the Nom PO condition should be split to further distinguish nominal cases from any residual non-nominal cases that may exist. Finally, we intend to do a detailed feasibility study of the approach and identify places it can be improved with the hope that eventually ISCaP can be adopted to support industrial practice."
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Well-structured approach towards defining a standardized assurance case for ML-based components. Even though the research itself it application-specific, ideas can be extended to other domains. 2) The authors have made a fair analysis of their research limitations and proposed relevant future work which can also be somewhat extended to other domains. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Technology-agnostic with regard to assessing AI. Unclear how to obtain the quantitative figures explored by the authors in a real-world application. 2) Some parts of the model are very application-specific.

8.324 REFERENCE [968]

Q-Index	2
Q1 Answer	To "explore how different stakeholders (patients, hospital staff, technology developers, regulators) think about safety and safety assurance of healthcare AI."
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"Assurance practices and regulatory frameworks for healthcare AI are still being developed, e.g., action plans and change programmes developed by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the UK Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) around the use of AI in software as a medical device."</p> <p>"(...) we explore how different stakeholders (patients, hospital staff, technology developers, regulators) think about safety and safety assurance of healthcare AI, using the example of AI-based intravenous infusion (IV) pumps within an intensive care unit (ICU) setting. (...) The use of AI might lead to the development of highly automated and partially autonomous infusion pumps with the potential to reduce errors and improve patient outcomes."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>Five themes were covered:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Advantages, disadvantages, and impact on patient experience: "Attitudes towards AI are positive and are based on trust in the health system. AI can increase efficiency and reduce errors, but it can also contribute to delays and errors. There is still a need for human contact, and the use of AI systems should not disrupt the relationship between patients and clinicians." 2) Human-AI interaction: "Training needs to enable clinicians maintain core clinical skills, and it needs to help clinicians build a baseline understanding of AI and its limitations. Clinicians in intensive care have a strong sense of autonomy. Clinicians need to build trust in AI. Feedback and alerts can provide clinicians with an awareness of what the AI is doing." 3) Safety assurance practices: "Existing assurance practices are a good starting point for safety assurance of AI in clinical settings. AI evolution poses new challenges, but might be addressed through real-time monitoring and continuous feedback, or by locking algorithms. The use of synthetic data could complement real-world data to provide more comprehensive training data sets." 4) Regulation: "Existing safety standards for medical devices are a good starting point for the regulation of AI in clinical settings. Regulation requires a culture change to deal with AI evolution. A more iterative approach to regulation will be required. Developers need to demonstrate they have competence and expertise in developing safe AI. Developers and regulators need to establish a dialogue." 5) Incident investigation: "AI systems can enhance traceability and auditability. However, responsibility and accountability for incidents might be pushed onto clinicians. The incident investigation process needs to include additional actors such as AI experts and AI developers."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 435 / 550	

	"(...) four important lessons for the safe design and adoption of healthcare AI stand out: (1) a socio-technical systems approach to understanding and designing healthcare AI; (2) the continued relevance of lessons learned from highly automated systems; (3) the critical role of the patient – clinician relationship; and (4) the need for a cultural change around the safety of healthcare AI and of digital health more generally."
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "The study set out to explore how different stakeholders think about safety and safety assurance of healthcare AI using a specific example. While the findings were rich, they are limited by the selection of participants and the scenario considered. All participants came from a UK context, and there might be national and cultural differences in perceptions internationally. The scenario was one of care delivery, but the potential for application of healthcare AI is much broader and different factors might be of greater relevance in other areas of healthcare, such as flow optimisation, logistics and drug development. Data were collected during 2019 and before the coronavirus pandemic, and attitudes and perceptions might have changed since then."</p> <p>Future work: "Lessons can be learned from the experiences with highly automated systems across safety-critical industries, but issues such as the impact of AI on the relationship between patients and their clinicians requires greater consideration. Existing standards and best practices for the design and assurance of systems should be followed, but there is a need for greater awareness of these among technology developers. In addition, wider ethical, legal, and societal implications of the use of AI in healthcare need to be addressed."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths: 1) The results related to safety assurance practices are in line with other studies, especially regarding the roles played by input datasets, online monitoring and 'locking algorithms' (i.e., 'safety envelopes') . Good reference to support with a survey on multidisciplinary stakeholders from the medical area.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) No details on AI technical aspects have been considered.</p>

8.325 REFERENCE [971]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present SMIRK, "a pedestrian automatic emergency braking system that facilitates research on safety-critical systems embedding machine learning components".
Q2 Answer	Machine learning in general; autoencoder (neural network).
Q3 Answer	<p>"The SMIRK product goal is to assist the driver on country roads in rural areas by performing emergency braking in the case of an imminent collision with a pedestrian. The level of automation offered by SMIRK corresponds to SAE Level 1 — Driver Assistance, i.e., “the driving mode-specific execution by a driver assistance system of either steering or acceleration/deceleration”."</p> <p>"SMIRK provides the first complete demonstrator that complements Open-Source Software (OSS) with a publicly available training set for the ML model and a complete safety case for its ML component. We posit that SMIRK can be used for various types of research on trustworthy AI as defined by the European Commission, i.e., AI systems that are lawful, ethical, and robust. SMIRK is an ML-based Advanced Driver-Assistance System (ADAS) that provides Pedestrian Automatic Emergency Braking (PAEB) in the industry-grade simulator ESI Pro-SiVIC. SMIRK’s perception system uses input from a radar sensor and a forward-facing mono camera."</p> <p>"A key safety mechanism in the safety argumentation is the “Safety Cage” (...)."</p> <p>"(...) the AD in the safety cage is an autoencoder provided by the third-party library AlibyDetect by SeldonIO. Autoencoders consist of an encoder part that maps input data to a latent space of fewer dimensions and a decoder that attempts to reconstruct the original data."</p>
Q4 Answer	"The Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment (HARA) for SMIRK revealed two categories of hazards. First, SMIRK might miss pedestrians and fail to commence emergency braking. Second, SMIRK might commence emergency braking when it should not, i.e., SMIRK might result in false positives. The first hazard can be fatal, but since SMIRK is an ADAS, the controllability is high, i.e., the driver can brake the car — false negatives are not safety-critical from the SOTIF perspective. The second hazard, however, involves no controllability, i.e., false positives can result in dangerous rear-end collisions. Mitigation of the second hazard included the introduction of a safety mechanism to minimize false positives, i.e., the safety cage providing OOD detection (...)."

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 436 / 550	

	"(...) we organize all data requirements according to the assurance-related desiderata (...), i.e., we ensure that the data set is relevant, complete, balanced, and accurate."
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: SMIRK so far reaches SAE Level 1.</p> <p>Future work: "We designed SMIRK with evolvability in mind; thus, future versions might include steering and thus correspond to SAE Level 2."</p> <p>"Identifying systems that balance the needs of relevance and simplicity is an ever-present challenge in software testing research. SMIRK allows researchers to explore data testing, ML model testing, integration testing, and system testing since data sets, ML model architectures, and the source code are publicly available."</p> <p>"We believe that SMIRK can facilitate such research [cross-simulator experiments], as it should be easily portable to other simulators."</p> <p>"In safety engineering research, SMIRK can support research into several related aspects. The concept of dynamic safety cases to support the recertification of modified systems is a popular research topic. Along these lines, we believe that studies on evolving the SMIRK safety case after expanding the operational design domain beyond the currently simplistic restrictions described would be rewarding. (...) Other topics related to safety engineering that SMIRK facilitates include software traceability, functional modifications according to SOTIF, regression testing, change impact analysis, and compliance to other existing and emerging standards such as UL4600 and ISO 4804."</p> <p>"We argue that the current SMIRK pipeline can be used to study ML pipelines and the MLOps (ML + DevOps) phenomenon. Furthermore, novel tools can be integrated into the pipeline as they become available, e.g., solutions for ML experiment tracking and data version control. The SMIRK ML pipeline is still under active development and will be included as a part of the next release.</p> <p>Finally, SMIRK can be used to study and evaluate new ML models for computer vision."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Good example of system with safety assurance of AI-based system arguments for low autonomy levels (using ISO/PAS 21448 (SOTIF). 2) Example of 'safety envelope' assurance principle. 3) High practical appeal. <p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The authors have not provided further justification on how an AI-based safety envelope (based on autoencoders) has been proven as safe. 2) AI plays a minor role on safety.

8.326 REFERENCE [972]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "propose a safety verification framework as a safety standard for driving controllers with full or shared autonomy based on compositional and contract-based principles" which enables to "synthesize safety guarantees over entire road networks by first building a library of locally verified models, and then composing local models together to verify the entire network".
Q2 Answer	No mention to AI is made throughout the paper whatsoever (only 'autonomous vehicles' are mentioned).
Q3 Answer	"(...) we propose a method to verify a broad class of controllers for autonomous vehicles navigating in urban environments. We leverage compositional verification, assume-guarantee contracts, and reachability theory to verify space-time properties of controllers. Instead of performing the verification over entire road networks, we verify local road models, such as road segments and intersections, against traffic models for other cars. Concurrently, assume-guarantee contracts, i.e., pairs of safe entry and exit sets, are synthesized that guarantee safe traversal of road models (reaching safe exit sets) if the vehicle enters the components in the safe entry sets. A controller is certified safe over a road network if all of its local road models can be composed together using their associated contracts. An important feature of the verification framework is that it applies to all controllers that abide by a controller contract, i.e., a set of safety constraints. The key idea is to propagate reachable sets

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 437 / 550	

	that guarantee safety through the contract, without explicitly considering the controller itself. The framework can be used to verify entire networks offline, or as a roll-out procedure to sequentially check routes as these are traversed."
Q4 Answer	The authors "(...) instantiate the verification framework to verify a specific receding horizon controller, also referred to as model predictive controller (MPC) that abides by the controller contract C." "We further demonstrated the effectiveness of our approach on a case study involving a library of local road models, which enabled us to verify a substantial part of Mid-Manhattan."
Q5 Answer	Shortcomings: Not identified / discussed. Future work: "Avenues for future work include extending the library of locally verified road models to capture a wider range of road geometries. We plan to use the extended library to certify larger, more complex road networks. At the traffic level, we want to extend the framework to handle more realistic behaviors of other vehicles and traffic situations, as well as relax the assumptions about the knowledge of other traffic participants. Finally, we are interested in complementing the verification framework with a roll-out strategy for controllers that leverages the local road models' safety certificates. The goal is to provide online constraints that ensure the long-term safety of the ego-car."
Q6 Answer	Weakness: 1) Despite the usage of reachability analysis for verifying autonomous vehicles traffic safety, the authors make little connection to AI-based controllers. 2) The proposed solution is fully application-specific and cannot be reused for other approaches.

8.327 REFERENCE [973]

Q-Index	3
Q1 Answer	"To interpret published guidance and policy related to AI and justify clinical safety assurance of digital healthcare interventions (DHIs)".
Q2 Answer	Artificial intelligence in general.
Q3 Answer	The authors have provided a list of safety-related recommendations which includes the following items: Data: Access to sensitive data; improve the availability of data / data quality and maturity; bias and discrimination / minimizing bias; representativeness; fit-for-purpose and sufficiency / self-fulfilling prediction; source integrity and measurement accuracy; timeliness and recency; relevance, appropriateness and domain knowledge. Operational use: Outcome fairness; decision-automation bias / technological halo effect / automation complacency; automation distrust bias; stakeholder engagement, trustworthiness, accountability; human-centered implementation processes. Performance: accuracy and performance metrics / unsafe failure modes; reliability, negative side effects, reward hacking; robustness; end-to-end AI safety, unscalable oversight; concept drift or distributional shift; brittleness; model hardening; misdirected reinforcement learning behavior, insensitivity to impact, unsafe exploration; transparency and explainability.
Q4 Answer	"The timeliness and accuracy of decision-making are two specific hazards highlighted by this analysis. By presenting the potential causes of such hazards, we can direct effort applied in risk mitigation to relevant sources with greater likelihood of success. Inadequate utilization of data, social acceptance or trust of AI technology influences clinical effectiveness and operational benefit to larger patient cohorts. Issues with algorithmic functions and data specific facets of bias, validation and revalidation have the potential to cause direct harm to a patient. There is risk in assuming increased accuracy/efficiency from AI decision-making and limited human involvement." "The complexity and dynamic nature of risk, together with increased HDO control of potential hazards, enhances the need for more effective methods for communicating safety justification. Addressing the causes of these issues, a body of evidence (sources) will support the clinical safety of the AI-based DHI. The correct use of DHIs adds greater burden on organizations, as unintended operation / use exposes risk beyond the immediate decision support function, and into future decision-making and algorithmic learning of the DHI. Operating AI-

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 438 / 550	

	based DHIs as intended, correct implementation within the clinical/patient pathway and effective periodic review of clinical outcomes would enhance safety claims. Manufacturers must consider collaborative engagement with HDOs to establish proven in use safety, reliability, and efficacy claims. Simplifying the explanation of decision making, diagnosis and foundation of operation may enable intelligent supervision to mitigate the clinical risk. The results align with current EU policy and industry body recommendations for the use of AI DHI, including medical devices."
Q5 Answer	No shortcomings nor future work have been discussed by the authors.
Q6 Answer	Strength: 1) Several of the identified safety recommendations are in line with what is expected for any safety-critical AI. Weaknesses: 1) Short paper without depth on the discussion of results and without further explanations on how recommendations and hazards have been identified / assessed.

8.328 REFERENCE [974]

Q-Index	1
Q1 Answer	To "present a customized Vision Transformer (named ViT-TA) that accurately classifies the critical situations around traffic accidents and automatically points out the objects as probable causes based on an Attention map".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	"Test plans based on such imperfect accident scenarios cannot fully assess AVs' safety functions on the road. Therefore, it is necessary to develop test scenarios based on actual accident data to obtain a broader spectrum of trustworthy safety criteria for AVs. However, obtaining actual AV accident data is highly challenging and costly. To address the limited availability of the actual AV accident data for research purposes, we employ real accident data of human-driven vehicles (HVs) as a source of scenario extraction because HVs are known to exhibit similar patterns of accidents as AVs, according to recent studies." "We accurately classify actual road accidents and critical situations using Vision Transformer-Traffic Accident (named ViT-TA), an Attention-based Transformer algorithm customized for computer vision data." "(...) ViT-TA can also highlight non-vehicle objects as a probable cause of accidents that otherwise could be overlooked by DSTA or human experts. We derived AV-oriented safety test scenarios that happen at the moment with a time to collision (TTC) shorter than the typical Perception-Reaction-Time (PRT) of human drivers in critical situations. We believe our method can improve the objectivity of the safety test scenarios for AVs as they are based on the accurate accounting of actual accidents by ViT-TA." "Each Transformer Encoder block is a network of normalization (Norm), Multi-Head Attention (MHA), and Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLP) blocks." "ViT-TA computes Attention scores in parallel and feeds the normalization of the output from every Attention Head to MLP, which uses Gaussian Error Linear Unit as the non-linear activation function. We stripped the Transformer decoder block from the original Transformer and let MLP determines the class of a given image. (...) Upon detecting critical situations, we regard the objects appearing over the image patches with high Attention scores as the probable causes of accidents. Note that we did have to encode the sequence of image frames explicitly using RNNs such as LSTM favored by many previous traffic studies. Instead, the explicit class labeling and the position encoding prevent ViT-TA from becoming confused with the proper order of transitions during critical situations. The MHA in ViT-TA as a rich semantic representation of image frames can be modeled in parallel. Thus, ViT-TA has a training speed advantage over RNNs as well."
Q4 Answer	"We empirically configured the ViT-TA structure to produce an optimal model (...). The Dense network at the end is connected to the Softmax layer to classify the scene in an image frame. We set the patch size to 32 x 32. We had a total of 12 Attention Heads in the Transformer Encoder. The length (D) of the combined embedding of each patch was 768. A set of 24,740 video frames from DAD was divided into train and test data at a ratio of 8:2. We varied the batch size between 16, 32, and 64. For normalization and model generalization, we used Categorical Cross Entropy as a loss function with label smoothing set to 0.2. For optimization, we employed

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 439 / 550	

	<p>Rectified Adam (RAdam), which complements the limitations of Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam). We iterated the training process up to an epoch of 1000 with early stoppage enabled."</p> <p>"After the training, ViT-TA achieved the highest test accuracy of 94% when we set the batch size to 64. According to the confusion matrix, ViT-TA remarkably never misclassified Collisions as Normal situations. A small portion of pre-collision situations was falsely identified as collisions. Despite a few FPs and FNs, we were not hampered in identifying the precursors of crashes as Attention maps were given (...)."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "(...) from the 2D video frames, we could not derive a Logical and Concrete scenario specified with the values of situational variables defined as 6-Layer information by the PEGASUS project such as TTC, vehicle speed, directions, and distance between objects."</p> <p>Future work: "(...) we propose a reference framework for automating the writing process of Logical and Concrete scenarios with minimal human intervention (...). We first extract features from data collected by the sensors on AVs. We train ViT-TA with the feature embeddings seen under Normal, Pre-collision, Collision, and Post-collision situations. After the training, ViT-TA detects and highlights objects contributing to the critical conditions. Through object recognition, semantic segmentation, and image classification techniques, the types and geometry of the highlighted objects can be inferred. Upon detection of the first appearance of the critical objects, video frames up to the Post-collision point are iterated to compute the values of the situational variables, such as speed and direction of the vehicles and the distance between critical objects. The situational variables can be randomly adjusted for scenario variations to cover peculiar AV accident patterns not typically seen in HV accidents. Finally, we can adopt text generation techniques to fill out the natural language description of the safety function required under critical situations. Understanding the text accident reports requires recognizing named entities and their inter-relationships that can be mined with various machine learning techniques. We expect that such an automation framework minimizes human intervention and promises a highly objective scenario for the safety assessment of AVs. To improve the credibility of the scenarios further, we plan to employ the latest development of statistical explanation techniques in addition to the Transformer-based visual interpretation approaches."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Weakness:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No strong arguments to support the safety assurance of the proposed method, since the analyses were all based on performance metrics only. 2) Hyperparameters have been justified as 'empirically selected for optimum performance'. It is not clear which performance criteria were selected to guide this optimization, nor how the so-called 'optimum' hyperparameters were obtained.

8.329 REFERENCE [976]

Q-Index	5
Q1 Answer	To "introduce an automated, formal, counterexample-based approach to synthesise Barrier Certificates (BC) for the safety verification of continuous and hybrid dynamical models".
Q2 Answer	Neural networks.
Q3 Answer	<p>"(...) BC synthesis problem, as studied in this work, cannot in general be reduced to a problem of Lyapunov stability analysis, and is indeed more general."</p> <p>"We introduce a method that efficiently exploits machine learning, whilst guaranteeing formal proofs of correctness via SMT. We leverage a CounterExample-Guided Inductive Synthesis (CEGIS) procedure, which is structured as an inductive loop between a Learner and a Verifier. A learner numerically (and unsoundly) trains a neural network (NN) to fit over a finite set of samples the requirements for a BC, which are expressed through a loss function; then a verifier either formally proves the validity of the BC or provides (a) counter-example(s) through an SMT solver: the counter-examples indicate where the barrier conditions are violated, and are passed back to the learner for further training. This synthesis method for neural BC is formally sound and fully automated, and thanks to its specific new features, is shown to be much faster and to clearly require less data than state-of-the-art results."</p> <p>"The first component is a Learner, which provides candidate BC functions by training a NN over a finite set of sample inputs. The network is then translated into a logical formula in an appropriate theory, by evaluating it with symbolic inputs, instead of canonical floating point numbers. (...) This encoded candidate is passed to the</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 440 / 550	

	<p>second component, a Verifier, which acts as an oracle: either it proves that the solution is valid, or it finds one (or more) instance (called a counter-example) where the candidate BC does not comply with required conditions. The verifier consists of an SMT solver, namely an algorithmic decision procedure that extends Boolean SAT problems to richer, more expressive theories, such as non-linear arithmetics."</p> <p>"We add [counter-examples] c to the samples set S as the loop restarts, hence forcing the NN to be trained also over the generated counter-examples c. Note that the NN retains its old weights, and restarts the training from the weights obtained at the end of the previous session. This loop repeats until the SMT verifier proves that no counter-examples exist or until a timeout is reached. CEGIS offers a scalable and flexible alternative for BC synthesis: on the one hand, the learner does not require soundness, and ensures a rapid synthesis exploiting the training of NN architectures; on the other, the algorithm is sound, i.e. a valid output from the SMT-based verifier is provably correct; of course we cannot claim any completeness, since CEGIS might in general not terminate with a solution because it operates over a continuous model."</p> <p>"A core contribution of this work is to tailor the CEGIS architecture to the problem of BC synthesis: we devise several improvements to NN training, such as a bespoke loss function and a multi-layer NN architecture that ensures robustness and outputs a function that is tailored to the verification engine. Over consecutive loops, the verifier may return similar counter-examples: we thus propose a more informative counter-examples generation by the SMT verifier that is adapted to the candidate BC and the underlying dynamical model. These tailored architectural details generate in practice a rapid, efficient, and robust CEGIS loop (...)."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>"We demonstrate that the proposed method finds provably correct BCs on benchmarks from literature comprising both polynomial and non-polynomial dynamics (...). (...) we newly tackle a hybrid model as well as larger, (up to) 8-dimensional models, which push the boundaries of the verification engine and display a significant extension to the state of the art"</p> <p>"(...) the outcomes suggest that we obtain much faster synthesis and verification times, whilst requiring up to only 0.1% (see Obstacle Avoidance Problem) of the training data (...). Evidently this gap in performance derives from the different synthesis procedure: it appears to be more advantageous to employ a smaller, randomly sampled initial dataset that is progressively augmented with counter-examples, rather than to uniformly sample the state space to then train the neural network."</p> <p>"Notice that all the case studies are solved with a small number of iterations (up to 9) of the CEGIS loop: this feature, along with the limited runtimes, is promising towards tackling synthesis problems over larger models."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "(...) we cannot claim any completeness, since CEGIS might in general not terminate with a solution because it operates over a continuous model."</p> <p>Future work: "(...) a parallel approach - i.e. the procedure running on several networks simultaneously - may be suited to quickly synthesise candidates." The variance on processing times is high, "(...) possibly indicating the need for larger architectures to enhance robustness." "Towards increased automation, future work includes the development of an automated selection of activation functions that are tailored to the dynamical models of interest."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength: 1) Well written paper on using barrier certificates to verify neural network-based systems. 2) The case studies show promising results that ensure the safety of the underlying neural networks in a reduced processing time.</p> <p>Weakness: 1) On the case studies, several parameters are set to constant figures and/or specific functions without further justification on how they were defined, nor the impacts these will have on the safety verification. It is not clear whether they could only impact the convergence speed of the proposed verification method.</p>

8.330 REFERENCE [978]

Q-Index	4
Q1 Answer	To present a review on supervised machine learning and big data applications for safety assessment in maritime applications, including accident prediction, accident severity, ship detentions, and ship collision risk.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO		Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 441 / 550

Q2 Answer	Supervised learning, machine learning in general, deep learning in general, logistic regression, support vector machine, random forest, decision trees, Bayesian networks, neural networks (ANNs, CNNs, LSTMs), boosting, Naïve Bayes.
Q3 Answer	<p>The authors have presented a review of 72 papers related to using machine learning in safety applications on maritime applications.</p> <p>"The most frequent research question investigated by the reviewed studies concerns predicting the likelihood of accident occurrence (...)."</p> <p>"With regards to accident factors analysis, these studies sought to determine the relative importance of different descriptive factors in accident occurrence."</p> <p>"Alternatively, some studies consider the consequences of hazards, whereby the task is to predict the severity of an accident, given an accident occurrence and the presence of different factors."</p> <p>"Four of the papers used machine learning for accident description and identification through text classification and natural language processing."</p> <p>"In order to construct a supervised machine learning algorithm, two principal types of training data are required: namely, a positive accident class and a negative non-accident class. The success of any derived algorithm is dependent upon the availability and representativeness of these datasets (...). Availability can be defined as whether there is sufficient accurately labelled training data for algorithms to learn the relationship between the two classes. By representativeness, it is meant that future or unseen data is similar to data on which the models have been trained." The authors have highlighted this aspect several times throughout the paper, illustrating it with example taken from the lreviewed literature.</p> <p>"The most widely applied is Logistic Regression, a type of generalised linear model that utilises a sigmoid function to make predictions that are representative of probability." It is followed by neural networks, support vector machines, random forests, bayesian networks, naïve Bayes, decision trees, boosting (XGBoost), LSTMs, and CNNs.</p>
Q4 Answer	Please refer to the answer to Question '3', as it summarizes the main findings of the SLR, which are the actual results of the research.
Q5 Answer	<p>Shortcomings: "This review has been limited to scoping the state-of-the-art in this topic, and further research is encouraged to compare and contrast conventional and machine learning methods for maritime risk analysis."</p> <p>Future work:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "The relationship between accidents and their casual factors is highly complex which makes prediction inherently challenging." This is related especially to the lack of balanced datasets to represent safe and unsafe scenarios. 2) "Two key areas of further development are necessary to improve the predictive capabilities of such models. Firstly, the greater inclusion of spatial temporal datasets such as metocean conditions, bathymetry and the behaviours of the vessel. These pose significant processing challenges that have as yet curtailed the application of machine learning towards certain hazards such as groundings. Secondly, human factors are inherently difficult to quantify but account for a considerable number of accidents. Methods to incorporate such features require greater exploration." 3) To explore models which are more explainable than 'black-box' ones.
Q6 Answer	<p>Strength:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Simple yet effective review to provide an overview on the usage of machine learning in maritime safety-critical applications. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Simplified usage of expressions related to safety-critical systems or AI-related expressions.

8.331 REFERENCE [980]

Q-Index	5
Q1	To present "a simulation-based approach will be developed to estimate the reachable set of state responses

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 442 / 550	

Answer	generated from a Nonlinear Autoregressive-Moving Average (NARMA) model" expressed by neural networks.
Q2 Answer	Neural networks in general.
Q3 Answer	<p>"The core step of the approach is the reachable set estimation for a class of feed-forward neural networks called Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). By discretizing the input space of an MLP into a finite-number of regularized cells, a layer-by-layer computation process is developed to establish an over-approximation of the output set for each individual cell. The union of output set of all cells is the reachable set estimation for the MLP with respect to a given input set. On the basis of the reachable set estimation method for MLPs, the reachable set over any finite-time interval for an NARMA model can be estimated in a recursive manner. Safety verification can be performed if an estimation for the reachable set of an NARMA model is established, by checking the existence of intersections between the estimated reachable set and unsafe regions."</p> <p>"In most of the real applications, an MLP is usually viewed as a black box to generate a desirable output with respect to a given input. However, regarding property verifications such as the safety verification, it has been observed that even a well-trained neural network can react in unexpected and incorrect ways to even slight perturbations of their inputs, which could result in unsafe systems. Thus, to validate the neural network NARMA model for a nonlinear dynamics, it is necessary to compute the reachable set estimation of the model, which is able to cover all possible values of output, to assure that the state trajectories of the model will not attain unreasonable values that is inadmissible for the original system. It is also necessary to estimate all possible values of state for safety verification of a neural network NARMA model."</p> <p>"Rather than directly computing the exact output reachable set for an NARMA model, a more practical and feasible way is to derive an over-approximation (...), which is called reachable set estimation."</p> <p>"In this work, we will focus on the safety verification for NARMA models. The safety specification for output is expressed by a set defined in the state space, describing the safety requirement."</p> <p>"(...) the state of an NARMA model is computed through an MLP recursively. Therefore, the first step for the reachable set estimation for an NARMA model is to estimate the output set of MLP."</p> <p>"Due to the complex structure and nonlinearities in activation functions, the estimation of output reachable set of MLP represents much difficulties if only using analytical methods. One possible way to circumvent those difficulties is to employ the information produced by a finite number of simulations."</p> <p>"(...) the next step is to develop a function a function that is able to estimate the output reachable set for each individual cell as the input to the MLP. A layer-by-layer approach is developed."</p>
Q4 Answer	<p>In addition to conceptual examples that illustrate the algorithms presented by the authors, a case study of a magnetic levitation (Maglev) system is also presented.</p> <p>"In order to achieve levitation, there are two principal concerns. The first concern is to exert a sufficient lifting force with which to counteract gravity and the second concern is stability."</p> <p>"Due to their unstable, complex, and nonlinear nature, it is difficult to build a precise feedback control model for the dynamic behavior of complex Maglev System. In most cases, a linearization of the nonlinear dynamics is susceptible to a great deal of inaccuracy and uncertainty. (...) Thus, to improve control schemes, a stricter adherence to the complex nonlinear nature of the Maglev Systems is needed. In the last several years, neural network control systems have received significant attention due to their ability to capture complex nonlinear dynamics and model nonlinear unknown parameters."</p> <p>"While neural control schemes have been successful in creating stable controllers for nonlinear systems, it is essential to demonstrate that these systems do not enter undesirable states. (...) As magnetic systems become more prevalent in transportation and in other domains, the verification of these systems is essential. Thus, in this example, we perform a reachable set estimation of an NARMA neural network model of a Maglev System."</p> <p>"(...) two inputs are supplied to the network: the first is the past value of the current flowing in the electromagnet and the second input is the magnet's previous position value. The output of the neural network is the current position. The network consists of one hidden layer with eight neurons and an output layer with one neuron. The transfer function of the first layer is tanh and purelin for the output layer."</p>

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 443 / 550	

	<p>The network is trained using a data set consisting of 4001 target position values for the output and 4001 input current values. (...) To avoid over-fitting the network, the training data is divided randomly into three sets: the training set, which consists of 2801 values, the validation set, which consists of 600 values, and a test set which is the same size as the validation set."</p> <p>"First, the reachable set estimation using 5 partitions is computed, followed by the reachable set estimation using 20 partitions. After both reachable set estimations are calculated, 200 random trajectories are generated and plotted (...)"</p> <p>"(...) all the randomly generated trajectories lie within the estimated reachable set. Also, it can be noted that the area of the reachable set estimation using a larger partition number, that is 20, (...), is smaller than the (...) area, which corresponds to the reachable set estimation using a lower partition number."</p> <p>"For this system, the computational time is approximately 10 times greater when 20 partitions are used. This means that every approach has its different advantages. For the cases when a more precise estimation is needed, we can increase the number of partitions, while for the cases when a larger over-approximation is enough, the number of partitions may be decreased to reduce its computational cost."</p>
Q5 Answer	<p>"In our example, we did not perform a safety analysis but rather demonstrated the robustness of [proposed] Algorithm (...) in capturing a large number of possible predictions of the NARMA network model. The magnet in our example was confined to moving in one dimension. In magnetic levitation systems that are not physically constrained to a set of axes, there are 6° of freedom (three rotational and three transnational). Thus, while we have demonstrated that our algorithm is robust for two-dimensional systems, it will be good to demonstrate its efficacy on higher dimensional systems. However, as the dimensionality and size of the neural networks increases, the computation time needed to compute the reachable set increases significantly as well."</p> <p>"Reducing the conservativeness caused by the increase of layers and generalizing it to deep neural networks will be a future focus for our approach."</p>
Q6 Answer	<p>Strengths:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Very didactic explanation on formally verifying neural networks by means of overapproximation. 2) Fair and clear analysis of limitations and future work. <p>Weaknesses:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The authors have not explored safety assurance on the case study; instead, an estimate of the reachable sets of neural networks was presented. 2) No analyses regarding system faults have been performed.

Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 444 / 550	

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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 445 / 550	

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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24 TH , 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 446 / 550	

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Technical Research Report Title REMARKS ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE SAFETY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED SYSTEMS		Date NOVEMBER 24TH, 2022	Revision 6
First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 447 / 550	

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First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 485 / 550	

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First Author: ANTONIO VIEIRA DA SILVA NETO	Second Author: PAULO SÉRGIO CUGNASCA	Page: 491 / 550	

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